

A f R E S
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24th Annual Conference

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Shaping the future of African Real Estate Markets: Exploring Opportunities

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Emmanuel Kofi Gavu, Dr.-Ing.

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Message from Conference Chair

It is a great honour to welcome you to Lagos for the 2025 AfRES Annual Conference. This year's gathering marks yet another milestone in our collective journey to advance the real estate profession across the continent. As Africa navigates rapid urbanisation, demographic change, and transforming investment landscapes, our theme – *Shaping the Future of African Real Estate Markets: Exploring Opportunities* – captures both the urgency and promise of this moment. Lagos, a dynamic hub of innovation and growth, offers the perfect backdrop for these timely conversations.

The conference proceedings you now hold reflect the exceptional intellect, creativity, and analytical depth of our contributors. Each research output featured here speaks to the evolving realities of our markets and the untapped opportunities that lie ahead. These contributions illustrate the power of rigorous scholarship and industry insight to guide policy, shape investment strategies, and strengthen

professional practice across Africa's diverse real estate environments.

I extend my deepest appreciation to the scientific committee chair, all authors, reviewers, and LOC members who devoted their time and expertise to ensuring the high quality of this publication. Your commitment reinforces AfRES's role as a leading platform for knowledge exchange, capacity building, and cross-disciplinary collaboration. It is through your dedication that we continue to expand the boundaries of research and practice in our field.

As we convene in Lagos, I encourage you to engage fully—challenge assumptions, share your experiences, and explore new partnerships. The conversations we have here, and the ideas captured in this volume will help shape the direction of African real estate for years to come. Together, we have an opportunity not only to study our markets but to influence their future.

Thank you for your continued support of AfRES. I look forward to an inspiring and impactful conference.

ESV Adediran Adetunji, FNIVS, MRICS

On behalf of the organising committee

Message from Scientific Committee Chair

Dear Esteemed Colleagues,

It is with great pleasure that I welcome you to Lagos, Nigeria, for the 2025 AfRES Annual Conference. Set in one of Africa's most dynamic and fast-evolving cities, this year's gathering provides the perfect backdrop for our collective exploration of new horizons in African real estate. Lagos, with its energy, creativity, and growing influence, embodies the very essence of our theme — *"Shaping the Future of African Real Estate Markets: Exploring Opportunities."*

Over the next few days, from 9–12 September 2025, we will engage in critical conversations that will define the next chapter of Africa's property landscape. Together, we will examine innovative investment models, urban development strategies, technological integration, and policy frameworks that are driving transformation across the continent. The diversity of expertise represented here — from academia, government, and industry — ensures that our dialogue will be both rich and impactful.

This year's conference has attracted an exceptional range of contributions, including peer-reviewed papers, industry case studies, and insightful panel discussions, each providing a unique perspective on how we can collectively unlock the vast potential of African real estate markets. Your research, experience, and commitment continue to inspire meaningful progress across sectors and borders.

I would like to extend heartfelt appreciation to all presenters, and reviewers whose dedication and intellectual rigor have ensured the high quality of this year's program. Your work forms the foundation upon which AfRES continues to grow as a leading platform for knowledge exchange and professional development in real estate.

As we conclude this remarkable event, let us leave Lagos with renewed purpose — to transform insights into action, to turn opportunities into realities, and to build a resilient, inclusive, and prosperous future for Africa's real estate markets. The connections we have made here will continue to guide our shared journey toward sustainable growth and innovation.

Thank you for your participation, your contributions, and your unwavering support. I look forward to continuing our collaboration as we shape the future of real estate across Africa.

With warm regards

Emmanuel Kofi Gavu, Dr.-Ing.

Message from AfRES President

Dear Distinguished Delegates,

It is with immense pride and gratitude that I welcome you to the 2025 AfRES Annual Conference, hosted in the vibrant city of Lagos, Nigeria. This gathering marks another significant milestone in our shared commitment to advancing real estate education, research, and professional excellence across Africa. The energy and ambition of Lagos perfectly reflect the dynamism of Africa’s real estate landscape — a sector that continues to evolve, inspire, and redefine the continent’s development trajectory.

This year’s theme, “Shaping the Future of African Real Estate Markets: Exploring Opportunities,” challenges us to think boldly about the future. Africa stands at a defining moment: rapid urbanization, demographic growth, and technological innovation are converging to reshape how we live, work, and invest. These shifts demand not only technical expertise but also visionary leadership, interdisciplinary collaboration, and a renewed sense of purpose. Through our collective efforts, we can ensure that the growth of Africa’s real estate markets is both inclusive and sustainable.

AfRES remains steadfast in its mission to serve as the leading platform for real estate scholarship and practice in Africa. The remarkable work presented at this conference — through research papers, policy dialogues, and industry case studies — reflects the depth of talent and commitment within our community. I extend my sincere appreciation to our partners, sponsors, academic contributors, and organizing committees for their dedication and professionalism in making this event a success.

As we engage over these four days, let us seize the opportunity to strengthen networks, challenge assumptions, and translate knowledge into action. The insights shared here will not only influence markets but also inform the policies and investments that shape Africa’s cities and communities for generations to come.

Thank you for being part of this important journey. Together, we are not only exploring opportunities — we are defining the future of African real estate.

ESV Dr **Adekunle Awolaja**, FNIVS

Message from AfRES Executive Director

Dear Colleagues and Partners,

It is a great honor to welcome you to the 2025 Annual Conference of the African Real Estate Society (AfRES), held here in the dynamic and enterprising city of Lagos, Nigeria. Each year, our conference serves as a vital platform for exchanging ideas, strengthening partnerships, and advancing the collective vision of a robust, innovative, and inclusive African real estate sector.

The 2025 theme — “Shaping the Future of African Real Estate Markets: Exploring Opportunities” — captures both the ambition and urgency of our time. Across the continent, real estate markets are undergoing rapid transformation driven by urban expansion, technological advancement, and shifting investment patterns. These changes present not only immense opportunities but also the responsibility to ensure that growth is sustainable, equitable, and

forward-looking.

As Executive Director, I am particularly proud of AfRES’s role in fostering collaboration between academia, industry, and government. Our network continues to expand, bridging research and practice, and empowering professionals to tackle the pressing challenges of urbanization, housing, land governance, and investment with insight and integrity. The papers, discussions, and case studies presented at this conference reflect the intellectual rigor and practical relevance that define AfRES’s contribution to Africa’s development journey.

I wish to extend my heartfelt gratitude to our hosts, the organizing committee, sponsors, and volunteers whose tireless work has made this conference possible. To our members and delegates, thank you for your dedication, your scholarship, and your unwavering belief in the transformative power of real estate to shape Africa’s future.

As we engage over these days in Lagos, may our conversations inspire innovation, strengthen professional connections, and reaffirm our shared commitment to excellence and progress. Together, we are charting a path toward a more resilient and opportunity-driven real estate landscape across Africa.

Regards.

Professor **Aly Karam**

The Conference Event

AfRES held its 24th Annual Conference from 9th to 12th September 2025 at the Oriental Hotel Lagos, Nigeria. The event hosted over 300 local and international attendees for an in-person conference.

Our conferences attract real estate stakeholders from all over the world, especially members of sister professional bodies, to discuss and present innovative solutions to real estate challenges especially with relevance to Africa. Professionals from real estate stakeholders, government agencies, academia as well as users of real estate services are encouraged to attend.

Conference format – In Person

Conference features

- Keynotes
- Panel
- Discussions
- Launches and Awards
- Parallel break-out sessions
- Social events – site tours

Organiser

The African Real Estate Society (AfRES) founded in 1997, is a continent-wide organization that seeks to promote networking, research and education among real estate professionals across Africa.

It is affiliated to the International Real Estate Society (IRES), along with sister societies in North America (American Real Estate Society – ARES), Asia (Asia Real Estate Society – AsRES), Europe (European Real Estate Society – ERES), the Pacific Region (Pacific Rim Real Estate Society – PRRES) and Latin America (Latin America Real Estate Society – LaRES).

The warmth and mutual support amongst members and between sister societies is characteristic, and anyone who wants to contribute is welcome.

AfRES Membership

Membership is currently organised on three (3) regions:

- Eastern Africa – Tanzania, Kenya, Uganda, Rwanda, Burundi, Republic of Congo, Seychelles, Eritrea, Djibouti, Comoros, Ethiopia, Sudan and Somalia
- Southern Africa – Republic of South Africa, Botswana, Swaziland, Lesotho, Mozambique, Madagascar, Zambia, Angola and Namibia
- Western Africa – Ghana, Nigeria, Mauritania, Senegal, Mali, Guinea, Burkina Faso, Cote D'Ivoire, Liberia, Sierra Leone, Togo, Benin, Cameroun, Chad, Central Africa Republic, Congo Brazaville and Gabon

List of Reviewers

Emmanuel Kofi Gavu	Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Ghana
Oluwaseun Damilola Ajayi	Harper Adams University, UK
Fayomi Igbo	Lead City University, Nigeria
Joseph Kwaku Kidido	Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Ghana
Farida Daphne Issah	Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Ghana
Aly Karam	University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa
Omokolade Akinsomi	University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa
Timothy Oluwafemi Ayodele	University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa
Yewande Adewunmi	University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa
Partson Paradza	University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa
Prisca Simbanegavi	University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa
Sibongile Zwane	University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa
Faranani Gethe	University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa
Matthew Ikuabe	University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa
Cynthia Zethu Shabangu	University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa
Nosipho Moloi	University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa
Neltah Tshepiso Mokgware-Monosi	University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa
	Mawazo Institute, Kenya
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Jonathan D. Oladeji	University of Johannesburg, South Africa
Rumbidzayi Taruvinga	University of Johannesburg, South Africa
Abel Olaleye	University of Johannesburg, South Africa
	Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria
Priscilla Oyebola Bello	Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria
Joseph Awoamim Yacim	Federal Polytechnic Nasarawa, Nigeria
Ibrahim Dabara Daniel	Henley Business School, Reading University, UK
Lewis Abedi Asante	Kumasi Technical University, Ghana
Opeyemi Ajayi	Aalto University, Finland
Peterson Owusu Junior	University of Cape Coast, Ghana
Ewuru Nonso	University of Botswana
Njideka Aguome	University of Botswana
Rotimi Boluwatife Abidoye	UNSW Sydney
Abiodun Odunalde Adejumo	Osun State University, Nigeria
Ephraim Munshifwa	The Copperbelt University, Zambia
Abubakar Sadiq Mohammed	University of the Free State, Bloemfontein, South Africa,
Victoria Oluwafunmike Odunfa	The Polytechnic, Ibadan, Nigeria
Abena Tweneboah Danso	Lands Commission, Ghana
Romeo Abraham	University of North Carolina, Wilmington, USA
Pat Onukwuli	The University of Bolton, UK
Kisekka John Wasswa	Uganda
Patrick Mireku	Volta River Authority, Ghana
Elizabeth M. Musvoto	University of Cape Town
Cletus Moobela	Edinburgh Napier University
Abubakar Sadiq Mohammed	Accra Technical University, Ghana
Raymond Narbi	Harvard University Graduate School of Design, USA
Raymond Juvenile Ehwi	Oxford Brookes University, UK
Felician Komu	Majengo Estate Developers

Conference Sub-themes

Affordable Housing/ Social Housing
Sustainable Real Estate/ Smart Housing/ Green Building Initiatives
Sustainable Financing/ Mortgage
Real Estate Investment Trusts (REITs)/ PropTech
Macroeconomic policy and Housing Developments
Real Estate Valuation
Land Administration and management
CREM/ Property & Facility Management
Real estate market research
Research priorities for real estate education/ curricula

Best Paper Award Categories

Best Investment Paper
Best Sustainable Real Estate Paper
Best Valuation Paper
IFC EDGE Best Paper Award for Green Buildings
IREBS Dupuis Award for Affordable Housing in Africa
Dr Gisela Schulte Memorial Award for Women in African Real Estate

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Contact: info@afres.org

Future Leaders of the African Real Estate Society (FLAfRES)

With a decline in new membership, an ageing membership, and a seeming lack of succession plan as challenges facing the African Real Estate Society (AfRES), the FLAfRES was inaugurated as a potential solution. The idea was that a youth-led committee within AfRES would appeal more to younger members in terms of volunteering their time for the organization. The target was early career academics, researchers, and professionals.

There was an urgent call to encourage younger colleagues to join the association to ensure sustainability and growth. This was achieved through the institutionalization of our primary mentorship program that pairs early career academics, researchers, and professionals to senior colleagues within the organization. The main object was to promote volunteering and mentoring the next crop of AfRES leaders and promote active participation among younger members. Volunteering activities include serving on seminar and conference organizing committees, seminar and conference supporting staff, editorial and logistics support during AfRES related programmes.

Another opportunity to train younger members is the feedback given to younger members who publish with the Journal of African Real Estate Society (JARER). JARER has a strong developmental dimension that mentors emerging African researchers. The journal offers quality feedback and support from the peer-review and publication process.

The first meeting of FLAfRES was held on 11th September 2019 in Arusha Tanzania. The meeting recorded 20 attendees. FLAfRES currently has an active WhatsApp membership of over 150 participants. This in our opinion is a complement to the AfRES organization in terms of new membership. We salute our founding directors Omokolade Akinsomi (currently the IRES President), Emmanuel Kofi Gavu and Tayo Odunsi (past FLAfRES Vice-Chair) for charting this path. It is our hope that this committee will grow in leaps in bounds to serve as a solid backbone to sustain AfRES for the next generation.

Emmanuel Kofi Gavu, Dr.-Ing.
(FLAfRES Chair, 2021 – 2025)

Full Papers (Peer-Reviewed)

**Peer Reviewed*

EXPLORING CHALLENGES OF LAND RIGHTS DOCUMENTATION IN ABOKOBI AND KWEIMAN AREAS ACCRA, GHANA *Lawrencia Adwowa Sam¹; Farida Daphne Issah²; and Ansa Nana Yaa Twum-Bobie³*

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Abstract

This study investigates the challenges faced in securing land documentation in the peri-urban areas of Abokobi and Kweiman in Accra as well as the most preferred policy interventions. Questionnaires and interviews were used to collect data from an official of Lands Commission as well as family heads and landowners. The findings revealed that land documentation remains a major challenge, with issues such as missing or inaccurate records, long processing times, and high costs making it difficult for individuals to secure legal ownership. Many landowners struggled with conflicting claims, multiple sales of land, and disputes owing to unclear ownership rights. Despite these challenges, the study also identified key opportunities to improve land documentation. Digitalization, better collaboration between traditional leaders and government agencies, and increased public awareness about land documentation processes can help streamline the process. Participants in the study called for reforms to simplify registration procedures, reduce costs, and make land documentation more accessible to the public. This study contributes to the discussion on land administration in Ghana by highlighting the struggles landowners face and suggesting ways to improve the documentation process. The findings can help policymakers and stakeholders develop better strategies to promote secure land ownership and reduce land disputes.

Key words: Land documentation, landowners, peri-urban areas, Accra, Ghana.

Introduction

Accra, Ghana's capital city, and the most important political and economic hub in Ghana, has grown in both population and physical size over the last decades (Acheampong, 2021). The Greater Accra Region, with a population of 5,455,692, is the most populated region in Ghana (Ghana Statistical Service, 2021b). Studies also report that over the last three decades, the city-region's built-up area has increased fourfold from 105.4 km² to 468.5km², and within the Accra metropolis, built-up expansion has doubled over the last three decades from an estimated 42.1km² in 1985 to 89km² in 2017 (Asabere et al., 2020; Acheampong, 2021). The pattern of urban physical growth, according to Acheampong (2021), reflects a process of rapid sprawling expansion from coastal cities and towns, including Accra and Tema, towards the peripheral areas inland. Asafo (2020) explained that rapid urbanization and increasing housing shortages are compelling many individuals to secure land for housing construction in peri-urban Accra as well as the availability and lower costs of land in peri-urban areas. This development, according to Asafo (2020), has caused significant transformative effects on the land market, tenure systems and ultimately on the peri urban spaces of Accra.

Given the increasing demand for land in peri-urban areas in Accra, this study explores land documentation practices in the peri-urban areas of Abokobi and Kweiman to identify key stakeholders involved and their roles, challenges faced during land rights documentation and opportunities for improving land documentation. Abokobi serves as the administrative capital of the Ga East Municipal Assembly and is part of the second largest settlements in the municipality. While Kweiman is part of the third largest settlements (Ghana Statistical Service, 2014; 2021b).

Researchers (such as Bugri & Yuonayel 2015; Agyeman-Yeboah, 2018; Asafo 2020; Ameyaw & de Vries, 2021; Azumah & Noah, 2023; UN-Habitat, 2024) have identified broad challenges faced in land registration in Ghana and described the land administration system in the country as multiple and complex. However, research has not focused on specific challenges experienced by residents of Abokobi and Kweiman in Accra during land documentation and residents' opinions on ways to address the land documentation challenges.

By focusing on Abokobi and Kweiman, this research seeks to uncover how socio-cultural dynamics and rapid urbanization influence land documentation practices, offering insights to inform policy and practice for enhanced land administration in Ghana. The next section provides a review of the literature relating to land rights documentation in Ghana. Afterwards the methodology used is discussed and the study findings presented. The final section concludes the paper.

Literature Review

Self-built housing is the main type of housing development in peri-urban Accra. It includes various stages, such as land acquisition and registration, building design and construction through to the completion of the structure (Asafo, 2020). Land acquisition in Ghana is organized along two main lines: customary and statutory or public. Customary lands (constituting about 80% of all land in Ghana) are owned by stools, skins, families or clans normally held in trust by the chief, family or clan head, or fetish priests for the benefit of members of that group. Private ownership of land can be obtained by grant, sale, gift or marriage. Public lands (constituting about 20% of all land in Ghana) are lands which are vested in the president for public use. Ownership is by way of outright purchase from customary landowners or private individuals or headed over from colonial governments (Ameyaw & de Vries, 2021; Azumah & Noah, 2023). Thus, in Ghana, customary lands offer the largest market base for land acquisition, both for private individuals and corporate bodies (Ameyaw & de Vries, 2021). Interests in and rights over land in Ghana include the allodial title, customary freehold, and usufructuary and leasehold interests (UN-Habitat, 2024).

Land acquisition in Ghana, whether from the customary or public sector, has been reported to be fraught with many challenges. These include multiple sales of the same land, difficulty in obtaining reliable land information by potential buyers, several unofficial charges in the acquisition processes, fraudulent land sales, and issuance of unreliable land documents (Bugri & Yuonayel 2015; Asafo, 2020; Ameyaw & de Vries, 2021, UN-Habitat, 2024). These challenges have been responsible for many other problems in the land sector such as land disputes and litigations that cause deaths in some instances, the use of land guards to protect land, and a substantial backlog of land dispute cases at the law courts of Ghana (Ameyaw & de Vries, 2021; UN-Habitat, 2024).

According to Bugri & Yuonayel (2015), one way to achieve tenure security is registration of the land (leasehold interests) obtained from the traditional authorities. Zevenbergen (2004) defined land registration as a process of official recording of rights in land through deeds or title on properties. It means that there is an official record of rights on land or of deeds concerning changes in the legal situation of defined units of land (Zevenbergen, 2004). There are two main types of land registration systems in Ghana: land title registration and deeds registration. Land title registration is mainly implemented in Accra and certain areas of Kumasi, while other parts of Ghana use deeds registration. These registration processes usually occur when there is a transfer of land ownership. It is further reported that the process for land documentation involves various institutions or units such as the Lands Commission, the Customary Lands Secretariat, and the Office of the Administrator of Stool Lands. The process for perfecting land title differs depending on the ownership and management of

the land, with many of these processes initiated through the Lands Commission. Figure 1 shows the processes involved in land title registration. The Lands Commission consists of the Public and Vested Land Management, Land Valuation, Land Registration, and Surveying and Mapping divisions. Each division has a part in the process of land registration. The land title registration process adds eight steps to those in the deed's registration process. For instance, if the grant is from the government or stool, the Public and Vested Lands Management Division of the Lands Commission must also work on the document for consent/concurrence (UN-Habitat, 2024).

Researchers further state that traditional authorities, such as chiefs and family heads, retain significant influence as custodians of customary lands. They exercise land allocation functions. Records of these allocations form the basis of further formal land documentation and signatures of these traditional authorities are required for leases to be validated (Bugri & Yuonayel, 2015; Agyeman-Yeboah, 2018).

Figure 1: Process of land title registration in Ghana (Source: Azumah & Noah, 2023)

Legally, land acquisition must be registered (UN-Habitat, 2011). This legal requirement, according to Asafo (2020), has not only become a necessity but also a tool that improves the effectiveness of land transactions in the peri-urban land market. However, some individuals fail to register their land. For example, many participants in research by Gough & Yankson (2000) and Agyeman-Yeboah (2018) had not done so regarding it as unnecessary, too difficult or it involved high costs. Research has found that informal payments/unofficial charges are normally paid (to obtain or speed up service) in addition to existing land documentation fees which increases costs involved. These charges and fees create a barrier for many, resulting in unregistered transactions. Besides this, lack of awareness/knowledge of land registration process and the complex and bureaucratic nature of the processes involved have been found to be reasons why people fail to register their land (Bugri & Yuonayel, 2015; Agyeman-Yeboah, 2018).

Furthermore, the UN-Habitat (2024) noted that land registration is a very time-consuming process. Asafo (2020) found that the present duration for land registration had worsened to between four and seven months owing to the increasing pressure of land registration amidst inadequate logistics and human resources at the Lands Commission. Additionally, increasing problems of indeterminate boundaries and multiple ownership accounted for the increasing duration in land registration processes (Asafo, 2020). Others have also found that it can take more than a year to register land in Ghanaian cities (Agyeman-Yeboah, 2018; Biitir et al., 2020).

In terms of opportunities for improving land rights documentation, researchers have stated that the integration of technology into land administration systems has the potential to revolutionize land rights documentation in Ghana (Ameyaw & de Vries, 2021). It is reported that Geographic Information Systems (GIS) can facilitate land transactions and timely title registration, offer tenure security, ease land application processes and information sharing as well as reduce disputes (Akeh & Mshelia, 2016). The use of technology in the operations of the Lands Commission has increased steadily over the years, according to Owusu Ansah et al. (2024). GIS technology has been employed in the Land Administration Project (LAP) to establish a comprehensive database of land ownership and transactions and offer a transparent and efficient management system (Owusu Ansah et al., 2024). Additionally, government initiatives such as the LAP initiated in the early 2000s, have focused on digitizing land records and enhancing tenure security. Moreover, to strengthen land administration and improve coordination between the customary institutions and public land sector agencies, Customary Land Secretariats (CLSs) were established in some traditional areas by the Ministry of Lands and Natural Resources during first and second Land Administration Projects (Owusu Ansah et al., 2024). It has been reported that LAP has made notable progress in improving access to land information and facilitating formal registration processes (Alhola & Gwaindepi, 2024). Blockchain technology has also emerged as a promising tool for secure land documentation, utilizing its decentralized ledger to eliminate fraudulent transactions and enhance land tenure security (Ameyaw & de Vries, 2021).

Furthermore, legislative measures such as the Land Act 2020 (Act 1036) are pivotal in harmonizing customary and statutory land systems. The new land law revises and consolidates the laws on land to ensure sustainable land administration and management in the country as well as ensures effective and efficient land tenure. It also seeks to improve transparency and accountability in land governance institutions (FAO, 2022). Bugri & Yuonayel (2015) also stated that improving on educational campaigns for awareness creation on the benefits of land registration can result in increased levels of participation by stakeholders in the process.

Methods

Study areas

The study was conducted in Abokobi and Kweiman in the Ga East Municipal, located in the northern part of the Greater Accra Region of Ghana. The Ga East Municipal has a population of 283,379, according to the 2021 Population and Housing Census. The municipal comprises around 52 settlements including Abokobi and Kweiman. As noted earlier, Abokobi, serves as the administrative capital of the Ga East Municipal Assembly and is about 29 kilometers from Ghana's capital city Accra. Also, as stated earlier, Abokobi is part of the second largest settlements in the municipality while Kweiman is part of the third largest settlements (Ghana Statistical Service, 2014; 2021b).

In terms of land tenure system, and according to the Ghana Statistical service (2014), chiefs and family heads own the land in the Municipality, and they hold the land in trust for their subjects. Land can be acquired through various means including direct purchase, leasehold arrangements, renting, or sharecropping. Additionally, land can be inherited, often passing through generations, which has resulted in significant sale and resale of land parcels with its attendant land litigations and chieftaincy disputes. It is further reported that this situation has contributed to the rapid loss of farmlands with its attendant unemployment and migration particularly the youth to nearby districts such as the Accra Metropolitan Assembly and Tema Metropolitan Assembly (Ghana Statistical Service, 2014).

Figure 2: Map of Accra showing the study areas (Source: Authors’ construct)

Data collection methods

The mixed methods approach, which combines both qualitative and quantitative methods was used to provide a complete overview of the research topic (Denscombe, 2010; Saraswati & Devi, 2023). The qualitative component offered deep insights into the subjective experiences, challenges, and perceptions surrounding land rights documentation. This was useful in uncovering the social, cultural and institutional factors influencing land tenure practices. The quantitative method complemented this by providing additional data on land documentation practices and challenges. Mixed methods

offered the opportunity to check the findings from one method against the findings from a different method which enhances the validity of findings (Denscombe, 2010).

Data was collected between November and December 2024. Questionnaires were used to collect data from 97 landowners in the study areas. The questionnaires collected data on their demographic information, number of years they had owned land, how they acquired their land, the stakeholders involved in land documentation process, challenges of land rights documentation, and opportunities they thought could improve the land rights documentation process. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with an official from the Lands Commission in Accra who had over 10 years’ experience as well as with four family heads in the study areas who had been heads of their families for at least nine years. The semi-structured interviews allowed for probing to uncover new and relevant insights. Purposive sampling technique was used to select participants. This technique is suitable for selecting participants who have privileged knowledge or experience about the topic (Denscombe, 2010), in this case, land rights documentation. The landowners, traditional authorities and Lands Commission official are directly involved in land transactions and documentation processes which makes them key to understanding land rights issues in the study areas. Campbell et al. (2020) also confirm that the rationale for purposive sampling is the better matching of the sample to the study aims and objectives, therefore enhancing the rigor of the research and trustworthiness of the data and findings. The interviews collected data on their demographic information, stakeholders in land documentation, challenges faced in documenting land rights in the study areas as well as opportunities for improving land rights documentation.

Table 1: Number of participants and their positions

Participants	Number
Landowners in Abokobi	50
Landowners in Kweiman	47
Lands Commission staff (Land Administration Officer) with 13 years of experience	1
Family heads in Abokobi	2
Family heads in Kweiman	2
Total	102

Data analysis

IBM SPSS Version 25 was used to analyze data from the questionnaires. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize and characterize the sample. For the interview data, the analysis began with data cleaning and transcription to ensure the accurate conversion of all audio and textual data into a format suitable for analysis. Thematic analysis was employed, following the guidelines of Braun & Clarke (2006) to identify and interpret patterns within the data. Informed consent was obtained from each participant, ensuring they understood the study objectives and voluntarily agreed to participate. To safeguard their privacy, confidentiality was maintained by anonymizing the data.

Findings

Demographic data of respondents

The results showed that the majority (66%) of the landowners were men, which implies a dominance of men over women in land acquisition and management. Moreover, most of them (66%) were between 35 and 54 years, a period where people show interest in land transactions and decision-making. Regarding their educational level, a majority (84%) of the landowners obtained Bachelor's and postgraduate degree. The results further showed that experience in landownership varied, with 43% having owned land for 6-10 years and 25% owning land for more than a decade, reflecting a blend of experienced and relatively newer landowners. The main mode of land acquisition was purchasing from traditional authorities, highlighting the pivotal role of customary institutions in land transactions.

Table 2: Demographic profile of landowners

Gender	Percentage (%)
Male	66
Female	34
Age	
Under 25 years	3
25 – 34 years	19
35 – 44 years	35
45 – 54 years	31
55 and above	12
Educational Level	
Secondary	16
Bachelor's	65
Postgraduate	19
Duration of land ownership	
Less than 1 year	8
1 – 5 years	24
6 – 10 years	43
Over 10 years	25
Mode of land acquisition	
Purchased from a family member	3
Purchased from traditional authorities	73
Purchased from a land agency	24

Sources: (Field survey, 2024)

Stakeholders in the land documentation process

The interview data obtained emphasized the pivotal role of traditional authorities particularly, family heads and chiefs in the land documentation process owing to their custodianship over customary lands. They managed transactions and oversaw land allocation, often without formal documentation. For instance, a family head mentioned that *“The key stakeholders include the traditional authorities, especially the family heads and chiefs, because we are the custodians of the land.”* This is consistent with research by Bugri & Yuonayel (2015) who emphasized the important role of traditional authorities in formal land documentation; they exercise land allocation functions, and their signatures are needed for leases to be validated.

The respondents also stated that statutory institutions such as the Lands Commission and local government bodies played a vital role in providing legal validation and regulatory oversight. Similarly, the UN-Habitat (2024) stated that land documentation and registration are carried out by purchasers at various land sector agencies, with the Lands Commission normally being the starting point. Additionally, surveyors and developers were acknowledged for their technical expertise in boundary demarcation. Participants also indicated emerging stakeholders such as financial institutions, legal advisors, and courts. As the staff at Lands Commission said, *“Surveyors, landowners, and the Lands Commission are key. Financial institutions like banks can also be considered.”* One of the family heads mentioned that *“Stakeholders are not just limited to government officials and family heads. Legal advisors and financial institutions are important players.”*

This was corroborated by the questionnaire data where most of the landowners identified government institutions as key stakeholders involved in land documentation processes, followed by traditional authorities, surveyors, legal professionals and real estate agencies. Ameyaw & de Vries (2021) equally mentioned that there are several parties involved in land transactions such as financial institutions and real estate agencies.

Roles of stakeholders in the land documentation process

This study found that traditional authorities played a central role in defining and mediating land ownership by upholding customary practices and serving as custodians of family and communal lands. While statutory stakeholders like the Lands Commission promote the legal framework for land registration and municipal assemblies enforce planning regulations, traditional authorities are instrumental in initiating and facilitating the documentation process. Their roles extend to ensuring the validity of land claims, mediating disputes, and preserving cultural practices. A family head explained that *“As a family head, I handle the allocation of family lands and ensure we adhere to customary practices. The Lands Commission provides the legal framework and registers the land.”* Another family head indicated that *“Our role is to mediate and verify ownership within our families.”* And another mentioned that *“Traditional authorities define ownership, government institutions formalize it, and surveyors and lawyers ensure proper documentation and conflict resolution.”*

Previous research has similarly mentioned that the customary authority, including the chief and his governing body, and family heads ensure the management of land and the settlement of land conflicts in the Ga East municipal (Asafo, 2020).

The study further explored the collaboration between traditional authorities and government agencies in the land documentation process. Interestingly, the responses here emphasised mutual reliance as one family head said, *“We work with the Lands Commission by providing historical records and confirming ownership.”* This mutual reliance was presented to encompass consultation, facilitation, and dispute resolution. Traditional authorities not only provided foundational knowledge of land boundaries but also acted as intermediaries between land buyers and the Lands Commission. The Lands Commission played a pivotal role in the initial stages of documentation, leveraging its Survey and Mapping Division to demarcate land boundaries and prepare essential site plans. As the Lands Commission staff put it: *“Basically, the Survey Division works with traditional authorities to demarcate their boundaries and prepare site plans for them.”*

It was found that this foundational collaboration ensures that landowners and traditional authorities can formalise their ownership and prevent future disputes. The role extended beyond technical support to include institutional capacity-building through initiatives like the establishment of Stool Land Secretariats. These secretariats aid in organising and maintaining proper documentation, a critical step toward formalised land ownership in Ghana. Furthermore, the results showed that the Lands Commission’s ability to notify landowners during title documentation about potential duplicate registrations reflects a proactive stance in combating fraudulent practices. Also, the Commission’s efforts to incentivise chiefs and traditional authorities to document their lands by waiving valuation fees highlighted its commitment to reducing financial barriers to land registration. The Commission’s oversight in ensuring that documents had the correct signatories underscored its focus on accountability and fraud prevention. As the Lands Commission staff said,

“Because the Commission is able to notify the allodial owners or landowners during title documentation that there are people trying to register their lands, it helps to prevent people from stealing their lands... The Commission also makes sure that the right signatories sign the document in order to prevent fraud.”

The findings here highlighted a dynamic relationship among stakeholders, marked by mutual reliance and collaborative efforts. Traditional authorities and government agencies rely on each other to streamline the documentation process, while surveyors and legal professionals act as intermediaries to ensure technical and procedural compliance. This interdependence reflects an evolving system that seeks to balance customary practices with statutory requirements. However, the coexistence of these diverse actors also introduces complexity. The pluralistic legal environment, characterized by overlapping customary and statutory laws, often creates ambiguity, leading to opportunities for exploitation and land disputes (Bugri & Yuonayel, 2015; UN-Habitat, 2024).

Challenges of land rights documentation

The findings revealed several significant barriers to land documentation in Abokobi and Kweiman. These were categorized into three main themes: documentation quality issues, financial and

educational barriers, and process inefficiencies. In terms of documentation quality issues, the study found that improperly documented land transactions, including missing signatures, outdated plans, and unverified transactions were widespread in Abokobi and Kweiman. These issues stem from a lack of engagement with legal professionals, such as lawyers and valuers, and the absence of demarcation for clear ownership boundaries. These flaws created confusion leading to multiple families potentially selling the same plot of land and introducing complexities in the registration process. The respondent from the Lands Commission highlighted this concern, stating that

"You can't see the head and tail of the documents presented because the people trying to do this don't engage lawyers or valuers. Another is that because of no demarcations, land buyers have to buy the same land from two or three families, and the person brings all three documents for registration. The question then is, which one are we supposed to register?"

The findings further showed that the dual land tenure system in Ghana, that is, customary and statutory, created significant ambiguities in land rights documentation. The lack of clear family boundaries under customary tenure makes it difficult to determine the legitimate family or individual to acquire land from. This confusion inevitably impacts the documentation process as potential buyers may inadvertently purchase land from the wrong family, leading to legal disputes later. As the Lands Commission staff said, *"Since there is no proper documentation of family boundaries, you wouldn't know the right family to buy from, and this affects the documentation."*

Financial and educational barriers were the next prominent challenge. It was discovered that high costs associated with registration and surveying, particularly for families who cannot afford such services was a persistent problem. New acts required more formal documentation, such as barcoded certified site plans, which can be prohibitively expensive for many individuals involved in land transactions. This financial burden, coupled with the need to gather signatures from deceased family members or navigate long-standing, informal agreements, resulted in a cumbersome, costly process that discouraged timely and accurate land documentation. For example, the staff at Lands Commission stated that

"Because most clients don't know what the new act is, they fail to prepare documents that conform to the statutes. Now, the new Act requires that you spend money like 2,500 Ghana Cedis for a barcoded certified site plan. And the Act may require you to go back to the family. So maybe the family head had to sign at the back of your document, but you bought the land 30 years ago and the person is dead."

Additionally, there was a significant gap in knowledge about the importance and process of land documentation. This lack of awareness often resulted in disputes and further delays in documentation as landowners and buyers only realized the necessity of proper records when they faced legal challenges or land ownership conflicts. For instance, a family head reported that *"One major challenge is the cost. Many families cannot afford the fees for registration and surveying."* Another family head stated that *"There's also a lack of knowledge. People don't understand the need for documentation until they face disputes."*

These findings suggest that the amount charged for land title registration can be substantial above GH¢2000 (US\$129¹). However, the majority of Ghanaians (over 75%) are employed in the private informal sector (Ghana Statistical Service, 2021a), and generally, salaries in Ghana are very low and even with many income sources, most urban Ghanaians struggle to make ends meet (UN-Habitat, 2024). The average monthly income of a Ghanaian household in 2019 was GH¢2828 (US\$182) (CAHF, 2023). Thus, it is not surprising that land registration remains unaffordable for some Ghanaians. As stated by Abbosey (2021), the site plan for registration must have a barcode and this is generated by the survey department as a source of information and a security measure to prevent duplication, without the barcode on the site plan registration cannot commence. Azumah & Noah (2023) also explained that by law all instruments attract stamp duty that are based on the value of the property. In title registration, payment of fees is based on property value. This makes title registration unattractive, according to these authors, as it seems as double taxation, and is regarded excessive compared to registration under the deeds system where applicants pay only a nominal fee and the stamp duty (Azumah & Noah, 2023). Besides this, the lack of knowledge found confirms Azumah & Noah's (2023) assertion that the introduction of title registration in Ghana was not accompanied by adequate public education, and public education was largely through the distribution of brochures and flyers, and some public lectures.

Concerning process inefficiencies, the study found that slow processing times and technological shortcomings were significant obstacles. The slow pace of land documentation often takes months or years, coupled with inadequate technological infrastructure being noted as sources of frustration. The absence of advanced servers or machines at the Lands Commission resulted in delayed processing, and power outages only exacerbated the problem. Besides this, the involvement of middlemen who charged excessive fees and provided inaccurate information introduced further confusion and mistrust. A family head, for example, said that *"The process is too slow. It can take months or even years to finalize documents which frustrates buyers."* Another also mentioned that *"Middlemen complicate things. They charge exorbitant fees and often provide wrong information, and this creates mistrust."* And the staff at Lands Commission further added that *"Because the Commission does not use advanced servers or machines, documentation can stall and then power outages compound the problem."*

The questionnaire results similarly showed that lack of proper records or documentation and delays in the registration process were the key challenges faced by landowners, followed by high cost of registration, conflicts between statutory and customary laws and multiple claims on the same land. Other challenges reported included lack of knowledge about the process, lack of transparency from traditional authorities, and difficulty in accessing government offices. The interview data further showed that many landowners and potential buyers were unaware of the new legal requirements or failed to comply with them, leading to delays and back-and-forth between parties. The Lands Commission staff noted the frequent failure of families to engage legal professionals which exacerbated errors in documentation and delayed the process. Moreover, it was reported that customary practices often overlook formal legalities, further complicating the registration process.

These findings align with broader literature on land documentation challenges in Ghana. Researchers have reported that the land registry in Ghana suffers challenges such as inaccurate land data, lack of updated land records and transparency, and a paper-based system that permits corrupt deals

¹ Exchange Rate as of March 2025; 1US\$= GH¢ 15.5

(Ameyaw & de Vries, 2021). Others have equally reported on high costs involved in land registration, evidence of little knowledge about formal land registration procedures, and the presence of unqualified middlemen, who complicate the process with unprofessional advice to clients and can charge large unofficial fees. Increasing duration in land registration processes, indeterminate boundaries and multiple sales of the same land have also been reported (Agyeman-Yeboah, 2018; Asafo, 2020; Ameyaw & de Vries, 2021; UN-Habitat, 2024).

Generally, these findings show that landowners in Abokobi and Kweiman are facing significant challenges in land registration even though land registration reforms have been implemented in Ghana through the first and second Land Administration Projects (Biitir et al., 2020). Consequently, participants were asked to suggest opportunities and ways to address the land rights documentation challenges. Their responses are presented in the next section.

Opportunities and ways to address land rights documentation challenges

Several strategies were presented by the participants to address the persistent challenges in land rights documentation. These fell into four main categories namely integration of systems, public education and capacity building, enhanced collaboration, and process simplification. Integration of systems emerged as a vital solution, with participants emphasizing the importance of creating a unified platform that combined customary and statutory processes. Participants also highlighted that formal registration mitigates the risks of disputes, facilitates future transactions, and curtails unlawful practices such as “land guardism.”

Public education and capacity building emerged as another key strategy. Several participants highlighted the widespread lack of knowledge about land documentation requirements and procedures among landowners and buyers, particularly in peri-urban areas. A robust educational campaign to raise awareness of the importance of the registration process and to equip individuals with practical guidance were identified to have the potential to significantly reduce errors and disputes. Bugri & Yuonayel (2015) also stated that improving educational campaigns for awareness creation on the benefits of land registration may result in increased levels of participation by stakeholders in the process. Azumah & Noah (2023) equally noted that in a society where over 60% of the population are illiterate, intensive, extensive and sustained public education is required in the key local languages within the registration district.

Regarding enhanced collaboration, closer partnerships between traditional authorities and government institutions were noted to bridge the gap between the two systems, ensuring that both statutory and customary requirements are met efficiently. Thus, even though this study found evidence of mutual reliance and collaborative efforts between traditional authorities and government agencies in land documentation process, more collaboration is still required to reduce challenges faced in land documentation.

Finally, simplifying the process and reducing costs, according to participants, would streamline the system and make it more affordable to encourage compliance and promote orderly land development. Digitalization emerged as a central opportunity with the potential to revolutionize land documentation processes. Participants mentioned digital mapping, online submissions, and digital tracking as tools to streamline processes, minimize disputes, and improve efficiency. Notably, the potential for preserving records through digital archives was underscored, mitigating risks associated

with the loss of physical documents and ensuring continuity in land documentation. Examples of their responses included:

“A single platform where both customary and statutory processes are streamlined would help resolve many issues.” (Family Head 1)

“Collaboration between the government and the family. Families should be encouraged to register their land because if the family has a titled land, it makes subsequent registration easier and faster. Families should keep records of transactions to prevent conflicts and land-guardism.” (Lands Commission Staff)

“Educating the public on the importance of land documentation and how to navigate the process is essential.” (Family Head 2)

“Opportunities lie in digitalizing our records. If we could have all our family lands mapped and digitized, disputes would reduce drastically. We need to improve education among landowners. Many don’t know the value of proper documentation. Community education programs could change this.” (Family Head 3)

“Simplifying the process and reducing the cost of documentation would encourage more people to register their lands.” (Family Head 4)

Owusu Ansah et al. (2024) reported that despite advancements by Lands Commission in Ghana, manual processes persist and coexist with digital ones. Likewise, Azumah & Noah (2023) noted that operation of all the land sector agencies is characterized by manual processes; manual types of record keeping and data management making them labour intensive and ineffective. Therefore, participants in this study were calling for a more digitized land management process as a way forward in land system in Ghana (Ameyaw & de Vries, 2021).

Conclusion

This study explored the challenges faced in securing land documentation in the peri-urban areas of Abokobi and Kweiman in Accra, Ghana as well as opportunities and ways to address the land documentation challenges. The findings revealed a complex and interdependent stakeholder system involved in land rights documentation in Abokobi and Kweiman, with traditional authorities, particularly family heads and chiefs, playing a central role due to their custodianship over customary lands. Statutory institutions, including the Lands Commission and local government bodies, provided legal validation and regulatory oversight. Surveyors and developers contribute technical expertise in boundary demarcation while emerging stakeholders such as financial institutions, legal advisors, and courts expand the socio-economic context of land transactions. It was further found that the collaboration between traditional authorities and government agencies, especially the Lands Commission, ensures smooth land documentation, with traditional authorities providing foundational knowledge and the Lands Commission facilitating formalization through survey divisions and land registration.

Regarding the challenges involved in land rights documentation, several barriers to efficient land documentation were found. Documentation quality issues, such as missing signatures, outdated

plans, and unverified transactions, were identified as the most significant problem, with respondents noting that the lack of proper engagement with legal professionals and unclear family boundaries often led to multiple claims on the same land. Financial and educational barriers also emerged as key obstacles, with many respondents citing high registration costs as a major challenge, while others identified a lack of knowledge about the documentation process. Additionally, process inefficiencies such as slow registration times and technological shortcomings were a common concern, with many respondents reporting delays in the registration process. Customary land tenure practices were found to further complicated the process by creating confusion about rightful ownership, leading to disputes. The financial strain of complying with statutory regulations, such as costly certified site plans, was also a significant issue identified.

Participants proposed several solutions to address these challenges, including enhancing public education to increase awareness of the importance of the registration process, fostering closer collaboration between traditional authorities and government agencies, and simplifying the documentation process to reduce costs and improve efficiency. The findings underscore the need for continued legislative reforms, technological advancements, and public education initiatives to improve land documentation in Ghana. This study provides insights into the complexities of land rights documentation in peri-urban Ghana, revealing the ongoing tensions between traditional and statutory systems and identifying actionable opportunities for reform.

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Disclosure Statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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**Peer Reviewed*

Built Environment Students' Perception of Sustainable Construction: How Significant is Students' Demographic Profile? *Timothy Oluwafemi Ayodele*

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Abstract

This study investigated the relationship between built environment undergraduate students' demographic variables and their perceptions and awareness of SC. A quantitative research approach was adopted, using one of the foremost public universities in Nigeria as a case study. A closed-ended questionnaire was distributed to 292 final-year built environment students, and 121(41.4%) questionnaires were completed and analyzed using descriptive and inferential analysis. The study reveals that while most students (60.3%) were introduced to “sustainability” within the last six years, awareness levels were medium-high (mean = 3.83), with awareness on environmental sustainability ranking highest (mean = 3.91), and eco-efficiency lagged (mean = 3.70). The study found that the course of study and duration of sustainability exposure significantly influenced students' awareness. The perception of the importance of sustainable features showed that the students prioritized energy/resource efficiency (mean = 4.11) and waste management/reduction (mean = 4.10). However, economic benefits/cost savings (mean = 3.98) and sustainable building materials/practices (mean = 3.70) were the least rated themes. The result showed that students' CGPA and course of study significantly influenced the level of awareness at $p < 0.05$. Also, results showed that awareness/understanding (mean = 3.69) and institutional/educational factors (mean = 3.52) moderately influenced students' perception of sustainability, though external/contextual factors had a lower (mean = 3.40). The CGPA had a statistically significant relationship.

Keywords: *sustainable construction practices, sustainability awareness, sustainable features, built environment, higher education, students' perception*

Introduction

The global push for sustainability has intensified in recent years, driven by mounting environmental pressures and the urgent need to address climate change. However, progress toward achieving sustainability goals remains slow, particularly in the built environment sector, where a lack of familiarity with sustainability concepts and insufficient knowledge sources among professionals have been identified as significant barriers (Ayodele and Ogunbayo, 2025). The built environment is a major contributor to global greenhouse gas emissions, accounting for nearly half of total emissions, with a significant portion generated throughout the lifecycle of buildings (Wilkinson, 2013). This underscores the need to promote sustainability education, particularly in emerging economies, where rapid urbanization and development often outpace sustainable practices. Understanding the level of awareness and perception of sustainability among built environment students is essential, as they represent the next generation of professionals who will shape the industry's future. Equipping built environment students with the necessary knowledge and skills can foster a more sustainable built environment and contribute to achieving global sustainability targets.

The term sustainability is meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (UN, 1987). Thus, the term is rooted in diverse concepts such as energy-related greenhouse gas emission (Wilkinson, 2013), use of natural resources (Okopi, 2020), green building practices (Chatterjee, 2009) waste management and recycling (Msengi *et al.*, 2019) zero-carbon footprint (Tan *et al.*, 2016), nanotechnology and green building rating systems

(Oluwunmi *et al.*, 2019). These principles are integral to the built environment discipline, offering a foundation for informed education, training, and resource management that can create equitable, safe, and healthy living environments (Cavicchi, 2021). Despite this, there remains a gap in understanding how undergraduate students in the built-environment disciplines perceive and engage with these sustainability concepts, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria.

While significant attention has been paid to sustainability awareness among construction professionals and postgraduate students in both developed and developing countries (Opoku & Egbu, 2018; Oluwunmi *et al.*, 2019; Okopi, 2020), undergraduate students in the built environment have received comparatively less focus. This gap becomes compelling as undergraduate education is a critical foundation for shaping future professionals. To facilitate students' transition into environmentally responsible built environment practitioners, it is imperative to understand their perceptions of sustainability and the factors influencing their awareness. Such insights can inform curriculum development and pedagogical strategies that align with the principles of sustainable development.

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development emphasizes the importance of empowering individuals with the knowledge and skills needed to contribute to a sustainable future (United Nations, 2015). Within the built environment, effective learning processes are crucial for achieving the SDGs and ensuring the successful implementation of sustainable projects. This study seeks to address this gap by exploring the influences of students' demographic variables, such as age, gender, cumulative grade point, and course of study on the perceptions and awareness of undergraduate-built environment students in Nigeria regarding sustainable construction. By examining the interplay between students' demographic profiles and their understanding of sustainability, this research aims to provide valuable insights into how sustainability education can be enhanced to meet the demands of a rapidly evolving industry. Ultimately, this study contributes to the broader discourse on sustainability education and its role in fostering a more sustainable built environment.

Literature Review

2.1. Awareness and Familiarity with Sustainability Concepts

Despite the critical role of sustainability in shaping future-built environment professionals, its integration into higher education curricula remains understudied in most emerging markets. Extant studies (Opoku and Egbu, 2018) underscore the importance of sustainability literacy in addressing environmental, social, and economic challenges. Al Saati *et al.* (2020) found that a high number of students had heard the term “sustainability” from educational sources. Similarly, Al Saffar (2024) submitted that students had a reasonable level of awareness and knowledge of sustainability, especially regarding sustainable actions and behaviours. Msengi *et al.* (2019) highlighted the limited awareness of campus sustainability initiatives in Texas. Focusing on built environment students, extant studies have revealed inconsistent levels of awareness among built environment students. For instance, while Zaki *et al.* (2016) found that 70% of construction students at Nuhu Bamalli Polytechnic (Zaria, Nigeria) were familiar with sustainable construction, only 30% grasped its core principles. Similarly, Oluwunmi *et al.* (2019) reported high awareness of green buildings among Covenant University (Ota, Nigeria) students (88.42%), yet adoption rates were low. These outcomes emphasize the need for increased awareness through curriculum reforms to bridge theoretical and applied learning.

2.2. Perceptions of the Importance of Sustainable Features

Submissions from extant studies suggest that students acknowledge the benefits of sustainable practices but struggle to translate awareness into action. For instance, Okopi (2020) demonstrated that Nigerian students value outdoor green spaces for well-being and academic performance, aligning with Oluwunmi *et al.* (2019), who noted student recognition of green buildings' advantages, such as energy efficiency and improved air quality. While Opoku and Egbu (2018) found that UK postgraduate students viewed sustainability literacy as a career asset, Tan *et al.* (2016) revealed that UK quantity surveying undergraduates prioritized sustainability education despite limited knowledge. Suganya *et al.* (2024) submitted that students often show a strong inclination towards responsible behaviours, such as waste management and a preference for eco-friendly products. There is, however, a gap between awareness and perception of the importance of sustainability. Thus, while students perceive sustainability as beneficial, institutional support is important towards ensuring the translation of perception into actual implementation as built environment professionals.

2.3. Factors Influencing Sustainability Awareness

Curriculum design, pedagogical approaches, and institutional policies significantly shape built environment students' engagement with sustainability. Cavicchi (2021) argues that fragmented, one-off modules hinder holistic understanding, advocating instead for interdisciplinary integration. In Nigeria, Erhabor and Braimoh (2020) identified low knowledge retention in waste management and green energy, attributing this to the teaching methods employed by faculties. Comparative studies such as Diaz *et al.* (2020) emphasized the role of socio-demographic factors and environmental attitudes in shaping student support for sustainability policies. Kukkonen *et al.* (2018) highlight the positive impact of trust in environmental information and self-efficacy on student advocacy, suggesting that participatory learning and community-driven projects could enhance awareness. Watson *et al.* (2017) noted that the importance of university sustainability efforts, supported by faculties or peers, significantly impacts students' environmentally responsible behaviours. Institutional sustainability initiatives and campus culture significantly influence students' sustainability awareness (Bajracharya and Maskey, 2016). Luna and Arce (2024) alluded to the importance of education in cultivating a profound understanding of environmental challenges and proposing effective solutions. Michel and Zwickle (2021) found that environmental knowledge gained in the classroom, both at the secondary and postsecondary levels, had the strongest positive influence on students' present sustainability knowledge. Integrating sustainability through course design and teaching modules has been found to enhance students' knowledge and awareness of sustainable design principles (Bedoya-Valencia *et al.*, 2014). However, the reliance of institutions of higher learning on theoretical instruction without hands-on projects or industry partnerships will not adequately instil practical skills into the students.

2.4. Demographic Influences and Student Sustainability Awareness

Extant studies have explored how demographic factors such as gender, age, socioeconomic status, and educational background impact students' awareness and behaviours towards sustainability. The results have turned out mixed outcomes. For instance, concerning the influence of gender on students' sustainability awareness, Şimşek *et al.* (2022) found that female students generally score higher in environmental sustainability awareness compared to male students. Other studies, such as Ruslindawati *et al.* (2022) found no significant gender differences in overall sustainability awareness

among students but rather the extent to which students understand sustainability problems and how strongly they want to apply the awareness in everyday life (Ruslindawati *et al.*, 2022). Luna and Arce (2024) found that students in higher semesters tend to have higher sustainability awareness. The study found that engineering students in their final semesters exhibited the highest scores in waste management attitudes compared to students in lower years of study. Similarly, Şimşek *et al.* (2022) found that students over the age of twenty scored significantly higher in environmental sustainability awareness. Also, Schrock *et al.* (2023) noted that students majoring in environmental science and sustainability tend to have higher awareness and are more likely to engage in sustainable behaviours compared to students from other disciplines. The presence of sustainability-focused themes within the curriculum also enhances students' sustainability consciousness (Suganya *et al.*, 2024). Erguvan (2024) identified influencing factors such as gender, type of high school, GPA, and prior exposure to the term “*sustainability*” as significant influences on students' knowledge and awareness of sustainability.

Diamond and Irwin (2013) identified conceptual awareness of sustainability issues in the real world as a core area towards ensuring successful student sustainability literacy. This study hypothesized that built environment students' demographic backgrounds will significantly impact their awareness and perception of SC as future built environment practitioners. Insights from this inquiry could inform curriculum enhancements, student engagement initiatives, and policy frameworks aimed at bridging awareness gaps and fostering a generation of built environment professionals equipped to address global environmental challenges. It could also aid in better contextualizing built environment students' perception towards tackling sustainability challenges in Nigeria's rapidly urbanizing landscape. Students with pro-environmental attitudes typically exhibit stronger advocacy for SC, demonstrate heightened recognition of its benefits and display greater alignment with sustainable practices. However, are such attitudes significantly moderated by variables like gender, prior environmental education, demographic backgrounds, and level and course of study? Thus, while extant studies highlight inconsistent awareness levels among students, there is a lack of localized research tailored to local realities, especially focusing on built environment students within the context of an emerging market. This study addresses these gaps by investigating the relationship between built environment undergraduate students' demographic variables and their perceptions and awareness of sustainable construction.

Methods

The study utilized a quantitative research approach, conducting a total enumeration of all 292 final-year students across the seven departments within the Faculty of Environmental Design and Management at a Federal University in Nigeria. These departments represent the core disciplines of the built environment and include Architecture, Building, Estate Management, Fine and Applied Arts, Quantity Surveying, Surveying and Geoinformatics, and Urban and Regional Planning. The final-year students, having completed approximately five years of their programs and having undergone a significant portion of their course modules, were the target population for the study. Primary data was collected through a closed-ended questionnaire, personally administered to the students in the faculty. Only 121 (41.4%) questionnaires were fully completed and analyzed.

The questionnaire was divided into sections. The first section focused on the respondents' profiles. Other sections assessed the students' awareness of sustainable construction (SC) terms/concepts, the

importance they placed on sustainable features, and the factors influencing their awareness levels. To ensure the validity of the research instrument, a pilot test was conducted with 15 final-year students. However, only five provided feedback and comments. Based on their input, certain terms and constructs were reworded for clarity, and additional suggestions regarding factors influencing awareness were incorporated into the questionnaire. The questions were rated on a 5-point Likert scale. Awareness levels range from 1 (not at all aware) to 5 (extremely aware), and the importance/influence of factors from 1 (not at all important/influential) to 5 (extremely important/influential). A benchmark mean value of 3.0, derived from the midpoint of the 5-point scale, was used to evaluate the scales/items. Consequently, the mean score range becomes,

- $x \geq 4.50$ - Very High Agreement/Awareness/Importance/Influence (V-H)
- $4.49 \leq x \leq 3.50$ - Medium-High Agreement/Awareness/Importance/Influence (M-H)
- $3.49 \leq x \leq 3.00$ - High Agreement/Awareness/Importance/Influence (H)
- $x < 3.00$ - Low Agreement/Awareness/Importance/Influence (L)

To ensure reliability, the study assessed internal consistency using the Cronbach alpha coefficient. According to DeVellis (2012), a Cronbach alpha coefficient of 0.7 or higher indicates adequate internal consistency and reliability of the constructs. The analysis yielded Cronbach's alpha values of 0.970 for the level of awareness, 0.971 for the level of importance, and 0.937 for factors influencing awareness. These results confirm that all the constructs demonstrated a high level of internal consistency and reliability.

The study categorized the factors related to the awareness and familiarity with SC terms/concepts to include environmental sustainability, sustainable building and design, social responsibility and sustainable development and eco-efficiency and resource management. Factors related to the perception of the importance of sustainable features were grouped into five categories: energy and resource efficiency, waste management and reduction, occupant health, comfort and productivity, economic benefits/cost savings, and sustainable building materials and practices. Lastly, the factors influencing students' level of awareness of SC were evaluated under three themes: external contextual factors, institutional/educational factors and awareness/knowledge factors. The internal consistency of these themes was evaluated using the Cronbach alpha test, while structural validity was assessed using Bartlett's test of Sphericity and the Kaiser-Meyer Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy. A KMO value greater than 0.6 and Bartlett's test p -value of less than 0.05 were considered indicators of valid scales. The analysis revealed KMO values greater than 0.70 for all the themes. Additionally, Bartlett's test of Sphericity confirmed that all scales had p -values below 0.05, further validating the structural integrity of the constructs. Kruskal Wallis H test, a non-parametric statistical test, was used to evaluate the statistical relationship between respondents' demographic profile and the level of awareness, importance attached to SC features and the factors influencing the level of awareness. The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$.

Findings

4.1 Respondents Demographics

The analysis of the respondents' profiles showed that while 1.7% are 20 years and below, most respondents, i.e., 67.8% are in the 21 to 25 years age bracket. A total of 28.9% are 26 to 30 years old, while a fractional 1.7% are 31 years and above. Also, the responses based on the gender of the

respondents show that 62.0% of the respondents are males, while 38.0% of the respondents are females. This could be attributed to the fact that the disciplines making up the faculty of the built environment seem male-oriented/dominated.

Table 1. Respondents' Profile

Profile		Frequency	Percentage
Age of respondents	20 years and below	2	1.7
	21 to 25 years	82	67.8
	26 to 30 years	35	28.9
	31 years and above	2	1.7
	<i>Total</i>	<i>121</i>	<i>100.0</i>
Gender of respondents	Male	75	62.0
	Female	46	38.0
	<i>Total</i>	<i>121</i>	<i>100.0</i>
Cumulative Grade Point Average	4.5 to 5.00	8	6.6
	3.5 to 4.49	65	53.7
	2.4 to 3.49	41	33.9
	1.5 to 2.39	5	4.1
	No response	2	1.7
	<i>Total</i>	<i>121</i>	<i>100.0</i>
Course of Study	Architecture	7	5.8
	Building	18	14.9
	Estate Management	39	32.2
	Fine and Applied Art	14	11.6
	Quantity Surveying	12	9.9
	Urban and Regional Planning	20	16.5
	Surveying and Geoinformatics	11	9.1
	<i>Total</i>	<i>121</i>	<i>100.0</i>
When the term "sustainability" was first heard	Less than 1 year	8	6.6
	Up to 6 years	73	60.3
	More than 6 years	19	15.7
	No response	21	17.4
<i>Total</i>	<i>121</i>	<i>100</i>	

Sources: Author's construct (2025)

An analysis of the respondents' cumulative grade point average shows that 6.6% were on first-class. While 53.7% and 33.9% were on a second-class upper and a second-class lower, respectively, a total of 4.1% of the respondents were on a third class. The respondents' course of study showed that 5.8% are Architecture students, 14.9% are building students, 32.2% are from Estate Management, and 11.6% are studying Fine and Applied Art. Quantity Surveying, Urban and Regional Planning and Surveying and Geoinformatics have 9.9%, 16.5%, and 9.1% response rate respectively. The respondents were further asked about the first time they heard about the word "sustainability". The responses show that 60.3% heard about sustainability within the last 6 years, while 6.6% heard about the term within the last year. A total of 15.7% have heard about the term for over 6 years. This could be due to their age and level of exposure.

4.2 Awareness/Familiarity with Sustainable Construction Terms/Concepts

The results of the level of awareness based on the mean scores of the individual factors and the themes show a medium-high level of awareness. Environmental Sustainability emerged as the theme with the highest level of awareness, with a mean score of 3.91 ($sd = 0.82$). This suggests a strong level of awareness of environmental sustainability among built environment students, likely driven

by issues of climate change, renewable energy, waste recycling, and energy efficiency, among others. Issues of renewable energy, water and energy efficiency and energy conservation are becoming major talking points across most emerging markets. Environmental sustainability efforts are becoming driving themes across most built-environment disciplines. Following closely is the second-ranked theme - Sustainable Building and Design, with a mean score of 3.86 ($sd = 0.84$). The level of awareness suggests that students are familiar with the sustainability implications of building construction and design, as it relates to green building rating systems, green building, design for the environment and sustainable building methods, among others. All the variables had mean values within the medium-high band. Ranked third is social responsibility and sustainable development, with a mean score of 3.83 ($sd = 0.88$). This shows the growing awareness and acknowledgement of the students on the need to balance environmental goals with social responsibility and sustainable development goals. Eco-efficiency and Resource Management had the lowest ranking, with a mean score of 3.70 ($sd = 0.81$). This suggests that the level of students' awareness of the theme was low compared to other themes. While concepts like eco-efficiency, green techniques and products, cleaner production and sustainable consumption are important aspects of sustainability, their lower level of awareness may indicate challenges in translating these ideas into actionable practices.

The aggregate mean score of 3.83 ($sd = 0.79$) shows an overall medium-high level of awareness of sustainability concepts by the students. This suggests that the students are aware of the sustainability concepts and practices and should be able to translate these into actionable practices as emerging professionals. The analysis of the level of awareness shows that Environmental themes had a higher level of awareness, perhaps due to their tangible metrics and local market realities. Additionally, addressing awareness gaps through education and internship programs may help increase the students' awareness and preparedness towards an impactful sustainability career in the built environment.

Table 2. Awareness/Familiarity with Sustainable Construction Terms/Concepts

Sustainable Construction Terms/Concepts	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Interpretation
<i>Environmental Sustainability</i>				
<i>Cronbach α - 0.921</i>				
Climate change	117	3.83	1.147	M-H
Waste recycling	115	4.13	1.022	M-H
Waste reduction	116	4.08	0.961	M-H
Renewable energy	116	4.18	0.974	M-H
Carbon footprint	116	3.42	1.224	H
Environmental impact analysis	116	3.77	1.025	M-H
Energy conservation	117	4.03	1.038	M-H
Energy Efficiency	113	3.95	1.076	M-H
Water Efficiency	116	3.83	1.041	M-H
<i>Aggregate</i>	117	3.91	0.823	M-H
<i>Sustainable Building and Design</i>				
<i>Cronbach α - 0.917</i>				
Green Building	117	4.01	1.079	M-H
Design for the environment	116	4.19	0.959	M-H
Indoor Environmental Quality	115	3.77	1.037	M-H
Environmental conditioning	117	3.69	1.192	M-H
Sustainable design	116	3.82	1.060	M-H
Sustainable construction practices	116	3.81	1.134	M-H
Green building rating systems; LEED, EDGE	114	3.74	1.205	M-H
Green building design	117	3.81	1.082	M-H

Sustainable building methods	117	3.87	1.126	M-H
<i>Aggregate</i>	117	3.86	0.838	M-H
<i>Social Responsibility and Sustainable Development</i>		<i>Cronbach α - 0.722</i>		
Cooperate social responsibility	116	3.96	1.025	M-H
Green agenda	116	3.47	1.197	H
Sustainable Development Goals	116	4.04	1.083	M-H
<i>Aggregate</i>	117	3.83	0.883	M-H
<i>Eco-efficiency and Resource Management</i>		<i>Cronbach α - 0.874</i>		
Eco-efficiency	116	3.73	1.130	M-H
Cleaner production and sustainable consumption	115	4.03	0.945	M-H
Life cycle assessment	117	3.75	1.082	M-H
Sustainable building materials	117	3.83	1.109	M-H
Nanotechnology	116	3.34	1.201	H
Green techniques and products	116	3.70	1.081	M-H
Cost saving/efficiency	117	3.84	1.114	M-H
Smart grid	117	3.37	1.149	H
<i>Aggregate</i>	117	3.70	0.808	M-H
<i>Overall Aggregate</i>	117	3.83	0.787	M-H

Sources: Author's construct (2025)

An examination of the statistical relationship between the students' demographic variables and their level of awareness of SC showed that the respondents' course of study and duration of knowledge of sustainability were statistically significant with the level of awareness of SC at $p = 0.002$ and $p = 0.016$, respectively. This suggests that the course of study and length of time respondents have heard about sustainability were statistically significant on the level of students' awareness. This corroborates Abd-El-Waheed and Al-Bahi (2021), who found that students exposed to sustainability themes within their courses developed a more nuanced understanding of sustainability. In addition, Schroer *et al.* (2015) noted that the length of time students have been exposed to sustainability topics tend to have a more developed understanding and commitment to sustainability practices

Table 3. Statistical relationship between students' demography and level of awareness

Variables	N	Mean Rank	Kruskal-Wallis H	Df	Asymp. Sig.	Effect of Size	
Age	20 years and below	2	61.50	1.612	3	0.657	0.014
	21 to 25 years	78	57.06				
	26 to 30 years	35	64.17				
	31 years and above	2	41.50				
	<i>Total</i>	117					
Gender	Male	73	62.46	2.019	1	0.155	0.017
	Female	44	53.26				
	<i>Total</i>	117					
Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA)	4.5 to 5.00	7	36.14	5.474	3	0.140	0.048
	3.5 to 4.49	63	63.44				
	2.4 to 3.49	41	53.84				
	1.5 to 2.39	5	65.70				
<i>Total</i>	116						
Course of Study	Architecture	7	59.57	21.295	6	0.002*	0.184
	Building	18	42.00				
	Estate Management	39	65.36				
	Fine and Applied Art	11	33.32				

	Quantity Surveying	12	59.67				
	Urban and Regional Planning (URP)	19	81.45				
	Surveying and Geoinformatics (SVG)	11	50.09				
	<i>Total</i>	<i>117</i>					
When the term “sustainability” was first heard	less than one year	25	42.18	8.330	2	0.016*	0.072
	up to 6 years	73	64.86				
	more than 6 years	19	58.63				
	<i>Total</i>	<i>117</i>					

* significant at $p < 0.05$

Sources: Author’s construct (2025)

4.3 Importance Attached to Sustainable Features

The top-rating of Energy and Resource Efficiency ($mean = 4.11$; $sd = 0.89$) reflects students’ awareness of energy efficiency and conservation and use of renewable energy as important aspects of sustainability, likely influenced by peculiar local realities. The high mean score aligns with sustainability concepts that energy efficiency as an important aspect for reducing carbon footprints. Though waste management and reduction had the second-highest mean score ($mean = 4.098$), it exhibited the highest variability ($sd = 1.06$). This suggests some divergent perceptions among the students regarding the level of importance attached. While students broadly attached importance to the waste management and reduction theme, the spread in responses reflects inconsistent perceptions on waste reduction and recycling or disparities in local waste infrastructure. For example, students from locations with robust waste management systems might rate this higher than students from locations lacking such. The rating of the theme on occupant health, comfort, and productivity ($mean = 4.01$; $sd = 0.944$) suggests a recognition of the importance of human-centred benefits of sustainability. This aligns with the “social sustainability” pillar, where health and safety considerations and enhanced occupant health and safety and internal building conditions impact directly on wellbeing. The importance of this factor may well resonate with the students through their first-hand experiences in poorly ventilated or ergonomically inadequate lecture spaces or dormitories.

Table 4: Students’ Perception of the Importance of Sustainable Features

Sustainable Features	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
<i>Energy and Resource Efficiency</i>				
			<i>Cronbach α - 0.914</i>	
Energy efficiency	117	4.06	1.093	M-H
Energy conservation	116	4.17	0.989	M-H
Use of renewable energy	116	4.18	1.018	M-H
Water efficiency	114	4.17	1.047	M-H
Reduced resource utilization	117	3.95	1.033	M-H
<i>Aggregate</i>	117	4.11	0.893	M-H
<i>Waste Management and Reduction</i>				
			<i>Cronbach α - 0.909</i>	
Waste reduction	117	4.09	1.075	M-H
Waste recycling	116	4.09	1.142	M-H
<i>Aggregate</i>	117	4.10	1.061	
<i>Occupant Health, Comfort and Productivity</i>				
			<i>Cronbach α - 0.944</i>	
Health and safety consideration	117	4.09	1.141	M-H
Reduced work stress	116	3.84	1.142	M-H
Increased/improved personal productivity	117	3.98	1.129	M-H
Improved overall productivity	117	4.01	1.055	M-H

Improved internal building conditions	117	4.03	1.021	M-H
Improved quality of work life	114	4.07	1.054	M-H
Enhanced occupant comfort and health	117	4.04	1.086	M-H
<i>Aggregate</i>	117	4.01	0.944	M-H
<i>Economic Benefits and Cost Savings</i>			<i>Cronbach α - 0.915</i>	
Cost savings/efficiency	114	4.11	0.972	M-H
Reduced overall and operating cost	115	3.97	1.051	M-H
Increased property value	117	3.88	1.205	M-H
Reduced energy cost	116	4.12	1.048	M-H
Lower health-related cost	116	3.85	1.218	M-H
<i>Aggregate</i>	117	3.98	0.963	M-H
<i>Sustainable Building Materials and Practices</i>			<i>Cronbach α - 0.731</i>	
Use of local building materials	116	3.78	1.150	M-H
Use of sustainable building materials	117	3.35	1.328	H
Minimize strain on local infrastructure	117	3.98	1.050	M-H
<i>Aggregate</i>	117	3.70	0.952	M-H
<i>Overall Aggregate</i>	117	3.99	0.869	M-H

Sources: Author's construct (2025)

The slightly lower mean score (3.98) of Economic Benefits and Cost Savings suggests that students perceive economic/cost benefits as secondary to environmental or health benefits, possibly due to misconceptions about initial and long-run costs of sustainable practices. However, Kats (2003) found that green buildings yield lifecycle cost savings exceeding initial investments by 10 to 20%, while the World Economic Forum (2020) submitted that sustainability leads to long-term financial resilience. The high standard deviation of 0.96 may reflect the mixed exposure of students to issues reflecting the economic benefits of sustainable features. Students in programs such as Estate Management, Quantity Surveying and Architecture might rate this theme higher than colleagues in other programs with less emphasis on cost-benefit analysis. The Sustainable Building Materials and Practices theme was the lowest-rated theme (*mean* = 3.70; *sd* = 0.95). This highlights a critical gap in the awareness of the students; their lower prioritization may stem from limited exposure to through modules on sustainable building materials or internship experience. However, students in architecture or Building programs might rate this theme higher than their colleagues who may lack the knowledge of the benefits of sustainable building materials. This aligns with Berardi's (2017) critique that sustainable materials remain underemphasized in non-specialized education, perpetuating their undervaluation.

In summary, the aggregate mean score of 3.99 suggests a high level of importance attached to sustainable features. This mirrors global trends where younger generations are increasingly demanding climate action (UNEP, 2021). However, the high standard deviation (0.87) suggests some form of fragmentation in students' perception of the importance. Some students may holistically integrate sustainability across the different themes, while others may silo it into specific domains related to their disciplines. These differences in perception reinforce the submission of Sterling (2004) that sustainability education must transcend disciplinary boundaries to foster systemic thinking.

Table 5: Statistical test between students' demography and importance attached to SC features

Variables		N	Mean Rank	Kruskal-Wallis H	df	Asymp. Sig.	Effect of Size
Age	20 years and below	2	72.25	1.417	3	0.701	0.012
	21 to 25 years	78	56.71				
	26 to 30 years	35	63.73				
	31 years and above	2	52.50				
	<i>Total</i>	<i>117</i>					
Gender	Male	73	61.21	0.827	1	0.363	0.007
	Female	44	55.33				
	<i>Total</i>	<i>117</i>					
Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA)	4.5 to 5.00	7	37.07	8.274	3	0.041*	0.072
	3.5 to 4.49	63	64.60				
	2.4 to 3.49	41	50.78				
	1.5 to 2.39	5	74.90				
	<i>Total</i>	<i>116</i>					
Course of Study	Architecture	7	72.57	13.522	6	0.035*	0.117
	Building	18	37.58				
	Estate Management	39	62.94				
	Fine and Applied Art	11	45.36				
	Quantity Surveying	12	61.54				
	Urban and Regional Planning (URP)	19	72.11				
	Surveying and Geoinformatics (SVG)	11	59.68				
	<i>Total</i>	<i>117</i>					
When the term "sustainability" was first heard	less than one year	25	51.88	2.169	2	0.338	0.019
	up to 6 years	73	62.51				
	more than 6 years	19	54.87				
	<i>Total</i>	<i>117</i>					

* *significant at $p < 0.05$*

Sources: Author's construct (2025)

An examination of statistical relationships, as shown in Table 5, showed no statistically significant differences in the dependent variable across most of the factors, except for students' CGPA ($p = 0.041$) and course of study ($p = 0.035$). Corroborating this view, Adhikari *et al.* (2023) submitted that students' perception of sustainability is influenced by their course of study, especially if it has direct relevance to their future careers.

4.4 Factors Influencing Students' Level of Awareness of Sustainable Construction

The results (Table 6) present the mean scores and standard deviation values reflecting students' perceived influence of these themes on their level of awareness of sustainable construction.

Table 6: Factors Influencing Students' Level of Awareness of Sustainable Construction

Factors Influencing Students' Awareness	N	Mean	Std.	Interpretation
			Dev.	
<i>External and Contextual Factors</i>				
<i>Cronbach α - 0.762</i>				
Conservative attitude/culture	119	3.29	1.075	H
Personal beliefs held by individuals	120	3.38	1.139	H
Lack of legislation and policies	120	3.54	1.166	M-H
<i>Aggregate</i>	120	3.40	0.937	H

<i>Institutional and Educational Factors</i>		<i>Cronbach α - 0.898</i>			
Adequacy of sustainability-related content in the course curriculum	118	3.43	1.230	H	
Low level of emphasis by lecturers	119	3.52	1.056	M-H	
Lack of specific course(s) related to Sustainable construction	119	3.61	1.222	M-H	
Lack of practical knowledge on incorporating green building concepts into projects	120	3.54	1.236	M-H	
Students are being left to learn concepts of sustainable construction independently	118	3.50	1.197	M-H	
<i>Aggregate</i>	120	3.52	1.014	M-H	
<i>Level of Awareness and Understanding</i>		<i>Cronbach α - 0.785</i>			
Level of awareness and enthusiasm about sustainable construction	120	3.64	1.044	M-H	
Lack of clear understanding of what sustainability is all about	120	3.73	1.165	M-H	
Volume of information in social media about news on sustainable construction	120	3.71	1.191	M-H	
<i>Aggregate</i>	120	3.69	0.949	M-H	
<i>Overall Aggregate</i>	120	3.54	0.898	M-H	

Sources: Author's construct (2025)

The theme on Awareness and Understanding, with a mean score of 3.69 ($sd = 0.949$) had the highest mean, suggesting students recognize the impact of awareness on their perception of sustainable construction. The result shows that the factor related to a lack of clear understanding of what sustainability is all about ($mean = 3.73$, $sd = 1.165$) had the highest mean factor under this theme. This reinforces the findings of Suklun and Bengu (2024), who noted that students are better prepared for future challenges in sustainability when taught through case studies and industry partnerships

Institutional and Educational Factors ($mean = 3.52$, $sd = 1.014$) had the second-highest mean score. This underscores the role of academic institutions in shaping students' awareness about sustainable construction. Universities with robust sustainability modules, interdisciplinary courses, and faculty expertise tend to foster higher students' awareness and vice versa. This finding supports Wals and Jickling (2002), who argued that institutional commitment, such as integrating sustainability across disciplines, is critical for student engagement. This finding aligns with studies showing that while sustainability is increasingly integrated into curricula, students often lack practical exposure to real-world applications. For instance, Lozano *et al.* (2013) found that programs that integrate sustainability into core modules, rather than treating it as an elective module, yield stronger outcomes. It suffices to add that theoretical coursework alone does not adequately bridge the gap between abstract sustainability concepts and hands-on skills.

The theme with the lowest mean, External and Contextual Factors ($mean = 3.40$, $sd = 0.937$), indicates that external influences, such as conservative attitude and culture, lack of legislation and policies, or personal belief held by individuals, play a significant role in shaping students' awareness of sustainable construction. The aggregate mean score of 3.54 and SD of 0.898 indicate a moderate impact of the factors. The SD of 0.898 suggests variability across the student population, likely tied to differences in the program modules, students' demographics, and personal exposure to sustainability practices. The results suggest that awareness does not necessarily translate into proactive engagement by the students. For instance, students may understand carbon foot printing theoretically but lack training to apply it in design studios or construction projects.

The results underscore the need for a holistic approach by institutions of higher learning by developing educational strategies to strengthen students' awareness of sustainable construction by

addressing institutional, curricular, and contextual gaps. There is a need to enhance practical training by partnering with industry to provide internships and project-based learning. Also, universities could amplify external drivers by leveraging public campaigns to contextualize sustainability in real-world scenarios. The result presented in Table 7 showed that only students' CGPA ($p = 0.045$) was statistically significant with the dependent variable.

Table 7: Statistical test between students' demography and factors influencing awareness

Variables		N	Mean Rank	Kruskal-Wallis H	df	Asymp. Sig.	Effect of Size
Age	20 years and below	2	67.00	3.918	3	0.270	0.033
	21 to 25 years	82	62.17				
	26 to 30 years	34	58.82				
	31 years and above	2	14.00				
	Total	120					
Gender	Male	74	63.28	1.232	1	0.267	0.010
	Female	46	56.03				
	Total	120					
Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA)	4.5 to 5.00	8	45.81	8.058	3	0.045*	0.069
	3.5 to 4.49	65	62.75				
	2.4 to 3.49	40	52.83				
	1.5 to 2.39	5	92.50				
	Total	118					
Course of Study	Architecture	7	85.14	11.636	6	0.071	0.098
	Building	17	52.85				
	Estate Management	39	56.18				
	Fine and Applied Art	14	48.71				
	Quantity Surveying	12	81.88				
	Urban and Regional Planning	20	58.30				
	Surveying and Geoinformatics (SVG)	11	67.64				
	Total	120					
When the term "sustainability" was first heard	less than one year	25	62.52	2.884	2	0.236	0.025
	up to 6 years	72	60.22				
	more than 6 years	19	46.71				
	Total	116					

* significant at $p < 0.05$

Sources: Author's construct (2025).

Conclusion

This study examined the influences of demographic profiles on the perceptions and awareness of undergraduate-built environment students in Nigeria regarding sustainable construction. While the students demonstrated a medium-high level of theoretical awareness of environmental sustainability, driven by global climate change and local realities, there are some critical gaps in practical aspects like eco-efficiency and sustainable building materials. The prioritization of energy efficiency and waste management reflects alignment with global trends. Yet the low rating of economic benefits and sustainable materials reveals possible shortcomings in the curriculum and misconceptions about lifecycle costs. The study revealed that the course of study and academic performance (CGPA) were significant predictors of students' awareness. Students' perceptions mirror academic and practical emphases on energy, waste, and health while underscoring gaps in economic and materials literacy. The findings emphasise the role of specialised education and institutional commitment in shaping

sustainability literacy among built environment students. However, the observed variability in the responses suggests fragmented perceptions and limited practical exposure. This reinforces the need for more practical engagements, as dependency solely on theoretical knowledge is insufficient to drive actionable competence. To bridge the theory-practice gap, there is a need for targeted curricula, interdisciplinary case studies, hands-on learning, internships, and the integration of real-world projects. There is also the need to contextualize sustainability efforts within local challenges, such as Nigeria's infrastructure deficits and climate vulnerabilities. These efforts will foster a generation of built environment professionals equipped to meet sustainability challenges. Overall, while students showed a high level of awareness and positive attitudes towards sustainability, there is a need for more emphasis on economic and social dimensions. Integrating sustainability into various aspects of the curriculum and providing practical experiences can help bridge the gap between awareness and practice. Further studies could examine the perception of built environment students across other institutions of higher learning, especially in the global South, and identify other demographic factors and local peculiarities that could influence students' perception of sustainable construction.

Disclosure Statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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**Peer Reviewed*

A game-theoretic approach to promoting green buildings among facilities managers *Lydia Tshibe Raphudufudu*¹; *Thulasizwe Percival Abednigo Hadebe*¹ *Ryan Mapfumo*¹ *Yewande Adewunmi*¹ and *Prisca Simbanegavi*¹

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Abstract

Facilities managers in South Africa are constrained by a lack of awareness and incentives, and may be hesitant to adopt green building practices. The study explored the game-theoretic approach towards the adoption of green building in facilities management in Johannesburg, South Africa. It specifically investigated the adoption of game theory strategies, application areas and game theory incentives towards promoting green buildings by facilities managers. In the context of green building adoption, understanding the behaviours of facility managers is helpful, as it aids in designing effective incentives for environmentally friendly practices. An online survey was sent to a convenience sample of facilities managers managing green buildings in Johannesburg, South Africa, to explore the possible game theory strategies between facilities managers and other stakeholders in the industry, as well as game theory incentives. The results were analysed using descriptive statistics, including mean scores, standard deviation, and correlation analysis. The study found that cooperative games, repeated games, evolutionary game theory, and Nash equilibrium were preferred game strategies. Cost-benefit analysis, resource allocation, regulatory compliance, incentive structuring, and strategic collaboration were sometimes game theory application areas. Non-financial incentives were rated as better than financial incentives for green building adoption. Facilities managers' limited knowledge of game theory can be overcome through joint efforts between researchers and educational institutions.

Keywords: Facilities management; Game theory; Green building adoption; Game theory strategies; incentives.

Introduction

Not many governments have focused on green buildings; however, progress remains slow due to various barriers, including resistance to new technologies, high costs of green materials, insufficient customer demand, and a lack of collaboration among construction stakeholders (Gluch et al., 2013). Research indicates that social and psychological factors hinder the transition to sustainable building practices more than technical challenges. Understanding stakeholder behaviour is crucial for the success of green building policies (Li, 2022).

Game theory is one method that can be used to understand how various stakeholders in the construction industry will act when deciding to produce environmentally friendly structures. Implementing environmentally friendly building practices creates a complex network of strategic interactions among various stakeholders, including users and facility managers. Game theory can help analyse the strategic interactions among stakeholders, providing insights into effective incentives for sustainable construction (Chauhan et al., 2022). Game theory, grounded in mathematical models of strategic interactions among rational decision-makers, provides a comprehensive framework for analysing and shaping decision-making processes in facilities management (Fudenberg and Tirole, 1991). Providing a mathematical framework often used in economics and political science, game theory offers a method for analysing situations of this kind (Myerson, 2013). This study provides valuable insights into the possible interactions that facilities

managers have with stakeholders in green building adoption, including building owners, contractors, and policymakers identified by facilities managers (Bekius and Gomes, 2023).

Game theory can be employed in facilities management to model the strategic interactions among various stakeholders. Player A, a facilities manager, must decide whether to invest in a green building upgrade. This decision affects the manager regarding investment costs and potential future savings while also influencing Player B, the building owner, who may see an increase in property value or incur specific costs (Cohen, Pearlmutter, and Schwarts, 2019). Using game theory to model these interactions allows for the prediction of potential outcomes and the identification of optimal strategies for all participants. This is especially beneficial for developing incentives that promote the adoption of green building practices. A game-theoretic model can illustrate how various financial and regulatory incentives influence facilities managers and other stakeholders (Qingfeng et al., 2021). It also can provide valuable insights into resolving conflicts and planning cooperative frameworks (Shahmohammadian and Ghafory-Ashtiany, 2025).

Locating specific case studies or examples of direct applications of game theory in facilities management presents a challenge. The available information is insufficient, necessitating extrapolation from the overarching principles of game theory and its applications in related domains, such as economics, politics, or the social sciences (Kapliński and Tamošaitienė, 2010). A game-theoretic model can be developed in facilities management involving the Facilities Manager (Player A) and Building Users (Player B). The choice to invest in a green building upgrade is primarily the responsibility of the Facilities Manager regarding operational efficiency. It also impacts the Property Manager, who focuses on the financial performance and marketability of the property (Saka et al., 2021; Alfalah and Zayed, 2020).

Facilities Management (FM) is vital in promoting environmentally friendly building practices. FM can contribute by conducting risk assessments, designing sustainable materials, and planning for future changes in the built environment. However, the lack of incentives is a significant barrier to sustainable development (Li Ang and Wilkinson, 2008). Incentives can be categorised into structural (non-monetary) and financial (monetary), with structural incentives being more feasible for financially constrained entities (Gundes, 2019). Government initiatives, such as the Green Building Policy introduced in 2018, aim to lead in sustainable building by managing resources efficiently and promoting awareness (Department of Public Works).

The construction industry is a major source of global carbon emissions. Green Buildings (GBs) have recently been recognised as a potential solution to this environmental challenge. However, their adoption has been slow due to cost, knowledge gaps, and perceived complexities. Despite advancements in green building research and implementation in South Africa, integration into academia remains limited. Existing regulations focus on waste management, resource efficiency, and environmentally friendly materials (Agbajor and Mewomo, 2024).

Because game theory relies on oversimplified assumptions about self-interested, rational actors, it may not adequately portray the complexity of human behaviour in actual building scenarios, which is why its use in this field is restricted (Shahmohammadian and Ghafory-Ashtiany, 2025). Despite this limitation game theory is still useful for this study. Facilities managers in South Africa are constrained by a lack of awareness and incentives, and may be hesitant to adopt green building practices (Mompati et al., 2025). Few studies in FM have applied game theory, particularly using

multiple techniques for green building adoption. The study aimed to explore a game-theoretic approach towards promoting green buildings by facilities managers. This study will specifically investigate how FM can use game theory strategies, application areas and incentives that South African facilities managers use to encourage the adoption of sustainable building practices, ultimately promoting a greener future. In the context of green building adoption, understanding the behaviours of facilities managers and stakeholders is helpful, as it aids in designing effective incentives for environmentally friendly practices

Literature Review

Game-Theoretic Strategies

Game-theoretic strategies can provide insights into decision-making dynamics, cooperation, competition, and strategic behaviour among stakeholders, aiding facilities managers in effectively promoting green building practices. Figure 1 shows the game theory strategies identified from the literature review.

Additional Strategies by facilities managers can also foster green building practices by creating incentives, altering local codes, standards, and permitting processes, and considering the building's carbon footprint throughout all planning and design stages (Armbruster and Boge, 1979).

Figure 1: Game theory strategies
Sources: Authors construct (2023)

The Significance of Incentives in Game Theory Models

Incentives are crucial in game theory models, significantly influencing the strategies chosen by players (Gundes and Yildirim, 2015). For example, financial incentives such as tax breaks can motivate facility managers to adopt green construction practices, while social incentives can enhance users satisfaction and improve a company's image (Gundes and Yildirim, 2015). Understanding these influences is crucial for promoting green building practices, particularly when stakeholders can coordinate their strategies (Gundes and Yildirim, 2015).

Financial incentives, including government grants, tax incentives, sustainable development fee refunds and sustainable project loan funds, help mitigate the initial costs of green building technologies, making them more attractive to developers (Simpeh and Smallwood, 2024). Regulatory incentives, such as density bonuses, expedited permit processes and preferential zoning, streamline the development of green projects (Simpeh and Smallwood, 2024). Recognition programs and certifications, such as awards, training, and energy efficiency programs, validate sustainability efforts and provide public acknowledgement (Matisoff et al., 2014; Simpeh and Smallwood, 2024). Other incentives, including free marketing and technical assistance and infrastructure compatibility improvement, address specific challenges in adopting green practices (Simpeh and Smallwood, 2024).

In South Africa, developing eco-friendly structures generally requires more resources, particularly financial, than non-eco-friendly structures. Incentives for green building are essential for promoting sustainable construction practices, particularly if significant compliance with established green building policies is anticipated (Agbajor and Mewomo, 2024). The GBCSA in South Africa supports green construction practices, offering rebates in housing stock and property rates that meet its rating system. The Department of Energy and the South African National Energy Development Institutes establish an income tax allowance for energy efficiency savings. The International Finance Cooperation issued a \$42 million loan package to a non-banking financing company to support small and medium enterprises' housing projects. However, the demand for net zero and positive energy building retrofits remains high, necessitating the development of realistic financial models for sustainable building achievement (Agbajor and Mewomo, 2024).

Game theory studies in facilities management.

In Sweden, Eriksson (2007) empirically utilised the prisoner's dilemma (PD) game to test whether game theory can explain buyer-supplier non-cooperation in construction and facilities management. The payoffs include investments, better communication, and profits from mutual cooperation. He said that a lack of long-term contracts may explain the inconsistent attitude of parties in the Swedish construction industry and that actors should aim to reduce the pay-off disparity to enhance cooperation. In Norway, Hopland (2015) used a game-theoretical approach using a Goodspeed model to examine regional governments' maintenance backlogs and goals. According to the research, regional governments may rationally handle maintenance backlogs if they anticipate the central government to “bail out” them with an additional grant for facility upgrades. Gauteplass and Hopland (2017) also examined how the central government may utilise game-theoretical principles to encourage local public facility supply via asymmetric information. Thus, the central government

would want to stimulate local public facilities by offering local governments a transfer to boost their supply. Tamošaitienė et al. (2013) used game theory to choose commercial estate service providers in Lithuania. Savage rule and Levi 3.0 were used for computations. The case study demonstrated real problem-solving utilising the model. Briata and Fragnelli (2020) in Italy examined the inefficiencies and free-riding that might result from sharing a facility's maintenance cost with possible users and splitting the cost of a check among agents who requested it. They proposed two ways to reduce free-riding and explored the possibility that the check indicates each agent's facility utilisation. The check became more profitable by using a TU-cost game to calculate each agent's total cost quota to please as many agents as feasible. Two options were examined, and the TU-cost game's balance was defined. In the Netherlands, Krogmann et al. (2021) created a model for non-cooperative facility locations where facilities and customers behave strategically and significantly influence one another in the Netherlands. Not all competitive facility placement models with strategic customers are practical, like the load-balancing two-sided facility location game.

Xu et al. (2017) researched multiobjective control in a facility setting in China and solved it using DMPC. A cooperative game theory-based weight allocation and Nash bargaining solution improved facility environment control performance. The simulation studies compared the suggested system to single objective control and linear weighted control to assess its practicality and efficiency. The cooperative game theory-based multiobjective DMPC technique was optimal for all control goals. Another work by Abensur et al. (2020) employed a Nash equilibrium model with competitor-related uncertainty to resolve a home insurance assistance base dispute between two insurers. The mathematical model yielded more realistic location techniques than previous models. In Malaysia, an empirical study by Sanzana et al. (2024) used a serious 3D game to train facility managers and maintainers of thermal energy storage (TES) chiller units in Malaysia. When learning chiller management, employees were more engaged and interested.

In Egypt, Saeed et al. (2023) used game theory and the Shapley value to optimally allocate excess energy to inadequate energy buildings depending on energy demand. Extra electrical power was the payoff. A review of these papers reveals a scarcity of empirical studies on the application of multiple game theory techniques in green building adoption, particularly in Africa. Also, there are limited papers on the application of game theory in the South African context.

Theoretical Framework

In summary, a combination of financial, regulatory, recognition, and other incentives significantly promotes green building practices, contributing to a more sustainable built environment. The theoretical framework for the research aims to provide an understanding of relevant concepts and theories. It focuses on applying game theory strategies and incentives to motivate facility managers to adopt green building practices. Game theory, which examines strategic decision-making among rational individuals, is instrumental in analysing situations where outcomes depend on the decisions of others (von Neumann and Morgenstern, 1944). In the context of green building adoption, understanding the behaviours of facility managers and stakeholders is helpful, as it aids in designing effective incentives for environmentally friendly practices (Li, 2022).

Figure 2: Theoretical framework of the study
Sources: Authors construct (2023)

The World Commission on Environment and Development (1987) defines sustainability as the ability to meet present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Elkington's (1997) Triple Bottom Line model further clarifies this concept by highlighting the interconnectedness of social, environmental, and economic factors. In green buildings, facility managers are crucial in integrating sustainable practices and technologies into building operations.

This research aligns with existing theories and studies by focusing on facilities management objectives, game theory principles, and sustainability practices. Successful realisation of these objectives could aid in implementing game theory to encourage facilities managers to adopt green buildings. By integrating game theory into facility management, we can better understand decision-making processes and strategic interactions among stakeholders. Designing effective incentive mechanisms may help overcome barriers and motivate facilities managers to adopt green building practices, leading to more sustainable built environments.

Methods

Data was collected using online questionnaires given to facilities managers in Johannesburg, South Africa. South Africa, and especially Johannesburg, has the highest number of green buildings on the continent of Africa (City of Johannesburg, 2021) and has an established institution guiding green buildings in other countries of Africa, which is the Green Building Council of South Africa. According to the Green Building Council of South Africa (2025), facilities managers play a crucial role in the context of green buildings. They provide essential information for selecting the right materials and are involved in the operations of green buildings through sustainability initiatives, maintenance, and decommissioning. A non-random convenience sampling technique was employed, as data collection was based on a specific set of conditions (Mukherjee, 2020); namely, the participating population consisted of individuals managing green buildings, which is useful for exploratory studies (Golzar et al., 2022). Questionnaires were sent to 50 respondents, and 33 were returned, representing a 66% response rate. The questions pertained to demographic information, game theory application, and game theory strategies to encourage green practices, which were based on possible strategic decision-making in facilities management for green building adoption that the facilities managers envisaged as possible scenarios between them and other stakeholders. This can be used in analysing situations where outcomes depend on the decisions of others (von Neumann and Morgenstern, 1944). These were presented to the respondents (these are in the text that describes the strategies and incentives/payoffs in figures 1a and 1b in the appendix). The questionnaire also revealed the effectiveness of possible financial and non-financial incentives to promote green practices. The questions were measured using a scale of 1-5. 1= never use, 2=rarely use, 3=sometimes use, 4=often use, 5=always use. 1- Not effective at all, 2= slightly effective, 3= moderately effective, 4= very effective and 5= extremely effective.

Analysis was conducted using SPSS version 20 software. The descriptive analysis was conducted on all the demographic data. Frequency and count analyses were performed on the relevant survey questions, and mean, standard deviation and correlation analyses were used to test for significance between different variables. The analysis employed statistical methods, presenting the findings clearly and concisely. Initially, correlation analysis assessed the strength and direction of relationships between various programs, with correlation values ranging from -1 to 1. A value near 1 indicates a strong positive correlation, a value near -1 indicates a strong negative correlation, and a value near 0 suggests no or a weak correlation. Subsequently, descriptive statistics, such as mean, mode, and standard deviation, were applied to understand the data comprehensively (Adewunmi et al., 2009). Cronbach's alpha was used to test the reliability of the scales, and the scores averaged 0.98, suggesting high reliability of the scales used. Informed consent and ethics clearance were obtained so that the survey would align with the ethics requirements of the School of Construction Economics and Management, University of the Witwatersrand.

Findings

Demographic details of respondents

Regarding education, the most striking observation is the dominance of respondents holding a Bachelor's degree, representing a substantial 63.6%. The next major group comprises those with a Diploma degree at 28%. This suggests that many participants hold at least an undergraduate degree.

The representation of diploma, and honours recipients is relatively minimal, suggesting either a lesser prevalence of these qualifications among the participants or perhaps a more focused target audience for the survey. Regarding work experience, 42% of the participants had up to ten years’ experience and 57% had less experience in green building practices. The designations and roles, including Facilities Manager, Property Manager, Asset Manager, Building Maintenance Manager, Architect, Sustainability Consultant, and Change Manager, had varied representations ranging from 27.3% to 3%. The dominant roles are those of the facilities manager, and the less dominant roles are those of the change manager and asset manager.

Game Theory Strategies

Descriptive Statistics Analysis

Table 1: Game Theory Strategies

Game theory strategies	Mean	SD	Mode	Minimum	Maximum	Sum
Nash Equilibrium	1.96970	0.2197	1	1	5	65
Prisoner’s Dilemma	1.96970	0.2323	1	1	5	65
Zero-sum game	1.7272	0.1756	1	1	5	57
Co-operative Games	2.2121	0.2293	1	1	5	73
Stakelberg model	1.6970	0.1921	1	1	5	56
Repeated Games	2.0909	0.2234	1	1	5	69
Signaling games	1.8788	0.2030	1	1	5	62
Bayesian Games	1.6970	0.1871	1	1	5	56
Evolutionary Game theory	2.0303	0.2282	1	1	5	67

Source: (Authors creation)

An analysis of game theory concepts reveals varying levels of evaluation by the respondents. We can identify the most positively perceived and less favourably regarded concepts by examining the mean values. The analysis showed that managers never or rarely use game theory tools to promote green buildings. The top five concepts with the highest mean values are cooperative games, repeated games, evolutionary game theory, Nash equilibrium, and prisoner’s dilemma. These concepts received mean values ranging from 2.2121 to 1.9697, in order of preference by the respondents. The standard deviations also vary, with values ranging from approximately 1.01 to 1.33, suggesting that the spread of responses is wider for some concepts than others. The mode for all concepts is 1, indicating that this was the most common response. The findings (see Figure 1a in the appendix) imply that the managers prefer green strategies where they can form partnerships, have ongoing relationships, analyse the evolution of green building practices, situations where multiple stakeholders collaborate and where there is a need for the facilities manager to understand the dynamics between tenants and facilities managers regarding shared responsibility (Kalai and Lerer, 1993, Bauso, 2014; Yao and Shao, 2022). The game strategies that were used in other FM studies include Nash equilibrium, repeated games, prisoner’s dilemma, Goodspeed model, savage rule, TU-cost game, and shapely value (Eriksson, 2007; Tamošaitienė et al., 2013; Hopland, 2015; Briata and Fragnelli, 2020; Abensur et al., 2020; Saeed et al., 2023) showing the potential to use evolutionary game theory and other strategies.

Additionally, high positive correlations are observed between certain pairs of game theory concepts. For example, "NASH EQUILIBRIUM" shows a strong positive correlation with "PRISONER'S DILEMMA." These correlations suggest that the other tends to increase as one variable increases.

Table 2: Correlation Analysis

	<u>CORRELATION FOR GAME THEORY TOOLS</u>								
	NASH EQ	PRISONO	ZERO-SU	COOPERA	STACKEL	REPEATIS	SIGNALLI	BAYESIA	EVOLUT.
					B	I	NG	N	C
NASH EQ	1								
PRISONO	0.500493	1							
ZERO-SU	0.680779	0.597484	1						
COOPERA	0.492766	0.750602	0.656591	1					
STACKEL	0.441957	0.672717	0.569251	0.604595	1				
REPEATED	0.676894	0.658504	0.695671	0.709082	0.748057	1			
SIGNAL	0.613201	0.720602	0.794763	0.749711	0.553376	0.7174	1		

LING									
BAYESI AN	0.315534	0.450985	0.497958	0.466219	0.736888	0.700077	0.593079		1
EVOLUT ION	0.567338	0.554501	0.50294	0.629739	0.460274	0.685574	0.738551	0.605656	1

Source: (Authors' creation)

The correlation matrix shows the strength and direction of the relationship between the game theory concepts. For instance, the correlation between Nash Equilibrium and Prisoner's Dilemma is 0.500493, indicating a moderate positive relationship. The correlation between Zero-Sum Games and Signaling Games is 0.794763, indicating a strong positive relationship. Correlation does not imply causation, and other factors could influence these relationships.

Game theory application areas

Table 3: Game Theory Application Areas

Game theory application areas	Mean	SD	Mode	Minimum	Maximum	Sum
Strategic Collaboration	2.6970		1	1	5	89
Resource allocation	3.1212		2	1	5	103
Incentive structuring	2.8489		4	1	5	94
Conflict Resolution	2.3636		1	1	5	78
Cost-Benefit Analysis	3.1818		5	1	5	105
Risk Assessment	2.9394		1	1	5	97
Negotiation strategies	3.1818		4	1	5	105
Regulatory compliance	2.9697		1	1	5	98
Market Dynamics and Competitive Positioning	2.3636		1	1	5	78
Public and Private partnerships	2.1515		1	1	5	71
Supply Chain Optimization	2.0606		1	1	5	68

Financial incentives	Mean	SD	Mode	Minimum	Maximum	Sum
Utility Energy Efficiency Programs	2.3636	0.2568	1	1	5	78
Rebates for Eco-Friendly Materials	2.3939	0.2173	1	1	5	79
Property or Sales Tax Rebates	2.4848	0.2428	1	1	5	82
Sustainable Development Fee Refunds	2.2424	0.2043	1	1	5	74
Permit Fee Discount or Waivers	2.2424	0.2089	1	1	5	74
State Income Tax Credits	2.3333	0.1978	1	1	5	77
Access to Sustainable Project Loan Funds	2.4545	0.2136	1	1	5	81
Federal Grants or Subsidies	2.1515	0.1952	1	1	5	71

Risk Asses	0.553263	0.626714	0.127848	0.027557	0.780767	1											
Negotiatio	0.515082	0.604902	0.033991	0.073779	0.565453	0.595001	1										
Regulator	0.545652	0.614408	0.011392	0.063586	0.817601	0.74783	0.741901	1									
Market Dy	0.340429	0.09156	0.635546	0.719738	0.193891	0.24681	0.053565	0.134213	1								
Public and	0.405814	0.17179	0.568246	0.752341	0.1188	0.318138	0.149279	0.113536	0.740034	1							
Supply Ch	0.233738	-0.04603	0.459187	0.72329	0.087188	0.080405	0.038667	-0.01674	0.650948	0.685787	1						
Energy Eff	0.220796	0.07813	0.584693	0.781037	0.123545	0.214643	0.012937	0.067362	0.802967	0.730946	0.802795	1					
Consumer	0.198619	0.029025	0.58463	0.724889	-0.00313	0.120087	0.017689	-0.04298	0.639211	0.739581	0.717506	0.794937	1				
Benchmar	0.407118	0.187096	0.46499	0.785006	0.188548	0.302312	0.12923	0.178666	0.71701	0.855251	0.754262	0.806221	0.752857	1			
Technolog	0.365522	0.449907	0.316304	0.364009	0.427015	0.444942	0.401991	0.442419	0.47293	0.425774	0.223806	0.49679	0.407285	0.40912	1		

Effectiveness of Financial Incentives in Promoting Sustainable Buildings

Table 5: Financial Incentives

Source: (Authors' creation)

The selected data represents descriptive statistics for various financial incentives that can be used for game theory. The incentives were generally believed to be slightly effective. Among these concepts, the five with the highest mean values are property or sales tax rebates, access to sustainable project loans, rebates for eco-friendly materials, and utility efficiency programs. These concepts received mean values ranging from 2.4848 to 2.3636. On the other hand, the five concepts with the lowest mean values are Federal grants or subsidies, sustainable development fee refunds, permit fee discounts or waivers, and state income tax credits. These concepts received mean values ranging from 2.1515 to 2.3333, suggesting they were less evaluated than others. The mode for all concepts is 1, indicating that this was the most common response for each concept.

Table 6: Correlation Analysis

	Utility Energy Efficiency Programs	Rebates for Eco-Friendly Materials	Property or Sales Tax Rebates	Sustainable Development Fee Refunds	Permit Fee Discounts or Waivers	State Income Tax Credits	Access to Sustainable Project Loan Funds	Federal Grants or Subsidies
Utility Energy Efficiency Programs	1							
Rebates for Eco-Friendly Materials	0.751208	1						
Property or Sales Tax Rebates	0.777418	.748347	1					
Sustainable Development Fee Refunds	0.687667	0.786025	0.74704	1				
Permit Fee Discounts or Waivers	0.760857	0.768771	0.842699	0.645082	1			
State Income Tax Credits	0.652379	0.763491	0.644038	0.687363	0.718111	1		
Access to Sustainable Project Loan Funds	0.613655	0.51182	0.634141	0.420262	0.559627	0.560207	1	
Federal Grants or Subsidies	0.513474	0.737246	0.570969	0.493677	0.784791	0.694713	0.538845	1

Source: (Authors' creation)

A comprehensive correlation analysis has been conducted on various funding and incentive programs associated with energy efficiency and sustainability. This analysis reveals significant relationships between specific pairs of programs. The correlation values, which can range from -1 to 1, suggest the strength and direction of these relationships. For example, the strong positive correlation of 0.751208 between Utility Energy Efficiency Programs and Rebates for Eco-Friendly Materials indicates that an increase in one tends to accompany an increase in the other. Similarly, Property or Sales Tax Rebates and Permit Fee Discounts or Waivers display a strong positive correlation of 0.842699, suggesting that these programs often rise in tandem. Further, a moderate positive correlation exists between Sustainable Development Fee Refunds and Federal Grants or Subsidies and between State Income Tax Credits and Access to Sustainable Project Loan Funds. These correlations, with a value of 0.493677 and 0.560207, respectively, indicate that these programs tend to increase together, although not as consistently as the previous pairs.

Non-Financial incentives	Mean	SD	Mode	Minimum	Maximum	Sum
Technical Assistance	2.5454	0.2136	3	1	5	84
Density Bonus (Higher Floor Area Ratio)	2.3030	0.2063	1	1	5	76
Expedited Permit and Review Process	2	0.1794	1	1	5	66
Free Marketing and Promotion	2.0909	0.2058	1	1	5	69
Recognition Programs	3.0303	0.2556	5	1	5	100
Training and Education Opportunities	3.0303	0.2518	3	1	5	100
Priority or Preferential Zoning	2.1212	0.2076	1	1	5	70
Certifications and Awards	2.8484	0.2467	2	1	5	94

Table 7 : Non-Financial Incentives

Source: (Authors' creation)

The data in Table 7 provides descriptive statistics for non-financial incentives that can be used in game theory. The strategies with the highest mean values, such as recognition programs, training and education opportunities, certifications and awards and technical assistance, with mean scores ranging from 3.0303 to 2.5454. These incentives were perceived to be moderately effective. Other incentives were seen as slightly effective: expedited permit and review process, free marketing and promotion, priority or preferential zoning and density bonus with mean scores ranging from 2 to 2.3030. The mode for all strategies is either 1 or 3, indicating that these were the most common responses for each strategy. However, the range of responses for each strategy extends up to 3 or 4, suggesting significant variability in the data for each strategy.

Findings from previous studies show that the predominant incentive is financial, such as profit and cost, grants and extra energy power (Ericksson, 2007; Briata and Fragnelli, 2020; Saeed et al. (2023). Non-financial incentives could be from learning and mutual cooperation (Ericksson, 2007; Sanzana et al., 2024). Other financial and non-financial incentives studied are in Tables 5 and 7. The findings regarding the incentives are that they are not effective. This could be due to perceived high initial costs, limited knowledge and awareness of green building practices, and a lack of strong regulatory support (Aigbavboa et al., 2017). In the previous section on game theory strategies, we found that cooperative games, repeated games, evolutionary game theory, Nash equilibrium, and prisoner's dilemma were preferred. This implies that when financial incentives such as property or sales tax rebates, access to sustainable project loans, rebates for eco-friendly materials, and utility efficiency programs and non-financial incentives

such as recognition programs, training and education opportunities, certifications and awards and technical assistance are used, they should be a combination of joint rewards, transferable incentives, and long-term, discounted incentives for cooperative and repeated strategies. In the case of the evolutionary and prisoner dilemma, the incentives should be higher, based on productivity, and visually presented. In the Nash equilibrium case, green buildings should not be incentivised (Kalai and Lerer, 1993; Bauso, 2014; Yao and Shao, 2022).

Table 8: Correlation Analysis

	<i>Density Bonus (Higher Floor Area Ratio)</i>	<i>Expedited Permit and Review Process</i>	<i>Free Marketing and Promotion</i>	<i>Recognition Programs</i>	<i>Training and Educational Opportunities</i>	<i>Priority or Preferential Zoning</i>	<i>Certifications and Awards</i>	
Technical Assistance	1							
Density Bonus (Higher Floor Area Ratio)	0.398415	1						
Expedited Permit and Review Process	0.420018	0.716075	1					
Free Marketing and Promotion	0.503283	0.82703	0.61544	1				
Recognition Programs	0.632384	0.138207	0.144554	0.196414	1			
Training and Educational Opportunities	0.624153	0.158478	0.083827	0.345498	0.82354	1		
Priority or Preferential Zoning	0.465907	0.85735	0.788033	0.767659	0.194166	0.215157	1	
Certifications and Awards	0.606218	0.195634	0.192572	0.232344	0.753432	0.703616	0.270112	1

Source: (Authors' creation)

The data represent a correlation matrix for various strategic factors. These correlation values range from -1 to 1. A value close to 1 suggests a strong positive correlation, a value near -1 indicates a strong negative correlation, and a value around 0 shows no or very weak correlation. In this data, Technical Assistance appears to show a strong positive correlation with

Recognition Programs and Training and Educational Opportunities, with values of 0.632384 and 0.624153, respectively; Density Bonus, represented by a higher Floor Area Ratio, exhibits a strong positive correlation with Free Marketing and Promotion and Priority or Preferential Zoning, with correlation values of 0.82703 and 0.85735 respectively. The Expedited Permit and Review Process also strongly correlates with Density Bonus and Priority or Preferential Zoning, with values of 0.716075 and 0.788033, respectively. Additionally, free marketing and promotion have a strong positive correlation with density bonuses, with a correlation value of 0.82703. Furthermore, Recognition Programs and Training and Educational Opportunities exhibit a strong positive correlation of 0.82354. Training and Educational Opportunities also have a strong positive correlation with Certifications and Awards, with a correlation value of 0.703616. Finally, Priority or Preferential Zoning is observed to have a strong positive correlation with the Density Bonus, with a correlation value of 0.85735. These correlations suggest that these strategic factors are often implemented in tandem or may be influenced by similar elements.

Conclusion

The study explored the game-theoretic approach towards the adoption of green building in facilities management in Johannesburg, South Africa. It specifically investigated the adoption of game theory strategies, application areas and game theory incentives towards promoting green buildings by facilities managers. Few empirical studies use a multiple-strategy approach to game theory in facilities management. The study found that cooperative games, repeated games, evolutionary game theory, and Nash equilibrium were preferred game strategies. Cost-benefit analysis, resource allocation, regulatory compliance, incentive structuring, and strategic collaboration were sometimes game theory application areas. Non-financial incentives were rated as better than financial incentives for green building adoption.

Based on the study, it is recommended that expanding and diversifying the data sources is crucial to improve the scope of this research. Along with utilising online surveys, researchers should engage in methods such as conducting interviews and analysing case studies. To mitigate regional biases and improve the relevance of results, researchers should conduct comparative analyses across regions. By thoroughly studying the effectiveness and consequences of game-theoretic tactics and incentive schemes in various areas, researchers can provide more precise guidance tailored to each region's particular needs. Facilities managers' limited knowledge of game theory can be overcome through joint efforts between researchers and educational institutions through advocacy, research and training. Research should focus on prioritising incentive scheme optimisation to improve green building adoption and study the barriers to using game theory strategies. Future research can study the behaviour of facilities management and that of other stakeholders in the built environment. Future research can use random sampling for generalizability of the results and can be conducted in another location or country apart from South Africa.

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No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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Appendix

GAME THEORY FOR FM STAKEHOLDERS

NASH EQUILIBRIUM

can help in situations where multiple stakeholders (like tenants, developers, and facilities managers) interact.

PRISONER'S DILEMMA

Understanding the dynamics between regarding stakeholders shared responsibility.

ZERO-SUM GAMES

applied in competitive tendering or contract negotiations between vendors and facilities managers.

COOPERATIVE GAMES

Used in the formation of partnerships between facilities managers, suppliers, and other stakeholders.

STAKELBERG MODEL

Useful in situations where regulatory bodies or industry leaders set standards or policies that others then follow.

REPEATED GAMES

Useful in ongoing relationships between facilities managers and other stakeholders, like tenants or vendors.

SIGNALLING GAMES

Used to understand how facilities managers might signal their commitment to green initiatives to attract tenants or partners.

BAYESIAN GAMES

Useful for modelling how stakeholders make decisions under uncertainty.

EVOLUTIONARY GAME THEORY

It can be applied to analyse how sustainable practices might evolve within the field of FM over time.

GAME THEORY PAYOFFS

NASH EQUILIBRIUM

Any chosen strategy is the best
No incentives
Cooperation driven.

PRISONER'S DILEMMA

Rewards
There can be betrayal
Penalties.

ZERO-SUM GAMES

Competitive rewards
Redistribution of resources

COOPERATIVE GAMES

Collaboration,
Joint rewards
Fair rewards
Transferable rewards
Common goals.

STAKELBERG MODEL

Leader determines reward
The follower's reward depends on the leader.

REPEATED GAMES

Discounted rewards
Has long term incentives.

SIGNALLING GAMES

Rewards depend on others' commitment and the facilities manager.

BAYESIAN GAMES

Rewards depend on the manager's experience and activities.

EVOLUTIONARY GAME THEORY

Rewards depend on productivity.
Higher incentives are preferred
Incentives should be presented visually

**Peer Reviewed*

Public-Private Partnerships in Urban Service Delivery: A Case Study of Riverside Park City Improvement District, Mbombela, South Africa *Minenhle Vuyelwa Qwabe¹, Benita Zulch², Partson Paradza³, Joseph Awoamim Yacim² and Steven Ngubeni⁴*

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Abstract

The ability of the public sector to adequately provide public services has declined due to mounting fiscal constraints, mismanagement and inadequate planning. This has led to governments seeking alternative service delivery mechanisms, such as public-private partnerships, to provide public services. City Improvement Districts (CIDs) are public-private partnerships where businesses and property owners collectively conduct landscaping, street cleaning and security services to enhance and improve commercial and business areas. This article examines the effectiveness of public-private partnerships in service delivery by assessing the Riverside Park City Improvement District and its implementation of services in the Riverside Park node, in the City of Mbombela. The study used a qualitative research method, and data were collected from public and private sector employees associated with the Riverside Park CID. The results established that public-private partnerships (PPPs) have great potential, particularly CIDs, to address the challenges faced by South African local, regional, and national authorities. The study concluded that successful urban development in South Africa depends on robust PPPs like CIDs, which alleviate municipalities' financial and operational burdens, freeing resources for essential core services. The paper recommended forming a team comprising the Riverside Park CID officials and the municipal officials for quarterly dialogue and future engagement.

Keywords: Public-Private Partnership, Service Delivery, Riverside Park CID, Mbombela, South Africa

1 Introduction

The presence and activities of CIDs in any region have assisted in shaping the urban neighbourhoods. Accordingly, Didier (2012) reports that establishing CIDs, a private-public partnership, has proven popular globally. This is because of their contributions to enhancing the city's status and the wellness of the people. In South Africa, there are CIDs in all major cities and smaller metropolitan areas. The establishment of CIDs around the world originated in response to socio-economic changes that have been taking place in cities since the 1960s. These socioeconomic changes have led to the deterioration of urban neighbourhoods, with residents and businesses leaving cities because of increased crime. City properties have declined in property value due to the disintegration of funding for metropolitan areas. With economic challenges being faced by local government authorities, CIDs have resulted in a new model for urban management that property owners have led to address the needs of neighbourhoods and communities (Ziebarth, 2020).

2 Background

With rapid population growth, it is anticipated that approximately 8 billion (Seto et al., 2011; Hoornweg and Pope, 2017), which is about 68% world's total population (Profiroiu et al., 2020), will be living in cities by 2050 (Hoornweg and Pope, 2017). This is concerning given the impact of continued population growth on land, air quality, infrastructure, services, and the

climate (U.N. Habitat, 2015). Continued and excessive population growth in cities/urban areas will ultimately lead to an increase in the required services in cities. Urbanisation has increased rapidly in South Africa over the last 20 years (Zhang, 2016; Kundu & Pandey, 2020). Consequently, the number of people who move to urban areas for work opportunities and a better living environment is fast exceeding the supply of services (Prinsloo, 2015).

Traditionally, it has always been the role of the public sector to ensure that basic services such as electricity, water and bulk infrastructure are provided in cities. In South Africa, providing services in cities is more difficult than in most countries due to the impact of an apartheid legacy (Shackleton & Gwedla, 2021). Municipalities have had to invest more in services and opportunities in townships and informal areas to address the service inequality (Heimann & Oranje, 2008). With municipalities having to provide services in townships and informal regions and keeping up with the demand for services in urban areas, it has become increasingly difficult for municipalities to keep up with the constant demand for services that outstrips the supply of services.

The continued disintegration of public services in urban areas has created significant gaps in service provision (Jaglin, 2008; Kanyane, 2014). To alleviate this gap, private property owners have identified the necessity of ensuring that their properties' precincts are safe and well-maintained (Landman, 2006; Cronje and Spocter, 2017). Furthermore, they understand that maintaining these conditions is necessary for promoting an environment conducive to continuous investment. Therefore, in addition to the rates and taxes paid for providing basic services and infrastructure to the Municipalities, private property owners are also willing to incur additional levy payments to offer top-up services in areas where their properties are located. A CID was needed to achieve a wholesome approach towards enhancing not only properties but the entirety of the neighbourhood. Therefore, Didier (2012) notes that establishing CIDs as a PPP scheme has proven popular in both minor and major cities in South Africa.

The establishment of CIDs commenced in the 1970s in North America, Canada, as a mechanism to provide supplemental and complementary services to the services offered by the local authorities. The concept of a CID works by establishing an association for property and business owners in specific geographic areas, where the property and business owners pay a "top-up" or additional levy to the association for the management and enhancement of the area. CIDs provide services such as improved safety, cleaning, landscaping, and the implementation of special projects that enhance the value of a CID area. According to Peyroux (2012), CIDs strengthen the partnership between property & business owners and the municipalities of cities by enhancing cities' economic value and generating more tax revenues for the municipality.

The future of successful development in cities lies in PPPs such as CIDs, which reduce the burden on municipalities to provide services and mitigate the declining budgets of municipalities. In addition, implementing CIDs allows municipalities to focus their attention and scarce resources on delivering basic services effectively. When service delivery and the budget to implement service delivery are diminishing, it is no surprise that initiatives such as CIDs would increase. Previous studies, including Wang et al (2019) and Li et al (2023) in China, Cook (2009) and De Magalhães (2014) in England and Didier (2012) and Ruiters and Matji (2016) in South Africa, focus on the use of PPPs in service delivery. However, while this holds sway when handling less capital-intensive services, what happens to more capital-intensive projects? Thus, little is known about the activities of CID in the City of Mbombela. Therefore, this study investigates the activities of the Riverside Park CID in the City of Mbombela. The primary motivation was to unravel its successes and failures (relative to more capital-intensive services) in resolving the challenges faced by the local authorities, thereby

providing effective services. Findings are expected to assist other South African cities in establishing a similar concern and thus extrapolate to other African towns and cities.

3 Historical Perspective and Literature Review

In gaining insight into Business Improvement Districts (BIDs) (as they are referred to internationally) or CIDs (as they are referred to in South Africa), it is vital to understand that the establishment of BIDs or CIDs has been to respond to global decline of city centres and to support commercial area improvement (Gross, 2013). The primary function of BIDs is to regenerate urban areas and city centres that have become dysfunctional and are struggling to attract businesses (Goldberg et.al, 2019).

Globally, many metropolitan areas commonly face rapid urbanisation due to rural-urban migration. The population in urban areas far exceeds the delivery of various services, including education, health, safety and security, water and electricity, which are considered basic and essential to be provided by the government to the public. In addition, urban areas face massive housing backlogs exacerbated by urbanisation (Kayembe & Nel-Saunders, 2022). According to the UN, the global human population was estimated to be at 2.5 billion in 1950, by November 2022, the international human population had reached 8 billion. In support of a rapidly growing population, local authorities have found providing basic and essential services in urban areas increasingly challenging. Not only has the global population increased at unprecedented levels, but the funds for local authorities to provide basic and essential services have declined, making it difficult for governments to provide these without assistance from private role players.

BIDs or CIDs emerged in North America and South Africa as a tool in response to suburbanization from the 1970s and 1990s, as well as deindustrialisation, which has resulted in commercial businesses relocating to suburbs and away from city centres. Unfortunately, city centres have become dysfunctional and have declined since the rise of suburbanization. Heightened crime, poor infrastructure and vandalism of properties in city centres ensued and this resulted in many inner-city buildings being left vacant and easy targets for vandalism, property owners not receiving income through their vacant buildings and thus this led to the decline in property values in city centres and municipalities losing revenue to finance service provision in these areas (Goldberg et.al, 2019). Around the world, the number of BIDs has increased significantly with there being over 1000 BIDs in the US and over 60 CIDs in South Africa.

Kudla (2022) defines BIDs or CIDs (as they are referred to in some parts of the world), as a group of business/property owners within a designated geographical area, who pay an annual levy to provide supplemental services to their commercial districts. BIDs have been praised for being organisations that supplement services that the public sector has been struggling to provide due to a lack of finances, with privately funded services. The services BIDs aim to provide have played a crucial role in revitalising decaying post-industrial cities experiencing increased crime, unemployment, and decreased tax bases (Kudla, 2022).

BIDs have been used for decades as an economic development tool for small businesses in urban areas. BIDs can be defined as designated or mapped subdivisions of neighbourhoods, where property owners are required to pay additional taxes to fund additional services within that designated area (Elmedni et.al, 2018). BIDs have become a vital tool for improving the physical appearance of neighbourhoods and improving the value of the real estate. They are set up by government laws that authorise the district's operations to provide supplemental services to the district. Guimaraes (2021:22) also notes that BIDs are privately run to solve the decline of some urban areas and are an essential structure between the private and public sectors.

According to Lippert (2012), funds arising from the BIDs are administered by a board that manages all funds from property owners. This is to prevent instances of property owners not covering costs to improve the security and physical appearance of the BID, and who benefit from these services that other property owners pay for. This has greatly benefited property owners by enhancing regional safety and increasing property values and property transactions in an area. An extensive negotiation process with stakeholders is required for a BID to be established. Property owners and business owners need to be a certain percentage for a BID to be formed, they all need to pay fees for the provision of services within the BID and a board of directors of stakeholders needs to be formed that will make decisions about the budget and the services that the BID provides. Without establishing a BID or an alternative initiative to deal with crime and cleaning in a neighbourhood, there is a greater risk of deterioration in those neighbourhoods (Lippert, 2012).

Establishing BIDs requires an obligatory financial contribution from all property owners and a municipality's institutionally controlled framework. Essentially, projects that property owners believe are missing in their neighbourhood or geographical area are identified and implemented in a way regulated by a municipality (Boehme & Warsewa, 2016). Typically, the group of property owners that recognises the need for the BID also identifies the geographic boundaries of the BID, proposes the financing model for the BID, identifies the services that will be conducted in the BID, and proposes the timeframes of implementation. This detailed plan needs to be endorsed by the local authority, and most of the property owners in the designated area must approve the plan (Gross, 2013).

Business Improvement District or City Improvement District By-Laws need to be put into place and endorsed by local government authorities before forming a BID or CID. It is also a requirement that a BID or CID management body is established to manage and control the implementation of a BID or CID plan (City of Nelspruit By-Law, 1999). Once the BID or CID has been endorsed, the board consists of the property owners within the BID boundaries. This board agrees on a management company that will report to the board and ensure that supplementary services are provided in the geographic area (Peyroux, 2019).

The first BID was established in 1970 in Toronto, Canada, as an attempt to fund the upgrading of the Bloor West Village commercial area (Kudla, 2022). This was where a business owner led businesses in the district to oppose an emerging shopping mall threat. The businesses agreed to pay additional taxes to improve the Bloor West Village district. This led to the establishment of over 150 BIDs in the province of Ontario (Holter, 2002). The concept of a BID then spread through the provinces of Ontario, Toronto, and Canada (Peyroux et.al., 2012). Since their establishment in the 1970s, the number of BIDs in Canada and the US has risen to over 800 (Ziebarth, 2020). As indicated by Kudla (2022:2838) the success of the BID concept in Canada led to the establishment of BIDs in the USA, the UK, New Zealand, Australia and South Africa.

A similar approach to establishing BIDs in the United States of America (USA) commenced. The first BID in the USA was established in New Orleans in 1975 and was called the Downtown Development District (DDC). The BID was established to encourage local businesses to prevent blight in New Orleans. Local businesses in New Orleans began to apply tax revenues to meet economic development needs, security, and cleaning (Holter, 2002). Globally, the most significant number of BIDs are found in North America, and the BID model is widely used as a developmental tool and as a long-term strategy to counter the trend of cities losing their businesses to suburbs and the decline in their tax revenue (Ellen et.al, 2007). It is clear from the establishment and growth of BIDs in the USA that they were viewed as a mechanism to prevent the loss of local businesses to suburbanization and as a solution to revitalise struggling downtown cores (D'Souza, 2020).

The spread of BIDs in America and later to many other parts of the world can be attributed to similar challenges faced by businesses in business and inner-city districts. The establishment and functioning of BIDs in America have become a model worldwide. The model has proven effective in guiding local governments on the importance of including private players in their public governance and planning space. Business Improvement in the UK was introduced as part of the Local Government Act in 2003 and came into force in 2004. The first BID was in Kingston, Surrey, and today, the number of BIDs across the UK stands at 290, with most BIDs located in towns or cities.

In South African cities, BIDs were adopted in the mid-1990s as CIDs and operate similarly to those in North American and European countries. City Improvement Districts are established by business and property owners who use funding from additional top-up taxes to improve commercial and residential areas that are in decline. The CIDs depend on a public-private partnership (PPP) – providing private services using public legislation to match the public sector's inability to implement efficient strategies to regenerate cities. As a solution for a significant decline in inner city tax returns, CIDs have provided cash-strapped municipalities a solution for upgrading and enhancing public spaces without burdening municipalities financially (Didier et.al, 2012). The services provided by CIDs include security, landscaping, cleaning, and maintenance.

These services are intended to be supplementary services to those provided by the local municipality and not replace those provided by the local authority. The local authority must agree to the services it offers and the services that the CID will provide. The CIDs in South Africa were established during a democratic transition that came with a change to public policies at the national level and the introduction of neoliberalism. From their initial focus on redistribution through the Reconstruction and Development Programme (RDP), which was the first socio-economic planning policy post 1994 aimed at eradicating social and economic inequalities created during the apartheid era, to the implementation of Growth, Employment & Redistribution strategy (GEAR) in 1996, a policy that was neoliberally inspired in that it had an economic focus to stimulate economic growth in South Africa (Peyroux, 2019).

Implementing the Growth, Employment and Redistribution strategy (GEAR) in 1996 further placed strain on all spheres of government (Chetty & Luiz, 2014). Cities and urban policies implemented since have mainly been influenced by the privatisation of various services and more impact from metropolitan cities concerning shaping economic impact in cities (Didier et.al, 2012). With the growing burden upon cities in their budgets due to backlogs in service provision, the CID concept, as a tool for urban management at a municipal level, has proven to be cost effective for municipalities and has also served as a strategy to aid in addressing the need for cities to address their changing economic needs (Didier et.al, 2012).

Several studies unravel the potential of BIDs or CIDs in city upgrading, albeit with some challenges. Consequently, we review a few of them here. Valli & Hammami (2020) examine the social and political implications of BID Gamlestaden in urban regeneration in Gothenburg, Sweden. The study found that despite its successes in solving problems of distressed localities, challenges of social justice relative to democratic participation, diversity and gentrification risks are its limitations. In Johannesburg and Cape Town, South Africa, Didier et al. (2012) found that issues similar to those of the North American private management model were noticeable. Thus, there is a need for a local framework that satisfies African needs. Similarly, Didier et al. (2013) in Johannesburg and Cape Town examined the resilience and challenges of implementing the CID model. They found a close link to the BID framework and local context, particularly the inherited apartheid legacy. The current study, apart from being undertaken in a

different Province, was meant to assess the performance of the Riverside Park CID relative to its successes and limitations, especially as it concerns bigger services.

4 Methods

This case study research is based on a qualitative research approach to understanding the challenges faced by the City of Mbombela Local Municipality regarding service delivery and the Riverside Park CID's role in effectively providing services. Through understanding the Riverside Park CID and its impact on service delivery, the challenges faced by the municipality and the impact of the Riverside Park CID are outlined.

A qualitative approach was used for this research, given the geographic area-specific focus of the study and the need to understand the research through the experiences of the research participants. This research approach was used to gain an in-depth understanding of the case study and assess the effectiveness of public-private partnerships in service delivery, as outlined in the research topic.

Semi-structured interviews were selected and conducted to allow the interview to have follow-up questions, should the need arise. To capture the interview accurately, recordings are generally made of an interview (Jamshed, 2014), as was the case for this study. One-on-one interviews were conducted with individuals from 4 different organisations to conduct this research. A specific interview guide was prepared for the interviews, allowing for an open-ended conversation with the participants. This permitted the topic to be discussed in detail and enabled the researcher to understand the subject more deeply.

Interviews were conducted with seven key informants who were chosen based on their involvement in establishing the Riverside Park CID in the City of Mbombela, as well as the management of the CID and who have first-hand experience of public-private partnerships. It can also be noted that the sample size could have been larger for this study; however, conducting further interviews with a larger sample size would not necessarily have yielded additional findings, given the shared working experience of individuals in the organisations.

5 Findings

Establishment of the Riverside Park CID

As highlighted by Guimares 2021:22 in the literature, CIDs are geographic areas that are delineated by government laws to authorise their operations and where business/property owners are required to pay levies for set services that are planned to improve the economic viability of that area. The services provided are supplemental services such as landscaping, cleaning and security services.

The above-mentioned characteristics of a CID were also identified in the data collection process from the participants, as they described the establishment of the Riverside Park CID. According to Participant 5,

“Halls Properties first established a property owners association called the Riverside Park Precinct Association which property owners were required to become members of once they purchase property in the precinct. After functioning as a property owners association with voluntary levies for a while, the Association decided to become established as a CID in terms of the Mbombela CID By-Law. This entailed putting a business plan and budget together,

sharing this with members at a public meeting and getting a majority vote of 51% or over to support the establishment of a CID.”

Halls Properties, as previously indicated, was instrumental in the establishment of the Riverside Park precinct and the CID, as noted in the research participant below:

Participant 2: “Halls Properties established the (RPPA), being the landowner of Riverside Park, becoming a member of the association was something incorporated in the title deed conditions of each property owner. This was all managed through the management company that manages the Riverside Park CID.”

A participant from SAPOA, given his proximity to property owners in South Africa and involvement with the government to ensure a good relationship between private property owners and the government, also provided valuable insights into the research on the relationship between the public and private sectors.

Participant 4: “SAPOA’s mission is to represent, protect and advance its members’ commercial property interests within the property industry actively and responsibly. SAPOA’s aims and objectives include, whilst maintaining non-political bias, expanding contacts with Government at all levels to ensure continued good relations and resignation as the authoritative voice of the commercial and industrial property industry.”

The Riverside Park CID was established with intricate planning from both HL Halls & Sons Properties as the property owner/developer and the Mbombela Local Municipality. The CID was established in the same way that CIDs globally have been established – the CID consists of business/property owners that pay levies to an association where set services are performed on behalf of the property owners. The Riverside CID has established good relations with the local government and with organisations such as SAPOA that protect the interests of property owners.

Significance of the Riverside Park CID

The research study is based on analysing public-private partnerships and their effectiveness. The Riverside Park CID, a collaboration between the RPPA and the City of Mbombela Local Municipality, has created a precinct in the City of Mbombela that didn’t exist before 1994. Based on the literature review, private-public partnerships such as CIDs were established in response to the decline of some geographic regions, infamously inner-city areas (Gross, 2013). The Riverside Park CID was based on the basis that investors who purchased in the Riverside Park precinct would become members of the RPPA and pay levies for a set of services that would benefit the precinct and their properties in the precinct. The RPPA would not have established the CID without buy-in from the local municipality; the same also applies to the regional municipality. The Riverside Park area has been developed to benefit the City of Mbombela, given the node's growth. The Riverside Park CID continues to be a beneficial partnership and valuable for the Riverside Park precinct (Riverside Park, 2023).

In an interview with an employee from Silulumanzi on 2024-11-21, it was established that the City of Mbombela Local Municipality put in place a private concession with Silulumanzi for a period of 30 years for the provision of water and wastewater services in the city.

Participant 6: “Once the concession was put in place, the overall quality of water supply to the city improved. There have been improvements in households being able to access basic water.”

According to Chetty & Luiz (2014: 573), this is further emphasised by the fact that in 1999, when the concession first came into place, approximately 44% of households in the Mbombela

area did not have access to basic water. In 2009, this number had decreased to 12%. It can be concluded that Mbombela Local Municipality's partnership with a private concessionaire improved the quality and provision of water services throughout the city.

However, the provision of water and wastewater services is also linked to the maintenance of and upgrading of bulk infrastructure that cannot be attended to without sufficient capital spending to maintain wastewater treatment plants and to build new reservoirs. The ability of the government to manage and prioritise capital remains a challenge in the South African water sector (Chetty & Luiz, 2014).

An interview with an employee of the City of Mbombela Local Municipality on 2024-11-22 confirmed that the City of Mbombela Local Municipality is trying to source alternative ways of funding bulk infrastructure projects for the city. Participant 7: *"The municipality lacks the capacity to fund major infrastructure projects. This is why public-private partnerships are important - they enhance the quality and efficiency of infrastructure development, benefiting both the municipality and its residents."*

In the Riverside Park CID, given the influence of Halls Properties in the area, the city has partnered with Halls Properties to ensure that critical bulk infrastructure is installed, and that the area continues to develop.

The Riverside Park CID has established itself as a world-class precinct and an area set apart from the rest of the city. In interviews with the management of the Riverside Park CID, held on 2024-06-24 and 2024-11-20 respectively, it was confirmed that:

Participant 1: *"In terms of the latest stats received from security companies in the city and the precinct, there has been a 90% increase in crime in the city and about a 10% increase in crime that takes place in the Riverside precinct."*

Participant 5: *"The Riverside CID has been hugely beneficial for the city, not only in attracting new development and as such expanding the rate base for the city, but also protecting the rate base by underpinning and increasing the property values and showcasing the city to visitors and tourists."*

In an interview with Participant 5 on 2024-11-20, it was further confirmed that the Riverside Park development was a greenfield development and that establishing a CID was always envisaged as part of the urban design framework for the development. The CID was established as a development opportunity and a means of growth for the City of Mbombela, given that this city section was undeveloped before the early 1990s. The management of the CID through a management company has ensured that the CID remains safe and clean. More recently, as indicated in the data collected, the CID has needed to assist the municipality with service delivery that is within the municipal work scope, as per the SLA. The CID has now stepped in to repair potholes, re-paint markings on the roads and fix streetlights, because of the financial state of the local municipality and lack of capacity. The CID has effectively implemented service delivery and can play a larger role in overall urban management in the City of Mbombela Local Municipality.

The Riverside Park CID has served the City of Mbombela well in economic and social growth. As also indicated by Participant 3, the Riverside Park CID area, with involvement from the private sector has developed into the precinct it is today.

In an aerial view, Figure 1 shows the Riverside Park precinct area before 1994 and before the precinct's establishment.

Figure 1: Riverside Park prior to 1994 (HL Hall & Sons 2016:114)

Figure 1 shows the greenfield nature of the area. Before any development in this area, the land was agricultural, and it was also not included within the urban edge of Mbombela at this time. From what the participants indicated in their interviews, it is clear that the Riverside Park precinct depicted above in Figure 1 was a precinct established from agricultural land and was meticulously planned with the growth of the city of Mbombela in mind.

Figure 2 depicts the same Riverside Park precinct area in 2021, with an aerial view, showing extensive township development that has taken place. The figure illustrates the establishment of the precinct, and as indicated by the participants, the “distinguishable” nature of the precinct. One can see the cleanliness of the precinct and how having an urban design framework in place has played a critical role in its physical appearance, almost 30 years after its establishment.

Figure 2: Riverside Park Phase I (Duncan, 2021)

Figure 1 shows the same area, as in Figure 2, taken in 2021, and shows the city's growth that has taken place through the Riverside Park node over 27 years. The precinct has developed into a mixed-use node that has completely changed the city's landscape. As indicated by the participants, the Riverside Park CID has significantly impacted the City of Mbombela. As

depicted in the above picture, it has attracted businesses and anchor tenants into Riverside Park, and effectively contributes to the property rates base in the city. As indicated by Goldberg et.al (2019), CIDs emerged in response to city centres becoming dysfunctional, heightened crime and infrastructure vandalism negatively influencing city centre property values. The evidence of how the Riverside Park precinct has changed the urban environment, especially since 1994, is visible. The extent of development also indicates the ability of the precinct to attract investors and businesses. Figure 3 depicts a street view of the Riverside Park precinct, taken in 2014.

Figure3: Riverside Park (HL Hall & Sons, 2016:118)

In Figure 3, one can visualise the physical state of the precinct – how it has been well-maintained and managed over the years since its establishment. The precinct accommodates numerous national companies, the provincial government offices, residential development and the University of Mpumalanga. This has also been affirmed by the participants stating that the precinct is set apart aesthetically from the rest of the city and has attracted much development and investment.

6 Conclusion

This study demonstrates the potential of Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs), specifically through implementing City Improvement Districts (CIDs), to address the challenges local authorities face in South Africa. The Riverside Park CIDs were used to evaluate the performance and constraints of PPP in the City of Mbombela, South Africa. The study found an enormous contribution of the Riverside Park CID to the sustained service provision in the City of Mbombela. The findings significantly affect urban development and policymaking regarding limited public resources and increasing urban challenges. Given the constraints faced by local governments, such as shrinking budgets and declining service delivery capacity, CIDs can offer a valuable alternative or complementary approach to urban management. Municipalities can leverage private resources and expertise to improve urban services, such as cleaning, security, and landscaping, by partnering with private sector stakeholders while focusing on critical infrastructure needs. Successful CID implementation requires careful planning, strong community engagement, and effective stakeholder collaboration.

Given South African municipalities' current challenges, including declining service delivery capacity and financial constraints, effective collaboration with the private sector is crucial for unlocking future urban development. The private sector possesses valuable resources,

including financial capital and skilled personnel, which can significantly enhance service delivery. It's essential to recognise that this is a mutually beneficial relationship. At the same time, the public sector relies on the private sector to address service delivery gaps, the private sector also requires a stable and supportive public sector environment to operate effectively.

This study has highlighted a critical gap: municipalities' diminishing capacity to fulfil service delivery mandates. This challenge is evident even within well-managed areas like City Improvement Districts (CIDs). CIDs are increasingly burdened by the shortfall in municipal services, struggling to maintain the high service levels they aim to provide while simultaneously addressing the municipality's failure to deliver basic services such as street lighting, pothole repairs, and road markings.

To address this, municipalities should explore innovative models of public-private partnerships. For example, municipalities could consider authorising CIDs to assume responsibility for additional services, beyond their current scope, particularly in areas where the municipality consistently fails to deliver. Like a concession model, this approach could empower CIDs to address critical service deficiencies within their boundaries directly. This model holds significant potential for the Mbombela Local Municipality, particularly in areas like Riverside Park and other urban centres, where declining municipal service delivery poses a considerable challenge to urban development and quality of life.

The future of successful urban development in South Africa hinges on robust public-private partnerships, such as City Improvement Districts (CIDs). These partnerships offer a crucial mechanism for alleviating municipalities' financial and operational burdens, allowing them to redirect limited resources towards essential core services.

To maximise these partnerships' effectiveness, the Riverside Park CID and the City of Mbombela are recommended to establish regular quarterly forums for dialogue and collaboration. These forums will serve as crucial platforms for:

- Joint service delivery reviews: Regularly assessing the performance of both parties in fulfilling their respective service delivery obligations.
- Enhanced accountability: Fostering a culture of accountability and transparency between the CID and the municipality.
- Proactive issue resolution: Identifying and addressing emerging challenges and proactively seeking solutions to service delivery gaps.
- Continuous improvement: Facilitating ongoing communication and collaboration to refine service delivery models and improve urban outcomes.

Disclosure Statement

The authors reported no potential conflict of interest.

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**Peer Reviewed*

Vacancy Rates of Shopping Malls in Ghanaian Cities: Key Drivers and Mitigating Strategies *Farida Daphne Issah*¹; *Kenneth Appiah Donkor-Hyiaman*²; and *Selina Oduro Acheampong*³

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Abstract

This paper investigates the key factors influencing current vacancy rates of nine shopping malls in Ghanaian cities and the strategies implemented to reduce vacant spaces. Drawing on key informant interviews, it discovers that the average vacancy rate has declined from 15.4% to 9.3% across all the nine shopping malls between 2021 and 2024 accounting years. This study found five key factors that influence vacancy rates of the selected malls. These included increasing competition and over-supply; economic weaknesses and budgetary expectations; service quality and responsiveness to tenant demands; rent tax effects; location as well as available facilities or amenities. Five main strategies are adopted to attract and retain tenants. These are enhanced property marketing, business marketing, rent free periods, tenant installation allowances as well as rent reduction to tenants occupying larger space and with long-term leases. The findings can be helpful to market analysts in forecasting future rents and development opportunities; properties investors for informed decision making; and stakeholders may recognize difficulties and improve plans.

Keywords: Malls, Vacancy rates, Tenants, Cities, Ghana

1.1 Introduction

Ghanaian cities, particularly Accra, the capital city, have witnessed significant growth in the number of Western-style shopping malls since the year 2000 (Eduful & Hooper, 2024). The Accra-Tema city-region, for instance, has over six malls such as the Accra, West Hills, Junction and Marina Malls. Eduful & Eduful (2022) explained that malls in Accra have been financed by foreign capital; developed with international architectural forms; have been occupied and run by international merchandize and brands, although local products are also showcased; and are patronized by various categories of people including Ghanaians, Africans and foreigners.

A key factor accounting for the growth in shopping malls is an increasing middle class (Yeboah et al., 2023). A Knight Frank report stated that with a growing middle class and urbanisation, consumer demand is steadily increasing, driving expansion in sectors such as shopping malls, supermarkets, and e-commerce platforms (Knight Frank, 2024). According to Eduful & Eduful (2022), malls provide not only shopping spaces but also multiple functions; social networking, recreation, symbolic consumption particularly for middle-income and, in part, low income groups. Research indicates that malls generate taxes and employment in Ghana, and informal retailing activities around some malls are key sources of livelihood and a possible important contributor to the alleviation of urban poverty (Oteng-Ababio & Arthur, 2015).

Despite the growth of shopping malls, the western-styled retail sector in Ghana has experienced challenging times (Broll Property Intel, 2018). The Oxford Business Group (2020) reported that even though the sector boomed in its first decade, the proliferation of retail space had begun to exceed demand, resulting in higher vacancy rates and a slowdown in new retail developments because the market had become more saturated. The average vacancy rate for retail space was 20% in the third quarter of 2018 (Broll Property Intel, 2018; Oxford Business Group, 2020). Additionally, it was recently

reported that general activity in Ghana's retail market in the second half of 2024 was subdued, and both the third and fourth quarters of 2024 saw minimal activity, with little improvement compared to the first half of 2024. Also, it was stated that the supply of retail spaces was mostly unchanged, with a significant portion of small to medium sized spaces vacant (Broll Ghana, 2024). Outside Ghana, and in South Africa and the UK in particular, it has equally been reported that key shopping mall and shopping centres are facing challenges with high vacancy rates and declining occupancy (BusinessTech, 2024; White et al., 2025).

This paper therefore principally investigates the key factors influencing vacancy rates of malls in Ghanaian cities, the challenges faced in filling vacant spaces, and the strategies implemented to reduce vacant spaces through a case study of nine shopping malls in Ghana – A&C, Accra, Achimota, Marina, West Hills, Junction, Kumasi City, Jubilee, and Takoradi Malls. While researchers including Hobden (2014), Eduful & Eduful (2022) Yeboah et al. (2023) and Eduful & Hooper (2024) have conducted studies on malls in Ghana, particularly Accra, there has been little research on factors influencing vacancy rates of malls in and outside Accra. Moreover, reports by the Ghana Investment Promotion Council (GIPC) (2022) and Broll Property Intel (2018) not entirely focusing on vacancy rates of malls have briefly stated past vacancy rates of key malls in Ghana. This paper seeks to fill this gap in knowledge. It contributes to research on the operations and performance of shopping malls in Ghana as Hagler (2024) emphasized that vacancy rates directly affect profitability and general asset value. Sterling (2024) also added that the vacancy rate is a key metric for assessing the financial performance and health of rental properties.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. The next section reviews literature relating to factors that influence vacancy rates of commercial properties. This is followed by a description of the research methodology with a discussion of data collection methods and the selected malls as well as analytical methods. Then, the findings are presented and discussed along with a conclusion.

2.0 Factors influencing Vacancy Rates of Commercial Properties Literature Review

Vacancy rates can be classified into natural and nominal types. Natural vacancy rate has been defined as the vacancy rate for a property market if supply and demand were in balance and the level to which vacancy rates will return to over the long term (Realestatewords.com, 2024). On the other hand, nominal vacancy rate is the percentage of units or properties unoccupied in a particular property or market. It is the opposite of occupancy rate which estimates the percentage of occupied units, and is calculated by dividing the number of currently vacant or unoccupied units by the total number of units, and then multiply by 100 to express it as a percentage (Geltner et al., 2006; Hagler, 2024; Sterling, 2024).

This study focuses on the nominal vacancy rate (hereafter called vacancy rate). It is reported that a lower vacancy rate indicates high demand and effective property management, whereas a higher rate can suggest challenges including over-supply or poor tenant retention (Sterling, 2024). Comendador (2023) also noted that high vacancy rate shows that the property is not generating as much rental income as it could, which can have a negative effect on an investor's return on investment. According to Luna (2024), a good vacancy rate is normally between 5% and 10%, rates below 5% mean high demand, whereas rates above 10% can indicate issues that need attention.

Geltner et al. (2006) stated that the vacancy rate is one indicator that shows the present balance between supply and demand in an area (the other is the present market rent level). This helps to forecast future rental price trends and opportunities for development (Sterling, 2024). Geltner et al. (2006) further explained that generally, anticipated tightening of the market (as indicated by an increasing space shortage) should result in higher rents and lower vacancy rates, and an expected surplus of supply will

lead to increasing vacancy rates and decreasing rents. Brueggeman & Fisher (2011) also noted that when local property investors and owners sense that vacancy rates are decreasing and rents are increasing, it generally suggests that the amount of rentable space is also decreasing consequently, more development could be feasible.

Figure 1 shows the vacancy rates of major malls in Ghanaian cities as of the second quarter of 2021. The GIPC (2022) reported that although malls house a considerable number of retailers, recent trends show some retailers are choosing converted residential developments while others operate from medium-sized retail plazas. Besides this, footfall to retail centers decreased considerably in 2020 owing to the Covid-19 pandemic which reduced demand and resulted in the closure of shops. The Takoradi Mall had the highest vacancy rate of 59% of grade A malls in Ghana. However, the retail market recorded a considerable increase in footfall during the 2021-2022 period after the lifting of most lockdown restrictions in 2020 (Northcourt, 2021; GIPC, 2022).

Figure 1: Retail Vacancy Rate: Q2-2021

Source: GIPC (2022)

Besides the Covid-19 pandemic, other factors influencing vacancy rates have been reported to include economic conditions; during economic downturns, consumer spending can reduce causing reduced sales for retail tenants, and this can lead to an inability to make rent payments and later eviction. Population growth, location and lease terms and conditions have also been reported as factors that influence vacancy rates. A property's location can affect desirability and people's decision to occupy a property and thus vacancy rates (Comendador, 2023; Hagler, 2024; Sterling, 2024). Also, property owners who provide flexible lease terms, attractive incentives, and competitive rents may retain existing tenants and attract new tenants unlike those who do not (Hagler, 2024).

Sterling (2024) further adds that property amenities and condition and seasonal fluctuations can influence vacancy rates; well-maintained properties with attractive features tend to retain tenants and for instance, in college towns, vacancy rates can be higher during holidays (Comendador, 2023). Moreover, the supply and demand dynamics of the market can affect vacancy rates; in a rental market with limited supply, vacancy rates are likely to be low and vice versa. The availability of new properties can also affect vacancy rates (Comendador, 2023). It was further reported that increasing operational costs had discouraged new entrants and limited the expansion plans of existing tenants in Ghana's retail market (Broll Ghana, 2024). Regarding strategies to decrease vacancy rates, Sterling (2024) and Luna

(2024) suggested improved property management (ensuring responsive service and timely maintenance), enhanced marketing, competitive pricing and adding/improving amenities, as well as improving tenant screening and lease terms; offering flexible lease options.

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Location and nature of selected malls

Six shopping malls were selected in Accra. Accra and West Hills malls were chosen because the former is the first fully-enclosed mall in Ghana and the latter is one of the largest in the country (both are enclosed malls). Achimota and Junction Malls were selected because they are strip malls, and A&C and Marina Malls were chosen because both have a combination of retail and office functions (Eduful, 2019; Yeboah et al., 2023). Outside Accra, the Kumasi City Mall was selected because it is the first world class shopping mall in the northern part of Ghana (Kumasi City Mall, 2023). Jubilee Mall was chosen because it is currently the only mall in Kumasi within a university campus; the Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology. The Takoradi Mall was chosen because it is the first modern shopping mall in the Western and Central Regions of Ghana (Takoradi Mall Limited, 2021). Figure 2 shows the location of the nine shopping malls.

The Accra, West Hills, Junction, Achimota and Kumasi City Malls were currently owned by Lango, a South African real estate investment firm while the Takoradi Mall was owned by RMB Westport, also a South African company. The A&C Mall was currently owned by the A&C Development Company (A&C Mall, 2025), Marina Mall was owned by Marina Market, a daughter company of Marina Group founded in Burkina Faso (Cobblah, 2019), and the Jubilee Mall was owned by HODA Properties Limited. Most (eight) of the malls under study were managed by Broll Ghana Limited who are responsible for leasing the spaces and carrying out some facilities management services. However, the Jubilee Mall was managed by Assenta Property Consulting. The retail tenants in these malls included health and beauty shops, restaurants, pharmacies, boutiques, fashion accessories shops, African crafts shops, airline ticketing, forex bureaus, department and electronics stores, supermarkets, and cinemas.

Figure 2: Map of Ghana showing the Location of the Malls

Source: Authors' Construct

3.2 Data collection methods

This study adopted the qualitative research approach. The main goal of qualitative research, according to Oranga & Matere (2023) is to investigate and offer deeper, comprehensive, and detailed description of phenomena from non-numeric data, often describing and explaining individual experiences, relationships, and group norms. Interviews were used to collect data from key informants from the malls in September 2024 and April 2025. The key informants included a property officer and manager, three lease administrators, and two operations managers. Pahwa et al. (2023) stated that key informants offer high level perspectives and comparative insights on questions or issues under study. Lokot (2021) also noted that within the hierarchy of research methods, key informant interviews can be positioned as generating more valuable knowledge owing to the status and expertise of the individual being interviewed.

The level of education of the informants was high, with most (57%) holding masters degrees and the rest having undergraduate degrees. This suggests that the informants are knowledgeable and are in a good position to offer appropriate data for the study. Most of the informants also had three or more years of experience in property management.

Table 1: Number and job positions of respondents

Demographic	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Job Title/Position</i>		
Property Officer	1	14%
Property Manager	1	14%
Lease Administrator	3	43%
Operations Manager	2	29%
<i>Education Level</i>		
Undergraduate	3	43%
Postgraduate	4	57%
<i>Years of Experience</i>		
1 – 5 years	3	43%
6 – 10 years	3	43%
> 10 years	1	14%

The interviews conducted were semi-structured, which involved a dialogue between the researcher and a participant, guided by a flexible interview topic guide and supplemented by follow-up questions, probes and comments (DeJonckheere & Vaughn, 2019). The method as stated by DeJonckheere & Vaughn (2019), allows the researcher to gather open-ended data, to investigate participant beliefs, thoughts, and feelings about a specific topic and to delve deeper into personal and occasionally sensitive issues. Data collected during the interviews included the current vacancy rates of the malls and their effects on mall performance, their view of the factors that influence vacancy rates of malls, the strategies used to reduce vacancy rates, and the challenges faced in filling vacant spaces.

Data from the interviews were transcribed and carefully read and reread so as to identify categories and themes that help to understand factors influencing vacancy rates of malls in major Ghanaian cities

(Dawadi, 2020). To ensure validity, interviews were conducted with officials who were in a position to comment authoritatively on the topic and efforts were made to corroborate the interview data with other sources, for instance, observations (Denscombe, 2010). Having discussed the research methodology, the next section presents the study's findings with quotes from participants in order to increase transparency and credibility of the findings. Tenny et al. (2022) stated that reporting in qualitative research involves adding details and descriptions of the setting involved as well as quotes from participants; this detail is known as "rich" or "thick" description and is a strength of qualitative research.

4.0 Findings

4.1 Description of Malls

Table 2 provides a description of the nine shopping malls based on the year of establishment, location within the cities, space size, as well as rent per use. Six of the malls are in the capital city, Accra (Greater Accra region); two are in Kumasi (Ashanti region); and the one in Takoradi (Western region) as noted earlier. The oldest and youngest are the A&C mall (2006) and Takoradi mall (2018) respectively. The West Hills, Junction, and Jubilee malls were established in the same year (2014).

The West Hills mall has the biggest retail space (27,000m²) while the smallest is the Jubilee mall (about 3,000m²). The total space stock per city location is positively correlated with the population and purchasing power of the respective cities. The capital city, Accra, has the highest population (2,388,000) with a biggest total space stock of 113,811m²; followed by Kumasi with population of 443,981 having a total space stock of 21,926m²; and the least populous city, Sekondi-Takoradi (245,382) (Ghana Statistical Service, 2021; Macrotrends LLC, 2025) has the smallest stock of 11,000m².

Table 2: Description of Selected Malls

Name of Mall	Year Opened	Location	Space (m ²)	Rent/m ² (US\$) Per Month	
				Office	Retail
A&C Mall	2006	East Legon, Accra	~30,000 (net leasable area of 20,000)	12 - 16	21 – 46
Accra Mall	2008	Tetteh Quarshie Interchange adjacent the Tema Motorway, Accra	21,311	10 - 70	10 – 70
Marina Mall	2013	Airport City, Accra	9,000	28	25 – 30
West Hills Mall	2014	New Weija along Accra-Cape Coast Highway, Accra	27,000	17 - 45	4 – 40
Junction Mall	2014	Nungua, Accra	11,500	32 - 61	14 – 70
Jubilee Mall	2014	KNUST (Commercial Area), Kumasi	3,221	7.74 - 9.67 ^a 5.16 - 7.74 ^b 3.87 - 6.45 ^c	
Achimota Retail Centre/Mall	2015	Achimota, Accra	15,000	20 - 60	25 – 30
Kumasi City Mall	2017	Asokwa, Kumasi	18,705	11 - 57	21 – 57
Takoradi Mall	2018	Cape Coast-Sekondi Road, Takoradi	11,000	30	20

Source: Field data, Accra Mall (2023); LEDing Hostels (2025); A&C Mall (2025)

Note: Unlike the other malls, rent/m² at the Jubilee Mall is not based on use (i.e., office or retail) but based on the location of the shop with rents decreasing from the ground floor to the second floor. The superscripts *a*, *b*, and *c* represent the ground floor, first floor, and second floor respectively.

The findings showed that rent charged at the malls differ per use – office or retail. The rent per square metre per month across both office and retail ranged from \$4 to \$70 dollars. The rent of office spaces ranged from \$10 to \$70 per square metre while that of retail shops ranged from \$4 to \$70 per square metre. According to Hobden (2014), rents in Accra mall are significantly higher than those in the other parts of Accra. There have been instances when mall tenants demanded reduction in high rents. For example, in 2020, it was reported that a group called the Accra Mall Tenants Association called on government to help them engage with mall management over exorbitant rent and service charges and to halt the charging of rent in dollars. This is because it is against Ghana's Foreign Exchange Act (Nettey, 2020). The Bank of Ghana (2022) bans pricing, advertising, or demanding payment for goods and services in foreign currency in Ghana. Despite these existing interventions, pricing in dollars still persists.

4.2 Vacancy Rates of the Shopping Malls

Figure 3 shows the 2024 and 2021 vacancy rates of the malls under study. The findings show that the 2024 vacancy rates of all the malls were relatively low, below 20% and largely lower than vacancy rates in 2021, except at Junction and A&C Malls. An ongoing major road project near the Junction Mall may be a reason for the current higher vacancy rate. A respondent explained that roadworks near the Junction Mall had affected business at the mall by reducing customer traffic. Thus, attracting tenants was difficult since access to the mall was challenging. Moreover, the respondents explained that the higher vacancy rate at A&C mall was mainly caused by empty offices owing to remote working, the emergence of new office and retail buildings near the mall and the conversion of housing in nearby areas into offices. They further noted that the existence of the mall in the neighbourhood gives added values to properties around the mall.

Generally, the current lower vacancy rates suggest that *demand for mall spaces has increased between 2024 and 2021*. Accra Mall currently had the lowest vacancy rate while the Takoradi Mall had the highest vacancy rate. According to respondents, the differences in vacancy rates is mainly due to the location and the purchasing power of people who access Accra Mall. They explained that most expatriates are in Accra and the Accra Mall has international brands, such as Mac and Apple as tenants, so when expatriates desire goods or luxury products, they tend to go to the Accra Mall. Moreover, the location of Accra Mall (at the Tetteh Quarshie Interchange adjacent the Tema Motorway and close to Villagio) makes it easily accessible to expatriates and middle/high income earners. Hobden (2014) also pointed out that the Accra Mall is located near the airport and at the center of some of Accra's most wealthy and exclusive neighbourhoods, such as Airport residential, East Legon, and Trasacco Valley (the most expensive gated housing development in Ghana). The author further confirmed that the development of Accra mall was consciously focused on attracting foreign travellers by providing them with amenities comparable to those they enjoy at home (Hobden, 2014).

There is also significant prestige associated with having an Accra Mall address although shops are usually empty with visitors preferring to browse from the safety of the wide, air-conditioned corridors where people-watchers crowd onto benches (ibid.). For tenants with shops in many locations throughout Accra, having a place in the mall has become a marketing strategy; foot traffic is high, with about 18,000 visitors daily. There are few places in Accra where one could advertise to so many prospective customers (Hobden, 2014).

Figure 3: Current and Past Vacancy Rates of selected Malls

Source: Field data (2024; 2025) and GIPC (2022)

However, the location of West Hills Mall (on the outskirts of Accra, close to Weija/Kasoa) reduces tenants' ability to attract customers. The mall is also located in a low-to-middle income neighbourhood (Eduful & Hooper, 2024). In addition, even though the vacancy rate at Takoradi Mall had significantly decreased, it was found that investors were unsuccessful in reaching the forecasted target market. Also, the residents of Sekondi-Takoradi hardly shop at the mall but instead, normally go to the Takoradi market circle because they consider the mall a luxury place. The Takoradi market circle is the main place for buying and selling in the city. The Oxford Business Group (2020) emphasized that even though Ghana has witnessed an extensive development of Western-style shopping malls in larger cities, the traditional market still dominates the retail sector, constituting 90% of retail trade in Ghana. It was further found that the Kumasi City Mall initially had two anchor tenants, so the mall attracted more tenants than the Takoradi Mall. Generally, these findings confirm Knight Frank's (2024) assertion that vacancy rates had reduced across most key malls, and by the beginning of 2024, Accra Mall, for example was virtually fully leased.

This study found that high vacancy rates negatively affected the general performance of malls. The vacant spaces directly affect the revenue stream of owners; each unoccupied unit represent lost rental income that may have contributed to debt payments, taxes, maintenance costs and other operational expenses. Higher vacancy rates can also decrease the overall profitability and value of a retail building, which corroborates the findings of Hagler (2024). These views are captured in the following observations:

“Vacancies result in a negative rental variance that goes on to affect the valuation of the mall. Since vacancy has a direct relationship with rental flow/cashflow, an increase in the former causes the latter to rise and the vice versa is true.” (Respondent 2).

“The vacancy rate has affected the overall profitability of the mall. It reduced rental income and hence reduced funds for operational costs, since most of the costs are fixed.” (Respondent 4)

4.3 Factors influencing Vacancy Rates of Shopping Malls

This study found five key factors that influence vacancy rates of the selected malls. These included increasing competition and over-supply; economic weaknesses and budgetary expectations; amenities, service quality, and responsiveness to tenant demands; rent tax effects; and location as well as available facilities or amenities.

4.3.1 Increasing Competition and Over-Supply

Informants attributed the current vacancy levels to over-supply of retail spaces due to increasing competition among property developers, both institutional and individuals. The development of new shopping centres and the rapid conversion of residential properties to commercial properties coupled with cheaper rents have all contributed immensely to the existing vacancies, which are consistent with GIPC (2022). These observations are highlighted in the following responses:

“I will attribute the factors influencing vacancy rates to supply and demand. The rate at which new developments are coming in is alarming. Almost every corner of Accra boasts of a commercial property whereas the rate of demand increases slowly annually.”(Respondent 3)

“The increasing conversion of residential properties into commercial properties has also increased the supply of commercial properties in the market. These converted commercial properties offer much cheaper deals to tenants making it challenging for us to maintain some of our tenants who eventually leave to these properties to sustain their business.” (Respondent 2)

The competition from new developments and conversions is however highest in Accra. The main source of competition for the Takoradi and the Kumasi Malls are existing retail markets like Takoradi Market Circle and Adum and Kejetia in Kumasi markets respectively.

4.3.2 Economic Weaknesses and Budgetary Expectations

The informants believed that the economic downturn, particular from 2020, contributes to the vacancy rates. In spite of the modest gains in the 4th quarter of 2024, the Ghanaian cedi depreciated against the US Dollar

on a year-to-date basis by a margin of -22.14% to close at GHC14.70 in December. Ghana's inflation also remained high in 2024; between 20% and 26% (Broll Ghana, 2024). The downturn has had two impacts that are acting in opposite directions. First, the combination of high and rising inflation and high currency depreciation has increased operational costs, hence, requiring commensurate increases in rent to maintain the required rate of return on these investments. Second, the rising inflation has reduced the purchasing power of consumers and reduced sales while the high currency depreciation is causing the dollarized rents to change by the day, often upwards. This is a major concern for the tenants given the exchange rate differentials they have to deal with on a daily basis since tenants price their goods in Ghana cedi and yet have to pay rents in dollars. Current economic conditions could worsen tenants' ability to pay rents and lead to eviction subsequently (Hagler, 2024). These views are reflected in the following:

“The current economic crisis has led to a decline in people’s interest in renting spaces at the mall. Exchange rates (cedi to dollar) keep changing to the disadvantage of the cedi and since we charge rent in dollars, prospective tenants feel operating in the mall would cost them too much money with little returns. Hence, their unwillingness to lease spaces in the mall.” (Respondent 5)

4.3.3 Amenities, Service Quality, and Responsiveness to Tenant Demands

The difficulty in finding the right tenant for a specific space and meeting the expectations of various tenants is key. From these responses, it appears tenant preferences are shifting towards flexibility, cost efficiency, sustainability, and improvement of amenities. Shorter lease terms attract tenants seeking flexibility while longer leases deter most tenants. Flexible lease terms are negotiable and may come in the form of friendly rent escalations and exit clauses. Flexibility may also come in the form of the ability of a tenant to downsize when needed. This has become necessary due to the volatile economy which poses serious cost and affordability implications for tenants. Flexible lease terms therefore enable tenants to manage business risk and cost. It seems therefore that property owners must adapt to these trends to retain and attract tenants. However, this can sometimes lead to conflicts with their financial goals, particularly in terms of rent payment structures and space availability. As one respondent put it:

“Tenants often times want a clean white box. However, post vacation of a tenant means the landlord may have to offer funds to fit out the space to attract new tenants. There is that difficulty of securing funds from landlord to repurpose the space for prospective tenants.”

Tenant preferences and demands viz-a-viz the responsiveness of property officials thus influence tenant decisions to rent, stay, or leave a property and thus influence vacancy rates of malls. The rising operational costs have made it difficult for landlords to meet all the demands of tenants. For instance, landlords fitting out costs would increase significantly if short-term leases are entertained but that flexibility is what tenants prefer. The following are some of the responses that highlight the observations above:

“Recently a tenant complained of AC issue and demanded that we change them. Because that tenant was a major tenant and occupies quite a huge area, all the ACs had to be changed so that we could retain them. We sought for the best AC to suit the tenant’s needs.” (Respondent 1)

“Currently the main trend noticed is that tenants want flexible lease terms. There is also a focus on green/sustainable buildings. Without these demands being met, some tenants opt to walk away.” (Respondent 4)

Additionally, some respondents believed that the availability or lack of amenities in a mall affected a potential or existing tenant's decision to occupy space or extend their lease agreement. One of the respondents stated that *“The facilities in a building are very key in attracting tenants. A building with lifts, sustainably designed, good finishes, occupational health and safety is able to attract and maintain premium tenants.”* Another respondent similarly said that:

“Tenants are aware that an attractive space invites more customers to shop in commercial properties. That is why we spend so much on our building facilities. Poor maintenance means an unattractive property and that leads to a fall in foot traffic. So yes, building amenities and facilities like lifts, escalators, spacious parking, well maintained washrooms, are of much importance to tenants and influence vacancy rates.”

However, a respondent was of the view that adequate amenities and facilities played a little role in attracting and retaining tenants owing to costs involved. In the words of this respondent:

“I believe amenities and facilities have less and, in some instances, negative influence on vacancy rates of commercial properties. Tenant would rather opt for a building that is well situated with no amenities and/or facilities and have access and reach to customers/shoppers. The rationale behind this is, amenities and facilities have cost attached to them, an example is service charges. Having to pay an extra fee outside the necessary amenities such as electricity and water can be a deal breaker for prospective tenants.”

4.3.4 Rent Tax Effects

Higher withholding rent tax reduces the amount of financial resources available to landlords to cover operating costs. In Ghana, rent tax is 15% on commercial properties. It was discovered that to meet their required rate of returns, landlords tend to shift the tax burden on tenants in the form of higher rents, which reduces affordability and increases vacancies. In the words of a respondent,

“A regular tenant pays within 6% to 21% tax component on their monthly rental obligations. These tax components create an additional burden on a tenant that makes low sales. This is a problem for even anchor tenants.”

4.3.5 Location and Available Facilities or Amenities

The location of malls was found to play a role in attracting or deterring tenants. According to one of the respondents, *“Location plays a key role in tenant attraction. People prefer to have their businesses located in prime and developed areas with good roads, visibility and a location that aligns with their target market in terms of their demographics.”* Another respondent opined that *“Location is key not only for tenants but also developers. Tenants prefer properties in prime locations in order to have direct access to the patronizing public. Location is an asset when a building is properly situated and a liability when misplaced.”* These findings suggest that a good location ensures visibility and accessibility for potential tenants and customers. Clearly, locating your premises in heavily populated or prime areas usually equates to higher foot traffic which tends to lead to higher patronage of goods and services.

Besides this, the difficulty in finding the right tenant for a specific space and meeting the expectations of various tenants were reported. Further, the lack of funds in undertaking refurbishment of a space after the

exit of a tenant made it difficult to secure new tenants which often affected vacancy rates in their properties. Respondents in this study were further asked about the various strategies adopted to reduce vacancy rates; their replies are presented in the next section.

4.4 Strategies adopted to reduce Vacancy Rates

Respondents adopt five main strategies to reduce vacancy rates – property marketing, business marketing, rent free periods, tenant installation allowances, and rent reduction to tenants occupying larger space and with long-term leases. These strategies could be applied individually or combined for effectiveness. They use various marketing channels to convey information about vacancies to prospective tenants. These marketing channels include the placing of billboards and signages in front of the properties and having meetings with estate agents as well as using digital marketing/social media tools, which are considered helpful in bridging the information gap. According to one respondent:

“Most of the estate agents drive around looking for properties, so these billboards often helps. There are also frequent calls to agents to update them on your vacancy. Sharing your property brochure with agents and having meetings with them builds a special rapport which is key in getting your properties leased.”

The management officials of malls also assist tenants to improve their business performance. Marketing campaigns are usually conducted to help tenants, especially the poorly performing ones, attract more customers, thereby improving their financial performance. As one of the respondents said:

“Through tenant performance which is determined by their effort ratio, we identified least performing tenants and help them with marketing campaigns. Also, through the effort ratio which compares a tenant’s total monthly sales to total monthly rental obligations we identify tenants that require rebates in order to survive and grant them accordingly.”

Some tenants are also offered rent free periods to enable them test the market. Rent free periods essentially reduces the financial burden on tenants in the short-term giving them the flexibility to adjust their business model to the new market and business environment. Also, tenant installation allowances and flexible lease terms are key tools in enticing tenants to take up spaces in the mall. According to a respondent:

“On rare occasions we have given opportunity to prospective tenants to operate in the mall for say a year just to test the market. That has helped us a bit.”

Other strategies that had been adopted included offering incentives in the form of rent reduction to tenants occupying large amounts of space and with long term leases. These strategies used to reduce vacancy rates align with those stated by Sterling (2024) and Luna (2024) who suggested improved marketing, competitive pricing and improving lease terms by offering flexible lease options.

5.0 Conclusion

This paper investigated the key factors influencing vacancy rates of shopping malls in Ghanaian cities and the strategies used to reduce vacancy rates. The findings showed that the 2024 vacancy rates of all the malls were relatively low, below 20% and largely lower than vacancy rates in 2021, except at Junction and A&C Malls. The Junction Mall situation could be attributed to an ongoing major road project which has affected

business at the mall by reducing customer traffic while that of A&C mall was mainly owing to remote working and the development of new commercial properties near the mall. This study found five key factors that influence vacancy rates of the selected malls. These included increasing competition and over-supply; economic weaknesses and budgetary expectations; amenities, service quality, and responsiveness to tenant demands; rent tax effects; location as well as available facilities or amenities.

Five main strategies are adopted to attract and retain tenants. These are enhanced property marketing, business marketing, rent free periods, tenant installation allowances, rent reduction to tenants occupying larger space and with long-term leases. Generally, these results show that the management of the malls have been successful in reducing the vacancy rates from previous levels. However, vacancy rates of malls are heavily dependent on broader economic improvements, such as currency stabilization and a decrease in operational costs. Thus, stakeholders may need to adopt innovative strategies to navigate the challenging landscape, while policymakers address the underlying economic issues to stimulate growth in the sector (Broll Ghana, 2024). This study adds to the literature on vacancy rates and shopping mall performance from Ghanaian context.

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No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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**Peer Reviewed*

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Abstract

Providing services within the built environment, particularly in residential properties, directly enhances people's satisfaction. People derive satisfaction from such properties and neighbourhoods, which is reflected in their demand and the amount they are willing to pay. Accordingly, the energy crisis in South Africa has led some property developers/owners to provide alternative power or energy to their new or existing properties. Even though previous studies have researched this subject, this study is the first to evaluate real estate agents' views on home seekers' demand for property with alternative energy and the feasibility of providing alternative energy to residential properties in Johannesburg. We gathered data from the real estate agents, who also supplied relevant information on residential properties in Johannesburg's different neighbourhoods/suburbs. The study established that it is financially feasible for property developers/owners to provide alternative energy to residential properties to alleviate the erratic Eskom electricity supply and save on monthly electricity purchases. Moreover, integrating alternative energy can significantly increase consumers' search and willingness to pay a higher premium for residential properties in Johannesburg. The study concludes that property developers/owners could incorporate alternative energy from the design stage or retrofit existing residential properties with clean and renewable energy to enhance their competitiveness in the market.

Keywords: Alternative Energy; Energy Savings; Eskom; Financial Feasibility; Residential Properties.

Introduction

Infrastructure provision within a property has been linked to the occupant(s) social and economic satisfaction. Thus, people look at the presence and quality of infrastructure facilities in a property when deciding about a house to live in and the amount to pay for rent or purchase. Even though several infrastructure facilities may be found in a property, the demand for facilities significantly varies across locations, regions, and countries. Again, while infrastructure facilities are essential, the study of Famuyiwa & Otegbulu (2012) and Feng et al. (2023) reports that water and electricity are at the top of consumers' quest for better living conditions in a property. However, this study's concern is the provision or availability of electricity within a property.

Before recent developments in the South African housing market, where the electricity supply has become erratic, emphasis was never placed on the availability of electricity. This is because of its ubiquity; thus, home seekers never saw it as a priority. The uneven spread of electricity within a geographical area (occasioned by load-shedding) is one of the reasons for the frequent changes of apartments by households in most South African cities and towns (Mbatha, 2023). Load-shedding continues to shape the attitudes of homeowners, homebuyers, and homesellers in the South African property market. According to the managing director at Sentinel Homes, enjoying one's home

during load-shedding and maintaining its future value have become closely intertwined (Maggie, 2023).

The importance of electricity when searching for a property or neighbourhood has resulted in some property developers/owners providing alternative electricity or energy. Property developers/owners often use generators as backup power for residential developments, but this practice contributes to excessive fossil fuel use and pollution (Magocoba, 2020). Alternative clean energy solutions are limited in implementation, and generators are preferred due to lower initial capital costs and design requirements. Implementing clean energy systems is also more feasible. Even though the installation cost is higher, the lower price of use makes it more attractive than the fossil fuel mechanism. Therefore, unravelling the financial feasibility of installing solar-powered electricity in a building becomes necessary.

As consumer preferences evolve, particularly with integrating renewable energy solutions, it is imperative to evaluate how these alternatives can harmonise with residential needs and thus promote energy efficiency and resilience. Hence, this study focused on the extent to which property developers/owners provide alternative energy to their new or existing residential properties. This is to determine the responsiveness of consumers to the provisions of alternative energy solutions in the property market. Thus, a critical property market analysis is imperative for property developers/owners to unravel the implications of installing clean and renewable energy and its worthwhileness in addition to the property purchase cost. Therefore, the question that readily comes to mind is whether installing clean and renewable energy affects developers'/owners' monthly energy savings.

Thus, it could be hypothesised that providing alternative energy for residential properties is not a worthwhile investment in Johannesburg. In the past, Mayr et al. (2015) explored the implications of alternative energy on electricity sales revenues and its viability for property investment in Cape Town. Also, Marope & Phiri (2023) focused on the impact of load shedding in multiple South African regions on the housing market. While the contributions of these studies are well noted, the current study is different because the current electricity situation is more severe than it was 10 years ago. Thus, more compelling reasons for investment in alternative energy are presenting themselves in South Africa. Additionally, this study focuses on alternative electricity, not just the consequences of load shedding on the housing market, as previous studies had midwived.

This research contributes to ongoing debates on energy transmutation frameworks, giving important insights for policymakers, industry stakeholders, and property developers/owners to navigate the complex alternative energy sustainability in South Africa.

Literature Review

Much empirical literature has explored the causal relationship between energy use and economic growth (Saad & Taleb, 2018; Kahouli, 2018; Armeanu et al., 2019; Fan & Hao, 2020). This underscores the significance of energy consumption as a driver of economic development (Chirwa & Odhiambo, 2020). Accordingly, Chirwa & Odhiambo (2020) point out four elements investigating the relationship between energy use and economic growth. These include (1) growth, (2) conservation, (3) feedback, and (4) neutrality. These four elements directly link electricity

consumption and economic growth. The relationship shows a bidirectional movement from electricity consumption to economic growth, and economic growth to electricity consumption. While the energy crisis significantly affects economic growth, as is noticeable in different sectors, the concern of this study is the property investment sector.

Electricity is a significant challenge in some countries, especially those with an energy crisis, which is linked to dwindling economic development and, to a large extent, return on property investment (Leskinen et al., 2020; Gajdzik et al., 2024). Thus, there is a need to harness the opportunities offered by generator and renewable energy technologies. Like many developing countries, South Africa is experiencing regular power outages, attributable to the ageing coal-fired power infrastructure. This situation has precipitated a growing interest in alternative energy sources, which present challenges and solutions for residential energy consumers (Tariq-Khan et al., 2016; Skosana et al., 2023).

While these challenges persist, much literature suggests that alternative energy, especially renewable sources such as solar and battery storage (solar photovoltaic (PV)), significantly influences property values (Gardiner et al., 2020; Leskinen et al., 2020; Qu & Jeon, 2022). The study of Ma et al. (2015) in Western Australia found an additional premium of 2.3 to 3.2 per cent that homeowners are willing to pay for properties fitted with photovoltaic systems. Thus, alternative energy efficiency and self-sufficiency are increasingly desirable for people, especially in regions with frequent loadshedding. The value attached to electricity by households in almost all regions is the reason for integrating battery backup systems with solar panels in some homes (Amrr et al., 2018; Sun et al., 2025).

Relative to energy cost in use, the study of Goebel et al. (2017) suggests that while battery prices may increase with prevailing market conditions and initial investment costs, future price reductions could boost profitability. The electricity challenges in South Africa are not as terrible as in Nigeria, where almost all federating states are battling an epileptic electricity supply. Thus, the study of Adepoju & Babaloba (2022) demonstrates how electricity challenges in Nigeria significantly impact investors' intentions to invest in residential real estate with alternative energy. In this premise, energy availability is necessary and an important component of property investment decisions. Furthermore, literature suggests that properties with superior energy could achieve higher transaction prices and quicker sales (Chegut et al., 2019; Brounen & Kok, 2011).

Alternative energy efficiency leads to increased investment in residential properties. The known South African study was Nurick et al. (2018), which came under Real Estate Investment Trust (REIT) scrutiny, showing how incorporating alternative energy-efficient and renewable power to properties may improve yields and value within diversified asset portfolios. The current study is different because it considers the feasibility of providing an alternative energy supply to residential properties for developers/owners relative to the monthly savings that could be made from electricity purchase. Additionally, the study surveyed the views of real estate agents in line with consumers' demand for houses fitted with alternative energy, which, to our knowledge, previous studies have not undertaken.

However, some studies identified consumer attitudes as critical determinants in purchasing energy-efficient appliances in residential properties. Waris & Ahmed (2020) assert that positive attitudes toward alternative energy-efficient home appliances significantly impact consumers' purchase intentions, affirming similar trends observed in previous research by Ha & Janda (2012). This suggests that awareness and positive perceptions of consumers can drive demand for alternative energy in properties. Again, the study highlights that consumer attitudes significantly influence purchasing decisions, indicating that fostering positive attitudes towards energy efficiency is essential for increasing the adoption of efficient products. Thus, it shows the need for targeted marketing strategies that emphasise the benefits of energy-efficient technologies.

Moreover, the study of Nguyen et al. (2016) affirms that knowledge of energy efficiency determines consumer attitudes and purchasing behaviour. The study emphasises the need for increasing consumer knowledge to boost demand for energy-efficient gadgets in emerging markets. However, despite positive consumer attitudes outlined in the preceding studies towards energy efficiency, barriers remain that could hinder widespread acceptance. Ali et al. (2021) reported that cost, inconvenience, and availability of energy-efficient devices can deter consumers who desire energy-efficient products from purchasing. The presence of green or energy-efficient elements in a property bred scepticism, as Francesca et al. (2023) reported, which could further complicate the landscape, potentially dampening demand even among environmentally conscious consumers.

Methods

This study utilised a survey of real estate agents and a sample of residential property case studies in Johannesburg's Bramley, Sunninghill, Fourways, Brynston, Roodepoort, Midrand, Waterfall Park, Sandton, Rhodesfield, Randburg, Boksburg, Kew, and Rosebank neighbourhoods/suburbs. The example property data with variables, including cost of acquisition, cost of alternative energy, alternative energy solutions, and estimated energy savings, among others, was supplied by Vicon Group. The sample contains twenty-nine properties, of which five were industrial and commercial, and thus were eliminated from the analysis. Two residential properties located in Pretoria were found in the sample. These were eliminated from the sample to keep the analysis within the Johannesburg jurisdiction. Thus, a total of twenty-two residential properties were used in this analysis.

Furthermore, we administered an online questionnaire to local practising resale state agents in Johannesburg, South Africa, via a Google Form link. Accordingly, forty-five real estate agents completed and returned the questionnaire to the repository. Questions about consumer preferences for residential properties with the alternative energy solution were also asked. Additionally, questions related to the cost of alternative energy, marketability, and competitiveness of residential properties with clean and renewable energy were included in the questionnaire. We used the percentile descriptive statistics to analyse the views of real estate agents, and the monthly energy cost savings to determine the feasibility or worthwhileness of investment in alternative energy in Johannesburg, South Africa.

The monthly energy cost savings from electricity purchase were tested using the payback period technique. This is to ascertain the duration for developers/owners to recoup the capital invested in

providing an alternative energy supply to their residential properties. Utilising the payback period in this analysis was to support the feasibility component of the investment in alternative energy supply. Accordingly, the following formula was used:

$$PBP = \frac{D}{G \times Y} \quad \text{eq. 1}$$

Where *PBP* is the payback period, the cost of an alternative energy solution is *D*, *G* is the estimated monthly cost of energy savings on electricity purchase, and *Y* is the 12 calendar months in the year.

Results and discussion

This section deals with data analysis, presents the results, and discusses the key findings. As previously noted, two data sets were used, including (1) those related to the properties fitted with alternative energy and (2) those collected from the real estate agents.

Results of sampled residential properties in Johannesburg

The sampled properties have alternative energy provided through retrofitting before or after purchase. The analyses demonstrate that alternative energy contributes to the habitability of properties (for occupiers), leading to more demand for them, reflected in the price that home seekers are willing to pay. Table 1 provides a detailed analysis of the sampled residential properties in Johannesburg.

Table 1: Feasibility analysis of the cost of alternative energy in residential properties in Johannesburg

No	A	B	C (x)	D (y)	E (x+y)	F	G	H
1	Alwayn Street Bronkhorstpruit	3kw hybrid PV System with 200ah gel batteries	R860,000.00	R48,000.00	R908,000.00	R980.00	R650.00	66.33%
2	Copperleaf Estate Centurion	5kw hybrid PV System with 5.1 kWh 48V Lithium batteries x 2	R4,500,000.00	R90,000.00	R4,590,000.00	R1,960.00	R1,720.00	87.76%
3	Copperleaf Estate Centurion	5kw hybrid PV System with 5.12 kWh 48V Lithium batteries x 2	R4,500,000.00	R100,885.00	R4,600,885.00	R1,960.00	R1,720.00	87.76%
4	Copperleaf Estate Centurion	10 Off-Grid PV System with 10 kWh 48 V Power Box PRO X 4	R7,500,000.00	R150,000.00	R7,650,000.00	R3,920.00	R3,440.00	87.76%
5	Copperleaf Estate Centurion	10kw Off-Grid PV System with 5.1 2kwh 48 v Lithium Batteries x 3	R7,500,000.00	R150,000.00	R7,650,000.00	R3,920.00	R3,440.00	87.76%
6	Copperleaf Estate Centurion	16kw Off Grid PV System with 100/80 Freedom One battery	R1,000,000.00	R385,000.00	R1,385,000.00	R6,160.00	R5,510.00	89.45%
7	Copperleaf Estate Centurion	5Kw hybrid PV System with 5.12 kWh 48V Lithium batteries	R4,500,000.00	R110,000.00	R4,610,000.00	R1,960.00	R1,720.00	87.76%
8	Midstream Estate	5kw hybrid PV System with 5.1 kWh 48V Lithium batteries x 2	R4,700,000.00	R90,000.00	R4,790,000.00	R1,960.00	R1,720.00	87.76%
9	Midstream Estate	5kw hybrid PV System with 5.1 kWh 48V Lithium batteries x 2	R4,700,000.00	R90,000.00	R4,790,000.00	R1,960.00	R1,720.00	87.76%
10	Ruimsig Country Estate	3kw hybrid PV System with 24V Lithium Battery	R3,200,000.00	R43,785.00	R3,243,785.00	R980.00	R650.00	66.33%
11	Second Street Randjiespark Midrand	3kw hybrid PV System with 24V Lithium Battery	R2,800,000.00	R48,000.00	R2,848,000.00	R980.00	R650.00	66.33%
12	Magalies Bryanston	5kw hybrid PV System with 5.12 kWh 48V Lithium battery	R5,100,000.00	R78,000.00	R5,178,000.00	R1,960.00	R1,720.00	87.76%
13	Aero City Vallei Road, Rhodesfield, Kempton Park, Ext 1	5kw hybrid PV System with 5.12 kWh 48V Lithium battery	R2,800,000.00	R73,499.00	R2,873,499.00	R1,960.00	R1,720.00	87.76%
14	Serengeti Estate	5Kw hybrid PV System with 5.12 kWh 48V Lithium batteries	R6,500,000.00	R96,000.00	R6,596,000.00	R1,960.00	R1,720.00	87.76%
15	Serengeti Estate	5Kw hybrid PV System with 5.12 kWh 48V Lithium batteries	R6,500,000.00	R96,000.00	R6,596,000.00	R1,960.00	R1,720.00	87.76%
16	Serengeti Estate	5Kw hybrid PV System with 5.12 kWh 48V Lithium batteries	R6,500,000.00	R96,000.00	R6,596,000.00	R1,960.00	R1,720.00	87.76%
17	Serengeti Estate	5Kw hybrid PV System with 5.12 kWh 48V Lithium batteries	R6,500,000.00	R96,000.00	R6,596,000.00	R1,960.00	R1,720.00	87.76%

18	Waterfall Estate	5Kw hybrid PV System with 5.12 kWh 48V Lithium batteries	R6,500,000.00	R96,000.00	R6,596,000.00	R1,960.00	R1,720.00	87.76%
19	Finch Street, Southernwood, Mthatha	16kw Off Grid PV System with 5.12 kWh 48v Lithium batteries x 3	R8,000,000.00	R215,000.00	R8,215,000.00	R6,160.00	R5,510.00	89.45%
20	Albert Street Weltevreden Park	5kw hybrid PV System with 5.12 kWh 48V Lithium battery	R2,900,000.00	R100,885.00	R3,000,885.00	R1,960.00	R1,720.00	87.76%
21	Cedar Creeks Estate Fourways	5Kw hybrid PV System with 5.12 kWh 48V Lithium batteries	R4,100,000.00	R96,000.00	R4,196,000.00	R1,960.00	R1,720.00	87.76%
22	Cedar Creeks Estate Fourways	5Kw hybrid PV System with 5.12 kWh 48V Lithium batteries	R4,100,000.00	R96,000.00	R4,196,000.00	R1,960.00	R1,720.00	87.76%

A = Name of Township/Suburb; B = Alternative power solution; C = Cost of acquisition (x); D = Cost of alternative energy/power solution (y); E = Total initial investment (x+y); F = Monthly electricity purchase before alternative energy; G = Estimated energy savings on electricity purchase; H = Estimated Saving on Electricity Purchase (Percentage). A Rand is exchanged for 0.057 United States Dollar as of 23/08/2025.

The results in Table 1 show that alternative energy provision is a worthwhile investment because it benefits the owners or occupiers of such properties. Accordingly, though all the residential properties sampled from these neighbourhoods/suburbs have a higher cost of alternative energy purchase, the savings made from the monthly purchase of electricity show that the running cost is minimal.

Take, for instance, the residential property in Copperleaf Estate, Centurion, in serial number 6; the cost of property acquisition was R1,000,000.00, while the cost of alternative energy was R385,000.00. The cost of alternative energy is relatively high, but there is a significant benefit in the monthly energy savings of R5,510. Thus, the result shows that the owner(s) or occupier(s) of such a property could only pay the monthly sum of R650 for electricity. In the feasibility appraisal, the savings from electricity are significant and thus demonstrate the feasibility of the investment. Going through the analysis in Table 1, we take another property at Ruimsig Country Estate, Roodepoort, in serial number 10. Though the cost of property is high (R3,200,000.00), there is a lower cost of installing alternative energy (R43,785.00) compared to other properties analysed. The type/capacity of alternative energy within the premises depends on the owner(s) or occupier(s)' energy needs.

The concern of this study is the users' energy-saving ability relative to the alternative energy installed within the property. In the example property, the monthly payment for electricity before the installation of alternative energy was R980, but after the installation, the user saved the sum of R650 on electricity. Again, the result implies that the user only pays a monthly sum of R330 for electricity. Thus, a considerable reduction in electricity costs shows that investment in alternative energy is worthwhile. The findings in this analysis reveal that integrating alternative energy, particularly solar power, in residential properties in Johannesburg has shown promising results in terms of economic feasibility and environmental impact. This is because apart from the savings owners or occupiers are making, the problems associated with using fossil fuels on the environment when using electricity generators are minimised.

As already stated, the payback period technique was used to perform further analysis, unravelling the time it takes to recoup the investment cost in alternative energy. Thus, the monthly savings from the electricity purchase cost were summarised in Table 2.

Table 2: Payback period for alternative power/energy solution

No	B	D	G	PBP	Actual payback
1	3kw hybrid PV System with 200ah gel batteries	R48,000.00	R650.00	6.1538	6 years, 1 month and 25 days
2	5kw hybrid PV System with 5.1 kWh 48V Lithium batteries x 2	R90,000.00	R1,720.00	4.3604	4 years, 4 months and 10 days
3	5kw hybrid PV System with 5.12 kWh 48V Lithium batteries x 2	R100,885.00	R1,720.00	4.8878	4 years, 10 months and 20 days
4	10 Off-Grid PV System with 10 kWh 48 V Power Box PRO X 4	R150,000.00	R3,440.00	3.6337	3 years, 7 months and 18 days
5	10kw Off-Grid PV System with 5.1 2kwh 48 v Lithium Batteries x 3	R150,000.00	R3,440.00	3.6337	3 years, 7 months and 18 days
6	16kw Off Grid PV System with 100/80 Freedom One battery	R385,000.00	R5,510.00	5.8227	5 years, 9 months and 26 days
7	5Kw hybrid PV System with 5.12 kWh 48V Lithium batteries	R110,000.00	R1,720.00	5.3295	5 years, 3 months and 28 days

8	5kw hybrid PV System with 5.1 kWh 48V Lithium batteries x 2	R90,000.00	R1,720.00	4.3604	4 years, 4 months and 10 days
9	5kw hybrid PV System with 5.1 kWh 48V Lithium batteries x 2	R90,000.00	R1,720.00	4.3604	4 years, 4 months and 10 days
10	3kw hybrid PV System with 24V Lithium Battery	R43,785.00	R650.00	5.6135	5 years, 7 months and 11 days
11	3kw hybrid PV System with 24V Lithium Battery	R48,000.00	R650.00	6.1538	6 years, 1 month and 25 days
12	5kw hybrid PV System with 5.12 kWh 48V Lithium battery	R78,000.00	R1,720.00	3.7791	3 years, 9 months and 10 days
13	5kw hybrid PV System with 5.12 kWh 48V Lithium battery	R73,499.00	R1,720.00	3.5610	3 years, 6 months and 22 days
14	5Kw hybrid PV System with 5.12 kWh 48V Lithium batteries	R96,000.00	R1,720.00	4.6512	4 years, 7 months and 24 days
15	5Kw hybrid PV System with 5.12 kWh 48V Lithium batteries	R96,000.00	R1,720.00	4.6512	4 years, 7 months and 24 days
16	5Kw hybrid PV System with 5.12 kWh 48V Lithium batteries	R96,000.00	R1,720.00	4.6512	4 years, 7 months and 24 days
17	5Kw hybrid PV System with 5.12 kWh 48V Lithium batteries	R96,000.00	R1,720.00	4.6512	4 years, 7 months and 24 days
18	5Kw hybrid PV System with 5.12 kWh 48V Lithium batteries	R96,000.00	R1,720.00	4.6512	4 years, 7 months and 24 days
19	16kw Off Grid PV System with 5.12 kWh 48v Lithium batteries x 3	R215,000.00	R5,510.00	3.2517	3 years, 3 months and 1 day
20	5kw hybrid PV System with 5.12 kWh 48V Lithium battery	R100,885.00	R1,720.00	4.8878	4 years, 10 months and 20 days
21	5Kw hybrid PV System with 5.12 kWh 48V Lithium batteries	R96,000.00	R1,720.00	4.6512	4 years, 7 months and 24 days
22	5Kw hybrid PV System with 5.12 kWh 48V Lithium batteries	R96,000.00	R1,720.00	4.6512	4 years, 7 months and 24 days

The payback period is an important metric to assess an investment's profitability. It indicates the duration required for an investment to generate enough cash flow to recover the initial investment cost. Generally, a shorter payback period signals a more attractive investment; it allows stakeholders' to recoup their investment quickly and reinvest the funds into new projects. Relative to investment in solar energy (as an alternative power source), monthly savings from electricity purchase were used to assess the feasibility of such an investment. Accordingly, the results in Table 2 provide the relative duration for the investment to pay back. Analyses show that in all, it will take three to six years to payback, thus affirming the worthwhileness of the investment in Johannesburg.

The studies of Prehoda & Pearce (2017) and Salim et al. (2024) suggest a reasonable payback period of between 5 and 10 years for investment in solar energy. This implies that the investment in alternative energy supply (solar energy) in the Johannesburg property market is feasible. These findings corroborate results from earlier studies by Benli and Gürtürk (2021) in Turkey and Tharo et al. (2022) in Indonesia. The studies found that households can substantially reduce their electricity bills after transitioning to solar energy. In particular, the study of Tharo et al. (2022) quantified monthly electricity expenditure reductions after installing alternative energy (solar power systems) and found monthly savings of around 100,000 rupiah. These savings indicate a simple payback period of approximately one year for the investment.

Furthermore, there are considerable studies, including Cerin et al. (2014) in Sweden, Seddiki & Bennadji (2019) in Algeria, and Pinto et al. (2022) in Spain, that illustrate the growing momentum towards renewable energy adoption, highlighting various factors that contribute to its feasibility in other jurisdictions outside the Johannesburg residential property submarkets.

Thus, the results in this analysis also support earlier findings of Cerin et al. (2014), whereby alternative energy solutions, such as solar photovoltaic (PV) installations, have economic and financial benefits for households. This study did not directly evaluate the implications of the alternative energy, using the rental movements, on the premium it adds to property prices compared to traditional properties, as Cerin et al. (2014) evaluated. Nonetheless, an inference from the results in Table 3 and the challenge of electricity in South Africa is that providing alternative energy could add a premium to property prices.

Results of the surveyed real estate agents on consumers' preference for alternative energy residential properties in Johannesburg

This section contains the results of the analysis of the real estate agents. The demographic background of the real estate agents reveals that 18 (40%) have 0 - 5 years, 10 (22%) have 6 - 10 years, 14 (31%) have 11 - 20 years, and 3 (07%) have > 20 years of experience in the agency business. This places them on a better platform to adequately answer all the questions raised in this analysis. The main area that characterises the activities and focus of the real estate agents' marketing shows that 13 (29%) are into middle-income housing, while 15 (33%) engage in mixed/other real estate business. Analysis also shows that 10 (22%) estate agents are engaged in luxury housing, and 7 (16%) are engaged in entry-level housing markets in Johannesburg.

Furthermore, we analyse the views of real estate agents on their perception of home consumers/buyers' preference for alternative energy properties in Johannesburg. The Cronbach Alpha test value of 0.776 shows an acceptable internal consistency among items within the Likert scale. This implies high reliability in this analysis according to the established guidelines. The guideline states that a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.7 to 0.8 is typically considered adequate for most scenarios (Burgos-Benavides et al., 2023). The results are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3: Estate agents' perception of consumers' preference for alternative energy properties

No	Perception of consumers' preference for alternative energy supplied (AES) properties	5	4	3	2	1	Mean	Std Dev.	Rank
1	Clients increasingly demand residential properties with AES due to persistent load shedding.	29(64.4)	12(26.7)	02(4.4)	01(2.2)	01(2.2)	4.489	0.8692	1 st
2	Properties with AES are easier to market and sell than those without.	24(53.3)	13(28.9)	03(6.7)	02(4.4)	03(6.7)	4.178	1.1734	2 nd
3	The cost of installing AES is a barrier to widespread adoption in residential properties.	21(46.7)	16(35.6)	04(8.9)	02(4.4)	02(4.4)	4.156	1.0651	3 rd
4	AES increases the appeal of residential developments among foreign or high-income buyers.	18(40.0)	17(37.8)	08(17.8)	01(2.2)	01(2.2)	4.111	0.9347	4 th
5	AES features provide a competitive advantage when marketing residential properties.	19(42.2)	16(35.6)	03(6.7)	06(13.3)	01(2.2)	4.022	1.1178	5 th
6	Retrofitted AES in existing properties adds significant resale value.	15(33.3)	16(35.6)	09(20.0)	04(8.9)	01(2.2)	3.889	1.0493	6 th
7	The absence of AES negatively affects property sales in the current market.	14(31.1)	13(28.9)	10(22.2)	04(8.9)	04(8.9)	3.644	1.2641	7 th
8	Incorporating AES improves the long-term value and marketability of residential properties.	14(31.1)	13(28.9)	06(13.3)	07(15.6)	05(11.1)	3.533	1.3751	8 th
9	Buyers are willing to pay a premium for homes equipped with AES.	11(24.4)	15(33.3)	05(11.1)	11(24.4)	03(6.7)	3.444	1.2890	9 th

The results in Table 3 show the views of real estate agents on consumers/buyers' behaviour towards alternative energy properties within the Johannesburg property market. Accordingly, the analysis shows a mean of 4.5, implying that buyers prefer properties with alternative energy to those without this technology. The buyers' preference for alternative energy properties in Johannesburg makes them easier to sell than those without these features. The mean to support this was 4.2, as shown in the results. Despite the importance buyers place on the alternative energy properties in the study area, the huge purchase cost, with a mean of 4.2, is a significant challenge. This was already found in Ali et al. (2021), where the installation cost was a substantial limitation to adoption in Pakistan. This notwithstanding, the lower use cost and the monthly energy savings make it a worthwhile investment.

Other findings in this study, including the appeal it offers to foreign or higher-income home buyers (mean=4.1), increase competitive advantage (mean=4.0), scaling up the value of retrofitted residential properties (mean=3.9), among other compelling variables, show that alternative energy properties are the real deal in the Johannesburg market. The study of Forýs et al. (2020) in Szczecin, Poland, supports the view that, given the increasing energy cost, buyers prioritise houses with alternative energy, thereby enhancing the market prices. Even though payment of a premium for properties with alternative energy in Johannesburg justifies consumers' demand, the analysis reveals it to be the least in the order of ranking among other variables, with a mean of 3.4. This, however, does not negate the fact that alternative energy is desirable among home seekers in the Johannesburg property market.

Analysis also shows that the absence of alternative energy affects property sales (mean=3.6). These findings generally aligned with the results of Pinto et al. (2022), indicating that using renewable energy systems in residential buildings can substantially reduce greenhouse gas

emissions, confirming that such systems benefit both residential energy demands and environmental sustainability. Even though the drive towards alternative energy solutions is growing across different jurisdictions, the heightened momentum is greater in countries with enormous energy crises. Thus, we reject the hypothesis that states providing alternative energy to residential properties is not a worthwhile investment in Johannesburg.

Conclusion

This study focused on evaluating costs associated with property purchase, and alternative energy relative to monthly energy savings and achieving owners' or occupiers' satisfaction. The study also assesses the perceptions of real estate agents towards home seekers/buyers' preferences for properties fitted with alternative energy. Renewable energy systems are increasingly becoming essential components of residential investments in both developed and developing countries. However, frequent load-shedding and an unreliable electricity supply usually necessitate their proliferation in developing countries. As climate challenges and energy costs increase, the marketability of homes featuring renewable energy technologies in comparison to the fossil fuel mechanisms is rising.

Accordingly, the study emphasises several critical findings relating to property acquisition costs, renewable energy expenses, and resulting savings, drawing from various case studies, literature and real estate agents to support these conclusions. The analysis reveals that the initial outlay for acquiring residential properties and the cost of installing alternative energy systems, primarily solar photovoltaic (PV), could be enormous. However, these investments yield substantial long-term savings. Properties that adopted solar energy solutions in Johannesburg reported savings between R650.00 and R5,510.00 monthly on electricity bills. This translates to considerable annual savings, which can recuperate the investment in renewable technologies within a reasonable time frame.

The payback period metric used in this analysis supports the claim that investment in alternative energy in Johannesburg and, to a large extent, the whole of South Africa is worthwhile. This is because within three to six years, the investment could repay the amount spent, which could be used for a reinvestment in other profitable undertakings. The findings were a testament that for owners/occupiers, the social and economic benefits of alternative energy solutions are a worthwhile investment. As reported in this study, the huge capital required for alternative energy investment is a matter of concern. Thus, with the desirability of alternative energy technology in the residential property sub-sector, some investors may find it challenging to acquire it. The government should provide incentives to real estate investors or work out a reduction in the cost of alternative energy so that investors and other home users can afford them.

The affordability of alternative energy technologies would benefit household electricity savings and reduce pressure on the already overstretched Eskom facilities. However, the current study could not extend to other cities in other provinces due to cost and time constraints. However, future studies may consider extending boundaries to other Provinces for generalised findings that reflect the South African housing markets.

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Disclosure Statement

The authors reported no potential conflict of interest.

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**Peer Reviewed*

A Conceptual Framework for Exploring the Interconnections Between Housing and Health for Sustainable Development in South Africa. *Prisca Simbanegavi¹, Koech Cheruiyot¹, John Karuitha¹, Ezekiel Lengaram¹, Yewande Adewunmi¹.*

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Abstract

Housing conditions are a critical social determinant of health, particularly in low and middle-income contexts such as South Africa, where historical inequalities and rapid urbanization contribute to persistent disparities. This study addresses the problem that, despite evidence linking housing to health outcomes, there is limited integrated conceptualization of how physical, socio-economic, environmental, and policy factors interact to shape health inequities in low-income urban settlements. The study aims to develop a conceptual framework that explains the interconnections between housing quality, affordability, stability, and safety, and their influence on physical and mental health outcomes. A desk-based rapid literature review was conducted using SCOPUS and EBSCO HOST databases, focusing on global frameworks from the WHO and UN-Habitat, African-specific scholarship, and empirical studies on housing and health. The resulting framework integrates physical, environmental, socio-economic, and policy dimensions, highlighting how structural deficiencies such as overcrowding, poor ventilation, inadequate sanitation, and insecure tenure do amplify vulnerability to communicable and non-communicable diseases. The findings provide a holistic lens for interdisciplinary research, guide empirical analysis, and inform policy integration between the housing and health sectors. Overall, the study demonstrates that improving housing systems is pivotal for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 3, 6, and 11.

Keywords: Housing conditions; Health outcomes; Low-income settlements; Conceptual framework; South Africa; Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Introduction

The legacy of apartheid in South Africa continues to shape housing conditions and access to essential services. During the apartheid era, legislation such as the Group Areas Act systematically denied Black South Africans access to adequate housing, relegating them to overcrowded and under-resourced townships (Marais, 2013). The apartheid era policies of forced removals and spatial segregation gave rise to informal settlements and low-income townships that continue to suffer from insufficient infrastructure and public services (Seekings, 2011). This spatial segregation reinforced socio-economic disparities, resulting in generations of Black South Africans enduring inadequate living conditions with limited access to health-supporting infrastructure (Gbadegesin, 2020; Moyo et al., 2021; Marais et al., 2018; Stull, Bell and Ncwadi, 2016). These environments foster persistent poverty, unemployment, and poor health outcomes (Kahn et al., 2017). According to Kararachi (2024), the spatial outcomes of apartheid have produced a dual economy, wherein developed, affluent urban centers coexist with underdeveloped townships, informal settlements, and impoverished rural areas. This strong duality contributes to South Africa's status as one of the most unequal societies globally, with persistent disparities based on space, race, and gender demonstrating how inadequate housing engenders a vicious cycle of physical, mental, and social deprivation, particularly for already marginalized populations (Smith, 2023). Urbanization on the other hand, compounds these pressures, with 69% of the population now residing in rapidly expanding urban areas (Turok, Todes and Smit, 2022). Thus, the consequences of spatial inequality extend into health, with socio-economic status and living conditions serving as major determinants of health

outcomes that impact on the United Nations Sustainable Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 3, SDG 6, and SDG 11.

Data from the Centre for Affordable Housing Finance in Africa (CAHF, 2024) highlights that, as of the 2022 Census, South Africa's population of 62 million people live in 17.8 million households, with an average household size of 3.5 people. While the proportion of formal dwellings has increased from 65.1% in 1996 to 88.5% in 2022, nearly one-third of households still rely on government-subsidized housing, underscoring persistent housing shortages and quality challenges. Despite considerable improvements in service provision, such as piped water access increasing to 82.4%, flush toilets to 70.8%, and electricity access nearing 95% of households, many communities still face inadequate living conditions (CAHF, 2024). Historical legacies and structural inequality continue to produce uneven housing outcomes, with systemic issues such as unaffordability, poor quality, limited access to services, energy poverty and weak policy implementation further constraining the wellbeing of people (Smith, 2023; Stull, Bell and Newadi, 2016).

Housing quality is a critical determinant of public health, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, where poor housing exacerbates health inequalities and reinforces socio-economic exclusion (Masuku, 2024). The South African case strongly illustrates how historical injustices, and current inequalities intersect to produce profound disparities in housing and health exacerbating widespread housing inadequacy marked by overcrowding, substandard sanitation, and heightened exposure to environmental hazards (Katukiza et al., 2012). Extensive research confirms that housing conditions are a major determinant of health (Kawachi and Berkman, 2001). Substandard housing, characterized by overcrowding, dampness, and lack of ventilation, has been linked to respiratory illnesses, mental health issues, and increased risk of infectious diseases (Sharif et al., 2024; Evans et al., 2003). Conversely, well-designed and adequately serviced housing contributes positively to physical and mental health and overall well-being (Whitehead et al., 2019).

The relationship between housing and health is multifaceted. In South Africa, addressing housing inequality is vital to promoting health equity. Barriers to adequate housing remain significant for marginalized populations, who often dedicate a disproportionate share of their income to housing costs, at the expense of other essentials such as food and healthcare (Habib et al., 2025). These financial burdens are intensified by energy poverty, which forces households to use harmful energy sources, with further health implications (Culwick & Khanyile, 2023; Guerra, and Eboime, 2021; Musango, 2014). Housing inadequacy, especially in urban contexts, is a major driver of health disparities. Overcrowded, poorly ventilated, and structurally unsound housing can lead to a range of adverse health outcomes, including respiratory infections, communicable diseases, and mental health challenges (Connolly et al., 2004; World Health Organization, 2018). Housing conditions are a critical social determinant of health, particularly in low and middle-income contexts such as South Africa, where historical inequalities and rapid urbanization contribute to persistent disparities. This study addresses the problem that, despite evidence linking housing to health outcomes, there is limited integrated conceptualization of how physical, socio-economic, environmental, and policy factors interact to shape health inequities in low-income urban settlements. The study aims to develop a conceptual framework that explains the interconnections between housing quality, affordability, stability, and safety, and their influence on physical and mental health outcomes. The interconnections between housing and health in South Africa are complex and

multifaceted, involving various SDGs, particularly SDG 3, SDG 6, and SDG 11. The question that begs is how this complexity can be conceptualized with the aim of harmonizing the approaches that are crucial for sustainable development through a conceptual framework.

Theoretical review of literature

This section covers theoretical perspectives on housing inadequacy and health. This section concludes with a conceptual framework to explore the interconnections between housing and health for sustainable development, particularly the United Nations Sustainable Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 3, SDG 6, and SDG 11 in the context of South Africa. This study draws upon four main perspectives that include the Social Determinants of Health (SDH), the Environmental Health Model, Vulnerability Theory, and the Ecological Model.

Social Determinants of Health (SDH)

The Social Determinants of Health (SDH) framework posits that socio-economic conditions, including housing quality, are fundamental drivers of health outcomes (Kawachi & Berkman, 2001). Housing inadequacy is considered a proxy for broader social disadvantage, influencing physical and mental health through environmental exposures and psychosocial stressors (Swope, & Hernández, 2019; Marmot et al., 2010). Low-income households often reside in informal settlements where access to clean water, sanitation, and healthcare is limited, compounding their health vulnerabilities (Kann et al., 2024; Culwick & Khanyile, 2023). Empirical studies reinforce the SDH framework by linking substandard housing to high incidences of infectious diseases, such as cholera and tuberculosis, and respiratory illnesses such as asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (Holden et al., 2023).

Mental health issues, including stress, anxiety, and depression, are also prevalent among individuals living in unstable or overcrowded housing conditions (Sharif & Dey, 2024). These health disparities are intensified by economic hardship, which not only affects housing conditions but also limits access to necessary healthcare services (Culwick & Khanyile, 2023). SDG 3 emphasises good health and well-being indicating that health outcomes emanate from housing conditions. Poor housing is linked to adverse health effects, including mental health issues and general well-being (Shortt and Hammett, 2013; Chatindiara et al., 2022; Ntema et al., 2021).

Environmental Health Model

The environmental health model emphasizes the direct physiological impacts of substandard housing conditions, such as inadequate ventilation, use of hazardous materials such as asbestos, dampness, and overcrowding (Kua & Lee, 2021). These structural deficiencies are closely associated with increased rates of respiratory infections, especially among children who are more susceptible to indoor pollutants. In the South African context, the use of solid fuels for cooking and heating in inadequately ventilated homes exacerbates indoor air pollution, contributing to chronic respiratory illnesses, affecting respiration in children (Liu et al., 2024). Poor sanitation and insufficient solid waste management further facilitate the spread of communicable diseases, such as cholera and diarrhoea infections (Narayan et al., 2021). Overcrowding and poor insulation in informal settlements lead to cold, damp environments where mould thrives, conditions strongly linked to asthma and other respiratory issues (Wimalasena et al., 2021). The environmental health burdens of inadequate housing are

compounded by noise pollution and neighbourhood disorder, which further aggravate mental health conditions (Masuku & Nzewi, 2021; Haselbach et al., 2009).

Vulnerability Theory

Vulnerability theory underscores how socio-politically marginalised populations are disproportionately exposed to housing inadequacy and its associated health risks (Masuku, 2024). In the South African post-apartheid context, historical patterns of segregation and economic exclusion have rendered informal settlement dwellers especially vulnerable. This framework highlights systemic inequities in access to adequate housing, clean energy, and essential services. This is because adequate housing must include access to clean water and sanitation (SDG 6). The lack of these services in informal settlements exacerbates health vulnerability (Ntema et al., 2021; Buthelezi et al., 2024; Tusting, et al., 2019). Improved housing with better sanitation facilities can significantly enhance health and well-being (Ntema et al., 2021).

Despite policy interventions such as the Integrated National Electrification Programme (INEP), energy poverty persists, reducing the ability of households to access clean energy for cooking and heating, thereby worsening health outcomes (Samarakoon, 2019; Broto, 2028; Ismail & Khembo, 2015). Globally, similar patterns are evident. For instance, in Canada, First Nations communities experiencing damp, mould-infested housing report higher respiratory illness prevalence than the general population (Waddell et al., 2024). These disparities reaffirm the core tenet of vulnerability theory, that housing inadequacy both reflects and reinforces broader social inequities.

Ecological Model

The ecological model adds a layered understanding by emphasizing how health is influenced by the interaction of individual, community, and environmental factors (Balashova et al., 2025; Bronfenbrenner, 1979). Inadequate housing impacts not only physical health through exposure to environmental hazards but also mental and social wellbeing by introducing stress, instability, and reduced social cohesion. This model is particularly valuable in highlighting the cumulative and interactive nature of housing-related health risks. For example, the stress of living in unstable housing situations can exacerbate anxiety and depression (Sharif & Dey, 2024), while also weakening immune responses, making individuals more susceptible to infections. In the South African context, these frameworks converge to portray a grim reality where structural deficits, poverty, and systemic inequities band together to exacerbate public health problems and violating SDG 11. Poorly located housing developments can limit economic opportunities and perpetuate inequality (Culwick & Patel, 2020). Studies show that overcrowding and unsanitary living conditions in informal settlements contribute to the transmission of communicable diseases such as tuberculosis and diarrhoea (Penrose et al., 2010; Moffa et al., 2019). The COVID-19 pandemic further exposed how housing inadequacy, particularly overcrowding and lack of isolation spaces do facilitate disease transmission, especially in high-density urban areas (Corburn et al., 2020; Nyashanu et al., 2020). The compounded effects of energy poverty, environmental exposures, and socio-economic stressors remain underexplored, suggesting a crucial area for future research to aid policy intervention.

Empirical literature review

Inadequate housing conditions have consistently been linked to a broad spectrum of diseases and health complications. This arises from multiple dimensions of housing inadequacy, that include overcrowding, poor sanitation, environmental hazards, structural instability, and insufficient access to clean water and safe materials. The World Health Organization (2018) emphasizes that in low and middle-income countries, where substandard housing is prevalent, the resultant health risks are particularly severe. Poor housing not only compromises physical health but also negatively affects mental and social well-being, underscoring its role as a critical determinant of public health outcomes (Usha & Nithiya, 2024). Access to health services is crucial. Improved integration of health services (SDG 3, 6 and 11) in housing policies can lead to better health outcomes (Ntema et al., 2021).

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 3, 6 & 9), housing & health

Good health and well-being (SDG 3) focusses on health outcomes indicating housing conditions significantly impact health outcomes. Poor housing, especially in informal settlements, is linked to adverse health effects, including mental health issues and general well-being (Shortt and Hammett, 2013; Chatindiara et al., 2022; Ntema et al., 2021). Upgrading housing can improve mental health and community satisfaction (Shortt & Hammett, 2013). Access to health services is crucial. Improved integration of health services in housing policies can lead to better health outcomes (Ntema et al., 2021).

Clean water and sanitation (SDG 6) focusses on sanitation and water access, indicating that adequate housing must include access to clean water and sanitation. The lack of these services in informal settlements exacerbates health issues (Buthelezi et al., 2024; Tusting, et al., 2019). Improved housing with better sanitation facilities can significantly enhance health and well-being (Tusting et al., 2019).

Sustainable cities and communities (SDG 11) focus on inclusive and safe housing indicating that creating inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable human settlements is a core objective of this goal. This includes providing adequate housing and basic services (Leboto-Khetsi et al., 2024). The transformation of housing in urban and rural areas has shown improvements, but many still live in inadequate conditions in South Africa (Tusting et al., 2019). Thus, sustainable urban development involves addressing housing quality, access to services, and environmental sustainability (Leboto-Khetsi et al., 2024). Poorly located housing developments can limit economic opportunities and perpetuate inequality (Culwick & Patel, 2020). This paper identifies eight categories of diseases linked to housing conditions covered below.

(i) Respiratory Diseases

A significant body of evidence links poor housing conditions with the onset and exacerbation of respiratory diseases, that include asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and acute respiratory infections (ARIs) (Azanaw et al., 2024). Poor indoor air quality, driven by dampness, mould, tobacco smoke, and inadequate ventilation has been widely recognized as a major risk factor (Aftab et al., 2022). Mold and dust mites, common in poorly ventilated and damp environments, trigger allergic responses and are linked to asthma development. Children are particularly vulnerable, with studies showing increased ARI symptoms among those living in homes with natural material floors or exposed to wood and coal heating, especially in countries like Pakistan and Ethiopia (Andualem et al., 2020).

Overcrowding exacerbates these risks by promoting the spread of airborne pathogens (Rennie and Lawson 2011). In settings such as disaster shelters and military barracks, insufficient ventilation and unhygienic living conditions have been directly associated with respiratory infections like tuberculosis (Shahzad, 2025; Adam et al., 2010). After the Türkiye and Syria earthquake, temporary shelters lacking clean water and sanitation facilities saw spikes in respiratory and gastrointestinal infections, underscoring how emergency housing conditions can intensify disease transmission (Smith, 2023; Yasui & Numada, 2021). Poor environmental health conditions in shelters include unhygienic bedding and lack of infrastructure also facilitate the spread of respiratory illnesses (Kishore et al., 2023). Such exposures are not only physical health risks but also have implications for mental health, as environmental stressors like pollution have been associated with elevated rates of depression (Parikh et al., 2022). Children living in inadequate housing often face dual risks of respiratory illness and psychological distress. Indoor exposures to tobacco smoke, mould, and other pollutants are especially harmful for children, who may develop chronic respiratory conditions and psychological distress because of prolonged exposure (Wu et al., 2024).

(ii) Infectious Diseases

Infectious diseases thrive in overcrowded and unsanitary living environments. Overcrowding increases interpersonal contact, which accelerates the spread of diseases such as tuberculosis, cholera, and gastroenteritis (Herath et al., 2024; Sharif, and Kanti, 2024). Poor sanitation and contaminated water sources further compound these risks, particularly in informal settlements and shelters that lack proper sewage systems (Echazú et al., 2015). The COVID-19 pandemic sharply revealed how overcrowded housing facilitates disease transmission. In urban settings like southwestern Sydney, households experiencing high levels of overcrowding exhibited elevated COVID-19 infection rates (Herath et al., 2024; Nyashanu et al., 2020). Health inequities persist in impoverished communities where poor housing is often accompanied by limited access to water and healthcare. Abrams et al., (2021) and Sharma et al., (2013) assert that such inequities not only elevate infection risks but also intensify mental health issues. Beyond respiratory and gastrointestinal infections, inadequate housing has been linked to viral diseases such as lassa fever, which is transmitted by rodents in structurally unsound homes (Kelly et al., 2013). There are also COVID-19 and influenza outbreaks in overcrowded shelters (Gazin and Brouqui, 2004). Bacterial infections also flourish in substandard housing. Pathogens such as staphylococcus aureus spread rapidly due to poor hygiene and close contact among residents, especially in shelters lacking adequate sanitation infrastructure (Shukla et al., 2020). Tuberculosis transmission is heightened in densely populated and poorly ventilated shelters.

(iii) Vector-Borne Diseases

Housing conditions that lack adequate drainage, clean water access, and sealed construction invite vectors such as mosquitoes, significantly increasing the risk of diseases such as malaria and dengue fever (Narayan et al., 2021). These diseases are particularly severe in urban informal settlements, where standing water and open waste attract disease vectors. Vector-borne diseases such as bartonellosis, chagas disease, and leishmaniasis are closely tied to unsanitary and overcrowded housing environments. These diseases are especially prevalent among homeless and displaced populations, who are more frequently exposed to insects and rodents due to lack of protective barriers and proper housing structures (Ralli et al., 2021; Karb et al., 2020).

(iv) Mental Health Problems

The psychosocial stressors inherent in poor housing such as insecurity, overcrowding, and environmental degradation significantly contribute to mental health disorders including anxiety, depression, and stress-related illnesses (Leta, 2021). Exposure to mould, dampness, and pollutants does not only cause physical illness but also elevates psychological distress (Parikh et al., 2022). Children living in these environments are doubly affected, with increased susceptibility to mental health disorders due to the compounding stressors of illness and environment. Living in insecure or inadequate housing also disrupts family functioning, reduces educational performance among children, and increases exposure to violence, all of which contribute to poor mental health outcomes.

(v) Chronic Diseases

Liu et al., (2024) finds long-term exposure to environmental stressors such as mould, chemical pollutants, and poor air quality in inadequate housing environments can lead to chronic conditions that include cardiovascular diseases, hypertension, and metabolic disorders. These chronic illnesses are often compounded by limited access to healthcare and a lack of resources for disease management, especially in low-income populations. Furthermore, poor housing design that promotes sedentary lifestyles, such as lack of recreational spaces and safe walking paths also contributes to chronic health conditions. The cumulative stress from poor housing conditions serves as a risk factor for cardiovascular disease by disrupting sleep, increasing anxiety, and fostering unhealthy behaviors.

(vi) Injuries and Accidents

Substandard housing poses numerous physical safety hazards that increase the risk of injuries and accidents. These include structural instability, unsafe staircases, poorly installed electrical wiring, and lack of smoke detectors. Falls, burns, and electrocutions are more prevalent in inadequately maintained housing, especially informal settlements (Nuwagaba, 2018). Children and the elderly are especially at risk due to mobility limitations and lack of proper safety features in their homes. Poor lighting, uneven flooring, and obstructed pathways further contribute to home-related injuries. In regions prone to natural disasters, poorly constructed housing is also more susceptible to collapse, placing residents at higher risk of injury or death during earthquakes or floods (Ergönül et al., 2021).

(vii) Lead Poisoning and Waterborne Diseases

Inadequate housing often contains outdated infrastructure, including lead-based paint and plumbing, which can result in lead poisoning, particularly in children. Exposure to lead has been linked to cognitive impairment, developmental delays, and behavioral problems (Guerra, and Eboreime, 2021). Ortega, (2021) finds a decreased brain volume in adults with childhood lead exposure. Contaminated water systems, often found in informal settlements, are another critical risk factor, leading to waterborne diseases such as typhoid, cholera, and dysentery (Ali, Foster and Hall, 2018). These diseases flourish in environments, where housing lacks reliable water supply and sanitation.

(viii) Cancer and Skin Conditions

The use of hazardous building materials, especially asbestos, in roofing and insulation is strongly associated with various forms of cancer. Asbestos exposure can lead to asbestosis, a

chronic respiratory condition and is a major risk factor for lung cancer and mesothelioma, a rare cancer affecting the lungs and abdominal lining (Reid et al., 2021; Carbone et al., 2022). Additional cancers linked to asbestos exposure include cancers of the larynx and ovary (Hodgson, 2020; van Mark, 2007; Cohen et al., 2023). In response to these well-documented health risks, the World Health Organization (2022) supports bans or restrictions on the use of asbestos in construction. Skin conditions are another overlooked consequence of inadequate housing. Poor sanitation and water access contribute to dermatological issues such as scabies, fungal infections, and dermatitis, especially in crowded and humid living environments (Chastonay & Chastonay, 2022). These conditions often go untreated in underserved populations, exacerbating discomfort and facilitating secondary infections.

Methodology

A desk-based rapid literature review was conducted using SCOPUS and EBSCO HOST databases, focusing on global frameworks from the WHO and UN-Habitat, African-specific scholarship, and empirical studies on housing and health. A rapid literature survey was conducted via SCOPUS and EBSCO HOST databases. These two databases were chosen because they are the largest abstract and citation sources of peer-reviewed literature. Using the topic called “housing conditions and health outcomes” and five key words (housing and human rights, socio-economic factors and health, environment and health, the categories of housing associated with housing inadequacy) as string of words, the search yielded 250 sources consisting of journals, books, and conference proceedings that gave relevant information on the study. 97 sources were found to be relevant in conceptualizing housing conditions and health outcomes as an output of this study, specified in figure 1.

Theoretical underpinnings

Theoretical and empirical evidence converge to demonstrate that housing inadequacy is not merely a shelter issue, but a multidimensional determinant of health shown in figure 1. As emphasized by Marmot et al., (2010), research necessitates a cross-sectoral approach that embeds health considerations within housing policy, ensuring adequate infrastructure, sanitation, ventilation, and energy access to promote holistic well-being (Smith, 2023). As emphasized by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2018), inadequate housing is closely linked to a broad spectrum of health issues that include respiratory illnesses, mental health disorders, and infectious diseases.

Findings: The conceptual framework

The resulting framework integrates physical, environmental, socio-economic, and policy dimensions, highlighting how structural deficiencies such as overcrowding, poor ventilation, inadequate sanitation, and insecure tenure do amplify vulnerability to communicable and non-communicable diseases. At the core of the framework lies the interconnection between key housing dimensions, quality, affordability, stability, and safety and their cumulative impact on health. Housing quality refers to the structural integrity and functionality of a dwelling, including aspects such as ventilation, presence of mould or pests, heating, and sanitation. The physical structure of housing and the surrounding environment play a critical role in residents' health. Poor housing conditions can lead to both physical and mental health issues (Shortt & Hammett, 2013; Chatindiara et al., 2022). Deteriorating conditions in these domains are strongly associated with adverse physical health outcomes, particularly respiratory ailments such as asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (Holden et al., 2023; Wu et al.,

2024). Affordability, defined as the cost of housing relative to household income, determines the extent to which households can allocate resources to other health, promoting essentials like nutrition, healthcare, and education. Excessive housing costs may force trade-offs that compromise overall well-being (Avčín et al., 2011). Jabali et al., 2025 found smaller households, with higher family incomes, and in private homes report better health.

Stability, another critical dimension, reflects the frequency and predictability of residential arrangements. Housing improvements can foster a sense of belonging and community cohesion, which are important for mental health and overall well-being (Shortt & Hammett, 2013). High levels of housing instability, including frequent relocations and homelessness, can disrupt daily routines and social networks, contributing to heightened levels of stress, anxiety, and depression (Sharif & Dey, 2024; Rogers et al., 2023; Kua & Lee, 2021; Ghinai et al., 2020). Furthermore, safety encompasses both the physical security of the built environment and the broader neighborhood context, including exposure to crime, environmental hazards, and accidents. Insecure and hazardous settings perpetuate chronic stress and increase vulnerability to both physical injuries and long-term psychological distress.

Socioeconomic status (SES) intersects with housing conditions, serving as a crucial social determinant of health. Lower SES, marked by constrained income, limited education, and unstable employment, often correlates with substandard housing and increased health risks (Anwar et al., 2021). Residents of informal settlements and overcrowded dwellings face a heightened likelihood of exposure to environmental health threats, including infectious disease transmission and insufficient access to healthcare services (Masuku, 2024). In this context, economic stressors such as unemployment and financial crises have been shown to exacerbate psychiatric morbidity (Nvo-Fernandez et al., 2025). For instance, the Greek financial crisis led to a noticeable rise in major depression rates, underscoring the influence of broader economic dynamics on mental health (Economou et al., 2018).

Environmental factors further compound the effects of housing inadequacy. These include neighborhood characteristics such as pollution levels, access to green spaces, and proximity to community resources (Kyne, 2023). Environmental degradation and poor air quality are particularly detrimental, serving as catalysts for respiratory illnesses and mental health conditions (Haselbach et al., 2009). Informal settlements, where poverty and overcrowding prevail, face unique challenges in implementing disease prevention and control measures, leading to elevated rates of infectious disease and compounding physical and mental health challenges. Sustainable housing must consider environmental impacts, such as resource consumption and carbon emissions. Adaptive reuse of buildings is one strategy to mitigate these impacts while addressing housing needs (Owojori et al., 2024). The cyclical and bidirectional nature of the relationship between housing and health is also evident. Poor health can undermine a household's ability to secure and maintain adequate housing, while housing inadequacy exacerbates health vulnerabilities (Marmot et al., 2010). This interdependence illustrates the self-reinforcing cycle of housing-related health inequities. Mental health, while traditionally overlooked in housing literature, warrants particular attention in marginalized populations. The mental health consequences of unstable, unsafe, and inadequate housing include heightened stress, depression, anxiety, and a diminished sense of agency or belonging (Sharif & Dey, 2024; Masuku & Nzewi, 2021). Environmental stressors such as noise, overcrowding, and social isolation contribute further to psychological strain, particularly in dense urban environments and informal settlements.

Figure 1: The interconnection between housing conditions, health outcomes & SDG 3, 6 & 9 conceptual framework

Source: authors

Discussion

There is a need for better integration of health considerations into housing policies. Current policies often overlook the health outcomes of housing interventions required to improve people’s wellbeing (Ntema et al., 2021). Efforts must be directed towards marginalized communities to ensure they benefit from sustainable development initiatives. This includes improving access to health services, sanitation, and adequate housing (Ntema et al., 2021; Buthelezi et al., 2024). By and large, achieving sustainable development goals requires collaboration between the state, community, private sector, and other stakeholders (Leboto-Khetsi et al., 2024). The framework shows that multicomponent and cross-sectoral interventions are essential to effectively address the complex interplay of housing and health in ways that fulfil SDGs 3, 6 and 11 (Leboto-Khetsi et al., 2024; Narayan et al., 2021).

Conclusion

The findings provide a holistic lens for interdisciplinary research, guide empirical analysis, and inform policy integration between the housing and health sectors. This conceptual framework underscores that housing is not merely a place of shelter but a critical site of health production if built with health outcomes in mind (Turley et al., 2013). It emphasizes that physical and mental health outcomes are not only determined by the built environment but are deeply embedded in social and environmental contexts shaped by economic hardship, policy choices, and historical inequities. Comprehensive strategies that integrate housing improvements with social support systems and equitable policy reforms are vital for promoting health equity and breaking the vicious cycle of poor housing and ill health. Overall, the study recommends

improving housing systems as it is pivotal for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 3, 6, and 11, and for promoting equitable health outcomes in South Africa and the Global South.

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**Peer Reviewed (delete what does not apply)*

Sustainable Solutions to Land Scarcity for Social Housing in South African Cities *Faranani Gethe*¹; *Prisca Simbanegavi*¹; *Pride Ndlovu*¹ and *Malcolm Roy Weaich*¹

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Abstract

Land scarcity near economic hubs in South Africa poses significant challenges to developing inclusive and sustainable cities, particularly for social housing. The purpose of this research is to explore practical strategies to address land shortages and high costs while promoting social housing within proximity to urban centres. A qualitative research design was employed, involving semi-structured interviews with housing development experts from Johannesburg, Cape Town, and Tshwane. The study used thematic analysis to identify recurring themes from expert perspectives. The key findings reveal five actionable strategies: (i) public-private partnerships (PPPs) for land acquisition, (ii) long-term municipal land leases, (iii) repurposing decayed buildings into low-income housing, (iv) integrating social housing into mixed-use developments, and (v) implementing government tax incentives for social housing in greenfield projects. These strategies emphasize leveraging existing urban spaces, innovative financing, and policy interventions to reduce development costs and foster inclusivity. The study concludes that overcoming land scarcity for social housing requires a multi-stakeholder approach integrating urban planning, innovative financial models, and regulatory support. By adopting these strategies, municipalities can mitigate spatial inequality, reduce commuting distances, and enhance the quality of life for low-income residents. Future research should focus on assessing the long-term viability and scalability of these interventions.

Key words: Land Scarcity; Social Housing; Sustainable Cities; Economic Hubs; South Africa.

Introduction

Housing inadequacy can be traced back to apartheid that caused spatial inequality in South Africa (Shahaboonin et al. 2023). During apartheid, segregation policies created townships where 43% of nearly sixty million people live on major city outskirts (Todes and Turok, 2017; Ogra & Onatu, 2013). This outskirts location is a key contributor to high poverty level (Turok, 2018). Literature shows that 52% of jobs are found in urban areas which only houses 34% of the workforce, an undeniable housing poverty that stimulates informal settlements closer to economic hubs (Turok and Borel-Saladin (2013). Staying on the outskirts of cities has great disadvantages. Popoola, Magidimisha-Chipungu & Chipungu (2022) find distance was a predictor of credit access among rural households in peri-urban villages and rural communities in the Southwestern region of Nigeria. This highlights the need for social housing, which is different from subsidised housing in the outskirts of metropolitan areas (Olanrewaju, Anavhe, & Hai1, 2016).

Government in Hong Kong, targets increasing housing supply via increasing supply of land closer to urban centres (Huang, Shen & Zheng, 2015). Government over the last decade has been making means of providing basic housing and land to millions of South Africans in need of shelter. These efforts, however, come short of eliminating the issue of unavailable social housing calling for a greater intervention to facilitate developing housing for the poor (Turok, Scheba, & Visagie, 2022). In South Africa, the closer land is to highways and economic hubs, the higher the bid rent is. This makes land closer to economic hubs more expensive given that land price is a residual value, taking its price from more profitable developments (Massyn et al. 2015). Given these costs associated with acquiring land, developers use 'highest and best use'

criteria to develop real estate which often crowd out social housing. This is because development focuses on buildings that bring better returns to cover the cost of land. This stimulates vertical development. This urban economics concept has dictated the outskirts location of RDP housing in the outskirts of most cities in South Africa. This has also resulted in insufficient development of social housing within the economic hubs leading to illegal occupation of abandoned residential buildings in the cities and rapid informal settlement erected on privately owned land. Little is known about how to circumvent the high cost of land within the economic hubs to expedite the development of social housing. In South Africa, there is need for the department of Human Settlement to find better interventions to achieve the goal of inclusive cities for social housing which is derailed by the cost of land closer to economic hubs. Surprisingly, Othman & Mia (2008) found an unwillingness by government to release sufficient suitable land for housing developments.

The aim of this study is to explore sustainable solutions to land scarcity for social housing in South African cities. Specifically, it seeks to (i) identify the key challenges that hinder the development of social housing in well-located areas, (ii) examine expert perspectives on feasible interventions, and (iii) recommend strategies that municipalities and developers can adopt to promote inclusive housing near economic hubs. Accordingly, the study is guided by the following research questions: *What are the main challenges of providing social housing in well-located urban areas? How do housing experts perceive potential solutions? What strategies can enhance the integration of social housing into economic hubs?.*

Literature Review

This literature review explores the topic on Social Housing (SH) and Economic Hubs (EHs), focusing on the opportunities and challenges associated with its developments. In a less inclusive ways, SH has been developed in the outskirts of cities. These developments are fragmented and do not promote integration and transformation (Onatu, 2012). Part of the problem is that the land closer to economic hubs is significantly more expensive than land on the outskirts where housing developers opt to develop there for the pursuit of profits. This is because land price is a residual value which is higher when a development is more profitable. Government has a role to play in redistributing land through its policies and intervention (Musakwa, Tshesane, & Kangethe, 2017; Makinde, 2014).

There is growing recognition of the potential benefits of developing SH in proximity to economic hubs as high-density rental housing (Massyn et al. 2015; Gunter, 2013). To promote development within economic hubs, municipalities should permit flexible building densities to maximize on shortage of land (Yan, Ge, & Wu, 2014). The benefits include improved access to employment opportunities, enhanced access to services and amenities, reduced transportation costs and commuting time and inclusivity that comes from possible social integration and reduced stigmatization (Simbanegavi, 2019). Thus, SH built closer to EHs avoids the negatives associated with informal settlements such as negative impacts on health (Nyashanu et al. 2020). Wider benefits of housing closer to economic hubs include access to employment, education, healthcare, and cultural amenities, positively impacting on residents' quality of life and social mobility.

A good example of a successful example of an SH development near EHs is the Marabastad Townlands SH in Tshwane. The multimillion-rand social housing project consists of 1 200 mixed units and covers residents of Tshwane who do not qualify for government subsidy houses

nor earn enough to qualify for a home loan. Beneficiaries of this SH development earn between R1 500 and R15 000 per month.

Figure 1: Social Housing in Tshwane

Source: Mathonsi Thobile, African News Agency (ANA)

Such examples have been achieved through innovative financing models and partnerships. Innovative financing models such as Land Value Capture (LVC) can be used to circumvent the budget constraints that exist in government (Gethe et al. 2023). Urban planning and policy are moving towards incorporating SH in urban regeneration plans, zoning and land use policies to facilitate social housing in central areas. There is also an angle on sustainability and environmental considerations where reduced carbon footprint and transportation emissions, sustainable building design and energy efficiency and urban greening and access to open spaces (Gethe & Simbanegavi, 2024; Liao, Ren, & Li, 2023).

There exist challenges of locating SH closer to ESHs. These include land availability and high cost, gentrification and displacement risks, NIMBYism (Not in My Backyard) and infrastructure and services provision. This is the reason sometimes Greenfields become default locations for SH. Mixed Use (MUDs) in greenfield can counter these challenges whereby a thriving ecosystem which contains the SH, public transportation and infrastructure can be a solution to housing the poor such as Cosmo City (Simbanegavi & Ijasa, 2022; Onatu, 2012). Such developments proved to save on costs of development in terms of bulk infrastructure that is already in place. This review of literature shows a knowledge gap in developers' perspectives and experiences on how to promote the development of SH closer to ESHs.

Methodology

Guidelines from Saunders et al. (2016), informed the study to use qualitative research design to investigate ways to deal with shortage of land for social housing given that such land is crowded out by the theory of highest and best use in most cities. Following approval of the research proposal by the Witwatersrand University Ethics Committee, four housing development experts were interviewed as a pilot study to test the research guideline (Majid et al. 2017). The interview guide was informed by the literature on previous studies on housing development (Sathvik, Krishnaraj, & Awuzie, 2023). Information from the pilot study helped to improve the questions specified in the research guideline that was extended to purposively selected experts in housing development, recruited through direct contacts from Johannesburg, Cape Town, and Tswane Metros (about 12 participants were interviewed). These participants had experience in sourcing land for housing development. Through the interview guideline, semi-structured questions were formulated and used to prompt viewpoints about land for social housing. Interviews were conducted as a flexible instrument to interact with expert stakeholders who are involved in developing low-cost housing in South Africa.

Data collection

Researchers sent letters and information sheets to the organisations inviting housing developers to take part in the research study. Only those who had agreed to take part in the research study had their names and telephone contacts forwarded to the researchers to organise interview dates and times where they would sign a consent form prior to taking part in the interview. The participants had an opportunity to read the information sheet and ask questions to get more clarity on this research where they had an option to withdraw from the study at any time without giving reasons. The interviews lasted for one hour and were conducted in English.

Data analysis

The tape-recorded interviews were transcribed verbatim, and all transcriptions were read back to the participants to verify the accuracy of the main points through Microsoft teams. All confirmed data was recorded into NVivo, a software that helps organise data for a robust thematic analysis. Repeatedly reading transcriptions made it possible to identify concerns about participants experiences that were important to the participant regarding land for housing. This made it possible to hear and understand the participant's views in their own words and keep their experience at the centre of the study. Relevant parts were summarised and assigned codes representing the researcher's interpretation of participants' viewpoints. Through cluster analysis, the identified codes were seen to cluster collectively into themes. A summary of these five themes constituted the final output of this research study and are presented in the section that follows.

Findings and Discussion

The paper finds five research themes on how to deal with land scarcity for social housing in metros listed below.

- i. Release of land for social housing through PPPs
- ii. Use of long term land leases by municipalities
- iii. Conversion of decayed buildings into low income housing for rent.
- iv. Design Mixed Use Developments (MUDs)

- v. Use of government tax incentives social housing in Greenfields.

Release of land for social housing through PPPs

There is extra pressure on the cost of land closer to economic hubs which makes it more expensive. This has led to most housing developers opting to buy cheaper land in the outskirts and developing it for social housing in partnerships with municipalities. This has resulted in disgruntled citizens who view this as failure to build inclusive cities. The advice mainly given is that through Public Private Partnership more houses can be rolled out. Housing developers are of the viewpoint that supply of land closer to economic hubs for social housing through PPPs. The bond between public and private investment must be stronger where both parties contribute to housing development that will sustain in the future where both parties can take advantage of the provision of social housing. Land is too expensive in the inner cities however municipalities can create a policy that makes municipalities give/donate land in inner cities for social housing through 20-30 year-long leases after which social housing is taken over by municipalities as an asset. This will stimulate construction of social housing closer to economic hubs by private developers bringing in the much needed supply that is need.

Use of long-term land leases by municipalities

Data suggested that the government and municipalities must make land available for social low-cost housing, and for the land that belongs to the municipality like those that are under construction near Marabastad in the City of Tshwane. This concurs with Molefe & Nkhahle (2019) who suggested that 'municipalities should have the right of first refusal to acquire state-owned land and land owned by State-Owned Entities (SOEs) when the State and SOEs intend to dispose of their land'. Based on the respondents regarding the cost of land near the economic hubs the Metropolitan Municipalities must work together with HDA to identify land that belongs to the city and give it to social housing agents for the development of social houses. Social housing is to ensure social and decent housing and to be part of urban regeneration. If government provides land within or closer to the economic hubs at a lesser value to social housing developers for the construction of social housing will better the revenue of the developers. Though this might be a solution in theory it is not practical because of the economic unfeasibility it poses. An alternative would be the government allocating specific plots of available land they own for the development of low-cost housing. This is called the eminent domain, and it is for the benefit of the public. The government needs to come up with laws and policies that will make land social for houses. All other metropolitan municipalities must just emulate what is done by the city of Cape Town and make land available for social housing and subsidised low-cost housing. For lower commuting costs it is highly recommended that the development of such housing be increased in centralized economic areas. There is land that belongs to the municipalities in the inner cities that is lying idle. Government must give this land to SHIs so that it can be developed into social housing near economic hubs.

Conversion of decayed buildings into low-income housing for rent.

Urban renewal can be a solution to lack of social housing in inner cities where existing dilapidated buildings can be regenerated into rental housing by the urban poor (Gethe & Simbanegavi, 2024) These options include converting abandoned buildings into decent living spaces, seems to be more feasible. This is a good opportunity as most owners of these buildings, in most cases, do not have funds to renovate these buildings. Thus, government can partly fund renovations of these buildings and have them converted into social rental units with private-

sector management. The Maboneng Precinct in Johannesburg inner city is an example of successful development that shows how the cost of land need not be a limiting factor in curbing the insufficient supply of decent housing close to the inner cities of Gauteng. Other metropolitan municipalities need to adopt the strategies that are used by the City of Tshwane and the City of Cape Town where some of the buildings that belong to the municipality are being converted to social housing institutions. Social housing can also be part of solving the problem as it is done in the City of Tshwane where the city gives a 20-year lease to the social housing developers like Yeast City Housing and in the City of Cape Town. Social housing is to ensure social and decent housing and to be part of urban regeneration. Most respondents agreed that people won't take a long trip to places of work, shopping centres, and government facilities if they are closer to the economic hubs. This study indicates that there is a high land cost near the economy, especially around Gauteng Metropolitan Municipalities. The city of Tshwane is giving some of the building that belongs to the municipality to the social housing developers on a 20-year lease agreement. The land is privately owned by individuals who don't want to give it to the subsidized low-cost housing for development they are selling it in small portions at a higher price.

Mixed Use Developments (MUDs)

While developers see the need for developing social housing closer to economic hubs, they shy away because the rate of return on their investment would prove to be very low. Most respondents agreed that people will not take long trips to places of work, shopping centres and government facilities if they are closer to the economic hubs. Participants view Mixed-Use Developments (MUDs) as a solution to promoting housing closer to economic hubs on the condition that incentives attached to MUDs will unlock cross-subsidization possibilities of some real estate asset classes such as retail, office space to the social housing asset. Redefining economic hubs may also be that the same infrastructure that is found in the inner city may be brought closer to the people on the outskirts, thus promoting more job opportunities and an effective transport system to allow people to commute from their homes to their places of work with ease.

Use of government tax incentives social housing in Greenfields.

Government should assist private developers developing on private land with tax rebates to bring the associated cost of acquiring land for social housing down. This can be in any form ranging from reduced bulk contributions, rates and taxes, tax rebates. Discussions elaborated that indeed land cost is the challenge when it comes to developing subsidised houses near or within the economic hubs. Other strategies have been applied as a plan of providing subsidised houses near or within the economic hubs while the cost of land is high. The challenges of developing subsidised houses near or within economic hubs are more or land related. This means that; the land is highly protected, and the owners of the land are not always willing to give away land without selling it. Therefore, the land policy focuses more on the protection of the owner without considering the public.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Land cost is still the major problem in the development of subsidised low-cost housing near the economic hubs of most metros in South Africa. The Gauteng Metropolitan Municipalities together with housing departments and government entities who are involved in the

subsidised low-cost housing and land for human settlement such as Housing Development Agency must come up with a plan that will involve the participation of private landowners and NGOs that are involved in the future of subsidised low-cost housing development in Gauteng Metropolitans.

The paper recommends that municipalities should give 20-year leases to social housing institutions that can develop low-income housing for rent (social housing) in South Africa. The state may need to investigate adopting methods used in other countries for long-term leasing of the land for housing development purposes. The lease-term turns out to be cheaper for the developers to acquire hectares of land as opposed to buying them at a high cost from the state or open market. With these houses, most people will not take long trips to places of work, shopping centres, and government facilities within the cities. Finding solutions to inclusive housing through land discourse is the main contribution and novelty of this research.

While the study provides valuable insights into strategies for addressing land scarcity for social housing, several limitations must be acknowledged. First, the research adopted a qualitative approach with a relatively small sample size of experts from three metropolitan municipalities. As such, the findings may not capture the full diversity of perspectives across all South African cities or reflect broader national dynamics. Second, the study relied on self-reported experiences and perceptions of housing experts, which may carry subjective biases. Third, the focus was primarily on metropolitan areas, potentially overlooking unique challenges and opportunities in secondary cities or rural contexts. Lastly, the study did not undertake a quantitative assessment of the financial or policy feasibility of the proposed interventions, which limits the ability to generalise their scalability and long-term impact.

Future studies could expand on these findings by incorporating larger samples, mixed-method approaches, and comparative analyses across different regions. Quantitative modelling of costs, benefits, and long-term outcomes of proposed strategies would also strengthen the evidence base for policy and practice.

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Disclosure Statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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**Peer Reviewed*

SHIELD OR MIRAGE? THE RESPONSE OF AFRICAN REIT CAPITAL RETURNS TO INFLATIONARY PRESSURES ¹*Ibrahim Dabara Daniel*, ²*Tosin Babatola Fateye*, ³*Emmanuel Itodo Daniel* and ⁴*Richmond Ehwi*

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Abstract

This study investigates the inflation-hedging effectiveness of Real Estate Investment Trusts (REITs) across mature markets (United States and United Kingdom) and emerging African markets (South Africa and Nigeria) over the period 2013–2024. Grounded in the Fisher hypothesis and its Fama-Schwert extension, the study decomposes inflation into actual, expected, and unexpected components, and analyses their relationships with REIT capital returns. Using monthly data and a suite of econometric models including Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) for the main analysis, and with Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS), Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares (DOLS), and Canonical Cointegrating Regression (CCR) as robustness checks. Results indicate mixed and often adverse inflation responsiveness across the sample. Notably, REITs in Nigeria exhibit strong hedging against unexpected inflation despite institutional fragility, while South African REITs demonstrate weak or negative inflation responsiveness. Conversely, REITs in the US and UK offer partial or limited protection, particularly in short-run scenarios. The findings challenge the notion that REITs offer uniform inflation hedging across global markets and highlight the importance of institutional structure, inflation volatility, and asset composition. The study underscores the need for investors and policymakers to contextualise REIT performance within both macroeconomic environments and market-specific frameworks.

Keywords: Real Estate Investment Trusts (REITs); Inflation Hedging; Emerging Markets; Capital Return Volatility; ARDL Modelling

1. Introduction

Inflation remains a critical macroeconomic indicator significantly influencing asset returns globally, with pronounced implications for real estate markets. Recent economic environments characterized by volatile inflationary pressures, shifting interest rates, and elevated market uncertainty have intensified scholarly and investor interest in evaluating how Real Estate Investment Trusts (REITs) respond to inflation scenarios (Hoesli et al., 2008; Connolly et al., 2024). Such interest is particularly urgent within emerging economies, notably in Africa, where empirical investigations into REITs' inflation-hedging capacities are markedly scarce.

Since their inception in the United States in 1960, REITs have expanded into established global investment vehicles, now adopted in over 40 countries with approximately 940 active REITs, having over \$2.5 trillion in global market capitalization (Pavlov et al., 2018; Muhlhofer, 2019; Neo et al., 2025; NAREIT, 2025). However, emerging markets account for only around 5% of this global total, reflecting their nascent developmental stage (Marzuki & Newell, 2020; Daniel, 2022). Within Africa, countries such as South Africa, Nigeria, Kenya, Zambia, Morocco, Rwanda, Tanzania, and Ghana have introduced REIT regimes, highlighting significant development disparities relative to mature markets like the US and UK (Dabara & Ogunba, 2020).

Understanding the relationship between inflation and REIT returns is essential for investors and policymakers, particularly given inflation's capacity to erode investment purchasing power.

Historically, real estate assets have been considered effective inflation hedges due to their potential for stable real returns (Hoesli et al., 2008). Nonetheless, the extent of REITs' inflation-hedging effectiveness in emerging markets, with their distinct economic conditions and institutional environments, remains inadequately explored (Dabara & Ogunba, 2019).

This study focuses deliberately on capital returns (i.e., price-based changes in REIT values) rather than total returns, which combine price changes with cash dividends. Capital returns isolate market-pricing responses to inflation and interest-rate expectations, whereas total returns embed payout policies, dividend timing, and jurisdiction-specific distribution rules. For investor decision-making, the distinction matters: capital returns inform tactical inflation responses, risk management, and timing, while total returns reflect strategic income resilience and distribution policy. Accordingly, this study's estimates should be interpreted as evidence on price dynamics under inflationary conditions; implications for income-augmented hedging are discussed in the policy section and identified as a priority for future total-return research.

It has been observed that prior research on inflation-hedging has largely focused on direct real estate assets, offering mixed findings. For instance, Taderera and Akinsomi (2020) observed that commercial real estate in South Africa provided limited short-term inflation hedging, whereas retail and industrial properties exhibited better long-term hedging capabilities. However, these findings have limited generalizability to REITs due to differing operational and regulatory complexities inherent to these financial instruments. Moreover, most existing studies use total (holding-period) returns, blending income and capital components, thereby obscuring distinct inflation sensitivity differences between these components (Ojo et al., 2022; Muckenhaupt et al., 2025; Nasreddine & Essafi, 2025).

To address these gaps, this study distinctly examines the capital return component of REITs, allowing precise measurement of their responsiveness to inflation. The research focuses comparatively on REIT markets in the US, UK, South Africa, and Nigeria from 2013 to 2024. The selection of South Africa and Nigeria, Africa's largest REIT markets, is deliberate given their contrasting economic and institutional contexts. South Africa's relatively stable economic and regulatory environment contrasts sharply with Nigeria's nascent market characterized by pronounced inflation volatility and evolving regulatory structures (Dabara & Ogunba, 2020). Nigeria, notably, has experienced consistently high inflation rates rarely dipping below double digits, significantly disrupting economic stability and diminishing investment appeal (Dabara & Ogunba, 2019; Ojo et al., 2022). Conversely, South Africa's more stable inflation environment provides a vital comparative benchmark within the African context. Inclusion of mature economies like the US and UK, with consistently lower and stable inflation trajectories, further enriches comparative analyses, offering global reference points.

Theoretically, this research is grounded in the Fisher hypothesis framework, extended by Fama and Schwert (1977), exploring whether REIT returns adequately compensate for expected inflation, thereby serving as effective inflation hedges. Evaluating this hypothesis across developed and emerging markets enhances theoretical understanding regarding inflation's non-neutrality effects on real estate returns. The study's methodological approach of isolating capital returns from income yields addresses a notable gap in REIT literature, providing critical strategic insights for investors navigating high-inflation African markets.

Consequently, the research addresses four central questions: What are the capital returns of REITs in the selected countries (US, UK, South Africa, Nigeria) from 2013 to 2024? What are

the actual, expected, and unexpected inflation rates during this period? Is there a significant relationship between these inflation components and REIT capital returns across these markets? How do African REIT markets, particularly Nigeria and South Africa, compare with established global benchmarks in terms of inflation-hedging capabilities?

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews relevant literature and theoretical frameworks; Section 3 outlines the research methodology; Section 4 presents empirical findings; Section 5 discusses implications for policy and strategy; and Section 6 concludes the study with final remarks.

2. Theoretical Underpinning and Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Perspectives on Inflation and Asset Returns

The theoretical nexus between inflation and asset returns is primarily articulated through the Fisher hypothesis (1930), asserting that nominal returns should inherently incorporate anticipated inflation, thus preserving constant real returns if markets are efficient and investors rational. Fama and Schwert (1977) further refined this hypothesis by delineating inflation into expected and unexpected components. Their research work revealed that expected inflation tends to be incorporated efficiently into asset prices, whereas unexpected inflation (representing deviations from anticipated rates) often adversely impacts asset returns due to market rigidities or inefficiencies (Fama & Schwert, 1977; Edionwe & Ogunba, 2017; Dabara & Ogunba, 2019; Daniel, 2022). This framework typically employs the Consumer Price Index (CPI) to proxy actual inflation, with short-term nominal interest rates approximating expected inflation. Unexpected inflation is thus the residual difference, although concerns over non-stationarity and spurious results remain pertinent limitations (Daniel & Ogunba, 2019).

Real estate assets have historically been regarded as robust inflation hedges, underpinned by their tangible nature and income-generating capacity, often indexed to inflation (Ojo et al., 2022). However, REITs, as publicly traded and financialized instruments, introduce complexities due to their exposure to capital markets and real estate fundamentals, raising important theoretical and empirical questions about their inflation-hedging effectiveness across varying contexts.

Empirical examinations have yielded mixed outcomes: Sirmans and Sirmans (1987) and Miles et al. (1994) highlight real estate's efficacy as a long-term inflation hedge due to periodic rent adjustments and capital appreciation. Conversely, Hartzell et al. (1987) and Devaney and Lizieri (2005) identified limitations stemming from market illiquidity, infrequent valuations, and contractual rigidity, undermining short-term inflation hedging. Stevenson and Murray (1999) further illustrated how property type and lease structures significantly influence inflation responsiveness, notably in office sectors with extended lease terms. However, these perspectives remain underexplored within African contexts, representing a critical research gap this study aims to address.

2.2 Inflation Hedging in Mature REIT Markets

The inflation-hedging capacities of REITs have been extensively scrutinized in advanced economies due to their significant roles in global investment portfolios (Christou et al., 2018). Early U.S. studies by Fama and Schwert (1977) indicated effective short-term inflation hedging

for residential properties, whereas later findings revealed mixed results (Gyourko & Linneman, 1988; Park et al., 1990). Chatrath and Liang (1998) concluded that REITs do not reliably hedge against short-term or long-term inflationary components. Recent scholarship underscores the nuanced and conditional nature of inflation hedging, with REIT returns varying notably across economic cycles (Hardin et al., 2010, 2012; Connolly et al., 2024; Muckenhaupt et al., 2025).

European studies similarly offer mixed insights: Hoesli et al. (2008) reported positive relationships between anticipated inflation and real estate returns in the UK over the long term. In France, Nasreddine and Zouari (2024) employed advanced wavelet quantile correlation methodologies, revealing enhanced hedging performance over longer investment horizons, with short-term effectiveness dependent on inflation type. Research from Germany (Obereiner & Kurzrock, 2012) and Switzerland (Hoesli, Lizieri & MacGregor, 2008) highlighted the complex and often inadequate hedging capabilities against unexpected inflation shocks.

Asian and Australian contexts further enrich the discourse. Leung (2010) found effective commercial property hedging in Australia, while Lee et al. (2011) identified insufficient long-term hedging in East Asian markets. These diverse results underscore inherent market-specific complexities affecting REITs' inflation responsiveness. Taken together, the mature-market evidence suggests that inflation hedging by listed real estate is conditional on macro-financial regimes, lease indexation, and market depth, foreshadowing potentially different dynamics where these conditions are weaker or more volatile.

2.3 REITs and Inflation in Emerging Markets

By contrast, emerging markets exhibit distinct institutional, macroeconomic, and transparency profiles that can reshape the inflation-return linkage. In these settings, higher inflation volatility, exchange-rate pass-through, and thinner capital markets may amplify unexpected-inflation channels and weaken the pricing of expected inflation. South Africa and Nigeria provide informative contrasts on these dimensions within Africa.

The African Context Emerging markets present distinct inflation-hedging landscapes, relatively underexplored compared to developed economies. African REIT markets, particularly South Africa and Nigeria, represent vital yet under-investigated contexts. South Africa, Africa's dominant REIT market established in 2013, holds considerable significance with a capitalization of approximately USD 20 billion. Nigeria, characterized by substantial economic volatility and institutional challenges, provides a contrasting perspective. Despite their growth potential, African REITs remain marginal globally, significantly trailing behind other emerging regions such as Asia-Pacific and South America (Olarenle et al., 2019; Daniel, 2022; EPRA, 2024b).

Existing literature on emerging markets highlights variability: Lee and Lee (2014) and Edionwe and Ogunba (2017) emphasize inadequate inflation hedging, attributing deficiencies to market immaturity and regulatory constraints. In contrast, studies from Malaysia (Aik, 2012) and Turkey (Erol & Tirtiroglu, 2008) revealed effective hedging, underscoring how market-specific institutional conditions influence REIT performance.

South Africa's established regulatory frameworks and relative market stability contrast markedly with Nigeria's high inflation volatility and lower market transparency (JLL & LaSalle, 2024). Despite rapid urbanization and substantial investment flows into these countries, empirical investigations into their REITs' inflation hedging remain limited,

constraining informed decision-making and market growth (Edionwe & Ogunba, 2017; Daniel, 2022).

This review identifies critical literature gaps: limited focus on emerging markets, aggregation of total returns neglecting distinct capital and income components, and insufficient analysis of inflation decomposition in African contexts. This paper addresses these gaps through a robust comparative analysis across mature and emerging REIT markets, distinctly examining capital return responsiveness to inflation components—actual, expected, and unexpected—and linking macroeconomic dynamics to institutional quality. Such nuanced insights contribute empirically and theoretically, offering investors strategic guidance for navigating inflationary environments in African and global REIT markets.

3. Methodology

The Data and Model Specification

This study examines inflation's impact on REIT capital returns, assessing inflation-hedging potential in mature markets (the US and UK) and emerging markets (South Africa and Nigeria). Monthly data (January 2013 - March 2024, totaling 138 observations) were used, aligning with the availability of consistent monthly inflation data. The selected start date corresponds with South Africa's REIT market inception. Variables analyzed include REIT capital returns (RCR), actual inflation (AINF), expected inflation (EINF), and unexpected inflation (UINF), with comprehensive variable descriptions and sources detailed in Table 1.

Table 1: Data Description and Sources

Variables	Description	Sources
RCR	REIT Capital Return generated from RIET closed prices on monthly basis (closed price, US\$), January 2013-March 2024	EquityRT: https://0-www-equityrt-com.innopac.wits.ac.za/ , 2024
AINF	Actual inflation generated from consumer price index (CPI) at the aggregate level on monthly basis, January 2013-March 2024,	OECD database (US, UK, SA) and Central Bank of Nigeria (2024)
EINF	Expected Inflation generated from 90days Treasury Bills as proxy, January 2013-March 2024	OECD database (US, UK, SA) and Central Bank of Nigeria, 2024
UINF	Unexpected inflation a derivative from differences between actual and expected inflation on monthly basis, January 2013-March 2024	OECD database (US, UK, SA) and Central Bank of Nigeria, 2024
US REIT	The United States Real Estate Investment Trust (REIT) market was established in 1960 and, as of 2023, comprises 233 REITs with a total market capitalization exceeding US\$1.3 trillion.	National Association of Real Estate Investment Trusts (Narriet), 2025 https://www.reit.com/
UK REIT	The United Kingdom Real Estate Investment Trust (REIT) market, one of the early adopters of the REIT structure, was established in 2007. It has since grown to approximately 40 REITs, with a market capitalization of \$62.47 billion.	London Stock Exchange, 2025 https://www.londonstockexchange.com/
SA REIT	The South African Real Estate Investment Trust (REIT) market was established in 2013 through the conversion of Property Loan Stocks (PLS) and Property Unit Trusts (PUT) into the REIT framework. Since then, the market has expanded to 33 REITs with a total market capitalization of USD 22.9 billion as of	Johannesburg Stock Exchange https://www.jse.co.za/

September 2024. The SA REIT market remains the largest and most prominent REIT market on the African continent.

NG REIT Nigeria's Real Estate Investment Trust (REIT) market was established in 2008 and currently consists of three REITs. The total market capitalization of these REITs fluctuates between US\$200 million and US\$300 million, driven by exchange rate volatility. Nigerian Exchange Group, 2025 <https://ngxgroup.com/>

Source: Authors compilation 2025

Note that Nigeria's listed REIT universe comprises three vehicles over the study window, which constrains generalisability and increases sensitivity to idiosyncratic pricing. Relatedly, dividend history and constituent-level disclosures are less comprehensive than in mature markets, limiting construction of consistent total-return series and ancillary controls. These constraints are typical of early-stage markets and are mitigated here by focusing on capital returns, cross-checking inflation series from official sources, and deploying multiple long-run estimators (FMOLS/DOLS/CCR) to assess stability. The study therefore interpret Nigerian estimates as indicative of market mechanisms under high inflation volatility rather than as sector-wide performance guarantees.

a) REIT Capital Return (RCR) and Inflation Decomposition: Actual Inflation, Expected Inflation and Unexpected Inflation

This study utilizes Fisher's (1930) Inflation Hedging Hypothesis, asserting that effective inflation hedging requires a linear relationship between asset returns and inflation. REIT capital returns (RCR) were calculated as percentage changes in monthly closing prices, excluding dividends to avoid data distortion (Bodie et al., 2018; Fama & French, 1992). The analysis covered mature markets (US: 167 REITs, UK: 34 REITs) and emerging markets (SA: 29 REITs, NG: 3 REITs), using natural log form of variables to reduce variability. Inflation was decomposed into actual (CPI-based), expected (90-day treasury bills), and unexpected (actual minus expected) components in line with previous studies such as Fama & Schwert 1977; Bodie et al., 2018 and Dabara & Ogunba (2019). The REIT capital return is computed as the percentage (%) difference between the previous closing price (cp_{t-1}) and the current closing price (cp_t), divided by the previous closing price (cp_{t-1}) as expressed in Eqn₁

$$REIT\ Capital\ Return\ (RCR) = \frac{cp_t - cp_{t-1}}{cp_{t-1}} \times 100 \text{ --- Eqn 1}$$

Due to irregular dividend distributions across companies and countries, dividends were excluded from REIT return calculations to maintain data consistency. Actual inflation (π_α) was measured using the Consumer Price Index (CPI), expected inflation (π_ϵ) was proxied via 90-day Treasury Bill rates, and unexpected inflation (π_∞) was computed as the residual difference as shown in Eqn₂ following Fama & Schwert (1977) and Bodie et al. (2018).

$$\pi_\infty = \pi_\alpha - \pi_\epsilon \text{ --- Eqn 2}$$

b) Unit Root and Residual Diagnostic Tests

To validate the econometric integrity of the dataset, Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) tests were employed to assess stationarity, crucial for preventing spurious regressions and ensuring sound statistical inference (Engle & Granger, 1987; Dickey & Fuller, 1979; Granger & Newbold, 1974). The null hypothesis (H_0) of a unit root was rejected if the test statistic was more negative than the critical value with a p-value less than 0.05.

Further robustness tests included CUSUM and CUSUM of Squares (Brown et al., 1975; Hansen, 2001; Pesaran & Pesaran, 1997), verifying the stability of regression coefficients over time, with stability inferred when estimates remained within 5% significance bounds. Residual diagnostics encompassed serial correlation testing following Breusch (1978) and Godfrey (1978), ensuring residual independence, and heteroskedasticity testing (Breusch & Pagan, 1979) to confirm homoscedastic errors.

Additionally, the Ramsey RESET test (Ramsey, 1969) was conducted to detect any model misspecification arising from omitted variables or incorrect functional forms. Econometric soundness required non-significant p-values (>5%) across these diagnostic tests, thereby confirming the model's reliability for subsequent regression analyses.

c) Fisher's Inflation Hedging Hypothesis

According to Fisher's (1930) Inflation Hedging Hypothesis, rising inflation expectations prompt nominal REIT prices to adjust, preserving the real value of underlying assets. This relationship between REIT capital returns and inflation dynamics is formalized econometrically, assuming no external factors disrupt REIT valuations beyond inflationary forces. Following Fisher's hypothesis, the interdependent relationship between REIT capital returns and inflation dynamics is generally expressed as follows

$$RCR_t = \alpha + \beta\pi_t + \epsilon_t \text{-----Eqn 3}$$

Where β is the coefficient that measures relationships between REIT capital return (RCR) and inflation dynamics (π) per time t .

However, three scenarios emanated from the Fisher's hypothesized that were tested in this study

First, we examine whether **REIT capital return (RCR)** has a **positive and statistically significant** relationship with **inflation dynamics**. In this case, if the **inflation coefficient (β) is greater than one ($\beta > 1$)**, it indicates that **RCR and inflation move in the same direction**. This outcome aligns with **Fisher's theory (1930)**, suggesting that **REITs exhibit strong inflation-hedging capabilities** by effectively preserving their **real value** in response to inflationary pressures.

The second scenario occurs when there is evidence of a **partial hedge**. In this case, the **inflation coefficient (β) is positive but less than one ($0 < \beta < 1$)**. This outcome suggests that while **REITs provide some protection against inflation, their hedging capacity is weak**. As a result, the **real value of REIT assets may decline**, particularly during periods of **high inflation**, as the nominal price adjustments are insufficient to fully offset inflationary effects.

The third scenario represents a **perverse inflation hedge**, where REIT capital return (RCR) and inflation move in opposite directions. In this case, the inflation coefficient (β) is negative ($\beta < 0$),

indicating that REITs fail to protect against inflation. This suggests a poor inflation-hedging capacity, as rising inflation leads to a decline in REIT returns, fully eroding their real value due to inflationary shocks.

In interpreting coefficients, values >1 on inflation terms denote over-hedging in nominal prices; $0-1$ indicates partial hedging; and <0 implies a perverse relation with inflation. Short-run coefficients capture immediate pricing responses, while the error-correction term indicates the speed at which deviations revert towards the long-run equilibrium.

d) Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Bounds Test for Cointegration

The increasing adoption of the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model advanced by Pesaran *et al.* (2001) for regression estimation and cointegration analysis among financial researchers (Srivastava *et al.*, 2025; Chakraborty, 2024; Kriskkuma *et al.*, 2022; Ali *et al.*, 2022; Menegaki, 2019; Sehrawat and Giri, 2015) has been attributed to its comparative advantages over traditional cointegration techniques such as the Engle-Granger and Johansen tests (Chi, 2018; Nkoro and Uko, 2016). Unlike traditional models, the ARDL approach is less sensitive to unit root issues and lag order selection challenges, as it accommodates variables of mixed integration orders $I(0)$ and $I(1)$, but not $I(2)$. Additionally, it effectively captures both short-run and long-run relationships within a single-equation framework while allowing for different optimal lag lengths for different variables. Given these advantages, the ARDL technique is well-suited for the present study, considering the relatively small sample size (monthly data over 138 months) and the stationarity properties of the data, which were confirmed by unit root tests indicating a mix of $I(0)$ and $I(1)$ processes. The conventional mathematical expression of ARDL (p, q) model is expressed in Eqn 4

$$\Delta Y_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=0}^p \beta_i \Delta Y_{t-1} + \sum_{j=0}^q \gamma_j \Delta \chi_{t-j} + \lambda_1 Y_{t-1} + \lambda_2 \chi_{t-1} + \epsilon_t \text{ --- Eqn 4}$$

In this study, Y_t represents the dependent variable, while ΔY_t denotes the first-difference transformation of the dependent variable, which corresponds to REIT capital return (RCR). The time-varying dynamic effects of RCR are explained by the independent variables, namely actual inflation (AINF), expected inflation (EINF), and unexpected inflation (UINF), collectively represented as χ_t . The short-run dynamics are characterized by the lagged first difference of the dependent variable ΔY_{t-1} (lagged RCR) and the lagged first differences of the independent variables ($\Delta \chi_{t-j}$). These short-run effects are captured by the coefficients β_i and γ_j respectively. Meanwhile, the long-run relationship between RCR and the independent variables is measured by the coefficients λ_1 and λ_2 , which indicate the equilibrium effects of inflation components on REIT capital returns. α_0 and ϵ_t respectively denotes drift term and stochastic error term. Thus, the adapted and specified for the study as presented in Eqn 5

$$\begin{aligned} &\Delta \ln RCR_t \\ = &\alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^{n1} \beta_i \Delta RCR_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{n2} \gamma_2 \Delta \ln AINF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{n3} \gamma_3 \Delta \ln EINF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{n3} \gamma_3 \Delta \ln UINF_{t-i} + \lambda_1 AINF_{t-1} \\ &+ \lambda_2 EINF_{t-1} + \lambda_3 UINF_{t-1} + \epsilon_t \text{ --- Eqn 5} \end{aligned}$$

As emphasized in Pesaran et al. (2001), the F-statistic in the ARDL model is employed to assess the statistical significance of the relationship between the dependent variable (RCR) and the independent variables (inflation variants). A statistically significant long-run cointegration relationship among the variables is established when the probability value (p-value) associated with the F-statistic falls below conventional significance thresholds: 10% (*), 5% (**), or 1% (***). Furthermore, the error correction term (ECT) reflects the speed of adjustment towards long-run equilibrium. The coefficient of the ECT is expected to be negative and statistically significant (i.e., p-value < 0.05), indicating a non-explosive and stable regression model, where deviations from the long-run equilibrium are corrected over time.

e) Robustness Checks: FMOLS, DOLS, and CCR

Robustness checks are critical for validating the outcomes of regression estimates, particularly in the presence of unrestricted cointegration relationships. These tests help to further assess the reliability, validity, and predictive accuracy of the regression results. In line with previous financial studies that have employed robustness testing techniques (Wieland, 2012; Vaz de Melo Mendes & Pereira Câmara Leal, 2005; Osterrieder et al., 2023), this study adopts three advanced cointegration estimation techniques for robustness analysis of the variables under consideration: Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS), Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares (DOLS), and Canonical Cointegrating Regression (CCR). These methods enhance the robustness of the findings by correcting for endogeneity and serial correlation in the long-run relationship estimates and to prevent model misspecification and inconsistent and unrealistic estimates.

The Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) techniques neutralize the challenge of serial correlation and endogeneity in data series, making the result of the regression estimates reliable. The mathematical function of FMOLS is presented in Eqn 6

$$\beta_{FMOLS} = (\sum_{t=1}^T (x_t - \hat{x})^2)^{-1} (\sum_{t=1}^T (x_t - \hat{x})(y_t - \hat{y} - \widehat{\Omega}_{12}\widehat{\Omega}_{22}^{-1}\Delta x_t)) \dots$$

Eqn 6

Where $\widehat{\Omega}_{12}\widehat{\Omega}_{22}^{-1}$ are long-run covariance matrices estimated using kernel methods, Δx_t is the first difference of the regressor, adjusting for serial correlation and endogeneity in the model.

The similar cointegrating techniques complimentary test Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares (DOLS) (see Eqn 7) make adjustment for leads and lags of the differenced for regression model correcting the endogeneity that can make the result misrepresented and bias estimate.

$$\beta_{DOLS} = \alpha + \beta x_t + \sum_{j=1}^q \gamma_j \Delta x_{t-j} + \varepsilon_t \dots$$

Eqn 7

The adjustment for leads/lags of the differenced regression is donated by Δx_{t-j} , while q is the number of leads/lags included.

The complementary test using the Canonical Cointegrating Regression (CCR) approach involves transforming both the dependent variable (RCR) and the independent variables (inflation variants—actual, expected, and unexpected inflation rates). This transformation is carried out to correct for the endogeneity and serial correlation between the cointegrating equation and the stochastic regressors in the model (Park, 1992). The mathematical expression for this transformation is presented in Eqn 8.

$$\hat{Y}_t = \alpha + \beta \hat{X}_t + \hat{\varepsilon}_t \text{----- Eqn 8}$$

Where \hat{Y}_t denotes the transformed dependent variable (RCR), and \hat{X}_t represents the transformed independent variables (i.e., the inflation variants—actual, expected, and unexpected inflation rates). These variables can be further expanded and expressed in Eqn 9 and Eqn 10

$$\hat{Y}_t = Y_t + \alpha + \beta^l \hat{Y}_t + \hat{\varepsilon}_t \text{----- Eqn 9}$$

$$\hat{X}_t = X_t + \alpha + \beta^l \hat{X}_t + \hat{\varepsilon}_t \text{----- Eqn 10}$$

Limitations and Mitigation Strategies

Despite rigorous econometric design, this study acknowledges limitations. Capital returns were analysed independently of dividends due to incomplete dividend datasets in Nigeria and South Africa, restricting interpretations to price-based capital dynamics. Inflation expectations, proxied by historical treasury bill rates consistent with adaptive expectations theory, may underrepresent anticipatory market behaviour. Nigeria’s concentrated and illiquid REIT sector posed statistical challenges, mitigated through robustness diagnostics and cross-validation against Global Transparency Index and monetary policy reports. Exclusively employing secondary publicly available datasets ensured compliance with research ethics, methodological transparency, and reproducibility standards critical for maintaining empirical credibility in international real estate research.

4. Empirical Result

4.1 Preliminary Result

Table 2 presents descriptive statistics for REIT Capital Return (RCR), actual Inflation (AINF), expected Inflation (EINF), and unexpected Inflation (UINF) across the United States (US), United Kingdom (UK), South Africa (SA), and Nigeria (NG) from January 2013 to March 2024. Nigeria posted the highest mean RCR (0.4924) but with the greatest volatility (standard deviation 2.4471), while the UK showed a return of 0.1691 with moderate risk (0.8163). The US exhibited the lowest RCR (0.0187) yet maintained strong risk-adjusted properties with a standard deviation of 0.2810.

REIT returns varied markedly, with minimum to maximum values of -0.5838 to 1.9449 (US), -2.5881 to 7.7110 (UK), -0.9873 to 5.1039 (SA), and -9.9873 to 17.4470 (NG), reflecting extreme fluctuations, especially in Nigeria. High leptokurtosis across countries and significant Jarque-Bera (JB) statistics confirmed non-normal return distributions, with Nigeria displaying the highest JB value (2633.58), underlining substantial volatility.

Inflation analysis revealed Nigeria had the highest mean AINF (14.4598%), followed by South Africa (5.2596%), while the UK (2.7511%) and US (2.6435%) remained relatively stable. EINF was also higher in Nigeria (7.9280%) and South Africa (6.2008%) compared to the UK (1.0520%) and US (1.3489%). UINF was highest in Nigeria (6.6178%), while South Africa recorded a negative mean (-0.8900), indicating that realized inflation was often lower than expected.

Table 2: Summary Distractive Statistics Results

Country	Var.	Mean	Std Dev	Median	Max	Min.	Skew	Kurt	J-B
US	RCR	0.0187	0.2810	-0.0001	1.9449	-0.5838	2.3527	17.9172	1376.24
	AINF	2.6435	2.2212	1.9528	9.0597	-0.1995	1.3769	4.0518	48.885
	EINF	1.3489	1.7290	0.3700	5.3300	-0.0100	1.2814	3.3383	37.590
	UINF	1.3710	2.2138	0.9595	8.0324	-2.2008	1.3010	4.5850	52.218
UK	RCR	0.1691	0.8163	0.0824	7.4118	-2.5881	5.1530	48.560	12273.
	AINF	2.7511	2.4317	2.0000	9.6000	0.2000	1.5022	4.2338	59.340
	EINF	1.0520	1.6167	0.4200	5.5200	-0.1200	1.9233	5.1232	108.59
	UINF	1.7722	1.8218	1.3200	7.0300	-1.4500	1.2430	4.3937	45.69
S/Africa	RCR	0.1114	0.5842	0.0731	5.1039	-0.9873	5.3870	44.408	10297.85
	AINF	5.2596	1.2770	5.2252	8.0664	1.9354	-0.0290	2.5938	0.9470
	EINF	6.2008	1.4361	6.4600	8.7200	3.4500	-0.3637	2.1528	7.0140
	UINF	-0.8900	1.7256	-0.8109	2.9364	-3.9099	0.1762	1.9123	7.3535
Nigeria	RCR	0.4924	2.4471	0.0157	17.447	-9.5221	2.8595	23.868	2633.58
	AINF	14.4598	5.6271	13.220	33.200	7.7000	1.0097	3.8067	26.603
	EINF	7.9280	4.5677	9.9300	17.0300	0.0010	-0.1548	1.7814	8.8922
	UINF	6.6178	7.8518	4.0300	25.570	-4.1200	0.4163	1.8162	11.7830

Note: The country acronyms are as follows: United States (US), United Kingdom (UK), and South Africa (S/Africa). In the Variable (Var.) column, the variables are: REIT Capital Return (RCR), Actual Inflation (AINF), Expected Inflation (EINF), Unexpected Inflation (UINF). For the descriptive analysis: Maximum (Max.), Minimum (Min.), Standard Deviation (Std. Dev), Skewness (Skew), Kurtosis (Kurt), and Jarque-Bera (JB). The analysis is presented in sections, with corresponding results for each country provided accordingly. The year under review is from Jan, 2013 to March, 2024.

At the upper end, maximum inflation values for the UK and US were relatively close: AINF peaked at 9.60 (UK) and 9.05 (US); EINF reached 5.52 (UK) and 5.33 (US); and UINF rose to 7.03 (UK) and 8.03 (US). These figures suggest broadly similar inflationary trends across these developed economies. In contrast, South Africa displayed greater stability compared to Nigeria, which exhibited extreme inflationary disparities, with AINF ranging from 7.70 to 33.20, EINF from 0.01 to 17.03, and UINF from -4.12 to 25.57. All variables exhibited non-normal distribution (Murthy & Okunade, 2016; Rushdi et al., 2012). Notably, Nigeria consistently recorded the highest Jarque-Bera statistics, underscoring its heightened inflationary shocks and the associated risk profile of its REIT market.

Figures 1(a) to 1(d) illustrate the trends in REIT capital returns (RCR) and inflation variables (AINF, EINF, UINF) from 2013 to 2024. In the US, a major spike in RCR occurred in 2020, coinciding with declining AINF and EINF, while UINF rose sharply. Both AINF and UINF peaked in 2021, followed by a steady decline, with unexpected inflation turning negative by 2023. In the UK, RCR surged between 2013 and 2014, while inflation variables showed co-movement, particularly falling from 2013 to 2015 and again between 2017 and 2020. From late 2020 to 2022, inflation sharply rose before stabilizing in 2023. Despite RCR differences, US and UK inflation trends were broadly similar, reflecting common global inflationary pressures.

In South Africa, notable RCR spikes were observed in 2013, 2017, and 2021. UINF often recorded negative values, suggesting uncertainty, while AINF and EINF moved inversely until rising together from late 2020. In Nigeria, UINF was mostly flat, with notable dips between 2013 and 2015, increasing in 2017–2018, and steady growth post-2019. Inflationary pressures were more pronounced and volatile in emerging markets, particularly Nigeria, reflecting structural vulnerabilities and greater inflation shocks compared to developed economies.

Figure 1(a) Trend Graphs for United States Model

Figure 1(b) Trends Graph for United Kingdom

Figure 1(c) Trend Graphs for South Africa Model

Figure 1(d) Trends Graph for Nigeria Model

Figure 1(a) to 1(d) presents a series of mixed graphs illustrating the trends in the monthly data of the study variables over the review period (January 2013 – March 2024). REIT Capital Return (RCP) is represented by a bar chart, while Actual Inflation (AINF), Expected Inflation (EINF), and Unexpected Inflation (UINF) are depicted using line graphs. The x-axis represents the variable indexes, while the y-axis corresponds to the periodic values of each variable.

4.2 Stationary and Stability Tests Results

Unit root testing was conducted using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) tests to ensure stationarity of the dataset. Results indicated a mix of integration orders: some variables were stationary at level [I(0)], while others became stationary only after first differencing [I(1)]. Specifically, at level [I(0)], many variables were non-stationary (p-value > 0.05), but at first difference [I(1)], all achieved stationarity (p-value < 0.05). This is consistent with macroeconomic data behaviour, affirming the suitability of the ARDL (Autoregressive

Distributed Lag) model, which accommodates a mix of I(0) and I(1) variables, provided none are I(2).

Following stationarity confirmation, stability was assessed using the Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) and Cumulative Sum of Squares (CUSUMSQ) tests. Figures 2 to 5 present the diagnostic plots for each country. The CUSUM and CUSUMSQ tests indicated that the regression parameters remained within the 5% significance bounds across all models. These results confirm the structural stability and robustness of the econometric models, providing a sound basis for subsequent dynamic analyses of the relationship between REIT capital returns and inflation components.

US-Models

Fig. 2(a) CUSUM Test

Fig. 2(b) CUSUM of Square Test

UK-Models

Fig. 3(a) CUSUM Test

Fig. 3(b) CUSUM of Square Test

SA-Models

Fig. 4(a) CUSUM Test

Fig. 4(b) CUSUM of Square Test

Fig. 5(a) CUSUM Test

Fig. 5(b) CUSUM of Square Test

The line graphs depict the CUSUM and CUSUM of Squares tests for model stability. The analysis generates two graphs for each country's models: (a) CUSUM test and (b) CUSUM of Squares test. The models are structured as follows: United States: US-Model 2a & 2b, United Kingdom: UK-Model 3a & 3b, South Africa: SA-Model 4a & 4b, and Nigeria: NG-Model 5a & 5b. The CUSUM critical values for the model estimates are assessed at a 5% significance level, determining the stability of the estimated models.

4.3 Main Result

The degree of association between the variables (RCR and inflation) under consideration was examined using a correlation matrix, and the results are presented in Table 3. In the US, inflation variables showed a weak positive correlation with RCR, suggesting synchronized movements. Conversely, in the UK, inflation variables negatively correlated with RCR, indicating inverse relationships. South Africa and Nigeria displayed mixed patterns: AINF and EINF were negatively correlated with RCR, while UINF positively correlated throughout the study period, highlighting market-specific inflation dynamics.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

Variables	US-RCR	UK-RCR	SA-RCR	NG-RCR
AINF	0.0741	-0.00531	-0.0073	-0.0204
EINF	0.0361	-0.0167	-0.0179	-0.0396
UINF	0.0669	-0.00251	0.0118	0.00048

The results are the extracts from the correlation matrix for each country. The corresponding actual inflation (AINF), expected inflation (EINF), and unexpected inflation (UINF) were correlated against REIT Capital Return for the United States (US-RCR), United Kingdom (UK-RCR), South Africa (SA-RCR), and Nigeria (NG-RCR).

4.4 Long-Run and Short Run Estimates

The long-run coefficients from the ARDL models provide valuable insights into the inflation-hedging capabilities of REITs across different market contexts. Table 4 reports the ARDL long-run elasticities of RCR with respect to inflation components. In the US, RCRs exhibit a significant negative association with actual inflation ($\beta = -0.152$, $p < 0.01$) and weak positive relationships with EINF ($\beta = 0.148$, $p < 0.1$) and UINF ($\beta = 0.145$, $p < 0.1$), indicating poor inflation-hedging effectiveness. In the UK, RCRs show negative but statistically insignificant relationships with EINF ($\beta = -0.661$) and UINF ($\beta = -0.616$), and a weakly positive but insignificant relationship with AINF ($\beta = 0.681$), suggesting inflation is not systematically priced.

South African REITs display a significantly negative relationship with EINF ($\beta = -1.662$, $p < 0.01$), while UINF is negative but insignificant ($\beta = -0.178$), reflecting investor pessimism regarding inflation expectations. In contrast, Nigerian REITs demonstrate a strong positive responsiveness to EINF ($\beta = 0.943$, $p < 0.05$) and UINF ($\beta = 1.974$, $p < 0.01$), suggesting that inflation shocks redirect investments towards REITs as real asset proxies, particularly during inflationary pressures. These findings highlight significant regional differences in REITs' inflation-hedging characteristics.

Table 4 ARDL Outcomes

Variables	US	UK	SA	NIG
Long-run				
<i>C</i>	0.017 (0.610)	0.082 (0.556)	-3.1053 (0.0225)**	0.975 (0.848)
<i>AINF</i>	-0.152 (0.081)***	0.681 (0.197)	3.154 (0.0053)*	-2.944 (0.194)
<i>EINF</i>	0.148 (0.073)***	-0.661 (0.193)	-1.662 (0.0588)***	0.943 (0.0241)**
<i>UINF</i>	0.145 (0.070)***	-0.6162 (0.200)	-0.1784 (0.2371)	1.974 (0.0015)***
Short-run				
$\Delta AINF$	-0.180 (0.090)**	0.6102 (0.193)	2.804 (0.0066)*	0.694 (0.0000)*
$\Delta EINF$	0.165 (0.075)**	-0.591 (0.188)	-1.4779 (0.0628)***	-2.045 (0.1873)
$\Delta UINF$	0.175 (0.073)**	-0.551 (0.195)	-0.1586 (0.2450)	1.3710 (0.0015)*
<i>ect(-1)</i>	-0.863 (0.000)*	-0.8267 (0.0000)*	-0.889 (0.0000)*	-0.694 (0.0000)*
Residual Diagnostic Tests				
<i>Serial Correlation</i>	0.8374 (0.4499)	1.9587 (0.1836)	0.1387 (0.8718)	0.8302 (0.4423)
<i>Heteroskedasticity</i>	0.2439 (0.9129)	0.3485 (0.8446)	0.1703 (0.9532)	1.1178 (0.3511)
<i>Ramsey RESET</i>	0.3985 (0.5358)	1.0734 (0.3084)	0.0168 (0.9049)	1.4707 (0.2312)
R^2 (%)	20.57	19.42	61.11	45.14
<i>Adj. R²</i> (%)	13.86	15.99	22.22	39.43

The table presents the long-run and short-run ARDL results, including residual diagnostic tests for each country. The dependent variable is REIT Capital Return (RCR), while the independent variables are Actual Inflation (AINF), Expected Inflation (EINF), and Unexpected Inflation (UINF). The ARDL analysis was conducted for four countries: the United States (US), the United Kingdom (UK), South Africa (SA), and Nigeria (NIG). The ARDL F-statistic coefficient is reported along with its significance level (in parentheses). In the short-run estimates, the error correction term, *ect*(-1), is included to indicate the speed of adjustment toward long-run equilibrium. Residual diagnostic tests assess model fitness, and the R-Square and Adjusted R-Square values are reported as percentages (%). Significance levels are denoted as follows: 1% (*), 5% (**), and 10% (***).

From Table 4, it has been observed that in mature markets (US/UK), inflation is not systematically priced in long-run capital returns; only weak, mixed short-run effects are observed. In South Africa, expected inflation exerts a negative long-run effect, consistent with rising risk premia and weaker indexation. Nigeria's capital returns load positively on unexpected inflation, indicating that inflation surprises dominate price formation under volatility.

In the emerging REIT market, inflation expectations and speculative pressures appear to undermine the ability of REITs to preserve their real value, particularly as inflationary pressure intensifies. In South Africa, RCR show strong short-run protection against AINF ($\beta = 2.804$, $p > 0.1$), but reveal a perverse inflation-hedging relationship with EINF ($\beta = -1.478$, $p > 0.1$) and UINF ($\beta = -0.159$, $p > 0.1$), consistent across long-run estimates. In Nigeria, REIT capital

returns show a strong positive and statistically significant response to UINF ($\beta = 1.371$, $p < 0.1$) and a moderate but significant relationship with AINF ($\beta = 0.694$, $p < 0.01$). However, they exhibit a perverse relationship with EINF ($\beta = -2.045$, $p > 0.1$). Nigerian REITs thus demonstrate the strongest inflation-hedging capacity among the markets analysed, particularly against UINF shocks, despite concerns over heightened market volatility for institutional and long-term investors.

4.5 Robustness Test

To reinforce the ARDL model outcomes, additional long-run estimators—Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS), Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares (DOLS), and Canonical Cointegrating Regression (CCR)—were employed. FMOLS results confirm limited inflation-hedging capacity for US REITs, particularly against EINF (-0.1190) and UINF (-0.6240). UK and South African REITs also exhibit erosive effects from EINF and UINF (-0.2379 ; -0.3210 and -1.7248 ; -0.2029 , respectively). Nigerian REITs display a significant perverse hedge against AINF (-1.0149). DOLS and CCR results align, showing poor inflation protection, especially in emerging markets, thus corroborating dynamic inflationary pressures affecting REIT performance.

Table 5: Robustness Tests

Variables	US	UK	SA	NG
<i>Fully Modified Least Squares (FMOLS)</i>				
<i>C</i>	-3.377 (0.0000)*	-1.725 (0.0137)**	-1.598 (0.0557)***	-2.9713 (0.3731)
<i>AINF</i>	1.617 (0.0023)*	0.509 (0.5572)	2.223 (0.0002)*	-1.0149 (0.4816)
<i>EINF</i>	-0.1190 (0.3323)	-0.2379 (0.2742)	-1.7248 (0.0010)*	0.7084 (0.0228)**
<i>UINF</i>	-0.6240 (0.0918)***	-0.3210 (0.5964)	-0.2029 (0.0557)***	1.2309 (0.0019)*
R²(%)	20.78	12.42	34.25	19.31
Adj. R²(%)	16.12	13.77	26.30	15.70
<i>Dynamic Least Squares (DOLS)</i>				
<i>C</i>	-0.0205 (0.5246)	0.1132 (0.4062)	-1.5150 (0.1321)	-0.5494 (0.9043)
<i>AINF</i>	-0.1355 (0.3310)	0.35725 (0.5613)	1.862170 (0.0077)*	-2.5147 (0.2360)
<i>EINF</i>	0.15522 (0.2571)	-0.34907 (0.5608)	-1.485866 (0.0121)**	1.263470 (0.0088)*
<i>UINF</i>	0.15174 (0.2667)	-0.3448 (0.5485)	-0.166118 (0.1572)	1.767211 (0.0055)*
R²(%)	17.71	4.715	29.86	35.69
Adj. R²(%)	13.82	1.432	9.825	21.41
<i>Canonical Cointegrating Regression (CCR)</i>				
<i>C</i>	0.0185 (0.5181)	0.0830 (0.5068)	-1.5753 (0.0576)***	-2.1167 (0.5699)
<i>AINF</i>	-0.1480	0.4066	2.1903	-1.4110

	(0.1052)	(0.4599)	(0.0001)*	(0.3937)
<i>EINF</i>	0.1448	-0.403091	-1.714624	0.7751
	(0.0936)***	(0.4501)	(0.0009)*	(0.0241)**
<i>UINF</i>	0.1493	-0.375291	-0.196559	1.3125
	(0.0785)***	(0.4547)	(0.0317)**	(0.0027)*
R²(%)	2.071	2.094	18.00	18.52
Adj. R²(%)	0.182	0.231	13.36	14.87

The table presents the results of the robustness tests, including Fully Modified Least Squares (FMOLS), Dynamic Least Squares (DOLS), and Canonical Cointegrating Regression (CCR). For each country over the review period, the table reports: the coefficient estimates with their respective probability values (in parentheses), the R-Square (R²) and Adjusted R-Square (Adj. R²) for model evaluation. Significance levels are denoted as follows: 1% (), 5% (**), and 10% (***)*

Table 5 shows that FMOLS/DOLS/CCR broadly corroborate ARDL patterns: mature markets show limited hedging, South Africa registers negative sensitivity to expected inflation, and Nigeria remains most responsive to unexpected inflation. Cross-method agreement on coefficient signs strengthens inference despite sample and disclosure constraints.

5. Discussion and Policy Implications

This study reveals a highly conditional and market-specific relationship between RCR and inflation dynamics, offering nuanced insights across mature and emerging economies. In mature REIT markets like the United States and the United Kingdom, the empirical results indicate negligible inflation responsiveness in the long run, confirming prior findings by Glascock et al. (2002), Hoesli and Oikarinen (2012) and Muckenhaupt et al. (2025). The weak inflation-hedging capacity observed can be attributed to factors such as stabilized inflation expectations, the dominance of long-term lease structures, and greater market efficiency. Consistent with the findings of Campbell and Shiller (1996) and Eichholtz and Yonder (2015), mature REITs often behave more like equities rather than direct real assets under inflationary pressure, with asset pricing being more influenced by broader financial market integration than by inflation fundamentals.

Conversely, the emerging markets show significantly different dynamics. South African REITs demonstrate a negative and statistically significant relationship with *EINF*, suggesting that inflation expectations act as a proxy for macroeconomic fragility, rising default risks, and diminished rental growth prospects. This finding corroborates studies by Edionwe and Ogunba (2017); Dabara and Ogunba (2019) and Daniel (2022), who observed that inflation expectations in emerging economies often reflect broader economic instability rather than predictable price movements. Moreover, the lack of effective inflation-targeting frameworks in emerging markets exacerbates speculative market behaviour (Menegaki, 2019; Ali et al., 2022; Chakraborty, 2024)

In Nigeria, the results demonstrate a strong and statistically significant positive relationship between RCR and *UINF*. This confirms prior findings by Dabara and Ogunba (2019) and Dabara and Ogunba (2020), suggesting that unexpected inflation shocks, rather than anticipated inflation, drive REIT price movements in high-volatility contexts. These findings challenge the universal validity of the Fisher Hypothesis (1930) and the classical Fama and Schwert (1977) framework, emphasizing that institutional weakness, low transparency, and investor speculation dominate asset pricing behaviour in emerging markets (Rushdi et al., 2012; Dabara and Ogunba, 2019; EPRA, 2024b).

The global policy implications are substantial. First, improving market transparency, financial reporting standards, and valuation methodologies remains essential for emerging market REITs to evolve into reliable inflation-hedging instruments (JLL & LaSalle, 2024; EPRA, 2024a; Marzuki and Newell, 2020; Dabara and Ogunba, 2020; Daniel, 2022). Regulatory reforms modelled after successful frameworks such as Belgium's REIT regime (Marzuki and Newell, 2019) should be prioritized to enhance investor confidence and reduce asymmetries in market information.

Secondly, inflation-indexed lease structures should be mainstreamed across African and emerging market REITs. As evidenced by Glascock et al. (2002) and further discussed by Fatnassi et al. (2014), contractual rent adjustments linked to inflation indices significantly strengthen the inflation-hedging capacity of real estate assets. Current African leases largely lack automatic CPI adjustments, exposing REIT cash flows to real-term erosion during inflationary periods.

Thirdly, macroeconomic stabilization is indispensable. Without effective monetary policy credibility, high inflation volatility undermines investor expectations and speculative shifts dominate market outcomes (Fatnassi et al., 2014; Menegaki, 2019; Ali et al., 2022; Chakraborty, 2024). Institutional frameworks modelled after inflation-targeting successes in the US and UK should be adopted.

For investors, the findings underscore the need for differentiated strategies between mature and emerging REIT markets. In developed economies, investors should supplement REIT allocations with alternative inflation hedges such as TIPS (Treasury Inflation-Protected Securities), commodities, and infrastructure assets (Simpson et al., 2007; Eichholtz and Yonder, 2015; Bodie et al., 2018; NAREIT, 2025; Muckenhaupt et al., 2025). In emerging markets, active portfolio rebalancing, diversified regional exposure, and scenario-based risk assessment are critical to manage the asymmetric inflation responsiveness of REITs (Murthy and Okunade, 2016).

Furthermore, institutional investors should integrate inflation scenario stress-testing within REIT investment models to address the nonlinear risk dynamics observed, particularly in emerging markets (Marzuki and Newell, 2020; Dabara and Ogunba, 2020; Daniel, 2022).

Importantly, while this study focused on capital returns to isolate pure price effects, it acknowledges the omission of dividends as a limitation. Dividends are crucial in mature REIT markets for total inflation protection (Pavlov et al., 2018; Marzuki and Newell, 2020; Muckenhaupt et al., 2025). Future studies should model total returns, allowing a richer understanding of REITs' inflation-hedging behaviour across different income structures.

Finally, at a regional scale, harmonising REIT regulations and establishing common transparency benchmarks under platforms like AfCFTA (African Continental Free Trade Area) could substantially improve market liquidity, cross-border investment, and resilience to inflation shocks (Dabara and Ogunba, 2020). A Pan-African REIT Index, coupled with joint listings, could reduce country-specific volatility, enhance economies of scale, and reposition African REIT markets as viable inflation hedges on the global investment map. In Summary the implications for practitioners and policy markers include:

Implications for practitioners.

(i) Treat listed real estate as a conditional rather than universal inflation hedge; combine REITs with inflation-indexed bonds and real assets where cash-flow indexation is explicit. (ii) In South Africa/Nigeria, emphasise scenario-based stress-tests for unexpected-inflation shocks and

rebalance tactically around monetary-policy events. (iii) Focus on lease indexation and sectoral mix when interpreting cross-market differences in price responses.

Implications for policymakers and regulators.

(i) Encourage CPI-linked lease clauses and standardised disclosure (dividend timetables, indexation, and sector exposures) to enhance price discovery. (ii) Strengthen the transparency and reporting regime (e.g., market-wide index methodology notes, sector-level free float thresholds). (iii) Support regional benchmarking and cross-listing (e.g., a Pan-African REIT sub-index) to dilute idiosyncratic country risk and facilitate hedging products.

6. Conclusion and Future Research Directions

This study assessed the inflation-hedging characteristics of REIT capital returns across two mature (United States and United Kingdom) and two emerging (South Africa and Nigeria) economies over the period 2013–2024. Grounded in the Fisher (1930) inflation hypothesis and the Fama-Schwert (1977) decomposition framework, our findings reveal that inflation responsiveness is far from uniform. Instead, it is shaped by structural, institutional, and behavioural dynamics unique to each market context.

In mature economies, REITs demonstrated negligible long-term responsiveness to inflation, consistent with prior research (Glascock et al., 2002; Hoesli et al., 2008; Muckenhaupt et al., 2025). This reinforces the notion that REITs in stable markets behave more like equities, influenced by long-term lease structures, anchored inflation expectations, and greater transparency. In contrast, emerging markets revealed complex inflation dynamics: South African REITs displayed perverse inflation-hedging relationships, while Nigerian REITs exhibited strong positive responses to unexpected inflation shocks, suggesting that inflation surprises—rather than fundamentals—drive REIT returns in volatile environments.

These findings advance the real estate finance literature by highlighting the critical importance of decomposing inflation and recognizing the behavioural underpinnings of REIT performance under inflationary pressures. Policy implications are profound. Enhancing REIT market transparency, instituting CPI-indexed lease structures, and strengthening inflation-targeting regimes are crucial for improving market stability, particularly in Africa and other emerging regions.

For global investors, the results caution against assuming universal inflation protection through REITs. Instead, context-specific strategies, dynamic portfolio rebalancing, and rigorous scenario modelling are imperative for effectively managing inflation risk. Future research should incorporate total return measures and sectoral differentiation to capture a fuller picture of REIT inflation resilience.

Ultimately, REITs are not homogenous inflation-hedging instruments; their effectiveness is highly contingent on macroeconomic stability, institutional quality, and investor sentiment. This nuanced understanding is critical for investors, policymakers, and scholars navigating the increasingly volatile global real estate landscape. As global inflation dynamics become increasingly unpredictable, the role of REITs as both investment vehicles and macroeconomic

stabilisers will demand continued empirical scrutiny, regional collaboration, and methodological innovation.

Notwithstanding the study's contributions, limitation exists. The African evidence is represented only by South Africa and Nigerian REITs, which constrains the external validity of any continent-wide inference. In particular, Nigeria's REIT market comprises very few listed vehicles (only 3 active REITs) with thin liquidity and heterogeneous disclosures, increasing sensitivity to issuer-specific events and limiting the reliability of inference for the broader Nigerian sector. These structural features, together with differences in index construction and reporting practices, imply that the results should be interpreted as indicative rather than definitive for African REITs as a whole. Future research should assemble harmonised total-return series (price plus dividends) and expand coverage to additional African jurisdictions with operating REIT regimes as sufficiently long and consistent time series become available, enabling cross-country panel estimation and finer sectoral disaggregation. These constraints reinforce our decision to emphasise capital returns; accordingly, our findings speak to price dynamics under inflation rather than to income-augmented, total-return performance. Future work could extend the analysis to total returns as dividend time-series improve in South Africa and especially Nigeria.

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**Peer Reviewed*

Will AI replace property valuers in a machine-driven real estate industry? *Priscilla Oyebola Bello¹ and Emmanuel Elijah Bassey²*

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Abstract

The property valuation landscape continues to undergo tremendous challenges due to rapid technological advancements such as AI, which have led to a more machine driven real estate industry. This study, therefore, investigates the awareness, adoption, and perception of estate surveyors and valuers of AI in property valuation in Calabar, Nigeria. The study adopted a quantitative approach. Questionnaires were administered to 32 Estate Surveyors and Valuers from 11 estate firms in Calabar. The data was analysed using frequency distribution table, weighted mean score, and factor analysis. The findings revealed that there is a very low adoption of AI-driven valuation methods (weighted mean = 1.66). The major factor influencing the adoption of AI is the operational and implementation factors. Furthermore, there is a relatively high perception that AI could replace human property valuers, with a weighted mean score of 3.25. The study suggests that property valuers remain abreast with the technological changes ongoing in the market. Also, the study recommends AI training for property valuers.

Key words: Valuation; Artificial Intelligence; Property Valuer; Machine Learning; Property Market

1. Introduction

Property valuation is an integral aspect of the real estate industry. It is the process of estimating the value of a property at a particular time for specific purposes, considering the overall understanding of property market regarding demand and supply, economy, legal impact, physical constraints, and other influencing variables (Shetty et al., 2020). This value is established with the selling price it can bring, considering that property value can vary based on the reason for carrying out the valuation, such as for sales, purchase, mortgages, taxation, amongst others (Parmar et al., 2018; Mankad, 2022). The essence of valuation is to provide a reliable, credible, and cost-effective appraisal of market value of a real property at a given point in time (Glumac and Rosiers, 2021).

Over the years, the property valuation landscape has been undergoing tremendous transformations, with valuation methods ranging from traditional (non-model) to model based methods. The traditional (non-model or manual) methods include sales comparison method, income method, profit method, cost method, and residual method (Gabrielli and French, 2021). These methods often rely on limited datasets and expert judgement and have proven to be subjective, unreliable, costly, and inaccurate (Zurada et al., 2006; Topraklı, 2024). The model based methods include functional form-based and non-functional form models, with the functional model consisting of linear regression (LR) and Geographical Weighted Regression (GWR), and non-functional form models consisting of Artificial Intelligence (Machine learning and deep learning techniques). Machine learning consists of K-nearest neighbour (KNN), Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), Fuzzy Logic (FL), Random Forest (RF), Expert Systems, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Decision Trees (DT). Deep learning encompasses Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) (Numan and Yusoff, 2024).

Presently, there is a growing reliance on property valuation automation facilitated by technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Blockchain (Royal Institution of Chartered Surveyors (RICS), 2016). AI has enhanced the efficacy and accuracy of the property valuation process due to its capabilities in image recognition, risks assessment, natural language processing (NLP), and higher predictive accuracy (Al-Tit et al., 2022). With AI, the valuation process becomes automated and optimised, leading to a more precise and timely property valuation process (Żróbek et al., 2020; Ayodele, 2022). AI-driven valuation techniques can predict future property values and market conditions with high accuracy, outperforming traditional methods of valuation (Sağlam et.al, 2023). For this reason, there is a growing use of AI-driven valuation techniques among general consumers, who are not property valuers and are not privy to the actual transaction price information and cannot evaluate the validity of the valuation (Ota and Uto, 2024). Ota and Uto (2024) further opined that there are over 20 AI property valuation services in Japan and are mostly used by consumers who want to buy or sell their properties because of its ease of use and availability.

In line with the above, there is a significant gap existing in both academic discourse and empirical research regarding the extent to which AI can or should replace professional property valuers. This gap is particularly relevant in this era, where rapid technological advancements are transforming human thought processes, work practices, and lifestyles. According to Stubbings et al. (2018), automation and ‘thinking machines’ are gradually displacing human tasks and jobs, and reshaping the skill sets that organisations require from their workforce. In the real estate industry, this raises critical questions not only about property valuers awareness and adoption of AI-driven valuation methods, but also about how these technologies are perceived in relation to their potential to enhance or undermine the valuer’s role. Understanding these dimensions and gaps are essential to evaluating the future of valuation practice in a machine-driven real estate industry and the theoretical understanding of technology adoption in emerging economies. Therefore, this research, attempts to address these critical questions and gaps by focusing on the awareness and adoption of AI-driven valuation techniques, perception of estate surveyors and valuers of AI-driven valuation techniques, and factors influencing adoption in Calabar, Nigeria.

2. Literature Review

This section is a review of the recent and relevant studies that have been done in the subject area.

2.1 Review of Past Studies

There has been a growing scholarly interest on the use of AI in property valuation in recent years. Cheung (2024) examined the use of Large Language Models (LLM) such as Chatgpt in property valuation reports. The findings revealed that adopting LLMs in property valuation processes, such as drafting contracts and generating reports led to enhanced efficiency, reliability, interpretability, transparency, and enhancement of client’s experiences. Ota and Uto (2024) examined the variation in property valuations conducted by artificial intelligence in Japan: a viewpoint of user’s perspective. Data was analysed using multiple comparison tests. The findings showed a 10.6% average variation in the AI property valuations, larger than the variations observed in traditional property valuations. However, Topraklı (2024) carried out a study on AI-driven valuation: a new era for real estate appraisal. The study adopted a comprehensive literature review and systematic analysis approach. The results showed that AI-

driven valuation techniques offered significant advantages over the traditional valuation methods, offering enhanced efficiency and accuracy, lower costs, and advanced risk management. The findings of both studies are contradictory as Ota and Uto (2024) highlighted the limitations of the use of AI-driven valuation techniques due to its high degree of variability in results.

These findings on the capabilities of AI-driven valuation techniques underscore the need to further explore the extent to which these techniques are actively used in valuation practice. Abidoeye et al. (2019) carried out a study on property valuation methods in practice: evidence from Australia. The data obtained was analysed using frequency distribution, X^2 test, and mean score ranking. The study found that traditional methods of valuation were still the most adopted by Australian property valuers, while the advanced valuation methods were rarely used in practice. Chan and Abidoeye (2019) conducted a study on advanced property valuation techniques: deciphering the artificial neural network technique. A detailed literature review was carried and the results showed that ANN technique could yield an average accurate and reliable value, but has not been widely adopted in practice. Kasim et al. (2025) examined the factors influencing property valuation models development and application as decision support systems. Data was analysed using a scoping review approach and snowball technique. The results reviewed that deficiencies in the use of traditional valuation methods have led to a shift in the use of advanced valuation techniques; however, technological challenges have hindered the adoption of these advanced valuation techniques. The findings of Kasim et al. (2025) supports that of Chan and Abidoeye (2019) and Abidoeye et al. (2019). The studies identified the disconnect between the potential advantages of AI and the actual use of it in property valuation.

The findings from previous studies reviewed in this research consistently indicate a lack of adoption of AI in property valuation practice. The results are not surprising, as several other studies have reported that many property valuers are not even aware of the existence or potential application of AI technologies in valuation processes. Abidoeye and Chan (2017) investigated valuers' receptiveness to the application of artificial intelligence in property valuation. The obtained data was analysed with percentiles, mean score, and chi-square tests. The results showed that more than half of the respondents were aware of AI valuation techniques. However, Adewusi and Gbadebo (2023) conducted a study on the awareness of artificial intelligence technologies for residential property valuation in Lagos Metropolis, Nigeria. The data obtained was analysed with weighted mean score and Chi-square tests. The results showed that the Estate Surveyors and Valuers in Lagos metropolis are generally unaware of artificial intelligence technologies. Both studies identified the minimal use of AI valuation but also reveals a divergent findings on awareness. Abidoeye and Chan (2017) surveyed valuers across Nigeria, while Adewusi and Gbadebo (2023) focused specifically on Lagos metropolis. This suggests that awareness levels may vary by regional location; hence, this research will focus on the awareness and adoption of AI-driven valuation methods in Calabar, which will further investigate the regional differences in AI valuation models awareness and adoption among property valuers.

With increasing awareness and adoption of AI in property valuation, there is a growing scholarly discourse surrounding the future of property valuers. Wilkinson et al. (2018) carried out a study on the future of the Australian valuation profession: new knowledge, emerging trends and practices. The data was obtained from focus group discussion and analysed using thematic analysis. The results revealed that majority of the respondents perceive that valuation

is caught up in a rapidly changing environment which poses several challenges such as the increasing use of automated valuation models. Lee et al. (2024) examined the future of property workforce: challenges and opportunities for professionals in the changing landscape. The data was analysed using thematic analysis. The study showed that a majority of the respondents perceived technology such as AI as a tool that would enhance property professionals and not replace their role as property managers. While both studies revealed the growing presence of technology in the real estate industry, neither of the studies focused on property valuers in relation to AI-driven valuation tools. There is a limited research focused on the perceptions of property valuers in an emerging economy such as Nigeria. Furthermore, there is no consensus in literature on whether AI is perceived to be a threat or a complement to human property valuers. This shows that there is a need to understand how property valuers in different regions interpret the implications of AI in their profession.

3. Methods

This section outlines the study population, data collection process, and data analysis adopted for this study.

3.1 Study Population

This research employed a quantitative research approach. The study population for this research are the Estate Surveyors and Valuers practising in eleven firms in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria. The number of firms in Calabar was gotten from the Nigerian Institution of Estate Surveyors and Valuers Firms Directory (2025). A total number of 43 Estate Surveyors and Valuers were identified working in the eleven firms. Although the exact number of practising Estate Surveyors and Valuers in Calabar may be higher, the study focused on those affiliated with the eleven registered firms in the city. The population of Estate Surveyors and Valuers practising in Calabar are relatively small and accessible. Therefore, a census approach was adopted.

3.2 Data Collection

The data collection instrument used for this study was a self-administered, structured, and close-ended questionnaire, which ensured uniformity of responses and facilitated ease of quantitative analysis. The questionnaires were designed by the researchers to capture information on the awareness, adoption, and perception of Estate Surveyors and Valuers regarding AI-driven valuation techniques, as well as factors influencing their adoption. No pilot survey was conducted and census approach adopted due to the relatively small population size. However, care was taken to ensure clarity of the questions. The questionnaire was physically distributed to 43 Estate Surveyors and Valuers, with follow-up visits to enhance response rates. Only 32 (74%) of the questionnaires were retrieved and found suitable for the analysis.

3.3 Data Analysis

Frequency distribution was used to analyse the Estate Surveyors and Valuers' profiles. Weighted mean score was used to analyse the awareness, adoption, and perception of Estate Surveyors and Valuers of AI-driven valuation techniques. Factor analysis was used to analyse the factors influencing the adoption of AI in property valuation. The weighted mean score was measured using a 4-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 4 (Strongly Agree). The midpoint of the scale was 2.5, calculated as the average of the minimum and maximum

scores (i.e. $\frac{1+4}{2} = 2.5$) (Salacut et al., 2025; Udoh et al., 2025). The benchmark was used to interpret the results as follows:

- 1.00 – 1.75 indicates a very low level of mean ranking
- 1.76 – 2.50 shows a fairly low level of ranking
- 2.51 - 3.25 represents fairly/moderately high level of mean ranking
- 3.26 – 4.00 reflects a very high level of mean ranking

4. Results and Discussion

This section encompasses the analysis of the data obtained from the questionnaire administered and the discussion of findings.

4.1 Estate Surveyors and Valuers' Profile

Table 1 describes the profiles of the respondents in terms of their age, gender, highest educational qualification, years of professional experience, and professional membership.

Table 1: Profile of respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percentages
Age Bracket		
21-30	9	28.1
31-40	12	37.5
41-50	6	18.8
51-60	4	12.5
Above 60	1	3.1
Total		100.00
Gender		
Male	24	75.0
Female	8	25.0
Total		100.00
Highest Educational Qualification		
HND	4	12.5
BSc	21	65.6
MSc	5	15.6
PhD	2	6.3
Total		100.00
Years of Professional Experience		
0-5 years	6	18.8
6-10 years	9	28.1
11-15 years	13	40.6
16-20 years	1	3.1
Above 20 years	3	9.4
Total		100.00

Professional Membership Status		
Probationer	1	3.1
ANIVS	25	78.1
FNIVS	6	18.8
Total		100.00

Field Survey (2025)

Table 1 shows the age distribution of the respondents, and it reveals a predominantly young to middle-aged demographic. The largest age group is 31-40 years, comprising 37.5% of the sample, followed by the 21-30 years bracket at 28.1%. Together, these two groups make up nearly two-thirds (65.63%) of the respondents, indicating a workforce that is relatively youthful and likely in the early to mid-stages of their careers. The 41-50 age group accounts for 18.8%, while those aged 51-60 and above 60 represent smaller proportions, 12.5% and 3.1% respectively. This age profile suggests that the majority of respondents may be more open to new technologies and innovations, such as AI adoption, given their potential adaptability and longer career horizons.

As seen in Table 1, the gender breakdown shows a significant male dominance within the sample, with males constituting 75% of respondents compared to 25% females. This disparity reflects a common trend in many professional sectors where male participation tends to be higher. The gender imbalance might influence the perspectives and experiences shared in the study, potentially affecting views on workplace diversity, inclusivity, and the adoption of new technologies. Understanding this gender distribution is crucial for tailoring professional development programmes and ensuring equitable opportunities for all practitioners.

Regarding educational attainment, the majority of respondents hold a Bachelor of Science (BSc) degree, representing 65.6% of the sample. Those with Higher National Diploma (HND) qualifications make up 12.5%, while postgraduate qualifications such as Master of Science (MSc) and PhD account for 15.6% and 6.3%, respectively. This distribution indicates a well-educated respondent base, with a substantial proportion having advanced degrees that may enhance their capacity to understand and implement complex concepts like AI in property valuation. The relatively small percentage of PhD holders suggests that while expertise exists, it is concentrated among a few individuals, highlighting potential opportunities for further academic and professional development.

In Table 1, the respondents' years of professional experience show a broad range, with the largest group (40.6%) having between 11 and 15 years of experience. This is followed by 6-10 years (28.1%) and 0-5 years (18.8%), indicating that most respondents are mid-career professionals with substantial practical exposure. Only a small fraction have over 20 years of experience (9.4%) or between 16-20 years (3.1%). This experience profile suggests a mature workforce with a solid foundation of industry knowledge, which is essential for critically evaluating and integrating new technologies such as AI. The presence of less experienced professionals also points to ongoing entry of fresh talent into the field.

In terms of professional membership, the majority of respondents (78.1%) are Associates of the Nigerian Institution of Valuers and Surveyors (ANIVS), while 18.8% hold the Fellow status (FNIVS), and only 3.1% are probationers. This distribution indicates a highly engaged and credentialed respondent pool, with most individuals having formal recognition within their

professional body. The predominance of ANIVS members suggests that many respondents are established professionals, though not yet at the highest fellowship level, which may reflect their career progression stage. This professional status distribution is important for understanding the level of expertise and commitment respondents bring to discussions on industry practices and innovations.

4.2 Awareness of AI in property valuation practices

Table 2 contains the responses obtained from the Estate Surveyors and Valuers in Calabar. The respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement with statements concerning their awareness of AI in property valuation. The table shows the analyses of the awareness of AI-driven valuation techniques, using weighted mean score.

Table 2: Awareness of estate surveyors and valuers of AI in valuation practices

Variables	Strongly Disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Agree (3)	Strongly Agree (4)	Weighted Mean Rating Value	Mean Ranking
Familiar with the concept of AI	1	3	13	15	3.31	1st
AI-driven valuation benefits	3	4	21	4	2.81	2nd
AI-driven valuation models function differently from traditional valuation methods	2	8	17	5	2.78	3rd
Follow developments in AI-driven valuation technology	4	8	11	9	2.78	3rd
AI techniques identification (ANN, KNN, etc.)	4	8	13	7	2.72	4th
AI-driven valuation techniques' limitation	3	8	17	4	2.69	5th
Received formal training or education on AI application in property valuation.	15	7	4	6	2.03	6th

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 2 reveals that the respondents' general familiarity with AI usage in property valuation is high, with a weighted mean score of 3.31. However, the awareness of the benefits of AI-driven valuation methods (2.81) and their distinction from traditional methods (2.78) remains moderately high. This suggests that while the estate surveyors and valuers recognise the relevance and potential of AI, their understanding of the benefits and how AI valuation techniques differ from conventional valuation approaches is still developing.

In Table 2, some respondents report following developments of AI technology in property valuation (2.78). However, this is further reflected in the respondents' low ability to identify specific AI-valuation techniques (2.72) and the low level of the limitations of AI valuation techniques (2.69). Table 2 also shows that the lowest weighted mean score (2.03) pertains to formal training or education on AI application in property valuation. This indicates a significant

gap, which may explain the respondents' difficulty in identifying AI valuation techniques and less knowledge about AI valuation methods in general.

The findings of this study aligns with the findings of Adewusi and Patunola-Ajayi (2021) and Adewusi and Gbadebo (2023) that there is a lack of awareness and inadequate technical-know how of AI valuation techniques in Lagos, Nigeria. It is not unexpected that there is a low level of awareness of AI-driven valuation techniques in Calabar, as previous studies have reported similar low levels in Lagos. Lagos has a more active and developed real estate market in Nigeria, than Calabar. The results show a wider, national trend of unawareness, pointing to the need for more training and education.

4.3 Adoption of AI Technology in the Valuation Process

Table 3 presents the responses obtained from the Estate Surveyors and Valuers within the study area. The respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement with statements concerning their current practices and future intentions regarding the adoption of AI in property valuation. The Table provides the analyses of the various dimensions of AI adoption using weighted mean score.

Table 3: Estate surveyors and valuers' adoption of AI in property valuation practices

Variables	Strongly Disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Agree (3)	Strongly Agree (4)	Weighted Mean Rating Value	Mean Ranking
Intention to use AI-driven valuation techniques in the next two years	0	1	17	14	3.40	1st
Resources allocation to learn about AI-driven valuation methods.	2	4	10	16	3.25	2nd
Adopted AI tools/software (chatgpt, etc.) for valuation report	4	5	9	14	3.03	3rd
Adoption of AI-driven valuation methods such as KNN and ANN.	18	9	3	2	1.66	4th

Source: Field Survey (2025)

In Table 3, the highest weighted mean rank is the intention to increase the use of AI-driven valuation techniques in the next two years, with a weighted mean score of 3.40. This suggests the future willingness of the Estate Surveyors and Valuers to adopt AI-driven valuation methods such as KNN and ANN in their valuation practice. This is followed by the allocation of resources such as time and money, with a weighted mean score of 3.25. This further reinforces the respondents' readiness to invest in AI skill acquisition. As seen in Table 3, the adoption of AI tools/software such as Chatgpt ranked 3rd, with a weighted mean score of 3.03. The result indicates that some of the respondents have already begun exploring some AI applications in their valuation practices.

Table 3 also shows the lowest ranked as the adoption of AI-driven valuation methods such as KNN and ANN for valuation, with a weighted mean score of 1.66. The results support the findings revealed on the awareness of AI technology in valuation process, where the respondents cannot identify several AI-driven techniques such as ANN. This low weighted

mean score reveals a critical gap; that is, while many respondents may be open to AI in general, they lack the technical exposure or practical experience needed with machine and deep learning valuation techniques. The findings align with the findings of Adejumo et al. (2024) that the adoption of AI valuation model is low in Lagos.

The results show that there is a clear disparity between the intention and actual adoption. The lack of adoption of AI methods such as ANN and KNN reflects the earlier awareness (see Table 2), confirming that the Estate Surveyors and Valuers cannot adopt what they do not understand or recognise. This affirms the argument that improving technical training, exposure, and firm-level integration are important for the successful adoption of AI-driven valuation methods.

4.4 Factors Influencing the Adoption of AI in Property Valuation

This section describes the factors influencing the adoption of AI in property valuation as shown in Table 4, 5, 6, 7, and figure 1. Table 4 presents the KMO and Bartlett’s test of the factors influencing the adoption of AI in property valuation.

Table 4: KMO and Bartlett’s test of factors influencing the adoption of AI in property valuation

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.680
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	577.863
	Df	120
	Sig.	.000

Field Survey (2025)

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy and Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity were conducted to determine the suitability of the data for factor analysis in examining the factors influencing the adoption of AI in property valuation. The KMO value of 0.680 indicates a moderate level of sampling adequacy, suggesting that the variables share enough common variance to justify factor analysis. Additionally, Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity produced a Chi-Square value of 577.863 (df = 120, p = .000), which is highly significant and confirms that the correlation matrix is not an identity matrix. The appropriateness of using factor analysis to explore the underlying constructs affecting AI adoption in the Nigerian property valuation sector was considered adequate. Table 5 shows the communalities of the factors influencing the adoption of AI in property valuation.

Table 5: Communalities of factors influencing the adoption of AI in property valuation

Factors	Initial	Extraction
Cost of implementing and maintaining AI technologies	1.000	.887
Technical knowledge and expertise requirements	1.000	.822
Reliability and accuracy of AI-generated valuations	1.000	.724
Access to quality data for AI model development	1.000	.929
Regulatory framework and compliance requirements	1.000	.923
Client acceptance of AI-generated valuations	1.000	.898
Time required to learn and master AI technologies	1.000	.867
Compatibility with existing valuation systems and processes	1.000	.696
Need for updated professional valuation standards	1.000	.905

Availability of AI and data science training in valuation education	1.000	.883
Availability of collaboration opportunities between valuers and data scientists	1.000	.834
Current readiness of Nigerian property market for AI adoption	1.000	.915
Potential for AI to create new professional opportunities vs. eliminate jobs	1.000	.827
Need for human oversight and supervision in AI valuation processes	1.000	.816
Shift in professional focus from manual valuation to interpreting AI outputs	1.000	.923
Availability of locally-specific AI models for the Nigerian property market	1.000	.737

Field Survey (2025)

From Table 5, the communalities of the factors were assumed to be 1.000 before extraction. However, after the extraction, the communalities show the shared variance within the data structure. The highest level of common communalities is the access to quality data for AI model development (.929), while the lowest level of common communalities is Compatibility with existing valuation systems and processes (.696) after the extraction. The sixteen (16) variables had their communality values greater than 0.5. Therefore, all the variable were retained and were all considered fit for factor analysis. Table 6 shows the total variance explained of factors influencing the adoption of AI in property valuation.

Table 6: Total variance explained of factors influencing the adoption of AI in property valuation

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	7.805	48.779	48.779	7.805	48.779	48.779	5.278	32.989	32.989
2	2.798	17.489	66.269	2.798	17.489	66.269	2.848	17.800	50.789
3	1.922	12.012	78.281	1.922	12.012	78.281	2.770	17.311	68.100
4	1.061	6.630	84.911	1.061	6.630	84.911	2.690	16.811	84.911
5	.722	4.510	89.421						
6	.516	3.227	92.648						
7	.327	2.043	94.691						
8	.266	1.665	96.355						
9	.171	1.072	97.427						
10	.134	.836	98.263						
11	.092	.573	98.836						
12	.076	.476	99.312						
13	.045	.284	99.596						

14	.034	.215	99.811						
15	.018	.115	99.927						
16	.012	.073	100.00 0						

Source: Field Survey (2025)

The extraction method of factor analysis used in this study was the Principal Component Analysis. Before extraction, sixteen linear items were identified within the dataset. After the extraction and rotation, there are four distinct linear components within the dataset for the eigenvalue > 1 . From the analysis in Table VI, four (4) groups of influencing factors (components) explained a total of 84.911% of the variance. Therefore, four components were identified. The components had Initial Eigen Values of 48.779%, 17.489%, 12.012%, and 6.630% respectively before rotation. After rotation, the four factors i.e., components 1, 2, 3, and 4 explained 32.989%, 17.800%, 17.311, and 16.811% of the total variance respectively. This shows that four major components explain the factors influencing the adoption of AI in property valuation in the study area.

Further screening was carried out using the scree plot to check the important components to retain. The plot is suitable when an elbow shape is formed and the points on the upper elbow are considered the important components. Figure 1 shows a clear steep at the fifth factor, indicating that the first four factors explained the majority of the variance in the data. Therefore, the four components earlier considered were retained as additional factors did not significantly improve the explanation of variance.

Fig 1: Scree plot showing the relationship between the factors and their eigenvalues

Table 7 shows the rotated component matrix using principal component analysis and varimax rotation revealed four distinct components that represent underlying dimensions influencing the adoption of AI in property valuation in the study area.

Table 7: Rotated component matrix of factors influencing the adoption of AI in property valuation

Variables	Component			
	1	2	3	4
<i>Operational and Implementation Factors</i>				
Cost of implementing and maintaining AI technologies	.925			
Regulatory framework and compliance requirements	.922			
Potential for AI to create new professional opportunities vs. eliminate jobs	.877			
Client acceptance of AI-generated valuations	.872			
Need for human oversight and supervision in AI valuation processes	.767			
Reliability and accuracy of AI-generated valuations	.580			
Compatibility with existing valuation systems and processes	.517			
<i>Market and Professional Adaptability Factors</i>				
Shift in professional focus from manual valuation to interpreting AI outputs		.910		
Current readiness of Nigerian property market for AI adoption		.898		
Availability of locally-specific AI models for the Nigerian property market		.527		
<i>Capacity Building and Professional Standards Factors</i>				
Need for updated professional valuation standards			.938	
Availability of AI and data science training in valuation education			.930	
Technical knowledge and expertise requirements			.720	
<i>Resource Accessibility and Collaborative Capacity Factors</i>				
Availability of collaboration opportunities between valuers and data scientists				.889
Access to quality data for AI model development				.819
Time required to learn and master AI technologies				.704

Source: Field Survey (2025)

The first component, labelled Operational and Implementation Factors, had strong loadings from variables such as the cost of implementing and maintaining AI technologies (.925), regulatory compliance (.922), and client acceptance of AI (.872), indicating that practical, regulatory, and operational concerns form a major dimension. The second component, Market and Professional Adaptability Factors, clustered around variables like the shift in professional focus from manual valuation to interpreting AI outputs (.910) and the current readiness of the Nigerian property market (.898), reflecting the sector’s capacity to transition. The third component, Capacity Building and Professional Standards, was defined by high loadings from variables such as the need for updated valuation standards (.938) and the availability of AI training (.930), underscoring the importance of education and institutional support. Lastly, the fourth component, Resource Accessibility and Collaborative Capacity, included collaboration opportunities with data scientists (.889) and access to quality data (.819), highlighting the enabling infrastructure required for effective AI integration. The clean separation of variables across the four components and the high factor loadings confirms a coherent and interpretable factor structure that aligns well with both theoretical expectations and the Nigerian valuation context. Overall, from Table 7, it shows that operational and implementation, with a total variance of 48.779% is the most important factor influencing the adoption of AI in property valuation.

4.5 Perception of the Impact of AI-driven Valuation Methods on Property Valuation Practices

This section shows the examination of the perception of the impact of AI-driven valuation methods on property valuation practices. Table 8 contains the data obtained from the Estate Surveyors and Valuers in the study area.

Table 8: Perception of estate surveyors and valuers of the impact of AI-driven valuation techniques

Perception	Strongly Disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Agree (3)	Strongly Agree (4)	Weighted Mean Rating Value	Mean Ranking
Replace Human Valuers	3	3	9	17	3.25	1st
Accuracy	2	3	16	11	3.13	2nd
Cost-effectiveness	1	5	18	8	3.03	3rd
Property valuers will become obsolete	2	4	17	9	3.03	3rd
AI needs Human Judgement	1	8	12	11	3.03	3rd
Enhancement	2	4	19	7	2.97	4th
Time-saving	2	2	24	4	2.93	5th
AI does not understand local market	7	5	11	9	2.69	6th
Clients’ preference for AI-driven valuation techniques	9	11	7	5	2.25	7th

Source: Field Survey (2025)

From Table 8, replace human valuers, accuracy, cost-effectiveness, property valuers will become obsolete, AI needs human judgment, enhancement, time-saving, and AI does not understand local market have fairly high weighted mean scores of 3.25, 3.13, 3.03, 3.03, 3.03, 2.97, 2.93, and 2.69 respectively. Clients' preference for AI-driven valuation techniques has a fairly low weighted mean score of 2.25.

From the Table, the highest weighted mean score (3.25) is that AI could replace human valuers, indicating that respondents perceive that AI is a potential threat to the property valuation profession. The result aligns with the study of Abidoye et al. (2021) that many valuers in Australia anticipate that AI will replace human valuers in the future. The findings reveal that despite the contrast in technology advancement in both countries, there is a significant concern about AI's possible threat. This reflects a shared global concern within the property valuation profession. As seen in Table 8, the perception of AI's accuracy (weighted mean score of 3.13) and cost-effectiveness (weighted mean score of 3.03) further affirms the notion that AI driven valuation methods are more superior to the traditional methods of valuation. Abidoye et al. (2021) also noted that cost reduction and enhanced accuracy were among the most significant perceived benefits of AI valuation methods. Similarly, Topraklı (2024) opined that AI valuation methods outperform traditional methods.

Table 8 also shows that respondents still acknowledge the continued relevance of human expertise. For example, property valuers will become obsolete and AI needs human judgment have received the same weighted mean score of 3.03 and 3.03. This shows that valuers acknowledge the risk of obsolescence if valuers do not adapt to AI and the need for human judgement in valuation. Furthermore, the perception that AI will enhance rather than replace valuers (weighted mean score of 2.97) and that it is time-saving (weighted mean score of 2.93) points to a more collaborative view of AI valuation methods. This is in line with Wilkinson et al. (2018) that valuers should regard AI as a strategic partner rather than a threat to their profession. Table 8 also reveals that clients' preference for AI-driven valuation methods scored the lowest, with a weighted mean score of 2.25. This suggests that there are limited client-targeted AI valuation methods or tools in the Nigerian context. In contrast, Ota and Uto (2024) reported that there are over 20 AI-powered property valuation platforms available to clients in Japan. The finding reveal a gap in technological adoption and accessibility in both markets. The results shows a dual perception as the respondents recognise the benefits of AI-driven valuation methods as well as the threats.

5. Conclusion

Technology continues to transform the Nigerian valuation profession, albeit at a slower pace than developed countries. Among these emerging technologies is Artificial Intelligence (AI), which is gradually reshaping traditional valuation methods through its increasing application in the valuation process. However, the awareness, adoption, and perception of AI in property valuation remain significantly under-researched in Nigeria.

The study found that the level of adoption among property valuers is low, with operational and implementation factors emerging as the major factor influencing adoption. Furthermore, there is a high perception that AI could replace property valuers. As such, property valuers stand at a crossroad of embracing the potential benefits of AI, while addressing its risks and challenges.

The results of this study hold important theoretical and practical implications for the property valuation profession in an era that is being shaped by AI. The findings can inform training initiatives, professional development workshops, and policy interventions aimed at enhancing the integration of AI technologies in the valuation process. By addressing these gaps, firms and professionals can improve efficiency, accuracy, and client service in property valuation. The research contributes to the academic understanding of AI adoption in property valuation within emerging economies. It reveals the gap between awareness and practical implementation, adding empirical evidence to the literature on technology adoption in professional services.

The study recommends that the Nigerian Institution of Estate Surveyors and Valuers (NIESV) advocate for revised valuation standards and promote technology literacy among professionals, ensuring that professionals can integrate AI tools effectively in carrying out their valuation tasks. Academic institutions are also encouraged to include technologies such as AI into real estate curricula.

This study is limited by its small and localised sample size which limits the generalizability of the results to other cities in Nigeria. Further research should explore other Nigerian cities and explore cross-country comparisons and incorporate client perspectives to provide a more holistic understanding of AI adoption in property valuation.

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Disclosure Statement

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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**Peer Reviewed*

A Systematic Review of Blockchain Technology Applications in Land Administration Systems *Opeyemi Ajayi¹, Riekkinen Kirsikka², and Oluwafemi Adekola³*

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Abstract

Land Administration Systems (LAS) reform is a global concern because land remains a critical resource for economic development, social justice, and political stability, and inefficiencies in land governance contribute to disputes, insecurity, and inequitable access worldwide. However, the advent of Blockchain technology (BT) has been heralded as an innovative tool for transforming LAS. BT application in LAS is considered a tool for tackling problems like organisational inefficiencies, fraudulent records, and lack of transparency. Despite its potential, there are limited studies on the developments and applications of BT in LAS. Therefore, this study presents a systematic review of current literature by examining the nature, extent, and impact of BT application in LAS. The study adopted a systematic literature review (SLR) approach, employing a structured search strategy within the Scopus database. This process involved defining keywords, applying inclusion and exclusion criteria, screening abstracts, and reviewing full texts, which ultimately recovered 15 publications eligible for further analysis. The findings revealed that BT-LAS publications are predominantly focused on three (3) key areas: (i) security and transparency, (ii) integration and system design, and (iii) adoption frameworks and challenges. The decentralised and immutable structure of BT increases trust, reorganises transactions, safeguards records, and computerised land processes in LAS. It also helps to optimise geospatial data and promotes equitable access to land. Despite the potential of BT to reform LAS, numerous hurdles hamper its implementation, such as legal recognition, data stabilisation, technological scalability, and stakeholder engagement. To tackle these challenges, a cross-disciplinary partnership among land stakeholders, policymakers, and technologists is required to ensure secure, transparent, and efficient governance systems. Overall, the review emphasised the necessity for additional research into advanced security instruments, regulatory structures, and scalable technical solutions to accomplish the potential of BT in land administration and governance matters globally.

Keywords: Blockchain Technology; Distributed Ledger Technology; Land Administration; Distributed Systems; Regulatory frameworks.

1. Introduction

Land administration systems (LAS) act as the fundamental basis for the organisation and management of land ownership rights, records, and transactions (Rupasinghe, 2021). LAS thus help to safeguard the security and transparency of land and property contracts across the globe (Rodima-Taylor 2021). Nonetheless, conventional LAS are prone to numerous challenges well-documented in the literature. For example, long-established LAS are prone to administrative incompetencies, fraud vulnerabilities, and poor interoperability (Rodima-Taylor, 2021; Jeram, 2024). Such constraints typically result in inadequacies in the registration of lands, delays in

resolving disputes, and limited ease of access to records on lands (Mintah et al., 2007; Hossain 2015).

Furthermore, the conventional LAS relies on centralised databases and paper-based documentation (Amadi-Echendu, 2017; Ahsan et al., 2025). However, they are susceptible to data manipulation, loss, and unauthorised alterations, leading to delays, increased costs, and ownership disputes (Lemmen, 2012; Shang and Price, 2019; Baligira, 2020). Therefore, there have been growing calls for more advanced strategies that enhance the inclusivity, trustworthiness, and efficiency of LAS worldwide (Morales et al., 2021; Chehrehbargh et al., 2024). Hence, to address these problems, blockchain technology (BT), although originally developed for some other purpose (e.g., Bitcoin), has since attracted significant interest across a range of fields beyond its initial application. BT provides an immutable, decentralised, and transparent structure, which could be successfully applied to the administration and governance of land-related matters globally (Zein & Twinomurinzi, 2024).

Moreover, the incorporation of BT into LAS is an innovative approach that utilises the decentralised and distributed features of blockchain to guarantee the security and transparency of land records and transactions (Ameyaw and de Vries, 2020; Bennett et al., 2021). Furthermore, smart contracts known to be self-executing arrangements on BT could be utilised to restructure land-based procedures by excluding administrative barriers and lowering human mistakes (Frazier 2018; Comincioli, and Governance 2021). Moreover, BT can help to improve records legitimacy, data safety, and organisational procedures thereby fostering trust among stakeholders in the sector (Abdullah et al., 2020; Keneth, 2024). Given these benefits, nations such as India and Ghana have been exploring BT-based land administration, registration and management (Ameyaw and de Vries, 2020; Comincioli and Governance, 2021), which demonstrates the need for enhanced integrity and accessibility of data on land matters.

The review of literature shows that BT could potentially impact LAS through enhanced efficiency, transparency, and security. However, the extensive implementation faces numerous problems, such as the lapses in legal and regulatory frameworks, infrastructural constraints, and scalability worries. Therefore, this review aims to identify and examine the most recent developments in BT applications in LAS across the globe by examining the nature, extent, and impact of these applications. Although, there is a little effort in exploring BT in LAS through a review. For instance, Ameyaw and de Vries, 2020 reviewed the role of BT in land administration. However, the paper is limited to the concept of transparency in BT applications in LAS and limited in scope to developments in Ghana. Hence, the current review presents a global perspective on recent developments in BT-LAS. It also identifies research trends and synthesises insights that may assist land administration stakeholders, policymakers, researchers, and technologists in developing more secure and efficient LAS.

The roadmap of the remaining part of the study is as follows: Section 2 discusses the research methodology adopted in this study. Section 3 presents the results and provides detailed discussion of the results. Section 4 provides future research directions. Finally, Section 5 summarises the conclusions drawn from this review study.

2. Research Methodology

This study adopts a systematic literature review (SLR) to identify and examine the most recent developments in BT applications in LAS across the globe. SLR is a research methodology that provides replicable and verifiable procedures for identifying, evaluating, and interpreting relevant studies pertinent to a specific research question (Pollock and Berge, 2018; Xiao and Watson, 2019; Adade and de Vries, 2024). According to Ansah et al. (2023), SLR is widely employed across various disciplines to deepen and broaden the understanding of specific subject areas. To ensure precision, quality, transparency and reproducibility, this study follows the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines. The PRISMA framework consists of four main phases: identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion, as presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Methodological Flowchart

Source: Source: Authors Construct (2025)

2.1 Identification, Screening, Eligibility and Inclusion Phases

The identification phase of the SLR involved a comprehensive literature search to develop a core database of relevant publications. This search was conducted using the Scopus database, recognised for its stringent indexing standards and robust citation tracking, which ensures a reliable collection of peer-reviewed literature (Schotten et al., 2017). Scopus was selected due to its broad coverage across multiple disciplines and its ability to provide a comprehensive overview of the research landscape, which was essential for this study. It has also been employed in previous systematic reviews on blockchain adoption in LAS (Ameyaw and de Vries, 2020; Ansah et al., 2023). Subsequently, the keywords string and search criteria were developed using Boolean operators as follows: TITLE-ABS-KEY (((("Land administration*" OR "Land administration system*") AND ("blockchain" OR "blockchain technology" OR "Distributed ledger*")))). The keywords were selected based on an initial review of prior studies and key articles (e.g., Ameyaw and de Vries, 2020; Saari et al, 2022; Ansah et al., 2023). The search was conducted between April and May 2025, resulting in the retrieval of 50 publications as of 15 May 2025.

In the *Screening Phase*, a total of 50 articles were reviewed based on their titles and abstracts, as shown in Figure 1. The retrieved studies were screened in accordance with the best practices outlined by Collins et al. (2021), ensuring the selection of high-quality and relevant literature that supports the research aim. Articles were included if they met the following criteria: (a) articles focused on BT and LAS; (b) peer-reviewed articles; (c) articles written in English language; and (d) employed clear and defined research methodologies while providing valuable insights into recent developments in BT applications in LAS across the globe. Articles were excluded if they met any of the following conditions: (a) articles not focused on BT and LAS or not aligned with the research aim; (b) non-peer-reviewed articles; (c) articles not written in English language; and (d) employed unclear or undefined research methodologies, such as unvalidated data sources or limited methodological rigor. Based on these criteria, 29 articles were removed as they did not address the research aim, leaving 21 articles for detailed analysis.

In the *Eligibility Phase*, the remaining 21 articles were considered for the full-text review. Following the full-text review, six additional 6 articles were excluded, resulting in a final set of 15 relevant publications from 2016 to 2024 for the final review. These comprised 40% conference papers, 33.33% journal articles, 13.33% book chapters, 6.67% review papers, and 6.67% short surveys (see Figure 2). The final set of 15 eligible articles was analysed using a thematic analysis approach, which ensured that the themes identified in the review were systematically derived rather than arbitrarily assumed, aligning with best practices for conducting systematic literature reviews (Xiao and Watson, 2019). An inductive coding process was conducted, in which each paper was examined for its core contributions to blockchain applications in LAS. First-order codes were developed based on recurring concepts (e.g., "smart contracts," "secure registries," "integration models," "geospatial blockchain," "adoption barriers"). These codes were then grouped into three higher-order analytical categories directly aligned with the stated review aim: (i) nature of application (what blockchain is used for), (ii) extent of application (how widely adopted), and (iii) impact of application (what outcomes or

improvements were reported). This iterative coding process was conducted by two reviewers, and disagreements were resolved through discussion until consensus was reached.

Figure 2: Publication Types
Source: Authors Construct (2025)

2.2 Mapping of Reviewed Publications to Key Themes

In order to identify and generate the key themes, a thematic analysis approach was employed. Hence, in line with the guideline of following the guidelines of Braun and Clarke (2006). This involved: (i) familiarisation with the data through repeated reading of the 15 selected publications, (ii) coding key concepts related to BT applications in LAS, (iii) grouping codes into potential themes based on patterns, and (iv) refining themes to ensure they align with the research aim (nature, extent, and impact of BT applications). The thematic analysis resulted in three key themes: (i) security and transparency, (ii) integration and system design, and (iii) adoption frameworks and challenges. Table 1 maps the reviewed publications to these themes, enhancing the transparency of the analysis.

Table 1: Mapping of Reviewed Publications to Key Themes

Publication	1	2	3
Ameyaw and de Vries (2020)	X		X
Bennett et al. (2019)			X
Bennett et al. (2021)	X	X	X
Beznosov et al. (2021)	X		
Biswas et al. (2022)		X	
Tahar et al. (2022)	X	X	
Niloy et al. (2022)		X	
Shukla et al. (2024)	X	X	
Ahmad (2024)	X	X	
Ansah et al. (2023)			X

Comincioli and Governance (2021)	X		X
Frazier (2018)	X		
Saari et al. (2022)	X		X
Pichel (2016)		X	
Krigsholm et al. (2019)	X		X

1 = Security and Transparency; 2 = Integration and System Design; & 3 = Adoption Frameworks and Challenges
Source: Authors Construct (2025)

3. Discussion of Results

This section presents the findings from the reviewed literature on blockchain technology in land administration systems (BT-LAS) and discusses their implications. The analysis of the published documents retrieved from the Scopus database shows that the research landscape on BT-LAS has largely evolved under three (3) key themes, namely: (i) security and transparency, (ii) integration and system design, and (iii) adoption frameworks and challenges. These themes form the crux of the review of developments in the field, as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Key Themes on BT-LAS

Source: Authors construct (2025)

3.1 Security and Transparency

Land is typically described as a scarce resource with socio-economic value, due to its influence on housing, incomes, and food production (Nyanga et al., 2016). Land ownership has substantial historical, socio-cultural, and sentimental implications for families and societies worldwide (Mbonea and Msoka, 2024; Naguib, 2024). However, current systems for administering and managing land titles face numerous challenges. Examples of such problems include corruption, fraud, poor digitalisation, ownership disagreements, lengthy procedures, and inadequate availability (Comincioli and Governance, 2021). However, BT is regarded as a panacea to the outlined problems due to its ability to enhance transparency, security, and efficiency in land administration practices, processes, and management (Ameyaw and de Vries, 2021; Rashid et al., 2025).

Over the years, many researchers have explored the impact of BT on lowering incidences of fraud, as well as addressing land disputes and stopping fraudulent practices. BT provides a distributed ledger for land transaction records that is tamper-proof and capable of reducing illegal changes, illegitimate land grabbing, and administrative inefficiencies (Njoroge, 2019; Ooi et al., 2022). For example, Ameyaw and de Vries (2020) investigated the role of BT in improving transparency in the LAS of Ghana. The study revealed that BT ensured stakeholder accessibility and participation in the LAS. The findings highlight the potential of BT to transform LAS by reducing corruption and fraud whilst safeguarding stakeholders' trust and enhancing efficiency (Ameyaw and de Vries, 2020).

Similarly, Beznosov et al. (2021) reported that the security and transparency of BT in LAS have the potential to enhance economic efficiency. In another study, Tahar et al. (2022) proposed and examined the impact of multi-signature authentication (MSA) implemented on a BT-LAS. The findings showed that the MSA ensures the security of land rights and enhances transparency in LA. Furthermore, it was reported that the MSA reinforces the security of LAS, so that publicly available and confirmable records on land transactions can be considered transparent and trustworthy (Tahar et al., 2022).

BT has also been used to implement smart contracts and automate land-based transactions (Frazier, 2018; Comincioli and Governance, 2021). This approach ensures that such land dealings and practices are streamlined to organisational procedures and conform with legal frameworks (Frazier, 2018; Comincioli and Governance, 2021). However, the successful execution of BT-LAS requires overwhelming challenges such as data normalisation, legal identification, and technical infrastructure (Krigsholm et al., 2019; Ameyaw and de Vries, 2021).

3.2 Integration and System Design

Traditional LAS are prone to several challenges due to their manual, outdated, and non-IT-compliant nature, among others (Amadi-Echendu, 2017). Hence, such systems need to be modernised and upgraded by incorporating advanced computational tools such as BT, geographic information systems (GIS), artificial intelligence (AI), cloud computing, and digital twin models. For instance, Pichel (2016) that BT can be integrated in LAS to offer better security, efficiency, and transparency. Furthermore, BT can considerably impact the system design and integration of LAS, which could greatly help in managing records and transactions on land across the globe. Additionally, researchers have investigated the influence of developing hack-proof registries, automated procedures, and efficient systems to ensure trust between stakeholders (Krigsholm et al., 2019; Ameyaw and de Vries, 2021). Such research has also examined the technological aspects of BT amalgamation, system architecture, and process optimisation for the administration and management of land.

Notably, one of the earliest studies on the integration of BT in LAS was published by Pichel (2016). The study revealed that BT has the potential to be integrated into LAS, which could curb fraudulent practices as well as unlawful adjustments in such systems. Moreover, the study highlighted the value of decentralisation in developing highly efficient systems for land administration and governance. The study paved the way for additional work on the application

and structuring of BT in LAS. In a separate study, the proof of concept for integrating BT in LAS was proposed by Tahar et al. (2022). The authors demonstrated that BT could be integrated into the Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) as part of the ISO 19152:2012. The study showed that the BT-based LADM complies with standards obtainable internationally. Overall, it was concluded that BT-based system designs and integration in LAS improve accessibility and integrity of data. As a result, stakeholders are reassured that land records are resilient to mismanagement, fraud, and unauthorised alterations, thereby promoting interoperability amongst several institutions responsible for LAS.

Furthermore, Niloy et al. (2022) developed the lightweight BT-LAS termed LANDCHAIN for application in Bangladesh. The objective was to develop an automated and scalable BT-based program for integration into LAS in the country. The study demonstrated that the system was able to modernise procedures for the registration and administration of land, at the same time as maintaining efficient security and management of land records. Similarly, Biswas et al. (2021) developed and examined the Digital Record Keeping in LAS termed (DRLAS). This BT-based system demonstrated the application and potential of BT for digitally keeping land records. It was observed that the DRLAS was successfully integrated and utilised to enhance data reliability, eradicate manual faults, and avert unlawful alterations.

Over the years, studies have also shown the transformative potential of BT in systems for land registration, predominantly in ownership verification and fraud prevention. According to Shukla et al. (2024), BT has transformed LAS by promoting automated transactions, smart contracts, and legal framework compliance in the sector. Overall, the study showed that it could help create a secure, trustworthy, and transparent ecosystem for LAS. Likewise, Ahmad (2024) proposed the use of BT-based geospatial technology for ensuring the security of data for land mapping as well as eliminating disputes on land boundaries. The study conducted in Pakistan shows that LAS problems are not only global but also provide opportunities to develop robust, scalable, and transmutable technologies and tools to ensure proper documentation, conflict resolution, and security of land tenure.

Overall, the review of studies shows BT-based systems for LAS can enhance security, transparency, and efficiency, but future challenges include legal recognition, technological infrastructure, and data standardisation.

3.3 Adoption Frameworks and Challenges

The potential and application of BT integration in LAS have been widely researched and published in the literature. Likewise, studies that have been conducted explore the influential success factors, acceptance obstacles, and general impact of BT in LA. Over the years, several studies have provided critical understanding of the application of BT in LAS.

Notably, the work of Bennett et al. (2019) investigated the universal influence of blockchain and other rising digital technologies such as big data and NoSQL-based analytics on LA. The study observed that the adoption of such tools is hampered by numerous technological and policy-related challenges. These challenges include poor technical expertise, project funding, and organisational inertia, among others. In another study, Saari et al. (2022) observed that BT application in the sector reduced transactional disagreements using its developed security

measures. As such, BT was adjudged an important tool for developing effective property records, which in turn helps to reduce illegal assertions regarding land ownership.

Furthermore, another critical area in the research landscape has been the adoption of various frameworks for BT in LA in a bid to address lingering issues in the sector. Bennett et al. (2021) examined various hybrid methodologies for developing and applying smart contracts in LAS. Furthermore, the study highlighted the importance of balancing BT-based automation with established legal formations for effective implementation in conventional models for land administration and governance. In line with this, Ameyaw and de Vries (2023) highlighted the impact of social and cultural influences in executing BT-based LA services. In addition, the authors emphasised that successful implementation requires both technological readiness and community engagement.

Conclusively, the adoption and implementation of BT in LA is prone to several challenges such as scalability and regulatory uncertainty (Bennett et al., 2019), interoperability and legal uncertainties (Saari et al., 2022), varying institutional structures (Bennett et al., 2021), high implementation costs, and specialised technical expertise (Ansah et al., 2023). Overall, the review of literature showed that the enhanced transparency, security, and efficiency of BT are critical to addressing the current challenges (e.g., regulatory uncertainty, technological limitations, and institutional resistance) in LAS.

4. Future Research Directions

Notwithstanding the rising body of knowledge on BT applications in LAS, many research gaps exist in the literature that necessitate further studies. The most notable gap in the research on BT-LAS is the absence of studies on the regulatory and legal frameworks on the topic. Although BT has been reported to enhance security and transparency, its lawful acknowledgement in many jurisdictions remains undefined. Therefore, future studies need to focus on creating in-depth policy bases to ease the incorporation of BT into current models for land administration and governance. Moreover, the lack of infrastructure and scalability of technology is another key obstacle that needs to be addressed. Although previous research has highlighted the potential of BT to revolutionise land record keeping, there are still apprehensions concerning the interoperability of systems and the standardisation of data. Hence, tackling these challenges will need research into scalable, lightweight, and adjustable solutions, as these will guarantee unified execution across diverse areas.

Furthermore, studies have emphasised the influence of land administration stakeholders' engagement in the adoption of BT-LAS. Nevertheless, numerous socio-cultural obstacles could hamper its successful enactment. Therefore, future studies will need to examine plans and policies that improve users' trust, stakeholders' engagement, and digitised literacy for seamless adoption of such technological systems. There is also a growing need for the creation of innovative security procedures that go beyond the existing smart contracts and multi-signature verification applications. Hence, future research that delves into methods for privacy preservation, quantum-resilient cryptography, and cutting-edge fraud-inhibition devices could additionally reinforce BT-based LAS.

Lastly, although BT-derived geospatial innovations have demonstrated potential in tackling disputes of land boundaries, additional effort is required to polish procedures for geospatial incorporation. Hence, future research ought to concentrate on computerised land dispute resolution, high-resolution mapping and AI-based authentication schemes to balance BT-LAS solutions. In conclusion, we affirm that the research gaps in BT-LAS require cross-disciplinary cooperation among technologists, policymakers, and stakeholders to unleash its full potential for transparent, secure, and efficient systems.

5. Conclusion

The paper presented a systematic literature review of the recent and emerging trends in the application of BT in LAS. The review of literature showed that BT-LAS research has evolved across three (3) key areas, namely: security and transparency, integration and system design, and adoption frameworks and challenges over the years. Further analysis highlighted the potential of BT in improving security, transparency, and efficiency in LAS through its decentralised nature, trust enhancement, record security, transaction automation, and tailored systems. In addition, the review highlighted the transformational influence of BT on LAS, such as decreasing fraud, transforming processes, and advancing stakeholder trust, despite the longstanding issues such as corruption and inefficiencies. However, the successful implementation of BT in LAS requires overcoming challenges such as technological infrastructure, legal recognition, data standardisation, and stakeholder involvement, while future studies need to focus on establishing vigorous supervisory agendas and comprehensive strategies for acceptance. Additionally, collaboration between policymakers, technologists and land stakeholders is fundamental for the successful deployment of BT, which can transform LAS globally using establishing transparent, secure, and efficient governance systems. Despite the progress recorded, BT-LAS faces challenges such as scalability, regulatory frameworks, infrastructure limitations, socio-cultural factors, and security advancements, necessitating ongoing research and strategic implementation for full potential realisation.

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Disclosure Statement

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**Peer Reviewed*

Unlocking Potentials: An Exploratory Factor Analysis of BIM Adoption Drivers in the Nigerian Facility Management Industry *Opeyemi Ajayi¹, Okanlawon Taofeek Tunde²*

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Abstract

In recent times, the facilities management (FM) industry has undergone a substantial transformation. This is due to the fact that it has transitioned from a traditional approach to a more digitalized approach. However, this transformation is largely due to the integration of technological innovations such as Building Information Modelling (BIM) which has emerged as a game changer within the FM industry. Despite its potential, the FM industry has underutilized this innovation for its activities. Based on this, this study examines the drivers for BIM integration in the FM industry, specifically its role in improving efficiency, sustainability, and cost-effectiveness in FM practices. The study adopted a quantitative research approach through a questionnaire survey that was conducted among FM professionals in Nigeria, using the purposive sampling technique. The survey yielded a total of 102 respondents. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA). The study identified improved productivity due to the easy retrieval of information as the highest-ranked driver. Further analysis using EFA categorized the drivers into quality related drivers, consistency related drivers and safety related drivers. The findings of this study will be beneficial to facilities management professionals, practitioners, and stakeholders in the Nigerian facilities management industry, providing insights into the potential of building information modeling and its application in enhancing FM.

Keywords: Building Information Modelling (BIM), Drivers, Digital Technologies, Facility Management, Real-time visualisation, Shapiro Wilk.

1. Introduction

Facility Management (FM) has witnessed significant transformation in recent years (Kamodyová et al., 2020). It has evolved from a maintenance department within organisations to adopt a more comprehensive and strategic approach (Lindberg, 2010). As a result, facility management has become the built environment industry sector with the fastest growth rate (Kamodyová et al., 2020). However, it is worthy to note that cutting-edge technologies have been instrumental in this development (Wong et al., 2018; Li et al., 2019). These technologies include building information modelling, digital twins, artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things, and blockchains technology (Zhan et al., 2023). Although, all these technologies have contributed to the growth and development of FM (Granberg & He, 2018). However, Building Information Modelling (BIM) has emerged as a transformative tool in the field (Pinti et al., 2022). Moreover, it has significantly altered the way stakeholders approach the planning, design, construction, and management of physical assets (Dahanayake & Sumanarathna, 2022). Ashworth (2021) stated that the advent of BIM has enabled the visualisation and integration of FM by constructing an all-inclusive 3D model that encompasses every building aspect including architectural, structural, and mechanical components (Jadhav, 2016). This advanced three-

dimensional model-based process provides stakeholders in the built environment with useful insights and tools needed for the effective planning, design, operation, and management of buildings and infrastructure (Autodesk, 2017).

According to Alizadehsalehi et al. (2020), BIM enables stakeholder cooperation, since it enhances stakeholders' understanding as well as promotes their active participation in a project. In addition to a plethora of related information, BIM offers a precise and comprehensive digital depiction of physical facilities. Furthermore, the integration of BIM in FM, as outlined by Pärn et al. (2017), has been identified as a seven-dimensional (7D) modelling approach. This modelling method is also famous for its ability to distinguish itself from other information systems (Okwe et al. 2023). Hence, several studies have demonstrated that the adoption of BIM can lead to a range of benefits like increased operational efficiency, improved competitiveness, enhanced performance, cost savings, and better maintenance management (Edirisinghe et al., 2017). However, there has been a greater focus on the design and construction phases, in both academic research and real-world applications (Toklu & Mayuk, 2021). Hence, while there is considerable emphasis on improving the performance of existing buildings and facilities, the deployment of BIM is not accorded as much attention during the management and operation stages as it enjoys during the design and construction phases (Krämer and Besenyői, 2018).

Although there is an exhaustive amount of research on the drivers that motivate the adoption of BIM in developed countries (Ghaffarianhoseini et al., 2017). However, only a limited amount of work has been done in this area in developing countries such as Nigeria. Nevertheless, a number of studies have been conducted in Nigeria to investigate the use of BIM in the FM industry. For instance, Ikediashi et al. (2017) found that the implementation of BIM in the FM industry in Nigeria can bring about a reduction in lifecycle costs and an acceleration in the delivery of FM services. Olapade and Ekemode (2018) also found out that the awareness of the BIM among FM stakeholders and its utilisation in the FM industry in Nigeria are low. In a different study, Jambil (2020) examined the readiness of FM professionals to use BIM for high-rise buildings in Nigeria and concluded that FM professionals lacked the preparedness to use BIM in FM practice. Ikediashi (2022) stated that the implementation of BIM in the FM industry in Nigeria faces three significant obstacles: lack of knowledge about BIM for FM; inadequate Internet infrastructure; absence of education and training. Furthermore, Okwe (2023) also discovered that although there is a growing awareness of BIM, its adoption and implementation in the FM industry in Nigeria is yet to be fully embraced.

Despite the growing body of literature examining BIM implementation in Nigeria's FM sector, existing studies have primarily focused on general awareness levels, implementation challenges, and professional readiness. However, there is a paucity of research that specifically investigates the underlying drivers that could enable or accelerate BIM adoption within the Nigerian FM context. Particularly absent are empirically grounded studies that use robust analytical techniques, such as Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), to uncover the latent constructs influencing BIM uptake for enhanced efficiency and resilience. This gap limits a comprehensive understanding of the motivating factors that could inform targeted policy interventions, stakeholder engagement strategies, and tailored capacity-building efforts.

Therefore, this research seeks to address this critical gap by identifying and analyzing the key drivers that can facilitate the broader integration of BIM in Nigeria's FM sector. Furthermore, from a theoretical perspective, this study is underpinned by the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989) and the Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) Theory (Rogers, 2003). TAM explains BIM adoption through constructs such as perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use, while DOI Theory emphasises innovation attributes like relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability, and observability. Applying these frameworks enables a structured understanding of how Nigerian FM professionals' behavioural intentions toward BIM are shaped by both technical performance and contextual readiness. Hence, this study contributes to the body of knowledge in four significant ways: (1) It enriches the theoretical discourse by integrating TAM and DOI Theory into the FM–BIM adoption narrative in a developing-country context; (2) It empirically identifies and categorises latent BIM adoption drivers into quality-related, consistency-related, and safety-related dimensions using EFA, an approach rarely applied in FM research; (3) It generates context-specific evidence from Nigeria's FM sector, addressing a geographical and sectoral research gap and offering insights transferable to other emerging markets; and (4) It provides a prioritised set of adoption drivers to guide policymakers, FM practitioners, and technology providers in designing targeted interventions and capacity-building strategies.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Building Information Modelling and Facilities Management

BIM has significantly impacted facility management (FM) through the provision of a digital strategy for managing building assets, from inception to disposal (Pärn et al., 2017; Mannino et al., 2021). Unlike traditional FM which is often inefficient owing to extended timeframes, lengthy processes, numerous contents, and complex personnel involvement (Xu et al., 2020), BIM technology in FM serves multiple purposes. It fulfils the essential operational needs of users, enhances investment returns, and facilitates information exchange between the design, construction, operations and maintenance phases. This integration results in more accurate information, creates a user-friendly management platform for all stakeholders, and ultimately boosts efficiency (Wang, 2013). Given that FM accounts for 80% of the overall expenditure during a facility's lifespan, BIM offers considerable potential for saving time and resources wasted on inefficient operations during the construction phase (Olapade & Ekemode, 2018).

Furthermore, BIM has been recognised for its capability to optimise operations and encourage collaboration among stakeholders in the FM industry (Salzano et al., 2023). It is deemed a valuable source of information that can support building owners and facility managers in planning and executing maintenance operations for new and existing structures (Volk 2014). By functioning as a comprehensive repository of organised data, BIM enables the creation of an asset information database that can be supplemented by FM stakeholders for operational and maintenance purposes (Aziz et al., 2016; Tsay et al., 2023). Furthermore, it offers real-time visualisation of various aspects of FM (Xu et al., 2020). The capacity of the BIM model to retain data indefinitely permits a comprehensive analysis that supports FM tasks. With BIM technology, FM stakeholders can easily monitor a building's condition, plan maintenance,

manage renovations, and ensure its preservation (Rodrigues et al., 2019). BIM can reduce the frequency of reactive maintenance activities during operations by implementing a proactive maintenance schedule and predicting potential conflicts accurately (Durdyev et al., 2022). This approach strengthens operational efficiency and minimises waste of time and resources during reactive maintenance (Liu & Issa, 2013).

Several studies, such as those conducted by Shalabi and Turkan (2017), Dawood et al. (2017), and Gao and Pishdad-Bozorgi (2018), have demonstrated the potential of BIM in FM. These researchers observed that incorporating BIM into the initial stages of FM can improve operation and maintenance, space management, emergency management, security management, and energy management. Despite these advantages and the increasing interest in BIM applications in FM, the effective use of BIM for these purposes remains something to be established. Although building owners are often considered the primary drivers of BIM implementation (Koch et al., 2019), they require a complete understanding of their information requirements for efficient BIM-driven asset management (Munir et al., 2020). Despite its benefits, BIM is not widely used in the FM phase (Mannino et al., 2021). This is probably due to the limited participation of facility managers in developing BIM models (Wong et al., 2018; Dixit et al., 2019).

2.2 Drivers of Building Information Modelling Integration in Facilities Management

The facility management industry has grappled with mediocre documents and information management, which adversely affect the quality of its services, traditionally (Ajayi, 2022). Due to these challenges, the industry has been slow in adopting Building Information Modeling (BIM) technology (Oluleye et al., 2023). This reluctance has expectably impeded the industry's growth and hindered its ability to keep pace with current trends. Embracing BIM in FM presents numerous advantages, namely enhanced productivity and improved project information management throughout a building's lifecycle (Kovacic & Filmoser, 2015; Singh et al., 2017; Terreno et al., 2018; Hoang et al., 2020). BIM acts as a platform to facilitate communication and information sharing among facility management professionals, thereby fostering collaboration (Alazmeh et al. 2018; Marmo et al., 2019). The Factors that primarily drive BIM adoption are geared towards fostering collaboration among project stakeholders, identifying clashes early, streamlining information requests, enhancing cost estimation and control, improving client satisfaction, refining construction specifications, meeting sustainability standards, and facilitating cost reductions (Rodgers et al. 2015; Alwan et al. 2017).

According to Olanrewaju et al. (2021), the primary drivers of BIM adoption in Nigeria include construction-related, digitalisation process and economics-related, sustainability- and efficiency-related, and visualisation- and productivity-related drivers. Other significant drivers include energy management, timely detection of inaccuracies, effective defect tracking and space management (Ghaffarianhoseini et al. 2017; Alvanchi and Seyrfar 2020). Moreover, the ability of BIM to streamline FM operations, reduce waste and expenses, improve efficiency, enhance the quality of facilities, ensure sustainability, increase productivity, optimise service delivery, cash flow, and profitability, and boost overall organisational performance summarises the primary drivers for integrating BIM into FM (Naghshbandi, 2016; Aziz et al., 2016;

Babatunde et al., 2018). As Becerik-Gerber et al. (2011) suggested, space management, emergency management, energy control and monitoring, and the simple identification of building components could also be considered as BIM drivers for FM. Similarly, according to Gerrish et al. (2017) and Minoli et al. (2017), BIM has the potential to function as a real-time assessment and forecasting tool for energy performance. Hence, by utilising monitoring and simulations, this approach enables the identification of discrepancies between actual data and expected results. Cavka et al. (2017) identified three crucial elements that play a significant role in driving the adoption of BIM: the facility management record model, increased efficiency and coordination, and enhanced quality and sustainability. However, Table 1 compiles several drivers confirmed by academics, scholars, and researchers to encourage and hasten BIM adoption as a cutting-edge technology in the FM industry.

Code	DRIVERS	Description	Reference
DR1	Improved productivity due to easy retrieval of information	BIM improves productivity while concurrently simplifying the management of information regarding facilities from their inception to their eventual decommissioning.	Kovacic & Filmoser, (2015), Singh et al., (2017), Terreno et al., (2018), Hoang et al., (2020)
DR2	Reduction in both costs and risks	BIM streamlines costs and risks, thereby enabling facility managers to promptly identify and rectify cost overruns and prevent financial constraints.	Naghshbandi, (2016), Aziz et al., (2016), Babatunde et al., (2018), Olanrewaju et al. (2021)
DR3	Communication improvement and harmonisation	BIM promotes a cooperative approach to FM by offering a platform for all relevant parties to access and exchange information throughout the life cycle of a facility.	Marmo et al., (2019), Alazmeh et al. (2018)
DR4	Visualisation and sharing of information	BIM offers a comprehensive understanding of facilities' design, enabling the identification of maintenance or repair measures. It also facilitates the visualisation of equipment locations, leading to an efficient process for obtaining relevant data and saving time.	Rodgers et al. (2015), Olanrewaju et al. (2021), Ghaffarianhoseini et al (2017)
DR5	Timely detection of inaccuracies	BIM enables facilities managers to keep track of the status of facilities and identify possible issues early on, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of maintenance operations.	Rodgers et al. (2015), Gerrish et al. (2017), Minoli et al. (2017)
DR6	Reduction of rework	BIM can improve FM efficiency by reducing errors, rework, and waste, while providing accurate and current information on the facility's status and needs. This information can help facility managers to plan and execute preventive and corrective maintenance tasks.	Naghshbandi, (2016), Aziz et al., (2016), Babatunde et al., (2018)
DR7	The ability to build and manage assets in a more efficient, cost-effective, and environmentally friendly manner	BIM serves a vital function in the analysis of buildings, with a particular emphasis on sustainability efforts that aim to minimise environmental impacts and operational costs.	Naghshbandi, (2016), Aziz et al., (2016), Babatunde et al., (2018), Olanrewaju et

			al. (2021), Cavka et al. (2017); Alwan et al (2017)
DR8	Quality Enhancement	BIM enables early error detection, improved coordination, data-driven decision-making, and streamlined processes during the building lifecycle.	Cavka et al. (2017), Olanrewaju et al. (2021)
DR9	Improvements in data value and dependability are expected to result in enhanced labour efficiency	BIM facilitates effective data management and streamlines operational procedures, leading to improved decision-making processes in FM and enhancing labour efficiency.	Becerik-Gerber et al. (2011), Olanrewaju et al. (2021)
DR10	Energy analysis and control	BIM aids in gathering and analysing data on energy use to optimise energy efficiency, leading to increased energy savings. It also allows for a comparison of various factors and critical indicators related to energy consumption.	Becerik-Gerber et al. (2011), Gerrish et al. (2017), Minoli et al. (2017), Alvanchi & Seyrfar, (2020)
DR11	Safety/emergency management	BIM plays a vital role in obtaining essential data that improves the efficacy of emergency response measures and reduces the risks associated with them.	Becerik-Gerber et al. (2011), Ghaffarianhoseini et al (2017)

Source: Authors Construct (2025)

3. Research Methodology

This study employed a quantitative methodology using a questionnaire survey to assess the critical drivers of BIM adoption in the Nigerian facilities management industry. Quantitative research methods encompass the gathering and examination of numerical data to address research inquiries or validate hypotheses (Yousefi Nooraie et al., 2020). Moreover, using quantitative research makes gathering unbiased data, which is then presented in a precise and statistical format, possible (Fox et al., 2022). This technique helps to improve our comprehension of the difficulties associated with the key drivers of BIM adoption in the Nigerian Facilities Management Industry. The key drivers of BIM adoption in the Nigerian Facilities Management Industry were obtained through an extensive review of related literature, and these drivers were prepared in a closed-ended questionnaire to collect information from respondents within Nigeria. Nonetheless, to test the scale's reliability and the questionnaire's internal consistency, Cronbach's alpha was used. It yielded a value of 0.880, which is higher than the acceptable value of 0.70 espoused by Okanlawon et al., (2023).

Participants of this study were required to complete the questionnaires by rating their level of agreement or disagreement with the drivers extracted from an extensive review of existing literature using the five-point Likert scale provided in the survey. As a precautionary measure, a pilot study was conducted with three academics and three professionals believed to have adequate knowledge of the subject matter to test the questionnaire's adequacy and ensure that respondents would easily understand the questions even before a large-scale study was undertaken without sufficient familiarity with the proposed methods. The identified target population for the primary survey consisted mainly of facilities management firms in Nigeria that are corporately registered with the International Facility Management Association (IFMA).

These target audiences were selected as the collective representatives of the IFMA, seeing as this group is the only recognised association for FM firms in Nigeria. Consequently, this study employed purposive sampling to identify a study population that possessed a high level of knowledge regarding BIM and FM. This sampling approach is a non-probability sampling technique in which researchers deliberately select individuals or cases that possess certain characteristics or meet specific criteria relevant to the research purpose (Campbell et al., 2020). Hence, this technique was deemed appropriate for the study due to the nature of the study, the target audiences and their affiliation with the recognized professional body.

Given that technological innovations are currently evolving in the FM industry, the study prioritized professionals who are familiar with and experienced in the use of BIM. The total population of such professionals in the study context could not be precisely determined; therefore, it was treated as effectively unlimited for sampling purposes. In this case, the Godden (2004) formula for large or infinite populations was applied:

$$n = \frac{z^2 \times p \times (1-p)}{e^2} \quad \text{Equation (1)}$$

Where: $Z = 1.96$, $Z=1.96$ for a 95% confidence level, $p = 0.5$ $p=0.5$ (maximum variability), and $d = 0.0895$ $d=0.0895$ (desired margin of error $\approx 8.95\%$). Substituting these values yields:

$$n = \frac{1.96^2 \times 0.25}{0.0895^2} = 120$$

Based on this calculation, 120 structured questionnaires were administered electronically via Google Forms to the defined professional categories. Of these, 102 were completed and returned, representing an 85% response rate, which was deemed acceptable for further analysis as espoused by Oyewobi et al. (2023). Moreover, this high response rate, coupled with the statistically acceptable margin of error for exploratory research, ensures that the sample size achieved is both statistically defensible and practically sufficient for drawing meaningful inferences within the scope of the study. However, the absence of an exact population figure for BIM-familiar FM professionals in the study area is acknowledged as a limitation, as it prevents a precise finite-population adjustment; nonetheless, the use of an infinite-population approach is widely accepted in similar contexts where population parameters are unknown. Figure 1.0 shows the research methodology process for the study.

Figure 1: Research Methodology Process

Source: Author's construct (2025)

3.1 Study Analysis

Based on the responses, the data retrieved was subjected to an in-depth analysis. The study adopted the Shapiro-Wilk test to determine the normality of the data set. The result of the Shapiro-Wilk test of normality led to the employment of the Kruskal-Wallis test to ascertain variations in the respondents' opinions. Subsequently, descriptive statistics and EFA were applied to analyse the collected data using Microsoft Excel and Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 26. EFA is a statistical analysis tool that can cluster large amounts of data into a small and manageable size by investigating the variables' fundamental theoretical structure (Oyewobi, 2023). Hence, to assess the appropriateness of the dataset collected for exploratory factor analysis (EFA), the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's tests were conducted. The outcome of these tests indicated a KMO value of 0.840, surpassing the recommended threshold of 0.70 (Okanlawon et al., 2023), and a statistically significant Bartlett's Test of Sphericity with a significance level of 0.00.

4.0 Research Findings

4.1 Demographic Information

From the analysis of the demographic attributes of the participants, the distribution of job roles was as follows: 74.51% of the individuals were facility managers; 3.92% were managing partners; 2.94% were quantity surveyors; while an additional 2.94% of them were lecturers. Other positions included contract managers, consultants, engineers, estate surveyors and valuers, managing directors, operations managers, practice managers, project managers, senior managers, site managers, and workplace managers. Significantly, more than 70% of the participants were facility managers, and therefore guaranteed a thorough portrayal of the Nigerian FM business.

4.2 Perception of Respondents on the Key drivers of BIM adoption in the Nigerian Facilities Management Industry

Table 2 presents the ranking of the drivers of BIM adoption in the Nigerian Facilities Management industry, as perceived by respondents from different categories. In addition to this, the table displays the outcome of the Shapiro-Wilk and Kruskal-Wallis tests. The Shapiro-Wilk test results indicated that the data set has a p-value of 0.00, which suggests a non-normally data distribution. Consequently, the Kruskal-Wallis test was employed to determine the extent of diversity in the respondents' opinions. The result of the Kruskal-Wallis test revealed that out of the 11 drivers identified, 10 have a converging opinion, whereas “timely detection of inaccuracies” has a diverging opinion. These views may have emerged from contrasting viewpoints on the significance of prompt identification of mistakes. Different stakeholders may have prioritised the promptness of error detection to different extents which resulted in divergent views on its importance. This could also be linked with varied professional background, skills and knowledge. Further, Table 2 presents respondents' prioritisation of the factors that influence the adoption of BIM in the Nigerian Facilities Management industry. In order to arrive at the level of agreement among the respondents regarding the identified factors, the study employed the decision framework proposed by Oyewobi et al. (2017). This framework categorises responses as follows: 1.0-1.49 as **Strongly Disagree**, 1.50-2.49 as **Disagree**, 2.50-3.49 as **Somewhat Agree**, 3.50-4.49 as **Agree**, and 4.50-5.00 as **Strongly Agree**.

From table 2, it is clear that “improved productivity due to easy retrieval of information” is the highest ranked driver with a Mean Item Score of 4.67. This implies that BIM can greatly improve the efficiency and efficacy of facility management activities by enabling expedient and accessible access to pertinent information. This finding is in line with the studies of Acheng et al. (2023) which state that BIM is being widely implemented globally to ameliorate communication among project stakeholders, facilitate design visualisation, identify potential conflicts, minimise redesign during project execution, enhance design quality, save costs, and optimise project returns. The finding is also consistent with the study of Samimpay and Saghatforoush (2020). The table goes further to show that the second ranked driver is “Quality Enhancement”, having an MIS of 4.63. This finding is harmonious with the study of Sadek et al. (2019), which concluded that BIM is a tool used to design quality enhancement and enhance design process. Conclusively, the table reveals that the least ranked drivers are “energy analysis control”, “reduction in cost and risk”, and “reduction in rework” with a mean score of 4.45, 4.37 and 4.32 respectively. These findings correspond with studies carried out by Alzoubi (2022).

Table 2: Perception of Respondents on the Key drivers of BIM Adoption

Code	Shapiro-Wilk Statistic	Sig.	Kruskal Wallis Chi-square	Sig	MIS	SD	Rank
D1	0.637	0.000	5.216	0.734	4.670	0.530	1
D8	0.647	0.000	4.144	0.844	4.630	0.530	2
D4	0.639	0.000	5.775	0.672	4.600	0.530	3
D11	0.690	0.000	6.546	0.586	4.600	0.490	4
D5	0.677	0.000	10.337	0.031*	4.570	0.570	5

D7	0.664	0.000	7.801	0.453	4.560	0.520	6
D3	0.682	0.000	7.151	0.520	4.530	0.520	7
D9	0.671	0.000	5.642	0.687	4.520	0.520	8
D10	0.739	0.000	4.809	0.778	4.450	0.670	9
D2	0.753	0.000	4.276	0.831	4.370	0.730	10
D6	0.779	0.000	5.993	0.648	4.320	0.750	11

Source: Authors Construct (2025)

4.3 Discussion of Findings

Based on the analysis presented in Table 3 and Figure 1, three clusters were formed from the identified drivers. The following subsections name these clusters following their characteristics.

4.3.1 Quality-related Drivers

A total of seven (7) variables were loaded in this cluster: “quality enhancement” (83%); “visualisation and sharing of information” (81%); “timely detection of inaccuracies” (64%); “improved productivity due to easy retrieval of information” (62%); “communication improvement and harmonisation” (61%); “improvements in data value and dependability are expected to result in enhanced labour efficiency” (59%); and “the ability to build and manage assets in a more efficient, cost-effective, and environmentally friendly manner” (52%). The overall variance explained by this cluster is 40.50%. The findings are consistent with those of Olanrewaju et al. (2021), which state that one of the key selling aspects of BIM is visualisation. It also aligns with the findings of Ashworth (2021), which avers that the potential benefits of a BIM-based approach to managing and visualising information regarding a building's energy efficiency may lead to more consistent information-management standards. This study's findings are also agreed with the conclusions of Sompolgrunk et al. (2023), which affirm that building information modelling (BIM) is an effective technique that has substantially increased productivity in the design and construction sectors.

This is largely due to how easily information can be extracted from BIM. The findings of this study closely correspond with Leygonie et al. (2022) research whose work reveals that building Information Modelling (BIM) is a powerful tool for enhancing quality in the design and construction industries. It also has a major impact on improving the quality of projects at every stage, from design to construction to long-term facility maintenance.

4.3.2 Consistency-related Drivers

A total of three (3) variables were loaded in this cluster, namely “reduction of rework” (79%), “reduction of cost and risk” (70%), and “energy analysis and control” (66%). This cluster illustrates why Building Information Modelling (BIM), which provides more than just a digital depiction of structures, is at the vanguard of transforming the engineering, construction, and design sectors. Thus, beyond its core function of modelling and visualising building plans, BIM is a game-changing instrument that improves project quality from inception to facility management (Ajayi, 2022). In this era of construction innovation, BIM is a dynamic force that not only streamlines operations but also fundamentally improves the quality of products

(Abrishami & Martín-Durán, 2021). These results are consistent with the study conducted by Soust-Verdaguer et al. (2022).

4.3.3 Safety-related Drivers

This cluster included a single variable, "safety/emergency management", which had a strong representation of 86%. The cluster proves the potentiality of Building Information Modelling (BIM) to oversee and ensure safety throughout the construction process. The dominance of this variable within the cluster demonstrates BIM's effectiveness in monitoring safety protocols and emergency management procedures in construction projects. These findings concur with the study of Teo Ai Lin et al. (2017), which states that the use of Building Information Modelling (BIM) to improve safety performance exemplifies a significant advancement in the construction industry. By using digital technologies to proactively discover, evaluate, and reduce possible hazards across the project's lifecycle, BIM integration fundamentally alters conventional methods of safety management. Moreover, it aligns with the study conducted by Fagnoli and Lombardi (2020).

Table 3: Exploratory Factor Analysis of BIM Adoption Drivers in Nigerian Facility Management for Enhanced Efficiency and Resilience

Category	S/ N	Drivers	Component			Variance Explained
			1	2	3	
Quality Related	D8	Quality Enhancement	0.83			40.5
	D4	Visualization and sharing of information	0.81			
	D5	Timely detection of inaccuracies	0.64			
	D1	Improved productivity due to easy retrieval of information	0.62			
	D3	Communication improvement and harmonization	0.61			
	D9	Improvements in data value and dependability are expected to result in enhanced labour efficiency	0.59			
	D7	The ability to build and manage assets in a more efficient, cost-effective, and environmentally friendly manner	0.52			
Consistency Related	D6	Reduction of rework		0.79		11.14
	D2	Reduction in both costs and risks		0.70		
	D10	Energy analysis and control		0.66		
Safety Related	D11	Safety/emergency management			0.86	9.70
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy = 0.840						
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity sig = 0.00						

Source: Authors Construct (2025)

5.0 Research Limitations

Although this study has made considerable advancements, it is important to acknowledge its limitations. The study was conducted in Nigeria; hence, this may restrict how the results are applied in a global context. Furthermore, the conclusions drawn from the study are subjective, as they are based on the responses of FM stakeholders. Conclusively, given that the adoption of BIM in the FM industry is still in the early phases, it is possible that the majority of respondents had more theoretical knowledge than actual experience with the adoption of BIM in the FM industry. Therefore, as more FM stakeholders gain practical experience with BIM-FM adoption, their perspectives on the factors that drive BIM adoption for increased resilience and efficiency in the Nigerian FM business may diverge from what is currently known.

6.0 Conclusion and Future Research

The adoption of BIM has the potential to transform the delivery of FM services in Nigeria significantly. By providing facilities managers with tools that enhance operational efficiency, resilience, and sustainability, BIM can catalyze a paradigm shift in the FM industry, enabling organisations to remain competitive while meeting the evolving needs of users. This study explored the drivers of BIM adoption in the Nigerian FM industry for enhanced efficiency and resilience. The drivers were determined through a review of relevant literature and assessed via a questionnaire survey of FM professionals. The Kruskal–Wallis and Shapiro–Wilk tests provided statistical validation, while Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) categorised the drivers into three clusters: quality-related, consistency-related, and safety-related. From a theoretical perspective, these findings provide empirical support for the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and the Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) Theory. Quality-related drivers align with TAM’s “perceived usefulness” and DOI’s “relative advantage” and “observability,” as they directly enhance performance and offer visible benefits. Consistency-related drivers relate to “perceived ease of use” in TAM and “compatibility” in DOI, as they simplify operations and align with organisational workflows. Safety-related drivers map to DOI’s “relative advantage” in risk reduction and operational reliability. By demonstrating how these theoretical constructs manifest in the Nigerian FM context, this study extends the applicability of TAM and DOI to the domain of BIM adoption in FM, particularly within emerging economies. Hence, the practical implications of the study include providing FM stakeholders with a prioritised set of adoption drivers to guide strategic investment, policy formulation, and training initiatives. For instance, quality-related drivers—such as improved productivity, visualisation, and quality enhancement—should be central in capacity-building programmes and awareness campaigns. Policymakers should incentivise BIM adoption through regulatory frameworks and subsidies for technology integration, targeting the identified high-impact drivers. Furthermore, the theoretical contributions lie in linking operational BIM drivers to technology adoption behaviour, thereby enriching the discourse on BIM–FM integration with a behavioural adoption lens. This study demonstrates that drivers traditionally described as operational benefits can also be conceptualised as behavioural motivators within established adoption frameworks. Future research should continue to operationalise TAM and DOI constructs in BIM–FM contexts, exploring moderating factors such as organisational size, digital maturity, and sector-specific requirements. Mixed-method approaches could further validate the driver categories and deepen understanding of their causal pathways in adoption decisions.

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Prospect Of Blockchain Technology Adoption in Lagos Property Market, Nigeria *Sulaimon Olawale Olaleye*¹; and *Timothy Oluwafemi Ayodele*²

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Abstract

Despite the importance of the real estate sector to national and global markets, its level of digital maturity is low compared to other sectors. This study assessed the prospect of BCT adoption across key areas of real estate practice and assessed the differences in perceived potential for BCT adoption based on firms' profile and sub-markets in the Lagos property market. The research adopted a quantitative research approach. Data were collected using a closed-ended questionnaire administered to 252 real estate firms, and 139(55.2%) were retrieved. Data were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. The results revealed that the potential for BCT adoption is high, especially in property management, valuation, and land administration, within the Lagos real estate market, with the adoption levels consistent across the submarkets. Firm size significantly influences the perceived adoption of BCT in facility management, as larger and small-sized real estate firms were more likely to adopt BCT than mid-sized firms. Across Lagos submarkets, adoption levels were generally consistent, meaning BCT strategies can be applied uniformly across the Lagos property market. The results are useful to real estate practitioners and professional bodies for designing integration strategy, prioritizing training and developing a uniform technological protocol across Lagos sub-markets. This study contributes to the literature on BCT by assessing the prospect of BCT in real estate practice.

Keywords: *Blockchain Technology, Adoption, Property Market, Real Estate Practice, Property Transaction*

Introduction

Despite the importance of the real estate sector to national and global markets, its digital maturity is often considered low compared to other sectors (Calvino *et al.*, 2018). Existing studies suggest real estate professionals' reluctance to embrace innovative technology may stem from the industry's slow adoption and resistance to operational changes (Spielman, 2016). The real estate industry is characterised by the adoption of traditional processes and fragmented systems, which contribute to market inefficiencies (Raji, 2024). However, digital transformations are rapidly transforming these traditional systems, offering new operational methods creating new opportunities (Schwab, 2016). One of such transformative technology is Blockchain Technology (BCT), a series of immutable and irrevocable digital records linked in a chain. BCT promises advanced capacities suitable for various industries, including real estate (Mourtzis *et al.*, 2023). Despite this potential, BCT has not gained widespread adoption among property practitioners, especially in emerging property markets.

BCT hold significant potential to address some of the challenges prevalent in the Nigerian property market. BCT integration into real estate practice could address issues such as inefficient property transactions (Hoxha & Sadiku, 2019), land disputes (Singh, 2020), high cost and delayed transactions (Hoxha & Sadiku, 2019), and complexities in land information management (Pankratov *et al.*, 2020). For instance, while the Lagos property market is developed and highly active (Famuyiwa, 2022), it is faced with transparency and bureaucracy issues, sluggish and high transaction costs, and lack of market liquidity (Gbonegun, 2019).

These lead to unreliable services that undermine trust in real estate firms' operations. BCT has emerged as a potential solution to these issues undermining the Lagos real estate market.

Several studies have investigated the potential of using BCT in the real estate industry, covering areas such as land administration (Nissi *et al.*, 2021), commercial real estate transactions (Wouda & Opdenakker, 2019), tokenization (Mistrangelo *et al.*, 2022), and property management (Patil *et al.*, 2023). However, these studies have often been conducted in piecemeal, without considering market-wide areas of real estate practice. Saari *et al.* (2022) attempted a more comprehensive study, identifying four major areas of general BCT usage in real estate. However, these studies were mostly theoretical. A deeper understanding among real estate professionals regarding BCT's prospects and how it can be leveraged to improve operations could significantly increase its integration into real estate practices. Therefore, investigating the prospect of BCT adoption in real estate practice in Lagos State is crucial. The study answers the following research questions:

- (i) What is the potential of BCT adoption across key real estate practice in Lagos State?
- (ii) How does the perceived potential vary across the firm profiles in the study area?
- (iii) How does the perceived potential vary across Lagos sub-markets?

Literature Review

Overview of BCT

BCT has been developed to successfully address several issues including double spending, stopping fraud, and proof of ownership, which is a major concern in the real estate industry (Oluwunmi, 2023). BCT has evolved through four evolutions, from Blockchain 1.0 to Blockchain 4.0. Blockchain 1.0 primarily focused on storing and transferring value using digital currencies such as Bitcoin, Ripple, and Dash (Shrimali & Patel, 2022). Blockchain 2.0 introduced smart contracts, significantly enhancing the programmability of the blockchain ecosystem (Shrimali & Patel, 2022). Blockchain 2.0 opens up new opportunities for innovation in a variety of sectors, including finance and supply chain management. By the mid-2010s, Blockchain 3.0 emerged, shifting BCT from a transaction-centric platform to applications-centric (Shrimali & Patel, 2022). The most recent iteration, Blockchain 4.0, represents a substantial advancement over earlier iterations. This phase addressed many restrictions that were present in earlier iterations, especially about scalability, throughput, and latency.

Businesses looking to make use of BCT can assess its potential by using one of the three deployment settings, and this include private (permissioned) BCT, public (permissionless) BCT, and hybrid (consortium) BCT. Vukoli (2017) asserted that the technology of the permissioned Blockchain ecosystem can bring about a revolutionary transformation in the real estate sector. This strategy has many advantages, such as increased security and transparency, increased effectiveness, and accuracy. Public or permissionless BCT is an open-source setting accessible to everyone who wants to utilise and participate in it (Bozic *et al.* 2016). An example of this type is the Bitcoin Blockchain. Any network user can observe and access transactions on a public Blockchain without having to first authenticate themselves (Lewis *et al.*, 2017). The hybrid combines elements of both public and private Blockchain (Li *et al.*, 2017). This kind of Blockchain is widely used by groups or businesses collaborating on projects, with read-only

access to data restricted to a small group of users. This approach allows consortium to benefit from BCT while still maintaining control over network access and usage.

Prospect for Application of BCT with the Property Industry

The application of BCT in the real estate sector has been widely recognised as a disruptive innovation capable of enhancing real estate practices. Studies have identified BCT as a potential solution for inefficiencies in real estate services. Wouda and Opdenakker (2019) argued that BCT offers a solution to address some of the inefficiencies and cumbersome real estate processes. Cunha and da Silva (2023) associated the delays in real estate operation with higher transaction costs. Spielman (2016) believed that where BCT is integrated into real estate operations, the use of intermediaries in real estate transactions would be minimized, hence, streamline transaction processes, reduce costs, and increase transparency. Dijkstra's (2017) reinforced this discussion and argued that BCT could address issues related to transparency, inefficiencies, inaccuracies, and security.

Uzair *et al.* (2018) suggested that smart contracts could reduce legal and transaction costs. Dakhli *et al.* (2019) argued that BCT could also lower project development costs and increase trust among stakeholders. However, it may be difficult to establish trust in a weak regulatory system. Ameyaw and Vries (2020) suggested that permissionless BCT could be applied to all aspects of land administration. Ferreira *et al.* (2021) highlighted some of the advantages of BCT in land registry, including enhanced security, transparency, efficiency and the potential to reduce fraud and improve trust among stakeholders. Ibrahim *et al.* (2021) noted that integration of BCT could solve 85% of the land administration problem. Nissi *et al.* (2021) identified the potential of using BCT in land administration in Nigeria to include enhancing transaction, reduce cost and delay, and eliminate intermediaries.

Another major area is property valuation. The valuation process in Nigeria is plagued with issues such as a lack of transparency and information asymmetry. By integrating BCT into property valuation, properties are registered and making it easier to get market data on comparable properties. The system's transparency will also enable all stakeholders to be aware of the valuation process to complete an arm's-length transaction and arrive at market value on the current market conditions and circumstances (Yildiz *et al.*, 2020). Similarly, Lazushvili *et al.* (2019) argued that access to comparable properties for valuation will be easier, faster, and transparent. Adilieme *et al.* (2024) also suggested that BCT could be a viable tool for reducing client influence in property valuation. The foregoing highlights key capacity of BCT in real estate practice. These technological capabilities of BCT suggest its ability to transform the property market. However, despite these capabilities, widespread adoption particularly in emerging property markets like Nigeria remain low.

Study Setting: The Lagos Property Market

Lagos State, with a population exceeding 16 million, is Nigeria's second most populous state and is the country's commercial hub, boasting vibrant economic activities and thriving business centres (Otegbulu, 2017). The Lagos property market is the most dynamic in Nigeria, characterised by significant development and transaction activity (Famuyiwa, 2022). This has positioned the market as an attractive destination for investors. However, the real estate sector faces a persistent challenge in lack of a reliable property data bank (Abere *et al.*, 2019). Thus,

to unlock its full potential, the Lagos real estate market requires a more systematic and transparent approach to data exchange across different areas of practice. Blockchain technology (BCT) has emerged as a promising solution to address these challenges.

Theoretical Framework and Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Frame
Source: Authors' construct (2025)

The conceptual framework (Figure 1) explains how the profile of real estate firms and the submarkets influence BCT adoption. The firms' profile such as size, ownership structure, age, directly influence the areas of adoption of BCT in real estate operations. However, the submarkets are expected to shape the pattern of adoption of BCT in real estate operation. For instance, the pattern of adoption of BCT could differ between Ikeja from Lagos Island due to the environmental factors including customer demand and competitive pressure. Hence, this framework shows how firms' and submarket characteristics determine the prospect of BCT adoption in real estate practice.

The theoretical framework is primarily drawn from Technological, Organisational, and Environmental (TOE) framework, which helps to understand firms' level of adoption of technology, such as technological readiness, external pressures, and resource availability. This framework is supported by the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT). UTAUT provides a useful insight into how professionals' behavioural intentions, and usages of the technology were influenced by factors such as performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions. These hybrid frameworks which integrate the firms, individual and social systems help to understand how the real estate professionals perceive the prospects of BCT adoption.

Methods

The study employed quantitative research design to investigate the potential for BCT adoption among registered real estate firms in Lagos State, Nigeria. According to the Nigerian Institution of Estate Surveyors and Valuers (NIESV) Directory (2023), the 415 registered real estate firms in Lagos State were stratified into three areas based on the submarkets: Lagos Island (170

firms), Lagos Mainland (156 firms), and Ikeja (89 firms) to ensure geographical representation and reduce sampling bias. A systematic sampling approach was used, with 50% of firms sampled from Lagos Island and Lagos Mainland, and a total enumeration for Ikeja. This follows the recommendation by Watson (2001). This resulted in a sample of 85 firms from Lagos Island, 78 firms from Lagos Mainland, and 89 firms from Ikeja. One real estate professional from each selected firm was sampled, totalling 252 respondents. The response rates were 62.9% for Lagos Island, 49.4% for Lagos Mainland, and 52.6% for Ikeja.

Data was collected through structured questionnaires personally administered. The questionnaire was divided into two sections. The first section gathered data on the profile of the firms' such as age, current total value of firm portfolio, number of employees, ownership structure. The second focused on the potential of BCT adoption in seven (7) areas of real estate practice including property agency, property valuation, facility management, and finance. The data was analysed using frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, and Kruskal Wallis Test. Kruskal-Wallis test is a non-parametric statistical test used to determine if there are statistically significant locational differences and the level of prospect of BCT adoption in real estate practice. A 5-point Likert scale was used to assess adoption potential, with responses analysed using weighted mean scores. The interpretation of mean scores was adapted from Nyutu *et al.* (2021).

- 1.00 to 1.80 - Very Low Level
- 1.81 to 2.60 - Low Level
- 2.61 to 3.40 - Average Level
- 3.41 to 4.20 - High Level
- 4.21 to 5.00 - Very High Level

To ensure validity, pilot survey was conducted with twelve professionals (four in each submarket). This helped in removing ambiguity and determining the meantime to complete the questionnaire. Furthermore, the instrument was reviewed by purposively selected professionals with BCT knowledge, who validated the relevance and coverage. Reliability analysis using Cronbach's alpha (Table 1) showed excellent internal consistency (above 0.9), based on George and Mallery (2003) submission, for all real estate operations examined.

Table 1: Reliability Analysis

Aspects of Real Estate Operations	Cronbach's alpha value
Property Agency	0.953
Property Valuation	0.915
Facility Management	0.955
Property Management	0.961
Property Development	0.952
Land Administration	0.964
Finance	0.962

Source: Authors' construct (2025)

Analysis and Findings

Socio-economic characteristics

a. Respondents

The analysis of the respondents' demographics (Table 2), showed that majority had 1 to 5 years of experience (27.3%), followed by 6 to 10 years (26.6%). This implies that a significant proportion (43.1%) had over 10 years of experience, and thus, the responses provided by the respondents are reliable.

Table 2: Demographic Characteristics of Real Estate Professionals

Respondents Profile	Variables	Ikeja	Lagos Island	Lagos Mainland	Total
		f(%)	f(%)	f(%)	f(%)
Years of Experience	1-5	22(39.3)	7(16.7)	9(22.0)	38(27.3)
	6-10	8(14.3)	17(40.5)	12(29.3)	37(26.6)
	11-15	7(12.5)	6(14.3)	10(24.4)	23(16.5)
	16-20	12(21.4)	5(11.9)	3(7.3)	20(14.4)
	21 & above	6(10.7)	4(9.5)	7(17.1)	17(12.2)
	No response	1(1.8)	3(7.1)	0(0.0)	4(2.9)
	Total	56(100.0)	42(100.0)	41(100)	139(100)
Position in the firm	Principal Partner	14(25.0)	10(23.8)	6(14.6)	30(21.6)
	Managing Partner	9(16.1)	4(9.5)	4(9.8)	17(12.2)
	Associate Partner	4(7.1)	6(14.3)	2(4.9)	12(8.6)
	Head of Practice	4(7.1)	2(4.8)	7(17.1)	13(9.4)
	Branch Manager	1(1.8)	3(7.1)	0(0.0)	4(2.9)
	Senior Surveyor	20(35.7)	15(35.7)	10(24.4)	45(32.4)
	Estate Officers	2(3.6)	1(2.4)	10(24.4)	13(9.4)
	No Response	2(3.6)	1(2.4)	2(4.9)	5(3.6)
	Total	56(100.0)	42(100.0)	41(100.0)	139(100.0)
	Professional Qualification	Probate/Graduate (NIESV)	20(35.7)	7(16.7)	9(22.0)
Associate (NIESV)		24(42.9)	17(40.5)	10(24.4)	51(36.7)
Fellow (NIESV)		6(10.7)	1(2.4)	2(4.9)	9(6.5)
RSV		14(25.0)	11(26.2)	2(4.9)	27(19.4)
RICS student		2(3.6)	1(2.4)	0(0.0)	3(2.2)
MRICS		1(1.8)	1(2.4)	0(0.0)	2(1.4)
	FRICS	1(1.8)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	1(0.7)

NIESV – Nigerian Institution of Estate Surveyors and Valuers; RSV – Registered Surveyor

Source: Authors' construct (2025)

The result of the position in the firm revealed that most of the respondents were senior surveyors (32.4%), followed by partner/principal surveyors (21.6%), 12.2% were managing partners of the firm, and 3.6% did not respond. For the professional qualification, the majority were Associate (NIESV) (36.7%) members, followed by Probate/Graduate (NIESV) (25.9%) members, then RSV (19.4%). The result indicates a strong representation of registered surveyors; hence, the response from the respondents is reliable.

b. Real Estate firms

Table 3 presents the profile of the real estate firms. For the ownership structure, the results of aggregates showed that most firms (58.3%) were sole proprietorships, followed by partnerships (31.7%) and limited liability companies (LLCs) (7.9%). The result is consistent with the study of Clement *et al.* (2013) and Idowu *et al.* (2012), which found that the majority of practitioners preferred to work independently. Results on the firm's age showed that the majority (40.3%) of firms were over 20 years old; 18.0% were less than 6 years old, which indicates an influx of

new real estate firms. Lagos Mainland had the highest proportion of older firms compared to Ikeja and Lagos Island. Handoyo *et al.* (2023) confirmed that the age of firms could influence the adoption of technology such as BCT.

Table 3: Profile of Real Estate Firms

Firm Profile	Variables	Lagos			Total
		Ikeja f(%)	Island f(%)	Mainland f(%)	
Ownership Structure	Sole Proprietorship	32(57.1)	24(57.1)	25(61.0)	81(58.3)
	Partnership	20(35.7)	14(33.3)	10(24.4)	44(31.7)
	Limited Liability Company	3(5.4)	4(9.5)	4(9.8)	11(7.9)
	No Response	1(1.8)	0(0)	2(4.9)	3(2.2)
	<i>Total</i>	<i>56(100)</i>	<i>42(100)</i>	<i>41(100)</i>	<i>139(100)</i>
Firm Age	Less than 6 years	9(16.1)	9(21.4)	7(17.1)	25(18.0)
	6 to 10 years	12(21.4)	4(9.5)	4(9.8)	20(14.4)
	11 to 15 years	8(14.3)	7(16.7)	6(14.6)	21(15.1)
	16 to 20 years	7(12.5)	6(14.3)	3(7.3)	16(11.5)
	Above 20 years	19(33.9)	16(38.1)	21(51.2)	56(40.3)
Current Total Value of Property Portfolio	No Response	1(1.8)	0(0)	0(0)	1(0.7)
	<i>Total</i>	<i>56(100)</i>	<i>42(100)</i>	<i>41(100)</i>	<i>139(100)</i>
	Under 10M	5(8.9)	0(0)	11(26.8)	16(11.5)
	10 to <50M	2(3.6)	2(4.8)	6(14.6)	10(7.2)
	50M to <100M	7(12.5)	4(9.5)	0(0)	11(7.9)
Number of Employees	Above 100M	41(73.2)	31(73.8)	24(58.5)	96(69.1)
	No Response	1(1.8)	5(11.9)	0(0)	6(4.3)
	<i>Total</i>	<i>56(100)</i>	<i>42(100)</i>	<i>41(100)</i>	<i>139(100)</i>
	Less than 10	27(48.2)	24(57.1)	20(48.8)	71(51.1)
	10 to 49	16(28.6)	12(28.6)	8(19.5)	36(25.9)
Geographical Scope	50 to 100	8(14.3)	1(2.4)	4(9.8)	13(9.4)
	Above 100	5(8.9)	3(7.1)	9(22.0)	17(12.2)
	No Response	0(0)	2(4.8)	0(0)	2(1.4)
	<i>Total</i>	<i>56(100)</i>	<i>42(100)</i>	<i>41(100)</i>	<i>139(100)</i>
	1 location in Lagos	12(21.4)	7(16.7)	8(19.5)	27(19.4)
Type of Client*	Several locations in Lagos	12(21.4)	11(26.2)	11(26.8)	34(24.5)
	Other states in Nigeria	19(33.9)	11(26.2)	10(24.4)	40(28.8)
	Regional Operation	10(17.9)	4(9.5)	6(14.6)	20(14.4)
	International	3(5.4)	4(9.5)	3(7.3)	10(7.2)
	No Response	0(0)	5(11.9)	3(7.3)	8(5.8)
Type of Client*	<i>Total</i>	<i>56(100)</i>	<i>42(100)</i>	<i>41(100)</i>	<i>139(100)</i>
	Private Individual (Local)	47(83.9)	29(69.0)	23(56.1)	99(71.2)
	Private Organisation (Local)	20(35.7)	24(57.1)	19(46.3)	63(45.3)
	Private Individual (Foreign)	32(57.1)	19(45.2)	16(39.0)	67(48.2)
	Private Organisation (Foreign)	15(26.8)	12(28.6)	9(22.0)	36(25.9)
	Government Institution (Local)	27(48.2)	15(35.7)	13(31.7)	55(39.6)
Government Institution (Foreign)	5(8.9)	2(4.8)	4(9.8)	11(7.9)	

*multiple choice

Source: Authors' construct (2025)

For the number of employees, the majority (51.1%) of the firms in Lagos State had fewer than 10 employees. This can limit the adoption of BCT as there may be a need for the employment of IT staff in the firms, however, the real estate firms are perceived to employ few number of real estate professionals, and the majority of them do not have IT professionals. Analysis of geographical scope showed that the majority of the firms (28.8%) operate in other states in Nigeria, and several locations in Lagos (24.5%). The geographical spread could necessitate the adoption of BCT by firms that need to improve their data and knowledge sharing, and collaborations. While most of the firms across the three submarkets served private individuals

Property Data Management	3.87	1.02	4.13	0.70	3.97	0.73	3.98	0.86
Automated Valuation Models	3.66	1.09	3.92	0.73	3.76	0.76	3.76	0.91
Data Provenance and Verification	3.67	0.96	3.89	0.75	3.87	0.59	3.79	0.81
Valuation process transparency	3.75	0.97	3.89	0.82	4.00	0.71	3.86	0.86
Data Sharing	3.82	0.97	4.03	0.69	3.87	0.67	3.89	0.82
Decentralized governance	3.74	0.94	3.72	0.70	3.81	0.74	3.76	0.81
Overall	3.76	0.86	3.93	0.59	3.88	0.53	3.84	0.70

Source: Authors' construct (2025)

c. Potential of BCT Adoption in Facility Management

This analysis of BCT for facility management (Table 6) shows that the overall perception of BCT's potential in Facility Management is average (3.77). Access control and security have the highest overall mean (3.84), while Energy Usage Optimisation is the lowest (3.72). Comparing regions, Lagos Mainland has a higher mean value for most FM operations, followed by Lagos Island and then Ikeja. While the use of BCT for facility management has not been identified by many researchers, BCT could be incorporated with other technologies, which could be used for access control and security, building system monitoring, and service records. This finding corroborates Sarfaraz *et al.* (2023) who identified BCT as a technological solution for access control.

Table 6: Potential of BCT for Facility Management

Property Facility Management	Lagos							
	Ikeja		Lagos Island		Mainland		Overall	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Building System Monitoring	3.71	0.94	3.83	1.00	3.97	0.87	3.82	0.94
Services Records	3.72	0.98	3.83	0.88	3.95	0.52	3.82	0.84
Energy Usage Optimization	3.59	0.98	3.61	0.87	4.00	0.75	3.72	0.90
Space and Lease Management	3.59	0.94	3.69	0.89	3.95	0.78	3.72	0.89
Access control and security	3.67	1.06	3.94	0.96	3.97	0.76	3.84	0.96
Asset management	3.63	1.09	3.81	1.01	3.82	0.67	3.73	0.96
Facility data management	3.64	1.04	3.75	0.87	3.89	0.74	3.75	0.91
Overall	3.65	0.09	3.78	0.81	3.94	0.61	3.77	0.81

Source: Authors' construct (2025)

d. Potential of BCT Adoption in Property Management

This analysis of the potential of BCT for property management is presented in Table 7. The overall average potential for PM is 3.85. The overall ranking shows that *Tenant Verification/Background Checks* are ranked first (3.94), followed by *Tenant Management* (3.94), while the lowest overall ranked operation is *Utility Management* (3.67). This indicates a high prospect of BCT adoption for PM practice. From the literature, tenant verification and background checks are not well identified by researchers. However, Jeong and Ahn (2021) have noted that BCT can be used in terms of background checks, that is, zero knowledge proof.

Table 7: Potential of BCT for Property Management

Property Management (PM)	Lagos							
	Ikeja		Lagos Island		Mainland		Overall	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Rental Contract	3.85	0.90	3.89	0.09	3.97	0.65	3.90	0.83

Tenant Management	3.91	1.01	3.97	0.81	3.95	0.71	3.94	0.87
Tenant Verification/Background Checks	3.96	1.01	3.92	0.97	3.95	0.88	3.95	0.95
Maintenance Requests and Scheduling	3.74	0.96	3.81	0.98	3.90	0.85	3.81	0.93
Transactions	3.74	0.98	4.14	0.72	3.87	0.77	3.89	0.86
Data Sharing and Collaboration	3.74	0.98	4.08	0.91	3.85	0.84	3.87	0.93
Predictive Maintenance	3.57	0.94	3.86	0.90	3.92	0.84	3.75	0.91
Insurance and risk management	3.67	0.92	3.72	0.95	3.72	0.76	3.70	0.88
Utility Management	3.55	0.89	3.75	0.94	3.77	0.87	3.67	0.90
Overall	3.82	0.89	3.90	0.80	3.84	0.73	3.85	0.81

Source: Authors' construct (2025)

e. Potential of BCT Adoption in Property Development

The result of the analysis of the potential of BCT for property development (Table 8) shows that the *property development* across all locations has high prospect (3.75). Overall, Secure and Transparent Record is ranked first (3.89), followed by Digital Identity and Authentication (3.82), while Predictive Maintenance is ranked last (3.67). Comparison across locations shows that Lagos Mainland has the highest prospect, followed by Lagos Island and then Ikeja.

Table 8: Potential of BCT for Property Development

Property Development (PD)	Lagos							
	Ikeja		Lagos Island		Mainland		Overall	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Planning Permission	3.49	1.09	3.81	0.95	3.87	0.83	3.70	0.99
Digital Identity and Authentication	3.64	1.15	4.00	0.68	3.89	0.82	3.82	0.95
Construction supply chain	3.50	1.01	3.78	0.80	3.85	0.63	3.68	0.86
Predictive Maintenance	3.52	1.04	3.78	0.87	3.77	0.78	3.67	0.92
Tokenisation/Fragmentation	3.56	1.08	3.81	0.75	3.85	0.75	3.71	0.90
Secure and Transparent Record	3.76	1.13	4.00	0.86	3.97	0.81	3.89	0.97
Overall	3.59	0.97	3.86	0.74	3.87	0.68	3.75	0.83

Source: Author's construct (2025)

This implies that BCT could be adopted for general use (property transaction), followed by more specific use (digital identity and authorisation). The finding is in accordance with Gupta and Jaysawal (2023) who revealed that BCT have potential to improve security and transparency of record keeping in various industries such as real estate.

f. Potential of BCT Adoption in Land Administration

The potential of BCT for land administration (Table 9) shows that the overall perception of BCT's potential in Land Administration is average (3.81). *Secure Land Titles and Ownership Record* has the highest mean (3.90), followed by *Transparency and Trust* (3.86) and *Access to Land Information* (3.86), while *Land Use Planning* (3.69) was the least ranked. There is no consistent ranking across the submarkets. Overall operations across the locations show that Lagos Island ranked first, followed by Lagos Mainland, and then Ikeja. The findings of this study are in line with previous studies. Ferreira *et al.* (2021) and Ameyaw and Vries (2020) identified land administration and title records as a potential area of application of BCT.

Table 9: Potential of BCT for Land Administration

Land Administration	Lagos			
	Ikeja	Lagos Island	Mainland	Overall

	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Secure Land Titles and Ownership Record	3.89	1.03	3.81	1.06	4.00	0.61	3.90	0.93
Streamlined Land Transfers/Registration	3.74	0.98	3.64	0.90	3.80	0.70	3.73	0.87
Transparency and Trust	3.78	1.06	3.92	0.94	3.92	0.81	3.86	0.95
Access to Land Information	3.72	1.05	3.92	0.97	4.00	0.76	3.86	0.95
Decentralized Land Administration	3.81	1.02	3.97	0.85	3.67	0.87	3.81	0.93
Integration with Other Technologies	3.76	0.98	3.83	0.91	3.83	0.81	3.80	0.91
Land Use Planning	3.80	1.05	3.66	1.06	3.56	1.07	3.69	1.06
Tax collection	3.74	0.98	3.81	0.89	3.86	0.76	3.79	0.89
Overall	3.78	0.93	3.83	0.87	3.82	0.64	3.81	0.83

Source: Authors' construct (2025)

g. Potential of BCT Adoption in Finance

Based on the data presented in Table 10, the results show that finance operations have a high prospect (3.84). *Rental and lease payments* (3.93) and *crowdfunding* (3.89) are ranked first and second, while *Diversification of Portfolio* is ranked least (3.73). Overall, Lagos Island ranked first, followed by Lagos Mainland, and then Ikeja. This suggests that BCT adoption for property finance is related to the general BCT application as earlier identified for property development and agency. The second-ranked area of application is crowdfunding of a project. The use of BCT for crowd funding has been identified by Alnabulsi (2024). The use of BCT for lending and borrowing could also improve property finance in Nigeria. Private individuals could borrow and lend on a designed BCT network at a particular interest rate.

Table 10: Potential of BCT for Property Finance

Finance	Lagos							
	Ikeja		Lagos Island		Mainland		Overall	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Tokenization/Fractional Ownership	3.92	1.05	3.86	0.81	3.62	1.23	3.81	1.05
Rental and Lease Payments	3.87	0.90	4.00	0.80	3.95	0.92	3.93	0.88
Diversification of Portfolio	3.66	1.19	3.80	0.76	3.77	1.06	3.73	1.04
Smart Contract	3.76	1.02	3.89	0.80	3.87	0.98	3.83	0.94
Lending and Borrowing of funds	3.85	0.98	3.89	0.80	3.90	0.97	3.87	0.92
Crowd funding	3.77	0.98	4.00	0.77	3.94	1.01	3.89	0.93
Overall Awareness	3.81	0.93	3.91	0.73	3.83	0.97	3.84	0.88

Source: Authors' construct (2025)

Statistical difference between prospect of BCT adoption and firms' profiles

The study assessed how firms' profiles influenced the prospect of BCT adoption across various aspects of real estate practice. The results (Table 11) showed that there were no statistically significant differences based on firms' profiles and the prospect of BCT adoption across the various aspects, except for facility management.

Table 11: Statistical Difference between Facility Management and Number of Employees

Demographic	Variables	N	Mean Rank	Kruskal- H	df	Sig
Number of Employees	Less than 10	63	69.25	10.07	3	0.018
	10 – 49	35	50.01			
	50 – 100	13	52.27			
	Over 100	14	77.32			
	Total	125				

Source: Authors' construct (2025)

The Kruskal-Wallis H test revealed a statistically significant difference in the prospect of adoption of BCT in facility management based on firms' number of employees ($H = 10.07$, $df = 3$, $p = 0.018$). Firms that employed over 100 employees had the highest mean rank (77.32), showing that they were more likely to adopt BCT, while firms with 10 to 49 and 50 to 100 employees had lower mean ranks (50.01 and 52.27, respectively), which indicates that they were less likely. Firms that employed fewer than 10 employees had a relatively high mean rank (69.25), indicating moderate interest. This may be because they could leverage the use of a decentralised application since the firm's size is smaller. Overall, the findings confirm that the size of the firm has a significant effect on perceived opportunities for implementing BCT in real estate facility management. This contrasts with Chen (2023) who claimed that firm size does not influence BCT adoption, indicating that firms have equal opportunity to adopt BCT. Conversely, the findings align with Clohessy and Acton (2019) confirmed that firm size influence BCT adoption in supply chain management. This highlights the need to consider firm size in BCT adoption model.

Statistical difference on the prospect of BCT adoption across sub-markets

The study assessed the level of statistical variation across the three submarkets regarding the prospect of BCT adoption (Table 12). The results of the Kruskal-Wallis tests showed that there were no significant variations at $p < 0.05$. However, at $p < 0.1$, the results showed that there were differences across the markets in terms of prospect of BCT adoption in aspects of Agency (document verification, p -value = 0.06) and Facility management (energy usage optimisation, p -value = 0.08).

Table 12: Prospect of BCT based on Location

Aspects of Real Estate Practice	Location of Firm	N	Mean Rank	Kruskal - W	p -value
Agency					
Document Verification	Ikeja	53	57.59	5.535	0.06
	Lagos Island	36	74.56		
	Lagos Mainland	37	61.20		
	Total	126			
Facility Management					
Energy Usage Optimisation	Ikeja	54	59.66	5.09	0.08
	Lagos Island	36	59.85		
	Lagos Mainland	37	74.38		
	Total	127			

Source: Author's construct (2025)

At $p < 0.05$, the results suggest that the prospect of adoption is the same across the Lagos property market. The professionals in the three submarkets shared a similar perception of the prospect of BCT adoption in property management practice. Hence, the strategies to enhance increased adoption of BCT could be generalised in Lagos State as the submarkets do not have significant differences.

Conclusion

This paper examined the potential for BCT adoption across various real estate practices within the Lagos property market. The results showed that property management, property valuation and land administration showed the highest potential for BCT adoption. Other areas such as agency, facility management and property development were also highly rated.

The study also examined how real estate firms' characteristics influence the prospect of BCT adoption. Overall, it found that most firm attributes, including size, and structure, did not significantly impact the prospect for adoption, except for the number of employees and BCT adoption in facility management. Larger firms, with over 100 employees, were more inclined to adopt BCT, due to their greater resources and capacity to implement new technologies. Interestingly, very small firms (under 10 employees) also showed a high interest, possibly due to ease of integrating decentralised applications. Mid-sized firms were less likely to adopt BCT, possibly due to resource constraints or organisational inertia. The study found no significant statistical differences in prospect of BCT adoption across different submarkets within Lagos, suggesting a uniform perception. However, at $p < 0.1$, there were variations in the prospect of BCT adoption for document verification in property agency and optimising energy usage in facility management.

The findings present some implications. Strategies to encourage BCT adoption should be tailored to firm size. Larger firms could be supported with investment incentives, and smaller firms guided towards cost-effective, decentralized applications. Facility management is highlighted as a promising area for BCT integration due to its potential to optimize energy usage, streamline maintenance, and automate service agreements. The uniformity of adoption prospect across the submarkets suggests that broad policies can be implemented without necessarily adjusting for peculiar variations across the submarkets. For areas with low prospect of adoption, training programs and collaborative platforms could be used to remove biases regarding costs and complexity. The paper recommends that professional and regulatory bodies develop guidelines for BCT adoption, including financial support and training programs. The constructs for BCT adoption were not operationally decomposed into attitude, intention, or infrastructure readiness. Future studies could use multi-dimensional operationalization and extend the research to other emerging markets.

Disclosure Statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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Examining the Relationship Between Commercial Property Attributes and Green Certification Outcomes: South Africa's Green Star Rating as a Case Study *Jonathan D. Oladeji¹, Chioma S. Okoro²*.

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Abstract

Despite the important role of green building certification in building sustainability, most studies focus on its value post-certification rather than its value in investment decision-making and asset allocation. This study evaluates the impact of commercial property attributes on Green Star certification outcomes in South Africa. It addresses the gap by determining which attributes influence certification outcomes pre-investment. The study employs a quasi-quantitative approach, analyzing data from the Green Building Council of South Africa. It employs descriptive statistics, Spearman's correlation, Chi-square tests, and ANOVA to evaluate associations and relationships between commercial property attributes and green certification in South Africa. The findings highlight location and rating category as statistically significant variables relative to certification outcomes. Additionally, the results demonstrate inconsistencies with car parking and rating year impacts, raising critical questions for investors to consider in decision-making. By identifying these relationships between green building certification and commercial property attributes, this study contributes to investor certainty in asset allocation before certification is obtained.

Keywords: Sustainability, Commercial property, South Africa, Green building, Investment.

Introduction

In the pursuit of economic development, construction plays an integral part in the form of housing delivery and provision. It is a major contributor to GDP, employment, and overall economic development. Giannetti, Demétrio, Agostinho, Almeida, and Liu (2018) assert that construction usually provides 5–10% of direct and indirect world employment and generates 5–15% of the GDP, on average. This highlights the importance of the construction industry and the economic opportunities inherent.

Building construction is not just important for housing and city growth, but also a critical contributor to economic growth. However, according to the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), buildings have a global demand of about 40% of total energy use, 60% of electricity, 25% of water, and 40% of all resources. They also release about 1/3 of global greenhouse gases over their life cycles. Therefore, investment in this sector is plagued with the risk of being perceived as detrimental to the environment and lacking in sustainability. Without an appropriate framework for anticipating green certification of commercial properties, asset allocation decisions in the South African market are rarely aligned with sustainable or green practices, increasing risk perception and reducing investment flows.

Meanwhile, South Africa's growing economy is emerging as a leader in the adoption of sustainability in the building sector (Masia, Kajimo-Shakantu, Opawole, 2020). Moreso, investors who prioritize sustainability might consider it imprudent to commit financially to projects whose potential for compliance with best environmental standards is highly uncertain. Therefore, green certification was developed to provide an objective measure of a building's sustainability. Yet, its role as a decision-making tool for asset allocation is largely underutilized. Without the certainty that Green Building Certification is achievable, there's the risk of investing in property that has the potential for sustainability but has attributes that are misaligned with green standards or upgrades.

Figure 1: Motivations for Measuring Sustainability

As seen in Figure 1, the interplay of economic growth and environmental sustainability has necessitated the development of frameworks to measure sustainability in the built environment. Markets like South Africa have established the Green Star rating system to provide a standard benchmark for a building's sustainability. This is important considering how South Africa's commercial property market has continued to grow. Valued at USD 9.99 billion in 2025, the South African Commercial Property market is expected to reach a value of USD 14.43 billion by 2030 (Modor Intelligence, 2025). The size of this market and its importance to the economy make the subject of sustainability much more important to investors. The South African Green Star employs a broad range of sustainability measures to promote sustainability at every stage of a building's lifecycle, from planning and community development to building and day-to-day operations. It is the nationally accepted framework developed by the Green Building Council of South Africa (GBCSA) for assessing the environmental sustainability of buildings. It involves a point-based system across multiple categories, including new buildings and major refurbishments, existing buildings, interior fit-outs, and sustainable precincts. Green star credits are earned across nine (9) categories as buildings are developed to meet the environmental and sustainability criteria in building design, construction, and operation stages. The star rating or certification outcome refers to the values ranging from 1-6 where each number represents on the journey, on the journey, good practice, best practice, South African excellence, and world leadership, respectively.

Over 20% of new commercial buildings in Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) nations were certified green, up from 15% previously, indicating a considerable increase in the market for green building certifications (United Nations Environment Programme, & Global Alliance for Buildings and Construction, 2025). However, most existing research on green buildings treats certification as an outcome of property investment decision-making that aligns with sustainability. This does not offer investors the confidence required to make asset allocation decisions based on uncertain certification potential. Yet, asset allocation decisions are being made earlier in the building life cycle and often in the planning phase.

This study demonstrates how green building certification may be used as a market signal to boost investor trust in sustainable assets. This study is grounded in Spence's (1973) Signal Theory, which

holds that obtaining credentials serves as a signal of expertise for stakeholders looking to stand out in the market. By integrating Signal theory, Hedonic Pricing, Sustainable Finance, and Decision Theory, this study demonstrates that certain sustainability attributes not only address environmental or sustainability goals but also signal expertise and added value to the market. This study provides a novel perspective by exploring the link between the achievement of green building certification and specific commercial property attributes.

Aim and Objectives

To examine the statistical relationships between commercial property attributes on Green Star certification outcomes in South Africa, to inform asset allocation decisions. To achieve this, the study pursues the following objectives:

1. Evaluate the influence of commercial building attributes on the likelihood of green certification success, specifically considering rating year, rating category, car parking size, building size, and building type.
2. Evaluate the significance of specific commercial property attributes (e.g., Gross Floor Area, Commercial Office Area, Car Parking) in determining Green Star certification outcomes.
3. Identify key commercial property attributes associated with higher certification scores to inform asset allocation decisions.

Research Questions

Therefore, this study considers the research question: Do certain commercial property attributes impact Green Star certification outcomes in South Africa? Key sub-questions include:

1. Which commercial property attributes demonstrate influence on the likelihood of green-certification outcomes in South Africa?
2. Do green-certified commercial property attributes (e.g., Gross Floor Area, Commercial Office Area, Car Parking) demonstrate significant associations with successful certification outcomes?
3. What commercial property attributes are associated with higher certification scores?

Literature Review

This literature review takes a thematic approach to uncovering critical arguments and perspectives surrounding asset allocation in the context of green building investment. It explores the potential role that commercial property attributes play in certification outcomes. This study seeks to address the challenges faced by investors in anticipating green building certification adoption, assessing how certification success integrates into sustainability-driven portfolio strategies. It addresses the question of whether commercial property attributes like location, size, and car parking impact the outcome of green building certification in South Africa.

Theoretical Framework

This study applies four interrelated and existing theoretical perspectives: hedonic pricing, stakeholder, signal, and sustainable finance theory. These theories provide a rigorous and interdisciplinary lens for evaluating the role of commercial property attributes in influencing sustainable asset allocation decisions with regard to potential certification outcomes. While these theories are not extended, they are applied to a novel investigation of certification uncertainty and investment strategy in South Africa's commercial real estate market. The Hedonic Price Theory is widely adopted in evaluating the influence of certain attributes on property value. Using the hedonic model, green building certification has been established as a value-adding attribute (Van Overbeek, Ishaak, Geurts, and Remøy 2023). Extant

literature affirms that green building certification aligns with certain property attributes, potentially adding to the value of the property (Zhang, Tu, and He, 2024; Van et al., 2023; Fuerst and McAllister, 2011). This study will explore existing associations between attributes like location, car parking size, gross floor area, and green certification star rating level.

The Stakeholder Theory developed by Freeman (1984) emphasizes the need for organizations to consider the interests of all stakeholders in the decision-making process. In the context of green certification, sustainability has become a growing concern for several stakeholders in the built environment, including investors, renters, buyers, and the general public. This study explores how asset allocation decisions incorporating sustainability practices can serve as strategic responses to stakeholder expectations and environmental accountability. Furthermore, studies like Zhang, Wu, and Liu (2018) have shown that a lot of building stakeholders agree on the need to prove the economic viability of green certifications to motivate adoption.

Building on this, Signal Theory by Spence (1973) offers a complementary approach to understanding how green certification acts as a market signal. It highlights green building certification as a market signal for improving investor confidence in sustainable assets. Stakeholders differentiate in the market by acquiring credentials as a signal of competence. Therefore, in the building and construction industry, green certification serves as a signal to investors about a property's sustainability and risk profile. Based on this theory, if certain attributes can impact certification outcomes, investors can strategically allocate resources in anticipation of certification. Finally, Sustainable Finance Theory suggests that incorporating environmental and sustainability principles into an investment portfolio enhances financial viability and resilience (Qiu, Su, & Wang, 2017). Applied to the South African building sector, this theory supports identifying commercial property attributes that align with sustainable investors' viability and feasibility requirements. These four theories, together, offer a multidimensional framework for assessing sustainability adoption in the South African property sector, an increasingly important asset class for local and international investors navigating certification uncertainty and ESG-aligned investment strategies. To further explore the gaps in literature, the following sections are organized thematically to highlight key arguments and contributions in extant literature.

Green Building Price Premiums

The price premium that Green Buildings attracts is the extra amount that buyers or renters are willing to pay for green features. For a while, it was debated whether green features attracted such premiums. In Singapore, Zhang, Tu, and He, (2024) found that high-performing certified GBs (rated Gold Plus or Platinum, the two highest ratings), fetch the highest price premium in new sales (10.1 %), followed by certified GBs rated, Certified or Gold (5.0 %) and quasi-GBs (3.5 %). This suggests not only that investments are rewarded with green building certification but that higher levels of certification attract greater returns. Their findings align with other studies across the globe. For example, in the Netherlands, Van et al. (2023) reported that certified office buildings command a rent premium of 10.3% on average. These premiums also vary between 5.1 and 12.6% in the five largest Dutch cities, suggesting locational differences. Other studies align with these reports on rental premiums for green-certified buildings in other countries like the UK, Germany, and others (Leutner, Gloria, and Bienert, 2024; Fuerst and McAllister, 2011). A major limitation of the extant literature is that it relies on the hedonic pricing models to explain value appreciation without identifying property characteristics that consistently lead to certification eligibility. This study addresses this gap, specifically considering the commercial property market in South Africa. While price premiums on certifications justify investment in sustainable projects, highlighting the mechanisms that drive adoption could potentially contribute to market-wide implementation.

Commercial Property Attributes

It has been established that a critical motivator for green certification, for a lot of building stakeholders, is financial (Ensign, Roy, and Brzustowski, 2021; Simpeh and Smallwood, 2020). Most of these studies consider developer incentives, investor behavior, and tenant preferences. However, they fail to consider how specific commercial property attributes might influence successful certification outcomes. One of the earliest perspectives on the relationship between commercial property attributes and certification was from Fuerst, McAllister (2011). They reported on the price effect of green certification on commercial property rent and price, justifying the additional costs associated. However, they also noted that eco-certified buildings tend to be in central business districts, within taller buildings, and 20 times larger than non-certified ones. However, the lack of empirical evidence for this observation creates a theoretical gap. This implies that while investors can measure the price effect of certification, they lack a framework for determining certification potential before asset allocation. Addressing this gap potentially provides investors with a framework for strategic site selection in their sustainability portfolio. While there are scarce studies on markets like South Africa, Windapo (2014) reported that economic drivers are more critical to the adoption of green buildings, particularly operational costs, and stakeholder demands. While this study lays the foundation for understanding the likelihood of green building adoption, it doesn't provide the insight needed for investors in the South African commercial property market to anticipate certification success.

A study by Qiu, Su, and Wang (2017) examined factors influencing green certification in commercial buildings in the state of New York, an important submarket of the United States. It achieves this by assessing the economic benefits of green certification. Employing multinomial logit and nested logit models, it analyzes commercial buildings in New York State. Some of the predictors of certification that it examines include ownership type (i.e., owner-occupied buildings) and size. The study controlled for location, and the results showed that larger, renter-occupied, and company-owned buildings are more likely to obtain certification. Meanwhile, owner-occupied buildings are less likely to obtain green certification. The study does not differentiate between building types or different states and has a limited scope within New York State. This highlights a gap in identifying other attributes that influence commercial property certification as a critical step to determining feasibility and viability.

Certification and Sustainability

The role of green building certification in achieving sustainability in the building and construction industry has been highlighted in literature (Mammadova and Akbarova, 2023). Particularly in South Africa, the need for standardization has continued to grow as the market premium for green claims motivates the growing adoption of green building certification (Oladeji and Okoro, 2024). While this study focuses on the South African Green Star, it has provided details regarding its design and application by Hoffman, Huang, van Rensburg, and Yorke-Hart (2020). The South Africa study by Simpeh and Smallwood (2024) also asserts that economic incentives and reward schemes significantly promote going towards certification. Fuerst and McAllister (2011) provide the earliest evidence of the green premium in their study measuring the effects of environmental certification on office values in the United States. They provided initial evidence for the price effect of green certification on commercial property rent and price, justifying the additional costs associated with sustainable building practices. They also identified drivers of observed price differences between certified and noncertified buildings, measuring the effects of LEED and Energy Star certification using a hedonic regression analysis for price measurement. While controlling for age, height, size, and location, their model explained over 60% of rent variation.

The study by Fuerst and McAllister (2011) found that eco-certified buildings have rental and sale price premiums. These premiums make certification attractive for stakeholders, particularly developers, investors, and owners. While the study provides evidence of post-certification value for investors, it aligns with more recent studies that treat green certification as an investment outcome rather than a predictive variable (Leutner, Gloria, and Bienert, 2024; Van et al., 2023; Leskinen, Vimpari, and Junnila, 2020). Therefore, this literature review highlights the potential for improving investor confidence in sustainable building projects. By identifying commercial property attributes that influence green building certification outcomes, this research offers asset and portfolio managers a framework for determining viability pre-certification.

Methodology

Since direct access to detailed and structured green building certification datasets was limited, this study employed a quasi-quantitative approach. It extracted numerical data from certification reports published by the Green Building Council of South Africa (GBCSA) using an AI-enabled data extraction tool called Parseur. This allowed structured analysis of commercial property attributes affecting certification outcomes. The aim is to examine the predictable impact of commercial property attributes on green building certification outcomes. The study population for this study was the total number of commercial properties that potentially qualify for the green building certification in South Africa. Considering that the Green Star database is directly focused on South Africa, the study uses data extracted from the GBCSA's certification database, the study takes a purposive sample of certification reports. 510 cases were selected from the total database of 897 building certifications. The study variables extracted from the database include total points, carparking area, rating category, location, rating year, star rating, commercial office area, and gross floor area. The star rating is the dependent variable, while other attributes are independent. The selected sample size (510) ensured sufficient statistical power for correlation and association tests while also aligning with similar studies focused on the South African market (Simpeh and Smallwood, 2020; Rogerson, 2014). The data collected spanned from 2011 to 2023, and this is considered a sufficient period for measuring the relationships that potentially exist and their significance. To ensure reliability, the data extraction was inspected manually and transformed into Excel spreadsheets. The rows represented individual cases, while the columns represented the variables extracted from each document. Data cleaning was conducted to resolve missing values and ensure consistency across the dataset. Although the GBCSA is an official and structured source, additional steps were taken to ensure reliability. The extracted data was manually reviewed, excluding duplicate cases, missing values, and ensuring that cases were consistent and comparable in the variables extracted.

Data Analysis

The analysis required descriptive statistics, which were readily available using Microsoft Excel. The range of the data was estimated using minimum and maximum values. Measures of central tendency and spread were also evaluated using the mean and standard deviation. Further inferential analysis was conducted using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The study conducted a Normality test to determine the appropriateness of a parametric or nonparametric correlation test. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests were used to assess normality to determine the suitability of parametric or non-parametric correlation analysis. Given the nature of the data, Spearman's correlation was preferred for testing the strength and direction of linear relationships. Chi-squared tests and ANOVA were also conducted to establish the significance of associations between categorical variables and to establish mean differences.

Findings

Descriptive Statistics							
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error
RatingCateg	454	1	7	1.74	1.580	2.466	.115
TotalPoints	419	20.0	92.0	52.247	10.3310	.323	.119
Starrating	380	1	6	4.13	.817	-.183	.125
CommercialOfficeArea	225	292.000	7657112.000	134971.44195	534018.725842	12.756	.162
GFA	335	1069.000	7657112.000	186318.56616	525886.713548	10.139	.133
Carparkingarea	66	101.000	1708532.000	193489.70642	390174.937685	3.336	.295
Valid N (listwise)	43						

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of the GBCSA Certified Building Attributes

In Table 1, the certification outcomes (rating category, total points, and star rating) show minimum and maximum scores, showing the range of values. Rating categories are Existing Building Performance v1 (1), Office as Built v1 (2), Public and Education Building Design v1 (3), Net Positive Ecology and Net Zero Carbon Pilots (4), Custom: Industrial Design (5), Multi-Unit Residential as Built v1 (6), and Retail Centre as Built v1 (7). The star rating ranges between 1-6, and the total points are based on a 100% scale. The variables, total points and star rating have near-normal distribution with moderate standard deviation (SD= 52.247, and 4.13, respectively) and low skewness (0.323, and -0.183). Meanwhile, rating category shows a higher skewness (2.466) demonstrating an asymmetry in category representation. Variables like the GFA, Commercial Office Area (COA), and Car Parking have high standard deviation (525886.713548, 534018.725842, and 390174.937685, respectively) and strong positive skewness (10.139, 12.759, and 3.336, respectively). These distributions deviate significantly from normality, supporting the use of non-parametric tests in subsequent analysis.

Region	Certified Buildings	Percentage of Total	Top Certified Locations
Gauteng	202	42.5%	Sandton, Johannesburg, Pretoria, Midrand
Western Cape	86	18.1%	Cape Town, Stellenbosch, Rondebosch
KwaZulu-Natal	40	8.4%	Durban, Westville, Riverhorse
Northwest	5	1.1%	No dominant hubs
Mpumalanga	4	0.8%	No dominant hubs
Limpopo	5	1.1%	Polokwane
International	1	0.2%	Botswana
Total	475	100%	-

Table 2: Green Star Certifications Aggregated by Region (2011–2023)

Table 2 illustrates the aggregated location of Green Star-certified buildings in the analysis. A total of 475 locations were coded for further inferential analysis. Locations like Sandton, Cape Town, and Durban showed significantly higher certification rates. Across the regions, Gauteng leads with 42.5%, demonstrating high sustainability adoption. Next to Gauteng are the Western Cape (18.1%) and KwaZulu-Natal (8.4%). There is evidence of minimal inclusion of other provinces that account for less than 5% and international certification (Botswana).

Tests of Normality						
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
LocationCoded	0.165	71	<0.001	0.870	71	<0.001
RatingCateg	0.375	71	<0.001	0.659	71	<0.001
RatingYear	0.195	71	<0.001	0.860	71	<0.001
Starrating	0.361	71	<0.001	0.747	71	<0.001
TotalPoints	0.163	71	<0.001	0.921	71	<0.001
CommercialOfficeArea	0.396	71	<0.001	0.216	71	<0.001
GFA	0.394	71	<0.001	0.226	71	<0.001
a. Lilliefors Significance Correction						

Table 3: Test for Normality

Table 3 provides data on the normality test for the dependent and independent variables in the analysis. The normality test results include the variables, "LocationCoded," "RatingCateg," "RatingYear," "Starrating," "TotalPoints," "CommercialOfficeArea," and "GFA." The results provide the statistical value, degrees of freedom (df), and significance (Sig.) for the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and the Shapiro-Wilk test. The null hypothesis for normality is rejected for all variables since they all return a value less than 0.05, which is the ideal threshold in normality tests. The use of Lilliefors' correction offers a more accurate assessment of normality by improving on the Kolmogorov-Smirnov, particularly when working with a smaller dataset. These results support previous descriptive statistics, particularly the large standard deviation and skewness shown in variables like CommercialOfficeArea, GFA, and RatingCateg. All of these findings support the use of non-parametric statistical techniques in follow-up analyses, guaranteeing robustness in spite of distributional anomalies.

Correlations										
			TotalPoints	Carparkingarea	RatingCate	LocationCoded	RatingYear	Starrating	CommercialOfficeArea	GFA
Spearman's rho	TotalPoints	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	0.134	0.232**	0.065	0.099	.852**	0.033	-0.080
		Sig. (2-tailed)		0.315	<0.001	0.187	0.118	<0.001	0.641	0.159
		N	419	58	416	419	253	350	208	312
	Carparkingarea	Correlation Coefficient	0.134	1.000	0.132	.314*	-0.242	0.150	.522**	.612**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.315		0.294	0.010	0.138	0.266	<0.001	<0.001
		N	58	66	65	66	39	57	59	61
	RatingCate	Correlation Coefficient	0.232**	0.132	1.000	0.074	-.183**	.268**	0.018	-0.024
		Sig. (2-tailed)	<0.001	0.294		0.115	0.003	<0.001	0.791	0.661
		N	416	65	454	454	271	374	222	332
	LocationCoded	Correlation Coefficient	0.065	.314*	0.074	1.000	.166**	0.100	0.026	-0.060
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.187	0.010	0.115		0.006	0.051	0.695	0.271
		N	419	66	454	475	273	380	225	335
	RatingYear	Correlation Coefficient	0.099	-0.242	-.183**	.166**	1.000	0.105	0.025	-0.010
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.118	0.138	0.003	0.006		0.103	0.769	0.888
		N	253	39	271	273	273	241	137	205

	Starrating	Correlation Coefficient	0.852**	0.150	.268**	0.100	0.105	1.000	0.047	-.136*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	<0.001	0.266	<0.001	0.051	0.103		0.533	0.019
		N	350	57	374	380	241	380	179	296
	Commerci alOfficeAr ea	Correlation Coefficient	0.033	0.522**	0.018	0.026	0.025	0.047	1.000	.866**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.641	<0.001	0.791	0.695	0.769	0.533		<0.001
		N	208	59	222	225	137	179	225	140
	GFA	Correlation Coefficient	-0.080	0.612**	-0.024	-0.060	-0.010	-.136*	.866**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.159	<0.001	0.661	0.271	0.888	0.019	<0.001	
		N	312	61	332	335	205	296	140	335

Table 4: Test for Nonparametric Correlations

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Since the study rejected the null hypothesis of normality for all variables. Table 4 illustrates a nonparametric correlation analysis conducted to establish the strength and direction of relationships between pairs of variables. Spearman's rho measures this for a non-normal distribution. There's a strong positive correlation between the Total Points and Star Rating, which is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), suggesting that using either of the two as our dependent variable would yield similar outcomes. The study preferred the star rating, which is consistent with previous studies like Hoffman et al. (2020). Other statistically Significant relationships identified include a moderate positive correlation between location and car parking area ($\rho = 0.314$; $p < 0.05$). Moderate positive correlation between Car Parking Area and Commercial Office Area ($\rho = 0.522$; $p < 0.01$), strong positive correlation between Car Parking Area and Gross Floor Area ($\rho = 0.612$; $p < 0.01$). There's a weak positive correlation between the Rating category and Total Points ($\rho = 0.232$; $p < 0.01$). Similarly, there's a weak positive correlation between Rating category and Star Rating ($\rho = 0.268$; $p < 0.01$)

Chi-Square Test for Relationship Significance

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	180.533 ^a	30	<0.001
Likelihood Ratio	78.169	30	<0.001
Linear-by-Linear Association	14.751	1	<0.001
N of Valid Cases	374		
a. 32 cells (76.2%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .01.			

Table 5i: Chi-square of Star rating and Rating category

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	0.695	<0.001
	Cramer's V	0.311	<0.001
N of Valid Cases		374	

Table 5ii: Symmetric Association of Star rating and Rating category

The results in Tables 5i and 5ii show a moderately significant association between rating category and star rating ($\chi^2 = 180.533$, $p < 0.001$). This suggests that certain rating categories are more likely to achieve higher rating scores than others.

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	45.922 ^a	32	0.053
Likelihood Ratio	35.080	32	0.324
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.069	1	0.793
N of Valid Cases	241		
a. 32 cells (71.1%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .01.			

Table 6: Chi-square of Star rating and Rating year

The results in Table 6 demonstrate a lack of significant association between Star rating and the rating year ($\chi^2 = 45.922$, $p = 0.053$). This suggests that certification scores do not improve or decline based on the year in which the rating was done. It could mean that rating requirements are not evolving sufficiently or that there is consistency in rating criteria.

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	507.695 ^a	507	0.483
Likelihood Ratio	322.965	507	1.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.349	1	0.555
N of Valid Cases	179		
a. 680 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.			

Table 7: Chi-square of Star rating and Commercial Office Area

Table 7 demonstrates no significant association between Star rating and the Commercial Office Area ($\chi^2 = 507.695^a$, $p = 0.483$). This suggests that commercial office space does not significantly improve the rating scores. While this use might be considered popular in the commercial property market, it does not get any preferential rating. This means that investors can confidently explore other uses for their investments in sustainable property.

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1108.923 ^a	1116	0.554
Likelihood Ratio	653.904	1116	1.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.004	1	0.950
N of Valid Cases	296		
a. 1400 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .02.			

Table 8: Chi-square of Star rating and Gross Floor Area

In Table 8, there's no significant association between star rating and Gross Floor Area ($\chi^2 = 1108.923$, $p = 0.554$). This implies that building size is not a determinant of certification outcome.

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	102.265 ^a	106	0.585
Likelihood Ratio	91.656	106	0.838
Linear-by-Linear Association	11.217	1	<0.001
N of Valid Cases	57		
a. 162 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .07.			

Table 9: Chi-square of Star rating and Car Parking Area

Table 9 demonstrates no significant association between Star rating and the Car Parking Area ($\chi^2 = 102.265^a$, $p = 0.585$). While larger buildings are more likely to have larger parking areas, this feature does not significantly influence certification scores. This raises questions regarding the rating criteria, which do not seem to consider larger car parking as evidence of transport-related sustainability issues.

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	332.921 ^a	135	<0.001
Likelihood Ratio	162.743	135	0.052
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.904	1	0.088
N of Valid Cases	380		
a. 150 cells (89.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .01.			

Table 10i: Chi-square of Star rating and Location

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	0.936	<0.001
	Cramer's V	0.419	<0.001
N of Valid Cases		380	

Table 10i: Chi-square of Star rating and Location

Tables 10i and 10ii illustrate a strong, significant association between location and star rating ($\chi^2 = 332.921$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting that locational differences impact certification outcomes. This is important for investors because it highlights the need to consider geographical bias in asset allocation for sustainability. The location sensitivity might be informed by differences in infrastructure, policy incentives, or investor priorities.

Starrating					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	40.373	27	1.495	2.479	<0.001
Within Groups	212.309	352	0.603		
Total	252.682	379			

Table 11: One-way ANOVA for Location

In Table 11, the ANOVA results confirm a statistically significant difference ($F = 2.479$, $p < 0.001$) in Green Star ratings across locations. This confirms that buildings in certain locations are more likely to score higher in the green certification. This also evidences a location bias, which might be the result of clustering patterns noted in Oladeji and Okoro (2024).

Discussion

Initial descriptive analysis showed that locations like Sandton, Cape Town, and Durban showed significantly higher certification rates. These are major urban hubs in the top three regions: Gauteng (42.5%), Western Cape (18.1%), and KwaZulu-Natal (8.4%). Not only does this show that these three provinces are the top adopters of green building certification. It also demonstrates that these green buildings are clustered around major urban areas. There is evidence of minimal inclusion of other provinces that account for less than 5% and international certification (Botswana). These findings can be explained by the high concentration of international and local business head offices and commercial hubs in these cities. This data provides preliminary evidence that commercial property location is an important attribute for green certification.

To ensure the robustness of the analysis, a normality test was conducted showing that all the variables selected for this analysis deviate significantly from normality. This informed the use of Spearman's Rho to test the relationship between variables. The strong positive correlation between the Total Points and Star Rating ($p < 0.05$) explains the use of the point assessment system as basis for the Green Star rating achieved by the buildings. This means that while these two variables are measured on different scales, they provide similar information regarding the outcome of certification applications. The study chose the star rating level as the dependent variable to maintain consistency with previous studies like Hoffman et al. (2020). Other statistically Significant relationships identified include a moderate positive correlation between location and car parking area ($\rho = 0.314$; $p < 0.05$). This suggests that certain locations are more likely to have larger parking facilities and, consequently, higher car usage. This can inform locational choices where investors want to prioritize uses that minimize the carbon emissions associated with higher car usage.

A moderate positive correlation between Car Parking Area and Commercial Office Area ($\rho = 0.522$; $p < 0.01$) infers that larger office area tends to have larger car parking spaces. This is also similar to the strong positive correlation between Car Parking Area and Gross Floor Area ($\rho = 0.612$; $p < 0.01$). These results can infer that the larger commercial properties tend to have larger car parking areas, which can be explained by the domination of these by office spaces. The weak positive correlation between the Rating category and Total Points ($\rho = 0.232$; $p < 0.01$) is comparable to the weak positive

correlation between the Rating category and Star Rating ($\rho = 0.268$; $p < 0.01$). It can be inferred from this result that rating levels can be infrequently higher or lower based on the category of the property between new buildings and major refurbishments, existing buildings, interior fit-outs, and sustainable precincts. However, this might not be strong enough to make a significant difference in the asset allocation's long-term plan, considering that a building can be recategorized based on subsequent certification applications.

The Chi-Square test shows a statistically significant relationship with a moderate association between rating category and star rating ($\chi^2 = 180.533$, $p < 0.001$). This confirms that certain rating categories might achieve higher rating levels, which suggests that investors need to assess category-specific information when determining certification potential. There's a lack of significant association between Star rating and the Rating year ($\chi^2 = 45.922$, $p = 0.053$), Star rating and the Commercial Office Area ($\chi^2 = 507.695^a$, $p = 0.483$), Star rating and Gross Floor Area ($\chi^2 = 1108.923$, $p = 0.554$), Star rating and the Car Parking Area ($\chi^2 = 102.265^a$, $p = 0.585$). This suggests that certification scores do not improve, or decline based on the year in which the rating was done, the size of the office area, gross floor area, or car parking size. These variables are not associated with any significant difference in the certification outcome. However, there is a strong, significant association between location and star rating ($\chi^2 = 332.921$, $p < 0.001$). The ANOVA testing confirm a statistically significant difference ($F = 2.479$, $p < 0.001$) in Green Star ratings across locations. It's possible to infer that locational differences play a significant role in the certification outcome and levels. This could be a result of the concentration of green buildings in urban areas. It highlights the potential for highly urbanized or commercialized locations to have greater incentives for adopting sustainability which aligns with the rental and sales premiums that green buildings have been found to attract.

Conclusions

This study aimed to assess the associations and significant relationships between commercial property attributes and Green Star certification outcomes in South Africa. A quantitative analysis was conducted using the GBCSA database of 510 certification reports to address the objectives, including assessing the influence of commercial building attributes on the likelihood of green certification success, determining the significance of specific commercial property attributes (e.g., Gross Floor Area, Commercial Office Area, Car Parking) to Green Star certification outcomes, and identifying key commercial property attributes associated with higher certification scores to inform asset allocation decisions.

Firstly, the study reported that location is a key influence on certification outcome and is an important attribute to consider for asset allocation decisions. Therefore, investors should use geospatial modelling approaches to prioritize locations with a higher likelihood of certification success. The results suggest that sustainability or green adoption is spatially uneven, which could be explained by differences in urban infrastructure, policy incentives, market maturity, urbanization, and other lifestyle preferences. This calls for targeted sustainability interventions, subsidies, and other financial incentives to promote dispersion in adoption in less likely locations, which other studies like Simpeh and Smallwood (2024) have recommended as well. This also aligns with signaling theory, demonstrating that green building certification aligns with certain property attributes, potentially adding to the value of the property (Zhang, Tu, and He, 2024; Van et al., 2023; Fuerst and McAllister, 2011). It further demonstrates that green building certifications can drive targeted responses to stakeholder concerns, a novel application of stakeholder theory in the built environment.

Secondly, the results show that building size does not significantly influence green building certification. This challenges conventional expectations and valuation practices, and emphasizes the

need to pursue sustainability as a function of environmental relevance and not merely as a function of scale. In hedonic pricing theory, this highlights the importance of testing specific attributes for the economic viability of property assets. Therefore, investors should not be limited to large property sizes in pursuing their sustainability goals. They should not assume that bigger buildings have a higher certification likelihood and vice versa. Furthermore, while parking size did not demonstrate a strong influence, investors should assess transport accessibility metrics in asset allocation. Commuting to work is an important consideration for urban residents. Larger parking spaces are critical evidence of transport-related sustainability issues, possibly a lack of proximity to work, which should be considered in decarbonizing commercial property portfolios.

Finally, the Chi-square and ANOVA results demonstrate that rating category is a significant factor ($\chi^2 = 180.533$, $p < 0.001$; $F = 2.479$, $p < 0.001$) for predicting certification outcomes. This means that investors should consider building typology to prioritize sustainability-focused asset allocation. On the other hand, the lack of any significant influence of rating year on certification outcomes raises concerns about the sufficient evolution of certification criteria. Investors should consider policy and rating criteria shifts to anticipate possible future shifts. Furthermore, regulators like the GBCSA should ensure continuously updating the rating system to reflect changing sustainability trends and requirements.

These findings are preliminary but may guide further research, including the use of logit and hedonic regression modelling of characteristics to predict certification outcomes and geospatial modelling of locational variances. The lack of expert opinions and additional primary data is one of the study's limitations that future studies can pursue. Future research analysing the impact of recognised architectural features on the Green Star rating would add to the knowledge.

Disclosure Statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors. Provide appropriate disclosure statement if there is potential conflict of interest.

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**Peer Reviewed*

Cyber-Physical Systems for Facilities Management: A Nexus Between Physical Assets and Digital Intelligence *Matthew Ikuabe*¹

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Abstract

Facilities Management (FM) is experiencing a notable digital shift as organisations strive for smarter, more efficient, and sustainable methods to manage built facilities. Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS), which combine computational and physical processes seamlessly, present a revolutionary way to meet the evolving needs of contemporary FM. This study examines the conceptual underpinnings, technological facilitators, current uses, and future directions of deploying CPS in FM. Drawing from various interdisciplinary research, this paper combines insights from innovative technologies driving the fourth industrial revolution. The review concludes that although CPS offers significant advantages regarding efficiency, sustainability, and occupant well-being, its widespread use encounters challenges. The study serves as a solid theoretical base for future studies geared towards the digital transformation of FM practices. Also, the study's outcome makes insightful contributions to the growing discussion of the digital transformation at the post-occupancy phase of buildings.

Key words: 4IR; Cyber-Physical Systems; Digital Technologies; Facilities Management; Post-Occupancy

Introduction

According to South African Facilities Management (SAFMA) (2012), facilities management (FM) refers to a process that supports sustainable enterprises concerning the comprehensive life management of organisations aimed at achieving productivity and practical business support. It is also characterised as “a practice that guarantees efficient operational management of buildings in both public and private sectors, encompassing a wide array of activities that range from strategic and operational planning to everyday physical maintenance, cleaning, and management of environmental performance issues” (Facilities Management Association of Australia, 2014, p.5). With these definitions of FM, it is crucial to recognise that it functions as a vital strategic element in fulfilling any organisation's key objectives.

The execution of FM tasks continues to face challenges due to inefficiencies and ineffective processes arising from outdated techniques and methods. Problems such as prolonged processing times, inadequate data collection, insufficient coverage of facility maintenance history, and low-quality control remain prevalent (Aldowayan et al., 2020). Additionally, Hudson (2004) observed that a primary challenge in delivering FM functions is difficulty keeping up with rapidly evolving innovative technologies. Given the numerous challenges in FM responsibilities, it is imperative to integrate modern approaches, such as digital technologies, into FM functions.

Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS) are computing systems that integrate computational capabilities and physical processes (Ikuabe et al., 2023; Yuan et al., 2016). As Gunes et al. (2014) stated, CPS represents a multidisciplinary, intricate, physically-aware generation of engineering systems that functions through integrating physical phenomena and embedded computing technology, utilising transformative systems. This integration mainly involves adding

observation, communication, and control segments to the physical component. The systems provide a foundation for addressing real-time issues by enabling the interconnection of various technologies, such as wireless sensor networks, control systems, real-time systems, and distributed systems (Lee, 2015; Ikuabe et al., 2024). For accomplishing tasks related to FM functions, CPS offers a framework that can assist in the coordination and monitoring of the components constituting a facility through real-time functionalities, stemming from the amalgamation of the system's virtual elements with technologies and networks and the physical facility (Terreno et al., 2020).

CPS have been utilised in sectors such as healthcare, manufacturing, aviation, mining, and agriculture. However, its application in FM is still in an early and disjointed stage, confronted with several technological, organisational, and regulatory hurdles. This study offers a thorough insight into how FM defines, executes, and assesses CPS. By examining existing studies published between 2010 and 2024, the study highlights current research patterns, theoretical models, real-world implementations, and prospective avenues for CPS in FM.

Applications of Cyber-Physical Systems

The advancement of digital technology has significantly improved the delivery of health care. Both patients undergoing treatment and medical personnel responsible for administering care have experienced the profound impact of technological progress. According to Milenkovic et al. (2006), innovations in wireless sensor networks (WSN), cloud computing, and medical sensors position CPS as a strong candidate for health care applications, including care for patients at home and in hospitals. With these technological advancements, there is a firm promise that patients' conditions can soon be monitored through CPS, regardless of geographical differences.

Kantarci (2015) presented a strategy for efficiently managing intelligent transport systems. The research created a model for route selection designed for paramedics, supported by implementing CPS, which includes components for user interaction, route selection, and alternative route optimisation. In emergencies where speed and timeliness are crucial, this helps guide paramedics to avoid unnecessary delays, such as heavy traffic. The combination of cyber systems with traditional transportation systems led to the term Transportation Cyber-Physical Systems (TCPS). This concept focuses on the monitoring, coordinating, and controlling of various transportation modes. The key components of a standard TCP include applications, cyberspace, and physical space. Cyberspace represents communication over interconnected computers, while physical space pertains to tangible occurrences in the real world. Achieving an intelligent transport system through CPS requires integrating advanced sensors with embedded computational systems technology, aligned with cellular, wireless, and satellite technologies for optimal traffic flow management, ensuring safety, and enhancing project situational awareness.

As production systems grow increasingly intricate to meet the rising consumer demand for advanced products, it is necessary to reorganise the processes and coordination involved in assembling the components that constitute the final product. Shafiq et al. (2015) emphasised that mechanical systems alone cannot ensure high-volume production, thus highlighting the importance of incorporating information and electronic technology within production processes. Heppelmann and Porter (2014) indicated the necessity of ongoing product monitoring and operational data analysis to enhance the efficiency of established service

systems and to develop new hybrid business models based on innovative, interconnected products. In the manufacturing industry, CPSs are highly recommended to achieve the objectives of Industry 4.0. Lee et al. (2013) claimed that integrating CPS with production, logistics, and services in current industrial practices would facilitate the transformation of existing factories into Industry 4.0 facilities with significant economic potential. The goals of the Fourth Industrial Revolution can be reached by combining advanced networks with intelligent production and processing systems. Given this perspective, CPSs play a crucial role in realising these objectives.

CPS has firmly established its role in the field of security. Its implementation in this area has aided in reducing crimes and facilitating monitoring private and public spaces. One such application is alarm systems. This system creates a connection through cyber links utilizing general packet radio codes with multiple access (Ma et al., 2010). With the introduction of mobile communication networks, a partnership has developed among communication control, terminal objects, and users. The alarm system detects the physical environment through the terminal object, which is then linked to the users. Conversely, the users can also control and monitor the physical environment through the alarm's communication system.

Conceptual Foundations of Cyber-Physical Systems for FM

Numerous FM systems are regarded as passive, relying on predefined rules; these systems struggle to adapt to evolving, flexible, and complex situations. It is undeniable that FM systems require proactive and contemporary intelligence reflective of cognitive capabilities. There is a significant need to create systems capable of effectively capturing and evaluating the dynamic interaction between users and facilities to address these issues. Notably, there is an increasing acknowledgement that the efficient coordination and oversight of FM management processes can be enhanced through advanced technological advancements (Terreno et al., 2020). A CPS approach can facilitate the coordination and supervision of facilities via real-time functionalities, arising from integrating the physical environment with virtual resources, networks, and technologies (Banerjee et al., 2022).

FM is recognised as trans-disciplinary or even multidisciplinary, incorporating knowledge from design, engineering, architecture, management, accounting, finance, and behavioural science (Teicholz, 2001). These functionalities significantly depend on human coordination to achieve the organisation's objectives. However, traditional CPSs fail to provide a precise quantitative assessment of the influence or effects of human input and control. This is mainly due to human contributions to the FM process's intricate, diverse, and uncertain nature. According to Lee and Seshia (2011), the significance of human operations in physical system interactions is not viewed as part of CPS. The capturing, analysing, and applying the human aspect in FM can be substantiated in managing and controlling facility performance through computational techniques and tools. This can be accomplished by developing interactive systems based on the interplay between physical and virtual systems (Yang et al., 2018).

Wu et al. (2014) state that the purpose of a cyber-driven FM is to enable FM components to perform cognitive functions such as perceiving, sensing, and interpreting the physical environment, allowing them to share observations and equipping FM entities with advanced intelligence. Huang and Mao (2017) noted that sensory data collection in various facility types in real-time can be achieved using wireless sensor networks (WSNs). Meanwhile, behavioural and movement data gathering can be accomplished through photogrammetry and

videogrammetry, along with the reconstruction of facilities using as-is and as-built digital models (Xu et al., 2020). Furthermore, Xue et al. (2018) highlighted that auto-identification technologies, such as QR codes and RFID, can be utilised in practical cases for real-time tracking, navigation, and localisation. Typically, the operations of such systems depend on components of computation, communication, and operational control. Usually, a four-tiered architecture of CPS can be implemented for FM purposes, encompassing sensing, processing, data fusion, and application.

Enabling Technologies for Cyber-Physical Systems in FM

CPS deployment in Facility Management (FM) is facilitated by various supportive technologies. At the forefront is the Internet of Things (IoT), which offers the sensory functionalities needed for CPS to engage with the physical world. IoT devices gather information on temperature, humidity, occupancy, and energy consumption, sending this data to centralised or dispersed processing units. Al-Obaidi et al. (2022) underscore the importance of IoT in forming adaptable environments that respond to user actions and environmental shifts. Building Information Modelling (BIM) significantly contributes to CPS-enabled FM as a digital archive of building architecture, systems, and operational details. When combined with real-time sensor data, BIM transforms into a fluid model that aids decision-making throughout the building's lifecycle. Banerjee and Nayaka (2022) point out that BIM delivers the spatial and semantic context needed to interpret CPS information and assist with maintenance, renovation, and space planning activities.

Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning are progressively integrated into CPS to provide predictive and adaptive features. Marzouk and Zaher (2020) argue that AI methods such as anomaly detection, clustering, and predictive analytics improve FM systems' capability to foresee failures, optimise resource utilisation, and customise occupant services. Additionally, the idea of the digital twin, a real-time updated virtual version of a physical asset, is becoming popular as a holistic CPS approach. Ghansah (2024) observes that digital twins offer a cohesive simulation, monitoring, and control platform, allowing FM professionals to explore scenarios and enhance performance without physical interventions. Cloud and edge computing serve as the computational foundation for CPS by enabling scalable data management and real-time analytics. Trigka and Dritsas (2016) outline the application of edge computing in minimising latency and boosting responsiveness by processing data close to the source, which is especially advantageous for urgent applications like emergency management and climate regulation in buildings.

Application Areas of CPS for FM

Incorporating CPS in Facility Management (FM) has resulted in various applications that enhance operational efficiency, sustainability, safety, and user experience. One of the key applications is energy management, where CPS facilitates real-time monitoring and regulation of HVAC systems, lighting, and plug loads. Qi et al. (2017) noted that CPS can optimise energy usage by responding to occupancy trends and external weather factors. Predictive maintenance is another vital area where CPS monitors the status of equipment and infrastructure elements to foretell failures and arrange timely repairs. Bonci et al. (2019) demonstrated that predictive maintenance minimises downtime and prolongs asset longevity, providing substantial cost savings compared to traditional reactive maintenance methods. CPS also enhances space utilisation and occupancy management by allowing for the flexible assignment of areas based

on actual usage. This is especially beneficial in flexible workspaces where space demand varies throughout the day. Azhar and Brown (2009) outlined how sensor data can guide space planning and decrease underutilization. Indoor environmental quality (IEQ) is yet another domain where CPS significantly improves outcomes. CPS can foster environments that enhance health, productivity, and overall well-being by continuously assessing air quality, temperature, lighting, and sound conditions. Shafaghat et al. (2016) contend that adaptive systems that cater to individual preferences can boost occupant satisfaction and lessen complaints. Additionally, security and access control systems have seen advancements through the integration of CPS. Kim and Hong (2017) explain how intelligent surveillance, automated locking systems, and integrated alarm mechanisms enhance building security while minimising the need for manual oversight.

Future Directions

The advancement of CPS is increasingly influencing the future of FM, offering the potential to revolutionise how buildings and infrastructure are managed, maintained, and optimised. As urbanisation speeds up and the appetite for smart, sustainable buildings increases, incorporating CPS into FM practices is becoming essential. Future developments in this area are expected to focus on improved system integration, enhanced data intelligence, and merging new digital technologies. One key future trend is the merger of CPS with digital twin technology. By uniting real-time sensor data and building systems with a dynamic virtual model, digital twins will facilitate more advanced simulation, prediction, and optimisation of facility operations. This combination will improve the decision-making abilities of FM professionals by enabling proactive measures and scenario planning. Digital twins can act as the operational foundation of CPS-enabled FM, offering a continuously updated depiction of building performance.

Conclusion

CPS signify a transformational approach to FM by presenting real-time assessment, intelligent control, and effective planning among the components making up the facility. This study has integrated current insights regarding CPS's technologies, uses, benefits, and future directions in FM. Although the potential benefits are considerable, such as efficiency gains, sustainability improvements, and enhanced user satisfaction, notable challenges are still hindering its implementation, especially from a developing country perspective. The abatement of these challenges would be driven by a combination of several forces, which include stakeholder collaboration, governance structures, setting up formidable policies to drive digital transformation, etc. The trajectory of FM depends on utilising CPS to develop flexible, resilient, and intelligent environments that address the changing demands of both organisations and society.

Notes on Contributors

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COVID-19 and the Real Estate Market – A PAGER Scoping Review *Rotimi Boluwatife Abidoye*¹; *Chibuikem Michael Adilieme*²; *Olalekan Shamsideen Oshodi*³; *Atinuke Adebimpe Orekan*⁴

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Abstract

The real estate market has been dominated by high prices, limited access and affordability, especially for young people and first-home buyers. The issues plaguing the market have been attributed to supply chain, migration, and the COVID-19 pandemic, to name a few. This study focuses on COVID-19 as a black swan event that has impacted the real estate market to draw insights that can help policymakers in property markets around the world. Accordingly, through a systematic manner, 101 journal articles on the COVID-19 pandemic and the real estate market were extracted from the Scopus database and reported using the Patterns, Advances, Gaps, Evidence for practice and Research recommendations (PAGER) framework to report the findings from the literature. The observable patterns include the impact of the pandemic on real estate prices and values, rent, indirect real estate and capital markets, demand, transactions, tourism, listings, time on market, migration patterns, response to the pandemic, macroeconomic indicators and interventions to moderate the impact of the pandemic. Overall, there were mixed (positive and negative) impacts on different property markets, with attempts to model and predict property prices to help investors and policymakers.

Keywords: COVID-19, Real Estate Market, Property, PAGER, Prices, Rent

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic, which began globally in the first quarter of 2020, is considered a black swan event that significantly impacted global property markets (see Ahmad et al., 2021). Black swan events are typically unexpected. Higgins (2013) posits that black swan events cause extensive destruction and, within the property sector, may affect the ability to forecast short-term property market elements. Information gleaned from the literature shows that the outbreak of disease led to a decline in house prices for brief moments before recovery (Wong, 2008; Francke and Korevaar, 2021). Also, this same pattern was observed during the Global Financial Crisis (GFC) (see Haffner & Hulse et al. 2021). This decline could be attributed to uncertainties in the economy, e.g. increases in the unemployment rate, or reduced demand for houses. Hence, it was expected that this same pattern would be observed during the outbreak of COVID-19.

Several studies have explored the impact of COVID-19 on house prices. Grybauskas et al. (2021) found that in Lithuania, contrary to expectations, the markets proved resilient and did not drop as expected. Belej (2021) and Trojanek et al. (2021) also found a form of resilience in the Polish market, bucking the prediction of a significant drop in housing markets. A similar trend was noticed in the USA (see Wang, 2021). Apart from displaying resilience, some markets such as Australia report a steep rise in housing prices between 2020 and 2022 by over 24% (Wong et al., 2024a). This increase was attributed to fiscal policy actions, including quantitative easing (Wong et al., 2024b). Australia makes an interesting case, given its reported

issues with rising property prices and housing market affordability (see Cho et al., 2021; Vij et al., 2021; Eacott, 2024; Wong et al., 2024b).

Accordingly, with reference to the expectation that COVID-19 would have a negative impact on the real estate market, and the evidence to the contrary in a few markets, this study reviews the literature related to the COVID-19 pandemic and the global real estate market with a view to identifying trends and patterns that drive actionable recommendations.

The findings of this review can assist academics and policymakers in reconsidering the narrative around COVID-19 and the real estate market, especially as it concerns the overly negative outcomes, which are not entirely absolute. In addition, the monetary and policy instruments applied in a few countries, which led to an ostensibly unintended upward trend in prices, bear caution for how black swan events are addressed.

Methods

According to Bradbury-Jones et al. (2022), a scoping review is a review method that allows researchers to map, describe and analyse a wider body of literature than a systematic review might allow while maintaining a more rigorous approach than that which is seen in a traditional narrative literature review.

Accordingly, this paper primarily follows the 5-step approach for conducting scoping reviews, as outlined by Arksey and O'Malley (2005). According to Arksey and O'Malley (2005), this involves first identifying the research question. The second is identifying relevant studies. Thirdly, selecting studies based on inclusion criteria. Fourthly, charting data and critical information. The fifth step is collation, summary and report of the results. In analysing the data and reporting the results, this paper followed the Patterns, Advances, Gaps, Evidence for practice and Research recommendations (PAGER) framework of Bradbury-Jones et al. (2022). The PAGER framework offers a consistent approach to presenting key insights and findings from scoping reviews (Bradbury-Jones et al., 2022). This method has been used for scoping review in the field of medicine (Moran et al., 2024), and property studies (Adilieme et al., 2023), among others.

To ensure transparency and replicability, the literature for the paper was selected using the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) framework of Page et al. (2021). PRISMA is a systematic review reporting guide for identifying, selecting, appraising and synthesising studies (Page et al., 2021). The Scopus database was used to extract the articles included in this study. The keywords used for the search included the following terms: (("housing" OR "house" OR "real estate") AND ("price" OR "value") AND ("Covid-19" OR "covid19")). Figure 1 shows the selection process and criteria; 1,325 results were initially obtained. However, the search results were restricted to journal articles published in English, leaving 101 studies for the review.

Figure

1: PRISMA flowchart of the selection procedure

Source: Authors' construct (2025)

Figure 2 presents the distribution of the publications selected for the scoping review by the year of publication. The highest number of publications was published in 2024, with 29 publications, followed by 24 publications in 2022 and 2023, respectively. The publication count has been growing since 2020, and there is no clear trend whether it will decline in 2025 (given studies for this study have already been identified).

Figure 2:

Distribution of publications selected, by year of publication

Figure 3 shows the share of the publications based on the case study countries of focus. Most (32) of the studies were conducted with the USA as the property market case study of focus, followed by China (16) and Poland (12). Others (20) refer to cross-country and region studies, including countries with a single count, such as Japan, Ireland, Ukraine, New Zealand, Portugal, and Hong Kong, among others. Surprisingly, there was no observed study conducted in any real estate market in Africa.

Figure 3: Distribution of publications, by country of focus

Findings

Five observable patterns emerged from the literature selected in this review. The observed patterns are:

- Impact of COVID-19 on housing prices and values
- Impact of COVID-19 on the rental market
- Other housing market issues, including impact on demand, transactions, tourism, listings, time on market, migration patterns, and response to the pandemic
- Macroeconomic indicators and interventions by different jurisdictions to moderate the impact of COVID-19
- Impact of COVID-19 on the REITs market.

The long-term direction of the impact of COVID-19 on the real estate market was not constant, and its impact was softened by government interventions through interest rates (Wong et al., 2024b), whereas in some markets, housing supply proved a factor in moderating the impact of the pandemic. Accordingly, both direct and indirect real estate showed a volatile, unpredictable relationship with COVID-19, and the effects differed across cities and locations. Studies highlighted that the markets did not behave as would be expected for black swan events (see Belej 2021; Grybauskas et al., 2021).

1 Patterns: Impact on housing prices and values

Advances: There is evidence of the COVID-19 impact on housing prices and values. However, the direction, positive or negative, differs across the different markets. Furthermore, studies (Allen-Coghlan & McQuinn, 2020; Cheung et al., 2021; Liu & Tang, 2021) in the immediate aftermath indicate a negative impact in property markets around Asia and Europe, whilst there seemed to be a positive impact in submarkets in the USA and other property markets in Europe (Wang, 2021; Trojanek et al., 2021). Studies highlighted that the price did not tend downwards as expected and the markets were resilient (see Belej 2021; Grybauskas et al., 2021); this could be due to policy interventions by government in different property markets around the world (highlighted in the following patterns).

Gaps: Whilst studies tend to show a negative impact of COVID-19 on property prices, the positive effect on property prices in some property markets makes it challenging to provide confident analysis on the impact of black swan events on property prices. Furthermore, given the unexpected behaviour noted in some studies, it presents an issue for predictions of property market behaviour in future, which will help different property market stakeholders in making informed decisions during periods of global pandemic.

Evidence for practice: Given the variations on the impact of COVID-19 on the property market, it presents a confounding situation as stakeholders cannot easily predict the direction of property prices. Furthermore, the expectation of the movement of property markets in a certain way in reaction to black swan events is under contention.

Research recommendations: Research scholars and policymakers can use different modelling techniques to evaluate the impact of government legislation on property prices during the COVID-19 pandemic period to identify the likely price reactions during future black swan events. In addition, the different variables and actions taken during the pandemic should be examined to identify their contribution to the property market outcome.

2 Patterns: Impact on housing rent

Advances: The majority of the studies focused on the impact on property prices and property values. However, there is evidence of COVID-19's impact on property rent. Firstly, the trends for rent appeared similar to the trend noticed in prices. Further, a few studies reported a decline in rent in the immediate aftermath of COVID-19 (see, Allan et al., 2021; Liu & Tang, 2021; Tomal & Marona, 2021), whilst the impact varied across different property sub-markets and property types. Furthermore, the studies reviewed indicated that rents were also impacted by government policy, population size, and supply.

Gaps: Similar to housing prices, it is challenging to accurately measure or model the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on property rents, as other macroeconomic and demographic variables affect the direction in which property rent will go during a black swan event.

Evidence for practice: Similar to prices, studies showed that rent will be impacted, but the manner of impact is dependent on the property market and a couple of other factors, such as demand and supply, household demographics, etc.

Research recommendations: Similar to prices, there is a need to identify dependent variables and modelling techniques that will capture the changes in rent due to the outbreak of pandemics. This information is vital for future planning (by all stakeholders), and it will be valuable to property investors in different property markets around the world.

3 Patterns: Other housing market issues: demand, transactions, tourism, listings, time on market, migration pattern, response

Advances: There was a relationship between population density and the impact of COVID-19 on property prices. A few studies indicated that the impact of COVID-19 on the housing market reduced as vaccination programs ticked up and lockdown mandates were relaxed (see, Cheung et al., 2021; Hu et al., 2021; Liu & Tang, 2021; Apergis, 2022; D’Lima et al., 2022). Furthermore, there was an indication of a change in the way real estate agents pursued transactions in reaction to the pandemic (see, Marona & Tomal, 2020), as well as a change in sentiment in properties in locations and around certain amenities that used to be in demand before the pandemic (see, Cheung & Fernandez, 2021; Duca et al., 2021; Li & Zhang, 2021).

Gaps: There were different reactions to the COVID-19 pandemic, including short-term rents, supply, transportation, etc. Whilst most studies focus on prices and rents, other important trends and behaviours can be identified from the housing market, showing how the COVID-19 pandemic impacted the real estate market beyond prices and rents.

Evidence for practice: The impact of COVID-19 is being felt in the real estate market beyond prices, including in choices in property classes and locations, transport, to name a few. Hence, it is important to note how people’s interaction with the property markets has changed due to the COVID-19 pandemic. More importantly, it is necessary to determine if those reactions persist as we move away from the pandemic period.

Research recommendations: Consider the different real estate market trends and behaviours resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic and how that influences demand for real estate.

4 Patterns: Macroeconomic indicators and interventions

Advances: To control the impact of COVID-19 on the real estate markets, the reviewed studies revealed that many governments around the world formulated deliberate policy measures on the macroeconomy and changes in interest rates, to moderate the impact of COVID-19 on housing prices (Zulkarnain et al., 2023; Akçay & Akyüz, 2024; Wong et al., 2024b). Furthermore, those property markets experienced an increase in property prices (see, Yiu, 2021).

Gaps: Policy interventions led to unintended outcomes in some property markets and exacerbated the housing prices and accessibility.

Evidence for practice: Timely macroeconomic policy interventions can soften the impact of black swan events on the housing market. However, there can be negative externalities, such as the skyrocketing property prices, which may be a second-order effect.

Research recommendations: It is essential to model how policy interventions can impact housing markets beyond the original intentions. That is, the ability to accurately model the impact of policy intervention on the housing market is essential for deciding on the "best" time to stop the intervention, to avoid the interventions being counterproductive.

5 Patterns: Impact on REITs and Capital Markets

Advances: There were comparatively few studies focused on the capital markets - REITs and CRE; these studies (Ling et al., 2020; Kowalski et al., 2023; Yoon et al., 2024) show that COVID-19 affected property portfolios on the capital market with variations across different property classes. Furthermore, some studies reported a decline in sales and profitability.

Gaps: Most of the reviewed studies focused on direct property holdings. Very few property studies assessed the impact on REITs. Given the size of the REIT markets globally and the unique nature of REITs, which may perform differently from other companies on the stock markets, it is important to understand how REITs performed during the period.

Evidence for practice: Given the linkage between direct property investment and REITs' performance, REITs may also not behave in the same way as other stocks on the capital markets.

Research recommendations: Analyse the behaviour of the capital markets and REITs during and after the COVID-19 pandemic.

Conclusions

The property markets around the world are generally impacted by numerous variables and factors such as economic headwinds, wars, pandemics, and trade wars, among others. This paper attempted to draw trends from the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the global real estate market, especially in light of property markets that attribute the challenges currently faced in the property market to the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic. Published journal articles that focused on the impact of COVID-19 on property markets around the world were extracted from the Scopus database and reviewed systematically. Through a scoping review reported via the PAGER framework, some trends emerged. The themes are - impact on property prices and property values, impact on property rents, impacts on other property-related factors such as demand, transactions, tourism, listings, time on market, migration pattern, etc., impact on macroeconomic indicators and interventions, and lastly, impact on REITs & Capital Markets. To sum it up, the review of the trends indicated that property markets reacted to the pandemic differently, and policy interventions led to a few unintended consequences. This study should be generalised with caution, because the studies reviewed were published when COVID-19 started up to 2025. If studies that were published before the COVID-19 pandemic started are added, the results could be different. Furthermore, the reviewed studies reported that

property markets did not behave as they were expected in times of black swan events, potentially indicating a change in how property market activities and outcomes should be predicted to aid decision-making. As a result, this study recommends assessing the predictability of housing market indicators in different property markets during the pandemic. This will help to establish the possibility of identifying tools that can help predict outcomes, especially in black swan scenarios, to help researchers and policymakers make more informed decisions with fewer far-reaching adverse effects. Also, because none of the articles retrieved were published in Africa, this creates a gap that needs to be filled. When the impact of COVID-19 on the property markets in Africa is examined, the results will allow for a comparison with other countries around the world.

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Disclosure Statement

The authors report no potential conflict of interest.

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**Peer Reviewed*

Reimagining Sustainable Facilities Management in Ghana: Integrating ESG Principles and Smart City Technologies for a Resilient Future *Abubakar Sadiq Mohammed*¹; *Timothy Oluwafemi Ayodele*²; and *Christopher Amoah*³

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Abstract

This study explores how Sustainable Facilities Management (SFM) in Ghana can be enhanced by integrating Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) principles with smart city technologies. Adopting a viewpoint approach, it offers an evidence-based perspective by synthesising secondary data and professional insights through a qualitative literature review. The topic is nascent in Ghana, with limited empirical data, requires multiple-disciplinary synthesis, and benefits from combining structured and scoping review methods to enable critical appraisal and forward-looking strategies. Peer-reviewed studies from databases such as Scopus, Emerald Insight, and Google Scholar were analysed using thematic coding on ESG frameworks, smart technologies (e.g., IoT, BIM, GIS), governance structures, and resilience strategies. Findings indicate that FM in Ghana remains largely detached from formal ESG frameworks, despite environmental, social, and governance challenges. Smart technologies present opportunities to operationalise ESG goals by enhancing energy efficiency, waste management, data transparency, and infrastructure resilience. However, barriers such as limited technical capacity, fragmented infrastructure, and high costs hinder adoption. Integrating locally tailored ESG metrics and fostering cross-sector collaboration are essential for effective SFM. The study contributes to academic discourse and practical policy development by highlighting pathways to embed ESG-aligned smart technologies, advancing resilience and sustainability in Ghana's FM.

Keywords: Sustainable, Facilities, Management, ESG, Smart City, Technologies, Ghana

1.0 Introduction

Facilities Management (FM) in Ghana must transition from reactive practices to proactive (Mohammed *et al.* 2025), strategies driven by Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) principles and supported by smart technologies (Yin, 2023). Mohammed *et al.* (2025) identify FM in Ghana as essential for enhancing user well-being, productivity, and operational efficiency. International Facilities Management Association (IFMA, 2024) asserts that FM supports sustainability by optimising building performance and user satisfaction within the

Architecture, Engineering, Construction, and Operations (AECO) sector (Rahman, 2025). Osei Assibey Antwi *et al.* (2024) argue that sustainability integration is crucial for Ghana's inclusive urban development. Lok *et al.* (2024) define Sustainable Facilities Management (SFM) as aligning environmental, social, and economic goals through energy efficiency, waste reduction, user comfort, and cost-effective maintenance. Karanasios, (2025) suggests that SFM supports institutional missions while advancing sustainability. Prabowo *et al.* (2021) link SFM to achieving SDG 11, creating inclusive, resilient, and sustainable cities. Ghana's infrastructural pressures highlight the urgency of aligning FM with national environmental and social goals (Akomea-Frimpong *et al.*, 2023; Mohammed *et al.* 2025).

Globally, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools are transforming FM (Gunasekara *et al.*, 2022). Lee *et al.* (2019) list Building Information Modelling (BIM), Geographic Information System (GIS), Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) and Augmented Reality (AR) as key innovations that increase efficiency and accuracy. Saraireh *et al.* (2020) explain that BIM enhances stakeholder communication; Liu *et al.* (2017) show that GIS aids spatial planning; Sulaiman *et al.* (2020) demonstrate that UAVs improve inspections; Williams *et al.* (2015) affirm that AR supports real-time decisions. Cheng *et al.* (2016) acknowledge challenges in applying these tools in low-resource countries, like Ghana. Osei Assibey Antwi *et al.* (2024) confirms that **Internet of Things (IoT) and Artificial Intelligence (AI)** and cloud computing enable predictive FM and data-driven decisions. These tools optimise energy, water, and space use. Yet, Dixit *et al.* (2019) identify interoperability and data limitations as barriers to BIM use. Also, Mohammed *et al.* (2025) attribute these challenges to inadequate infrastructure and inadequate budget, limited FM expertise, and insufficient institutional readiness in Ghana's public sector. Ghansah (2025) notes that Digital Twin (DT) technology enhances lifecycle decisions but faces adoption challenges. Lee and Lee (2021) warn of costs and cybersecurity risks. Tsaples *et al.* (2024) further cite outdated infrastructure, fragmented systems, limited funding, and skills shortages. Still, Bäcklund *et al.* (2024) emphasise DT's potential to support ESG-aligned space optimisation and energy conservation.

Globally, ESG frameworks are reshaping FM practices (Yin, 2023). Tahir *et al.* (2021) claim ESG promotes accountability and transparency. Muhamat *et al.* (2021) suggest aligning ESG with local values like stewardship and transparency. This enhances relevance in Ghana. As Alam *et al.* (2023) indicate, this alignment contributes to SDG targets amid climate and socio-economic risks. Metwally *et al.* (2019) argue that ethical leadership and culture are key to ESG

integration. Singhania and Saini (2023) report that public institutions face ethical and technical gaps. Kristijono *et al.* (2022) highlight leadership deficits as barriers to ESG adoption. In contrast, Gill *et al.* (2023) show that values-driven leadership enables ESG compliance. This paper proposes integrating ethical leadership with smart city technologies to guide Ghana's FM towards a proactive, resilient model.

Ojo *et al.* (2015) warn that rapid, unplanned urbanisation undermines sustainability. Kim *et al.* (2021) define smart cities as systems combining information technology, infrastructure, and social innovation to enhance efficiency and quality of life. Anthopoulos *et al.* (2018) describe smart cities across mobility, governance, environment, and economy. Catalano *et al.* (2021) stress the need for embedding sustainability in smart city design. Evans *et al.* (2019) recommend a Smart and Sustainable City and Communities (SSCC) approach focused on resilience, inclusivity, and environmental stewardship. Recent studies have explored how technological innovations support ESG objectives. Singh and Kumar (2024) identified strategic factors driving blockchain deployment in infrastructure development aligned with SDGs and ESG goals. Jensen *et al.* (2024) emphasised the role of FM in ESG reporting, highlighting FM's potential to drive sustainability through either compliance or strategic intent. Barykin *et al.* (2023) focused on smart city logistics, showcasing how digital tools can advance ESG outcomes. Most research centers on corporate or urban contexts, leaving a gap in reimagining SFM in Ghana: integrating ESG principles and smart city technologies for a resilient future. This gap is especially evident in the absence of frameworks that integrate ESG principles with smart city technologies to support resilient and SFM. It underscores the need to reposition FM as a strategic enabler of sustainability, resilience, and social value in the Ghanaian context. This paper adopts a viewpoint approach to explore how SFM in Ghana can be strengthened through the integration of ESG principles and smart city technologies. A viewpoint paper presents a well-informed, technically grounded perspective on a particular issue, supported by critical analysis of case studies, professional guidelines, and personal experience (Mohammed *et al.* 2025). Unlike original research articles, it is not based on new experimental data but relies on expertise, interpretation of existing literature, and unique insights to substantiate its position. Given the limited empirical data and fragmented ESG adoption in Ghana, this approach is particularly suitable. Drawing on secondary literature, professional insights, and contextual analysis, the paper examines the global best practices and their applicability to local conditions. RQ: *How can ESG principles and smart city technologies be effectively integrated into Ghana's FM practices to enhance sustainability, resilience, and governance outcomes?*

Addressing this question requires a multi-disciplinary synthesis spanning environmental science, governance, digital innovation, and infrastructure resilience. By combining structured and scoping review methods, the paper critically appraises current practices and proposes strategic pathways for embedding ESG-aligned smart technologies in Ghana's FM industry. Considering the research problem, the following are the objectives:

- 1) **To identify key challenges and gaps in the integration of ESG principles within**
- 2) **To explore the role of smart city technologies in enhancing ESG-driven sustainability and resilience in Ghanaian FM.**
- 3) **To propose strategic frameworks for effectively embedding ESG principles and smart technologies into FM for sustainable urban development in Ghana.**

2.0 Methods

This study adopts a viewpoint approach, grounded in secondary data, to critically explore how SFM in Ghana can be enhanced through the integration of ESG principles and smart city technologies. Rather than generating new empirical data, it reflects on existing literature to identify emerging trends, assess contextual relevance, and propose strategic directions for Ghana's FM industry. A qualitative literature review was employed, drawing on a dual-framework methodology that combined Okoli and Schabram's (2015) eight-step structured review process with Arksey and O'Malley's (2005) five-stage scoping review approach. This combination ensured both methodological rigour and broad coverage, making it suitable for analysing emerging concepts within Ghana. The literature search was conducted using scholarly databases including Scopus, Emerald Insight, and Google Scholar. Boolean search strings such as (((“Sustainable Facilities Management” AND “ESG” AND “Smart City Technologies” AND “Ghana”))) were applied to identify relevant studies. The inclusion criteria were: peer-reviewed journal articles and conference papers, with a focus on ESG integration, smart technologies, and SFM practices in Africa. Only articles written in English and available in full-text format were considered. To maintain academic credibility, theses, non-peer-reviewed reports, book chapters, and newspaper articles were excluded from the review. Data extraction was guided by thematic coding of key variables, which were synthesised into four overarching analytical themes: **(1)** ESG-Aligned Decision-Making, linking governance structures with environmental and social sustainability in FM; **(2)** Smart Infrastructure and Digital Transformation, focusing on the adoption of IoT, AI, BIM, and GIS to optimise FM operations; **(3)** Institutional Challenges and Opportunities, addressing resource limitations, capacity-building needs, and potential policy reforms; and **(4)** Contextual

Adaptation of Global Best Practices, examining how international FM standards such as those from Singapore and Dubai can be tailored to Ghana’s socio-economic realities. These themes were mapped onto Ghana’s FM landscape to identify key policy and practice gaps, assess technological and strategic opportunities, and examine alignment with international standards such as ISO 41001 and IFMA Core Competencies. The research question guiding the study was: “How can ESG principles and smart city technologies be effectively integrated into Ghana’s FM practices to enhance sustainability, resilience, and governance outcomes?” This question framed the synthesis of literature and enabled a comparative analysis of Ghana’s current FM practices against international benchmarks. The resulting conceptual insights are intended to inform strategic recommendations for advancing sustainable and resilient FM within Ghanaian public institutions, particularly in sectors such as education, healthcare, and administration.

3.0 Results and Discussion

This section presents the study's key findings, organised around the three main objectives. It highlights critical challenges, the transformative potential of smart city technologies, and proposes strategic pathways for integrating ESG principles into FM practices in Ghana, as indicated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Thematic Analysis Framework

Source- Authors’ Own Creation

Identifying Key Challenges and Gaps in the Integration of ESG Principles

The research uncovered a notable disconnect between existing FM practices in Ghana and the integration of ESG principles. While ESG principles have gained traction globally, supported by frameworks such as Global Real Estate Sustainability Benchmark (GRESB), Global

Reporting Initiative (GRI), and Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures (TCFD) and investments surpassing US\$23 trillion (Newell *et al.*, 2023). Ghanaian FM remains largely reactive and fragmented (Mohammed *et al.*, 2025). The key challenges include energy inefficiency, ineffective waste management, and poor climate resilience (Matheri *et al.*, 2020; Mohammed *et al.*, 2024). Furthermore, Ghanaian facilities lack structured sustainability models to guide ESG alignment (Lotsu, 2024), with existing global frameworks often ill-suited for local implementation due to infrastructural and resource constraints (Harahap *et al.*, 2023). The study also revealed institutional weaknesses, including inadequate policy enforcement, poor governance, and limited stakeholder engagement (Nameog and Abubakari, 2025). These gaps prevent the seamless integration of ESG practices into FM operations. Embedding ESG within FM is essential for addressing ecological and social issues, lowering operational costs, and achieving sustainability goals such as SDGs 7, 11, and 13 (Lok *et al.*, 2024). However, localised frameworks that reflect Ghana's socio-economic and infrastructural context are urgently needed to bridge the ESG adoption gap (Owusu-Ansah, 2024).

Exploring the Role of Smart City Technologies in Enhancing ESG-Driven Sustainability and Resilience

The study's second objective focused on the transformative potential of smart city technologies in reinforcing ESG-aligned FM practices. It emphasises that digital innovations such as IoT sensors, energy management systems, BIM, and **Computer-Aided Facilities Management (CAFM)** can drastically improve transparency, data analytics, and operational efficiency (Ghosh *et al.*, 2021; Edwards *et al.*, 2022). These technologies not only optimise resource usage but also enable predictive maintenance and emission tracking, supporting environmental sustainability and resilience (Argyroudis *et al.* 2022). However, despite the evident potential, the adoption of smart technologies in Ghana faces substantial barriers (Acakpovi *et al.*, 2019). These include high initial costs, limited technical expertise, unreliable energy supply, and fragmented digital infrastructure (Ullah and Sepasgozar, 2019; Ofori-Amoah, 2020). There also exists a cultural and institutional inertia against digital transformation in FM, as traditional practices persist and leadership in digital innovation wanes (Ba *et al.*, 2023). Furthermore, the lack of robust governance frameworks undermines efforts to ensure digital accountability and effective oversight (De Bruyne and Gerritse, 2018). Nonetheless, the study suggests that targeted smart solutions such as solar integration, smart meters, and digital monitoring could be pragmatically adopted in phases. These technologies, if coupled with local capacity-building

and public-private partnerships, can catalyse a sustainable FM ecosystem tailored to Ghana's needs (Akomea-Frimpong *et al.*, 2023).

Proposing Strategic Frameworks for Embedding ESG and Smart Technologies in FM for Sustainable Urban Development

To achieve meaningful transformation, the study advocates for a localised, multi-stakeholder strategic framework that aligns ESG principles with smart city technologies in FM. The proposed framework integrates three strategic imperatives: policy reform, capacity development, and cross-sector collaboration. From a policy perspective, FM practices in Ghana must be restructured to prioritise ESG goals (Vitoh and Serbeh-Boateng, 2025), aligning them with national development strategies and the SDGs (Saeed *et al.* 2025). Institutional accountability, budget transparency, and participatory governance must be central to this reform (Harahap *et al.*, 2023; Namooog and Abubakari, 2025). In terms of capacity development, the digital upskilling of FM personnel is essential. This includes training in the use of digital tools such as CAFM and BIM and fostering a culture of innovation to support adaptive and anticipatory planning (Ba *et al.*, 2023). Cross-sector collaboration is also vital. Engineers, ICT experts, urban planners, and community stakeholders must work together to co-develop smart, resilient, and inclusive FM systems (Kaginalkar *et al.*, 2022). ESG-aligned FM must also embrace indigenous values of stewardship, equity, and sustainability, embedding them into infrastructure planning and service delivery (Sirignano, 2025; Singh, 2025). Moreover, the study calls for the development of context-specific performance indicators and compliance mechanisms to monitor ESG implementation in FM (Shalhoob, 2025). Institutions should be incentivised through tax breaks, green financing, or certification schemes to pursue ESG-integrated practices (Kim and Lee, 2025). Ghana can draw inspiration from global ESG leaders while adapting innovations to local realities, thus reimagining FM as a cornerstone of sustainable urban development (Owusu-Ansah, 2024). The findings of this study underscore the urgency of reimagining FM in Ghana through the dual lenses of ESG principles and smart city technologies. While numerous challenges persist, ranging from infrastructural deficits to policy inertia, the strategic integration of ESG frameworks and digital innovations presents a viable pathway toward resilient, inclusive, and sustainable FM (See Table I). For Ghana to meet its urban development goals and international sustainability commitments, FM must evolve from a reactive operational role to a proactive, strategic function embedded in governance, technology, and ethical responsibility.

Table I: Strategic Intersections between FM and ESG Principles in Smart City Technologies for a Resilient Future for Ghana

ESG Principles	FM Strategic Focus Area	Relevance to Ghana (Smart City and Resilience)
<i>Environmental</i>	<i>Smart Energy Management</i>	Deploy solar PV systems, energy-efficient Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC), and IoT-enabled energy monitoring to reduce costs and improve energy resilience in facilities.
	<i>Water Conservation Technologies</i>	Utilise smart meters, leak detection systems, and rainwater harvesting to manage water sustainably in drought-prone and urbanising areas.
	<i>Smart Waste Management</i>	Implement digital tracking, smart bins, and recycling systems in schools, markets, and public institutions to foster circular waste practices.
	<i>Green and Smart Building Design</i>	Promote green construction codes and retrofit legacy buildings using eco-materials and automation for energy and resource efficiency.
	<i>Climate Resilience Planning</i>	Integrate GIS-based flood risk analysis, green roofs, and heat-resistant materials into FM strategies to protect vulnerable infrastructure.
<i>Social</i>	<i>Health and Wellness Technologies</i>	Enhance indoor air quality, sanitation, and thermal comfort through Indoor Air Quality (IAQ) sensors, smart HVAC, and touchless hygiene systems.
	<i>Inclusive Smart Infrastructure</i>	Ensure universal access via sensor-assisted accessibility tools (e.g., automatic doors, voice-guided navigation) in public and educational buildings.
	<i>Digital Community Engagement</i>	Use mobile apps, SMS platforms, and civic tech tools to involve local communities in planning, usage feedback, and maintenance roles.
	<i>Capacity Building and Digital Training</i>	Provide FM training on ESG integration, smart systems (IoT, BIM), and sustainable operations to prepare stakeholders for tech-enabled futures.
<i>Governance</i>	<i>ESG Compliance and Regulatory Alignment</i>	Align FM strategies with Ghana EPA, building standards, and global ESG disclosure frameworks (e.g., GRI, SASB).
	<i>Digital Transparency and Reporting</i>	Use real-time dashboards, digital twins, and performance analytics to report on ESG indicators and facility performance.
	<i>Sustainable Procurement Systems</i>	Leverage e-procurement platforms to source local, ethical, and environmentally certified products and services.
	<i>Risk Management and Resilience Building</i>	Integrate FM into national disaster preparedness, using predictive analytics,

		remote sensors, and continuity planning tools for asset resilience.
	<i>Smart Asset and Space Management</i>	Utilise CAFM, BIM, and IoT for real-time space optimisation, lifecycle cost analysis, and predictive maintenance in public assets.
	<i>Data Governance and Cybersecurity</i>	Implement a secure digital infrastructure to ensure privacy, compliance, and reliability in data from smart campuses and facilities.

Sources: Authors' Own Creations

4.0 Discussion of Findings

Objective 1: To identify key challenges and gaps in the integration of ESG principles within Ghana's FM industry

The study highlights significant structural and operational deficiencies that hinder the effective integration of ESG principles within Ghana's FM landscape. As Khan (2019) contends, there is a global push for ESG accountability driven by heightened stakeholder awareness and investment preferences. However, this momentum has yet to translate effectively into the Ghanaian FM context. The research reveals that existing FM practices remain fragmented and largely reactive (Mohammed *et al.*, 2025), with minimal strategic alignment to ESG benchmarks. Mohammed *et al.* (2025) and Matheri *et al.* (2020) point to inefficiencies in energy usage, inadequate climate resilience planning, and poor waste management as core issues. These concerns are compounded by a lack of cohesive policy frameworks and poor institutional enforcement, as also documented by Namooog and Abubakari (2025). While Aguilera *et al.* (2021) emphasise the value of robust ESG governance in driving resilience and long-term infrastructure value, Carmine and De Marchi (2023) caution that implementation barriers, especially at the board level, often arise from conflicting interests and limited stakeholder engagement. This tension is especially visible in Ghana, where FM decision-making often suffers from poor coordination and low transparency (Oduro, 2020). The study therefore, asserts that ESG frameworks must be localised to effectively reflect Ghana's socio-economic, regulatory, and infrastructural realities (Ko *et al.*, 2025). In line with Lok *et al.* (2024), the research stresses that embedding ESG principles in FM can facilitate the achievement of sustainability goals, particularly SDGs 7 (clean energy), 11 (sustainable cities), and 13 (climate action). However, it concludes that global ESG models must be adapted to fit the Ghanaian context, with tailored performance indicators and governance tools (Lotsu, 2024).

Objective 2: To explore the role of smart city technologies in enhancing ESG-driven sustainability and resilience in Ghanaian FM

This section of the discussion examined how smart city technologies can reinforce ESG-aligned FM practices, and the findings suggest a transformative but underutilised potential. Yigitcanlar *et al.* (2019) argue that smart city technologies without a foundation in sustainability are ineffectual, a position which this study affirms in the Ghanaian context. The research finds that digital innovations such as IoT sensors, BIM, CAFM, and digital twins are capable of enabling real-time monitoring, predictive maintenance, and data-driven decision-making, all of which are crucial for operational efficiency and sustainability (Ghosh *et al.*, 2021). Despite these opportunities, the study observes that Ghana's FM industry is yet to fully leverage these technologies due to systemic barriers (Twum-Bobie *et al.*, 2025). High upfront costs limited digital infrastructure, unreliable power supply, and a lack of trained personnel all serve as inhibitors (Ullah and Sepasgozar, 2019). Ba *et al.* (2023) highlight the cultural resistance to digital transformation, which is echoed in this study's findings on institutional inertia and the persistence of manual FM practices. Furthermore, De Bruyne and Gerritse (2018) argue that effective digital governance is a prerequisite for technological success, a point underscored by this study's identification of weak oversight frameworks in Ghana. Nevertheless, the research advocates for a phased adoption model whereby specific technologies such as smart meters, solar systems, and digital monitoring tools are gradually integrated into existing FM systems. Akomea-Frimpong *et al.* (2023) support this pragmatic approach, suggesting that tailored adoption, backed by capacity-building initiatives and public-private partnerships, could create a more sustainable and resilient FM ecosystem in Ghana. The study therefore, positions smart technologies not as stand-alone solutions, but as critical enablers of ESG compliance and urban resilience.

Objective 3: To propose strategic frameworks for effectively embedding ESG principles and smart technologies into FM for sustainable urban development in Ghana

In addressing the third objective, the study proposes a comprehensive, locally grounded strategic framework that fuses ESG principles with smart technologies in FM. Lindkvist *et al.* (2021) argue that the success of smart city initiatives depends on integrated policy, technical, and social frameworks, an assertion that this study expands to the FM domain. The proposed framework rests on three pillars: policy reform, capacity development, and cross-sector collaboration. Firstly, the study asserts that ESG objectives must be embedded in national FM policies and aligned with broader development agendas and SDGs. Harahap *et al.* (2023)

underscore the importance of policy coherence, institutional accountability, and inclusive governance factors identified by this study as central to reforming FM governance structures. Secondly, the research emphasises the urgency of equipping FM professionals with the digital competencies needed to navigate tools such as BIM, CAFM, and IoT platforms (Ashworth, 2021). Training initiatives and educational programs must therefore be prioritized to overcome the existing knowledge gap (Adhikari and Shrestha, 2023). The third pillar advocates cross-sector collaboration among engineers, urban planners, ICT specialists, policymakers, and local communities. Zurba and Papadopoulos, (2023) and Zidny *et al.* (2020) emphasise that sustainability solutions must integrate indigenous values and participatory approaches, a viewpoint that the study reinforces by calling for the contextualisation of ESG and smart technology practices. Furthermore, the study argues for performance-based incentives, including green financing and certification programs, to encourage the voluntary uptake of ESG practices across FM stakeholders. Drawing on global standards such as those of the OECD, GRI, and IFMA, the study contends that Ghana can adopt best practices while tailoring them to local challenges (Owusu-Ansah, 2024). Ultimately, it concludes that reimagining FM through ESG and smart city technologies is not a luxury but a necessity. Without this integrated approach, Ghana risks falling short of its urban resilience and sustainability targets (Mensah *et al.*, 2021). The study therefore, calls for a paradigm shift in FM from a narrow focus on operations to a broader, proactive, and strategic function rooted in ethical responsibility, technology, and governance.

5.0 Conclusion

This study presents important implications for research, practice, and societal development, particularly within the context of Ghana's evolving urban landscape and FM industry.

Implications for Research

The integration of ESG principles and smart city technologies in FM presents a fertile ground for academic inquiry. Future research can explore localised ESG frameworks that align with Ghana's socio-economic and environmental realities. This study contributes to bridging the theory-practice gap by contextualising global ESG benchmarks and smart FM models to the Ghanaian setting. It enriches the body of knowledge on sustainable FM in emerging economies and highlights interdisciplinary opportunities across urban planning, engineering, and governance.

Implications for Practice

Facilities managers and urban developers can use the findings to rethink FM strategies. The adoption of IoT, BIM, and digital twins can transform FM from reactive maintenance to proactive, data-driven decision-making. Local governments and Corporate Real Estate Management (CREM) professionals should implement ESG-aligned procurement, green building designs, and smart asset monitoring tools. Community engagement tools like mobile-based platforms and kiosks offer practical solutions for inclusive public space management.

Economic and Commercial Impact

Sustainable FM practices such as smart energy systems, efficient lighting, and waste reduction technologies can cut operational costs and attract ESG-conscious investors. Green design standards and local sourcing promote job creation, support the circular economy, and enhance long-term asset value. These solutions also increase the viability of public-private partnerships in Ghana's infrastructure industry.

Implications for Teaching

Curricula in FM and urban planning programs must integrate ESG and digital technology modules to equip future professionals with relevant competencies. Institutions can use case studies from this research to illustrate how theoretical concepts translate into real-world strategies.

Policy and Governance Implications

The study recommends actionable policy reforms, including the enforcement of green building codes, enhanced protocols, and the adoption of smart technologies for urban management. These insights can guide public institutions and policymakers in aligning national climate goals with local development strategies. ESG-focused governance frameworks promote accountability, transparency, and fiscal responsibility in public infrastructure management.

Societal Impact

By promoting equitable access to services, clean environments, and participatory planning, the integration of ESG and smart city approaches contributes to improved quality of life. Citizen-focused urban policy free from political interference can drive long-term resilience, social cohesion, and inclusive development. These outcomes are consistent with the Sustainable

Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities) and SDG 13 (Climate Action).

Reimagining FM in Ghana through ESG integration and smart technologies is vital for sustainable and resilient development. ESG principles align facility operations with environmental, social, and governance goals, reducing emissions, promoting inclusive design, and enhancing transparency. When localised and tech-enabled, they can transform public infrastructure into efficient, future-ready systems. However, this study is limited to Ghana and based on secondary data, which may affect generalisability and limit deeper contextual insights.

Limitations of the Study and Future Research Directions

This study relies on peer-reviewed literature and secondary data, offering theoretical insights but lacking real-time, context-specific evidence from Ghana's FM industry. The absence of primary data means stakeholder perspectives, operational challenges, and cultural nuances remain underexplored. The geographic focus on Ghana limits transferability to other contexts. Furthermore, some emerging digital innovations in IoT, AI, and BIM may have appeared after the literature review cutoff. Also, Future research should adopt mixed methods, including surveys, interviews, and focus groups, to capture stakeholder views and operational realities. Longitudinal studies could track the impact of ESG and smart technology adoption on efficiency, sustainability, and satisfaction. Comparative studies across African and global contexts, along with simulation models and pilot projects, would help test the feasibility and scalability of proposed strategies within Ghana's regulatory and socio-economic landscape.

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No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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**Peer Reviewed*

Access and Security to Land Through Cooperatives: Insights from Eswatini Women on Drivers, Barriers and Strategies *Cynthia Shabangu*¹; *Prisca Simbanegavi*²; *Koech Cheruiyot*³ and *Partson Paradza*⁴

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Abstract

Eswatini women face considerable barriers in their pursuit of land ownership, which are deeply rooted in a complex interplay of socioeconomic and cultural factors. As such, this paper aims to fill the knowledge gap regarding how cooperatives can act as mechanisms to improve women's access to land. A quantitative methodology was employed, with structured questionnaires distributed to 92 women from seven cooperatives, and the data were analyzed through descriptive statistics and chi-square tests. The paper adopted a quantitative approach and administered questionnaires to women in seven cooperatives. The paper established the critical role that land acquisition plays in enhancing women's economic status, as driven by various factors, such as the need to acquire land to embark on entrepreneurial initiatives that emerged statistically significantly. However, several barriers (statistically significant) hamper the possibility of crowdfunding to enhance women's economic status. The findings reveal that while land ownership is closely associated with economic empowerment, food security, and asset accumulation, women face considerable challenges such as insufficient income, lack of collateral, and restrictive land tenure laws. The study concludes that specific reforms, especially supportive legal frameworks, financial innovations like crowdfunding, and gender-sensitive cooperative models, are essential for promoting women's land rights and empowerment in Eswatini. Financial assistance programs tailored to women's unique needs can also play a crucial role in providing the necessary resources for land acquisition and sustainable development.

Key words: Land Acquisition; Women; Cooperatives; Drivers; Eswatini

Introduction

The rising global demand for commercial and industrial infrastructure has led to significant real estate investment, especially in the residential sector. In rapidly developing economies like China, India, and South Korea, foreign investments have positively impacted market growth (Shahrokhi & Parhizgari, 2020). However, domestic investment remains limited, creating opportunities for women in the sector. The real estate investment landscape includes three dimensions: distribution channels, property types, and investment purposes. Distribution channels consist of public and private investments, similar to trends in Eswatini (Malaga et al. 2018). Property types include commercial, residential, industrial, and land, with commercial investments further divided into retail, office, and recreational spaces (Malaga et al. 2018).

The demand for private capital in real estate is increasing in emerging economies like Eswatini, where urban migration, population growth, and a rising middle class increase the need for urban real estate investments (PWC, 2020; FSRA, 2022). However, high capital requirements pose barriers for many women, particularly those with low incomes (FAO, 2011; World Bank, 2012). Funding sources for real estate investments include traditional bank loans, private lenders, hard money lenders, partnerships, seller financing, and crowdfunding (Shahrokhi &

Parhizgari, 2020; Legenzova & Leckè, 2022). Land-related challenges in Eswatini significantly affect real estate investments, as the King holds all land in trust for the people, and non-residents face land access restrictions (UN Women, 2020). Women can only own land through a child, and most land is classified as Swazi Nation Land (Mutangadura, 2004; Kachika, 2009). To navigate these challenges, women in Eswatini can employ various strategies, such as building networks, fostering collective action, education, and engaging with local and national policymakers (Jacobs, 2004; Rüniger, 2006). Crowdfunding platforms can offer a unique financing option for women in Eswatini, allowing them to access capital for land acquisition and share their stories and projects (Adjakou, 2021; Kunz et al., 2018). The paper focuses on the problem of poor investment in real estate, particularly among women in Eswatini, and the secondary research questions include the drivers of land acquisition for women in stokvels/cooperatives, the barriers faced in acquiring land, and strategies to improve land acquisition efforts. To conceptually frame this study, we utilize Empowerment Theory, specifically Rappaport's (1981) focus on collective action as a strategy for tackling structural inequalities. Empowerment Theory underscores the mechanisms by which marginalized groups obtain resources, enhance their control over decisions that impact their lives, and realize social justice outcomes. In the context of women's cooperatives in Eswatini, this theory serves as a valuable perspective for comprehending how collective agency can confront discriminatory land tenure systems, alleviate financial obstacles, and foster sustainable approaches to land ownership.

Literature Review

Empowering Women Through Land Ownership

Land ownership significantly enhances women's economic empowerment by creating avenues for income generation, asset accumulation, and entrepreneurial ventures. It acts as collateral for obtaining credit and capital, which facilitates the initiation or expansion of businesses. Furthermore, land ownership contributes to food security, as it enables women to participate in agricultural practices to produce food for their families and communities. Additionally, owning land opens opportunities for diversifying income sources through activities such as livestock farming, horticulture, and agro-processing (FAO, 2012). The provision of ownership rights is crucial for the sustainable advancement of agriculture, given that land is a vital resource influencing the economic welfare of peasants (Roy and Tisdell, 2002). Nonetheless, institutional biases persist in numerous developing countries, often privileging men. Land ownership can enhance self-esteem and provide both physical and psychological security, therefore, safeguarding women's land rights may help reduce gender inequalities and diminish women's dependence on men for their livelihoods.

Stability in land tenure is linked to improved food security, particularly for women. Securing and respecting women's land rights can enhance a family's overall access to resources necessary for nutrition and food security, thereby increasing agricultural productivity and promoting shared decision-making within households (Allendorf, 2007). Research indicates that female farmers perform on par with their male counterparts and would achieve similar yields if granted equal access to resources and services. As noted by Agarwal (2007), women's land rights in South Asia empower them to negotiate for less restrictive norms and improved treatment from their spouses.

Barriers to Obtaining Land for Women in Cooperatives

Discriminatory legal frameworks and customary practices often limit women's land ownership and access. Poor enforcement of land laws, along with a lack of financial resources and awareness of funding options like crowdfunding, worsen these challenges (Mubuu, 2013). Sociocultural factors, such as restricted mobility and limited decision-making power, further impede women's ability to secure land. For instance, Saudi Arabia has the lowest female land ownership rate globally, despite women having legal rights under Sharia law (FAO, 2016; Almazi, 2016). Cultural norms favor men in inheritance, and women's educational disadvantages hinder their land acquisition, often leading them to forfeit inheritance to their husbands. In Kenya, cultural resistance to women's land ownership is significant, with 49% of the population opposing it and fewer than 12% believing in women's equal rights to land (Mwagae, 2013). Evidence shows gender disparities in land access, with women less likely to own or manage property or control agricultural resources (FAO, 2011; Deere et al. 2011).

Gender inequality persists in Africa and parts of Asia, with women facing significant barriers to land ownership. In Eswatini, only 20% of landowners are women, a trend worsened by diverse social and economic contexts that restrict women's access to land. Runger (2006) highlights those complex legal systems in Ghana and Kenya disadvantage women in property rights, compounded by lower income and literacy rates. Legal challenges related to marriage and sharecropping further hinder their access. Research indicates that land property rights can empower women and help combat poverty. Mutangadura (2004) identifies the exclusion of women from property ownership as a severe human rights violation, while Kachika (2009) emphasizes the need for women to have full access to land to reduce poverty and meet the Millennium Development Goals.

In Uganda, women are key agricultural producers but face significant challenges in accessing and owning land. Agarwal (2003) notes a "lack of a voiced demand" for independent land rights, with studies focusing more on racial disparities than gender issues. Prevailing gender attitudes affect women's perceptions and use of land, hindering their advancement. This challenge is common in rural areas across Africa, South Asia, Latin America, and the Caribbean. Although customary law in Latin America is less restrictive than in Saudi Arabia, women still face barriers to land ownership due to legal and social frameworks. Historically, while women had land rights, titles were often held by their husbands, and agricultural reforms in the 1970s recognized men as primary producers, reducing women's bargaining power in global markets.

Techniques to Enhance Women's Land Acquisition in Cooperatives

Gender-sensitive land legislation is vital for protecting women's rights and preventing discrimination, requiring transparent title acquisition processes and supportive institutional frameworks (USAID, 2008). Several countries have adopted reforms to strengthen women's land rights: Tanzania guarantees equal succession and marital property rights; Ethiopia includes both spouses on joint land titles; and Guatemala, India, and Mozambique mandate co-registration or recognize women's equal rights to use land. Such measures address poverty, food insecurity, and social inequalities (Stanley et al., 2012). Beyond legal reforms, improving literacy, public awareness, and education empowers women to claim their entitlements. At the same time, crowdfunding has emerged as an innovative strategy to enhance women's land ownership by mobilizing resources and building social networks, though challenges such as high campaign costs remain.

Theoretical Literature Review

The theoretical foundation of this study is anchored in two complementary perspectives, African Feminist Theory and Empowerment Theory.

African Feminist Theory

African Feminist Theory was developed by African women to address their specific socio-cultural challenges and challenge patriarchal systems that perpetuate gender inequality. It emphasizes egalitarian relationships between men and women and aims to dismantle oppressive structures limiting women's access to vital resources like land. This theory highlights that women's marginalization in property ownership is not just an economic issue but is also rooted in cultural, legal, and institutional practices. It critically examines discriminatory inheritance customs, restrictive land tenure systems, and male-dominated decision-making, underscoring the importance of collective action, solidarity, and advocacy for equitable land rights (Jacobs, 2004; Kachika, 2009).

Empowerment Theory

Rappaport (1981) introduced an empowerment theory that serves as a framework for understanding how marginalized groups gain control over their lives through engagement, resource access, and increased awareness. It defines empowerment as both a process where individuals build capacity and agency, and an outcome, reflected in improvements in economic and social status. For women in cooperatives, empowerment manifests through collective agency, allowing them to tackle challenges like restrictive tenure laws and financial exclusion. Cooperatives illustrate Rappaport's idea of 'power through collective action,' creating pathways for women to secure land rights, enhance food security, and promote community development. This research uses Empowerment Theory to frame women's land struggles within a broader context of resilience and structural change.

Complementary Theories of Crowdfunding

This study integrates feminist and empowerment frameworks with theories explaining motivations for crowdfunding participation, a key financing method for land acquisition. Social identification theory posits that individuals are more likely to support causes that resonate with them (Bamberger & Webb, 2015). The theory of planned behavior highlights how positive attitudes, social norms, and perceived control influence contributions. Social exchange theory points to non-monetary benefits like social recognition and emotional satisfaction, while cognitive evaluation theory stresses the importance of perceived value in motivating contributions (Smith & McKeen, 2012). Together, these theories clarify how crowdfunding can empower women in cooperatives to secure resources for land acquisition and community development.

Synthesis

Feminist Theory and Empowerment Theory form the core framework of this study, situating women's land rights within broader themes of social justice, agency, and gender equity. Additionally, crowdfunding participation theories enrich this framework by offering insights

into innovative financial strategies that can overcome structural barriers and enhance empowerment outcomes.

Conceptual Framework

This study identifies several barriers to women's land ownership, including discriminatory legal frameworks, inadequate land laws, insufficient financial capital, and gender norms. It also highlights the need for policies to ensure equal access to land for both males and females. The study concludes that crowdfunding can be a powerful tool for women in cooperatives to acquire land, thereby promoting economic empowerment and gender equality.

Conceptual Framework (Source: Authors)

Methods

The study focuses on the question: "What key factors, challenges, and strategies affect women's access to land through cooperatives in Eswatini?" While primarily quantitative, future studies could enhance understanding by incorporating mixed methods to capture personal narratives behind the data. This study used a quantitative methodology, collecting data through a structured questionnaire with closed-ended questions about land acquisition among women in cooperatives. The questionnaire was distributed to seven cooperatives: Lubane, Bunye Betfu Buhle Betfu, SNAT, Uneswa-Luyengo, Impumelelo, Sibonelo, and Eswatini Rural Women Assembly, targeting approximately 9,150 members (Kamar, 2019). To reduce sampling bias, simple random sampling was applied, with the sample size calculated using a specific formula.

$$n = Z^2(p(1-p)/ME^2), \tag{equation 1)}$$

where n is the sample size, Z² is the z-score, p is the proportion of individuals who are members of a cooperative (usually equal to 0.5), and ME is the margin of error.

From equation 1, it was determined that the optimal sample size was determined to be 92 respondents, selected randomly from the cooperative membership list based on their availability for telephone interviews. The research was conducted with a 95% confidence level and a 10% margin of error, with a proportion set at 60% (Creswell, 2017).

Ethical considerations were crucial for maintaining research integrity, involving permissions from cooperatives, a cover letter outlining the study's purpose, confidentiality measures (no names on questionnaires), and anonymization of data. Potential conflicts of interest were managed by allowing participants to disclose them freely. The questionnaire was translated from English to Siswati to address language barriers.

To ensure validity and reliability, a pilot study was conducted, and the Cronbach alpha (α) coefficient was applied (Finfgeld-Connett & Johnson, 2018; Middleton, 2019), with a score above 0.7 indicating the effective measurement of the intended variable.

Data Analysis and results

The study applied descriptive analysis and chi-square tests of association to determine the significance of different variables on land acquisition among women. Charts and graphs were used to present the data visually, where applicable. Data was captured and analysed using SPSS 20.

The study received 93 complete questionnaires, indicating a 100% response rate since the anticipated sample size of 92 respondents. Demographic information of participants was also discussed, including age, education level, and monthly income. Presentation of results includes demographic and socio-economic analysis, drivers, barriers, and strategies related to land acquisition among women in cooperatives. Discussion of drivers and barriers incorporates chi-squared tests of association to establish significant drivers and obstacles related to land acquisition among women in cooperatives.

Demographics and Socio-economic Analysis

Many respondents were aged 31 to 40 years, followed by those aged 41–45 and over 50 years. Nearly half (42%) of the respondents earned more than E6000 per month, categorizing them as high-income earners. Alongside the second-largest group earning between E4001 and E6000 (moderate-income), these two categories together accounted for 72% of the sample, indicating that most participants have moderate to high earnings. A smaller group earning between E2001 and E4000 falls into the middle-income bracket, with steady yet limited financial capacity. The smallest group, likely to earn below E2000, reflects low-income respondents who may face economic hardship and need additional support.

Figure 2. Demographic and socio-economic status of respondents

Drivers of Land Acquisition Among the Women in Cooperatives

This section explores the factors driving land acquisition among women in cooperatives in Eswatini. Figure 3 shows key drivers, including enhancing income, achieving economic empowerment, increasing asset accumulation, securing access to credit, ensuring household food security, affirming self-worth, maintaining independence, and pursuing entrepreneurial activities that motivate land acquisition among women in cooperatives. One key result is that the majority, composed of “strongly agree” and “agree”, of respondents identified all the drivers in Figure 2 as motivating them to acquire land.

Figure 3. Drivers of Land Acquisition Among Women

Economic Empowerment and Income Generation

Land ownership plays a crucial role in enhancing women's economic status, enabling them to actively engage in entrepreneurial ventures and agricultural production. The results indicate that a majority (83%) of participants identified economic empowerment and income generation as major motivating factors for acquiring land. This aligns with Kachika (2009), who states that complete control over land is necessary for the decrease of poverty and the fulfillment of the Millennium Development Goals. The empowerment not only allows women to generate income but also fosters a sense of agency and control over their financial futures. By owning land, women can cultivate crops, raise livestock, and explore various business opportunities,

thereby contributing to their households' economic well-being and the broader community (FAO, 2013).

Asset Accumulation

For a majority (88%) of the women surveyed, land is perceived as a vital asset that significantly contributes to their financial stability. Ownership of land provides women with a tangible resource that can be leveraged for economic advancement. Specifically, land can be used as collateral for loans, which facilitates access to credit and enables women to make additional investments in agriculture or small-scale businesses. As noted by Doss et al. (2011), women's authority over land directly influences their capacity to accumulate assets, thereby enhancing their bargaining power within households and communities. The security afforded by landownership enables women to engage in long-term planning, make independent financial choices, and mitigate their vulnerability to economic shocks. Consequently, land serves not merely as a productive asset but as a cornerstone for empowerment, resilience, and sustainable development for women.

Asset to credit

Access to credit is a vital element that affects women's capacity to obtain land. In this research, 67% of the women interviewed concurred that land ownership improves their chances of obtaining loans, indicating that land serves not only as a productive asset but also as significant collateral within formal financial frameworks. Nevertheless, women frequently encounter systemic obstacles when pursuing loans or other financial services, primarily due to gender biases, insufficient collateral, and inequitable inheritance rights. The World Bank (2012) emphasizes that women experience discrimination in land markets and credit systems, which limits their involvement in both redistributive reforms and land acquisition through purchase.

Food Security

Land ownership is directly linked to food security, especially for rural women in Eswatini. Secure access to land enables women to engage in agriculture, ensuring a reliable food supply for their families. In this study, 8 out of 10 of the women interviewed identified land as essential for food security, underscoring its role in sustainable livelihoods. This aligns with the FAO (2012), which states that women's land ownership enhances food security by enabling crop production and livestock rearing. Secure land tenure encourages women to adopt sustainable farming practices, improving productivity and resilience to food shortages. In Eswatini, where agriculture is vital and food insecurity is prevalent, women's access to land is crucial. It reduces dependence on external food sources, improves nutrition, and strengthens women's economic status in their families and communities (FAO, 2012; Slaymaker & Rowlands, 2012).

Self-Worth and Independence

Land ownership significantly enhances women's self-esteem and independence, particularly in settings where they face systemic barriers to economic participation. In this study, two-thirds of the women indicated that owning land is a major motivator, symbolizing autonomy and the ability to make impactful choices for themselves and their families. The (RDI, 2009) notes that land ownership fosters self-worth and provides security, enabling women to plan and engage more actively in their communities. Rao (2005) argues that property rights can reduce gender inequalities and lessen women's economic dependence on men, despite ongoing institutional discrimination. Jacobs (2004) highlights that in traditional societies like Eswatini, land often

symbolizes male dominance, making women's access to it fraught with social and legal challenges (Mutangadura, 2004). Duflo (2012) adds that cultural norms often keep men in key decision-making roles, even when women have legal property rights. Thus, land ownership can significantly enhance a woman's bargaining power, improving her economic outcomes, self-worth, and social standing.

Entrepreneurship

Land acquisition is crucial for entrepreneurship, with nearly half of women acknowledging its importance for starting businesses in agro-processing, livestock farming, and agriculture. Owning land provides women with resources to cultivate crops, raise animals, and create value-added products, leading to sustainable income. FAO (2011) notes that land ownership can serve as collateral for loans, enabling women to expand their businesses and explore new opportunities. This entrepreneurial participation not only promotes individual financial independence but also contributes to community development and economic growth. Mutangadura (2004) highlights that improving women's land tenure in Southern Africa, including Eswatini, can lead to job creation and poverty alleviation. Women's entrepreneurship empowers them and positively impacts community development as they reinvest in their families and inspire other women (Doss et al. 2007).

A further step using the chi-square analysis was made to test the relationship between crowdfunding as a solution to financing and the drivers of land acquisition among the women in stokvels/cooperatives. The correlation results measuring the relationship between crowdfunding as a solution to financing and the drivers of land acquisition among the women in stokvels show that none of the constructs of the drivers were statistically significant at $p < 0.05$ (Table 1). However, the need to acquire land to embark on entrepreneurial initiatives was statistically significant, $p < 0.1$. In this latter case, it implies that there is a strong positive relationship between crowdfunding as a solution to financing and the need to acquire land to embark on entrepreneurial initiatives, as depicted in Table 1. Simply, those who considered crowdfunding were also interested in acquiring land to embark on entrepreneurial initiatives.

Table 1. Chi-square test of association between crowdfunding as a solution to financing and the drivers of land acquisition among the women in stokvels/cooperatives

Drivers	Chi-Square Statistics	
	Coefficient	P-Value
I need to acquire land to improve my income level and for overall economic empowerment.	7.531	0.582
I need to acquire land to improve my asset accumulation.	11.999	0.213
I need to acquire land to facilitate access to credit	9.796	0.367
I need to acquire land to ensure food security in my household.	10.547	0.568
I need to acquire land to validate my self-worth.	15.671	0.207
I need to acquire land to maintain my independence and dignity.	15.405	0.22
I need to acquire land to embark on entrepreneurial initiatives	19.51	0.077

Barriers to Land Acquisition for Women in Cooperatives

Women involved in cooperatives face a multitude of challenges when it comes to acquiring land. These obstacles not only hinder their aspirations but also limit the overall potential of cooperatives to thrive and contribute to community development. Figure 4 shows the key obstacles to land ownership by women in cooperatives.

Figure 4. Obstacles to Land Acquisition for Women in Cooperatives

Financial Limitations

A significant barrier to land acquisition for women is financial constraints. A staggering three-quarters (77%) of participants in the survey cited low earnings as the foremost challenge, highlighting the broader difficulties encountered by women who are mainly involved in informal employment and subsistence agriculture. These fields generally provide limited and unstable income, hindering women's ability, particularly those in cooperatives, to save enough for land purchases. This financial instability is further intensified by limited access to credit, as numerous women do not possess the formal employment, credit history, or collateral that traditional banking institutions require.

Studies conducted by FAO (2011) and the World Bank (2012) validate that women in rural and informal sectors frequently experience systemic financial exclusion due to deep-rooted gender disparities in credit markets and institutional bias. In Eswatini, the scenario is further complicated by a dual legal system that may compromise women's financial autonomy and property rights under customary law (UN Women, 2020). In the absence of specific reforms aimed at fostering gender-sensitive financial inclusion, women continue to be structurally disadvantaged in land markets, which restricts their capacity to accumulate wealth and break free from cycles of poverty (Deere et al. 2011).

Cultural Norms and Gender Disparities

Cultural norms and deeply entrenched patriarchal traditions in Eswatini pose significant challenges to women's rights to land ownership. Over half (56%) of the respondents acknowledged that societal attitudes and resistance to women's property rights create an environment where women are discouraged from pursuing land ownership. This confirms the (Mutangadura, 2004) argument that women's land rights continue to face significant discrimination. These cultural barriers not only affect women's confidence but also perpetuate

the notion that land ownership is primarily a male domain, further marginalizing women in the agricultural and economic landscape.

Legal and Institutional Barriers

The complexity of land tenure systems and restrictive policies disproportionately affect women. More than half (54%) of respondents highlighted land tenure regulations as a significant challenge. Relating to other studies, this supports that inadequate implementation and enforcement of existing land laws hinder women's ability to acquire and secure land (Mubuu, 2013). The lack of legal acknowledgment often results in women being unable to claim land that they may have worked on or contributed to, thereby perpetuating cycles of poverty and inequality.

Insufficient Collateral and Awareness of Funding Options

The inability to provide sufficient collateral is another major hurdle for women seeking loans for land acquisition. Many women lack valuable assets that could be used as security for loans, which limits their borrowing capacity. Additionally, there is a notable gap in awareness regarding alternative funding options, such as crowdfunding or community-based financing initiatives. This lack of knowledge further restricts women's opportunities to explore diverse financial avenues that could facilitate land acquisition.

Level of Education

Education plays a crucial role in empowering women to engage in land acquisition activities. According to a study focused on the Khwisero Constituency in Kenya's Kakamega County, a lack of knowledge was the biggest obstacle to women owning land there (Gail, 2016). In contrast to this study, many respondents did not perceive education as a barrier; only a notable 24% highlighted that lower literacy rates and limited legal knowledge pose significant challenges (Rünger, 2006). Women with lower levels of education may struggle to navigate the complexities of land acquisition processes, including understanding legal documents, negotiating contracts, and advocating for their rights. This lack of knowledge can lead to missed opportunities and exploitation, as women may be less equipped to challenge unfair practices or to fully comprehend the implications of land ownership. Furthermore, the absence of educational resources tailored to women's needs can exacerbate these challenges, leaving them at a disadvantage in a predominantly male-dominated field. A study that was done in Ghana confirms this, stating that Ghanaian women frequently have lower incomes and lower literacy rates than men (Rünger, 2006).

A further step using the chi-square analysis was made to test the relationship between crowdfunding as a solution to financing and the obstacles of land acquisition among the women in stokvels/cooperatives. Table 2 shows correlation results measuring the relationship between crowdfunding as a solution to financing and the barriers to land acquisition. Table 4 shows that three of the seven constructs on the barriers were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). These constructs are limited income level hinders access to land barrier (chi-square coefficient = 25.151, $p = 0.014$); lack of assets or collateral hinders my access to land (chi-square coefficient = 22.937, $p = 0.028$); and my level of education hinders my access to land (chi-square coefficient = 22.104, $p = 0.036$).

Firstly, these results reveal that those who considered crowdfunding as a solution to financing faced limited income level as a barrier to accessing land as a barrier. Secondly, those who considered crowdfunding as a solution to financing also had a barrier of a lack of assets or

collateral that hinders their access to land. Lastly, those who considered crowdfunding as a solution to financing also had a barrier to their level of education, as well as a barrier to their access to land, as shown by Table 2. The existing land tenure laws as a hindrance to access to land were marginally statistically significant at $p < 0.1$.

Table 2. Chi-square test of association between crowdfunding and barriers to land acquisition

Barriers	Chi-Square Statistics	
	Coefficient	P-Value
Limited income hinders my access to land.	25.151	0.014
Cultural norms hinder my access to land	14.195	0.288
The existing land tenure laws hinder my access to land	16.899	0.091
Lack of assets or collateral hinders my access to land.	22.937	0.028
Limited knowledge of funding options for land acquisition hinders my access to land	13.47	0.336
Gender disparities around land ownership hinder my access to land	13.307	0.347
My level of education hinders my access to land	22.104	0.036

Strategies for Land Acquisition by Women in Cooperatives

The study also explored strategies for land acquisition by women in cooperatives, focusing on key areas: revising land tenure laws to include women's rights, utilizing crowdfunding for land purchases, offering tax incentives to encourage women's participation in real estate, changing cultural norms to combat discrimination, improving access to credit for women, addressing gender disparities in the real estate sector, and promoting educational programs on land ownership for women.

Figure 5. Strategies for land acquisition among women in cooperatives in Eswatini

The most widely supported (a total of 86% of respondents either strongly agreed or agreed) approach involves the establishment of intermediate courses on land acquisition and ownership, specifically designed for women by training institutions. This initiative addresses the necessity for skill development and education aimed at empowering women within the real estate sector. In a similar vein, Ikdaahl et al. (2005) posited that the effectiveness of women's land rights is obstructed by gender-biased norms and practices that predominantly benefit men. Following this, the call to address gender disparities emphasizes the importance of achieving gender equity in land ownership. Additionally, the use of crowdfunding as a financing mechanism and the enhancement of credit access for women ranked third in support, with approximately 80% of respondents endorsing these measures. These recommendations underscore the financial obstacles faced by women and the urgent need for innovative funding solutions, as highlighted by the UN (2010).

Furthermore, three-quarters of the respondents concurred that revising land tenure laws to be more inclusive of women's land rights represents an effective solution, underscoring the critical role of policy reforms in dismantling systemic barriers. However, only 66% of women expressed support for the implementation of tax incentives for those investing in real estate, such as property tax deductions or capital gains exemptions for women-owned properties, aimed at providing financial relief and encouraging land acquisition. Lastly, 63% of respondents acknowledged that cultural transformation is vital for eradicating discrimination against women in land ownership.

This study has several limitations. First, it relies on a small sample of cooperative members from Eswatini, which may limit the findings' applicability elsewhere. Second, the use of self-reported survey data introduces potential response bias, as participants may exaggerate or minimize their experiences. Third, the exclusive focus on quantitative methods, while statistically rigorous, limits the understanding of personal narratives and social dynamics that qualitative approaches could better explore. Addressing these limitations in future research would strengthen the evidence on women's access to land in sub-Saharan Africa.

Conclusion, recommendations, and further research

The acquisition of land is fundamental to the economic empowerment of women in Eswatini. Land ownership not only provides women with a tangible asset but also serves as a critical foundation for financial independence, enabling them to invest in their families, communities, and businesses. However, to realize this potential, it is essential to address the multifaceted obstacles that hinder women's access to land. These challenges include limited income, which restricts women's ability to purchase or lease land; entrenched cultural practices that may prioritize male ownership; and insufficient funding opportunities that leave women without the necessary financial resources to secure land rights.

To facilitate women's land ownership and promote their financial autonomy, a multifaceted approach is required. Innovative strategies such as crowdfunding can empower women by pooling resources from a broader community, thereby enabling them to acquire land collectively. Additionally, policy changes that promote gender equality in land ownership are vital. This includes revising existing laws and regulations to ensure that women have equal rights to land and access to legal recourse in cases of disputes. Furthermore, educational programs aimed at raising awareness about women's rights to land and providing training in land management and agricultural practices can equip women with the knowledge and skills needed to navigate the complexities of land ownership.

Strengthened collaboration among cooperatives, governmental bodies, and financial institutions is crucial for achieving sustainable development and gender equality in land ownership. By fostering partnerships that leverage the strengths of each stakeholder, it is possible to create a more equitable real estate environment. Cooperatives can provide a support network for women, while government initiatives can create a regulatory framework that promotes gender-inclusive policies. Financial institutions can play a pivotal role by developing tailored financial products that cater to the unique needs of women seeking to acquire land.

In summary, empowering women through land ownership is not only a matter of social justice but also a catalyst for economic growth and community development in Eswatini. By addressing the barriers to land access and implementing comprehensive strategies that promote women's rights, we can pave the way for a more equitable society where women can thrive as landowners, entrepreneurs, and leaders. The journey towards gender equality in land ownership is a collective effort that requires commitment, collaboration, and sustained action from all sectors of society.

Recommendations

To tackle gender inequalities in real estate, most respondents support targeted interventions for land acquisition. Additionally, specialized courses on land ownership for women could be beneficial. Key strategies include:

Encourage Young Women's Participation in Cooperatives by actively recruiting young women through outreach in schools, workshops on cooperative benefits, and mentorship programs linking them with experienced members. Enhance Access to Legal Knowledge by Providing women with legal education on land rights through workshops, brochures, and online resources to empower them in navigating legal processes. Facilitate Women's Participation in Land Acquisition Groups by establishing women-only land acquisition groups to create safe spaces for collaboration and advocacy on land rights. Offering Financial Support and Improving Credit Access to encourage financial institutions to develop tailored products like microloans and grants to support women in land acquisition and cooperative projects. Lastly, develop Mentorship and Networking Opportunities to create mentorship initiatives to connect women with experienced professionals in the field.

Further Studies

Future investigations should assess the effectiveness of policies protecting women's land rights to understand their impact and outcomes, identifying strengths and weaknesses for improvement. Longitudinal studies are vital for tracking changes in women's land ownership and empowerment over time, providing insights into trends and long-term policy effects. Additionally, further research is needed to analyze how current policies address gender inequalities in land acquisition, considering economic, social, and cultural factors. Identifying barriers women face can highlight legislative gaps and inform targeted interventions. In summary, a comprehensive approach involving policy evaluations, longitudinal studies, and analyses of gender inequalities is essential for advancing women's land rights and promoting gender equity.

Disclosure Statement

No potential conflict of interest.

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Breaking the Tenancy Cycle: The Case of the Khaya Lam Municipal Title Transfer Project in South Africa Partson Paradza¹, Prisca Simbanegavi¹ and Marius H. Muller¹

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Abstract

In many post-colonial African contexts, social housing has entrenched forms of quasi-tenure that deny residents full ownership rights, thereby undermining their ability to leverage property as an economic asset. Without legal title, residents are excluded from using their homes as collateral, investing confidently in home improvements, or securing long-term wealth through rising property values. This paper explores these dynamics through a qualitative case study of South Africa's Khaya Lam project, a groundbreaking initiative by the Free Market Foundation ("FMF") that had facilitated the transfer of over 15,000 title deeds to former municipal tenants by June 2024. Using thematic analysis, the study uncovers the key enablers of the project's success, including multi-stakeholder collaboration, cost-effective legal processes, and strong community engagement. The findings highlight how legal empowerment through title transfer can break cycles of dependency and unlock pathways to asset-based wealth generation. The paper concludes by offering transferable lessons from the Khaya Lam model, arguing for its potential scalability and adaptability as a replicable framework for title reform in other African social housing systems.

Key words: Social housing, Municipal Tenants, Khaya Lam, Quasi-Tenancy Tenure, Title Transfer, South Africa

Introduction

As the world is faced with a ballooning urban population, governments are faced with a mammoth task of providing adequate affordable housing to the low-income population (Granath Hansson et al., 2024). Social housing, a key strategy employed by governments globally to address housing needs among low-income populations, often involves direct state provision of social housing (Moss, 2003; Costarelli, Kleinhans & Mugnano, 2020; Scheba & Turok, 2023). However, the public housing model, particularly in post-colonial African contexts like South Africa, has been criticized for perpetuating a form of quasi-tenancy system, a condition where residents occupy homes without full legal ownership rights, thereby significantly limiting their socio-economic prospects and perpetuating cycles of poverty and dependency (Pienaar, 2011; Bolt, 2021). According to Lawson (2023), approximately 20 million South Africans do not have title deeds. This is despite efforts by the post-apartheid government to transfer ownership to these beneficiaries.

Even after decades of payments, residents often lack full ownership rights (Lemanski, 2011), hindering their ability to use their property as collateral for loans, invest in home improvements, or fully benefit from rising property values (Barry & Whittal, 2016). This absence of formal property rights, often described as a manifestation of "dead capital" (De Soto, 2000), profoundly exacerbates economic vulnerability among marginalized communities. This lack of legal title undermines housing security and limits opportunities for intergenerational wealth building (Byrne & Diamond, 2007), perpetuating a cycle of dependency and preventing residents from fully benefiting from their housing investment.

The theoretical implications of this phenomenon are well-documented in existing literature. Property rights frameworks assert that secure tenure significantly promotes economic investment, wealth accumulation, and community stability (Demsetz, 1967; Besley, 1995).

Complementarily, socio-economic theories, notably the life-cycle theory articulated by Modigliani and Brumberg (1954), posit that property ownership profoundly influences long-term financial security and intergenerational wealth transmission. Under such frameworks, formalizing ownership through the issuance of title deeds, transitions property from merely a basic shelter to a dynamic economic asset, capable of substantially altering households' financial trajectories and broader community stability.

Addressing this persistent gap requires innovative interventions capable of operationalizing dormant legal frameworks and effectively translating policy into tangible socio-economic outcomes. The Khaya Lam Municipal Title Transfer Project, spearheaded by the FMF, emerges as a significant and illustrative case study in this context. Since its inception, Khaya Lam has successfully facilitated the transfer of over 15,000 title deeds from municipal authorities to longstanding residents of social housing (Free Market Foundation, 2024). This initiative not only represents a pioneering example of civil society actively bridging the gap between legislative intent and practical implementation but also offers a valuable opportunity to critically assess the socio-economic impacts of formalizing property rights within historically marginalized communities.

This study, therefore, aims to provide an in-depth qualitative exploration of the Khaya Lam project, seeking to uncover the mechanisms and processes that have enabled its notable success and to understand its nuanced socio-economic implications. By doing so, the research specifically contributes to existing property rights and urban economics scholarship by elucidating how civil society interventions can effectively address entrenched policy implementation gaps in land tenure reform. Furthermore, this paper critically engages with broader scholarly debates on housing commodification and socio-economic empowerment. It explores the potential tensions and trade-offs involved in transitioning municipal social housing from quasi-tenancy arrangements into fully commodified property assets. This offers a more nuanced perspective on the "dead capital" discourse by examining whether the Khaya Lam project truly decommodifies housing by empowering residents, or if it re-commodifies it by making it a tradable asset within a potentially unequal market, and the implications of this dynamic.

This paper also explores the Khaya Lam title transfer project to draw themes to the broader discourse for a potential model replication that has potential for scaling up in implementation. The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: literature review, research methodology, findings, discussion, conclusion, and recommendations.

Literature Review

Theoretical Underpinnings on Title Deeds for Homeownership

Title deeds serve as legal proof of property ownership, granting homeowners exclusive rights over their dwellings. Without title deeds, renting becomes the default tenure through a contractual agreement where tenants have temporary rights to occupy a property without ownership. This review draws from economic, sociological, and legal theories.

Well-defined property rights through deed of title incentivize investment, economic efficiency, and security in tenure where homeowners are granted the legal authority to modify, transfer, or leverage their properties for financial benefits (Demsetz, 1967; Besley, 1995). This contrasts

renters who operate under lease agreements with restrictions imposed by landlords, limiting their autonomy (Acolin, 2022).

Modigliani & Brumberg (1954) put forward the life-cycle theory of housing consumption postulating that housing decisions vary according to an individual's stage in life. This means younger individuals and households with uncertain financial stability tend to prefer renting due to lower upfront costs and flexibility. However, as income stabilizes, individuals seek homeownership for wealth accumulation and long-term security. Thus, title deeds serve as an instrument for intergenerational wealth transfer and retirement planning (Henderson & Ioannides, 1983). Title deed engenders homeownership, which is a type of tenure that is strongly associated with wealth accumulation due to the potential appreciation of real estate assets (Shiller, 2014). Title deeds authorize property owners to leverage their homes as collateral for loans, fostering financial growth. On the other hand, renting is considered a less effective means of wealth accumulation as it lacks asset appreciation benefits (DiPasquale & Wheaton, 1996).

Rosen & Smith (1983) linked title deeds with a sense of tenure security in ways that reduce the risk of displacement and fostering community stability where homeowners are more likely to invest in local amenities, participate in governance, and form stronger neighborhood ties. Conversely, rental tenure is often associated with instability due to periodic lease renewals and potential evictions (Hulse & Milligan, 2014).

Gyourko, Linneman & Wachter (1999) postulated that the capital-intensive nature of acquiring title deeds makes homeownership less accessible, particularly for low-income households. This is the reason renting is often the only viable option for many residents in high-cost urban centers. Government policies, such as subsidies and mortgage assistance programs, including interest reduction, play a crucial role in improving access to homeownership (Quigley & Raphael, 2004). The legal framework governing title deeds influences the attractiveness of secure title deeds that prevent land disputes and fraudulent claims, enhancing confidence in homeownership (Besley, 1995).

However, the discourse on property rights is not without its complexities and critiques, particularly concerning the consequences of informal tenure and the commodification of housing. De Soto (2000) famously introduced the concept of “dead capital,” describing how vast assets in developing economies, including housing, remain economically inactive due to the lack of formal property documentation. His argument is that formalizing property rights via title deeds unlocks this dormant capital, enabling wealth generation through access to credit, expanded market participation, and increased investment. The Khaya Lam project directly engages with this premise.

Yet, this perspective faces significant scrutiny from critical urban scholars who warn that while formalization can offer individual benefits, the commodification of housing can exacerbate existing inequalities, lead to displacement, and undermine the social function of housing in favour of its exchange value. Marcuse (2021), a prominent voice in this critique, argues that viewing housing primarily as a commodity, risks turning a fundamental human right into a speculative asset, leading to increased unaffordability, gentrification, and the marginalization of vulnerable populations. This critical lens emphasizes the potential for formalization initiatives to inadvertently accelerate market integration in ways that may not universally benefit all residents, especially in historically marginalized communities with limited

economic leverage. The debate extends to how property rights, even when formalized, operate within existing power structures and market dynamics, potentially reinforcing rather than alleviating socio-economic disparities. Therefore, understanding the Khaya Lam project requires not only an appreciation of the "dead capital" thesis but also a critical engagement with the potential socio-economic trade-offs inherent in the commodification of housing, especially in a context like post-apartheid South Africa where historical inequalities are deeply entrenched.

Existing Academic Discussion on Housing Supply

For decades, local authorities have been on the forefront of directly providing public sector rental housing for the urban poor (Quigley, Stegman and Wheaton, 2000; Walker, 2001). According to Przymeński (2021) the goal of public sector rental housing “...is to satisfy at least the basic housing needs of people and families at risk of housing exclusion.”

However, from the 1980s there was a wave of change which has resulted in local authorities disposing of their public housing stock to sitting tenants (Gardiner and Hills, 1992; Wilcox, 1994; Forrest, Gordon and Murie, 1996; Mackay, 1999; Ginsburg, 2005). This paradigm shift was motivated by several factors, chief among them being the view that privatization will bring efficiency in housing delivery (Wilcox, 1994). Local authorities have proved to be inefficient landlords as seen by lack of maintenance in public housing stock and discriminatory allocation procedures (Power, 1987) which was evidenced by the decaying building fabric and dysfunctional basic services like electricity and water (Mackay, 1999; Gibb, 2003).

Furthermore, Gibb (2003) and Mackay (1999) noted that local authorities were also facing a challenge of collecting rental resulting in high levels of housing debt which in turn affected their capacity to provide property maintenance to their public housing stock. Gibb (2003) went on to point out that another reason which justifies the disposal of municipal housing was the transfer of risk and management responsibility to the new owner.

Czischke and Van Bortel (2023) have noted a significant reduction in government funding for council rental housing. This shows a change in policy direction where the government sees itself as a facilitator and not a direct provider of housing. Furthermore, with high default rates and limited government funding, local authorities are left with no option except for disposal of their rental housing stock before they deteriorate further and cause health hazards. The other justification for disposal of public housing is that privatization is believed to create security of tenure of the occupants (Power, 1987). The idea is that once tenants have ownership rights, they will be secure and motivated to improve their houses. Also, privatization of council rental housing opens the housing market as it allows the properties to exchange hands (Gardiner and Hills, 1992; Forrest, Gordon and Murie, 1996).

Some others like Odoyi and Riekkinen (2022) argue that housing goes beyond brick and mortar, in that it must be understood from a broader perspective which encompass “...well-being, survival, and health of human beings.” This school of thought explains why it is not proper for one to be a life tenant in a Council owned house. Homeownership is linked to increased financial resilience, which is associated with a decrease in mental health disorders (Essel-Gaisey et al., 2023). Furthermore, the empowerment function of housing, as a basic human need, can help individuals gain more control over their lives, linking them to the economy and breaking cycles of poverty (Sobantu, 2022).

Furthermore, some scholars subscribe to the notion that the sense of belonging and citizenship associated with secure housing can enhance mental health by providing individuals with a stable identity and social status (Millstein, 2020). Additionally, the quality and location of housing are crucial determinants of mental health outcomes. In South Africa, the delivery of housing has often been criticized for its substandard quality and poor integration with employment and transportation, which can perpetuate socio-spatial inequalities (Levenson, 2021). Adequate housing conditions, including infrastructure and neighborhood quality, are essential for improving individual and community well-being (Moghayedi et al., 2023).

Despite these purported benefits, critics fiercely counter that public housing privatization, particularly when implemented without robust social safeguards and supporting mechanisms, can profoundly intensify socio-spatial inequalities and trigger gentrification, leading to the displacement of vulnerable and low-income groups from their established communities (Kinnaird, 1994; Horlitz, 2017). They argue that the focus on individual asset accumulation often overshadows the collective social benefits of publicly provided housing, leading to a diminished social safety net and increased housing precarity for those unable to participate in the formal market. Moreover, declining public funding for housing and urban development has further reframed the state's role from a direct provider to a facilitator, increasingly reliant on market mechanisms, private sector investment, and civil society initiatives to address housing needs (Czischke & Van Bortel, 2023). This shift highlights a crucial gap in provision, particularly for the most marginalized, thereby necessitating alternative approaches.

In South Africa, before early 1980s, the local authorities provided public sector rental housing to the low-income groups who were mainly black Africans (Ile and Makiva 2013). Disposal of public rental housing also started in the 1980s. According to Mackay (1999): *“In 1983 tenants of half a million public housing units were given the option of purchasing their property at a discount...”*

Before independence in 1994, not much was done in terms of changing the ownership from the local authorities to seating tenants since most of them could not afford the discounted prices. The move to sell public rental housing intensified just after the country's independence in 1994 as the new administration was working on reversing the discriminatory ills of the apartheid regime (Goodlad, 1996; Cirolia, 2016; Fieuw and Mitlin, 2018).

Empirical Case Studies of Title Transfer Initiatives

The global landscape of land tenure reform is rich with empirical studies illuminating the varied approaches, complexities, and outcomes of title transfer initiatives across diverse developing contexts. These studies offer valuable insights into the socio-economic impacts of formalizing property rights for low-income populations.

In Latin America, several rigorous empirical studies have demonstrated the nuanced socio-economic benefits of large-scale land titling initiatives. Galiani and Scharfrodsky (2010), in a quasi-experimental evaluation of a natural land titling experiment in Greater Buenos Aires, Argentina, found that formal property rights led to significantly higher levels of housing investment, improved child educational attainment, reduced fertility rates, and greater female empowerment—primarily through increased household headship by women. These outcomes were attributed to enhanced tenure security and long-term household planning. Similarly, Field

(2005), in her influential study of Peru's Programa de Titulación de Tierras Urbanas (PROTITULO), observed that formal land titling substantially increased household labor supply, particularly among women, by reducing the need for home-based informal labor to protect property. Moreover, titled households exhibited greater investment in housing quality and a notable reduction in child labor. However, both studies converged on the finding that access to formal credit markets did not materially improve post-titling, challenging earlier theoretical expectations and underscoring the importance of complementary financial sector reforms.

Across Africa, land titling initiatives have yielded varied yet generally positive outcomes, contingent on local institutional and socio-political contexts. While large-scale titling has the potential to catalyze property investment and promote tenure security, empirical evidence underscores the importance of complementary systems to realize these gains. For example, Buabeng, Yankson, and Mensah (2025), in a Namibian context, illustrate that customary land governance structures often mediate the impact of titling on sustainable development, highlighting the significance of culturally embedded governance in program success. Similarly, Enemark, McLaren, and Lemmen (2021) argue that a "fit-for-purpose" approach—focusing on flexible, inclusive, and cost-effective land administration—is critical for delivering secure land rights at scale across sub-Saharan Africa. Both studies point to recurring challenges that constrain the effectiveness of titling efforts, including gender-based disparities in access to formal titles, unintended market speculation following formalization, and the need for post-titling support mechanisms such as legal aid, infrastructure provisioning, and access to finance. These insights reinforce the view that successful titling programs in Africa require not only legal reform but also sustained multi-stakeholder collaboration, institutional capacity building, and ongoing community engagement.

Mexico's historically significant Programa de Certificación de Derechos Ejidales y Titulación de Solares Urbanos (PROCEDE) illustrates how governance structures can significantly shape the implementation efficiency and scalability of titling initiatives. PROCEDE, launched in 1992 as part of a constitutional reform to Article 27, sought to regularize land rights within Mexico's ejido system—an agrarian model originating in the post-revolutionary period, in which land was held communally by rural communities (ejidatarios), who were granted hereditary use rights but not private ownership. While ejidos were intended to protect peasant livelihoods and prevent land concentration, their legal framework restricted land sales and often limited productivity and investment (Assies, 2008). PROCEDE aimed to privatize these rights, allowing for individual titling and formal entry into land markets. However, as a centrally managed, state-led programme, it was frequently hampered by bureaucratic inertia and limited community involvement, which constrained its adaptability and responsiveness (de Ita, 2022).

Critical Assessments of Title Transfer Impacts

While the preponderant empirical evidence generally supports the economic benefits of formal property rights, critical assessments identify notable caveats and potential negative externalities, underscoring the complexities of land tenure reform. Building on the theoretical concerns regarding housing commodification, Marcuse (2021) critically warns that titling programs, particularly in burgeoning urban centers, can inadvertently foster speculative land markets. This unchecked speculation, if not coupled with robust and inclusive tenure safeguards, can contribute to rapid gentrification and the displacement of the very vulnerable populations they initially aimed at benefiting. The formalization of titles, by integrating

previously informal assets into the formal market, can inadvertently expose low-income owners to market pressures, including rising property taxes or the allure of quick sales, potentially leading to a loss of their homes.

Horlitz (2017) further argues that the rapid commodification of formerly social housing units, or previously informally held land, may fundamentally erode affordability for vulnerable populations unless such initiatives are accompanied by robust regulatory frameworks. These frameworks should include mechanisms to prevent predatory lending, ensure access to affordable credit, and potentially implement land value capture tools or anti-speculation measures.

Moreover, a profound area of critical assessment centers on the socio-cultural significance of land. Koster and van Ommeren (2022) highlight that in many indigenous, communal, or historically marginalized contexts, land transcends a purely economic asset; it embodies social identity, spiritual connection, and customary practices.

Methods

This study employs a qualitative case study design, a methodological approach particularly well-suited for the in-depth exploration of complex social phenomena within their real-life contexts (Yin, 2018). This design facilitates a comprehensive understanding of "how" and "why" questions pertaining to intricate processes and outcomes. This study investigates the Khaya Lam Land Reform Project in South Africa, an initiative led by the FMF, which had successfully transferred over 15,000 title deeds to former municipal tenants by June 2024 (Free Market Foundation, 2024). The focus of the research is to understand the legal processes, and socio-economic impacts of legal titles from leasehold.

Data collection relied on two primary sources that include a two key informant interviews and documentary analysis. Purposive sampling was used to identify two key informants with direct and extensive experience in the Khaya Lam project. The selected informants met the criterion of having at least 20 years of involvement in project implementation, thereby ensuring in-depth, experience-based insights into the land titling project. The deliberate choice to rely on a single, highly experienced key informant was a critical methodological decision, prioritizing information power and depth over breadth, given the unique nature of the Khaya Lam project. This information possessed over two decades of direct, continuous involvement in the initiative since its inception, positioning them as an "information-rich case" capable of offering unparalleled, comprehensive insights into the project's historical evolution, intricate operational dynamics, strategic decision-making processes, stakeholder coordination, and observed socio-economic impacts across various stages of implementation (Patton, 2015). The interview guide was meticulously designed to elicit granular details across these areas, allowing for a holistic understanding from a central, authoritative perspective. The interview was audio-recorded with explicit consent from the participant and subsequently transcribed verbatim to ensure accuracy and facilitate rigorous analysis.

The semi-structured interview with the key informant was conducted in April 2025. During the interviews, the researchers followed a flexible interview guide designed to elicit detailed narratives on project execution and the perceived impact of title deeds. The interview lasted approximately one hour and was conducted in a confidential setting. Informed consent was obtained beforehand, ensuring that the participant fully understood the purpose of the study and their rights. Anonymity was preserved using pseudonyms, and all personally identifiable

information was excluded from the final analysis. In addition to the interview, documentary analysis was conducted using project reports, official communications, and public records, including materials detailing the project's recognition through awards such as the 2024 Reside Award and the FW de Klerk Foundation Goodwill Award (Free Market Foundation, 2024). Relevant books and academic literature on land reform and titling were also reviewed to contextualize findings and strengthen interpretive depth.

Thematic analysis was applied to interpret the qualitative data. Although only one interview was conducted, the data was triangulated with documentary sources to enhance credibility and rigor. Coding was carried out iteratively, allowing for the identification of recurring themes linked to property ownership, investment and maintenance. The flexible nature of the analysis enabled emergent insights to be captured effectively into three broader themes.

Findings & Discussion

This section presents a structured interpretation of the qualitative data collected through a key informant interview and documentary analysis. The findings are organized under three interlinked themes that emerged from the data: (i) Historical and institutional evolution of leasehold conversion to freehold, (ii) Titling as a mechanism for unlocking dormant capital, and (iii) Ownership as a driver for property investment and maintenance. Each theme reveals critical insights into the transformative role of property titling, particularly within the context of the Khaya Lam Land Reform Project.

Historical and institutional evolution of leasehold conversion to freehold

The conversion of leasehold rights into full ownership is not a novel development in South Africa. The foundations for this transformation were laid decades ago with the enactment of the Upgrading of Land Tenure Rights Act (Act No. 112 of 1991), which aimed to facilitate the conversion of leasehold tenure in government-provided housing into freehold title (South African Government, 1991). This legislative provision reflects a long-standing institutional and legal framework that has supported land tenure reform efforts, though progress has remained slow and fragmented. According to one key informant, while the institutional infrastructure existed, the government's actual implementation of tenure conversion over the past four decades was limited in scope and impact. This view supports claims by KI1 that the Khaya Lam Project did not create the legal pathway for tenure reform but rather capitalized on pre-existing mechanisms. The project can therefore be seen as a civil society-led intervention that sought to operationalize stalled legal and policy commitments. As Lawson (2023) confirms, prior to the implementation of Khaya Lam, millions of South African households remained without title to the homes they occupied, despite the legal frameworks being in place. This underscores the gap between legislative intent and practical realization, which Khaya Lam sought to bridge.

Titling as a mechanism for unlocking dormant capital

A central theme emerging from the Khaya Lam initiative is the conceptualization of leasehold public housing as "dead capital." According to KI2, "*The project was founded on the principle that homes held under lease agreements, particularly in government-owned rental housing schemes, represent underutilized assets. Without formal ownership, occupants cannot use their homes as collateral, nor can they fully participate in formal property markets. This limits both personal economic mobility and broader urban development.*" KI2 emphasized that converting

leaseholds into freeholds through titling allows beneficiaries to break the cycle of tenancy, empowering them to treat their homes as tradable and financially productive assets. This transition reclassifies their homes from static dwellings into dynamic capital assets with the potential to generate income or secure loans. Moreover, titling enables the legal transfer and sale of properties functions that leasehold rights do not typically afford. KI1 underscored that *“Under most leasehold systems in South African public housing, transfer is limited to inheritance or surrender back to the state, without legal recourse to monetization.”* By enabling ownership, Khaya Lam activates economic value previously locked in tenure arrangements, validating its mission to “wake up the dead capital.”

However, KI2 was quick to emphasize that despite the formalization of property rights through the Khaya Lam title project, most beneficiaries are still unable to leverage their properties as collateral for mortgage financing. This is largely because mainstream financial institutions in South Africa continue to perceive such properties as high-risk investments, often citing factors such as the relatively low market value of the assets, the perceived instability of tenure in historically disadvantaged areas, and the higher likelihood of default among low-income borrowers. As a result, the transformative potential of title deeds in unlocking access to credit and enabling upward socio-economic mobility remain constrained.

Sociocultural Dynamics and Community Resilience

The emergent theme reflects the complex and often nuanced interplay between formal title and broader community dynamics. Beyond the individual economic gains, the interviewees indicated a visible trend towards investment in improvements. There was an increase in efforts towards improving homes, with both key informants observing an increase in such initiatives. These actions directly align with Rosen and Smith’s (1983) tenure security theory, which posits a strong link between secure property ownership and heightened community engagement, collective action, and enhanced social cohesion. The sense of permanence and shared stake fostered by formal titles appears to motivate residents to invest in their individual properties.

Comparative Reflections

Comparative analyses are essential for transcending context-specific findings and identifying generalizable insights into land titling program design and execution. A focused comparison between South Africa’s Khaya Lam Municipal Title Transfer Project and Mexico’s historically significant Programa de Certificación de Derechos Ejidales y Titulación de Solares Urbanos (PROCEDE) illustrates how governance structures can significantly shape the implementation efficiency and scalability of titling initiatives. In contrast to PROCEDE discussed by (Assies, 2008), the Khaya Lam initiative spearheaded by South Africa’s Free Market Foundation, represents a decentralized, civil society-led model. It facilitates the conversion of apartheid-era leasehold tenure into freehold titles through community engagement, partnerships with local municipalities, and agile project delivery mechanisms. This operational flexibility has allowed Khaya Lam to issue thousands of titles efficiently, fostering legal certainty and local development (Atlas Network, 2021; Free Market Foundation, 2024).

The juxtaposition of these cases highlights the influence of governance models on titling outcomes, demonstrating the importance of institutional agility, legal contextualization, and community participation in the design of effective property rights reforms. These findings collectively indicate that successful title transfer initiatives, particularly in contexts of historical informal tenure and institutional constraints, require a nuanced balance between procedural

efficiency, the provision of robust economic incentives for beneficiaries, and the implementation of essential protective safeguards against adverse market impacts. The Khaya Lam model thus stands as a compelling empirical case study, exemplifying how civil society can effectively operationalize long-dormant theoretical insights on both property rights activation (Demsetz, 1967) and the potential for life-cycle wealth accrual through homeownership (Modigliani & Brumberg, 1954). Crucially, it simultaneously acknowledges commodification concerns (Marcuse, 2021) by implementing tenure safeguards.

Ownership as a driver for property investment and maintenance

A further key finding centers on the role of formal property ownership in encouraging investment in housing quality and upkeep. The issuance of title deeds emerged as a powerful incentive for residents to invest in home improvements, a view strongly affirmed by KI1. Ownership not only enhances psychological security but also creates material incentives for households to allocate resources toward structural upgrades and long-term maintenance.

With legal title comes a shift in perception from passive occupancy to proactive ownership. KY2 highlighted that title deeds promote a deeper sense of responsibility and agency among homeowners, resulting in noticeable improvements in the physical condition and value of homes. *“These improvements range from cosmetic enhancements to significant structural changes, including expansions, roofing upgrades, and sanitation enhancements”* (KI2). Therefore, it can be inferred that the sense of permanence reduces fear of displacement and supports long-term investment decisions, which are often avoided in insecure tenure contexts. Furthermore, ownership strengthens the property’s function as a financial instrument. It enables residents to borrow against the value of their homes or to derive rental income, reinforcing the asset’s productivity and the incentive to maintain it. Thus, the titling initiative operates not only as a tenure regularization tool but also as a catalyst for broader socio-economic empowerment.

Conclusion

The findings reveal that the Khaya Lam Land Reform Project functions at the intersection of legal empowerment, economic activation, and social transformation. While grounded in pre-existing legislation, its success lies in bridging the gap between dormant legal frameworks and practical outcomes. By converting leaseholds into ownership, such projects awaken the economic potential of low-income housing and inspire meaningful investment in property improvement. The case of Khaya Lam demonstrates that land tenure reform, when effectively implemented, can transcend legal regularization to achieve tangible developmental impacts.

Implications for policy, industry & academia

Policymakers should prioritize the operationalization of legislation such as the Upgrading of Land Tenure Rights Act (Act No. 112 of 1991) by allocating targeted resources, streamlining administrative processes, and enhancing interdepartmental coordination at municipal and national levels. The success of Khaya Lam, a civil society initiative, demonstrates the value of partnerships between the state, NGOs, and the private sector. Future policy frameworks should institutionalize such collaborations by embedding them in national land reform strategies to increase reach, efficiency, and accountability. The study confirms that title deeds can unlock capital for low-income households. Policies that link titling with access to financial services (such as affordable credit, home improvement loans, or insurance) can maximize the economic

utility of housing assets. This may require a revision of lending regulations to recognize newly titled low-value properties as valid collateral.

With formal ownership on the rise, banks and microfinance institutions have an opportunity to develop tailored financial products for new homeowners. This includes low-interest loans secured against titled property and financial literacy campaigns targeted at first-time landowners. The observed increase in property improvements post-titling suggests market potential for building materials, renovation services, and informal construction labor. Companies in this sector should anticipate growing demand and consider inclusive service models that cater to emerging low-income homeowners. The study points to a gradual integration of previously untitled properties into the formal housing market. Real estate professionals that include conveyancers, agents, and valuers must adapt to serving these new market entrants while advocating for ethical practices and protection against land exploitation or gentrification.

This study adds empirical weight to existing theories on the socio-economic benefits of formal land and property titling, particularly within low-income and post-colonial urban contexts. It opens pathways for comparative studies between state-led and NGO-led titling initiatives in Africa and beyond. The study invites multidisciplinary inquiry into the intersections of law, economics, urban planning, and development studies. Future research could explore how titling interacts with gender, inheritance systems, or environmental resilience in informal settlements. Using key informant interviews in this study proved effective in uncovering institutional and operational dynamics of tenure conversion. Academic researchers are encouraged to adopt similarly focused qualitative methodologies in land reform research, while expanding to include household-level surveys, geospatial analysis, and longitudinal impact assessments.

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No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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**Peer Reviewed*

Information Transmission between Holiday Homes and Inbound Tourism in South Africa: The roles of COVID and Exchange Rates *Omokolade Akinsomi¹, Kolawole Ijasan², Peterson Owusu Junior¹, and Nosipho Moloji*

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Abstract

We examine the information transmission between international inbound tourist volume (ARR) and Holiday Towns Index (HTI), having controlled for the US Dollar - South African Rand exchange rate (USDZAR). The study is premised on sentiment-driven behaviour in the travel and tourism sectors at instance of the COVID pandemic. Using quarterly data between 30th June 2000 to 30th September 2021, we employed a frequency-domain Rényi's information transfer approach. We find ARR drives HTI in the frequency-domain to confirm sentimental nature of the dynamic nexus. The findings have implications for both policy and tourism-related businesses and economic growth in the South Africa.

Keywords: Holiday towns; Exchange rates; Tourism; International arrivals; COVID-19; Entropy

Introduction

Thriving largely on mobility and sociability, tourism and travel are also influenced by sentiments (emotions) (Rogerson & Rogerson, 2020). Seasonal weather, special days, and other activities tend to trigger several mood indicators (Dragouni et al., 2016) that influence the sentiments of both local and international tourists (Padilla et al., 2018). Even business success triggers business confidence garners positive impact on outbound travels and tourism expenditure (Gholipour & Foroughi, 2020). This realisation could be an explanation for popularisation of sentiment analytics (Kirilenko et al., 2018) employing big data and machine learning techniques based on a wide range of data (Li et al., 2018) including online reviews (see; Alaei et al., 2019) in the tourism industry. A systematic review of the hospitality and tourism literature reveal several themes and sub-topics in sentiment analysis (Mehraliyev et al., 2021).

Travel for tourism has been at the forefront of the global economy for several years as international visits have more than doubled since 2000 until pre-pandemic 2019 (Herre et al., 2023). For instance, pre-pandemic reports indicate that between 2014 and 2019, the global travel and tourism sector generated 1 in 10 new jobs. By the end of 2019, the travel and tourism sectors were responsible for about 11% of all jobs (333 million), and about 10% GDP of the global economy, as reported by the World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC, 2022). Further,

total international tourism receipts amounted to about USD 1.7 trillion in 2019. Moreover, real international tourism growth exceeded global GDP by 54% and 44% between 2009 and 2019, respectively, United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO, 2021).

While the extant literature relies on explicit mood indicators, there are rare events that produce a sector-wide negative sentiment, rendering complex analytics unnecessary. The COVID-19 crisis triggered global fear and uncertainty, leading to widespread travel restrictions and drastically reduced mobility (UNCTAD, 2021; Bonaccorsi et al., 2020). In this context, actions driven by emotions (like travel cancellations) became easily observable proxies for sentiment. The resulting reduction in tourism had significant economic spillovers, affecting housing, exchange rates, employment, and GDP (Herre et al., 2023; Butcher, 2021). There was a 74% drop in inbound tourist arrivals in 2020 which corresponds to about 1 billion trips globally (UNCTAD, 2021), contraction of global GDP by about 50% equivalent to USD 4.9 trillion in 2020 (WTTC, 2022), and a reduction in total international tourism receipts by USD 1 trillion leading to a real GDP loss of USD 2.5 trillion (representing 2.5-fold contraction) leading to 62 million jobs lost by 2020 (UNCTAD, 2021). Although sentiments are not directly measurable, their influence is embedded in the data patterns of prices and indices. This study leverages this insight by applying tools capable of extracting implied sentiment effects, specifically, information flow driven by the pandemic, within the relationship between tourism and South Africa's housing (holiday homes) market.

Regionally, Africa and Middle East suffered a 12% and 11% reduction in arrivals, respectively, representing the least affected economies. Nonetheless, South Africa was the most affected country in Africa by August 2020 (Rogerson & Rogerson, 2020), with a 70% drop in inbound tourist arrivals in 2020 (UNCTAD, 2021) and 18% (3 million jobs) fall in employment between February and April 2020 (Ranchhod & Daniels, 2020). In general, the hospitality industry was the most affected by the pandemic due to community lockdowns, social distancing, stay-home orders, travel, and mobility restrictions (Gursoy & Chi, 2020). For many developing countries that rely heavily (about 50%) on tourism as one of their largest contributors to economic development, contractions in GDP and a rise in unemployment were witnessed (Herre et al., 2023; Butcher, 2021).

There is also a natural link between tourism and travel and accommodation (especially short-term). Thus, the sentiments from the pandemic overflows to the short-term accommodation sub-sector of destinations countries. However, a long span study on the impact of the pandemic on the housing market and tourism in South Africa is lacking, apart from a rapid response

assessment report of Rogerson and Rogerson (2020). As the largest real estate market and the most affected in Africa, the lack of this literature is unmissable. In sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), South Africa remains the market leader in terms of mortgage market performance (see, CAHF, 2022) and hence the investment opportunity is huge as are the ramifications of the housing markets on the general economy. Further, South Africa is the only country in Africa with a holiday/vacation accommodation (hereafter referred to as holiday homes) sub-market index. Therefore, it is important to examine the impact of the pandemic on holiday homes prices. This study broadens our understanding of the housing sector and the holiday homes sub-sector for both investment and policy purposes in times of crisis.

An examination of the few studies on the link between the pandemic and real estate prices exposes further limitations. First, apart from Wu et al. (2021), the dynamic and complex relationship between tourism and house prices have not been expressly addressed. In addition to Li (2022) and Del Giudice et al. (2020) alluding to short- and long-run, non-linear, asymmetry, and heterogeneous nexus must be captured. To do this, we apply the heterogeneous market hypothesis (HMH) (Müller et al., 1993) and the adaptive market hypothesis (AMH) (Lo, 2004). The HMH classifies market players into different groups by delineating short-, medium-, and long-term (denoted by intrinsic mode functions (IMFs)) whereas the AMH explains how tourism and housing industry players adapt to the fluctuating phases of the global and destination economies. Second, the critical role of exchange rates in influencing tourists' purchasing power for travel and accommodation and foreign holiday housing investments has been ignored in the literature. Volatile exchange rates tend to exert concomitant pressure on the effect of the link between house prices and tourism (see, Agiomirgianakis et al., 2014; Rathnayake, 2018; Salman, 2003). In this study, we have included exchange rates to ascertain their role in the relationship between the variables.

Third, we also observe that studies do not consider the information content (i.e. the battle between belief and evidence in making business decisions under different circumstances) associated with the generation of tourism and holiday housing price data. Given that tourism and holiday house prices are driven by information such as macroeconomic variables (e.g. exchange rate fluctuations) and news on locational (e.g. earthquakes) or global occurrences (see; Chen et al., 2022), these tend to create irrational responses from stakeholders (noise) to drive the markets (Aït-Sahalia & Mykland, 2009). As indicated earlier, empirical studies captured sentiments through survey data and principal component analysis (Marcato & Nanda, 2016) which are biased and prone to noise and information asymmetry as the data come from

either demand or supply side (Wang & Hui, 2017). To mitigate against this, we use the holiday price index as it more closely reflects the sentiments on the market and aligns with Wang and Hui's (2017) use of transaction-based data. We employ the transfer entropy approach to capture the aspect of the relationship that is driven by the sentiments of the market players, implemented under different time-horizons to divulge granular details for better decision-making. We also minimise the noise in the data via empirical mode decomposition to ascertain fundamental relationship rather than unessential dynamics.

In so doing, our study bears significance for all stakeholders in the tourism and housing sectors. Policy-makers will be informed on the complex relationship between tourism and the sub-housing market. In the future, they can take necessary and directed actions to moderate the impact of either “over-tourism” or “undertourism” on the already fragile economy, especially during troubled times. Investors in the housing and holiday accommodation arena would have more information on future pricing and rebalancing of portfolios without haste in the face of natural and global occurrences that affect mobility and sociability. Individuals who have a demand for short-term rentals (i.e. tourists) and residents will also stay abreast with the dynamics of residential prices during turbulent times. For these reasons, detailed and informed assessment of the situation is needed to make travel, tourism, and housing decisions.

Our study also addresses the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) on habitation for all individuals. Rising house prices have a direct impact on household expenditure, especially for South Africa where income levels are low amidst housing deficits. Thus, continuous increase in house prices undermines Goal 11 (i.e. make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable). Inter alia, the goal targets “*ensuring access for all to adequate, safe, and affordable housing and basic services and upgrade slums*”². For policy-makers, to ensure affordable housing, all the causes of house price rises (including inbound travels) must be fully understood and updated to strike a good balance between these two socio-economic drivers of development.

Theoretical background

This study is situated in the broad context of the tourism-led growth hypothesis (TLGH) by Balaguer and Cantavella-Jordá (2002). Brida et al. (2016) suggests that overall international

² <https://sdgs.un.org/goals/goal11>

tourism drives economic growth and the devastating impact of travel restrictions on national economies is a testament to the TLGH. However, with the rises in house prices in the face of stay-home orders and restrictions on travel during the pandemic, the question as to whether tourism causes housing economic growth or whether housing economic expansion contributes to the growth in tourism (Wu, 2019) remains unanswered (see also, Cró & Martins, 2023). Muzekenyi et al. (2018) intimates that economic growth is highly influenced by international tourism receipts from the number of foreign tourist arrivals. By using the holiday housing market, the study incorporates bi-directional causality with tourist arrivals to throw more light on this nexus.

Transmission channel between tourism, travel, and house prices

The channels through which tourism affects short- to long-term economic activities are revealed in diverse ways. First, in the quest to attract more visitors and be a desired destination, governments and private business are motivated to invest in the new infrastructure, local housing, and the economic and business environment. Second and cumulatively, tourism generates employment and income generation directly and indirectly through spillover effects (Wu et al., 2021). The impact on housing can be inferred from the TLG in any economy, especially the impact on tourism-related housing sub-market. Increased flow of tourists creates locational desirability because of increased potential for investments, infrastructural growth, local business growth, employment generation, and national income growth which tend to increase the demand for housing. Further, residential facilities face supply decline due to substitution for tourism-related spaces (Wu et al., 2021). Surprisingly, house price and holiday homes indices have continued to rise in South Africa and other countries. This may be explained by a stayed (reduced) housing supply in the face of increases (stayed) demand. The common explanations for increased home prices in response to the various dimensions of the socio-economic shock (Bonaccorsi et al., 2020) are increased demand paired with reduced housing supply deriving from stay-at-home orders and subsequent shifts to work-from-home accommodation (Zhao, 2020).

Transmission channel between tourism, travel, and exchange rates

As a foreign exchange earner, inbound tourism increases the demand for local products and services. This translates to expenditure and cost implications for tourists. For these reasons, exchange rate fluctuations are important factors in the decision-making process for travel and hence accommodation. For several developing countries, tourism is the largest earner of

foreign exchange (Čavlek & Wanhill, 2014) and hence its effect on international arrivals and short-term accommodation, and other sectors of the destination economy have attracted attention. An unstable exchange rate can have contemporaneous effect on the link between short-term house prices and tourism (see, Agiomirgianakis et al., 2014; Rathnayake, 2018; Salman, 2003). If the South African Rand appreciates against other currencies, it will cost more for international tourists and thus likely to reduce the volume of visitors. The reverse is also true for this effect on purchasing power. The exchange rate can also affect foreign investors decisions in the tourism sector, especially in holiday homes, and hence affect the prices.

Empirical review: tourism and housing in South Africa

Empirically, there is about enough literature on the impact of the pandemic on the South African economy (Ranchhod & Daniels, 2020) and the tourism industry (Gössling et al., 2020; Rogerson & Rogerson, 2020). Nonetheless, these studies are largely rapid response and hence fail to tell the full story and elicit the right policy and investment responses over a long period. While there is Zhao (2020) allude to an impact on housing demand and prices, there has been no study that has tracked the impact of the pandemic on the housing to date in South Africa. In particular, the specific relationship between inbound international tourist arrivals and holiday home is non-existent. Further, we find that while exchange rate is an important factor that determines affordability of international travel and hence tourism and accommodation, it has not been controlled for in these studies.

The empirical literature on sentiments and tourism and house prices is rather scanty in general except for the US market and non-existent for South Africa. Some studies, like Alonso-Almeida et al. (2019), use social media to explore overtourism, while others focus on emotional dimensions of travel (Hosany et al., 2015; Rahmani et al., 2019). In real estate, Freybote and Seagraves (2018) show sentiment affects market liquidity and Beracha et al. (2019) find news-based sentiment predicts commercial property returns. Also, Marcato and Nanda (2016) ascertained that sentiment in real estate conveys valuable information that can be used to forecast changes in real estate returns.

Two things are clear. First, the sentiment-tourism-housing for Africa is missing. For a continent that is home to several tourist attractions and destinations and some earning considerable amounts for national income, this is an important omission that we address. Second, most of the studies rely on come constructed sentiment index based on survey data and online reviews online reviews (see, Alaei et al., 2019). Others also employ sentiment indicators based on

macroeconomic variables such as the consumer price index except for Wang and Hui (2017) who construct sentiment index from housing transaction data. This is free of biases and information asymmetry between supply and demand sides. In our study, we employ the actual prices and indices of the market, but the transfer entropy is able to extract the sentiments (information/noise) in the data for use. This is tantamount to using transaction data because the house price index is constructed from transaction data.

Materials and methods

Data

We examine the bi-directional relationship between international inbound tourist volume (ARR), Holiday Towns Index (HTI), House Price Index (HPI) in South Africa with the US Dollar per South African Rand exchange rate (USDZAR) as a control variable. All data were collected at a quarterly frequency between 30th June 2000 to 30th September 2021 from Quantec database. The HTI comprises houses in towns (both coastal and inland) whose housing markets are strongly driven by holiday and vacation accommodation demand. The ARR includes all foreign inbound arrivals (same-day visitors and tourists) into the country of which tourist is the larger proportion. All data are converted to percentage change by logarithm.

Methodology

Complete Ensemble Empirical Mode Decomposition (CEEMDAN)

As already noted, due to non-stationarity, non-linearity, noise, heterogeneity in the behaviour of tourists, and structural breaks caused by events on the market, care must be taken to address them before further analysis (Dimpfl & Peter, 2013). We use the complete ensemble empirical mode decomposition with assisted noise (CEEMDAN) is best to improve the signal-noise ratio (Wu & Huang, 2009) to delineate the data into timescales. Our data was decomposed into five intrinsic mode functions (IMFs) along with a residual component akin to short-, medium-, and long-term dynamics. The IMFs are used as data input for the transfer entropy estimations. Wu and Huang (2009) and Torres et al. (2011) provide detailed description on the technique.

Transfer entropy

Transfer entropy is based on the mathematical theory of communication of Shannon (1948) inferred from the information theory of Hartley (1928), as a measure of uncertainty. The basic idea of entropy is the trade-off between belief and information used in decision-making. Thus, entropy quantifies the transfer of as a discrete random variable J with probability distribution

$p(j)$, being the average number of bits (information) needed to optimally encode independent draws (Behrendt et al., 2019) as

$$H_J = - \sum_{j=1}^n p(j) \log_2 p(j). \quad (1)$$

Suppose two time series processes are Markov, Shannon's transfer entropy (STE) between these processes borrows from the Kullback and Leibler (1951) distance model. We present I and J as two discrete random variables with corresponding marginal probabilities of $p(i)$ and $p(j)$, joint probability $p(i, j)$, with a Markov process of order κ (process I) and l (process J). The Markov property implies that the probability to observe I at time $t + 1$ in state α conditional on the κ previous observations is $\rho(\alpha_{t+1} | i_t, \dots, \alpha_{t-\kappa+1}) = \rho(\alpha_{t+1} | \alpha_t, \dots, \alpha_{t-\kappa})$. To encode the observation at $t + 1$, the average bits number needed before k values are known and can be given by

$$h_\beta(\kappa) = - \sum_i \rho(\alpha_{t+1}, \alpha_t^{(\kappa)}) \log_2 P(\alpha_{t+1} | \alpha_t^{(\kappa)}) \quad (2)$$

where $\alpha_t^{(\kappa)} = (\alpha_t, \dots, \alpha_{t-\kappa+1})$ (comparable in the same regard regarding the process J). In a bi-directional context, the transfer of information from process I to process J is assessed by the Kullback-Leibler distance $\rho(\alpha_{t+1} | \alpha_t^{(\kappa)}) = \rho(\alpha_{t+1} | \alpha_t^{(\kappa)}, \beta_t^{(l)})$. Behrendt et al. (2019) introduces Shannon transfer entropy as

$$T_{J \rightarrow I}(\kappa, l) = \sum \rho(\alpha_{t+1}, \alpha_t^{(\kappa)}, \beta_t^{(l)}) \log_2 \frac{\rho(\alpha_{t+1} | \alpha_t^{(\kappa)}, \beta_t^{(l)})}{P(\alpha_{t+1} | \alpha_t^{(\kappa)})} \quad (3)$$

where $T_{J \rightarrow I}$ ($T_{I \rightarrow J}$) calculates the flow of information originating from J to I (I to J) and the net can be derived subsequently.

To address the issue of asymmetry in information transfer in the market, the Rényi Transfer Entropy (RTE) (Rényi, 1961) modifies the STE by introducing a weighting parameter q as

$$H_\tau^q = \frac{1}{1-q} \log \sum_\tau \rho^q(\tau), q > 0 \quad (4)$$

where $0 < q < 1$ signifies a higher weight for events with low probabilities, while $q > 1$ favors outcomes with greater probabilities, and for $q \rightarrow 1$, RTE converges to STE. This highlights the significance of diverse distribution areas, as emphasised by Behrendt et al.

(2019). In this study, the importance of asymmetric weight is supported because the fear the pandemic instilled in all people influenced their economic and travel decisions.

We note RTE can be in negative values indicating that knowing the history of J depicts even greater uncertainty than would otherwise be indicated by only knowing the history of I . As an inverse relationship between belief and information the transfer entropy quantifies the uncertainty that drives decision-making process and hence employed as a measure of risk. Thus, negative values depict higher risks while positive values indicate lower risks.

For robustness of results in small samples to avoid biases, Marschinski and Kantz (2002) calculate effective transfer entropy (ETE)

$$ETE_{J \rightarrow I}(\kappa, \iota) = T_{J \rightarrow I}(\kappa, \iota) - T_{J_{shuffled} \rightarrow I}(\kappa, \iota), \quad (5)$$

where $T_{J_{shuffled} \rightarrow I}(\kappa, \iota)$, is the transfer entropy via the shuffled time series J ; that is, a new time series is formed by randomly selecting values from the known values of time series J and rearranging them with the observed values of J . This removes the time series dependencies of J , in conjunction with the statistical dependencies between J and I . The convergence of $T_{J_{shuffled} \rightarrow I}(\kappa, \iota)$, with increasing sample size is zero, whereas small sample effects of $T_{B_{shuffled} \rightarrow A}(\kappa, \iota)$ results in non-zero value.

Preliminary analysis³

The ERS (Elliott et al., 1996) test fails to accept the null hypothesis of stationarity in all the series given the small critical values (in parenthesis) compared to the benchmark critical values of -2.59, -1.94, and -1.62 at the 1%, 5%, and 10% confidence levels, respectively. In terms of serial independence, the Ljung-Box (Ljung & Box, 1978) shows a mixture of both serial correlation for HTI and no autocorrelation (ARR and USDZAR). Lastly, the Teraesvirta Neural Network test (Teräsvirta et al., 1993) for non-linearity fails to accept the null hypotheses of linearity in “mean” for ARR, but fails to reject for HTI and USDZAR. The evidence of non-stationarity, non-normality, non-linearity, and asymmetry exhibited in the data are further grounds for using CEEMDAN and entropy approaches for estimation and analysis.

³ These are not presented for brevity reasons.

Main Results

Effective Information transfer (Entropy)

For the frequency-based entropy, the data decomposed into 5 IMFs and a Residual, representing short-term (IMF1 – IMF2), medium-term (IMF3– IMF4), and long-term (IMF5 – Residual). We analyse the asymmetric bi-directional Rényi effective transfer entropy (ETE) among the variables at a default asymmetry weight of 0.30 to account for non-normality in the data. To interpret these results, in Figure 2, ETEs are indicated by black points inside blue bars. The length of blue bars denotes 95% confidence bounds. Thus, significant ETEs should be within these confidence bounds and should not be zero, otherwise we fail to reject the null hypothesis of no information flow. In addition, we present the ETE estimates together with their standard errors and t-values in Table 1.

Table 1: Renyi ETE between ARR, HTI, USDZAR, and HPI at composite level

Direction	ETE	SE	t value	Direction	ETE	SE	t value
Panel A				Panel B			
HTI -> ARR	-0.04067	0.071758	-0.56674	HTI -> ARR	-0.04036	0.072622	-0.55574
ARR -> HTI	0.145019	0.10475	1.384435	ARR -> HTI	0.140366	0.101373	1.384644
				HTI -> USDZAR	0.041779	0.059206	0.705656
				USDZAR -> HTI	0.158412	0.099895	1.585786
Panel C				Panel D			
HTI -> ARR	-0.04224	0.076984	-0.54867	HTI -> ARR	-0.04511	0.094844	-0.47566
ARR -> HTI	0.14618	0.112126	1.303716	ARR -> HTI	0.135059	0.102215	1.321317
HTI -> HPI	-0.07346	0.079226	-0.92717	HTI -> HPI	-0.07563	0.075305	-1.00437
HPI -> HTI	0.099357	0.10035	0.990108	HPI -> HTI	0.098741	0.077733	1.27026
				HTI -> USDZAR	0.047116	0.065977	0.714125
				USDZAR -> HTI	0.155946	0.107945	1.444679

Note: ETE – effective transfer entropy, SE – standard error, t value – ETE/SE.

Source: Authors construct (2025).

In Figure 1, we present the ETE for composite series ARR and HTI (A) and ARR, HTI, and USDZAR (B). We found that there is no material difference in the results between (A) and (B) and hence points to the fact that the entropy estimation is independent of the number of variables in the system since it is bi-variate in nature. Therefore, in the frequency- domain estimations, we do not make these separations.

Figure 1: Information transfer among the variables at composite level.

Note: ARR-Arrivals, HPI-House price index, HTI-Holiday towns index. Holiday Homes in the plots is the same as HTI.

Source: Authors construct (2025).

We observe from Figure 1 and Table 1 that while there are both negative and positive ETEs of different magnitudes from both directions, none of them is statistically significant. Thus, ARR, HTI, HPI, and USDZAR not causally related at the composite level in terms of information transmission. For the USDZAR, this can be known that the large number of tourists into South Africa have their currencies not denominated in the US Dollar. Saayman & Saayman

(2012) indicate that 75% of all tourists in South Africa come from Africa and 75% of them are from neighbouring countries. This also corroborates Habanabakize and Dickason (2022) which precludes exchange rates from the number of macroeconomic factors that affect house prices in South Africa as opposed to competitive exchange rates being an attraction for tourists (Eita et al., 2011). Further, the no cause-effect at the composite level can be attributed to the dynamic and complex relationship between tourism and holiday house prices (Wu et al. 2021) emanating from the usually adaptive (Lo, 2004) and heterogenous (Müller et al., 1993) behavior of the stakeholders. Hence, we expand the analysis to the frequency-domain to unearth these complexities to expand the insights for informed decision-making.

In Figure 2, we present information transfer at these timescales (frequency-domain). In the short-term (IMF1 – IMF2), HTI transmits positively to USDZAR but not the reverse at IMF1. At IMF2, HTI transmits negatively to USDZAR but not the reverse and ARR transmits negatively to HTI but not the reverse. Thus, HTI poses low-risk (high-risk) to USDZAR at IMF1 (IMF2) and ARR poses high-risk to HTI unlike seeing no impact of falling ARR on HTI. In perspective, rising USDZAR makes travel to South Africa affordable including paying for accommodation even at higher prices. The opposite is true at IMF2 where HTI poses high-risk to USDZAR. This also implies negative relationship where rising HTI makes travel unaffordable and unattractive, even if USDZAR is not falling. At this scale, there is opportunity for an investor in holiday accommodation to diversify by investing in the forex market, especially during times of low international inbound travels and demand for short-term rentals. These clearly confirm the roles of international inbound travels and exchange rates in the prices of holiday homes and house prices, at least in the short-term. This short-term behaviour is confirmed in the literature (see, Eita et al., 2011; Agiomirgianakis et al., 2014; Rathnayake, 2018; Salman, 2003). On the other hand, it contradicts Habanabakize and Dickason (2022).

Figure 2: Information transfer among the variables in frequency-domain.

Source: Authors construct (2025)

In the medium-terms (IMF3 – IMF4), at IMF3, HTI negatively transfers to HPI but does not receive. At IMF4, HTI negatively transmits from HPI and receives in almost the same quantities from HPI. At the scale, it is unwise to combine both HTI and HPI as housing portfolio, just as HTI negatively impacts on the total housing market. In the long-term (IMF5 – Residual), HTI transmits positively to HPI at both frequencies without any significant information transmission with ARR, USDZAR. The positive transmissions in the long-term may be suggestive of convergence between HTI and HPI which started from the medium-term (IMF3 – IMF4). There is a clear evolution in the interdependent sharing of information and risks of transmission among the variables through the various investment and decision-making time-horizons. Note is taken of the fact that, in the long-term, international arrivals and the exchange rates do not exert any influence on the housing market in South Africa, just as in the short-term. Convergence here is also corroborated by Els and Von Fintel (2010) and Burger and Van Rensburg (2008) who find that property prices converge across sub-markets in South Africa. Elsewhere, Tomal (2023) who find growth convergence in the secondary sales housing market, and a weakening growth convergence in the rental housing market in Poland.

Investment prospects

For real estate stakeholders, the short-term rental market, dominated by holiday and vacation homes may present profitable opportunities. Given the volatile nature of tourist arrivals and exchange rates, Holiday Towns properties could be combined with long-term housing (HPI) to mitigate the adverse impact of shocks. This is evidenced by our results pointing to portfolios in different combinations of USDZAR, HTI and HPI being beneficial at varying timescales. In the long-term where HTI and HPI tend to converge, diversification benefits deplete unlike in the short- and medium-terms (see Table 3). All of these must be done under the backdrop of the fluid relationship tourist arrivals have with holiday housing, general housing, having controlled for foreign exchange influence over time and across time-horizons.

Table 3: Summary of results

Series	Time-horizon	Diversification potential	Series involved
Composite	-	No	-
IMF1	Short-term	No	-
IMF2	Short-term	Yes	HTI vs. USDZAR
IMF3	Medium-term	Yes	HTI vs. HPI
IMF4	Medium-term	Yes	HTI vs. HPI
IMF5	Long-term	No	-
Residual	Long-term	No	-

Source: Authors construct (2025).

Conclusions and recommendations

This study explored the extent to which tourism-dependent housing sub-sector, Holiday Towns Index have interacted with international inbound tourist arrivals to South Africa, at the backdrop of the COVID pandemic. We also controlled for the influence of exchange in impulse-response information transmission (transfer entropy) approach. The expected dynamic nexus between ARR and HTI, extenuated by the COVID pandemic was revealed. The results showed insignificant information transmission among the variables at the composite level but a diversity of interrelationships across the timescales. We find that ARR drives in HTI only in the short-term, USDZAR and ARR are linked in the medium-term, and no significant information transfer from ARR and USDZAR in the long-term. But there was a suggestion convergence except between HTI and HPI in the long-term.

For policy, we emphasise the need for a more balanced development to reduce dependence on tourism for revenue and foreign influence on local economy. Despite international tourism rebounding post-pandemic, maintaining a competitive exchange rate, good infrastructure, and low crime rates are important for sustained growth. However, Butcher (2021) maintains that post-pandemic reforms should be along the lines of tourism degrowth considering sustainability concerns. For tourism-dependent economies, like South Africa, this is almost unacceptable, hence, policy-makers need to pursue a healthy blend of the economic gains from tourism and exploit diverse domestic revenue sources (e.g. taxes) (Pamba, 2022). The evidence that international inbound arrivals are influenced by neither house prices, holiday town prices, nor exchange rates is both surprising and telling. The COVID pandemic and other forces of nature which reduce both sociability and mobility are uncontrollable, the outcomes of which can only be managed. However, policy, infrastructure, macroeconomy, crime, political stability are within the reach of governmental policies.

The evidence that international inbound travels drive house prices in South Africa has implications for SDG 11. Apart from arrivals making housing unaffordable, it also serves as an investment incentive for residential real estate investors to transfer resources to the short-term rental (holiday/vacation) sub-market. While this serves its investment purpose, it is unfavourable to the 2.5 million units housing deficit South African economy, especially for low-income earners.

For future research, it is important to include exchange rates of the South African Rand with other neighbouring currencies, considering that 75% of visitors/tourists are from neighbouring African countries. Additionally, while crime and tourism arrivals in South Africa have been the subject of many studies (see, Thobane, 2016; Moyo & Ziramba, 2013), the role of crime in the link between holiday towns housing and inbound tourism will be an interesting study. Furthermore, the long-term connections between HTI and HPI evidenced from the transfer entropy, and non-linear causality results hint at convergence in the South African housing market. It is appropriate for convergence to be examined in subsequent studies across all the housing sub-markets to inform policy, investor strategies, and housing affordability.

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Disclosure Statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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**Peer Reviewed*

Examining Quality Corporate Governance Mechanisms on Investor Liquidity Preferences of South Africa's REITs *Nosipho Moloj, Omokolade Akinsomi, Peterson Owusu Junior*

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Abstract

This study examines the relationship between corporate governance (CG) quality and investor liquidity preferences in the South African Real Estate Investment Trusts (REITs) market. Specifically, the impact of various CG mechanisms, including board composition, audit committee effectiveness, stakeholder relationship management, risk governance, and executive compensation on investor their liquidity preferences are assessed. We use all 33 REITs listed from 2013 to 2024. Our analysis employs panel regression analysis via the Prais-Winsten method, supplemented by random and fixed effects, for robustness purposes. Our findings corroborate our primary hypothesis, revealing a positive relationship between quality CG and investor liquidity preferences within the South African context. We also find that quality CG structures influence liquidity level, transparency and disclosure quality. However, we couldn't confirm a relationship with diversified REITs and CG quality. The study makes substantial contribution to the understanding of the intricate relationship between CG quality and investor liquidity preferences, with a view to informing policy decisions and optimising the overall efficiency of the South African REIT market.

Keywords: Corporate governance, Liquidity, REITs, Investor sentiments

Introduction

Corporate governance (CG) spans over nine decades of literature, it has been an area of interest globally (Berle & Means, 1932; Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Shleifer & Vishny, 1997; Brown & Caylor, 2006; Wardhani et. al. 2025). Solomon (2020) and Tricker (2019) defined CG as system of rules, practices by which a company is controlled and directed, it includes the mechanisms through which stakeholders interact and shape the company's directions. Governance structures must be aligned with best practices and principles for quality governance (Klapper & Love, 2004).

Much of the CG literature is in developed countries with limited studies in emerging markets, especially in the African context. South Africa (SA) has the most matured CG framework within Africa and a great representation in emerging markets. The SA CG framework is unique as it adopted the traditional mechanisms from the Anglo-American Toms and Wright (2005); Letza, Sun and Kirkbride (2004) and the United Kingdom (UK) Cadbury report (Dahya & McConnell, 2007), with SA unique attributes (Ntim, 2013; Ntim & Soobaroyen, 2013). The SA CG framework is built in arrangement of King reports; these have been modified since the first King report I in 1994. All listed corporations must currently comply with the latest report, King IV.

Real estate Investment Trusts (REITs) are seamless to study CG, as public companies that utilise the merged capital of several investors to hold, manage, and develop income-producing properties (Marzuki & Newel, 2018; Li & Zhu, 2022). Globally, REITs have been in existence since the 1960s with a global market capitalisation of USD 2.5 trillion FTSE EPRA/NAREIT (2023). Marcato and Ward (2007) report that REITs are required to distribute a significant portion of their earning in various countries, which impact liquidity. In most developed nations REITs distribute at least 90% of their earnings in the Americas, Europe. In Asia, countries like Singapore, Malaysia, India, and Japan also have similar outcomes. As a results REITs are left with less cash as compared to other public corporations (Hardin et al. 2009).

SA is proxied because it is the only prominent real estate investment in the emerging markets in Africa (JSE, 2025). The SA REITs are expected to share 75% of their earning like their counterparts (JSE, 2023), hence the liquidity issue prevalent. In this regard, the impact of governance structures and disclosure requirements on investor liquidity preferences is a critical area of inquiry. The SA REIT market has undergone significant transformations over the past decade since the inception of SA REITs in 2013 (JSE, 2023). As of 2024, the top 10 REITs by market capitalisation are listed in Table 1, along with their management structure. Market capitalisation is a key indicator of a company's value on the stock market, as noted by Bauer et al. (2004). REITs specialise in various sectors, including retail, industrial, office, and storage, with some maintaining a diversified portfolio and hence can differ in their liquidity profiles.

Marzuki's (2018) study highlights the significant improvement in the performance of SA diversified REITs between 2013-2016. The diversified REITs market is poised for substantial growth, driven by increasing demand for commercial and income-generating assets. This growth is further accelerated by demographic trends, urbanisation, and the country's expanding economy, which is projected to grow at a rate of 2.2% annually until 2025 (JSE, 2023). The market is, hence, poised to attract significant investments from both domestic and international investors.

Table 1: Top 10 SA REITs by market capitalisation

REITs	Focus	Market Capitalisation in Rands	Market Capitalisation in US Dollars	Management
(1) Growth Point	Diversified	R37.22bn	2.19bn \$	Internal
(2) Redefine	Diversified	R25.81bn	1.52bn \$	Internal
(3) Fortress Real Estate Investment	Diversified	R22.17bn	1.304bn \$	Internal
(4) Resilient	Retail	R14.55bn	856m \$	Internal
(5) Vukile Property Fund	Diversified: without residential	R13.82bn	813m \$	Internal
(6) Hyprop Investment	Retail	R11.73	689m \$	Internal
(7) Equities Property Fund	Industrial	R9.77bn	575m \$	External
(8) Attaq	Diversified	R6.08bn	358m \$	Internal
(9) Investec Property Fund	Diversified	R5.83bn	343m \$	Internal
(10) Storage Property REIT	Private Storage	R5.98bn	352m \$	Internal

Sources: Centre for Affordable-Housing-Finance in Africa (2017); Wall Street (2025); Real-estate Investment Trust (Website, 2023)⁴

⁴ Real-Estate Investment Trust Association, 2017. [online] 20 July. Available at <<www.sareit.com->> [Accessed 22 August 2017 and 25 October 2023].

Research problem

Conflict of interest may arise between managers and investors, Boussenna & Kimouche (2024) (2023) and Alregab (2023) mentioned, effective CG plays a pivotal role in mitigating these conflicts and agency costs by aligning the interests of managers and investors. Georgen and Renneboog (2006) these conflicts can include empire building and *free cash flow* (FCF). Empire building can include various perks that benefit to the manager, at the cost of the shareholders. The second conflict occurs when shareholders are more concerned about pursuing growth than value maximisation. The cash flow that remains after investment is known as FCF. The liquidity aspects concerns arise at the instance of FCF when managers may request bonuses and renegotiate payout policies. In terms of theory, it is imperative to note that investors prefer stable income producing instruments but also remain sensitive to governance risk as noted by Gibilaro and Mattarocci (2021). Investors flee illiquid assets during volatility unless by governance trust. It is, therefore, essential probe into the matter and provide valuable insights into the complex relationships between CG and investor's behaviour towards liquidity. High-quality CG can contribute to the enhancement of investor liquidity preferences.

Previous literature in the SA context by Ntim et al. (2013) and Moloji et al. (2024) has emphasised the importance of investigating individual CG mechanisms. Study by Kitulazzi et al. (2025) proved that governance has positive effects on returns. Several CG studies have focused on performance and not on liquidity. However, with recent evidence from Moloji et al (2025) is on liquidity and disclosure policy not CG. Even though liquidity has been deemed to mitigate agency problems (Yun, 2009). The signalling theory posits that weak governance leads to higher perceived risk and then reduced participation and eventual abandoning the failing investment (Connelly et al. 2011). The information asymmetry theory proposes that quality CG can foster perception of increased risk among investors. This study investigates governance compliance with the focus on transparency and disclosure quality. Good CG practices can foster improved risk management and effective boards, then eventually culminating in enhanced investor confidence. CG can minimise the agency cost and, therefore, mitigate the conflict of interest between managers and investors (Berle & Means, 1932, Jensen & Meckling, 1976).

The foregoing discourse enjoins us to as the question: "Does CG quality affect investor liquidity preference in SA REITs and which governance attributes are more influential in driving liquidity?" In order to answer the research question, the primary purpose of this study is to provide empirical evidence for the impact of various CG mechanisms on investor liquidity preferences in SA REITs. The CG mechanisms considered for this study include board composition, risk governance, compliance governance, ownership structure, and audit quality, on the liquidity of South African REITs. This will help shed light on the specific governance attributes that influence liquidity.

This study contributes to the literature in two main ways. First the study closes the gap in the literature on CG and investor liquidity preference by undertaking an in-depth examination of the dynamics between these two constructs within the SA REITs framework. The SA CG framework index is incorporated, whereby 75 principles from King III and 17 principles from King IV, and the index adopted from Moloji et al. (2024). In this study the quality governance metrics are adopted. The multidimensional understanding of the complex relationships between ownership structure, board composition, disclosure quality, and investor confidence are investigated.

Second, liquidity is under researched globally to a larger extent and in the African context. This study provides actionable insights for a diverse range of stakeholders, including investors, regulatory bodies, REIT managers, policymakers, and other entities integral to the development and governance of the SA REIT sector. The study is expected to facilitate informed decision-making and contribute to the promotion of efficient capital allocation and transparency.

Hypothesis formulation

Following from the discourse so far, we propose a positive relationship between robust CG structures and investor liquidity preferences within the SA REITs sector. This is further based on the foundations of Ntim et al. (2013) and Moloï et al. (2024). We draw on signalling theory to understand how quality CG practices and transparency influence investors' liquidity preferences (Connelly et al., 2011). Furthermore, the flight-to-liquidity theory supports investors to flee illiquid assets during periods of volatility (Vayanos, 2004; Rosch & Kaserer, 2014). Subsequently, we formulate the following hypotheses.

Hypothesis

H1: A positive relationship exists between quality CG and investor preference for liquidity within the context of SA REITs.

Sub-hypotheses

H1a: REITs with quality CG structures, show a propensity for acceptable liquidity levels by investors.

H1b: The effectiveness of CG in REITs is positively related with increased transparency and disclosure quality.

H1c: Diversified REITs have a positive relationship with high CG framework.

H1d: Weak governance indicators (e.g. poor audit, CEO duality,) are associated with higher investor liquidity preference (e.g. desire for quicker exit options).

Corporate governance quality framework

This conceptual framework provides a theoretical foundation for examining the intricate relationships between CG quality and investor liquidity preferences in SA REITs. By identifying the need for empirical research to validate these proposed relationships, the framework lays the groundwork for a more in-depth investigation into the complex dynamics of CG.

Figure 1: Corporate governance quality framework
Sourced: Sharma (2015).

Literature Review

Theoretical framework

Behavioural & market microstructure theories

There are three key theories that help explain the behaviour of investments and their impact on liquidity. These theories include signalling, information asymmetry, and flight to liquidity behaviour theories. According to signalling theory, quality CG practices send a strong signal of high quality and transparency to investors (Connelly et al., 2011). This attracts investors seeking improved returns. A comprehensive analysis of the theoretical framework highlights the profound impact of CG on both investor behaviour and the liquidity of REITs.

In contrast, information asymmetry theory proposes that quality CG can foster a perception of increased risk among investors. This, in turn, can lead to broader bid-ask spreads, reduced market participation, and ultimately eroded investor confidence (Mavlanova et al., 2012). The resulting downward spiral can have far-reaching consequences, including a decline in market capitalisation and stock performance (Berg et al., 2019).

The flight-to-liquidity behaviour suggests that investors tend to flee illiquid assets during periods of volatility, unless protected by governance trust. This phenomenon is supported by research from Vayanos (2004) and Rosch and Kaserer (2014). The study periods cover both the recession periods that were in 2018 and during the COVID era 2020-2021. REITs returns were severely affected during these periods and thus a dummy variable was created for it.

Corporate governance theories

The agency theory was first introduced by Berle and Means (1932) to understand the relationship between managers and investors. Agency costs are reduced when conflict of interest is minimised (Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Georgan & Renneboog, 2006). The liquidity of REITs is affected because of the nature of REITs, and several conflicts of interest may arise. First the empire buildings, whereby there might be a conflict between managers and shareholders on perquisites, benefits offered to the managers which are financed by the shareholders.

The second CG theory is the stewardship theory, first introduced by Hamilton (1918) later modified by Gaur et al. (2015). Li et al. (2020) and on the other hand, posits that managers are stewards of the organisation and its resources, and that they will act in the best interests of shareholders without the need for extensive governance mechanisms. However, this theory assumes that managers are motivated by a sense of responsibility and duty, rather than self-interest.

The third CG theory is the resource dependency theory, initially introduced by Srinavakatrakul (1919). This focuses on the role of the board of directors (BOD) in providing access to company's resources needed by the firm or corporates. The BOD is perhaps the most central internal governance mechanism in CG applied in this study. These include the board's expertise, diversity, and size.

Empirical evidence on corporate governance quality and capital market behaviour

Governance quality

CG and REITs have been studied globally, and most of these were central to performance and CG in the Americas (Bauer et al., 2010; Campbell et al., 2011), in Europe Marzuki & Newell, 2019), in Australia (Newell & Lin, 2012), in Asia (Chong et al., 2016; Lecomte & Ooi, 2013). Jiraporn et al. (2011) conducted a review of various countries on governance standards of large corporations over 16 000 firms whereby the governance categories include board, audit, charter, ownership. They concluded that shareholders of firms with better governance quality are able to force managers to disgorge more cash through dividends, thereby reducing what is left for expropriation by opportunistic managers. Furthermore, CG quality is influenced by social, environmental and economic indicators influence quality governance in the Turkish market. Corporate governance quality is a concept that has not been fully studied, with limited literature. De Nicolo et al. (2008) developed a corporate governance quality index proxying reporting in various emerging and developed economies from 2018 to 2003 but there is still a vast lack in literature in this aspect.

In the African context there is limited literature on CG and REITs. Recent literature on CG and REITs include Kitulazzi et al. (2025), Moloi et al. (2024), Moloi (2024), and Akinlana et al. (2019). The elements of CG are often combined into composite indice to facilitate empirical analysis. Although this approach is well-established in developed markets, its application in African contexts is still developing. Empirical evidence has consistently shown a positive link between the quality of disclosure and adherence to King II, III, and IV reporting guidelines in the South African context. Specifically, this relationship has been found to enhance investor confidence in the market.

Governance and liquidity

Organisations that uphold quality CG practices tend to show enhanced market liquidity, marked by increased trading volumes and narrower bid-ask spreads (Morri & Baccarin, 2016). Similar results exist for emerging markets (Apergis et al., 2014). Investors who foster substantial influence in shaping market dynamics have been found to favour companies with quality governance frameworks.

A review by Yun (2009) highlighted a significant relationship between CG and market liquidity, suggesting that firms with robust internal governance mechanisms tend to manage their liquidity more effectively. The importance of prioritising quality CG mechanisms, that foster a more liquid and efficient market environment that benefits both firms and investors. Liquidity measures are significantly linked to changes in the governance index over time. Bushee et al. (2014) indicates that institutional investors, particularly those leaning towards growth-oriented firms, show increased sensitivity to CG mechanisms. These mechanisms prove instrumental in reducing the monitoring costs associated with substantial growth prospects.

Gaps in the literature

Existing literature has overlooked the heterogeneity of investor types, for instance retail, industrial, offices and other property types. Our study employs decade long dataset for SA based on the Kings CG framework. The King III has 75 principles and King IV with 17 principles⁵ are used to extend Moloi et al (2024). However, this study unpacks the quality governance mechanisms as identified in empirical evidence. The study establishes a critical link between governance quality and investor liquidity behaviour, making a strong case for the adoption of a governance quality index. This study demonstrates that the implementation of high-quality CG standards can effectively mitigate informational asymmetries.

Second, the application of advanced liquidity metrics, such as Amihud illiquidity, order imbalance, and depth ratios, has been underutilised in the analysis of SA REITs. Importantly, this study underscores the crucial relationship between CG and market liquidity. Given the SA REITS spend substantial amount (about 75%) of their earnings this affects their liquidity, this study closes the critical gap by specifically providing the relevant information required by the investors. We adopt the agency cost theory to help mitigate the conflict of interest between managers and shareholders.

Data and Methodology

Data

The data comprises all 33 listed REITs on the Johannesburg Stock Exchange (JSE) as of December 2024. The data span a decade from 2013 to 2024 and was gleaned from company annual reports and Bloomberg database. No REITs was omitted and where missing data was, we employed interpolation. To investigate the relationship between CG quality and investor liquidity preferences, the data extraction focused on key governance quality indicators,

⁵ The SA REITs do not comply with principle 17 in the King IV report, as this principle is meant for institutional investors.

including board composition, audit committee independence, and executive compensation, which have been identified as crucial in prior studies.

Model specification

The current study draws from Chung et al. (2010), Bushee et al. (2014), and Liu and Wu (2016) for a panel analysis with slight modification to obtain the specifications in equations (1) and (2).

$$InvPreLiq_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_{i1}CGI_{it} + \beta_{i2}VARP_{it} + \beta_{i3}TQ_{it} + \beta_{i4}X_{it} + \beta_{i5}Y_{it} + \varepsilon_i \quad (1)$$

$$InvPreLiq_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_{i1}CGI_{it} + \beta_{i2}CPRI_{it} + \beta_{i3}D/E_{it} + \beta_{i4}TQ_{it} + \beta_{i5}VARP_{it} + \beta_{i6}X_{it} + \beta_{i7}Y_{it} + \varepsilon_i \quad (2)$$

where $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$ and $i = 1, 2, \dots, 33$.

The equations are estimated using the Prais-Winsten (PW) (1954) panel regression approach. This method considers autoregressive of order 1 (AR(1)) serial correlation of the errors in the regression model. The procedure recursively estimates the coefficients and the error autocorrelation of the specified model until sufficient convergence of the AR(1) coefficient is attained. In the PW estimation, semi robust covariance matrix is estimated for the parameters to provide robust results.

For robustness check we estimates both the random and fixed effects (FE) models of each of the equations. These allow us to examine the influence of REIT-specific characteristics as well as unobservable features that have bearing on the CG performance of the REITs. We use the Hausman test to choose between the fixed and random effects (RE) models.

Identification of key variables

CGI and Mechanisms

There are various restructuring methods available, including principal component analysis (PCA) and multiple correspondence analysis (MCA), among others. Principal component analysis (PCA) is the most used method and is suitable for restructuring continuous variables only (Adediran et al., 2020). In contrast, multiple correspondence analysis (MCA) is better suited for restructuring categorical variables (Greenacre & Blasius, 2006). To develop the CG index, we leveraged MCA, a statistical technique that allows us to uncover relationships between variables. By transforming the Kings framework dataset into dummy variables and forming an indicator matrix, MCA enables us to examine cross-tabulations among variables in a more nuanced way. To operationalise this approach, we adopted a binary coding system. Whenever a firm meets the predetermined criteria, it is assigned a value of 1 (Yes); otherwise, it receives a value of 0 (No). From equation 2, $CPRI_{it}$ measures CG principles such as board composition, board size, risk governance, compliance governance and stakeholder relationship. The indicator matrix is formed, and a binary coding system is used like in CGI.

Investor liquidity preference

The measurement the investor liquidity preference in this study follows established precedents (Cannon & Cole, 2011). $InvPreLiq_{it}$ denotes investor preference liquidity for which four distinct proxies are employed. Further, the share turnover and trading volume are used as two

key activity measures. The resistance measurement of liquidity is calculated using two primary metrics: the bid-ask spread and Amihud's (2002) liquidity measure, which represents the price impact measure.

Other Variables

Variables that represent various REITs portfolios are represented by $VARP_{it}$ which includes $DIVR_{it}$ (Diversified) REITs, $RETR$ (Retail) REITs and $INDURET$ (Industrial) REITs, a value of 1 is given provided the REIT is diversified, retail and or industrial. Cross listing is measured on foreign stock markets tend to have better CG structures (Black et. al. 2006; Ntim et. al. 2013). It takes the value of 1 is a REIT is cross listed on foreign stock or 0 otherwise. Big 5 indicates corporations audited by five large reputable auditing firms. We indicate the value of 1 if the firm is audited by the five big audit firms in SA or 0 otherwise. De Angelo (1981) argue that firms audited this way garner reputation for corporate governance purposes. Debt ratio means the ratio of debt to equity. TQ denotes the Tobin's q or market-to-book ratio. The vector X_{it} captures these variables. Lastly, the vector Y_{it} denotes macroeconomic variables (i.e. CPI, GDP, and interest rate) which are obtained from data stream and Quantec database which is originally sources from StatsSA6. The macroeconomic variables are included as controls because changes in the economy can affect REITs. For instance, changes in CPI, GDP, employment levels, among others have both direct and indirect correspondence of with REITs performance

Empirical analysis

Estimation procedures

This study utilises the PW panel regression and for added robustness, we also employ fixed and random effects models. This approach enables us to control for time-invariant components in the model. We calculate the annual compliance count for each firm, thereby creating a basis for distinction between Kings III and IV.

Descriptive statistics

Table 2 provides a summary of key statistics for the selected SA REITs. Investor liquidity preferences are measured by the dependent variable, liquidity, which has a mean value of 521131.6 and a standard deviation of 1,380,230. The liquidity values were not logarithmically transformed. Tobin's Q is the proxy by market to book ratio with a minimum of 0 and a maximum of 227.08. For brevity reasons, the summary statistics show sufficient variability in the data for further analysis.

Table 2. Summary statistics

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min.	Max.
InvPrLiq	521131.6	1380230	0	13181084
CG-King III	2	3.5842	0	9
CG-King IV	9.2231	7.2673	0	17
CGI-Index	11.2231	5.3492	0	17
Total AssetT	0.9427	2.9363	-6.67	16.31

⁶ <https://www.statssa.gov.za/>

Debt Equity	13.2727	123.4484	0	1459.92
TOBINQ	1.5534	14.5727	0	227.08
Big5	0.4545	0.499	0	1
Crosslist	0.686	0.4651	0	1
CPI.	4.4528	0.1523	4.201	4.6968
Interest Rate.	2.1986	0.1236	1.9518	2.3474
Employment.	16.1418	0.1594	16.0199	16.6309
Diversified (DIV)	0.686	0.4651	0	1
Retail (RETR)	0.2231	0.4172	0	1
Industrial (INDURET)	0.0455	0.2087	0	1
Storage (ST)	0.0455	0.2087	0	1
Stakeholder Rel.	0.6198	0.4864	0	1
Compliance Gov	0.8264	0.3795	0	1
Leader/BOD	0.876	0.3302	0	1
Risk Gov.	0.8471	0.3606	0	1

Note: King III and IV implies combined CGI index, Liquidity implies investor liquidity preference. All observations are 242.

Unit root tests

The stationarity of investor preference liquidity and its covariates was examined using the Levin-Lin-Chu (2002) unit root tests. At the level of investment and savings, the panel unit root test results were not statistically significant. However, the variables became significant when tested at first difference. This works well with the AR(1) in the PW approach.

Table 3: Levin–Lin–Chu Unit-root test

	At level	First difference
Test statistic	0.55266	-28.51
p-value	0.7098	0.000

Notes: Under the null hypothesis of non-stationarity. Variables used: Volume, TotalAsset, DebtEquity, TOBINQ, CPI, Interest Rate, and Employment.

Correlations analysis

The analysis reveals a positive correlation between investor preference liquidity and the Corporate Governance Index (CGI), with a correlation coefficient of 15%. Furthermore, both CG-King III and CG King IV exhibit positive correlations with investor preference liquidity, at 4% and 9%, respectively. These align with the hypotheses for the study.

Table 3. Pairwise correlation

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)
(1) InvPreLiq	1									
(2) CG-King III	0.0424***	1								
(3) CG-King IV	0.0933***	-0.7111***	1							
(4) CGI	0.1552***	-0.2961***	0.8821***	1						
(5) Total Asset	-0.0804***	-0.0617***	-0.0973***	-0.1735***	1					
(6) Debt Equity	-0.0139***	0.2035	-0.1328	-0.0441	-0.0293	1				
(7) TobinQ	0.0195***	0.1448	-0.0984***	-0.0367***	-0.01	0.0103	1			
(8) CPI	0.0889***	-0.6134***	0.8074***	0.686***	-0.0747***	-0.1161	-0.1309***	1		
(9) Interest Rate	0.0249***	0.1787	-0.2149***	-0.1722***	0.1435***	0.0249	-0.0156	-0.3642***	1	
(10) Employment	0.0645***	-0.3143***	0.4112***	0.3481***	-0.0849***	-0.0617	-0.0654***	0.6668***	-0.2017***	

Note: ***, **, * indicate 1%, 5% and 10% significant levels, respectively.

Source: Authors' own creation.

Variance Inflation factor

Table 4 presents the variance inflation factor to assess the possibility of multicollinearity among the variables. The rule of thumb says that VIF must not exceed 10. However, all the key variables have VIF scores that are less than 10 and thus we can proceed.

Table 4: Variance inflation factor

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
CG1-Index	Inf	0.000
CG-King III	Inf	0.000
CG-King IV	Inf	0.000
DIVR	6.2123	0.1609
RETR	6.0523	0.1652
INDURET	2.2914	0.4364
Total asset	1.4245	0.7018
Debt/Equity ratio	1.0658	0.9383
TobinQ	1.0497	0.9527
Audited by Big 5 firm	1.5354	0.65129
Cross-listing	1.2105	0.8261
CPI	6.1796	0.1618
Interest rate	1.2270	0.8150
Employment	2.0356	0.4912
Stakeholder Rel	3.5535	0.2814
Risk Gov	6.074	0.1646
Compliance Gov (Tran/Qua)	4.519	0.2213
Leader/BOD	12.4595	0.0803

Main results

The results from the PW regression are presented in Tables 5 and 6. Table 5 presents the relationship between CG quality and investor preference for liquidity. The findings reveal a significant and positive nexus between the CGI and investor preference for liquidity, aligning with existing literature. Quality CG is associated with increased investor preference for liquidity. A similar study by Alregab (2023) reported comparable results. Our main hypothesis, H1, which proposes a positive relationship between quality CG and investor preference for liquidity in SA REITs, is substantiated by the results.

Table 5. Investor preference liquidity and CG

	Variable	Estimate	t-value	p-value	R ²
(Obs. = 242)					
Model 1	Intercept	-6598858.5 (9207862.7)	-0.717	0.4743	
	CG1	52892.5* (31260.1)	1.692	0.0920	

	DIVR	645230.2 (462141.7)	1.396	0.1640	
	RETR	288813.3 (491863.9)	0.587	0.5577	
	INDURET	782427.1 (638267.9)	1.226	0.2215	
	Total AssetT	-39789.3 (30825.3)	-1.291	0.1981	
	Debt Equity	-163.5 (722.6)	-0.226	0.8212	
	TOBINQ	1000.8 (6031.2)	0.166	0.8684	
	Big5	-558604.0*** (182967.1)	-3.053	0.00253	
	CPI	1964398.7*** (914638.0)	2.148	0.0328	
	Interest Rate	979588.5 (695547.4)	1.408	0.1604	
	Employment	-256303.9 (677460.0)	-0.378	0.7055	
					0.08886

Note: ***, **, * indicate 1%,5% and 10% significant levels, respectively. Standard errors are in parenthesis.

There is also a significant positive correlation between CPI and investor preference liquidity. This suggests that higher CPI values are consistently associated with improved investor preference liquidity, indicating that robust CG practices contribute to enhanced market liquidity. These findings resonate with the research of Moloi et al. (2024), which highlighted the significant impact of macro-economic factors on liquidity.

Table 6. Investor preference liquidity and CG principles

	Variable	Estimate	t-value	p-value	R ²
(Obs. = 242)					
Model 2	Intercept	-5.8020 (7.8890)	0.735	-0.4628	
	CGI	-7.6800 (3.4300)	-0.224	0.8231	
	DIVR	5.9440 (4.6320)	1.283	0.2007	
	RETR	8.0740 (5.0190)	0.161	0.8723	
	INDURET	7.9560 (6.2360)	1.276	0.2033	
	Total AssetT	-1.0280	-0.360	0.7194	

		(2.8570)			
	Debt Equity	9.6230 (6.7340)	0.143	0.8865	
	TOBINQ	-6.2650 (5.6240)	-0.111	0.9114	
	Big5	-1.1910*** (1.9400)	-6.139	0.0000	
	lnCPI	1.3900 (9.901)	1.404	0.1618	
	lnInterest Rate	8.1790 (6.0400)	1.354	0.1770	
	lnEmployment	-1.0150 (5.9680)	-0.170	0.8651	
	Stakeholder	1.3360*** (2.3940)	5.580	0.0000	
	Risk Gov	-7.3760 (5.2820)	-1.396	0.1640	
	Compliance Gov (Trans/Qua)	1.2320*** (-4.3130)	-2.856	0.0047	
	Board/ Leader /Comp/size	1.1010 (7.3370)	1.501	0.1348	
					0.22

*Note: ***, **, * indicate 1%,5% and 10% significant levels, respectively. S.E are in parenthesis.*

Table 6 shows three variables that have statistically significant variables (i.e. CGI, CPI, and Big 5). Our findings indicate that stakeholder relationships have a statistically significant and positive relationship with investor preference liquidity. This suggests that maintaining effective relationships with various stakeholders is crucial, with a profound impact on investor liquidity. Our hypothesis H1a is supported, indicating that REITs with quality CG structures, characterised by effective stakeholder relationships, exhibit a higher propensity for investor liquidity preference. However, we found no significant relationship between leadership and investor preference liquidity.

Furthermore, our results show that compliance governance has a significant positive relationship with investor preference liquidity. Therefore, our hypothesis H1b is also supported, indicating that the effectiveness of CG in REITs is positively related to increased transparency and disclosure quality. Our findings suggest that transparency and compliance with laws and local regulations have a significant influence on investor liquidity preference, as intimated by the signalling theory.

Our results show a significant negative relationship between firms audited by the Big 5 and investor preference liquidity among SA REITs. This supports Hypothesis H1d, which suggests that weak governance indicators, such as poor audit practices, are associated with a higher investor liquidity preference. This implies that investors tend to prefer faster exit options when firms are not audited by the Big 5.

While the Prais-Winsten approach is important for to address serial correlation in the data, it does not isolate unobserved REIT-specific characteristics. We employ the FE and RE to see which best captures the relationship.

Table 7. Investor preference liquidity and CG (FE and RE)

	Variable	Estimate	t-value	p-value	R²	Hausman test
Fixed Effects						
<i>Model 3</i>	CG1	24876.698 (24327.156)	1.0226	0.3077		
	DIVR	245125.951 (970894.687)	0.2525	0.8009		
	Total Asset	-1824.861 (26755.393)	-0.0682	0.9457		
	Debt Equity	-84.434 (528.608)	-0.1597	0.8732		
	TOBINQ	-5423.455 (4243.815)	-1.2780	0.2027		
	CPI	1335812.534* (690276.663)	1.9352	0.0543		
	Interest Rate	736738.569 (516885.248)	1.4253	0.1555		
	Employment	-60575.885 (510022.191)	-0.1188	0.9056		
					0.0416	
Random Effects						
<i>Model 4</i>	Intercept	-6.2336E06 (6.9066E06)	-0.9026	0.3668		
	CG1	2.7257E06 (2.4042E04)	1.1337	0.2569		
	DIVR	7.1117E05 (1.2819E06)	0.5548	0.5791		
	RETR	2.8452E05 (1.3341E06)	0.2133	0.8311		
	INDURET	7.3621E05 (1.8076E06)	0.4073	0.6838		
	Total Asset	-4.7859E03 (2.6245E04)	-0.1824	0.8553		
	Debt Equity	-9.1237E04 (5.2330E03)	-0.1743	0.8616		
	TOBINQ	-5.0693E03 (4.2112E03)	-1.2038	0.2287		

	Big5	-5.0184E05 (5.4717E05)	-0.9172	0.3591		
	CPI	1.3895E06** (6.8427E05)	2.0306	0.0423		
	Interest Rate	7.5550E05 (5.1376E05)	1.4706	0.1414		
	Employment	-9.2379E04 (5.0116E05)	-0.1843	0.8538		
					0.0447	1.1499 (0.9971)

Table 7, the RE model reveals a significant and positive correlation between the CPI and investor preference liquidity. This positive relationship is consistently confirmed when using fixed effects, further emphasising the strong link between CPI and investor preference liquidity. The null hypothesis (H_0) of the Hausman test indicates that individual REITs (fixed) features are uncorrelated with the explanatory variables. In this case, the RE estimator appropriate and efficient. From the test statistic and the p-value of the Hausman test, we fail to reject the null hypothesis indicating that in SA REITs, the unique features of the REITs are irrelevant to determine investors' liquidity preference.

Table 8: Investor preference liquidity and CG principles (FE and RE)

	Variable	Estimate	t-value	p-value	R ²	Hausman test
Fixed Effects						
<i>Model 5</i>	CGI	-54780.22* (32441.10)	-1.6886	0.0928		
	DIVR	183475.40 (975270.82)	0.1881	0.851		
	Total Asset	424.22 (27474.49)	0.0154	0.9877		
	Debt Equity	-42.16 (581.13)	-0.0725	0.9422		
	TOBINQ	-5015.53 (4272.00)	-1.1740	0.2417		
	CPI	2257245.21** (923870.04)	2.4432	0.0154		
	Interest Rate	864843.99 (526308.67)	1.6432	0.1019		
	Employment	-263160.40 (529442.01)	-0.4971	0.6197		
	Stakeholder Rel.	235274.08 (273782.04)	0.8593	0.3911		
	Risk Gov	136484.59 (598052.45)	0.2282	0.8197		
	Compliance Gov	-44034.28	-0.0888	0.9293		

		(495622.91)				
	Leader /BOD	55715.89 (725921.95)	0.0768	0.9389		
					0.05253	
Random Effects						
<i>Model 6</i>	Intercept	-6.7549E06 (6.9907E06)	-0.9663	0.3339		
	CGI	-4.6263E04 (3.2073E04)	-1.4425	0.1492		
	DIVR	8.0759E05 (1.1638E06)	0.6939	0.4877		
	RETR	3.8250E05 (1.2174E06)	0.3142	0.7534		
	INDURET	7.6749E05 (1.6338E06)	0.4698	0.6385		
	Total Asset	-2.3917E03 (2.7073E04)	-0.0883	0.9296		
	Debt Equity	-4.4312E01 (5.7028E02)	-0.0777	0.9381		
	TOBINQ	-4.5581E03 (4.2760E03)	-1.0660	0.2864		
	Big5	-5.8747E05 (5.0290E05)	-1.1682	0.2427		
	CPI	2.0883E06** (9.1699E05)	2.2774	0.0228		
	Interest Rate	8.5313E05 (5.2797E05)	1.6159	0.1061		
	Employment	-2.4948E05 (5.2488E05)	-0.4753	0.6346		
	Stakeholder Rel.	3.6633E05 (2.6488E05)	1.3830	0.1667		
	Risk Gov	1.1830E05 (5.7112E05)	0.2071	0.8359		
	Compliance Gov	-1.7795E05 (4.7216E05)	-0.3769	0.7063		
	Leader /BOD	7.9994E04 (7.0580E05)	0.1133	0.9098		
					0.05414	127.97 (0.000)

In Table 8, FE indicates a significant positive link between liquidity preference and CPI but a negative relationship with CGI. These findings are consistent with existing research, which suggests that macroeconomic factors can contribute to improved liquidity in the REIT market (Tricker, 2019). Interestingly, the results also reveal a marginally negative relationship between investor preference liquidity and the CG index when using random effects. However, if the RE is

rather the best model for the data. In general, we find that the PW panel regression is the best approach to evaluate the relationship between CG and liquidity preference and previous performance serve as a signal for subsequent years.

Conclusions

This study examined the relationship between CG quality and investor liquidity preferences within the SA REIT market. The objective is to contribute to improving transparency and stability. The findings are poised to offer actionable insights for pivotal stakeholders, encompassing investors, regulatory entities, and REITs managers. This study confirms the primary hypothesis, revealing a positive relationship between CG quality and investor preference liquidity. In essence, this demonstrates that higher CG standards are linked to increased investor liquidity preferences.

Several hypotheses were tested. The first (H1a) was accepted due to the strong relationship found between stakeholder relationships and investor preference liquidity. The study's findings emphasise the crucial role of good CG frameworks in creating an investment-friendly environment that promotes growth and stability in the REIT market in SA. Increased transparency and compliance with regulatory levels are positively related to higher investor preference liquidity. In contrast the analysis revealed no significant relationship between diversified REITs, the Big 5 and investor preference liquidity.

The derived insights can enable policymakers to foster a conducive investment environment by implementing robust governance frameworks, promoting transparency, and ensuring auditor independence. The study's contributions can inform evidence-based policy decisions that enhance the overall stability and attractiveness of the REIT market.

Limitations of the study include deeper understanding of what is embedded in investor sentiments and liquidity and how these factors influence investment decisions. Further studies may be required for comprehensive understanding of the complex interplay between CG quality, auditor reputation, investor sentiment, and liquidity.

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**Peer Reviewed*

Climate Resilience and Investment Performance in South African Shopping Centres Evidence from a GIS-enhanced panel study *Nosipho Moloji¹; Omokolade Akinsomi¹; Peterson Owusu Junior¹*

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Abstract

As the frequency and intensity of climate-related hazards escalate, commercial real estate, particularly retail centres, emerge as both vulnerable to disruption and strategically positioned for adaptation. This study explores the critical role of climate resilience in determining investment performance in South African shopping centres (SCs), where the acute impacts of droughts, flooding, and infrastructure volatility converge with evolving investor expectations and regulatory imperatives. This study develops a Climate Resilience Index (CRI) to measure the vulnerability of SCs to the physical impacts of climate change on SCs performance. Our panel analysis of 322 shopping centres from 2019 to 2024 using the ordinary least squares (OLS), random effects, and fixed effects estimations reveal a compelling link between climate resilience and SCs performance. The SCs that have invested in robust climate mitigation measures - such as flood protection infrastructure, renewable energy integration - tend to outperform their peers financially. Specifically, these measures are correlated with improved net operating income (NOI), higher trading density, and increased occupancy rates. This finding has significant implications for retail real estate investors and developers to prioritise climate change preparedness in order maintain sustainable investment returns.

Keywords: Climate change; Climate resilience; shopping centres; performance

Introduction

The threat of climate change to real estate investments has gained significant attention in recent years (Giglio et. al. 2021). As extreme weather events intensify and become more frequent due to human-induced climate change, commercial properties are increasingly exposed to substantial risks. These risks have far-reaching consequences, affecting not only the environment but also the financial, operational, and reputational performance of assets. Recent studies by Newell and Marzuki (2022) and Warren-Myers (2022) also underscore the property sector's vulnerability to a range of climate-related risks, including flooding, heat stress, water scarcity, infrastructure failure, and energy unreliability. Each of these risks carries distinct implications for asset valuation, operating expenditures, and long-term investment performance, highlighting the need for urgent action. Investors and stakeholders must proactively adopt strategies to mitigate these risks and ensure the resilience of their assets in the face of climate change.

South Africa (SA) is uniquely vulnerable to the widespread impacts of global climate change, as noted by du Plessis et al. (2003). The country is grappling with a multitude of climate-related challenges, including the persistent droughts that have affected the Western Cape, recurring floods in KwaZulu-Natal, and the ongoing energy insecurity that threatens the nation. As Jensen (2005) highlights, urban centres, where most retail assets are concentrated, are particularly susceptible to these pressures. Aging infrastructure, entrenched spatial inequality, and inconsistent governance capacity make these areas vulnerable. As crucial hubs of commerce, employment, and consumer services, shopping centres (SCs) are disproportionately exposed to climate-related stressors, which can significantly impact their investment potential (Adanlawo & Vevi-Magigaba, 2021).

As investors increasingly incorporate Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) factors into their investment strategies, the relationship between climate resilience and investment performance has become a pressing concern (Newell & Marzuki, 2022). Climate resilience refers to the ability of assets, systems, and institutions to absorb and recover from climate-related disruptions while maintaining their core functions (IPCC, 2014). According to prevailing theories, climate resilience is amplified in shopping centres due to their strategic location, shopper behaviour, and surrounding land use.

According to the Central Place Theory (CPT), first proposed by Brown in 1933 and later reviewed by Litz and Rajaguru (2008), a well-designed system is vital for ensuring uninterrupted service provision in shopping centres. A resilient hierarchy is essential in avoiding single points of failure, which can have devastating consequences in the event of a climate-related disruption. They highlight the importance of incorporating backup centres in low-risk locations, enabling shopping centres to minimise downtime and ensure business continuity.

The Behavioural Location Theory (BLT), first introduced by Claus & Claus (1971) and later refined by Harvey (2015), plays a vital role in shaping the effectiveness of a shopping centres' climate resilience strategy. This theory emphasises the importance of human behaviour in determining how individuals and organisations respond to climate-related shocks at every stage - before, during, and after. By gaining a deeper understanding of human behaviour and preferences, shopping centres can proactively design systems that promote planning, resilience, and adaptability, ultimately enhancing their ability to navigate the challenges of climate change in a continuous way.

Further, considering the land use accessibility (LUA) theory, first introduced by Hansen (1959) and later reviewed by Geurs & Van Wee (2004) and Liu & Li (2020), climate resilience can be greatly enhanced by considering physical connectivity and proximity. Strategically locating shopping centres near public transportation hubs, emergency services, and other critical infrastructure, businesses can ensure that people can quickly access alternative services and facilities in the event of a disruption, thereby increasing climate resilience.

Despite the growing recognition of climate resilience as a critical factor, its importance remains largely unquantified in mainstream investment analysis, particularly in emerging markets like South Africa (SA). According to the Clur Shopping Centres Index (2024), shopping centres in SA face numerous challenges. As significant real estate holdings, they are vulnerable to moderate to severe climate change impacts, making climate resilience a necessity. To address this, shopping centres are required to publish various Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) metrics in their annual reports, including their Green Building Council of South Africa (GBCSA) compliance and energy performance certificates (EPC). The SCs must report on five key areas of climate resilience: physical, energy, water, operational, and location resilience. Based on these, we construct a create a climate resilience index using the correspondence multiple analysis (MCA) approach and explore its relationship with shopping centre performance.

Problem statement

The increasing frequency and severity of climate-related hazards, such as flooding, droughts, heatwaves, and wildfires, pose a significant threat to the built environment, with commercial real

estate assets, particularly SCs, being notably vulnerable (Mujongode-Kanonhuhwa & Mupukuta, 2019; Gapsper et. al. 2011). SA has diverse climatic regions and socio-economic disparities which make it susceptible to environmental disruptions that jeopardise the long-term sustainability and profitability of retail infrastructure investments (Ziervogel et. al. 2014; DEA, 2016). SCs are heavily exposed to climate-related risks due to their large size, high energy and water consumption (Nel & Rogerson, 2016).

A growing body of global research, as noted by Eichholtz et al. (2010) and Kaza et al. (2019), has established a clear link between environmental risk and real estate performance. While green building certifications have gained popularity, the concept of climate resilience encompasses a broader scope, including location-specific adaptation strategies, infrastructure robustness, and socio-economic responsiveness (Smit & Wandel, 2006; UNEP FI, 2021). Thus, there are gaps in empirical studies within the South African context, particularly in exploring how a property's ability to anticipate, absorb, recover from, and adapt to climate-related shocks impacts its overall performance.

First, there is a lack of clear understanding of how climate resilience factors influence investment decisions and risk-adjusted returns in the SA context. Second, there is a need for integrated assessment models that directly link climate risk exposure and adaptive capacity to crucial investment performance metrics, such as net operating income, capitalisation rates, and asset valuation over time (Deng et al., 2012; Hudson et al., 2019). To address these gaps, this study tests whether climate-resilient feature can predict superior financial and operational performance.

Considering this, two research questions are apparent - what resilience attributes are integrated into South African SCs to mitigate climate-related risks and enhance their adaptability in the face of climate change? And to what extent do these resilience features correlate with key investment performance metrics?

Literature review

South African Retail Sector

The retail industry occupies a vital position in the South African economy, yielding substantial contributions to the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and employment rates (Statistics SA, 2023). Large-scale SCs, such as superregional and regional malls, have emerged as significant players in the market, with examples including Mall of Africa and Canal Walk, which serve extensive catchment areas. According to SACSC (2024) SA boasts one of the highest concentrations of retail space per capita on the African continent. This SCs expansion can be attributed to the influx of institutional investments and the increasing presence of Real Estate Investment Trusts (REITs) such as Hyprop, Growthpoint, and Attacq. These REITs have been instrumental in shaping the country's retail landscape, driving growth, and development.

The Clur Shopping Centre Index, which tracks an impressive 5.4 million m² of retail space, reported a remarkable annualised trading density of R40,724 per m², accompanied by a year-on-year growth rate of 3.5% in 2024 (Clur Shopping Centre Index, 2024; SAPOA, 2023). Table 1 shows the top performing shopping centres in SA. Among other things, the ability to the SCs to be

resilient to climate-induced disruptions is not only crucial for investors but also critical for the national economic stability.

Table 1: Top 5 Performing shopping centres

Rank	Shopping Centre	Location	Monthly Turnover / GMR	Trading Density	Foot Traffic	Owner	Key Highlights
1	Mall of Africa	Midrand, Gauteng	R61 million+ (GMR)	R4,571/m ²	~1.8 million/month	Attacq	SA's highest GMR; strong footfall & leasing
2	Canal Walk	Cape Town, Western Cape	R4.31 billion (H2 2024)	R4,934/m ² /month	~1.68 million/month	Hyprop (80%)	High turnover & premium tenant mix
3	Fourways Mall	Johannesburg North	R500 million (Dec 2024)	Not disclosed	1.5 million (Dec 2024)	Accelerate (50%)	Strong festive season growth; improving stability
4	Rosebank Mall	Rosebank, Johannesburg	Not disclosed	↑ 8.3% (YoY growth)	↑ 8.5% (YoY growth)	Hyprop	Strong YoY growth in tenant and foot traffic
5	The Glen	Johannesburg South	Not disclosed	↑ 0.7% (YoY growth)	↑ 0.5% (YoY growth)	Hyprop	Modest performance, steady footfall

Source: (SAPOA, 2023; STATS SA, 2023; Clur shopping centre index, 2024).

Climate change and South African SCs

Research underscores the profound impact of climate change on the operational expenditures of SCs, with a particular emphasis on the escalating costs of energy consumption (Weththasinghe et al. 2022). Moreover, the existing literature suggests that climate change may also exert a detrimental effect on customer visitation rates. An examination of climate data from 2010 to 2022 in SA reveals a marked warming trend, as evidenced by rising temperatures over the past decade (Figure 1). Furthermore, a surge in extreme weather events is evident, which has the potential to disrupt business operations and result in increased maintenance costs. A subtle decline in foot traffic is apparent, customer visits may be influenced by climate-related factors such as heatwaves

or storms. The bottom right chart shows a steady upward trajectory in the energy costs, driven by heightened cooling needs and rising prices.

Figure 1: SA weather and SCs metrics
 Source: Esri (2025); Climatology Lab (2025)

An examination of the spatial variability in vulnerability of SCs to climate change reveals that both coastal and inland regions are susceptible to its impacts, as illustrated in Figure 2. The energy costs exhibit the most pronounced correlation with extreme weather events. Furthermore, the relationship between extreme weather events and foot traffic patterns in SCs varies spatially, as evident in Figure 2. A cost-centric approach appears to be a more suitable framework for assessing the repercussions of extreme weather conditions on SCs performance.

Figure 2: SA weather and impact on shopping centre foot count (Coastal and inland)
 Source: Esri (2025); Climatology Lab (2025)

Figure 3 shows distinct spatial distribution of SCs around major South African cities, including Johannesburg, Pretoria, Cape Town, and Durban. The map also reveals a concerning concentration of high-risk SCs along the country's coastal regions, which are disproportionately vulnerable to the impacts of climate change. The accompanying legend enables a clear differentiation between the four categories, allowing for a thorough evaluation of both climate risk and resilience exposure across South Africa's retail landscape.

Figure 3: All SA shopping centres (SCs) and climate resilience
 Source: Esri, (2025), Climatology Lab (2025); Clur shopping centre index (2024)

Hypothesis formulation

The threat of climate change has far-reaching implications for the global real estate market, with SA being particularly vulnerable to the devastating consequences of extreme weather events. The country’s large-scale retail assets, such as SCs, is increasingly susceptible to the dual threats of physical and transitional climate-related risks. As complex, long-term investments with substantial embedded energy, SCs capacity to adapt to the impacts of climate change has become a critical consideration for investors and asset managers seeking to mitigate potential losses and ensure long-term sustainability.

By drawing on central place theory, behavioural location theory, and land use accessibility theories, this study proposes that SCs that demonstrate climate resilience are likely to exhibit superior investment performance. This is attributed to several key benefits, including lower operational disruptions, reduced insurance costs, higher tenant retention, and reputational

advantages among ESG-oriented investors (Eichholtz et al. 2010; GRESB, 2022). Specifically, we propose the following hypotheses:

H1: There is a significant positive relationship between the climate resilience level of South African SCs and their investment performance.

The performance of SCs is significantly influenced by their resilience to climate-related events. Research has demonstrated that properties with resilient features exhibit reduced exposure to revenue fluctuations (Baker et al., 2018). As noted by, Deng et al. (2012) and Hudson et al. (2019) the incorporation of physical adaptations, such as stormwater management systems and passive cooling mechanisms, as well as organisational responses, including ESG governance, can significantly contribute to long-term income stability.

Climate change poses a significant threat to the financial performance of shopping centres, particularly those located in high-risk areas. Hudson et al. (2019) highlighted the critical tradeoffs between affordability and risk reduction, emphasising the need for effective climate resilience measures. The absence of these measures can lead to increased insurance premiums, ultimately affecting the financial performance of shopping centres. This underscores the importance of implementing climate resilience measures that not only reduce risk but also improve overall performance. By incorporating climate resilience measures into their strategies, shopping centres can mitigate the impacts of climate change, reduce insurance premiums, and ultimately enhance their financial performance. The absence of climate resilience measures can significantly impact cash flows.

Further, enhancing infrastructure can substantially mitigate the impact of physical shocks on shopping centres, leading to lower maintenance and insurance costs (GCEC, 2018). As highlighted in the foundational paper by Smit and Wandel (2006), climate resilience is directly associated with adaptation, which requires addressing physical vulnerability and adaptive capacity, hence affecting operational performance. Hence, we propose a sub-hypothesis as

H1a: Climate related infrastructural features of SCs such as energy efficiency, water efficiency, and backup power are positively related to operational performance.

It is important to note that these hypotheses are also motivated by the Central Place, Behavioural Location, and Land Use and Accessibility theories presented in the introductory section.

Conceptual review

Climate resilience in the built environment

The concept of resilience has evolved since its inception in ecological systems, and has since been applied to various fields, including urban planning, infrastructure development, and real estate management, as first introduced by Holling (1973). Building on this concept, Walker and Salt (2006) define resilience as the inherent ability of a system to absorb and reorganise in response to disruptions. In the context of the built environment, climate resilience refers to a property's ability to withstand, recover from, and adapt to climate-related stressors, a concept explored in-depth by Meerow, Newell, and Stults (2016).

This is increasingly being acknowledged as a multifaceted phenomenon, operating at various scales. At the individual asset level, resilience encompasses a range of physical and design-related characteristics. At the portfolio and urban scales, resilience is characterised by locational robustness (Sharifi & Yamagata, 2016). These interconnected attributes collectively contribute to the notion of investment-grade resilience. A holistic concept introduced by Lin and Lin (2022) integrates adaptive capacity and financial risk mitigation to support sustained long-term performance in the face of uncertainty.

Climate risk and investment performance in retail real estate

According to Geltner (2015), the conventional evaluation of commercial real estate investment performance typically relies on a range of metrics, including rental yields, net operating income, vacancy rates, and internal rate of return. However, the performance of retail properties, such as SCs, is also significantly influenced by a distinct set of factors, including pedestrian traffic (CBRE, 2020). Pedestrian traffic is a subject to continuous safe and appealing physical and infrastructural resilience. Climate-related risks exert a multifaceted impact on the performance of real estate assets, operating through various transmission channels. Studies have shown that buildings with green certifications can command higher rental and sales prices (Eichholtz et. al. 2010). However, Keenan (2021) and Bernstein (2024) highlights that it is not just environmental performance, but rather resilience, that has emerged as a crucial differentiator of risk-adjusted returns.

Empirical review

Studies have shown that commercial properties in areas prone to sea-level rise in the United States are sold at a significantly lower price compared to similar properties located inland (Bernstein, 2024). A similar phenomenon is likely to occur in SA, where numerous SCs are situated in coastal regions, although no such studies have been conducted locally. Furthermore, research by Addoum et al. (2020) has established a correlation between climate volatility and increased operational costs, insurance premiums, and reduced asset liquidity. Consequently, institutional investors and REITs are progressively incorporating climate risk assessments into their portfolio management strategies (Urban Land Institute, 2021).

Anecdotal evidence suggests that South African SCs are vulnerability to climate change and that varies significantly across regions. Coastal cities, such as Durban, are susceptible to flooding and sea-level rise, whereas interior regions, including Gauteng and the Free State, are more prone to heatwaves, water scarcity, and load shedding. Nonetheless, there is no empirical evidence support these claims.

Literature gaps

A review of existing literature on climate change and SCs performance reveals several significant knowledge gaps. A key issue is the disconnect between climate resilience frameworks and traditional investment analysis, highlighting the need for a more holistic approach. Moreover, there is a lack of empirical evidence on the impact of resilience strategies, such as green building certifications and climate-smart design, on long-term returns and risk mitigation in the South African retail sector. Existing research on the impact of climate change on SCs performance has

primarily focused on mature markets, where extensive data is readily available, such as in the United States, Europe, and Australia. However, the empirical evidence in emerging markets is scarce and disjointed. Hence, this study aims to investigate the intersection of climate-resilient strategies and financial and operational performance in the South African SCs industry. By constructing a climate resilience index (CRI) that accounts for the dynamic interplay between climate-related risks, this the relationship between climate resilience and financial and operational performance of SCs can be ascertained with some degree of confidence.

Methodology

Data

We examine the link between CRI and the performance of SCs. A comprehensive dataset is assembled, aggregating information from credible sources, including the South African Council of Shopping Centres (SACSC) and SAPOA, supplemented by financial data extracted from financial statements and annual reports, spanning a five-year period from 2019 to 2024. The research focus is concentrated on investment-grade SCs in SA, specifically those managed by listed REITs and institutional investors. The study incorporates a range of climate-related metrics, including water efficiency scores, flood mitigation infrastructure, renewable energy integration, and insurance costs. A diverse sample of 322 SCs was selected, encompassing a wide range of sizes, from small community-based centres (1000 square meters) to large regional malls (over 170,000 square meters), thereby ensuring a comprehensive representation of the landscape.

Model

Equation (1) tests the first hypothesis to ascertain the relationship between climate resilience and SCs' financial performance proxied by internal rate of return (IRR)

$$IRR_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_{i1}CRI_{it} + \beta_{i2}Climate\ Risk_{it} + \beta_{i3}X_{it} + \beta_{i4}Y_{it} + \varepsilon_i \quad (1)$$

In equation (2), the second hypothesis is tested ascertain the operational resilience, proxied by NOI as a function of climate risk factors.

$$NOI_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_{i1}CRI_{it} + \beta_{i2}EnergyEfficiency + \beta_{i3}WaterEfficiency + \beta_{i4}Op.Disruption + \varepsilon_i \quad (2)$$

where $t = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, 322$, X_{it} denote a vector of property features and Y_{it} is a vector of property costs.

Given the panel nature of the dataset and for robustness purposes, we estimate both the random and fixed effects (FE) models for the relationships. The ordinary least squares (OLS) regression which pools that the data is equivalent to fixed effects estimation of the relationship. These allow us to examine the influence of REIT-specific characteristics as well as unobservable features that have bearing on the CG performance of the REITs.

Climate resilience index construction

A climate resilience index (CRI) is constructed using composite scoring incorporating five key dimensions. These include physical resilience, energy resilience, water resilience, operational resilience, and location vulnerability as shown in Table 2.

There are various restructuring methods; these include principal component analysis (PCA), and multiple correspondence analysis (MCA) among others. Measurement or nature of the variables always informs the preferred an appropriate method to use. The commonly used method is PCA, and it is appropriate for the restructuring of continuous variables only. Whereas MCA is appropriate for the restructuring of categorical variables (Greenacre & Blasius 2006). We constructed a CRI using MCA. In the context of this work, we transform the climate resilience dimensions (indicators) adopted by the SCs into categories of Yes (1), and No (0). Across the dimensions (indicators) listed in Table 2, a SC may have measures in place to that ensure resilience in that direction or otherwise. For instance, a SC that has infrastructure for flood defence systems, fire-resistance materials, structural adaptation for heat/wind, etc. are scored 1 and 0 otherwise under the Physical Resilience dimension. These are then converted into contributions such as can be used in the regression for this study. The MCA uses a singular decomposition and weighted least squares techniques to find low-dimensional best fitting subspaces with minimal inertia and information loss (LeRoux & Rouants, 2010).

Table 2: Climate resilience indicators

Dimension	Sub-indicators	Source / Proxy Data
A. Physical Resilience	- Flood defence systems	Architectural/engineering audits, GBCSA Green Star documentation
	- Fire-resistant materials	
	- Structural adaptation for heat/wind	
	- Rooftop cooling/albedo strategies	
B. Energy Resilience	- On-site renewable energy (solar, etc.)	Energy audit reports, sustainability disclosures
	- Energy storage systems	
	- Smart grid integration	
	- Energy Efficiency Ratings (EPCs)	
C. Water Resilience	- Rainwater harvesting	Infrastructure reports, Green Star ratings
	- Water-efficient fixtures	
	- Onsite water storage	
	- Borehole use and recycling	
D. Operational Resilience	- Business continuity plans (BCPs)	Lease documentation, insurer data
	- Climate risk insurance coverage	
	- Emergency protocols (evacuation, fire drills)	
	- Security and disaster response systems	
E. Location Vulnerability	- Climate risk exposure score (flood/fire/drought)	NDMC risk atlases, CSIR Geo-spatial data, IPCC regional assessments
	- Elevation, proximity to rivers or coastlines	
	- Municipality-level climate hazard zoning	

Table 3: Variable specification

Variable	What the variable represents	Variable type and measurement
Per_{it}	IRR, NOI, Occupancy rates	Dependent variable: Financial performance - IRR (annualised rate of return that an investment is expected to generate) Operational performance - NOI (Income generated from property minus expenses)
CRI_{it} $Climate Risk_{it}$	Energy efficiency (kWh/m ² /year) Water efficiency (litres/m ² /year) Green building certification (binary/ordinal) Flood/drought mitigation infrastructure (binary) Emergency preparedness (ordinal scale)	Independent and continuous variables Detailed explanation in table 2 for CRI Climate risk variable has three components (flood, heat, waters stress) suggest overall climate risk each rated 1-5
X_{it}	Property age, construction year, location dummy, GLA, Renovation date,	Control variables Property age (age of the centre) Property size (GLA) Property location (categorical, a 1 is allotted if property in coastal 0 otherwise)
Y_{it}	Maintenance costs, insurance costs, security costs	Continuous variables Maintenance and insurance costs are derived from the function of value Security costs are directly calculated from annual rates and property size Occupancy rate (percentage of tenanted space) Operational disruption (operational costs, annual events)

		that interrupt normal property operations)
α_i	Constant	

Empirical analysis

Descriptive analysis

Descriptive results are presented in Table 4. Occupancy rates demonstrate a remarkably high average of 94%, coupled with relatively low variability, indicating a high level of tenancy stability across the SCs. The IRR, Property Age, and maintenance costs among others show adequate levels of variability to suggest that the right regression models can be applied to answer the research question. This provides valuable insights into the investment performance of these retail assets.

Table 4: Descriptive statistics

Variables	Mean	Std. dev.	Min.	Max.
IRR	5.27111	1.353815	2.652963	9.500001
Property Age (Years)	26.93665	5.414201	5	35
Occupancy Rate (%)	93.98636	2.572056	88.27099	99.73644
GLA (m ²)	19813.66	8415,267	15000	35000
Climate Adaptation Cost (R)	2854323	1243208	1714435	6475000
Maintenance costs	7938228	3434737	5173221	16117144
Insurance costs	1587646	686947.5	1034644	3223429
Security Cost (R)	1022919	404301.3	517565.3	2040000
Flood Risk (1-5)	2.869565	0.591324	2	4
Heat Risk (1-5)	3.214286	0.784828	2	5
Water Stress Risk (1-5)	3.108696	0.587829	2	5
Energy Cost (R)	8578923	3550997	4949218	15750000
Green Star Rating	1.779503	1.804063	0	4
Water Cost (R)	2511231	1202450	1304264	5040000

Note: Number of observations is 1,610 for all variables.

Correlation analysis

Table 5 presents the correlation matrix revealing a clear pattern of correlation among the variables. There are moderate to strong positive and negative correlations suggesting the complex nexus between the dependent variables and the independent variables. Having established no evidence for multicollinearity based on results from Table 6, this paves way to further examine these relationships through the panel regressions employed in the subsequent sections.

Table 5: Pairwise correlation

Variables	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9
(1) IRR	1.000*								
	(0.000)								
(2) Property Age (Years)	0.011	1.000*							
	(0.651)	(0.000)							
(3) Location_Coastal	0.308*	-0.045	1.000*						
	(0.000)	(0.074)	(0.000)						
(4) Occupancy Rate (%)	0.047	-0.052*	-0.032	1.000*					
	(0.057)	(0.035)	(0.205)	(0.000)					
(5) GLA (m ²)	-0.047	0.557*	0.046	-0.072*	1.000*				
	(0.062)	(0.000)	(0.066)	(0.004)	(0.000)				
(6) COVID_dummy	-0.085*	-0.074*	-0.000	-0.003	0.000	1.000*			
	(0.001)	(0.003)	(1.000)	(0.905)	(1.000)	(0.000)			
(7) Construction Year	0.100*	-0.948*	0.047	0.061*	-0.588*	0.000	1.000*		
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.059)	(0.014)	(0.000)	(1.000)	(0.000)		
(8) Maintenance costs	0.014	0.592*	0.075*	-0.096*	0.988*	-0.028	-0.586*	1.000*	
	(0.582)	(0.000)	(0.003)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.254)	(0.000)	(0.000)	
(9) Insurance costs	0.014	0.592*	0.075*	-0.096*	0.988*	-0.028	-0.586*	1.000*	1.000*
	(0.582)	(0.000)	(0.003)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.254)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)
(10) Security Cost (R)	0.224*	0.242*	0.184*	0.045	0.564*	-0.031	-0.213*		

Note: ***, **, * indicate 1%, 5% and 10% significant levels, respectively.

Variance inflation factor

In Table 6, we use variance inflation factor (VIF) to assess the possibility of multicollinearity among the variables. Following the rule of thumb of a maximum VIF of 10, the values are within the acceptable range, indicating that multicollinearity is not problem to affect the results.

Table 6: Variance inflation factor

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
CRI	2.874	0.348
COVID_dummy	1.293	0.774
Location_Coastal	1.337	0.748
Security Cost (R)	9.175	0.109
Net Operating Income	8.798	0.114

Main results

Climate resilience and SCs' financial performance (OLS results)

The OLS results provide insight into Hypothesis 1, revealing a significant negative relationship between CRI and IRR presented in Table 7. Our analysis reveals that a decline in CRI is associated with a substantial 1.94% decrease in IRR. This counterintuitive finding suggests that SCs with

higher CRI may experience lower returns, possibly due to the associated higher upfront costs or market valuation effects. Climate risk has a detrimental effect on IRR, leading to a significant reduction of -0.35%. This highlights the importance of finance and climate disclosure, as emphasized by Ameli et al (2020).

SCs located in coastal areas command a premium, with a 1.19%-point increase in IRR. Additionally, we found a positive relationship between occupancy rates and IRR, indicating that well-occupied SCs tend to outperform those with lower occupancy rates. In contrast, larger properties, as measured by GLA, tend to exhibit slightly lower IRR.

Table 7: Climate resilience and SCs' financial performance (OLS)

R-squared	0.345			
Adjusted R-squared	0.340			
F-statistic	51.79***			
Prob (F-statistic)	2.36e-90			
Observations	1,610			
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	P-value
Constant	-68.874***	15.941	-4.320	0.000
CRI	-1.937***	0.374	-5.184	0.000
Climate Risk	-3.054***	0.621	-4.921	0.000
Location_Coastal	1.191***	0.105	11.356	0.000
Occupancy Rate (%)	0.051***	0.013	4.075	0.000
GLA (m ²)	-0.0003***	2.64e-05	-12.691	0.000
COVID_dummy	-0.091	0.075	-1.209	0.227
Construction Year	0.040***	0.008	4.889	0.000
Climate Adaptation Cost	5.73e-08	2.55e-07	0.225	0.822
Maintenance costs	8.71e-07***	1.08e-07	8.055	0.000
Security Cost	-7.21e-07***	2.31e-07	-3.120	0.002

Note: ***, **, * indicate 1%, 5% and 10% significant levels, respectively. Dependent variable is IRR.

Figure 5 illustrates graphically the OLS regression coefficients for each variable in the model as they appear in Table 7. Except for the COVID dummy and climate adaptation costs, several variables exhibit high statistical significance, including CRI, Climate Risk, Location on the Coast, Occupancy Rate, GLA, Construction Year, Maintenance Costs, and Security Costs.

Figure 5: Climate resilience and SCs’ financial performance

Except for coastal location, occupancy rate, and maintenance costs, construction year, all variables have negative relation with IRR. The main variable of interest CRI is inversely related with IRR. This is understandable given that there are several capital-intensive infrastructures to improve and maintain climate resilience. Hence, in the short- to medium-term, increased cost will have downplay profitability. However, in the long-term, it is expected that SCs will reap the benefits of their capital investment. In subsequent years, a long span of data may be able to reveal this expectation. In the same vein, the other variables such as insurance and GLA are implicit cost items and can be understood in the manner of CRI’s nexus with IRR. For positive relationships, coastal located SCs tend to have higher IRR than inland ones and could be explained by high upper-class patronage and holiday patrons. It does also imply that, the coastal SCs may not have higher costs to forestall climate-related disruptions because of their locations. For occupancy rate, at about 94% as indicated in the descriptive statistics, it makes sense for it to impact financial performance positively from rental income, all things being equal.

Operational resilience and SCs’ climate related risks and costs

To motivate the use of NOI for operational performance, we employ a strip plot analysis as depicted in Figure 7. The visual representation of NOI performance across the sample reveals a discernible hierarchical structure, where SCs demonstrate stable operational growth year-on-year. Examined together with Figure 8 which presents the Year-on-Year NOI for selected SCs, this finding opens avenues for further investigation, including the examination of regional performance patterns to identify geographically specific trends influencing NOI. Additionally, an analysis of the impact of sustainability metrics on NOI could provide insights into the relationship between environmental considerations and financial performance. Alternatively, an investigation into the tenant mix of top-performing SCs could offer valuable lessons for optimising retail composition. Furthermore, identifying investment opportunities in underperforming SCs could yield potential for revitalisation and growth. Lastly, a comparative analysis with industry benchmarks could contextualise the findings within a broader market framework.

Figure 7: Year-on-Year distribution of NOI all SCs

Figure 8: Year-on-Year NOI for selected SCs

Operational resilience and SCs’ climate related risks and costs (random and fixed effects)

The random effects panel regression analysis reveals a significant relationship between property NOI performance and climate operational resilience, water efficiency, providing a compelling business case for investing in ESG initiatives in these areas. Unlike the IRR, while the efficiency metrics are also cost related, in the specific context of NOI measuring efficiency of operations, this finding are expected, at least in the short- to medium-term. It is also expected that in the long-term, these efficiencies will translate into improved financial performance. A surprising exception is the finding that investments in energy efficiency do not appear to yield significant returns in this sample, mirroring the results of Baker and Nofsinger (2012). This disparity highlights the need for

further investigation into the methodologies used to measure energy efficiency investments, for instance.

Given that CRI and water efficiency are substantial positive drivers of NOI but energy efficiency is not, albeit statistically significant, we cannot fully confirm hypothesis H1b. Further, operational disruptions show a positive and highly significant nexus with NOI, in which further jeopardises the hypothesis. This raises questions worth investigating subsequently.

Table 8: Operational resilience and SCs' climate related risks and costs

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	P-value
Climate Resilience	2,546,000***	1,133,000	2.25	0.025
Energy Efficiency	-971,300	678,000	-1.43	0.152
Water Efficiency	1,910,000***	660,200	2.89	0.004
Operational Disruptions	62.18***	1.47	42.24	<0.001
Diagnostic Test	Result			
Overall Model Fit	F = 2,814.2, p < 0.001			
Robust F-test	F = 912.14, p < 0.001			
R-squared (Overall)	0.9164			
R-squared (Within)	0.8868			
R-squared (Between)	0.9165			

Note: ***, **, * indicate 1%, 5% and 10% significant levels, respectively. Dependent variable is NOI.

Lastly, as indicated earlier, the panel data necessitates examining the unique and largely unobservable SCs features that may affect their operational performance. Thus, the fixed effect (Within) and random effect (Between) estimators were both employed, under the diagnostics of the model. While there are advanced techniques for examine this, for the purposes of simplicity and brevity, we use these for distinction. The *Within* model assumed heterogeneity across the SCs as against the *Between* model, and hence, ignore their differences and examines the data across time only. We find that in testing H1b, the random effects (Within) model boasts of higher explanatory power (about 92%) as against 89% for the fixed effect. This provides a simple robustness check for the model.

In terms of scaling, we acknowledge the somewhat differences in the data variables. However, have allowed the regression estimator to use its internal scaling to be applied on the data. We have avoided making external transformation of the data (at this stage). This will be considered in the subsequent fully-fledged study on the subject.

Conclusion

This research investigates the relationship between SCs and diverse performance metrics, with a particular emphasis on their resilience to climatic factors. A rigorous analysis of the data revealed statistically significant relationships between SCs performance indices and climate-related variables.

Our CRI and IRR outcome suggest that these measures may have a detrimental impact on returns on investment in the short term, but potentially safeguarding long-term sustainability and financial stability by minimising climate variability and its associated risks. Furthermore, the findings of

this study suggest that SCs that prioritise CRI are more likely to maintain their competitiveness in the face of climate-related disruptions. According to Litz & Rakaguru (2008) the central place theory emphasise that climate shocks reduce the centers' range and raise their threshold. High CRI sustains catchment and competitive hierarchy, even if short term IRR declines. Liu & Li (2020) suggests that the land use and accessibility theory resilient measures protect effective accessibility, that leads to upfront costs but preserves long term locational rent and tenant stability. Furthermore, Harvey (2015) emphasise that the behavioral location theory posits that many investors outweigh short-term IRR, but managers who prioritise CRI hedge against catastrophic climate risk

We conclude that SCs, with higher physical resilience, exhibit stronger investment performance. Shopping centre managers and owners can capitalise on the CRI to inform them of their decision-making and enhance their property's overall resilience. Operational features such as energy efficiency, water reuse systems, and backup power contribute positively to NOI. Moreover, these findings suggest that SCs with robust operational features can better withstand climate-related disruptions and ensure business continuity. From a central perspective these features enable SCs to sustain their range and threshold during climate disruption, thereby maintaining their competitive position within the retail hierarchy. The Land use accessibility theory reinforces this by framing resilience measures to preserve effectiveness. CRI enhances both short term efficiency and long-term competitiveness by stabilizing NOI.

The practical applications of this research underscore the necessity for South African SCs to develop and implement customised climate-resilience strategies that can be integrated into their existing business models. The creation of financial instruments and funding mechanisms is crucial to facilitate the adoption of climate-resilient design, technologies, and practices. To mitigate the financial and operational risks associated with climate change, whilst capitalising on emerging opportunities, it is imperative for SCs in SA to prioritise CRI and adapt to the changing climate.

Future research directions could explore the impact of climate change on property valuations and investment strategies. By prioritising CRI, South African SCs can differentiate themselves in the retail market and contribute to the country's growth and development.

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Factors Influencing Female Access to Mortgage Facilities in the Lagos Property Market *Abiodun Odunalde Adejumo¹; Matthew Oluwale Oyewole²; Funmilayo Moyinoluwa Araloyin³ and Timothy Oluwafemi Ayodele⁴*

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Abstract

There is increasing conversation on gender equity and inclusivity in financial systems, especially mortgage financing, across most emerging markets. This study investigates female access to mortgage facilities in the Lagos property market. The Lagos property market was stratified into two: Lagos mainland and Lagos Island. From these, a total of 105 buildings were surveyed in three randomly chosen gated estates from each stratum. Descriptive and Inferential statistics, frequency, mean ratings, and ANOVA were employed to analyse the data. The study revealed that access to mortgage facilities remains limited due to structural and cultural constraints rather than financial incapacity alone. Key barriers identified include lack of collateral, gender discrimination, and cultural norms, while limited awareness and unstable income were rated as less significant. The study concludes that addressing mortgage accessibility for women in Lagos demands policy reforms beyond income support, including gender-sensitive financial frameworks and legal reform of land and collateral systems. These findings underscore the urgent need for inclusive housing finance strategies that reflect the lived realities of women in Nigeria's urban real estate landscape.

Keywords: *Mortgage Facility, female accessibility, Gender equality, and Policy Reforms*

Introduction

Access to mortgage finance is a crucial factor for housing security, wealth creation, and significant economic growth in both developed and developing countries. However, in many developing economies, gender disparities still exist in access to mortgage systems, as women often face limitations due to economic, legal, and cultural factors. Certain barriers, including a lack of collateral, unequal income distribution, and embedded biases within financial institutions, hinder women's active participation in the real estate market (Chant, 2013; World Bank, 2022). Globally, financial inclusion has improved substantially; however, developing markets reveal that women remain largely marginalized from credit markets, which disrupts their agency in real estate financing and ownership. These challenges are rooted in monetary, legal, institutional, and behavioral frameworks that sustain inequality.

In emerging nations like Nigeria, these challenges are more evident. According to Premium Times (2022), 98% of Nigerian women have limited access to formal credit markets, mainly due to engagement in informal work, which creates difficulties in meeting standard mortgage requirements such as income verification and collateral provision. Male-controlled customs hinder women's efforts to gain property rights or ownership, and the limited presence of primary mortgage institutions worsens the situation (Spaces for Change, 2022). However, some women still seek loans from microfinance banks or credit societies, but these often come with higher interest rates, smaller loan amounts, and short repayment periods, often insufficient for purchasing real estate. Lagos' real estate market, one of the most vibrant and promising in sub-Saharan Africa,

faces these challenges, fueled by bureaucratic delays, strict eligibility criteria, and social bias (Chukwumeka & Adebayo, 2021).

Despite increasing research on residential housing finance in Nigeria, a gap remains in understanding the specific socio-economic, cultural, and institutional factors. These factors influence women's access to mortgage finance in high-demand, developed markets like Lagos. Most literature generalizes mortgage accessibility without effectively addressing gender-specific barriers or explaining how market dynamics in major commercial centers contribute to these limitations. Therefore, the study aims to examine the factors affecting female access to mortgage facilities in Lagos real estate by analyzing the profile of female mortgage seekers, assessing the level of accessibility to mortgage finance, and identifying the key influencing factors. To provide a well-rounded financial overview and promote gender-balanced structures, the research offers insights for policy evaluation, enhances institutional practices, and promotes a gender-responsive housing system in Lagos and Nigeria at large.

Literature Review

2.1 *Mortgage Facilities*

Mortgage facilities are financial products that enable individuals and businesses to buy real estate by borrowing funds, using the property as collateral. These arrangements are vital for homeownership, allowing buyers to access large sums of money that would otherwise be unavailable. Borrowers generally repay these loans in installments that include both principal and interest over a set period. Because residential mortgage facilities facilitate the purchase and refinancing of real estate, they play a key role in boosting the flow of funds in real estate markets. Mortgages offer a systematic approach that promotes economic growth and long-term investment, especially when initial capital requirements create significant barriers to entry (Fabozzi, 2020). Mortgage facilities support homeownership and help maintain overall economic stability by bridging the gap between immediate financial capacity and property value through ongoing market activity (Gyourko & Tracy, 2017; Mian & Sufi, 2014). On the other hand, the current study tends to view mortgage markets as gender-neutral, assuming equal access for all intended borrowers. This assumption overlooks fundamental inequalities that especially affect certain groups, notably women involved in property ownership. Although these issues reveal the economic importance of mortgage finance, they also show how sociocultural, organizational, and gender-specific challenges can restrict access to mortgage facilities. This gap highlights the need for more context-specific research, especially in regions like Nigeria, where financial mortgage markets are deeply intertwined with gender and socio-economic issues.

2.2 *Challenges of Female Access to Mortgage Facilities*

Despite Nigeria's increasing efforts to promote financial inclusion, women still encounter major obstacles when trying to obtain home financing. Economically, women's eligibility for mortgages is restricted by the gender wage gap, inconsistent income sources, and absence of verifiable credit history (Olawumi *et al.*, 2019; Ghosh, 2022). Since many women work in the informal sector, it might be challenging to provide the documentation and evidence of income that lenders seek. Even women with steady incomes struggle to satisfy mortgage terms due to the high interest rates, which are frequently above 20%, and the sky-high cost of real estate in Lagos (BuyLetLive Report, 2024; Abbey Mortgage Bank, 2024). Women, especially those without male co-signers or institutional support, are disproportionately discouraged or excluded by the bureaucratic, lengthy wait times and opaque approval systems that plague the mortgage process itself (Smith *et al.*, 2018; Nwuba & Chukwuma-Nwuba, 2019).

Beyond financial constraints, long-standing institutional and sociocultural obstacles further limit women's access to home finance. Overt and systemic gender discrimination persists in lending processes, as women are often scrutinized more closely or denied decision-making authority over property ownership (Chant, 2013; UN-Habitat, 2023). Since many women lack direct land rights or valid collateral, land ownership laws and the complexity of title documents also pose legal challenges (Akinmoladun, 2021; *Frontiers in Built Environment*, 2024). These issues support institutional theory, demonstrating how formal procedures and informal rules equally restrict women's access to mortgage finance. Moreover, women's limited knowledge and financial literacy, especially outside affluent circles, discourage them from exploring mortgage options (Rockefeller Philanthropy Advisors, 2022; Adegbile & Oluwatobi, 2020). These complex problems expose gaps in the implementation of inclusive housing financing policies and emphasize the urgent need for targeted reforms that empower women to fully participate in the real estate market (World Bank, 2021; Ghosh, 2022). The findings of this study reveal that women's challenges are not only economic but also systemic, highlighting a profound gender imbalance in Nigerian society. However, previous studies often identify these barriers without adequately examining the specific context of Lagos and its unique urban economy. This study investigates the interaction between cultural, institutional, and structural factors influencing mortgage finance in Lagos, Nigeria.

2.3 Factors Influencing Female Access to Mortgage Facilities

Extant studies have examined gender differences in access to mortgage financing. Studies such as Ghosh (2022) have demonstrated how cultural norms, institutional biases, and socioeconomic variables restrict women's access to official housing finance systems. Similarly, Smith *et al.* (2018) pointed out that discriminatory land tenure arrangements and systemic banking practices continue to cause gendered financial exclusion in many developing nations, despite governmental attempts. In the same vein, Adegoke *et al.* (2016) and Nwuba & Chukwuma-Nwuba (2019) highlight the systemic barriers that Nigerian women encounter while attempting to obtain mortgage financing. These barriers include strict lending requirements, lower income levels, and strict collateral requirements as a result of land ownership concerns. These studies highlight how gendered economic and legal systems distort access to mortgage finance for females. In another study, Olawumi *et al.* (2019) revealed that interest rates, collateral requirements, and bureaucratic bottlenecks are impediments in the mortgage market that disproportionately affect women. Olateju (2018) went one step further and looked at the direct effects of sociocultural norms, like the belief that men should own real estate, on women's involvement in credit and mortgage programs. The financial exclusion of women was also highlighted by Rockefeller Philanthropy Advisors (2022) and *Frontiers in Built Environment* (2024), which identified inadequate credit history tracking, informal job status, and ignorance as the main obstacles.

Although these reviewed existing studies contribute significantly by identifying two analytical gaps, they also reveal limitations. First, most studies focus on the typical form of gendered financial segregation by examining how these dynamics unfold in Lagos' real estate market, where rapid urbanization, rising property values, and segmented financial access create unique barriers. Second, current studies tend to be descriptive rather than investigative, stopping at identifying barriers without deeply questioning issues of control, inequality, and agency. This study addresses these gaps by adopting a feminist economics perspective, which emphasizes how gendered divisions of labor, credit allocation, and ownership rights are fundamentally inconvenient for women. In relation to financial inclusion theory, which highlights unbiased access to financial

products, female mortgage exclusion is seen not as a mere setback but because of socio-economic and functional dynamics. By focusing on Lagos, the study offers a nuanced analysis of how universal patterns of gender separation manifest within a megacity framework and proposes policy interventions to address them.

Methodology

The study adopted a quantitative research design. Explored structured questionnaires distributed to female homeowners in selected gated estates across Lagos Island and Lagos Mainland. The study sought numeric data that offers a measurable understanding of women's mortgage accessibility within the Lagos urban market context. Data were explored through three research questions: (i) the socio-economic characteristics, female property owners, and factors influencing mortgage access. (ii) the extent of female access to mortgage finances (iii) factors influencing female access to mortgage facilities. The study population comprises all gated estates on Lagos Island and the Mainland, from which a purposive sample of 12 estates was selected based on socio-economic characteristics and housing types. Through multi-stage sampling, six (6) estates, 3 from each area, Lagos Mainland, and Lagos Island, were randomly selected. Within each estate, a systematic sampling technique was applied to choose a total of 105 buildings, with questionnaires administered only in buildings where a woman is the property owner. This approach ensures both geographic and demographic representation, allowing for a focused exploration of barriers female homeowners face in the property financing process. The study's variables were designed with women's mortgage access as the dependent variable, which was measured using affordability, approval, documentation, and collateral criteria. Financial (income, credit history), institutional (bank regulations, bureaucracy), and social (gender norms, inheritance rights) aspects were all considered independent variables. Expert review and pilot survey testing were used to guarantee validity, while a Cronbach's alpha greater than 0.70 was used to prove dependability. For data analysis, the study employed descriptive statistical tools, including frequencies, percentages, and mean ratings. Opinion-based responses are evaluated using a five-point Likert scale and calculated through the Summation of Weight Value (SWV) to derive a Relative Accessibility Index (RAI). This measured rate of accessibility was assessed by comparing the financial, institutional, and socio-economic background challenges among respondents. The methodology interjects both accuracy and adequate representation based on reliable perceptions into the barriers' women property owners face in Lagos's mortgage financial market.

Discussion and Analysis

Table 1: Socio-economic Characteristics

Socio economic Characteristics		Lagos Island (%)	Lagos Mainland (%)	Lagos (%)
Age	Less than 20 years	--- (0.0%)	--- (0.0%)	--- (0.0%)
	20 to 39 years	15 (38.5%)	18 (50.0%)	33 (44.0%)
	40 to 59 years	22 (56.4%)	14 (38.9%)	36 (48.0%)
	60 years and above	2 (5.1%)	4 (11.1%)	6 (8.0%)
	Total	39 (100.0)	36 (100.0)	75 (100.0)
Marital Status	Single	10 (25.6%)	8 (22.2%)	18 (24.0%)

	Married	20 (51.3%)	19 (52.8%)	39 (52.0%)
	Divorced	3 (7.7%)	3 (8.3%)	6 (8.0%)
	Widowed	6 (15.4%)	6 (16.7%)	12 (16.0%)
	Total	39 (100.0)	36 (100.0)	75 (100.0)
Number of Dependent	One	5 (12.8%)	11 (30.6%)	16 (21.3%)
	Two	14 (35.9%)	22 (61.1%)	36 (48.0%)
	Three	13 (33.3%)	2 (5.6%)	15 (20.0%)
	More than three	7 (17.9%)	1 (2.8%)	8 (10.7%)
	Total	39 (100.0)	36 (100.0)	75 (100.0)
Educational Level	Basic Education	1 (2.6%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (1.3%)
	Secondary Education	7 (17.9%)	4 (11.1%)	11 (14.7%)
	Tertiary Education	31 (79.5%)	32 (88.9%)	63 (84.0%)
	Total	39 (100.0)	36 (100.0)	75 (100.0)
Employment Status	Employed	37 (94.9%)	33 (91.7%)	70 (93.3%)
	Retired	2 (5.1%)	3 (8.3%)	5 (6.7%)
	Total	39 (100.0)	36 (100.0)	75 (100.0)
Active Years in Service	Less than 10 years	32 (82.1%)	27 (75.0%)	59 (78.7%)
	10 to 29 years	6 (15.4%)	7 (19.4%)	13 (17.3%)
	30 years and above	1 (2.6%)	2 (5.6%)	3 (4.0%)
	Total	39 (100.0)	36 (100.0)	75 (100.0)
Monthly Income	Below N500,000	5 (12.8%)	4 (11.1%)	9 (12.0%)
	N500,000 to N999,999	20 (51.3%)	16 (44.4%)	36 (48.0%)
	N1,000,000 and above	14 (35.9%)	15 (41.7%)	29 (38.7%)
	Total	39 (100.0)	36 (100.0)	75 (100.0)
Income Stream	Single	9 (23.1%)	17 (47.2%)	26 (34.7%)
	Multiple	30 (76.9%)	19 (52.8%)	49 (65.3%)
	Total	39 (100.0)	36 (100.0)	75 (100.0)
Types of Property	Single Flat	14 (35.9%)	16 (44.4%)	30 (40.0%)
	Block of Flats	11 (28.2%)	11 (30.6%)	22 (29.3%)
	Duplex	12 (30.8%)	8 (22.2%)	20 (26.7%)

	Mansion	2 (5.1%)	1 (2.8%)	3 (4.0%)
	Total	39 (100.0)	36 (100.0)	75 (100.0)

4.1 Respondents Profile

The study first examined the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents who are female residents in selected gated estates in Lagos. Studies have established that socio-economic characteristics of respondents are important in the current discourse (Adebara, 2021; Nubi, 2001). Given the foregoing, the characteristics of the female respondents, as presented in Table 1, require a descriptive summary of the respondents in both Lagos Island and the Mainland. The findings revealed that 92% of the respondents were mostly between the ages of 20 and 59, which is the economically active age range. 52% married, and 84% of respondents have completed tertiary education, reflecting high levels of education among the female respondents. 93% are actively employed, indicating a high level of employment. These findings established a clear line of the sample populace, which is moderately educated, economically active, and primarily married, demographic features that are highly relevant to understanding mortgage awareness and adoption.

Furthermore, the table reveals extra drifts pointing out the possible correlation between socioeconomic attributes and property ownership. The finding of the research shows that 39% of income distribution groups make ₦1,000,000 and above each month, while nearly half (48%) make between ₦500,000 and ₦999,999. Given that a sizable percentage of respondents own higher-value assets like duplexes and apartment buildings, these comparatively high-income groups are consistent with trends in property ownership. Financial diversity may also have an impact on housing investment decisions, as evidenced by the statistics on income streams, which indicate that property owners are more likely to have various sources of income (65.3%). Without inferential testing, these associations, while significant, remain descriptive and should not be taken as relevant. The result of the analysis shows that during the active years of service, the respondent had 10 years or below active years in service. In particular, 78.7% of the respondents had 10 years or below active years of service in Lagos Island and Lagos Mainland, while 75.0% of the respondents had 10 years or below active years of service. Only 2.6% and 5.6% of the respondents had 30 years or above active years in service in Lagos Island and Lagos Mainland, respectively. Questions on the types of property owned by respondents were raised. The result of the analysis shows that the majority of the respondents owned a single flat. For instance, 35.9% of the respondents in Lagos Island and 44.4% of the respondents in Lagos Mainland owned a single flat. This was followed by respondents with block of flats (29.3%) and duplexes (26.7%). Having examined the socio-economic characteristics of respondents, the female access to mortgage facilities and factors influencing access to mortgage facilities were equally examined.

Table 2: Female Access to Mortgage Facilities

Variables for Accessibility	Island	Mainland	Lagos
Lack of collateral	3.11	3.44	3.28
Gender discrimination	3.01	3.21	3.11
Cultural/societal norms	2.01	2.19	2.10
High interest rate	2.05	2.01	2.03

Negative credit history/lack of credit	1.57	1.68	1.63
Complex documentation requirement	1.91	1.07	1.49
Bureaucratic delays	1.01	1.51	1.26
Low or unstable income	1.11	1.00	1.06
Limited awareness of options	1.02	1.05	1.04
Mean	1.87	1.91	1.89

4.2 Females’ Access to Mortgage Facilities

Table 2 shows female access to mortgage facilities in Lagos Island, the Mainland, and the overall Lagos average. The variables are barriers women face when accessing mortgage facilities, rated on a Likert scale of 1-5, where 1=Strongly Disagree, 2=Disagree, 3=Neutral, 4=Agree, and 5=Strongly Agree. The findings reveal that cultural and societal norms score high across Lagos Island and Mainland (2.01, 2.19), with Lagos overall scoring (2.10). These are followed by high interest rates (2.01, 2.05). Additionally, lack of collateral and gender discrimination are the most highly rated barriers among all variables for female access to mortgage finance, with scores of 3.11, 3.44, respectively. Bureaucratic delays and complex documentation show moderate barriers of (1.01, 1.91), with the Mainland experiencing a higher rate of bureaucratic delays. Awareness and unstable income rank the lowest among all variables (1.00, 1.11). The overall mean scores in both areas are (1.87 and 1.91), with an overall mean of (1.89 across Lagos, indicating significant challenges women face when accessing mortgage finance in Lagos. The findings imply that traditional beliefs and gender roles are significant obstacles for women seeking mortgage facilities. Interest rates also highlight the importance of affordability for borrowers, supporting the findings of Ojo (2022) and Akinwale et al. (2023), which suggest that cultural norms in Nigerian society are significant hurdles to women's economic empowerment in real estate finance. The Mainland consistently displays slightly higher constraint values (overall mean = 1.91) than the Island (1.87), suggesting that women on the Mainland encounter more obstacles when seeking a mortgage. This may be because the Mainland has a more diverse socioeconomic environment, while the Island tends to have a greater concentration of formal employment, income opportunities, and exposure to financial services (Ajayi & Adebayo, 2017). Therefore, the study confirms that female access to mortgages in Lagos is primarily hindered by structural and cultural barriers, rather than just financial capacity or knowledge. Policies focused solely on income support overlook the broader issues of discrimination and collateral problems.

Table 3: Lagos Island and Mainland T-Test Analysis Result

Variable	Island (M)	Mainland (M)	t-value	p-value
Lack of collateral	3.11	3.44	2.04	0.05
Complex documentation requirement	1.91	1.07	2.78	0.02
Bureaucratic delays	1.01	1.51	2.23	0.04

4.2.1 T-Test Analysis Result

The results of the paired t-test, presented in Table 3 below, indicate notable differences between Lagos Island and the mainland in terms of specific obstacles to female mortgage access. On the Mainland, the lack of collateral is more noticeable (t = 2.04, p = 0.05), which may indicate that the collateral requirements of financial institutions there are more stringent. Similarly, bureaucratic delays (t = 2.23, p = 0.04) are more bothersome on the Mainland, whereas sophisticated documentation requirements (t = 2.78, p = 0.02) are

reported to be more burdensome on the Island. These differences suggest that while impediments are systemic, their severity varies geographically, which may reflect the administrative procedures and institutional capabilities in different locations (Ajayi & Adebayo, 2017; Kuma, 2015).

Table 4: ANOVA Analysis Result for both Lagos Island and Mainland

Variable	F-Value	p-value
Lack of collateral	3.61	0.04
Complex documentation requirement	5.42	0.02
Bureaucratic delays	4.18	0.03

4.2.2 ANOVA Analysis Result

The ANOVA Result, shown in Table 4 below, validates that women's experiences of important barriers are highly influenced by location. Differences in bureaucratic delays ($F = 4.18$, $p = 0.03$), documentation requirements ($F = 5.42$, $p = 0.02$), and lack of collateral ($F = 3.61$, $p = 0.04$) are statistically significant. This supports the claim that, although these barriers are widespread, local institutional practices and market dynamics influence how severe they are. For example, respondents on the Lagos Mainland seem to be disproportionately impacted by delays and collateral, which is indicative of systemic injustices in banking procedures (Adedeji & Akinlolu, 2021).

Table 5: Regression Analysis Results.

Predictor	Beta (β)	p-value
Lack of collateral	0.35	0.003
Complex documentation requirement	0.32	0.005
Bureaucratic delays	0.28	0.011
Gender imbalance	0.19	0.080
Income uncertainty	0.11	0.211

4.2.3 Regression Analysis Result

The predictive power of structural barriers on female mortgage accessibility is demonstrated via regression analysis. Complex documentation ($\beta = 0.32$, $p = 0.005$), bureaucratic delays ($\beta = 0.28$, $p = 0.011$), and a lack of collateral ($\beta = 0.35$, $p = 0.003$) are all statistically significant predictors, indicating that institutional barriers continue to be the most restrictive factors. Although socially significant, gender imbalance ($\beta = 0.19$, $p = 0.080$) and income uncertainty ($\beta = 0.11$, $p = 0.210$) were not significant predictors, indicating that the more pressing institutional requirements of paperwork and collateral may take precedence over these variables. These results support previous research that found that the main mechanism excluding women in Nigeria is structural impediments in the loan markets (Ajayi & Adebayo, 2017; Nwuba & Chukwuma-Nwuba, 2018). Putting together the findings revealed that institutional constraints like collateral, paperwork, and bureaucracy, which vary in degree depending on the location, restrict women's access to mortgages in Lagos more than gender or income. This implies that rather than concentrating only on gender

advocacy, reforms aimed at banking practices and collateral arrangements may produce more equitable results.

Table 6: Factors Influencing female accessibility to Mortgage Facilities

Factors Influencing	Island	Mainland	Lagos
Discrimination based on gender	4.92	4.92	4.92
Income level and employment type	4.86	4.91	4.89
Cultural or religious limitations	4.71	4.82	4.77
Documentation and bureaucratic process	4.57	4.66	4.62
Availability of collateral	4.94	4.58	4.60
Interest rates	4.62	4.34	4.25
Experience dealing with financial institutions	4.16	3.79	3.98
Financial literacy or knowledge of loan procedures	3.75	3.42	3.59
Educational background	3.57	3.45	3.51
Credit history or rating	3.10	3.12	3.11
Access to information about loan products	3.05	3.03	3.04
Support from spouse/family	2.04	2.01	2.03
Mean	4.02	3.92	3.94

4.3 Factors Influencing Female Accessibility to Mortgage Facilities

The study examined factors influencing female accessibility to real estate mortgage facilities. The respondents were asked about their perception of the factors influencing female accessibility to real estate mortgage facilities using a Likert scale, 1-5, 1= Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Neutral, 4= Agree, and 5= Strongly Agree. Their responses are presented in Table 3. In explaining these factors, the mean values are compared with the range of values on the Likert scale to determine the extent of their influence.

As presented in Table 6, most of the respondents from Lagos Island agreed that the identified factors significantly influence access to real estate mortgage finance. This is supported by the aggregated mean score of 4.02, which approximates the "Agree" benchmark on the 5-point Likert scale. Specific high-impact variables include availability of collateral (M = 4.62), discrimination based on gender (M = 4.92), income level (M = 4.86), cultural or religious limitation (M = 4.71), interest rate (M = 4.62) documentation and bureaucratic process (M = 4.57), experience dealing with financial institution (M = 4.16) financial literacy or knowledge of loan procedures (3.75) educational background (3.57) credit history or rating (3.10) access to information about loan product (3.05) While, support from spouse/family (2.04). The findings inferred that collateral is non-negotiable in the Nigerian mortgage system. Additionally, gender bias is intricately woven

into the loan approval process. These results are consistent with earlier studies by Ajala (2017), who found that women often lack asset ownership due to a male-dominated inheritance system, and UN Women (2023) revealed that many Nigerian women still face informal discrimination even when documentation is complete and income is stable. Also, high interest rates make mortgages unattractive and inaccessible.

Respondents from Lagos Mainland revealed similar trends, with an aggregated mean score of 3.92, confirming that the indicated criteria have an important impact on mortgage accessibility. The key influencers mirrored those of Lagos Mainland: gender discrimination (M = 4.92), income level (M = 4.91), cultural and religious limitations (M = 4.82), documentation and bureaucratic process (M = 4.66), collateral availability (4.58), interest rates (4.34), experience dealing with financial institutions (3.75), educational background (3.45), financial literacy (3.42), credit history (3.12), and access to loan product information (3.03). On a scale of 1 to 5, support from a spouse or family was the least influential factor. The study found that the primary factors influencing mortgage facility accessibility include deeply embedded structural and institutional issues such as collateral availability, income level, and gender discrimination. The issues include not only a lack of knowledge or education but also systemic financial gatekeeping that promotes male-dominated ownership systems. Extant studies, such as Ajala (2017) and Adekunle *et al.* (2024), noted that Nigeria's land tenure and collateralization system strategically excludes women.

Conclusion

The study explored the factors influencing women's access to mortgage facilities in the Lagos property market. It examined the socio-economic characteristics of female homeowners, their ability to access mortgage finance, and the barriers that hinder this access. The findings showed that the socio-economic profile of the respondents indicated that these women were highly educated and financially empowered, with multiple sources of income. However, the results also revealed that financial capacity alone does not guarantee equal access to property ownership through mortgage loans. Women in Lagos continue to face significant systemic, structural, and institutional barriers to obtaining mortgage financing not because of a lack of income or financial knowledge, but due to institutionalized gender discrimination, cultural norms, and lack of collateral. These factors limit their chances of accessing mortgage finance fairly within the real estate market. Even with steady income and high levels of education, female borrowers are often considered high-risk by lenders because of patriarchal inheritance laws, assumptions about income stability, and male-centered financial regulations. These findings support theories of structural inequality in lending markets and expand our understanding of housing finance by illustrating how gender-based financial exclusion persists even among socio-economic groups with higher levels of power. Additionally, the study emphasizes the need for fundamental reforms in mortgage policies, shifting focus from basic affordability and awareness initiatives to addressing deeper structural issues and developing inclusive credit systems that eliminate discriminatory lending practices and collateral requirements.

The data also show that the general inadequacies of the mortgage market in developing countries are inextricably linked to the exclusion of women, regardless of gender-specific impediments. All potential borrowers are impacted by problems, including lenders' judgments of high risk, short payback terms, and high interest rates, and these systemic inefficiencies exacerbate the experiences of women. Acknowledging this interplay provides a more nuanced theoretical implication: gender-based financial exclusion is both a subset of, and amplified by, wider structural shortcomings in African mortgage systems.

The implications of the study suggest the need for systemic reforms in the mortgage and property acquisition policies and frameworks. Policies must transcend surface-level interventions and address deep-rooted gender biases entrenched in the lending practice and financing systems. Additionally, there might be a need to reform collateral requirements and lending practices. The study theoretically adds to the body of knowledge on women and housing finance by placing the disadvantage of women in Africa's underdeveloped mortgage markets and institutional gender bias. This will contribute significantly towards broader economic growth and social equity. The limitations of the study's findings include the exclusive focus on women in gated communities. This may not reflect the realities of women living in informal settlements and rural areas. Also, the socioeconomic class of the respondents suggests a predominantly high-income group with a high literacy level. This may not represent the demographic characteristics of females across most other areas within the state. Finally, while the study identified institutional barriers, to ensure a targeted reform, there might be further studies to examine specific policies and legal instruments that tend to influence female exclusion.

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**Peer Reviewed*

Women's Land Ownership and Rights in Botswana: An Institutional Analysis of Policy Implementation and Customary Constraints *Neltah Tshepiso Mokgware-Monosi¹; Prisca Simbanegavi²*

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Abstract

The 2015 Land Policy of Botswana, which was approved by the National Assembly of the Republic of Botswana on July 16, 2015, was met with mixed emotions by Batswana, particularly women. The consensus was that the Policy discriminated against women as it stipulated that ‘married women, widows and their children, were not allowed to own land or be allocated land if their husbands were landowners. This stripped women of their independence and economic rights, and was met with criticism for promoting gender inequality. In September 2020, the then-President of Botswana, Mokgweetsi Eric Masisi, revised the land policy, allowing every citizen of Botswana, regardless of their gender or marital status, an equal opportunity to own land of any tenure. This paper’s objective is to examine the impact of the 2015 Botswana Land Policy on women's land ownership, its subsequent amendment in 2019, and the importance of women owning land independently, regardless of their marital status. Empirical research formed the core of the research design, with the study adopting a qualitative policy review, supported by secondary empirical data on land ownership trends. Findings suggest that further research is necessary to provide reliable and up-to-date statistical data, enabling researchers to accurately evaluate the post-amendment results. Notably, the ownership of land by women has increased significantly across all age groups; however, it is also hindered by the backlog of land allocation by the land boards in Botswana. Further investigations are required to assess the effectiveness of policy implementation, particularly in addressing land board backlogs, improving gender-disaggregated data systems, and monitoring the long-term impacts across different age groups of women. Policymakers must strengthen implementation and data systems, while the industry should engage women as emerging landowners, as society benefits through greater gender equity and economic inclusion.

Keywords: Botswana; Gender Equality; Land Allocation Board; Land Policy; Land Ownership

1.0 Introduction

The Republic of Botswana, formally known as the Bechuanaland Protectorate, gained its Independence from Britain on September 30, 1966 (Mogalakwe, 2017). With only a population of 2,346,179, 1,246,709 males and 1,222,984 females as of 31st December 2022 (Statistics Botswana (2022), Botswana has progressed from being one of the poorest countries in Africa upon gaining its Independence (Lekobane, 2022) to one of the fastest-growing economies in Africa (Phiri, et al., 2022). The country has frequently been referred to as one of the exemplary countries of economic and societal development and growth (de Satgé, 2021). Being a landlocked country of 560,877sqm in size (Suh, et al., 2022), with a semi-arid climate due to the Kgalagadi desert extending to 900,000 square kilometres of the country (Saarinen, et al., 2020), the land dynamics and administration in Botswana are an ongoing topic for policymakers and the lawmakers of the country (Ntebang, 2018).

The rural population was reported to be approximately 28% in 2022 (The World Bank Organisation, 2022), leaving the majority of the population residing in urban areas. The rural-to-urban population migration over the years has been rapid due to the shortage of serviced land in rural areas (Kalabamu & Lyamuya, 2017).

Table 1 summarises the land tenure and the percentage of the land they cover in Botswana (Malatsi & Finnstrom, 2011; Kalabamu, 2019).

<u>LAND TENURE</u>	<u>PERCENTAGE</u>
Freehold land	3%
State land	24%
Tribal land	73%

Table 1: Land Tenure and Statistics in Botswana (Sources: Authors)

Given the vast availability of tribal land, under the Botswana Land Policy of 2015, plots are allocated by the government to individuals who meet the following requirements:

- Citizens of Botswana aged 18 years and above, and controversially;
- Unmarried women, excluding married women and surviving spouses, were not allowed to be allocated land, let alone apply for allocation (Republic of Botswana, n.d.).

The following section provides a detailed discussion of the Botswana Land Policy of 2015.

1.1 Background: Botswana's Law Policy of 2015

The issue of land administration in Botswana has long been a matter of significant contention among policymakers, government officials, and the general public. It is noted that Botswana's first land policy was introduced in 1985 (Adams et al., 2003). The Government engaged in nationwide consultations in 2004, 2006, 2010, 2011, and 2013 to develop the 2015 land policy (Kalabamu, 2021). The latter was then amended in 2019.

The 2015 Land Policy of Botswana, approved by the National Assembly of the Republic of Botswana on July 16, 2015 (Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations, 2023), was met with mixed emotions by the citizens of Botswana, particularly women. The consensus was that the Policy discriminated against women as it stipulated that 'married women, widows and their children, were not allowed to own land or be allocated land if their husbands were landowners. This stripped women of their independence and economic rights, and was largely met with criticism for promoting gender inequality.

As a result of the widespread condemnation from the public, international organisations and academics, (Griffiths, 2011) of what was called an infringement of women's rights and human and economic inequality (Martorano, et al., 2021), the government of Botswana decided to review the existing policy of 2015, which resulted in the well-received changes in the Deeds Registry Act and Married Persons Property Act.

Women and Property/Land Ownership in Botswana

The Deeds Registry Act and the Married Persons Property Act have modified the application and ownership of land by married persons (SADC Gender and Development Monitor, 2018, 2019). The Married Persons Property Act of 1971 was amended in 2014 (Government of Botswana, 2014) to allow women married under customary law to have their property administered under civil law. Married women are now allowed to change the property ownership between themselves and their husbands from 'in community of property' to 'out of community of property' and vice versa. Prior to the amendment,

married women were not allowed to own property (Republic of Botswana, n.d.). Despite these progressive legal reforms, significant gaps remain in the practical realisation of gender-equitable land ownership, particularly in the interpretation, implementation, and enforcement of these statutes across diverse socio-cultural contexts.

1.1 Problem Statement

The then-President of Botswana, Mokgweetsi Eric Masisi, whose tenure ended in 2024, revised the land policy, allowing every citizen of Botswana, irrespective of their gender and marital status, an equal opportunity to own land of any tenure of their choice. The reversal of this discriminatory policy has demonstrated the Government's support for gender equality in land ownership. Despite progressive reforms in Botswana's land policy, particularly the 2019 amendment aimed at gender equity, women's access to and control over land remains constrained by entrenched customary practices, patriarchal norms, and gaps in implementation. The coexistence of statutory and customary systems under legal pluralism creates ambiguity and inconsistency in land governance, often disadvantaging women. Furthermore, the limited availability of disaggregated data and insufficient longitudinal research hinder the ability to accurately assess the real impact of these reforms on women's empowerment and development outcomes. This paper seeks to critically examine how gendered land rights are conceptualised and governed in Botswana, and to identify the structural, legal, and cultural barriers that continue to undermine women's land security.

In light of these persistent challenges, this study formulates targeted research questions and objectives to examine the evolving landscape of gendered land rights in Botswana and assess the extent to which recent policy reforms have led to substantive change.

1.2 Research Objectives and Questions

This study aims to critically examine existing literature and policy developments to understand how legal reforms, customary norms, and gender dynamics interact to shape women's access to land in Botswana. The following research objectives guide the enquiry, each paired with a corresponding research question:

- **Objective 1:** To establish the importance of women owning land independently in Botswana.
Research Question 1: What are the socio-economic and legal implications of women owning land independently in Botswana?
- **Objective 2:** To assess the effects of the 2015 Land Policy prior to its amendment. **Research Question 2:** How did the 2015 Land Policy affect women's access to and control over land before the 2019 amendment?
- **Objective 3:** To evaluate the impact of the 2019 amendment on women's land ownership, empowerment, and development outcomes.
Research Question 3: To what extent has the 2019 amendment improved women's land ownership, legal recognition, and socio-economic empowerment in Botswana?

Having outlined the research's key objectives and guiding questions, the following section considers the broader significance of the study, highlighting its potential contributions to policy reform, gender equity, and inclusive land governance in Botswana and beyond.

1.3 Significance of the Study

This study holds significant importance in advancing both academic understanding and policy discourse on gendered land rights in Botswana. By examining the effects of the 2015 Land Policy and its 2019 amendment, the research provides evidence-based insights into how legal reforms influence women's access to property, autonomy, and socio-economic empowerment.

Specifically, the study:

- Illuminates the intersection of law, custom, and gender in Botswana's land governance, providing a nuanced perspective on how legal pluralism impacts women's rights.
- Evaluates the real-world impact of policy reform, contributing to the growing body of literature on gender equity in land ownership and informing future legislative and administrative decisions.
- Supports advocacy and institutional accountability, equipping stakeholders, policymakers, land boards, civil society, and researchers with data and analysis to promote inclusive land governance.
- Addresses a regional gap in empirical research, particularly in Southern Africa, where customary tenure systems continue to shape access to land.
- Empowers women through knowledge by highlighting the importance of independent land ownership as a pathway to economic stability, agency, and development.

Ultimately, the study contributes to the broader goal of ensuring that land reform processes are not only legally sound but socially just and gender-responsive.

In light of the preceding, the next section, which is the literature review, delves deeper into the existing literature on the land policy in Botswana, prior to its amendment in 2015, its implications for women and the impact of the subsequent revision of Section 72(iii) of the Land Policy in 2019. Furthermore, it will pinpoint the specific section in the policy that highlights the gender discriminatory aspect of the land policy, which prompted the National Assembly's advocacy, action and amendment. The discussion, findings and conclusion will then follow this section.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

Since attaining its independence in 1966, Botswana has introduced various land-related laws, policies and Acts (Kalabamu, 2021). The country's three land tenures are freehold land, state land, and tribal/customary land (Adams et al., 2003), which were adapted from the colonial rule of Botswana by the British monarchy. These tenures were formally referred to as freehold, native and crown land, correspondingly (Mathuba, 2003).

'Land tenure' is defined as the centralisation and management of a country's natural resources in which the ownership of the land is by individuals or entities, legally or under customary law (Prof. Kasimbazi, 2017). Professor Kasimbazi (2017) further explains that land tenure governs the relationship between individuals, the government and the utilisation of the land. This includes land associated with different tenures, including their use, control, and transfer. The three land tenures in Botswana, forming the theoretical framework, are explained in the following section.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Building on the foundational understanding of land tenure, the following theoretical framework outlines Botswana's tripartite land tenure system: State land, Tribal land, and Freehold land, which are each governed by distinct legal and administrative mechanisms that shape access, ownership, and control.

State land

Previously referred to as 'crown land' during the Colonial era, state land belongs to the nation and comprises national parks, urban land, and game reserves (Ng'ong'ola, 1996). The state's land management is governed by the State Land Act of 1966, as enacted by the President of Botswana (Land Links, 2010).

Freehold land

Freehold gives the owner perpetual ownership of the land (Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations, 2023). The same study by FAO reports that Botswana has a small percentage of freehold land, at 4.2 per cent, while tribal land comprises 70.9 per cent of the total land area, and state land covers 24.9 per cent of the country's total land area. When comparing the demand for land by prospective landowners, freehold land is in high demand due to its perpetual ownership.

Tribal land

Tribal land, which forms the majority of the land tenure in Botswana, is allocated to eligible applicants, specifically citizens of Botswana, through a decentralised system administered by land boards as per the Tribal Land Act (Kalabamu, 2021). Before this decentralisation, tribal land was allocated by Dikgosi (the vernacular word for 'Chiefs') (Ministry of Lands and Housing, 2015). As it stands, the allocation of tribal land falls under Customary and Common Law, in accordance with the Tribal Land Act (CAP 32:02). Unlike freehold land, tribal land is granted for a specific period, as part of a lease agreement between an individual and the government. According to the Botswana Land Policy of 2015, the fixed lease term for citizens is 99 years, while that for non-citizens is 50 years. Leases of 5 to 25 years can also be granted.

Given the central role of tribal land in Botswana's tenure system, recent revisions to the Land Policy Act warrant close examination, mainly in how they seek to address historical inequities, clarify administrative procedures, and promote gender-responsive land governance. Critically, this study draws on Legal Pluralism, Feminist Political Ecology, and the Rights-Based Approach to examine land rights, gender, and governance in Botswana, with the Rights-Based Approach being most relevant to the 2019 Land Policy Amendment.

Legal Pluralism

Legal pluralism refers to the coexistence of multiple legal systems within a single context. Griffiths (1986) defines weak legal pluralism as a situation where state authority recognises customary law, and strong legal pluralism as a situation where distinct systems operate without a hierarchy. In Botswana, this is reflected in statutory law, customary tenure, and policy frameworks. Tribal land operates under customary norms while statutory provisions promote equality, highlighting tensions between patriarchal practices and reforms aligned with gender equality.

Feminist Political Ecology

Feminist Political Ecology connects gender, power relations, and resource governance. Rocheleau, Thomas-Slayter, and Wangari (1996) emphasise that resource access is a political phenomenon, shaped by patriarchy. In Botswana, this framework reveals how patriarchal customs have excluded women from land ownership, limiting their empowerment and participation in development.

Rights-Based Approach

The Rights-Based Approach views land as a human right, grounded in conventions like CEDAW. It emphasises:

- Empowerment of women as rights-holders
- Government accountability
- Non-discrimination in land access
- Women's participation in governance

While Legal Pluralism and Feminist Political Ecology provide context about customary-statutory tensions and patriarchal structures, the Rights-Based Approach best frames this study, aligning with the 2019 Amendment's focus on eliminating gender discrimination in land rights. The 2019 Land Policy Amendment embodies this approach by removing discriminatory clauses against married women, recognising land access as a legal right aligned with human rights frameworks.

2.1 Assertion of Revised Sections in the Land Policy Act

The Botswana Land Policy Review of the 2015 Land Policy took place in 2019 (FAO, 2019) after issues in the then-existing land policy required its review on some of the clauses of the policy; these include:

- **Section 58 (i)**- Every Motswana will be eligible for allocation of a restricted allocation of only one plot at an area of their choice within a residential plot per person.
- **Section 58 (ii)** - 'One is deemed to be allocated a plot if they have lawfully acquired a plot, if it is registered in their name'.
- **Section 58 (iii)** - 'Once a person has a residential plot registered in their name, they will not be eligible for allocation of another residential plot'.
- **Section 69 (iv)** - A person will not be allowed to alienate their last residential plot acquired directly from the Land. '
- **Section 60(v)** - 'Ploughing fields (Masimo) on fertile land will be restricted, efficient land protected through zoning. Once zoned, a change of land use will not be allowed.

- **Section 77(ii)** - 'Title holders will not be allowed to change agricultural land holdings in tribal land to non-agricultural developments'.
- **Section 78 (viii)** – ‘Ploughing fields (Masimo) on fertile land will be protected through zoning and gazetment. Once gazetted as such, a change of land use will not be allowed.

2.2 Conceptualising Land Rights and Gender

Land rights in Botswana are closely tied to citizenship and tenure regimes. Historically, gender inequality has been evident, particularly in women’s limited access to and control over land. Before the 2019 Land Policy Amendment, women, especially married women, faced discriminatory clauses that restricted their eligibility for land allocation if their spouse had already been allocated a plot (FAO, 2015).

Section 72(iii) addresses gender inequality and the unequal treatment of women regarding land ownership. In 2019, the Land Policy Act was revised to ensure equality, fairness, protect property owners, and create better systems for the administration of land to Botswana and non-citizens, especially women.

Gender Discrimination in the Botswana Land Policy of 2015

Leading to the run-up to Botswana’s 2019 General Election, Presidential Candidate, now His Excellency the President of Botswana, Dr Mokgweetsi Masisi, pledged to ensure that the land policy was reviewed to not discriminate against married women (Daily News, 2020). The particular clause of debate is Section 72 (iii) of the Land Policy, which reads: “Each Botswana will be eligible for allocation of one residential plot at an area of their choice within the country, on both state land and tribal land.” (FAO, 2015). The Botswana Land Policy of 2015 was reviewed in the old Botswana Land Policy of 2015 and was found to have discriminatory clauses against married women. If a woman got married and their spouse had already been allocated a residential plot, the woman could not be allocated a plot.

<u>Age Groups</u>	<u>Men-owned Land</u>	<u>Women-owned Land</u>
20-24	110	35
25-29	687	184
30-34	1 277	936
35-39	829	1 501
40-44	1 442	1 871
45-49	2 203	2 736
50-54	3 895	4 941
55-59	5 231	5 530
60-65	5 754	4 205
65+	17 347	15 848
TOTAL	38 775	37 787

Table 2.1 Number of property ownership by age group and gender (SADC Gender and Development Monitor 2018, 2019)

2.3 Legal Pluralism and Land Governance in Africa

From 2015 to 2019, the year when statistical property ownership data became available, the proportion of land and property ownership held by women in Botswana has steadily increased. In 2019, 49.3% of landowners were women (SADC Gender and Development Monitor, 2018, 2019). Table 2.1 breaks down these statistics by age group. These figures are graphically represented in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1 Graphical Representation of Table 2.1 (Authors' compilation)

Accessing the database or primary data on property ownership, especially quantitative information, in Botswana has been quite challenging, even after consulting the Ministry of Lands, Water, and Sanitation, which oversees the administration of land in Botswana by the Department of Lands (Ministry of Lands and Housing, 2015). However, based on the literature covered in this chapter, there is evidence of significant gender inequality and discrimination before the Land Policy Amendment Policy of 2019, in property/land ownership which does not favour women (Kampamba & Mosweu, 2020) (Convention for the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women, 2022) (Kalabamu, 2021).

To fully understand the persistence of gender disparities in land ownership, it is essential to examine the interplay between customary tenure systems, patriarchal structures, and the broader legal and policy environment that continues to shape women's rights in Botswana.

2.4 Customary Tenure, Patriarchy and Women's Rights in Botswana: Legal and Policy Context

The Botswana Land Policy of 2015, presented in the Introduction, was reviewed in 2019. Section 2.2 notes the Sections of the Act that the National Assembly of Botswana reviewed. This will be followed by Section 2.3, which focuses on the gender review aspect of the Act review, specifically Section 78 (viii). Section 72 (iii) stated that since only one spouse can apply for a plot, the surviving spouse must, as a right, inherit their land allocations. This was reversed to allow women to apply for land allocation, irrespective of their marital status.

- **Property Ownership Trends:** Statistical data from 2015 to 2019 indicate steady growth in women's land ownership. By 2019, 49.3% of landowners in Botswana were women (SADC Gender and Development Monitor, 2018, 2019).
- **Policy Implications:** Despite legal progress, gender disparities persist, influenced by customary norms, patriarchal attitudes, and practical barriers to women's empowerment.

While legal reforms have begun to challenge patriarchal constraints within Botswana's land governance system, the accurate measure of progress lies in the extent to which secure land rights translate into tangible empowerment and development outcomes for women, which will be explored in the following section.

2.5 Land Rights, Empowerment and Development Outcomes

Secure land rights are widely acknowledged as a crucial element for empowering women, enhancing household welfare, and fostering inclusive socio-economic development. In Botswana, where land is a key asset for livelihood, investment, and social standing, women need to have access to and control over land. Many women depend on agricultural activities, informal trade, and home-based businesses for their income.

Women's access to land leads to:

- **Increased economic security and independence:** Owning or having a long-term lease on land enables women to engage in productive activities, access credit, and accumulate assets. This reduces their reliance on male relatives or spouses and strengthens their negotiating power within families and communities.
- **Enhanced household food security and agricultural productivity:** Research indicates that when women have secure land tenure, they are more inclined to invest in land improvements and sustainable farming methods, resulting in higher yields and improved nutritional outcomes for their families.
- **Social equity and poverty reduction:** Land rights serve as a tool for redistributive justice, particularly in societies where historical and customary systems have historically excluded women from property ownership. By enabling women to own and inherit land, reforms help close gender gaps in wealth, opportunities, and decision-making.

The reforms implemented in Botswana, particularly the 2019 amendment to the Land Policy, mark a significant move towards removing structural barriers to women's land ownership. These policy changes are beginning to challenge deep-rooted patriarchal norms and legal uncertainties that previously disadvantaged women, especially in tribal and customary tenure systems. The rise in female land ownership, as shown in national statistics, indicates progress not only in legal recognition but also in the broader empowerment of women as economic agents and rights holders.

However, the transformative potential of land rights relies on more than just statutory reform. It necessitates effective implementation, public awareness, institutional accountability, and the alignment of customary and statutory systems. Without these, women may still encounter

informal exclusion, administrative obstacles, and social resistance that undermine the goals of progressive legislation.

In conclusion, secure land rights are not just a legal entitlement; they are a driving force for gender equity, poverty reduction, and sustainable development. Botswana's evolving land governance framework provides valuable insights into how targeted reforms can achieve these outcomes, while also emphasising the need for ongoing vigilance, research, and advocacy to ensure that policy advancements translate into real-life benefits for women across the country. Secure land rights are a critical enabler of women's empowerment, household welfare, and broader socio-economic development.

The reforms in Botswana demonstrate how land rights can significantly impact gender equity and inclusive development outcomes.

2.6 Critical Gaps in the Literature

- **Limited quantitative data:** Accessing disaggregated land ownership data in Botswana remains difficult despite attempts to obtain primary records (Ministry of Lands and Housing, 2015).
- **Customary vs. statutory conflict:** Research has yet to fully capture how customary norms continue to limit women's land rights despite statutory reforms.
- **Intersectional dimensions:** Few studies assess how age, marital status, and socio-economic background intersect with gender to affect land access.
- **Implementation challenges:** Although laws have been reformed, there is a lack of analysis on how effectively they are enforced at the local level.

The trajectory of property ownership by women and their married counterparts will be discussed in the following Methods section of this paper. Furthermore, the research objectives, as stated in the introduction section, will be investigated through assessments of existing literature.

3 Methods

3.1 Research Design

This study adopts a quantitative, cross-sectional research design supplemented by documentary analysis. The primary aim is to assess whether the 2019 policy amendment has led to statistically significant changes in land ownership patterns between men and women. A chi-square test of independence was used to examine associations between gender and land ownership status. The design also integrates a legal-historical lens to interpret findings within Botswana's evolving land governance framework.

3.2 Study Area

The study focuses on Botswana, with particular attention to the allocation of tribal and state land across urban and peri-urban districts. Given the decentralised nature of land administration through land boards, the study area includes representative regions such as Kweneng District, Gaborone, and Francistown, where land demand and gender disparities are most pronounced.

3.3 Sampling Strategy

A purposive sampling strategy was employed to select a dataset of 76,562 land ownership records disaggregated by gender and age. The sample was drawn from publicly available administrative records and secondary sources, ensuring representation across tenure types and demographic cohorts. The inclusion criteria focused on individuals aged 21 and above, in line with statutory eligibility for land application.

4.0 Data Collection and Analysis

Data were collected through Legal documents and policy texts, including the 2015 and 2019 Land Policy Acts, the Tribal Land Act, and relevant parliamentary debates, as well as academic literature and gender equity reports (e.g., CEDAW, Kampamba & Mosweu, 2020). Due to limited access to primary administrative databases, the study relied on triangulation to validate trends and contextualise gaps. The core analytical method was the chi-square test of independence, used to determine whether there is a statistically significant association between gender and land ownership.

4.1 Validity, Reliability and Trustworthiness

Trustworthiness was enhanced through methodological transparency, triangulation of data sources, and acknowledgement of limitations in data availability and scope.

4.2 Ethical Consideration

Although the study relied on secondary data, ethical considerations were observed by:

- Ensuring the confidentiality and anonymity of individual records
- No personal interviews or identifiable data were used, and all analysis was conducted in accordance with academic integrity standards.

4.3 Limitations of the Methodology

Key limitations include:

- Restricted access to gender-disaggregated application data, which limits the ability to assess demand-side dynamics.
- Potential biases in administrative records, such as underreporting or inconsistent categorisation.
- Legal pluralism complicates interpretation due to overlapping statutory and customary systems.

The Act has been the driver of land equity between the two genders; however, numerous challenges face the overall allocation of land in Botswana. In 2020, it was reported that about 700,000 applicants were awaiting allocation of both tribal and state land in Botswana (Seitshiro, 2020). This same report states that the most extended waiting period for applicants is 27 years. Unfortunately, the statistics on applications by gender are not available, which makes it challenging to assess whether, although the Act raised hopes for married, surviving spouses, and heirs, the reality on the ground may be that women are generally unfavoured and still own less land or property than men.

Contextual demographic data and legal eligibility constraints were also taken into account. For example, the statutory minimum age to apply for land is 21, which influences ownership trends in

younger cohorts. Additionally, marriage statistics were referenced to correlate asset accumulation periods with life-stage variables (Statistics Botswana, 2021).

5 Results

5.1 Land Ownership Patterns and Tenure Security

The analysis of 76,562 land ownership records reveals a nearly balanced gender distribution, with 50.6% of ownership attributed to males and 49.4% to females. However, tenure security varies across age cohorts. Women aged 35–59 show the highest ownership rates, particularly in the 50–54 age group, where they surpass men (4,941 vs. 3,895). This suggests that tenure security has improved for women in economically active life stages, likely influenced by the 2019 policy amendment. In contrast, younger women (20–29 years old) and older women (60 years and older) remain underrepresented, reflecting both recent eligibility constraints and historical exclusion.

5.2 Legal Awareness and Institutional Engagement

The increased representation of women in the 35–59 age bracket may indicate a rise in legal awareness and proactive engagement with institutional reforms. The 2019 amendment, which removed marital status as a barrier to land application, appears to have empowered women to assert their rights more confidently. However, institutional challenges persist, including administrative delays, a lack of gender-disaggregated application data, and limited outreach to younger and rural women.

5.3 Barriers to Land Access

Despite policy reforms, several structural and procedural barriers continue to hinder equitable land access:

- **Application backlog:** Over 700,000 applicants are awaiting allocation of tribal and state land (Seitshiro, 2020).
- **Extended waiting periods:** Some applicants face delays of up to 27 years.
- **Minimum age requirement:** The statutory minimum age of 21 delays access for younger women.
- **Data limitations:** Absence of gender-disaggregated application statistics obscures demand-side dynamics.
- **Customary gatekeeping:** Informal norms and local practices may discourage or delay women's applications.

These barriers disproportionately affect women, particularly those outside the dominant age range of ownership.

5.4 Customary Practices and Gender Norms

Botswana's dual legal system, comprising statutory and customary law, continues to shape land governance outcomes. While statutory reforms promote gender equity, customary tenure systems often reinforce patriarchal norms. Older men dominate ownership in the 60+ age group, reflecting historical patterns of male inheritance and allocation of property. Even with decentralised land boards, informal biases persist, particularly in tribal land contexts where customary law still influences decision-making.

5.5 Women’s Agency and Coping Mechanisms

Women aged 35–59 demonstrate strong agency, leveraging legal reforms to secure land ownership. Their increased representation suggests strategic engagement with institutional processes and growing confidence in asserting land rights. However, younger women and those in rural areas may rely on informal tenure arrangements, family networks, or delayed applications due to systemic constraints. The findings highlight the need for targeted support mechanisms, including legal literacy programs and streamlined administrative procedures.

5.6 Overview of Land Ownership by Gender

Women aged 35–59 consistently owned more land than their male counterparts, with the most notable difference observed in the 50–54 age group (4,941 women vs. 3,895 men). This age bracket represents the highest concentration of female land ownership, suggesting an alignment with both economic maturity and policy impact post-2019. Conversely, younger women (aged 20–29) owned significantly less land than men. In the 20–24 group, only 24.1% of landowners were women, and in the 25–29 group, women comprised just 21.1% of landowners. Among those aged 60 and above, male land ownership surpassed that of women, with men in the 65+ category holding 17,347 plots compared to 15,848 for women. This likely reflects pre-reform gender imbalances.

The observed and expected frequencies are presented in Table 4.1 below.

Table 4.1: Observed and Expected Frequencies of Land Ownership by Age Group and Gender (Author’s Compilation)

<u>Age Group</u>	<u>Men (Observed)</u>	<u>Women (Observed)</u>	<u>Men (Expected)</u>	<u>Women (Expected)</u>
20–24	110	35	73.44	71.56
25–29	687	184	441.12	429.88
30–34	1,277	936	1,120.78	1,092.22
35–39	829	1,501	1,180.03	1,149.97
40–44	1,442	1,871	1,677.88	1,635.12
45–49	2,203	2,736	2,501.37	2,437.63
50–54	3,895	4,941	4,475.01	4,360.99
55–59	5,231	5,530	5,449.93	5,311.07
60–65	5,754	4,205	5,043.76	4,915.24
65+	17,347	15,848	16,811.68	16,383.32

The chi-square statistic was $\chi^2(9) = 1,116.89$, with a p-value < 0.001 , indicating a highly significant association between gender and land ownership across all age groups. The test confirms that land ownership is not evenly distributed by gender and is influenced by both historical and policy-related factors.

6. Discussion

Key Findings

The results of this study illustrate a statistically significant association between age, gender, and land ownership patterns in Botswana, confirming the tangible impact of the 2019 amendment to the Botswana Land Policy. Specifically, the results show a marked increase in land ownership among women aged 35–59. This group is likely to have actively benefited from the removal of gender-based restrictions on land allocation.

This upward trend in female ownership aligns with the hypothesis that the policy reform enabled married women and widows, who were previously excluded from land allocation, to gain legal access to land in their own right. It also coincides with the economically active phase of life, during which women are more likely to have the resources and need for independent property ownership.

However, the analysis also reveals persistent disparities. Women aged 20–29 are significantly underrepresented in land ownership, likely due to both structural barriers, such as land board backlogs and recent eligibility status. As the minimum age to apply for land is 21 and waiting periods can exceed two decades (Seitshiro, 2020), this age group remains marginalised despite being legally eligible.

For older age groups (60+), the results confirm entrenched gender disparities, reflecting a legacy of patriarchal land practices that predate reform. This underscores the importance of historical context when assessing the effectiveness of contemporary legal frameworks.

Policy and Practical Implications

Notably, while legal reform has opened the door for gender equity in principle, administrative and structural inefficiencies, such as long allocation waitlists and limited transparency, continue to impede equitable access in practice. Moreover, the absence of gender-disaggregated application and allocation data from land boards limits a complete understanding of current progress.

These findings underscore the importance of ongoing monitoring of land policy implementation and the development of enhanced data systems that can effectively track gender-specific land rights. A gender-responsive land information management system (LIMS), as recommended in international best practices, could improve transparency, accountability, and equity.

Ultimately, while the 2019 policy amendment represents a significant milestone for women's land rights in Botswana, the path toward full gender equity requires continued policy refinement, targeted implementation strategies, and structural support mechanisms to address both historical disadvantage and current inefficiencies.

Limitations of the Study

Although married women have been empowered through this legislative amendment, the full extent of this empowerment, along with its socio-economic outcomes, remains difficult to quantify due to the unavailability of gender-disaggregated allocation data. For more robust assessments, the Ministry of Lands, Water and Sanitation must improve data accessibility, allowing researchers to analyse and evaluate the impact of legal reforms on land equity in a transparent and informed manner.

Policy Recommendations

To consolidate the gains and address remaining challenges, the following policy recommendations are proposed:

- **Develop a Gender-Responsive Land Information Management System (LIMS)**

A digital system capable of tracking and analysing land ownership and allocation by gender and age should be implemented. This would support data transparency, monitor the impact of legal reforms, and enhance policy responsiveness (Land Links, 2010; FAO, 2023).

- **Prioritise the Reduction of Land Allocation Backlogs**

With over 700,000 applicants still awaiting allocation (Seitshiro, 2020), the government must improve administrative efficiency, streamline processing systems, and reduce barriers that disproportionately affect women and first-time applicants.

- **Enhance Public Education on Land Rights**

Nationwide legal literacy campaigns, particularly in rural areas, should empower women with knowledge about their rights to land ownership, how to navigate application processes, and how to safeguard their property rights. These campaigns must be culturally appropriate and linguistically accessible (Dow & Kidd, 1994).

- **Institutionalise Gender Audits in Land Boards**

Periodic gender audits should be embedded into land board operations to monitor equity outcomes, uncover hidden biases, and ensure accountability in line with national gender equality strategies (SADC Gender and Development Monitor, 2019).

- **Integrate Land Access into Broader Gender Equality Policies**

Land rights should be mainstreamed into Botswana's wider gender equity and economic development frameworks. Collaboration between the ministries of lands, gender affairs, urban planning, and finance is essential to drive systemic transformation (African Development Bank, 2021).

- **Promote Ongoing Dialogue between Government, Private Sector, and Researchers**

Multi-stakeholder forums should be established to regularly review the implementation of the Land Policy amendments. Engaging researchers, legal professionals, and community leaders will ensure the continuous alignment of legal reforms with lived realities and emerging challenges.

Areas for Future Research

By anchoring gender equality in both legal frameworks and institutional practice, Botswana has the potential to position itself as a continental leader in equitable land governance. Future research could investigate the mechanisms by which gender-sensitive reforms in land policy translate into tangible outcomes, such as enhanced access, improved tenure security, and increased economic participation for

women and marginalised groups. This includes longitudinal studies on the impact of statutory changes, the harmonisation of customary law, and institutional capacity-building efforts.

Conclusion

This study set out to critically examine the gendered dimensions of land ownership in Botswana, guided by three research objectives and corresponding questions. The findings offer evidence-based insights into the socio-legal shifts brought about by the 2019 Land Policy amendment and the persistent barriers that continue to shape women's access to land.

The results demonstrate that independent land ownership by women is strongly associated with increased economic autonomy, improved household welfare, and enhanced legal recognition. Women aged 35–59, who represent the highest ownership rates, exemplify how secure tenure enables asset accumulation, access to credit, and decision-making power. These outcomes affirm the critical role of land rights in advancing gender equity and inclusive development.

Prior to the amendment, the 2015 Land Policy maintained structural constraints that limited women's access, particularly through provisions that allowed only one spouse to apply for land, often defaulting to the male spouse. Customary practices further compounded these exclusions, resulting in lower ownership rates among women, especially in older cohorts. The data reflect this legacy, with men dominating ownership in the 60+ age group, underscoring the long-term impact of discriminatory policy and practice.

The 2019 amendment has led to measurable improvements in women's land ownership, particularly among economically active age groups. The removal of marital status as a barrier has facilitated more equitable access, with women now comprising 49.4% of landowners. The chi-square test confirms a statistically significant association between gender and ownership patterns, suggesting that the reform has begun to shift entrenched norms. However, persistent challenges, including long waiting periods, lack of gender-disaggregated application data, and the influence of customary tenure, continue to limit the full realisation of these gains.

In sum, while Botswana's policy reforms have laid a strong foundation for gender-equitable land governance, the findings highlight the need for continued institutional reform, improved data systems, and harmonisation between statutory and customary law. Addressing these gaps is essential to ensure that every woman, regardless of age, marital status, or social position, can access, own, and benefit from land as a secure and empowering resource.

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Diaspora Cooperatives and Sustainable Real Estate Finance: A Discrete Choice Modelling Approach
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Abstract

This study examines the trade-offs Nigerian diaspora investors will consider funding energy-efficient affordable housing in high-sovereign-risk markets and maps the residual viability gap. An integrated theoretical lens informed a Bayesian D-optimal partial-profile discrete-choice experiment. Employing a sample of 350 diaspora investors in the UK, USA, Canada and Germany, 12 investment profiles varying in ticket size, expected IRR, certification and risk shielding were evaluated. Data were analysed using a multinomial logit model implemented in Python's xlogit library to interpret the willingness-to-accept (WTA) estimates. Results show that investors waive up to 1.06% for sustainable real estate investment cost premium, which falls below the standard 2–7% incremental cost. Conversely, escrow, audit and FX-plus-sovereign cover elicit 1.32–2.27% discounts, confirming loss-aversion's (Prospect Theory) dominance over altruistic impact (Risk-Return Impact Frontier). Wealth, experience and risk tolerance significantly moderated preferences (McFadden pseudo- $R^2=0.287$). Practical implications of the study entail that developers should securitise sustainable investment projects with transparent escrow and FX cover. Policymakers could absorb the remaining spread through green guarantees and diaspora-indexed bonds. This study quantifies diaspora investors' willingness-to-accept yield reductions for sustainable housing (up to 1.06% for LEED-Gold certification), and demonstrates that risk mitigation mechanisms command higher premiums than sustainability features, informing blended finance design.

Keywords: Blended finance, Diaspora investment, Impact-adjusted IRR, Sustainable real estate, Willingness to Accept

Introduction

Despite three decades of policy experimentation, sub-Saharan Africa still faces a deficit in housing infrastructure due to under-capitalised formal supply chains, also causing the inadequacy globally, in Africa and Nigeria (UN Habitat, 2024). While global estimates of more than 2.8 billion people occupying inadequate shelter (UN Habitat, 2024) suggest that this is not a solely African problem, a 2023 African Development Bank (AfDB) report narrows it down to the continent (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Housing Deficit by Country

Source: Researchers' Visualisation of AfDB (2023) Housing Deficit Statistics

Nigeria has Africa's largest affordable housing deficit with over 20 million, Kenya/South Africa/Angola (2 million) and Cameroon/Côte d'Ivoire (>700,000) (Figure 1). Nigeria urbanises at a mean annual rate of 3.5% (World Bank, 2023), annual population growth of 2.38 amid an affordable housing deficit stock that rises by an average 3.9% (Figure 2) (Adedeji et al., 2023). Impliedly, despite financial constraints, the residential housing stock may be doubled by mid-century. Yet, traditional financing mechanisms, such as government subsidies, commercial lending, and public-private partnerships, have proven inadequate globally, with fiscal constraints limiting public sector capacity and commercial lending excluding low-income populations due to credit risk in Nigeria (Oluwummi, 2023).

Figure 2: Housing Shortfall in Nigeria

Source: Researchers' Visualisation

The convergence of Africa's housing deficit with energy poverty affecting 600 million people creates a compounding crisis for urban populations and policymakers, where failure to mobilize sustainable financing mechanisms will result in doubled housing shortfalls and perpetuated energy exclusion by 2050 (AfDB, 2023). While existing literature documents remittance flows and housing finance challenges separately, a critical knowledge gap exists in quantifying diaspora investors' willingness to accept below-market returns for impact-verified sustainable housing projects in high-risk climates. The diaspora refers to citizens of a nation who work and live in a foreign country. The Nigerian diaspora is emphasised because of the energy landscape that has >85 million off-grid (Onyekachi, 2024), on-grid aggregates at <8 hours/day (Amadi & Ekeng, 2024) and is the largest energy deficit globally (World Bank, 2024a). Thus, the housing and sustainable energy deficits create a wicked policy knot for the country.

Impact investment theory (Brest & Born, 2013) proposes a risk-return-impact blend that explains the additional environmental and social impacts of an economic venture. We visualise this theoretical import through the lens of the diaspora, as the risk-absorbing entity capable of creating substantial ripple effects in the muddy waters of affordable housing and sustainable energy crisis in Nigeria. Certain remarkable statistics make them a pertinent reflection. First, diaspora remittances represent a critical and growing source of external finance for Africa, consistently surpassing Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in recent years (AfDB, 2025). This is exemplified by the total remittances to Africa in 2023, which were estimated to be over US\$90 billion (World Bank, 2024b; African Diaspora Network, 2025), confirming diaspora remittances as the largest non-debt source of financial inflows to the continent.

Extant research posits that Nigeria accounts for over 36% of these remittances (Welde et al., 2022). Research advocating for channelling these remittances into public or donor agency partnerships (Abigael, 2024; Akanle & Ola-Lawson, 2022) overlook their use in sustainable real estate financing. Its exclusion highlights the research gap on estimating diaspora capital's willingness to trade higher financial return for financing Excellence in Design for Greater Efficiencies (EDGE) or Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design (LEED) compliant affordable units in high-risk sovereign areas like Nigeria. The study bridges this research gap using a synthesis of Prospect Theory (Kahneman & Tversky, 1979), to model diaspora loss-averse return expectations, and Random Utility Theory (McFadden, 1974), to monetise their attribute trade-offs in discrete-choice settings.

This approach contributes to knowledge by employing discrete choice experiment (DCE) to estimate how diaspora investors adjust their required internal rate of return (IRR) once ESG-impact factors are considered (Mannino & Esposito, 2024). The experiment, which mixes preference parameters with project-level cashflow simulations, extends the predominant finance-first behaviour of the diaspora towards a novel sustainability impact-first area, not fully understood in African real estate research. The research speaks directly to the research gap on diaspora contribution to sustainable housing financing. It is one of the first cross-continental behavioural dataset on African diaspora impact finance, with implementable pathways for real estate practitioners and policymakers to effectively manage the housing and energy crisis in the continent towards sustainable outcomes.

Theoretical Framework

A clear understanding of the prospects of diaspora crowdfunding for energy-efficient affordable housing demands a setup that captures both the financial calculus and the behavioural heuristics that shape cross-border investment. The derived framework therefore synthesises the Risk–Return–Impact Frontier, Prospect Theory, and Random Utility Theory. Brest et al.’s (2013) impact-investment thesis reconceptualises capital allocation as an impact-adjusted IRR modelling of trade-offs between sustainability financing and reduced economic returns. Since critics argue that without audited measurement, impact can be rhetorical (Kaufmann, 2022), we enriched the methodology with EDGE/LEED certifications to provide quantifiable metrics of assessing sustainability compliance. From this theory, we propound that diaspora investors will accept a statistically significant IRR discount when EDGE- or LEED-certified impact disclosures accompany affordable housing projects.

Nigeria’s macro volatility, broadened into exchange-rate swings, regulatory inconsistencies, insecurity, infrastructural deficits, construction delays and others make it a high sovereign risk area (Aladejare, 2021). Since diasporans may perceive this as downside risk, we used Prospect Theory (Kahneman et al., 1979) to predict how they compare potential losses relative to equivalent gains in the atypical sustainable property financing. Thus, loss-averse diaspora investors will demand higher nominal yields unless risk-mitigation devices, such as escrow structures, third-party audits, secure outcomes as sure gains (Proposition II).

To monetise attribute trade-offs formally, the study embeds a DCE grounded in RUT (McFadden, 1974). Recent related scholarship on this integration (Bauer et al., 2025) avers that it explains the idea that an investor selects the alternative that maximises latent utility, decomposed into systematic components (attribute weights) and an idiosyncratic error term. We adhere to this process in linking utility theory to the willingness-to-pay experiment, arguing that the DCE can monetise attribute trade-offs, such as certification level, exit horizon, and investment capital. Accordingly, the marginal willingness-to-accept yield reduction for green certification will exceed that for generic social-impact reporting, reflecting higher perceived verifiability (Proposition III).

The integration enabled the generation of an impact-adjusted IRR curve, which was benchmarked against EDGE cost premiums to pinpoint the viability gap that blended finance must close. The theoretical framework is further enriched by Social Capital Theory to explain collective diaspora action (Coleman, 1988), Behavioural Economics principles which complement Prospect Theory by capturing how diaspora investors process incomplete information about emerging market risks and sustainability outcomes (Thaler, 1980), and Sustainable Development Theory as the normative foundation for emphasizing economic viability, environmental responsibility, and social equity outcomes (Brundtland Commission, 1987). This unification evinces empirical behavioural evidence of diaspora impact premiums in sub-Saharan real-estate crowdfunding, and calibrated discount curves that developers and policymakers can embed in sustainable real estate financing. Thus, remittances shift from passive transfers to a precisely modelled lever for Africa’s housing and energy deficits.

Conceptual Perspectives

In conceptualising sustainable real estate, UN Habitat blends the notion of adequate shelter with low-income affordability while minimising life-cycle environmental impacts through resource-efficient design (Hyland, 2023). In parallel, the EU's Affordable Housing Initiative (2023) stresses that true sustainability arises only when deep energy-efficiency retrofits are delivered at price points that curb energy poverty. On the International Financial Cooperation website, citing EDGE, these sustainability principles were fragmented into measurable thresholds, typically a 20% cut in operational energy and water use relative to local baselines, while imposing strict caps on the incremental capital premium to keep units within reach of median-income buyers (IFC-EDGE, n.d.).

Research operationalises this further, arguing that affordability, health and net-zero performance must be co-optimised rather than traded off (Rosenow & Hamels, 2023). Impliedly, achieving truly sustainable housing requires a holistic approach where financial accessibility, occupant well-being, and environmental neutrality are pursued simultaneously as interconnected goals, rather than being seen as competing objectives where one must be sacrificed for another. Accordingly, this study views sustainable housing as dwellings that achieve at least a 20% reduction in operational energy demand, through practical and affordable means of energy and water conservation, ensuring that homes remain within letting and buying budgets for low/middle-income African families.

Literature broadens this view around four mutually reinforcing component bundles that delineate simultaneously affordable and energy-efficient real estate. Resource-efficiency attributes capture the technical upgrades that cut operational energy and potable-water use by at least 20% while advancing low-embodied-carbon, cost-effective materials (Singh, Joshi and Mani, 2021). Such thresholds are embedded in standards like IFC and EDGE and some national councils, like the Green Building Council Indonesia (GBCI) which emphasise keeping incremental capital costs within reach of low- to middle-income buyers or renters (Sia, 2017). Another component is the indoor-air-quality (IAQ) considerations which advance human wellness at the core of sustainability (Niza et al., 2023). Guidelines from the World Green Building Council elucidate this as buildings that have fresh air, limit harmful chemicals, and maintain comfortable indoor temperatures. The argument presented here is that with these in place, efficiency gains do not have to compromise occupant well-being. Accessibility considerations of sustainable real estate encompass the location of the investment within a low-carbon mobility network, with proximity to public transport, walkable streets and cycling infrastructure. Kong & Pojani (2023) confirm these variables' significant reduction of household expenditure, thereby reinforcing affordability.

Narrowing the location to site selection, Kaur & Gupta (2022) suggest that this involves selecting sites with little impact, designing landscapes that handle water naturally, and including plenty of green areas. Such selections do not only save maintenance money over time but also make homes better able to handle climate changes and keep them affordable for life (Satterthwaite et al., 2020). Worthy of note is that as these bundles demonstrate sustainability, they also introduce incremental capital premiums, which are difficult to recoup in immature and volatile markets like Nigeria's (Anago, 2024). More comprehensive analyses quantify this incremental cost premium between 0% to 10%, with many projects achieving certification within a 0-3% premium, particularly if

green strategies are integrated from the design phase (World Green Building Council, 2019). Justifying the need for a diaspora-backed support in this regard, Appolloni et al. (2022) doubles down on the market immaturity challenges with the assertion that the cost premium can be influenced by market maturity and specific certification goals, where the lower the maturity, the higher the cost premium.

To test whether such premiums are absorbable, scholars deploy willingness-to-pay (WTP) elicitation, defined by Horowitz & McConnell (2003) as the maximum sum an economic agent is prepared to exchange for a given good. Early work used open-ended contingent valuation questions (Martinsson & Carlsson, 2006), while contemporary studies employ DCEs grounded in RUT, allowing estimation of marginal WTP (MWTP) for each bundle (Aguome et al., 2024). It must be noted that most of these studies focused on households and investors, not diasporans. Unlike typical investors or households, diasporans often possess a unique blend of financial motivations (usually stronger currencies like US Dollar vs Naira) and lesser economic ties to their home country, which can influence their willingness to pay for impact beyond purely market-driven returns.

Coming from a supposedly more stable socioeconomic climate than their home countries, the affordability reflections of diasporans, especially those in Europe and America may be shaped not only by stated preferences but also by risk aversion (Kader, 2024). Behavioural finance shows that loss-averse investors demand supra-normal returns under volatility (Kahneman et al., 1979). However, the study's hypothesis may also be seen as reverse coding this theory to suggest that non-economic factors explained by social value constructs may eliminate risk-averse behaviour and enhance WTP. Brest et al. (2013) impact-investing and Blended Value Proposition (Emerson, 2003) combine to allude that investments produce a blend of financial return, social value, and environmental value. This implies that risk-averse individuals might be willing to accept lower financial returns if the investment generates significant and measurable social or environmental impact for their nation. Thus, the study integrates this impact into the RUM, reimagining it as a desired form of return.

However, African real estate research sees such investments as risky (Ametefe et al., 2023; Oluwumni, 2023), arguing that investors expect higher returns to make up for that risk (Naidoo et al., 2025). This view assumes that high expectation for financial returns often makes the added cost of energy-saving upgrades appear expensive, despite their sustainability potential. Crucially, the field needs better understanding of the trade-offs between high financial expectations and impact-investing in driving diaspora WTP for energy-efficient affordable homes in volatile markets. Filling that missing piece is the aim of this study.

Materials and Methods

Research design

The study followed a sequential explanatory mixed-methods design, commencing with an online DCE to elicit diaspora investors' preferences. This was followed by a project cash-flow modelling that translated the stated preferences into an impact-adjusted IRR. Integration of the three theories

helped capture financial calculus and behavioural heuristics influencing diaspora-backed sustainable real estate financing.

Sources of Data

The study collected data from primary and secondary sources. Primary data was obtained from the DCEs, while the choice sets were developed using various data from secondary sources, encompassing green building cost premium, home loan sizes, IRR and Nigeria's sovereign risk index. The green building cost premium was obtained from IFC-EDGE, showing that incremental capital costs typically $\leq 2\%$ and rarely above 5% for achieving the standard 20% savings threshold. Another secondary data used in the study was the ticket prices of such investments.

Consistent with related methodological applications (Niendorf et al., 2023), data on common home loan amounts from the Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria was initially considered. On validation by real estate developers who work with Nigerian diaspora, we understood that loan sizes from US\$3,300 to US\$33,300 are typical for their clients. On returns benchmarks, African real estate funds aggregate 18–20% USD IRR targets for Nigerian deals (Boston Consulting Group, 2025). The country-risk premium was obtained from Nigeria's USD sovereign bonds yield $\approx 10\%$, a ~ 600 base points (bp) spread over the US 10-year Treasury (Trading Economics, 2025). These values anchor attribute levels for the experiment.

Population and Sample

The target population comprised Nigerian adults residing for more than 2 years in OECD countries, and earning over US\$50,000 p.a. Because no sampling frame exists, a multi-seed snow-ball strategy was used consisting of four diaspora association leaders in the UK, U.S., Canada and Germany. Leaders of identified diaspora organizations, cooperative federations, and community groups were contacted, through referral, to seek their endorsement and assistance in disseminating the survey. Based on established guidelines for DCEs (de Bekker-Grob et al., 2015), a minimum sample size of between 300-500 completed responses is typically recommended for robust analysis. Accordingly, data collection stopped immediately we reached 350 to account for potential incomplete responses.

The DCE survey was administered online using Ngene, due to its suitability for DCEs. A unique link was provided on the survey forum on Telegram application, which was selected due to its heavier file capacity than WhatsApp. Participants received a clear information sheet detailing the study's purpose, what their participation entails, estimated time commitment, data confidentiality, and their right to withdraw at any time. Gentle reminders were sent to encourage completion of the survey. Inclusion criteria entailed self-confirmation as a Nigerian diaspora member, aged 18 years or older, fluent in English, demonstrates an interest in real estate investment or cooperative savings, and willingness to provide informed consent.

Discrete Choice Experiment

Table 1 highlights attributes, levels and rationales.

Table 1: Attribute set and levels

Attribute	Levels (coded)	Rationale
Investment amount X₁	US\$25k · 50k · 100k · 200k	Property developer perspectives on typical diaspora ticket sizes.
Expected IRR X₂	8 % · 12 % · 16 % · 20 %	Matches bond-equivalent to Africa private equity targets.
Certification X₃	None · EDGE-Basic · EDGE-Adv. · LEED-Gold	Captures the sustainability impact intensity.
Risk-protection package X₄	None · Escrow · Audit · FX + Sovereign cover	Implements Prospect-theory manipulation.

An opt-out option (“invest elsewhere”) helped preserve realism.

The experiment implemented a Bayesian D-optimal partial-profile design, where each respondent completed 12 choice tasks, with four attributes varied per choice (Mao et al., 2024). Prior means were seeded from a 30-respondent pilot survey.

Utility Specification

For diaspora investor n and alternative i , Equation I was employed:

$$U_{ni} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 X_{1ni} + \beta_2 X_{2ni} + \beta_3 X_{3ni} + \beta_4 X_{4ni} + \gamma' Z_n + \varepsilon_{ni} \quad (I)$$

Where, $\beta_1 \dots \beta_4$ represent the coefficients for each attribute, ε_{ni} is the random error term, $X_1 \dots X_4$ represent the attribute levels, and $\gamma' Z_n$ represents characteristics of diaspora member n (such as their age, income, risk tolerance, education level, financial literacy). Under random utility theory, the model aids in quantifying the relative importance of each attribute (Carvajal, (2022).

Impact-Adjusted IRR and Impact Discount Function

IRR_{impact} added verifiable social-environmental value to the yield calculation through an adapted Risk–Return–Impact Frontier to reveal the “impact premium/discount” diaspora investors tolerate when accepting below-market returns for measurable impact. The utility coefficients for sustainability certification (X_3) generate a continuous curve linking higher EDGE/LEED tiers to progressively lower IRR requirements to map the exact trade-off investors make between certification depth and financial yield.

Loss-Aversion Integration

Loss aversion (Prospect Theory) was integrated by including the “risk-protection package” attribute (X_4) in the DCE design. To mitigate perceived risks, the levels (None, Escrow, Audit, FX

+ Sovereign cover) aimed to reframe outcomes as sure gains (Tapas & Pillai, 2022). The coefficient β_4 (Equation I) captures the marginal utility of risk protection, where if positive, it indicates that these mechanisms reduce perceived risk, increase utility, and lower demand for nominal yields. This empirically estimates their influence on investment decisions.

Choice Probability Estimation

The choice probabilities were estimated using a multinomial logit (MNL) model, consistent with Random Utility Theory (McFadden, 1974). For each choice task, the probability of diaspora investor n choosing alternative i over any other alternative j was calculated using Equation II:

$$P_{ni} = \exp(V_{ni}) / \sum_{j \in J} \exp(V_{nj}) \quad (\text{II})$$

Where P_{ni} is the probability of choosing alternative i , V_{ni} is the systematic (observable) component of utility for alternative i for investor n , and J represents the set of all available alternatives in each choice task. The systematic utility V_{ni} was defined by Equation III:

$$V_{ni} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 X_{1ni} + \beta_2 X_{2ni} + \beta_3 X_{3ni} + \beta_4 X_{4ni} + \gamma' Z_n \quad (\text{III})$$

The coefficients ($\beta_1 \dots \beta_4$) represent the marginal utility associated with each attribute level, while α_i is the alternative-specific constant for the opt-out option, capturing the utility of choosing to "invest elsewhere." The socio-demographic characteristics (Z_n) were interacted with relevant attributes to explore heterogeneous preferences. The MNL model assumes independence of irrelevant alternatives (IIA), which was assessed post-estimation.

Willingness to Accept (WTA) Calculation

WTA was calculated to quantify the monetary value (in terms of IRR percentage points) that diaspora investors are willing to forgo for a one-unit change in a non-monetary attribute, such as sustainability certification or risk protection. Getnet & Taw (2021) provided guidelines for calculating the marginal WTA for a specific attribute k as the negative ratio of the coefficient of that attribute (β_k) to the coefficient of the expected IRR attribute (β_2) (Equation IV):

$$WTA_k = -\beta_k / \beta_2 \quad (\text{IV})$$

Since the expected IRR (X_2) is a continuous attribute measured in percentage points, the WTA values are expressed in percentage points of IRR. A slightly similar study in Kenya (Mutai et al., 2025) used this to directly interpret the trade-offs diaspora investors are willing to make between financial returns and other project characteristics. For categorical attributes, WTA was calculated for each level relative to the base level (example, "None" for certification or risk protection), while confidence intervals for WTA estimates were derived using the Delta method to ensure statistical robustness (Getnet et al., 2021).

Analysis

The DCE data were analysed using MNL model on Python xlogit library, with Mixed Logit Model (MLM) as robustness check for preference heterogeneity (Diriye et al., 2022). Model selection was validated through IIA tests (Hausman-McFadden: $\chi^2=12.34$, $p=0.137$). Robustness tests included bootstrap standard errors (1,000 replications), cross-validation (80:20 split), and cross-platform verification using R mlogit.

Validity and Reliability

Construct and content validity were addressed by grounding attributes in established theories and empirical literature, prior to refining with a pilot survey (n=30). Internal validity was supported by a D-optimal partial-profile design and an "opt-out" option (Lizin et al., 2022). Response consistency across the 12 choice tasks and the stable estimated coefficients on Ngene (use minimising bias) confirmed reliability.

Limitations

As the multi-seed snowball sampling may introduce selection bias, the use of trusted diaspora community leaders helped mitigate the bias. As a stated preference method, the DCE relies on hypothetical choices, which may not fully reflect actual investment behaviour given uncaptured real-world factors. This is why an opt-out option was included in the choice sets to enhance realism.

Results

Table 2 lists the demographics of all 350 participants, indicating that most respondents are well-educated, financially secure, and have strong investment potential.

Table 2: Demographic Characteristics

Characteristic	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	198	56.6%
	Female	152	43.4%
Age Group	25-34 years	89	25.4%
	35-44 years	142	40.6%
	45-54 years	87	24.9%
	55+ years	32	9.1%
Country of Residence	United Kingdom	126	36.0%
	United States	98	28.0%
	Canada	78	22.3%
	Germany	48	13.7%

Annual Income (USD)	\$50,000-\$74,999	94	26.9%
	\$75,000-\$99,999	108	30.9%
	\$100,000-\$149,999	89	25.4%
	\$150,000+	59	16.9%
Education Level	Bachelor's or a Lower Degree	147	42.0%
	Master's Degree	158	45.1%
	PhD/Professional Cert.	45	12.9%
Years in Diaspora	2-5 years	78	22.3%
	6-10 years	125	35.7%
	11-15 years	89	25.4%
	16+ years	58	16.6%
Previous Real Estate Investment	Yes	201	57.4%
	No	149	42.6%
Risk Tolerance	Conservative	98	28.0%
	Moderate	189	54.0%
	Aggressive	63	18.0%

Source: Field Survey (2025)

The demographic profile (Table 2) reveals a predominantly middle-aged (65.5% aged 35-54), highly educated (87.1% with bachelor's degree or higher), and financially established diaspora population. Over half (57.4%) have previous real estate investment experience, with moderate risk tolerance being the dominant investment profile (54.0%). The geographic distribution shows concentration in the UK (36.0%) and US (28.0%).

Multinomial Logit Model Results for Diaspora Investment Preferences

Table 3 presents the core model results examining diaspora investment preferences across the four key attributes.

Table 3: Diaspora Investment Preferences

Attribute	Coefficient (β)	Standard Error	t- statistic	p-value	95% Confidence Interval
Investment Amount					
\$25,000 (base)	-	-	-	-	-
\$50,000	0.142	0.089	1.596	0.110	[-0.032, 0.316]
\$100,000	0.218	0.095	2.295	0.022**	[0.032, 0.404]
\$200,000	0.087	0.103	0.845	0.398	[-0.115, 0.289]
Expected IRR	0.186	0.012	15.500	<0.001***	[0.162, 0.210]
Sustainability Certification					
None (base)	-	-	-	-	-
EDGE-Basic	0.089	0.087	1.023	0.306	[-0.081, 0.259]
EDGE-Advanced	0.134	0.092	1.457	0.145	[-0.046, 0.314]
LEED-Gold	0.198	0.098	2.020	0.043**	[0.006, 0.390]
Risk Protection Package					
None (base)	-	-	-	-	-
Escrow	0.245	0.089	2.753	0.006***	[0.071, 0.419]
Third-party Audit	0.287	0.094	3.053	0.002***	[0.103, 0.471]
FX + Sovereign Cover	0.423	0.108	3.917	<0.001***	[0.211, 0.635]
Alternative Specific	-1.892	0.156	-12.128	<0.001***	[-2.198, -1.586]
Constant (Opt-out)					

Model Statistics: N = 4,200 observations (350 respondents \times 12 choice tasks), Log-likelihood=-4,126.8, McFadden's pseudo- $R^2=0.287$, AIC=8,277.6

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.10$

Table 3 reveals that expected IRR is the dominant driver of investment choice ($\beta=0.186$, $p < 0.001$), confirming the dominance of financial returns in diaspora investment decisions. Risk protection mechanisms demonstrate strong positive utility, with comprehensive FX and sovereign coverage showing the highest coefficient ($\beta=0.423$, $p < 0.001$). The effects for sustainability certification are positive but modest, with only LEED-Gold certification achieving statistical significance ($\beta=0.198$, $p=0.043$).

WTA Yield Reductions for Sustainability Certification

Table 4 presents the calculated WTA values for sustainability certification levels.

Table 4: Yield Reductions for Sustainability Certification

Certification Level	WTA (IRR 95% Confidence Interval)	Standard Error	Statistical Significance
EDGE-Basic	0.48 [-0.44, 1.40]	0.47	Not significant
EDGE-Advanced	0.72 [-0.25, 1.69]	0.49	Not significant
LEED-Gold	1.06 [0.03, 2.09]	0.53	Significant**

** $p < 0.05$

Incremental Cost Comparison:

- EDGE certification premium: 2-5% of construction cost
- LEED-Gold certification premium: 3-7% of construction cost
- Maximum diaspora WTA: 1.06 percentage points IRR reduction

The WTA results demonstrate diaspora investors' limited willingness to accept yield reductions for green building features. Even for the highest certification level (LEED-Gold), investors are only willing to accept a 1.06 percentage point reduction in IRR. This modest concession is insufficient to offset the typical 2-7% incremental capital costs associated with green building certification. The implication of this outcome is a substantial viability gap for sustainable property development.

WTA Yield Reductions for Risk Protection Mechanisms

Risk protection mechanisms demonstrate significantly higher utility than sustainability features (Table 5).

Table 5: Yield Reductions for Risk Protection Mechanisms

Risk Protection Level	WTA (IRR 95% Confidence Interval)	Standard Error	Statistical Significance
Escrow Protection	1.32 [0.38, 2.26]	0.48	Significant***
Third-party Audit	1.54 [0.55, 2.53]	0.51	Significant***
FX + Sovereign Cover	2.27 [1.13, 3.41]	0.58	Significant***

** $p < 0.01$

Risk mitigation mechanisms command substantially higher WTA values compared to sustainability certification (Table 5). It further indicates that comprehensive FX and sovereign coverage generates the highest willingness to accept yield reduction (2.27%), more than double the maximum sustainability premium. This pattern aligns with Prospect Theory predictions, where loss-averse investors prioritize downside protection over impact generation.

Heterogeneous WTA

Analysis of preference heterogeneity across demographic segments was detailed in Table 6.

Table 6: Heterogeneous WTA Yield Reductions across Key Demographic Segments

Demographic Segment	LEED-Gold WTA	FX+Sovereign WTA	Sample Size	F-statistic	p-value
Age Groups				3.24	0.022**
25-34 years	0.64	1.89	89		
35-44 years	1.18	2.31	142		
45-54 years	1.23	2.49	87		
55+ years	0.91	2.18	32		
Income Levels				4.17	0.006***
\$50-74k	0.73	1.94	94		
\$75-99k	0.98	2.15	108		
\$100-149k	1.34	2.42	89		
\$150k+	1.67	2.89	59		
Years in Diaspora				2.89	0.035**
2-5 years	0.82	1.98	78		
6-10 years	1.03	2.21	125		
11-15 years	1.19	2.35	89		
16+ years	1.24	2.67	58		
Previous RE Investment				5.23	0.001***
Yes	1.28	2.51	201		
No	0.76	1.89	149		
Risk Tolerance				6.81	<0.001***
Conservative	0.69	1.87	98		
Moderate	1.14	2.32	189		
Aggressive	1.52	2.89	63		

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$

The heterogeneity analysis (Table 6) reveals variations in WTA across demographic segments. For instance, higher-income diaspora members (\$150k+) demonstrate the greatest willingness to accept yield reductions for sustainability (1.67% for LEED-Gold), nearly double that of lower-income segments. Investment experience significantly influences preferences, with experienced investors showing 68% higher WTA for sustainability certification. Risk tolerance exhibits a strong positive relationship with both sustainability and risk protection WTA. The inference of this result is that impact investment in real estate emanates more wealthier and more experienced investors.

Proposition Testing and Theoretical Implications

The proposition that diaspora investors will accept a statistically significant IRR discount when EDGE/LEED-certified impact disclosures accompany affordable housing projects was rejected. Despite LEED-Gold certifications' statistical significance ($p=0.043$), the maximum WTA (1.06% is economically inadequate to offset the 2-7% incremental cost premium for sustainable real estate.

The results support the proposition that loss-averse diaspora investors will demand higher nominal yields unless risk-mitigation devices reframe outcomes as sure gains. Risk protection mechanisms demonstrate WTA values ranging from 1.32-2.27% ($p<0.01$). This result which indicates strong preference for comprehensive risk coverage (FX + Sovereign) aligns with Prospect Theory predictions of loss aversion in high-risk sovereign contexts.

Since the LEED-Gold certification (1.06%) shows higher WTA than basic EDGE certification (0.48%, $p>0.01$), the hypothesis that marginal willingness-to-accept yield reduction for green certification will exceed that for generic social-impact reporting was accepted. It should be noted, though, that the absolute magnitudes remain modest compared to risk protection preferences.

Impact-Adjusted IRR Analysis

The integration of stated preferences with financial modelling reveals critical insights for sustainable real estate viability. Figure 3 illustrates the relationship between certification levels and required IRR adjustments.

Figure 3: Impact-Adjusted IRR

Source: Researchers' Visualisation

The analysis (Figure 3) demonstrates that while diaspora accept lower IRR for impact investments (None=18% to LEED-Gold-16.94), the 1.06% reduction is grossly insufficient to cover the sustainable investing cost premium (escalating from 2.0% to 5.0%). Impliedly, diaspora social impact preferences alone cannot bridge the incremental costs. Successful sustainable real estate financing in emerging markets like Nigeria with high sovereign risk therefore requires blended finance mechanisms, policy interventions, or additional concessional capital.

Model Validation and Robustness

The MNL model is robust, supported by a non-violation of the IIA assumption (Hausman-McFadden chi-square=12.34, $p=0.137$) and stable coefficients across subsets since variations were within 5%. Its strong explanatory power and statistical reliability are further validated by a high McFadden's pseudo- R^2 (0.287) and significant likelihood ratio test ($p<0.001$).

Discussion of Results and Conclusion

The findings reveal that Nigerian diaspora investors are loss-averse and align with Prospect Theory than with philanthropic impact investing (Risk–Return–Impact). While investors positively value sustainability attributes, their WTA peaked at substantially below the 2–7% green premium, supporting the contention that green certification premia are often unrecouped in emerging markets (Appolloni et al., 2022; World Green Building Council, 2019), but contradicts impact-first assumptions in Emerson's (2003) Blended Value Proposition.

Conversely, risk protection mechanisms, especially FX and sovereign cover, produced significantly higher WTA (up to 2.27%), confirming the core tenets of Prospect Theory (Kahneman & Tversky, 1979) that downside risk dominates investment decision-making in emerging economies. This agrees with Ametefe et al. (2023), who emphasized sovereign risk as a major barrier to green real estate in Africa. Thus, it can be concluded that diaspora preferences conform more to the risk-return calculus than to normative impact investment expectations. Accordingly, while sustainable real estate holds appeal, its viability under high sovereign risk depends on blended financing mechanisms and not on diaspora altruism alone.

Implications of the Study

This is denoted in Table 7 and in textual form.

Table 7: Practical Implications for Market Actors

Stakeholder	Actionable recommendation	Pay-off
Developers	Before engaging diaspora cooperatives, embed escrow management provisions and automatic independent-audit triggers within the capital-stack term sheets.	90–140 bp reduction in target yield, narrowing the green-premium gap by up to one-third.
Diaspora cooperatives	Structure the offer as a pooled note that is hedged against FX risk and secured in escrow, with tiered sustainability tranches unlocking at verified EDGE or LEED milestones.	Higher subscription rates from moderate-risk investors.
Impact fund managers	Use the calibrated discount curve to price mezzanine or first-loss layers that crowd-in diaspora equity while preserving project-level hurdle rates.	Bankable pipelines that satisfy both fiduciary and impact mandates.

Policy Implications

The results advance the need for expanding Nigerian mortgage financing towards issuance of sovereign-backed green guarantees that cover the first 3% of IRR shortfall for certified projects. Policymakers could consider offering a 50% rebate on the incremental cost of sustainable real estate investments financed by registered diaspora cooperatives. The non-pecuniary impact could be converted into a tradable financial return if floating hard currency bonds whose coupon is indexed to verified CO₂-e could be considered.

Societal Contributions

Deploying even a fraction of the US\$20 billion annual Nigerian diaspora remittance into the proposed risk-mitigated, green-certified structures could deliver 24,000 EDGE-compliant units p.a., significantly cutting the annual affordable housing deficit. The positive externalities for such intervention could be felt in an estimated 38,000 skilled jobs it could create, including the mainstreaming of net-zero design literacy in the wider building sector.

Research Limitations and Agenda

This study relied on a stated preference design (DCE), which, while theoretically robust, may differ from actual behavioural commitments under real-world constraints. Longitudinal tracking of diaspora cooperative investment performance under varying risk-cover structures is thus recommended. Lastly, future studies could develop predictive behavioural models that integrate non-monetary values (nation-building sentiment) into willingness-to-invest functions for policy simulations.

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Disclosure Statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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A Stakeholder Approach to Designing Real Estate Graduate Employability Checklist: Employer and Alumni Perspectives from Nigeria *Njideka Maryclara Aguome*¹, *Neltah Tshepiso Mokgware-Monos*², *Nkiruka Evangeline Aso*³, *Nonso Izuchukwu Ewurum*⁴, *Partson Paradza*⁵, *Ifeanyi Edwin Ihemeje*⁶, *Stella Onwubuya-Ezeala*⁷

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Abstract

The disconnect between real estate education and labour market requirements in sub-Saharan Africa has raised concerns about graduates' employability and sectoral relevance. The study adopts a stakeholder engagement approach to investigate how employer and alumni insights can inform the development of the context sensitive employability checklist for real estate graduates in Nigeria. A sequential dialogic–Best–Worst Scaling experiment was applied. This involved the use of three focus groups (n=37) with employers and alumni to produce 243 competency statements, subsequently distilled into nine themes. These became the object set in a balanced-incomplete-block BWS experiment completed by 117 respondents (42 employers, 45 employed, 30 unemployed alumni) in Enugu. Multinomial Logit utilities and latent-class segmentation were validated through split-sample checks (pseudo-R² = 0.29). The results indicate that seven attributes, comprising practice-rich site immersion, cross-functional mindset, critical curiosity, digital fluency, hybrid-work competence, entrepreneurial orientation, and trainability were ranked highest as employability priorities. Innovation-seeking firms highly prioritise digital and AI competences (+36%) and entrepreneurial flair (+28%), whereas risk-averse incumbents prefer traditional site practices and practical experience. The checklist operationalises four curriculum pillars from these priorities, including site-immersion modules, digital-fluency, cross-functional rotations, and venture-creation studios, with diverse implications for curriculum redesign and aspiring industry professionals. The study makes a theoretical contribution in extending, refining and synthesising Resource Dependence, Path Dependence and Signalling theories. Methodologically, the dialogic-BWS approach is a novel contribution to related literature and practice, particularly its premise for co-creating and quantifying priority competences that advance real estate education and practice in Nigeria. Practically, the study supplies a scalable template for co-design of curricula, which if adopted, promises shorter onboarding times and lower supervisory costs for industry professionals, as well as accelerated SME formation, which advances SDGs 8 and 11.

Key words: Dialogic co-creation, Graduate employability, Industry professionals, Property Curriculum, Property market evolution

Introduction

One of the cardinal obligations of African real estate programmes is to prepare graduates who can create demonstrable value and adapt to the profession's continually shifting demands. Early studies appraising performance of these programmes concentrated on degree level and employment

outcomes (Cotgrove, 1962); only from the 2000s did researchers turn their attention to empirical diagnosis of graduate competency and employability (Mason, Williams and Cranmer, 2009). More recent studies follow this approach to enumerate deficits in graduate competences without commensurately supplying instruments for closing them. In this paper we define graduate employability as the capability of real estate graduates to obtain, sustain, and progress in meaningful professional roles by mobilising a demonstrable portfolio of domain knowledge, transferable skills, professional dispositions, and social capital that align with evolving market needs. A deficit here speaks to shortfalls in both soft skills like negotiation and critical thinking (Ayodele et al., 2021; Esaku, 2021) and core technical competences such as valuation, marketing and property investment analysis (Ayodele et al., 2020; Bello et al., 2024).

The task of curricular alignment is further complicated by employers' demand of additional proficiencies in data analytics, licensed-driving, digital platform use, and social media marketing as a means of coping with the ever-rising competitive pressures (Civilcharran & Maharaj, 2023). This presents a murky market skill signal with the unusual implication that core real estate competency is no longer adequate for employers. This paradigm transformation also takes unexpected turns towards the valuation of localised property market knowledge over that obtained from foreign universities (Tran, Blackmore and Rahimi, 2021) and preference for entrepreneurial pedigree over first-class degree holders (Boshoff & Serfontein, 2014). This shift purports that the foundational competencies of property professionals are being re-evaluated, reinforcing a change of empirical approach from gap identification to reconciliation framework development.

These pressures are especially acute in many African markets, against a backdrop of deep structural change across the continent, where PropTech start-ups, big-data analytics and unmanned aerial vehicles are redefining professional practice. This diverges employer expectations from real estate graduate capabilities, sometimes predicting a preference for broader built environment graduates who have relatively more hands-on capabilities (Ebekozi et al., 2024). The ripple effects of real estate graduate skill gaps and increasing preference for other built environment candidates pose dire consequences for the industry (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Top-Down Ripple Effects of Current Real Estate Graduate Unemployability

Figure 1 paints a picture of the current situation in real estate graduate employability and its attendant costs for the industry. It illustrates that rejection of real estate graduate skill set leads to the priority of other built environment graduates, which leaves the rejected graduate frustrated. It further illustrates that when this mental state is conveyed, it may generate disillusion for the profession among tertiary education applicants, thereby frustrating efforts of professional bodies' campaign for increased interest for the profession among pre-tertiary level students.

Although recent studies have begun to embed industry feedback into curricular design (Ewurum et al., 2024), their conclusions are fragmented, as some isolate advanced data analytics (Abidoeye, Ahiadu and Adegoke, 2024), others interpersonal agility (Ayodele et al., 2021) or entrepreneurial flair (Kabonga & Zvokuomba, 2021; Nyukorong, 2022). Extant evidence indicates that the disconnect stems from a persistent dependence on diagnostic, rather than dialogic, strategies, an orientation that has entrenched fragmented curriculum updates which routinely lag the ever-evolving demands of professional practice (Revesai & Ruvunga, 2024). Diagnostic approaches adopt isolated expert-led problem framing and solution generation (Cao et al., 2021), whereas dialogic approaches emphasise collective solution-building through interactive dialogue with stakeholders (Peippo, 2023).

The use of dialogic approach in this study necessitates a richer theoretical lens to transcend an explanation of why such misalignments persist, towards the development of a comprehensive framework co-created with employers and alumni. Resource Dependence Theory describes firms' dependence on competences developed by external institutions such as universities (Pfeffer & Salancik, 1978). Path-Dependence Theory goes further to explain how employers' experiences

predict graduate recruitment decisions (David, 1985). Signalling Theory, on the other hand, clarifies how employers decode credentials and extracurricular profiles when inferring graduates' potential (Spence, 1973). The dialogic intervention employed facilitation to guide stakeholder interactions, enabling participants' co-design of a graduate employability framework that emphasizes employer demands and alumni experiences (Parkinson & Davey, 2021).

The investigation employed a Best–Worst Scaling (BWS) experiment that elicited employer and alumni rankings of specific knowledge areas, technical skills and competencies. We use dialogic co-creation to denote a structured, facilitator-led process that convenes employers and alumni to jointly articulate, refine, and prioritise competence statements; and BWS as a discrete-choice method that converts these statements into comparable utilities reflecting stakeholder preferences. This approach transcends prior studies that rely solely on isolated attributes, qualitative judgements or single-stakeholder viewpoints (Kitulazzi et al., 2024).

Focusing on the Nigerian context, the resulting employability checklist serves two purposes: (1) it offers a systematic lens for comparing industry demands from employers, employment success strategies from recently employed alumni, and reasons for remaining unemployed from yet unemployed alumni; and (2) it provides real estate programmes with a comprehensive evidence-based tool for curriculum realignment. Consistent with contemporary employability scholarship (Mason et al., 2009), we operationalise the Graduate Employability Checklist as the empirically ranked set of attributes generated by this study to guide both curriculum redesign and employer screening. Unlike developed markets where real estate firms defer graduate employment to recruitment agencies who deploy digital analytics, like social media mining and online assessments to generate interview invitations, the Sub-Saharan African space possesses some sort of market immaturity that justifies the theoretical approach employed by this study.

Research Questions

- i) Which graduate attributes do employers and alumni prioritise for real-estate employability in Sub-Saharan African markets?
- ii) How convergent or divergent are these priorities across stakeholder segments?
- iii) How can a stakeholder-endorsed Graduate Employability Checklist be constructed and validated to realign curricula?
- iv) In what ways do the findings refine and integrate Stakeholder, Resource Dependence, Path-Dependence and Signalling theories in this context?

Literature Review

Introduction

Current debates on graduate employability prevalently address co-produced competence frameworks in which universities, alumni, and employers jointly define market-relevant outcomes. In higher education, policy reforms have moved toward competence-based standards and qualification frameworks, but the extent and quality of stakeholder engagement, and its demonstrable impact on curriculum and hiring, remain uneven and under-evidenced. This review synthesizes what is known, examines Nigeria’s tertiary education reforms, and identifies gaps that the present study addresses.

Theoretical Framework

Table 1 illustrates a review of the theoretical synthesis.

Table 1: Theoretical Synthesis

Theory	Core proposition	Empirical traction in real estate or cognate fields	Integrative role in the study
RDT (Pfeffer et al., 1978)	Organisations must secure critical resources from an uncertain environment; collaboration reduces dependency risk.	Mbithi et al. (2021) show African property firms forming curriculum partnerships to mitigate skill shortages.	Positions universities as strategic resource suppliers and employers as resource demanders who can legitimately intervene in curriculum design.
PDT (David, 1985; Arthur, 1989)	Past choices condition actor decision-making even when the external environment changes.	Rocha & Pozzoli (2024) document employee experience predicting hiring patterns.	Explains why employers cling to familiar competence heuristics.
ST (Spence, 1973)	Conceptual understanding of how information is conveyed under asymmetry.	Bassi & Nansamba (2022) find that in times of information asymmetry, employers rely on their interpretation of applicant’s private information to make decisions.	Clarifies how curriculum artifacts and experiential badges communicate graduate potential.

*RDT=Resource Dependence Theory, PDT=Path Dependence Theory, ST=Signalling Theory

We extend the synthesis by emphasizing Stakeholder Theory (Freeman, 1984) within a theory-method-evidence chain that anchors the study’s design. First, employers and alumni are viewed as attribute co-creators (Peippo, 2023), thereafter, their contributions are quantified through BWS, producing priorities that balance stakeholder interests in curriculum reform. RDT enables the

identification of critical resources (skills/capabilities) firms expect from universities (Pfeffer & Salancik, 1978); while PDT reveals the lock-ins between risk-averse and innovation-seeking stakeholders (David, 1985) in managing curricula transitions. With ST, the greater consideration given to practice-rich experience and digital/entrepreneurial skills over legacy GPA signals (Parkinson et al., 2021; Spence, 1973) clarify how curricula should produce verifiable market signals. This integration justifies the dialogic-BWS approach as a theoretically validated method of converting fragmented critiques into ranked, unified competencies.

Conceptualizing Graduate Employability

From this, the conceptual framework is generated (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Conceptual Framework

Source: Researchers

Figure 2 illustrates that graduates' observable signals are filtered through employers' path-dependent heuristics; if those heuristics no longer secure the resources firms need, the dependence gap widens, triggering calls for curricular reform. A dialogic curriculum co-design loop, in which employers and alumni periodically renegotiate attribute priorities, acts simultaneously on all three theories by (i) narrowing RDT's resource gap, (ii) disrupting PDT's lock-in, and (iii) clarifying ST's signalling environment.

Methodological Framework

Areal and Pérez (2025) together with Zander et al. (2024) confirm BWS robustness in respondents' evaluation of cognitive trade-offs. Yiu (2022) extended it to the development of a mental wellbeing diagnostic framework. Zhang et al. (2023) confined the method to employment-related preferences, yet did not translate those findings into a comprehensive employability model, and, to date, comparable work is virtually absent in African real-estate scholarship. Even so, research

is beginning to fuse dialogic techniques with BWS as evinced by Marshall et al.'s (2025) integration of BWS items within focus-group conversations to co-create a framework for understanding patient priorities. Additionally, Rafique et al. (2023) used a similar integration to rank university performance improvement targets. Despite this, empirical studies that deploy this hybrid approach to prioritise graduate attributes specifically for the real-estate industry, however, remain notably limited.

With this justification of the study's novelty, the study operationalises the theories as follows:

- i) RDT: Dialogue converts passive resource acquisition into active resource co-creation.
- ii) PDT: Iterative experiments expose and contest locked-in competence myths before BWS codifies updated priorities. Locked-in explains how employers lock into what they know in assessing what they do not know.
- iii) ST-BWS utilities empirically rank which signals employers and alumni trust most in an opaque market, shrinking information asymmetry.

This Dialogic-BWS approach therefore transcends diagnostic "gap identification" and delivers a scalable, stakeholder-endorsed graduate employability checklist.

Alumni and Employer Engagement in Curriculum Design

Substantial research demonstrates that organized involvement from employers enhances graduate success, particularly when they collaborate on developing curricula, assessments, and real-world work-integrated learning (WIL) experiences (Mason et al., 2009; Rowe & Zegwaard, 2017). However, the level of engagement differs widely; analyses reveal that co-creation can be superficially advisory or truly cooperative, with more intensive partnerships leading to better synchronisation but requiring strong management, funding, and assessment capabilities (Zarandi et al., 2024). Employers often highlight ongoing challenges like high operational expenses, mismatched schedules, and vague benefits, indicating that universities need to formalize roles that bridge gaps and implement frameworks for engagement that set clear goals and prove effectiveness (Mann, 2018; Suleman et al., 2021). Alumni represent a valuable yet underutilized resource: in addition to supporting donations, their networks can boost curriculum applicability, offer guidance, and enhance innovation hubs, though their involvement is inconsistent and poorly assessed (Baroncelli et al., 2022).

Higher Education Reform: Nigeria

Reforms in Nigeria have primarily targeted financing and quality benchmarks. The Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) Act of 2011 established a specific tax to support facilities, employee training, and research in public higher education institutions; studies show notable advancements in resources, but the shift toward updated curricula and job-market results remains inconsistent (Ananyi & Onyekwere, 2024; TETFund Act, 2011). Lately, the Core Curriculum and Minimum Academic Standards (CCMAS) require results-oriented programs that prioritise cross-disciplinary approaches, business skills, and interpersonal abilities to strengthen ties between higher education and industry (Nigeria Universities Commission, 2023). Supporting measures,

such as the 2023 Access to Higher Education/Student Loan Act, focus on making education more affordable, broadening participation while pushing institutions to prove value in employability (Ewurum et al., 2024). Together, these initiatives form a supportive structure, but lasting progress depends on actively involving stakeholders in joint creation, and using reliable metrics from employers and alumni.

Gaps in Literature

First, compared to developed countries, there is minimal definitive evidence from Sub-Saharan Africa regarding a dialogic approach involving employers, academics and alumni in designing a graduate employability checklist for the real estate industry (Zarandi et al., 2024). Second, while ideas about alumni involvement are abundant, data on how their input leads to tangible improvements in curricula and employment results is sparse, as alumni insights are rarely combined with assessments of employer benefits (Baroncelli et al., 2022). Third, although Nigerian initiatives like CCMAS and TETFund tackle resources and benchmarks, there are few thorough, theoretically grounded evaluations that map the progression from policy to curriculum development, learning proof, graduate skills, and work outcomes. Lastly, ongoing obstacles to employer participation, such as costs, organization, and motivations, are not well-analyzed in developing settings (Suleman et al., 2021).

Conclusion

Global research supports intensive, collaborative curriculum development driven by stakeholders. Nigeria's existing policy framework is promising but needs detailed, locally adapted studies that position employers and alumni as key collaborators in generating data and connect educational choices to clear enhancements in graduate abilities and achievements.

Methods

Research Design

The inquiry followed an exploratory design that coupled dialogic focus-group work with a best-worst scaling (BWS) experiment. Dialogic sessions first produced an attribute inventory through structured, multi-stakeholder exchange (Michaelides & Laouris, 2024); the subsequent BWS phase then quantified the relative salience of those attributes (Marshall et al., 2025). This architecture simultaneously operationalises the co-creation imperative central to Resource Dependence Theory and the systematic evaluation of labour-market signals posited by Signalling Theory.

Sampling and Participants

Purposive sampling drew three constituencies into the study: employer representatives (senior managers or HR officers; $n = 42$), alumni employed within 12 months of graduation ($n = 45$), and unemployed alumni ($n = 38$). BWS power-analysis was used to figure out the sample size, which was based on the suggestion that there should be 30–50 respondents in each stakeholder group (Louviere et al., 2000). The study total participants were drawn from Enugu, Nigeria ($n=118$),

while the remaining 7 participants from Gaborone, Botswana enriched the data by giving their peculiar perspectives.

Data Collection

In Phase 1, three online dialogic focus group discussions, comprising 8 employers, 12 employed alumni, and 17 unemployed graduates, were conducted using Microsoft Teams, under a facilitation protocol adapted from Parkinson et al. (2021). Current competency requirements, emergent skill demands, employment barriers, and success strategies informed the discussion scope. Analysis of the transcripts yielded 16 graduate attributes grouped into four domains including technical knowledge (practice and digital competencies) – 4 items, professional skills – 4 items, personal attributes – 4 items, market-readiness indicators – 4 items.

BWS Experimental Design

A balanced incomplete block design (BIBD) was used for Case 1 (object-case) BWS (White II, 2021) in Phase 2. Accordingly, using a Google Form instrument, each choice set was designed to display four attributes for respondents to identify the most and least important items (Equation I).

$$\lambda(r-1) = k(k-1) \quad (I)$$

Where: λ =number of times each pair appears, r =number of replications of each item, k =items per choice set. With 16 attributes and 4 items per set, this yielded 20 choice sets with each attribute appearing 5 times and each pair appearing once.

BWS Model Specification

The analytical framework employed a Random Utility Theory model (Equation II):

$$U_{ij} = V_{ij} + \epsilon_{ij} \quad (II)$$

Where: U_{ij} =Utility of item i for individual j , V_{ij} =Observable component, ϵ_{ij} =Random component (McFowland III, Gangarapu and Bapna, 2021). The probability of selecting item i as best and item m as worst in choice set t is (Equation III):

$$P(i \text{ best, } m \text{ worst}|t) = \exp(\beta_i - \beta_m) / \sum_r \sum_s \exp(\beta_r - \beta_s) \quad (III)$$

Where: β_i , β_m =Scale values for items i and m , r,s =All possible best-worst combinations in set t (Heo et al., 2022).

Analysis

BWS scores were calculated using Multinomial Logit (MNL) to model the probability of an item being chosen as "best" relative to "worst" (or best relative to not-best, and worst relative to not-

worst, depending on the specific model setup) (Grant & Leslie, 2023). The coefficients from the MNL model represent the utility or importance of each attribute.

Validation

The resulting checklist underwent content validity which integrated feedback from 3 industry practitioners, 3 property market researchers and 1 professor of estate management.

Results

Dialogic Results

Three facilitated dialogic sessions encompassing employers=8, employed alumni=12, and unemployed alumni=17 were conducted. The total talk-time for all the sessions was seven hours thirty-six minutes, with an average of two hours per session. The session generated 243 raw competency statements which were condensed with axial coding on NVivo, resulting in 9 mutually exclusive themes ($\kappa = 0.82$ intercoder agreement). Table 2 summarises the saturation metrics and quotes that supplied rhetorical authority to each theme, while Figure 3 (heat-map above) visualises the intensity with which each stakeholder group emphasised the themes.

Table 2: Saturation Metrics

Theme	Illustrative remark (speaker)	First-mention frequency	Cumulative saturation reached at focus-group
Curriculum practicality	“The real education should be out here, not classroom.” (Employer E3)	38	1
Digital & AI	“If you don’t understand that AI is your biggest competitor and you may have no future because of ChatGPT, you’re behind.” (Alumnus A7)	31	2
Critical curiosity	“Come in and question why we still file deeds this way.” (Employer E1)	29	2
Trainability	“There should be greater focus, humility and patience, and not I’d rather be self-employed than break bad habits.” (Employer E5)	26	2
Entrepreneurship	“Commission work taught me client empathy overnight.” (Alumnus A9)	24	3

Hybrid work	“Your laptop is your first site visit.” (Employer E4)	22	3
Networking	“Start shaking hands with the industry before shaking hands with the registrar at convocation.” (Employed alumnus EAL5)	15	3
City familiarity	“Know the backroads before we hand you the keys.” (Employer E7)	12	3
Professional conduct	“Code of ethics is your passport.” (Alumnus A11)	20	3

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Figure 3: Dialogic Phase showing Stakeholder Emphasis on Emergent Attribute Themes

Source: Field Survey, 2025

From Table 2 and Figure 3, the following dominant themes (dialogic insights – DI) emerged.

DI 1: There was convergent urgency for practice-rich learning. Employers and alumni independently emphasized the need for more site immersion long before the facilitator prompted pedagogic topics.

DI 2: AI and cloud-tool fluency were framed not as ‘advanced electives’ but as baseline competences (“computer literacy is the first step, not the finish line”). This emphasized that

employers need graduates who can leverage AI for their future, and not those whose future are threatened by AI.

DI 3: Entrepreneurship was deemed a significant labour-market signalling shortcut. Stakeholders viewed commission-based agency start-ups as proof of resilience, thereby relaxing the need for extensive supervision and salary dependence.

DI 4: Employers welcomed constructive critique from graduates yet cautioned that it must be “evidence-driven, not rebellious for its own sake.”

BWS Experimentation

These co-created themes became the attribute labels embedded in the BWS experiment, thereby operationalising the theoretical mandate for stakeholder-driven curriculum design. The subsequent sections translated this qualitative consensus into a ranked, policy-actionable hierarchy. It utilised 117 completed, returned and internally consistent copies of the questionnaire, totalling 4,680 best-worst choices (20 choice sets × 2 picks × 117 respondents). Upon analysis with Multinomial Logit (MNL) estimation, the results converged after five iterations (McFadden pseudo- $R^2=0.29$; log-likelihood= $-5\ 424.3$; $\chi^2=1\ 958.7$, $p<0.001$), comfortably exceeding the 0.20 benchmark for attribute-ranking studies. Hausman–McFadden diagnostics confirmed no violation of the independence-of-irrelevant-alternatives assumption.

Figure 4 report the top 10 graduate attributes arising from the MNL ranking, from which seven signals dominate the joint employer–alumni preference space based on the normalised utilities (0 = least preferred, 100 = most preferred) (Table 3).

Figure 4: Top 10 Graduate Attributes Ranked by MNL Utilities

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 3: Ranking by Normalised Utilities

Rank	Attribute (condensed label)	Normalised utility
1	Practice-rich curriculum (less theory, more studio/site immersion)	100
2	Cross-functional learning mindset (willingness to rotate through valuation, agency, FM)	88
3	Self-starting and critical curiosity (challenge legacy policies; propose digital upgrades)	85
4	Digital fluency and AI applications (prop-tech analytics, prompt engineering)	81
5	Hybrid-work competence (cloud collaboration; asynchronous teamwork)	77
6	Entrepreneurial orientation (commission-based agency start-ups)	75
7	Trainability/humility (“ready to be trained”)	70

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Figure 4 and Table 3 delineate the most prioritised attributes by employer and alumni selection. Those that did not make the table include traditional academic badges like “high GPA”, which got 24, and “elite foreign degree” (21). Surprisingly being at the extreme lower tail signals a decisive employer swivel towards applied, market-knowledge, practice-verifiable indicators.

Wald test results from examining stakeholder convergence and divergence in the data indicate broad consensus on the first five attributes ($\chi^2=10.9$, $p=0.17$). Yet, latent-class modelling uncovers two employer segments entailing innovation-seeking firms (46% of employers), who emphasize AI competency (+36%) and entrepreneurial flair (+28%) relative to the grand mean. The other segment of employers was risk-averse incumbents (54%), who emphasize practice-rich curricula and hybrid-work modes, but low-rank entrepreneurship and policy-challenging behaviour.

Employed alumni echo employer priorities but diverge in terms of the additional weights assigned to city/market familiarity (62), professional code literacy (60) and pre-graduation network cultivation (65). By contrast, unemployed alumni place significantly higher importance on baseline computer literacy ($t=3.21$, $p<0.01$) and salary flexibility at entry ($t=2.88$, $p<0.01$), signalling perceived screening hurdles. “Willingness to fund a commission-based estate agency” attains a utility of 75 overall, rising to 86 among owners of firms with <10 staff. Qualitative follow-ups confirm that principals view entrepreneurial drive as “evidence of lower supervision burden and faster revenue ramp-up.”

Pearson correlations between MNL utilities and (i) best-minus-worst raw counts ($r=0.93$) and (ii) a five-point direct-importance scale ($r=0.79$) demonstrate convergent validity. Split-sample cross-validation (70/30) produced $\leq 4\%$ coefficient drift, while no single attribute exhibited dominance ($>30\%$ within-task attendance).

Thematic Findings

The qualitative analysis of Phase 1 transcripts identified four interconnected thematic domains that support graduate employability in the real estate sector. Employers and alumni consistently emphasised practical competencies specifically related to valuation, property management, urban analysis, and digital fluency in property technology. Although these were deemed fundamental prerequisites for entry-level positions, both groups noted disparities in competencies and inadequate familiarity with contemporary industry tools. Stakeholders identified problem-solving, critical and analytical reasoning, and adaptability as fundamental cognitive skills essential for career advancement. Nevertheless, numerous graduates were deprived of opportunities to implement these competencies in practical projects.

Employers indicated that they valued graduates who demonstrated initiative and effective communication with diverse stakeholders; however, they noted that these behavioural competencies were seldom developed through structured pedagogical interventions. Indicators of market readiness, including work experience, professional networking, entrepreneurial skills, and industry certification, were considered critical. Graduates lacking relevant internships or portfolio evidence experienced extended job searches, indicating a lack of systematic industry placement mechanisms.

Stakeholders identified persistent gaps between higher education provision and labour market requirements. They opined that course syllabi were insufficient to provide new insights for employer's development and often lagged industry practice in some instances like the adoption of emerging proptech, sustainability frameworks, and automated valuation approaches. In addition, they further decried the limited fieldwork and laboratory simulations that constrain graduates' ability to operationalise their skills. Also, students do not visit firms or engage seasoned practitioners to build a mentorship network. These constraints were particularly acute for unemployed graduates, who reported that employability deficits were magnified by a lack of targeted reskilling initiatives and limited access to professional licensure pathways.

Conclusion

This study offers a synthesized account of graduate employability attributes in Nigeria's real estate markets. Employers and alumni strongly emphasised practice-rich curricula, entrepreneurial adaptability, and digital skills, agreeing with RDT by valuing new critical resources amidst proptech disruption. Differences also emerged, where employers tended to rely on risk-averse hiring practices, while alumni promoted more innovative competences, aligning with Path-Dependence

implications for deliberate curricular disruption. The low emphasis on grades and the growing premium on demonstrable skills support Signalling Theory's emphasis on what is seen over imagined. Moreover, Stakeholder Theory is extended by showing how cross-group negotiations can yield a balanced Graduate Employability Checklist.

Discussion and Contribution

The discrete-choice estimates and the thematic analysis produce a stakeholder-endorsed employability framework. Stakeholders prioritized practical knowledge and verifiable signals over grades, consistent with graduate and signalling studies (Tomlinson, 2017; Yorke, 2006). Yet the translation of these preferences into capability was dampened by programme-level gaps, such as outdated syllabi, limited practical exposure, and weak mentoring/career guidance, a pattern mirrored in engagement syntheses and barrier studies (Suleman et al., 2021; Zarandi et al., 2024). In Nigeria, the existence of enabling policy levers (CCMAS; TETFund) yet does not address implementation frictions and resource-dependence constraints, a contradiction of RDT. Thus, this dialogic-BWS-MNL approach contributes to extant research by converting fragmented skill critiques into a rigorously ranked, stakeholder-endorsed Graduate Employability Checklist. The checklist has the potential to prompt a curriculum-redesign tasked with embedding (i) site-immersion modules, (ii) AI-fluency, (iii) cross-functional rotations, and (iv) venture creation ability (Table 4).

Table 4: Stakeholder-Endorsed Graduate Employability Checklist

Rank	Attribute Signal	*Implicated Curriculum Element	Implications for Aspiring Industry Professionals
1	Practice-Based, Site-Immersion Learning	Site-immersion modules: studio charrettes, live valuation briefs and practical, field audits	Enter the labour market with verifiable, field-tested competencies that shorten the “time-to-billable-productivity” curve.
2	Cross-Functional Learning Mindset	Structured rotations: across valuation, brokerage, facilities & prop-tech labs	Demonstrate versatility across valuation, agency, FM and prop-tech. Show resiliency to market cycles and attractiveness to multidisciplinary teams.
3	Self-Starting and Critical Curiosity	Problem-based “policy-challenge” modules: engage students in peer-reviewed improvement proposals of policies and practice	Fresh from the production line, bring something new to the industry. Challenge employers with logical questions.

			Signal capacity to identify inefficiencies, propose data-driven solutions and thrive under minimal supervision.
4	Digital Fluency and AI Leverage	AI-fluency track: include more PropTech modules, drone-use practical, digital platforms for various aspects of practice, data analytics, and social media maturity	Secure a competitive edge by automating routine analytics, generating faster client insights and integrating with PropTech ecosystems.
5	Hybrid-Work Competence	Cloud-collaboration studios: studio-style course in which student teams deliver real-estate projects entirely through cloud platforms, like Microsoft 365, rather than on-campus lab PCs.	Collaborate seamlessly in cloud environments, because these capabilities are now embedded in employer workflows.
6	Entrepreneurial Orientation	Venture-creation sequence: ideation → minimum viable product (MVP) → client pitch, embedded in later or final years	Live your profession. Build personal revenue streams, showcase client-acquisition skills and signal low supervisory burden.
7	Trainability and Humility	Transformation for passive instruction-takers to self-regulated learners: create a learning environment that mirrors workplace scenarios	Appeal to employers seeking adaptable staff by evidencing teachability and openness to continuous professional development.
8	Networking Cultivation	Encourage students to get an industry mentor in their first year: the mentor supervises the student's progress, hands them non-confidential industry briefs to tackle (like produce a rent-optimisation strategy for our CBD portfolio). Conduct structured academia meets industry workshops at least once in an academic session.	Expand industry experience, access to hidden job markets, mentorship and partnership opportunities well before graduation.
9	City-Specific Market Familiarity	Engage students in fieldwork around the city for them to understand the layouts and local	Offer immediate local insight, including zoning,

		market: Grouped practical and field assignments, Use of digital maps and GIS-based city briefs	property rents and house prices. Understand stakeholder maps (knowing who-is-who and where to find them) These reduce onboarding time for region-focused firms.
10	Professional Code Literacy	Inculcate professional body ethical requirements in all modules: conduct applied ethics simulations	Reduce compliance risk for employers and enhance client trust This will accelerate pathway to professional licensure.

*Each curriculum element feeds one or more of the four flagship redesign pillars: (i) site-immersion, (ii) AI-fluency, (iii) cross-functional rotations, (iv) venture-creation ability.

Theoretical Implications

The challenges Resource Dependence Theory by demonstrating that employer resource gaps can be closed through co-created competencies, not unilateral university supply. It furthers Path-Dependence Theory by showing how dialogic laboratories disrupt locked-in hiring heuristics. The findings enrich Signalling Theory’s empirical granularity with the results that employers discount legacy GPA signals in favour of action-oriented credentials (practical experience, entrepreneurship, digital fluency). Collectively, the study offers an integrative model that links resource gaps, heuristic lock-in and signalling noise in producing a framework that challenges the propositions of extant theoretical arguments.

Methodological Implications

The study introduces a sequentially designed dialogic-BWS pipeline that co-generates attribute universes with stakeholders, quantifies their salience through MNL utilities, and validates the result using split-sample and cross-method triangulation. This hybrid corrects the diagnostic bias of prior gap-cataloguing studies and is transferable to allied disciplines facing volatile skill demands.

Practice Implications

The study presents an evidence-ranked checklist for curriculum committees, accreditation panels, and HR recruiters. It is argued that deploying this stakeholder-endorsed checklist as a live accreditation instrument can transform real estate education from piece-meal curriculum reform to a comprehensive, continuous, data-driven co-design process. Particularly, embedding the four

flagship pillars could compress onboarding time, improve graduate billable productivity, and reduce supervisory overhead. This ensures that African graduates and budding industry professionals remain adaptive value creators in an increasingly digital and entrepreneurial property marketplace.

Policy Implications

The study provides a framework for national higher education regulators and professional councils to institutionalise a practical-dominated curriculum for real estate programmes. Instead of teaching the student to define valuation, the student should be taught to visualise valuation and describe it to a client in a manner that accords them the brief. It further highlights the urgency of ensuring that curricula remain dynamically aligned with industry 4.0 realities, especially the digital revolution. Educators should not worry about students' use of AI because it is like preventing one from using a calculator in favour of manual calculations. Rather, they should design assessments that AI cannot assist the students in. The study advocates for the use of incentive schemes like tax credits for firms, and seed funding and grants for universities to stimulate partnership and co-ventures that operationalise venture-creation modules between the industry and ivory tower.

Societal Implications

The checklist reduces real estate graduate under-employment and advances inclusive economic growth in African real-estate markets. The entrepreneurial pillar advances SME formation, in compliance with SDG 8 (decent work & economic growth), while digital-fluency and hybrid-work competence widen opportunities for gender-balanced, location-flexible careers. Likewise, the study's conclusion is an advocacy for improved professional conduct and city-specific insight that will accentuate and sustain consumer protection and urban governance quality among industry professionals. This aligns with SDG 11 on sustainable cities.

Limitations and Research Agenda

Self-reported data from employers and alumni may reflect perception biases rather than observed hiring practices. Thus, future research should employ longitudinal and experimental designs to track how graduate attributes evolve with technological and labour market dynamics. Further, testing the Graduate Employability Checklist through pilot curricular interventions could validate its practical utility.

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Public Real Estate Asset Management: Current Challenges in South Africa *Lerato Mompoti¹ and Thabelo Ramantswana²*

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Abstract

Governments globally own extensive public real estate portfolios, yet managing these assets effectively remains a persistent challenge, particularly in developing countries like South Africa. This study explores how the South African central government manages its public real estate and identifies the key challenges hindering optimal asset performance. Using a qualitative research approach grounded in interpretivism, the study combines a literature review with semi-structured interviews conducted with ten professionals from the Department of Public Works and Infrastructure (DPWI). Thematic analysis was guided by Abdullah et al.'s (2012) property management framework, focusing on five dimensions: process, performance, organization, technology, and knowledge. Findings reveal critical issues, including insufficient funding, poor lease and maintenance practices, fragmented roles, inadequate digital systems, and limited human resource capacity. These insights offer practical implications for policymakers and asset managers seeking to improve public real estate governance and strategic asset management in South Africa.

Key words: public real estate; asset management; challenges; central government; South Africa

Introduction

Public real estate asset management (PREAM) plays a critical role in enabling governments to deliver essential services such as healthcare, education, and housing. In South Africa, the mismanagement of public real estate has led to deteriorating infrastructure, illegal occupations, and compromised public safety (Auditor General of South Africa, 2023). Buildings that are not properly maintained pose risks of collapse, fire, and health hazards, underscoring the urgency of effective asset management.

Globally, governments own vast real estate portfolios, yet managing these assets efficiently remains a challenge, particularly in developing countries where institutional capacity and strategic frameworks are often lacking (Kaganova & Nayyar-Stone, 2000; Bikam & Chakwizira, 2021). South Africa is no exception. Despite the scale of its public real estate holdings, the central government faces persistent challenges in managing these assets due to fragmented responsibilities, outdated systems, and limited financial and human resources (Phathela & Cloete, 2018; Sekalo et al., 2022).

Existing literature has largely focused on local government asset management, leaving a gap in understanding the specific challenges faced by central government departments (Kaganova & Amoils, 2020). This study addresses that gap by examining how the South African central government manages its public real estate and identifying the key challenges that hinder effective asset performance.

Key concepts such as “asset management,” “fragmentation,” and “public real estate” are often used interchangeably in policy and academic discourse, yet they require clear definition and contextualization. Asset management refers to the systematic process of maintaining, upgrading, and operating assets cost-effectively (Davis, 2012). Fragmentation in this context refers to the disjointed allocation of roles and responsibilities across departments, which impedes coordinated decision-making and strategic planning (Dobrucká et al., 2024).

To guide this investigation, the study draws on three theoretical frameworks: New Public Management (NPM), which emphasizes efficiency, accountability, and performance in public sector operations (Shava & Mazenda, 2021); the Dynamic Capabilities View (DCV), which explores how organizations adapt to changing environments (Teece et al., 1997); and Modern Portfolio Theory (MPT), which, although traditionally applied to investment, offers insights into optimizing asset performance and minimizing risk (Zhang, 2024).

The main objective of this study is to explore the methods used by the South African central government in managing its public real estate and to analyse the challenges associated with these methods. By doing so, the study aims to contribute to the development of more effective asset management strategies and inform future policy interventions.

Theoretical Framework

Understanding the challenges of public real estate asset management (PREAM) in South Africa requires a multi-theoretical lens due to the complexity of governance structures, institutional dynamics, and strategic decision-making processes. This study is guided by three interrelated theoretical frameworks: New Public Management (NPM), the Dynamic Capabilities View (DCV), and Modern Portfolio Theory (MPT). Together, these frameworks provide a robust foundation for analysing the operational, strategic, and policy-level challenges in managing public real estate assets.

New Public Management (NPM)

NPM emerged in the late 20th century as a response to inefficiencies in public sector governance. It advocates for the adoption of private sector principles, such as performance measurement, accountability, and customer orientation, within public institutions (Shava & Mazenda, 2021). In the South African context, NPM is particularly relevant given the findings of commissions such as Zondo and Mkhwanazi, which have exposed widespread inefficiencies and corruption in public administration (Munzhedzi, 2021). Applying NPM to PREAM highlights the need for transparent lease management, performance-based maintenance strategies, and streamlined decision-making processes.

Dynamic Capabilities View (DCV)

The DCV framework, developed by Teece et al. (1997), focuses on an organization’s ability to adapt, integrate, and reconfigure internal and external competencies in response to changing

environments. In the public sector, this theory has been used to explain how institutions respond to political shifts, budgetary constraints, and evolving service delivery demands (Pablo et al., 2007). For South Africa's Department of Public Works and Infrastructure (DPWI), DCV underscores the importance of strategic agility, particularly in managing a vast and diverse asset portfolio under conditions of fiscal pressure and administrative fragmentation.

Modern Portfolio Theory (MPT)

Originally developed by Markowitz (1952) for financial investment, MPT emphasizes diversification to optimize returns and minimize risk. While governments do not manage real estate for profit, the principles of portfolio optimization are applicable in ensuring cost-effective use of public assets. In the context of South Africa, where funding is limited and asset utilization is uneven, MPT provides a conceptual basis for evaluating trade-offs between maintenance costs, asset performance, and long-term value (Zhang, 2024). It also supports the argument for treating public real estate as a strategic portfolio rather than isolated assets.

Literature Review

Management Structure of Public Real Estate in South Africa

The management of public real estate in South Africa is embedded within a three-tier governmental framework comprising national, provincial, and local levels. These levels are constitutionally defined as separate but interdependent and interrelated entities (Nzimakwe & Pillay, 2014). According to Section 43(a) of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa (1996), national government is responsible for policy and legislative frameworks, which are then adopted and implemented by provincial and local governments.

South Africa operates under a decentralized governance model, which theoretically promotes democratic participation, accountability, and development (Chilenga-Butao, 2020; Mokgopo, 2017). However, decentralization also introduces challenges such as fragmented responsibilities, bureaucratic delays, and limited coordination between national and sub-national entities (Feinstein, 2015; Visser & Chigwata, 2022). These structural issues directly impact the effectiveness of public real estate asset management (PREAM).

The Department of Public Works and Infrastructure (DPWI) is the central authority mandated to manage and maintain the state's immovable assets. Its responsibilities include maintaining an asset register, interfacing with municipal valuation rolls, and overseeing construction, facilities, and real estate management (DPWI, 2025). Within the DPWI, the Property Management Trading Entity (PMTE) executes operational functions through four specialized units: Real Estate Investment, Real Estate Management Services, Facilities Management, and Construction Management (DPWI, 2020).

Despite this structured approach, the DPWI faces significant operational challenges. Maletswa and Boshoff (2015) highlight that lease management practices are outdated and inconsistent, with poor

tenant screening and ineffective rent collection mechanisms. These issues are compounded by underutilized properties and illegal occupations, with over 1,200 buildings identified as illegally occupied (PMTE, 2025).

The scale of the DPWI's portfolio, comprising 29,955 land parcels and 80,630 buildings valued at over R143 billion, requires a strategic, portfolio-based management approach (DPWI, 2025). However, studies suggest that the government often treats assets as isolated entities rather than as part of an integrated portfolio aligned with public service delivery goals (Dobrucká et al., 2024; Gross & Wolny-Kucińska, 2021).

Furthermore, the lack of a unified asset management strategy and the absence of performance management tools hinder effective oversight and accountability (Buys & Mavasa, 2007; Phathela & Cloete, 2018). The fragmentation of roles and responsibilities across departments leads to inefficiencies in decision-making and resource allocation, exacerbating maintenance backlogs and service delivery failures (Ngobeni et al., 2015; Mahlangu & Worku, 2023).

Although South Africa has a formalized structure for managing public real estate, the implementation is hampered by systemic governance issues, outdated practices, and a lack of strategic integration. Addressing these challenges requires not only policy reform but also institutional capacity building and the adoption of modern asset management frameworks.

Strategic and Policy-Level Challenges

Strategic and policy-level challenges in public real estate asset management (PREAM) in South Africa are deeply rooted in fragmented governance, inconsistent implementation of frameworks, and a lack of long-term planning. Although the Department of Public Works and Infrastructure (DPWI) has developed comprehensive policies and frameworks, their execution remains inconsistent and often ineffective (Maletswa & Boshoff, 2015; PMTE, 2025).

One of the core strategic issues is the absence of a unified asset management strategy that aligns with national development goals. The Government Immovable Asset Management Act (GIAMA) was introduced to guide the strategic management of public assets, yet its impact has been limited due to poor enforcement and lack of integration across departments (Phathela & Cloete, 2018). McKenna (2019) argues that the South African government's approach to asset management is disjointed, with decisions often made on an ad hoc basis rather than through structured lifecycle planning.

Policy-level challenges are further exacerbated by bureaucratic inefficiencies. Decision-making processes are often delayed due to excessive administrative requirements, such as multiple signatories for approvals, which hinder timely responses to market opportunities and urgent maintenance needs (DPWI, 2025). This red tape undermines the agility required for strategic asset management and results in missed investment opportunities and increased operational risks.

While strategic frameworks exist, they are not supported by adequate implementation guidelines or monitoring mechanisms. This gap between policy and practice reflects a broader issue of institutional capacity and accountability (Davis, 2012; Shava & Mazenda, 2021). Moreover, the lack of alignment between asset management and fiscal planning means that budget constraints often prevent the execution of strategic initiatives, such as preventative maintenance or portfolio optimization (Buys & Mavasa, 2007; Sekalo et al., 2022).

South Africa has made strides in developing strategic and policy frameworks for PREAM, but their effectiveness is undermined by poor implementation, bureaucratic inertia, and inadequate resource allocation. Similar implementation challenges have been observed in other developing countries such as Tanzania and Indonesia, where strategic asset management frameworks exist but are poorly enforced or inconsistently applied (Assey et al., 2017; Atikoh et al., 2017). Addressing these challenges requires not only policy reform but also institutional strengthening, capacity building, and the integration of strategic asset management into broader public sector planning.

Operational Challenges

Operational inefficiencies are a defining challenge in South Africa's public real estate asset management (PREAM), particularly in the areas of lease administration, maintenance, and interdepartmental coordination. These operational inefficiencies mirror those found in Tanzanian and Indonesian public sectors, where poor record-keeping, reactive maintenance, and fragmented responsibilities have similarly hindered asset performance (Assey et al., 2017; Atikoh et al., 2017). These inefficiencies not only reduce the financial performance of public assets but also compromise the quality and safety of infrastructure critical to service delivery. They also reflect deeper institutional and strategic weaknesses that hinder the effective use of public assets.

Lease Administration and Space Utilization

Lease management remains inconsistent and poorly regulated. Government departments often lease private properties at higher costs while state-owned buildings remain vacant or illegally occupied. Over 1,200 such cases have been identified (PMTE, 2025). Lease contracts are frequently outdated, tenant screening is irregular, and there is no standardized process for handling non-payment (Maletswa & Boshoff, 2015). This practice reflects poor coordination between departments and a lack of centralized oversight in space planning. The absence of standardized lease agreements and tenant screening procedures further exacerbates inefficiencies, leading to revenue losses and legal disputes.

Maintenance and Lifecycle Management

Maintenance of public buildings is largely reactive and underfunded. The DPWI's data shows that only 642 buildings are in excellent condition, while over 6,900 are in poor or very poor condition (PMTE, 2024) (Figure 1). This backlog is exacerbated by delayed procurement processes, lack of preventive maintenance planning, and insufficient funding (Ngobeni et al., 2015; Mahlangu & Worku, 2023). As a result, many government-owned properties are aged and require substantial

refurbishment, yet maintenance budgets are frequently constrained or misallocated. Studies have shown that the lack of lifecycle asset management planning leads to deferred maintenance, which not only increases long-term costs but also compromises safety and service delivery (Ngobeni et al., 2015; Davis, 2012). These inefficiencies increase long-term costs and compromise the safety and usability of public infrastructure.

Figure 1. Building Condition (PMTE, 2024)

Fragmented Operational Structures

The operational structure within the Department of Public Works and Infrastructure (DPWI) and its Property Management Trading Entity (PMTE) is divided into multiple units: real estate investment, management services, facilities management, and construction management. While specialization can enhance technical focus, the lack of integration across these units often results in duplication of efforts, miscommunication, and inconsistent service delivery (Buys & Mavasa, 2007). This fragmentation undermines the efficiency of asset management operations and complicates accountability.

Inadequate Performance Monitoring

There is a notable absence of performance management systems to monitor asset condition, utilization, and financial returns. Without robust key performance indicators (KPIs) and benchmarking tools, it is difficult to assess the effectiveness of operational decisions or identify areas for improvement (Hanis et al., 2010; Wojewnik-Filipkowska et al., 2015). This lack of data-driven oversight contributes to poor decision-making and limits the government's ability to optimize its asset portfolio.

Capacity and Resource Constraints

Operational challenges are compounded by limited human and financial resources. Many departments lack adequately trained personnel to manage complex asset portfolios, and funding

for operations is often insufficient or inconsistently allocated (Ruparathna et al., 2017). These constraints reduce the government's ability to implement modern asset management practices and respond to emerging needs.

Technological Challenges

Technological challenges in public real estate asset management (PREAM) in South Africa are primarily linked to outdated systems, fragmented data management, and limited adoption of digital innovations. Effective asset management requires accurate, timely, and integrated information systems to support decision-making across the asset lifecycle. However, the Department of Public Works and Infrastructure (DPWI) continues to rely on legacy systems that do not fully support modern asset management practices (Steyn, 2018).

The asset register, which is central to tracking and managing government-owned properties, remains incomplete and unreliable. Studies have shown that the register lacks critical technical, legal, and financial information, making it difficult to assess the value, condition, and utilization of assets (Buys & Mavasa, 2007; Horni et al., 2020). Without a centralized and validated database, strategic planning and financial reporting are compromised, and the risk of asset mismanagement increases. Salah and Bisogno (2023) emphasize that asset information frameworks are essential for valuation, budgeting, and maintenance planning, yet South Africa's public sector has struggled to implement such systems effectively.

The absence of international asset information standards and digital integration further limits the government's ability to manage its portfolio efficiently. In many cases, data is siloed across departments, and there is no unified platform for sharing or analyzing asset-related information. This fragmentation hinders transparency and coordination, especially in large-scale infrastructure planning and maintenance scheduling (Heaton et al., 2019; Kim & Ebdon, 2021).

Globally, governments are increasingly adopting technologies such as Geographic Information Systems (GIS), Building Information Modelling (BIM), and Internet of Things (IoT) solutions to enhance asset visibility and performance monitoring. These tools enable real-time tracking of asset conditions, predictive maintenance, and data-driven decision-making. However, in South Africa, the uptake of such technologies has been slow, and their application remains limited to select projects or newer buildings (Ullah et al., 2018).

Technological challenges in PREAM reflect a broader issue of digital underdevelopment and institutional inertia. Addressing these challenges requires investment in modern asset management platforms, adoption of global data standards, and capacity building to ensure that public sector personnel can effectively leverage technology for improved asset governance.

Human Resource and Capacity Challenges

Human resources and capacity challenges are among the most critical barriers to effective public real estate asset management (PREAM) in South Africa. The management of complex and diverse asset portfolios requires skilled personnel with expertise in property management, facilities maintenance, strategic planning, and financial oversight. However, the public sector continues to face a shortage of qualified professionals in these areas, which undermines the implementation of asset management strategies and compromises service delivery.

Studies have shown that many facilities managers and property officers within the Department of Public Works and Infrastructure (DPWI) lack formal training and experience in asset management practices. Mukori (2013) found that while senior officials in the Western Cape were well-qualified and experienced, the study did not assess the capacity of non-managerial staff, who are often responsible for implementing asset management strategies. Buys and Tonono (2007) found that over half of facilities managers in the public sector were inexperienced, highlighting a significant skills gap. This lack of expertise is particularly problematic given the technical nature of asset lifecycle planning, valuation, and maintenance coordination.

The disconnect between operational knowledge and strategic decision-making further exacerbates capacity issues. While senior officials may possess the qualifications to develop policy frameworks, the implementation of these strategies often falls to junior staff who may not have the necessary training or support (Ruparathna et al., 2017). This misalignment between policy formulation and execution leads to inconsistent practices and poor outcomes.

Moreover, human resource development in the public sector is constrained by limited investment in training and professional development. Asset management is a dynamic field that requires continuous learning, especially with the integration of digital technologies and evolving governance models. Yet, opportunities for upskilling and certification in asset management remain scarce within government departments (Henry et al., 2021).

Institutional capacity is also affected by staffing shortages and high turnover rates. Many departments operate with insufficient personnel to manage large portfolios, resulting in delayed maintenance, poor record-keeping, and reactive decision-making. This lack of capacity not only affects operational efficiency but also limits the ability to adopt and sustain strategic reforms in asset governance.

Addressing human resource and capacity challenges in PREAM requires a comprehensive approach that includes targeted recruitment, structured training programs, and institutional support for professional development. Strengthening the human capital base is essential for improving asset performance, ensuring compliance with policy frameworks, and achieving long-term sustainability in public real estate management.

Regulatory Bottlenecks

Regulatory bottlenecks present a significant challenge to effective public real estate asset management (PREAM) in South Africa. These bottlenecks arise from complex, overlapping, and often outdated legislative frameworks that hinder timely decision-making and efficient asset governance. While the Government Immovable Asset Management Act (GIAMA) was introduced to streamline asset management practices, its implementation has been inconsistent across departments and provinces, leading to fragmented compliance and limited impact (Phathela & Cloete, 2018).

One of the key issues is the lack of harmonization between national policies and provincial or municipal regulations. This misalignment creates confusion regarding roles and responsibilities, particularly in the acquisition, disposal, and maintenance of public assets. The decentralization of governance, while intended to promote accountability and responsiveness, has in practice led to duplication of efforts and jurisdictional disputes (Nzimakwe & Pillay, 2014; Chilenga-Butao, 2020).

Procurement regulations also contribute to regulatory delays. The Public Finance Management Act (PFMA) and related supply chain management policies impose stringent requirements on asset-related transactions, including leasing, renovations, and disposals. While these controls are designed to prevent corruption and ensure transparency, they often result in prolonged approval processes that delay critical interventions and increase operational risks (Madue, 2007; Feinstein, 2015).

Furthermore, the absence of clear guidelines for implementing strategic asset management frameworks has led to inconsistent practices across government entities. Departments often interpret regulations differently, resulting in varied levels of compliance and performance. This regulatory ambiguity undermines efforts to standardize asset management procedures and adopt best practices (Sekalo et al., 2022).

In addition, regulatory frameworks have not kept pace with technological advancements. The lack of provisions for digital asset management systems, data integration, and performance monitoring tools limits the government's ability to modernize its asset governance approach. As a result, opportunities to enhance transparency, efficiency, and accountability through digital transformation remain underutilized (Horni et al., 2020; Salah & Bisogno, 2023).

Regulatory bottlenecks in PREAM reflect a broader need for legislative reform, policy coherence, and institutional alignment. Addressing these challenges requires simplifying regulatory processes, clarifying mandates across government levels, and embedding flexibility to accommodate innovation and evolving asset management standards.

Research Methodology

This study employed a qualitative approach within the interpretivist paradigm to explore the challenges of public real estate asset management (PREAM) in South Africa. Interpretivism acknowledges that knowledge is shaped by context and social interactions, making it suitable for understanding institutional dynamics and stakeholder perspectives (Levy, 2015; Alharahsheh & Pius, 2020). Data was collected through semi-structured interviews with ten professionals from the Department of Public Works and Infrastructure (DPWI), including asset, facilities, and property managers at national and provincial levels. Participants were selected using purposive sampling to ensure relevance and depth of insight (Tongco, 2007). Interviews were conducted online via Microsoft Teams between April and May 2025, recorded and transcribed with informed consent. Thematic analysis was employed to analyze the interview data, following the framework proposed by Clarke and Braun (2016). This method involves systematically identifying, organizing, and interpreting patterns within qualitative data. The analysis was guided by the five dimensions of the property management framework developed by Abdullah et al. (2012): process, performance, organization, technology, and knowledge. Constant comparison techniques were used throughout the analysis to refine emerging themes and ensure coherence with existing literature. Ethical clearance was obtained from the University of the Witwatersrand. All participants were assured of confidentiality and anonymity, and ethical principles were upheld throughout the research process.

Findings

The sample size consisted of ten Public Works and Infrastructure employees working in the PMTE department, specifically as an asset manager, property manager, or facilities manager (Table 1). The participants are employed at either the national or provincial level within the department.

Table 1: List of Participants

Position	Office	Experience	Highest Qualification
Director- Asset Management	Provincial	8 years	MSc Urban and Regional Planning
Director- Property Management	Provincial	13 Years	BSc Social Science in Public Administration
Asset Manager	Provincial	10 Years	PGDip Property Development and Management
Director- Asset Management	National	15 Years	PGDip Property Development and Management

Deputy Director- Property and Facilities Management	National	19 Years	PGDip Property Development and Management
Facilities Manager	National	21 Years	B-Tech Electrical Engineering
Facilities Manager	National	6 Years	Advanced certificate in Facilities Maintenance Management
Facilities Manager	Provincial	25 Years	PGDip Facilities Management
Asset Manager	Provincial	20 Years	MBA
Asset Manager	National	20 Years	PGDip In Business Management

Challenges

Despite the scale and significance of public real estate holdings in South Africa, the central government continues to face persistent challenges in managing these assets effectively. Public real estate asset management (PREAM) is a complex undertaking that requires strategic planning, operational efficiency, technological integration, and skilled human resources. However, systemic issues such as fragmented governance, outdated systems, and limited institutional capacity have hindered progress. This section presents the key challenges identified through qualitative interviews with professionals in the Department of Public Works and Infrastructure (DPWI), organized around five thematic dimensions: process, performance, organization, technology, and knowledge (Tabel 2). These findings offer a comprehensive view of the structural and operational barriers that constrain the government's ability to manage its real estate portfolio sustainably and strategically.

Table 2: List of challenges

PREAM Challenge	Theme
Insufficient lease management. Insufficient funds	Process
Lack of maintenance	Performance
Lack of asset management strategies, identifying the lowest cost versus the highest returns. Lack of explicit policies	Organization
Inadequate information systems and asset register management	Technology
Uneducated, unskilled and inexperienced personnel, Insufficient training, fragmentation of roles and responsibilities	Knowledge

Theme 1: Process

Insufficient lease management and insufficient funding

The findings reveal that the lack of funding and budget is the main challenge facing the department. Without a budget, the real estate cannot be managed optimally. Building condition assessments are an essential element in managing real estate; however, without funding, these assessments cannot be conducted, especially for buildings in remote areas where extensive travel is required. Participant 1 states that National PMTE has greater control of the budget than provincial PMTE. PMTE's current funding challenges stem from rental nonpayment by client departments. This was highlighted by participant no 5: *Currently, the government's fiscal policy is strained. We lack the funds to repair the buildings and properties nationwide, leaving client departments to endure deplorable conditions. I think the main challenge is that it's going to take a while for those properties to be brought to their normal standards. I think that's the main challenge, and the other challenge obviously is when it comes to leases, we have a situation where landlords are not honouring their contracts, lease agreement status.*

Theme 2: Performance

Lack of maintenance

As literature has suggested, poor lease management practices lead to poor rental collection. The findings align with the literature; the respondents reveal that poor rent collection is affecting maintenance. *"The main challenge obviously is when it comes to leases, we have a situation where tenants are not honouring their contract lease agreement"*. The PMTE is struggling to collect rent, with most departments owing millions of rands. This causes financial strain on the PMTE. The PMTE cannot fund the needed maintenance. *"The portfolio is a large portfolio, and the government is unable to fund the maintenance and therefore DPW cannot manage the assets optimally."* Although

Theme 3: Organisation

Lack of Explicit Policies and Systems Gaps

Government policies and processes often make it difficult to make simultaneous decisions. Decision-making thus becomes a critical challenge. Usually, there are too many signatories involved in making a decision, which can prolong the procurement process and result in missed opportunities or increased risk in critical property decisions. *"red tape around, decision making sometimes they take too long, like by the time a decision is taken, the opportunity to invest has passed, because the market is not waiting for 50 signatures in one document, but that you have to find those 50 signatures by the time you get the last signature, that opportunity is long gone."*

Identifying the lowest cost versus the highest returns.

The challenges faced with asset management include identifying the lowest cost versus the highest returns to maximize the benefit of an asset. Developing countries are attempting to comprehend the expenses associated with the life cycle of infrastructure, while more developed countries are seeking ways to extend the lifespan of their infrastructure (Davis, 2012). Therefore, having a proper asset management strategy can provide structure in managing both these challenges (Davis, 2012). The majority of the respondents have identified this as a challenge. The government has developed the policies; however there is a lack of guidelines and implementation plan making, in difficult to follow the policies and legislation *“The Government has great frameworks which are the same or if not better than the ones in the private sector. It's the execution or the implementation that is the challenge for the government. The guidelines for those policies and the processes and procedures leave a lot to be desired.”*(P9)

Theme 4: Technology

Inadequate information systems and asset register management

The DPWI utilizes ACUBUS as a management system; however, not all aspects of this system are being used. The FM respondents were aware of digital technology than the other respondents (AM and PM). They indicated that the new buildings in the portfolio have implemented digital technology, such as the Internet of Things and building management systems.

Asset information influences decision-making throughout the entire asset life cycle; this information is recorded in the asset register (Steyn, 2018). This includes setting up all information systems and the continuous management and recording of information to ensure optimal functionality throughout the entire infrastructural asset's life (Steyn, 2018). Asset registers capture the technical, legal, and financial information of government assets, enabling accurate financial reporting practices (Horni et al., 2020). Governments must establish and maintain asset registers (Horni et al., 2020). Strategic decision-making cannot be achieved without international asset information standards and information management (Horni et al., 2020). Therefore, an asset register is paramount to the effective and efficient management of immovable assets (Phathela et al., 2018).

However, despite this, a recurring theme emerges in the challenges of capturing, storing, and validating data across a diverse and complex asset portfolio (Heaton et al., 2019). Some countries have inadequate asset information that is not centralized, making it difficult to assess the conditions and needs of the assets sufficiently (Kim and Ebdon, 2021). Only 60% of the participants indicated the asset register as a challenge. This is an indication of the work the department has committed in updating the asset register.

Theme 5: Knowledge

Uneducated, unskilled, and inexperienced personnel

The findings reveal that capacity is a challenge. DWP does not have sufficient qualified personnel for specific tasks and roles, and duties. Most of the personnel in the department have been there for many years, however do not have the correct education and skill set for asset management. *“The challenge is the capacity of people, mainly not just in the technical sector but also from the real estate sector, having skilled and educated staff, also assist in terms of ensuring that asset management is done properly.”*(P1). *“The expertise and skills are not there* (P3).

Discussion

This study contributes to the growing body of literature on public real estate asset management (PREAM) by revisiting established theoretical frameworks and offering new insights specific to the South African central government. The findings reaffirm several challenges previously identified in the literature, such as fragmented governance, outdated lease management, and poor maintenance practices. These align with the principles of New Public Management (NPM), which advocate for efficiency, accountability, and performance in public sector operations. However, the study reveals that despite the existence of strategic frameworks like GIAMA, implementation remains inconsistent, and performance tracking tools are largely absent, echoing concerns raised by Buys and Mavasa (2007) and Phathela and Cloete (2018).

From the perspective of the Dynamic Capabilities View (DCV), the study highlights the limited agility of the Department of Public Works and Infrastructure (DPWI) in responding to evolving asset conditions and stakeholder needs. While previous research has noted capacity constraints, this study adds new evidence of how internal fragmentation and underutilization of digital systems, such as ACUBUS, impede adaptive asset governance. The lack of integration between operational units and the slow adoption of technologies like GIS and BIM suggest that the organization’s dynamic capabilities are underdeveloped, limiting its ability to innovate and respond to change.

Modern Portfolio Theory (MPT), though traditionally applied to investment contexts, offers a useful lens for understanding inefficiencies in asset utilization and financial planning. The study confirms that the government continues to lease private properties at higher costs despite owning underutilized assets, indicating poor portfolio-level decision-making. This supports earlier observations by Maletswa and Boshoff (2015) but introduces a new dimension: the financial strain caused by rental non-payment from client departments, which directly affects the DPWI’s ability to maintain and optimize its portfolio.

Importantly, this study presents several new findings that have not been extensively documented in previous literature. First, it identifies the lack of a clear implementation plan for existing policies as a critical barrier to effective asset management. While frameworks exist, their operationalization is hindered by vague guidelines and excessive bureaucracy. Second, the study reveals that

decision-making processes are slowed by the requirement for multiple signatories, which delays procurement and investment opportunities. Third, it uncovers the uneven awareness and use of digital tools among different professional roles within the DPWI, suggesting a need for targeted digital literacy and training initiatives.

Comparative insights further contextualize these findings. Similar challenges have been observed in countries like Tanzania and Indonesia, where incomplete asset registers and reactive maintenance dominate (Assey et al., 2017; Atikoh et al., 2017). However, South Africa's centralized governance model and scale of holdings present unique complexities. Within the country, provincial disparities also exist. For instance, the Western Cape has demonstrated stronger institutional capacity and digital adoption than other provinces (Mukori, 2013), suggesting that localized best practices could inform national reforms.

Conclusion

This study explored the current challenges faced by the South African central government in managing public real estate assets, using a qualitative approach grounded in interpretivism. The findings revealed persistent issues across five key dimensions: process, performance, organization, technology, and knowledge. These include insufficient lease management, maintenance backlogs, fragmented roles and responsibilities, underutilized digital systems, and a shortage of skilled personnel. While many of these challenges echo those identified in previous studies, this research contributes new insights by highlighting the lack of clear implementation plans for existing policies, the bureaucratic delays caused by multi-layered approval processes, and the uneven adoption of digital tools across professional roles.

The study is limited by its small, purposively selected sample of ten professionals from the Department of Public Works and Infrastructure, which may not fully represent the broader public sector. Additionally, the focus on central government perspectives excludes insights from local government, private sector partners, and service users. Despite these limitations, this study offers valuable contributions to understanding the institutional and operational dynamics of public asset management in South Africa.

Future research should expand the scope to include comparative analyses across provinces and other tiers of government, as well as longitudinal studies to assess the impact of policy reforms and digital interventions over time. Mixed-methods approaches could also enhance the depth and generalizability of findings.

The study highlights the critical need for reform in public real estate asset management, with implications for policy, practice, and stakeholders. From a policy perspective, clearer implementation frameworks, streamlined decision-making processes, and mandatory performance tracking systems are essential to promote accountability and integration across government levels. Policies should also mandate the use of standardized digital tools and establish performance benchmarks to guide asset management. Practically, the Department of Public Works and

Infrastructure (DPWI) must invest in digital infrastructure, complete and validate its asset register, and build technical capacity through targeted training, while also streamlining lease and maintenance processes to enhance operational efficiency. These reforms are vital not only for improving functionality but also for ensuring that public real estate assets effectively support service delivery, economic development, and long-term sustainability. For stakeholders, including government departments, service providers, and citizens, effective asset governance is crucial for maintaining safe, functional infrastructure and delivering reliable public services.

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**Peer Reviewed*

ESG Disclosure by South African Listed REITs and its Impact on Investment Performance *Unarine Nemavhulani¹, Sibongile Zwane^{2*}*

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Abstract

This study investigates the effect of ESG disclosure on the investment performance of South African REITs listed on the Johannesburg Stock Exchange (JSE). With the growing global focus on sustainable investment practices, the study seeks to assess the influence of ESG disclosure on investment appeal and financial outcomes within the South African market. Employing a quantitative methodology, data spanning from 2016 to 2023 was sourced from EquityRT and analysed using various statistical techniques, including descriptive statistics, and regression analysis. The findings indicate a nuanced relationship between ESG disclosure and investment performance indicators, such as Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), the Sharpe Ratio, and Dividend Yield. Despite the gradual improvement in ESG disclosure among South African REITs, the financial performance metrics demonstrate an inverse relationship with ESG disclosure, suggesting that investors may not yet place significant emphasis on ESG factors in their investment strategies. This research contributes to an understanding of ESG practices in emerging markets and offers insights for strengthening ESG disclosure frameworks within the South African REIT industry. Future research directions include broadening the sample size to include other emerging markets and considering alternative performance measures for a more comprehensive analysis.

Key words: Emerging Markets Finance, ESG Disclosure, Investment Performance, South African REITs, Sustainable Real Estate

Introduction

In recent years, climate change has become a defining challenge for economies worldwide, prompting global commitments such as the 2015 Paris Agreement and the United Nations' 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). In response, regulators and investors have embraced Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) frameworks, particularly through mechanisms like the Principles for Responsible Investment (PRI) and the Task Force on Climate-Related Financial Disclosure (TCFD), to promote responsible and transparent investment practices (Feng & Wu, 2021; Zanin, 2022). Within this context, the real estate sector is uniquely positioned to contribute to global sustainability goals due to its long-term investment horizon, inflation-hedging potential, and significant environmental impact.

Real Estate Investment Trusts (REITs) offer an indirect yet highly liquid route into the real estate market and have gained traction globally, including in emerging markets such as South Africa. While developed markets like the U.S., Europe, and Australia lead in ESG integration within the REIT sector, emerging markets lag in both implementation and transparency (Newell, 2023). In South Africa, REITs listed on the Johannesburg Stock Exchange (JSE) play an increasingly important role in the local and regional property investment landscape (Ntuli & Akinsomi, 2017). However, despite their market significance, South African REITs remain behind in ESG disclosure practices (Johnson, Mans-Kemp & Erasmus, 2019).

The growing global emphasis on ESG integration has triggered demand for transparency and accountability in investment decision-making. Real estate-specific ESG disclosure tools, such as the JLL Global Real Estate Transparency Index, EU Taxonomy, and the Carbon Risk Real Estate Monitor (CRREM), have been developed to support sustainability and climate-aligned investment strategies (Robinson et al., 2022). However, many of these tools prioritise environmental performance while often overlooking social and governance dimensions, underscoring the need for a more holistic ESG approach (Newell, 2023).

Current literature tends to focus on green certifications and energy performance in REIT portfolios, often neglecting the full spectrum of ESG impacts on financial performance. Empirical evidence from other markets indicates that when ESG factors are assessed as a combined unit, rather than in isolation, they may positively influence a firm's cost of capital and operational performance (Shao, 2022). Yet, research exploring such dynamics in the South African REIT context remains limited. This study responds to that gap by examining how ESG disclosure affects the financial performance and investment appeal of South African REITs.

A substantial body of research has examined the internal impact of ESG disclosure on the performance of Real Estate Investment Trusts (REITs), focusing on how enhanced transparency affects firm-level efficiency and valuation (Aroul et al., 2022; Ascherl et al., 2019; Carstens & Freybote, 2019; Feng & Wu, 2021; Newell et al., 2023; Shao, 2022). However, there remains limited knowledge on the external implications of ESG disclosure—particularly its role in attracting capital, shaping investor confidence, and influencing financial performance in emerging markets (Feng & Wu, 2021). This gap is significant in the South African REIT sector, where ESG disclosure practices lag behind global leaders (Newell, 2023) and where disclosure is often narrowly focused on governance, with less emphasis on environmental and social dimensions.

Given the rising global demand for sustainable investments, the absence of comprehensive ESG reporting frameworks in South Africa constrains both investor decision-making and the ability of REITs to demonstrate long-term value creation. This study therefore seeks to address this gap by examining the effect of ESG disclosure on the investment performance of South African REITs, thereby contributing to the broader discourse on how ESG practices can support both market competitiveness and sustainability outcomes in emerging economies (199)

Research Aim and Objectives

This paper aims to analyse the influence of ESG disclosure by South African listed REITs on their investment performance. Specifically, the study seeks to:

- Assess the proportion of South African REITs disclosing ESG performance.
- Evaluate the impact of ESG disclosure on REIT financial performance.
- Analyse trends in ESG disclosure and investment outcomes post-SDG implementation.
- Examine ESG disclosure scoring trends across the sector.

By exploring these dimensions, the study contributes to the growing discourse on ESG integration in property investment, offering insights for investors, regulators, and policymakers seeking to enhance sustainability-driven real estate practices in emerging markets.

Literature Review

ESG Disclosure and Financial Performance

The growing importance of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) considerations in investment decision-making has prompted firms across industries to enhance the transparency and quality of their non-financial disclosures. ESG disclosure refers to the systematic communication of a company's environmental, social, and governance-related practices and performance. Scholars have highlighted its rising importance in improving corporate image, stakeholder trust, and competitive advantage (Raimo et al., 2021; Albarrak, Elnahass & Salama, 2019).

Research shows that firms implementing effective ESG strategies benefit from improved financial performance and broader investor appeal. ESG disclosure is increasingly viewed as a strategic tool that supports long-term stakeholder relationships and enhances firm valuation (Eliwa et al., 2019). For example, studies have shown that firms with higher ESG transparency attract more investors, enjoy reduced cost of equity, and benefit from improved market perception (Albarrak et al., 2019). This was evident in a U.S.-based study where firms that disclosed carbon-related information on social media experienced enhanced investor visibility and lower equity costs.

The relationship between ESG disclosure and the cost of debt has also been explored. Raimo et al. (2021) found a negative correlation between ESG transparency and firms' cost of debt, reinforcing findings from Chi et al. (2020) and Xu et al. (2019). High-quality ESG disclosure appears to signal reduced risk to lenders, resulting in more favourable financing conditions. However, some studies caution against treating ESG dimensions in isolation. Eliwa et al. (2019) argue that assessing ESG as a compound factor yields stronger explanatory power, whereas isolated components—especially governance—may not independently influence financial outcomes.

Despite the growing consensus on the benefits of ESG disclosure, contradictory findings remain. For instance, Wang, Hu, and Zhong (2022) note that the academic literature remains divided on whether ESG disclosure consistently translates into value creation. This suggests that context-specific factors—such as industry type, geographic location, and regulatory environment—may influence the impact of ESG disclosures on firm performance.

ESG Disclosure in the Real Estate Sector

The real estate sector has increasingly acknowledged its responsibility to integrate ESG principles into corporate practices. Real estate assets are closely linked to environmental performance, urban well-being, and social equity, making the sector particularly relevant in achieving sustainability goals (Chiang, Wachtel & Zhou, 2017). ESG integration in real estate, therefore, not only aligns with global agendas like the UN SDGs but also enhances long-term asset value and reduces portfolio risk (Cloutier, Robinson & Sullivan, 2021).

REITs, as publicly listed real estate investment vehicles, are uniquely positioned to lead this transition. Given their reliance on capital markets for funding and their relatively low cash reserves, REITs are particularly vulnerable to market perceptions and information asymmetry (Devos et al., 2018; Kim, Lim & Wiley, 2021). Consequently, transparency in ESG disclosure has

become an important differentiator for REITs seeking to improve capital access and reduce funding costs.

Feng and Wu (2021) examined ESG disclosure among REITs globally and found a negative relationship between ESG transparency and both cost of debt and firm value. Their analysis—based on a sample of 376 REITs using S&P Global Market Intelligence data—used measures such as weighted average interest rate and market-to-book equity ratio to assess financial performance. Interestingly, the study reported that REITs with high institutional ownership had higher ESG disclosure scores, suggesting that investor pressure is a key driver of transparency.

However, this finding diverges from other literature that consistently links ESG disclosure to improved firm valuation and performance (Albarrak et al., 2019; Shad et al., 2020). The discrepancy highlights the need for further research in emerging markets such as South Africa, where ESG disclosure practices are less mature, and regulatory pressures are still developing.

ESG Disclosure vs ESG Performance

It is important to distinguish between ESG disclosure and ESG performance. ESG disclosure concerns the communication of sustainability-related activities, whereas ESG performance reflects actual operational outcomes. While both influence investor perception, disclosure plays a more direct role in reducing information asymmetry and shaping market expectations (Feng & Wu, 2021; Eliwa et al., 2019). This distinction is essential for empirical studies aiming to examine causality between sustainability practices and financial performance.

As illustrated in **Figure 1**, this study develops a theoretical framework that integrates *stakeholder theory* and the *resource-based view (RBV)* to explain how ESG disclosure and ESG performance jointly influence financial outcomes in South African REITs. From a stakeholder perspective, disclosure reduces information asymmetry and enhances legitimacy by signalling alignment with investor and regulatory expectations, thereby potentially improving access to capital and investor confidence (Freeman, 1984 and Deegan, 2019). From an RBV perspective, ESG performance functions as a strategic, intangible resource that reduces operational risk, enhances efficiency, and strengthens competitiveness, with long-term benefits for firm resilience and market positioning (Barney, 1991; Bénabou & Tirole, 2010). Importantly, the framework underscores that disclosure without substantive performance may be perceived as symbolic or “greenwashing,” while strong performance without adequate disclosure remains invisible to capital markets, thereby diluting potential financial benefits. This framework informs the empirical analysis by linking ESG disclosure to four investment performance measures—Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), the Sharpe Ratio, and Dividend Yield—allowing the study to evaluate whether disclosure operates primarily as a signalling mechanism for legitimacy, a source of competitive advantage, or both, in the context of South Africa’s evolving REIT market.

Figure 1: Theoretical framework linking ESG disclosure and ESG performance to financial outcomes.

Relevance to REITs and Capital Markets

As REITs are embedded within stock markets, they are subject to the same pressures and expectations regarding disclosure and accountability (Gertsekovich et al., 2019). Their dependence on capital markets makes ESG transparency a critical factor in securing investor confidence and maintaining competitiveness. Disclosure thus becomes a strategic tool not only for regulatory compliance but also for capital efficiency.

According to Robinson and McIntosh (2022), investor and regulatory demand for ESG data has prompted REITs to evolve their disclosure strategies, creating new opportunities for research into the intersection between ESG and financial outcomes. Firms that effectively communicate their sustainability efforts are more likely to access favourable financing terms, reduce risk exposure, and attract long-term capital (Shad et al., 2020).

Summary of Key Findings

The literature establishes a growing consensus on the positive relationship between ESG disclosure and financial performance, particularly in terms of cost of capital and investor perception. Although some studies show conflicting results regarding firm value, especially in the REIT sector, the broader trend suggests that enhanced ESG disclosure offers strategic benefits in both developed and emerging markets. Given the limited research on South African REITs, this study contributes to closing the gap by investigating how ESG transparency influences financial performance within this context.

Methods

Research Strategy and Sampling

The research strategy employed a quantitative method, leveraging publicly available secondary data. The population consisted of all REITs listed on the Johannesburg Stock Exchange (JSE), with the sample narrowed to the top 11 REITs by market capitalisation. This approach mirrors previous studies which focused on large-cap, publicly traded firms due to their greater emphasis

on ESG practices (Nazarova & Lavrova, 2022). Financial and ESG data covering the 2016 to 2023 financial years were collected.

Development of Research Instrument

There are multiple attributes to data collection in quantitative research. According to Nazarova and Lavrova (2022), ESG considerations are generally more significant for large publicly traded companies. In this research study, a similar approach was used, that entailed analysing REITs which form part of the public equity market, the Johannesburg Exchange in South Africa. The study focused exclusively on the top 10 REITs, as determined by their market capitalisation. The critical items to analyse in the financial statements were the net income, total assets, and total equity. This data was used to build performance indicators, namely, Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), Sharpe Ratio and Dividends Yield.

ROE evaluates investment performance by assessing net income in relation to the use of shareholders' investments, whereas ROA measures investment performance by comparing the company's net income to the performance of its entire portfolio (Cheruiyot, Martell and Motani, 2023).

The Sharpe ratio is a market-based measure used to evaluate the risk-adjusted return of an investment or portfolio (Lo, 2002). It quantifies the excess return an investment generates for each unit of risk assumed, with risk being represented by the standard deviation of the investment's returns. By utilising the Sharpe ratio, investors can assess the efficiency of an investment in compensating for the risks undertaken, where a higher ratio signifies superior risk-adjusted performance (Barillas, Kan, Robotti and Shanken, 2019).

The Dividend Yield is a financial indicator that reflects the annual dividend payments made by a company as a percentage of its share price (Marito and Sjarif, 2020). It represents the return on investment derived exclusively from dividends, without accounting for any capital gains or losses resulting from fluctuations in the stock's market price (Marito and Sjarif, 2020). This metric is particularly valuable for income-focused investors, as it provides insight into the income generated from dividends relative to the stock's current market value.

The formulae which were used as the research instruments have been detailed below.

$$\text{Return on assets (ROA)} = \left(\frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Total Assets}} \right) \times 100$$

$$\text{Return on equity (ROE)} = \left(\frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Shareholder's Equity}} \right) \times 100$$

$$\text{Dividends Yield} = \left(\frac{\text{Annual Dividends per share}}{\text{Price per share}} \right) \times 100$$

$$\text{Sharpe Ratio} = \left(\frac{R_p - R_f}{\sigma_p} \right)$$

Where:

- R_p is the return of the portfolio or investment.

- R_f is the risk-free rate of return (the return on an investment with no risk, often represented by government bonds).
- σ_p is the standard deviation of the portfolio's returns (a measure of the investment's volatility).

The trading details which are listed on the EquityRT platform were used to determine the annual mean return based on the stock price. In addition, a South African 10-year yield government bond was used as the risk-free rate. The annualised return of the REIT stocks and the 10-year yield government bond were utilised to develop the Sharpe ratio instrument, as a measure of investment performance on the public equity market (Meyer, Neethling and Ślusarczyk, 2020).

Data collection Protocol

The financial data was collected from EquityRT, which was accessed through the Wits electronic database. A dashboard was generated on the platform with all the relevant REITs which form part of the sample of the study. The data was filtered to range between 2016 and 2023. The ESG data was collected from the Bloomberg database. According to Johnson (2020), the Bloomberg database has ESG disclosure scoring data of over 10,000 publicly listed companies. Although there are other platforms which could be used to access the data, EquityRT and Bloomberg were the most easily accessible and reliable platforms.

ESG Trend Analysis Hypothesis

An analysis of the ESG disclosure score trend was conducted. In order to fully analyse the scoring, the different components of the ESG scoring were analysed to evaluate the contribution of each component to the overall ESG disclosure scoring. A One-Way ANOVA test was utilised to further emphasise the trend of the ESG disclosure scoring by testing the level of significance at a 95% level of confidence. The following hypotheses were tested:

Data Analysis

The data for the study was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The use of descriptive statistics has enabled the determination of the minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation of the variables of interest (Aifuwa and Embele, 2019). The descriptive statistics provided an efficient, effective, and clear approach for presenting and summarizing the research data that was collected. Econometric model

A linear regression with ESG disclosure scoring as the independent variable and the investment performance measures as the dependent variable was run. Therefore, four regression models were determined. The regression models consist of various control variables, namely, Log of the market capitalisation, debt-to-equity ratio, GDP growth rate and the FTSE/JSE All Property Index return. An additional control variable was the Covid-19 dummy variable to account for the exogenous factors of Covid019 and its impact on business operations. The formulae have been defined as follows:

$$ROA_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ESG\ Score_{i,t} + \beta_2 GDP\ Growth_{i,t} + \beta_3 Covid\ Dummy_{i,t} + \beta_4 \ln MarketCap_{i,t} + \beta_5 Property\ Index\ Return_{i,t} + \beta_5 Debt/Equity_{i,t}$$

$$ROE_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ESG\ Score_{i,t} + \beta_2 GDP\ Growth_{i,t} + \beta_3 Covid\ Dummy_{i,t} + \beta_4 \ln MarketCap_{i,t} + \beta_5 Property\ Index\ Return_{i,t} + \beta_5 Debt/Equity_{i,t}$$

$$SharpeRat_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ESG\ Score_{i,t} + \beta_2 GDP\ Growth_{i,t} + \beta_3 Covid\ Dummy_{i,t} + \beta_4 \ln MarketCap_{i,t} + \beta_5 Property\ Index\ Return_{i,t} + \beta_5 Debt/Equity_{i,t}$$

$$Div.Yield_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ESG\ Score_{i,t} + \beta_2 GDP\ Growth_{i,t} + \beta_3 Covid\ Dummy_{i,t} + \beta_4 \ln MarketCap_{i,t} + \beta_5 Property\ Index\ Return_{i,t} + \beta_5 Debt/Equity_{i,t}$$

These formulae were used to determine how well the explanatory variables can predict and explain the variability of the predicted variables.

Findings and Analysis

The following chapter provides the findings for evaluating the investment performance of the sampled REITs and the ESG disclosure scores based on their published ESG information. The chapter provides an analysis of the data with reference to the literature which was utilised in compiling the literature review.

Table 1 illustrates the REITs that form part of the top 11 South African REITs, ranked based on their market capitalisation as of the 2nd of August 2024, that were sampled for the study. The addition of one more REIT to the sample, to make it a ‘top 11’ sample selection, was to improve the reliability of the study.

Table 1: Sampled REITs

Rank	REIT Name	Type/Industry	Market Capitalisation
1	Growthpoint Properties (GRT)	Diversified	R 48.203 billion
2	Redefine Properties (RDF)	Diversified	R 35.192 billion
3	Resilient REIT (RES)	Retail	R 21.649 billion
4	Vukile Property Fund (VKI)	Retail	R 21.030 billion
5	Hyprop Investments (HYP)	Retail	R 15.889 billion
6	Equites Property Fund (EQU)	Logistics	R 11.472 billion
7	Attacq (ATT)	Diversified	R 9.820 billion
8	SA Corporate Real Estate (SAC)	Diversified	R 7.670 billion
9	Burstone Group (BTN)	Diversified	R 7.421 billion
10	Stor-Age Property REIT (SSS)	Self-Storage	R 7.176 billion
11	Emira Property Fund (EMI)	Diversified	R 5.572 billion

Source: Compiled by Author using EquityRT

ESG Disclosure

In the top 10 South African REITs, only 6 of them have been publishing their ESG disclosure. This indicates that only 60% of the top 10 South African REITs publish their ESG disclosure.

It was identified that Emira, which is ranked 11th publishes their ESG report. In order to increase the number of data points, Emira was added to the sample of REITs which publish their ESG disclosure. Out of the 27 listed REITs, only the 7 REITs sampled for the study publish their ESG

disclosure. Therefore, out of the South African listed REITs approximately 25.93% publish their ESG disclosure.

Table 2 illustrates the ESG scores of the different REITs which were selected for the study. In the top 10 of the REITs, based on market capitalisation, Six of the REITs have ESG scoring based on their ESG disclosure over a period of 8 years.

Among the top 10 JSE-listed REITs by market capitalisation, six firms reported ESG disclosure scores over the 8-year period. Growthpoint and Redefine displayed consistent upward trends, with Redefine achieving the highest average ESG score, reflecting strong commitment to disclosure practices. Vukile, Resilient, and Emira maintained relatively stable scores between 2016 and 2020, followed by notable improvements from 2020 onward.

Vukile recorded the lowest average ESG disclosure score (34.59%), indicating limited progress in sustainability disclosure. Redefine showed the highest variability (variance: 0.91%, SD: 9.53%), reflecting more dynamic changes in ESG disclosure practices over time. In contrast, Hyprop's scores were the most stable (variance: 0.01%, SD: 1.13%) with only modest growth. Resilient and Attacq also demonstrated low variability and gradual improvement, suggesting a more measured approach to ESG integration. Based on average ESG disclosure scores from 2016 to 2023, the REITs can be ranked as follows:

1. Redefine Property
2. Growthpoint
3. Hyprop
4. Attacq
5. Vukile Property Fund
6. Resilient
7. Emira

The ESG disclosure scores of South African REITs indicate a general upward trend in transparency and sustainability practices. However, notable disparities exist in both the average disclosure levels and the pace of improvement across firms. Redefine leads in ESG disclosure, while Vukile trails behind its peers. These differences may have significant implications for financial performance and investor attractiveness, especially as ESG considerations play a growing role in investment decisions.

Table 2: ESG Disclosure scoring

ESG Disclosure Scoring							
Year	GRT	RDF	VKE	RES	HYP	EMI	ATT
2016	37.86%	46.56%	31.15%	32.18%	52.09%	33.62%	38.92%
2017	46.24%	47.79%	31.50%	32.18%	52.09%	37.01%	43.15%
2018	47.81%	49.64%	30.39%	32.37%	52.61%	34.92%	44.04%
2019	49.38%	56.74%	30.39%	32.33%	52.61%	34.79%	44.90%
2020	51.55%	59.15%	30.39%	32.33%	50.65%	37.27%	45.29%
2021	57.91%	66.17%	37.56%	37.24%	49.35%	40.02%	47.72%
2022	61.72%	67.56%	40.56%	37.89%	51.00%	44.05%	45.66%
2023	59.44%	71.06%	44.74%	39.04%	51.09%	47.07%	44.72%
Mean	51.49%	58.09%	34.59%	34.45%	51.44%	38.59%	44.30%
Variance	0.63%	0.91%	0.32%	0.09%	0.01%	0.23%	0.06%
Standard Deviation	7.93%	9.53%	5.63%	3.03%	1.13%	4.79%	2.55%

Source: Compiled by Author using Bloomberg

Table 3 illustrates the descriptive statistics of the overall ESG disclosure scoring for the Top 7 REITs which were sampled. The highest average disclosure scoring was achieved in 2023 (51.02%), where the maximum scoring was the highest (71.06%). The average ESG scoring per annum appears to be escalating over the indicated period.

Table 3: ESG disclosure scoring - Annual mean values

Year	Means	Standard dev.	Min.	Max.
2016	38.91%	8.56%	31.15%	52.09%
2017	41.13%	8.72%	31.50%	52.09%
2018	41.29%	9.79%	30.39%	52.61%
2019	42.71%	11.51%	30.39%	56.74%
2020	43.56%	11.80%	30.39%	59.15%
2021	48.04%	11.99%	37.24%	66.17%
2022	50.46%	11.97%	37.89%	67.56%
2023	51.02%	11.53%	39.04%	71.06%

Source: Compiled by Author using Bloomberg

The average ESG disclosure score among South African REITs increased steadily from 38.91% in 2016 to 51.02% in 2023, highlighting growing commitment to ESG transparency despite disruptions such as the COVID-19 pandemic, which coincided with a decline in ROA. Variability in disclosure also rose, with standard deviation increasing from 8.56% to 11.53%, indicating widening differences in ESG disclosure across firms. The sharp rise between 2019 and 2020 reflects the heightened uncertainty triggered by the pandemic. Encouragingly, even the lowest ESG scores improved over time, with the minimum score rising from 31.15% in 2016 to 39.04% in 2023—suggesting an industry-wide shift towards improved sustainability practices.

As shown in Figure 2, Governance consistently contributed the most to overall ESG scores. From 2016 to 2020, Social was the second-largest contributor, with Environmental scores trailing behind. However, from 2021 to 2023, Environmental scores surpassed Social, becoming the second-highest contributor—indicating increased environmental awareness in recent years.

Figure 2: ESG disclosure scoring trend

The consistently high annual mean Governance scores may be attributed to the influence of the King IV Report, which sets corporate governance standards for all companies incorporated in South Africa. King IV promotes not only compliance but also the integration of governance practices tailored to each company’s context, aligning with its 17 guiding principles (Ferguson, 2019). The upward trend in ESG disclosure scores suggests that REITs with published ESG reports have taken a deliberate approach to enhancing their sustainability practices. The gradual rise in Social scores further reflect a growing emphasis on social initiatives within REIT operations over the review period.

Investment performance

Table 6 and 7 illustrates the differences in the investment performance of REITs which disclose their ESG information.

Table 6: Return on Assets (ROA)

Year	Mean	Standard Dev.	Min.	Max.
2016	0.07	0.02	0.05	0.11
2017	0.06	0.02	0.02	0.09
2018	0.05	0.08	-0.11	0.10
2019	0.05	0.06	-0.02	0.14
2020	-0.15	0.15	-0.44	0.00
2021	0.004	0.05	-0.09	0.06

2022	0.08	0.03	0.05	0.12
2023	0.05	0.05	0.01	0.12

Source: Compiled by Author using EquityRT and SPSS

Table 7: Return on Equity (ROE)

Year	Mean	Standard Dev.	Min.	Max.
2016	0.11	0.02	0.08	0.14
2017	0.09	0.03	0.04	0.12
2018	0.08	0.11	-0.14	0.16
2019	0.07	0.08	-0.04	0.18
2020	-0.20	0.15	-0.42	0.00
2021	0.03	0.05	-0.04	0.10
2022	0.13	0.05	0.06	0.20
2023	0.07	0.06	0.02	0.18

Source: Compiled by Author using EquityRT and SPSS

Performance Trends

Both ROA and ROE displayed positive means in the pre-pandemic years, suggesting stable financial performance. However, in 2020, coinciding with the onset of COVID-19, both metrics recorded their lowest values (ROA: -0.15; ROE: -0.20), reflecting widespread operational and financial disruption. A gradual recovery followed, with ROA rebounding to 0.08 in 2022 before stabilising at 0.05 in 2023, and ROE rising to 0.13 in 2022 and 0.07 in 2023.

Volatility and Firm-Level Variation

Volatility in ROA spiked significantly between 2017 and 2018, with the standard deviation rising from 0.02 to 0.08, indicating increasing disparities in firm performance. This peaked in 2020 (SD: 0.15), reflecting high uncertainty during the pandemic. Volatility declined post-2020, signaling financial stabilisation among REITs. Similarly, ROE demonstrated considerable variability, particularly in 2018 and 2020, where standard deviation rose sharply. While ROE consistently recorded higher mean values than ROA—indicating stronger returns to equity holders—its greater standard deviation highlights increased sensitivity to earnings fluctuations, likely due to leverage in REIT capital structures.

Overall Performance (2016–2023)

As shown in Table 8, the average ROA over the 8-year period was 3%, while ROE averaged 4%. ROA exhibited lower overall variability (SD: 0.09) compared to ROE (SD: 0.12), reinforcing the observation that equity returns were more volatile than asset returns.

Table 8: ROA & ROE

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
ROA	56	-0.44	0.14	0.03	0.09
ROE	56	-0.42	0.20	0.04	0.12

Source: Compiled by Author using EquityRT and SPSS

Implications

These results suggest that ESG-disclosure REITs experienced a significant performance dip during the pandemic but have shown signs of recovery and resilience in recent years. The persistent volatility underscores the importance of continued financial discipline and risk monitoring. Additionally, the stronger performance of ROE relative to ROA reflects effective leverage usage but also exposes equity holders to higher earnings risk—an important consideration for investors focused on ESG-aligned real estate portfolios.

Sharpe Ratio and Dividends Yield

The Sharpe ratio and Dividends yield represent the market-based measures of investment performance for the study. The tables below illustrate the annual mean values of the market-based measures, including the standard deviation, minimum and maximum.

Table 9: Sharpe Ratio

Year	Mean	Standard Dev.	Min.	Max.
2016	-0.05	0.35	-0.59	0.38
2017	-0.03	0.40	-0.45	0.65
2018	-1.61	0.37	-2.06	-1.16
2019	-0.26	0.51	-0.97	0.64
2020	-1.11	0.27	-1.48	-0.74
2021	1.59	0.32	1.14	2.10
2022	0.01	0.29	-0.30	0.52
2023	-0.11	0.45	-0.70	0.67

Source: Compiled by Author using EquityRT and SPSS

Table 10: Dividends' Yield

Year	Mean	Standard Dev.	Min.	Max.
2016	0.06	0.03	0.00	0.10
2017	0.06	0.04	0.00	0.11
2018	0.09	0.02	0.05	0.10
2019	0.10	0.03	0.07	0.13
2020	0.11	0.05	0.02	0.16
2021	0.08	0.05	0.00	0.14

2022	0.09	0.02	0.07	0.12
2023	0.10	0.02	0.06	0.11

Source: Compiled by Author using EquityRT and SPSS

Sharpe Ratio Performance

The Sharpe Ratio, which measures risk-adjusted returns relative to a risk-free benchmark, demonstrated high volatility and mixed performance over the period. From 2016 to 2020, the annual mean Sharpe Ratio remained negative, suggesting underperformance relative to the risk-free rate. The lowest point was recorded in 2018 (-1.61), reflecting significant market challenges. In 2021, the metric rebounded sharply to a positive mean of 1.59, indicating exceptional risk-adjusted performance during the early post-pandemic recovery. However, this rebound was short-lived. By 2023, the mean had declined back to -0.11, pointing to renewed underperformance and increased market uncertainty.

Standard deviation trends further underscore this volatility. A notable increase from 0.37 in 2018 to 0.51 in 2019 suggests heightened variability in risk-adjusted returns, while the drop to 0.27 in 2020 reflects temporarily compressed performance during peak pandemic disruptions. The return to higher variability in 2023 (SD: 0.45) indicates divergent performance across REITs, possibly driven by uneven recovery strategies and market repositioning.

In summary, the Sharpe Ratio findings highlight the fragility and fluctuation of risk-adjusted performance in the REIT sector, with limited consistency and brief periods of strong rebound surrounded by underperformance.

Dividend Yield Performance

In contrast, Dividend Yield trends exhibited greater stability and a more predictable trajectory. Between 2016 and 2020, the average dividend yield rose steadily from 6% to 11%, reflecting consistent income generation across the sector. A temporary dip occurred in 2021, where the yield declined to 8%, likely due to pandemic-related earnings pressures. From 2021 to 2023, yields recovered gradually, returning to 10% in 2023.

Standard deviation values across the period remained low and stable, suggesting uniformity in dividend payments among the sampled REITs. This reflects the sector's adherence to mandated payout structures and its ability to maintain reliable investor income, even during economic downturns.

Overall, the dividend yield performance paints a picture of resilience and consistency, in contrast to the more erratic nature of risk-adjusted returns captured by the Sharpe Ratio.

Key Insights and Implications

The Sharpe Ratio's volatility and recurring negative means underscore the sensitivity of REITs to broader market shocks and their uneven ability to deliver returns commensurate with risk, especially during turbulent periods.

The Dividend Yield trend, on the other hand, affirms the sector’s strength in delivering steady income, enhancing its attractiveness for income-focused investors even during macroeconomic uncertainty.

The contrast between these two indicators suggests that while capital gains and risk-adjusted returns may be unstable, South African REITs retain their appeal through reliable dividend performance, which is crucial for portfolio diversification and income strategies.

Correlation Results

The correlation analysis aimed to assess the relationships among the independent and control variables to understand how changes in one variable may be associated with changes in others. While correlations can indicate the strength and direction of a relationship, they do not imply causation. A coefficient closer to 1 signals a strong positive correlation, near 0 indicates a weak or negligible correlation, and a negative value reflects an inverse relationship. The analysis followed the interpretation guidelines provided by Schober, Boer, and Schwarte (2018).

Table 11: Conventional approach to interpreting a correlation coefficient

Absolute magnitude of the observed correlation coefficient	Interpretation
0.00 – 0.10	Negligible correlation
0.10 – 0.39	Weak correlation
0.40 – 0.69	Moderate correlation
0.70 – 0.89	Strong correlation
0.90 – 1.00	Very strong correlation

Source: (Schober, Boer and Schwarte, 2018)

The table below illustrates the correlation coefficients between all variables.

Table 12: Correlation coefficients

	ESG Score	Debt-to-Equity Ratio	Annual GDP	All Property Index Return	LnMarketCap	Dummy - Covid	ROA	Return on Equity	Sharpe Ratio	Dividends Yield
ESG Score	1.0	0.264	0.065	0.106	0.341	0.07	-0.141	-0.135	0.046	0.173
Debt-to-Equity Ratio	0.264	1.0	-0.275	-0.036	-0.256	0.381	-0.203	-0.402	0.055	0.14
Annual GDP	0.065	-0.275	1.0	0.52	0.157	-0.442	0.586	0.644	0.338	-0.301
All Property Index Return	0.106	-0.036	0.52	1.0	-0.003	0.07	0.292	0.335	0.878	-0.304
LnMarketCap	0.341	-0.256	0.157	-0.003	1.0	-0.247	0.213	0.195	-0.145	0.0
Dummy - Covid	0.07	0.381	-0.442	0.07	-0.247	1.0	-0.602	-0.626	0.268	0.134
ROA	-0.141	-0.203	0.586	0.292	0.213	-0.602	1.0	0.842	0.174	-0.002
Return on Equity	-0.135	-0.402	0.644	0.335	0.195	-0.626	0.842	1.0	0.236	-0.186
Sharpe Ratio	0.046	0.055	0.338	0.878	-0.145	0.268	0.174	0.236	1.0	-0.288
Dividends Yield	0.173	0.14	-0.301	-0.304	0.0	0.134	-0.002	-0.186	-0.288	1.0

Source: Compiled by Author using SPSS

The ESG score exhibits a weak positive correlation with the log of market capitalisation, leverage ratio, and debt-to-equity ratio, all statistically significant at the 95% confidence level. However, ESG score shows no significant correlation with GDP growth or the All-Property Index return, indicating limited macroeconomic sensitivity. The log of market capitalisation is significantly correlated only with the ESG score, suggesting that larger REITs are more likely to engage in ESG disclosure. The leverage ratio has a weak negative correlation with GDP growth (95% confidence) and a strong positive correlation with the debt-to-equity ratio (99% confidence), reflecting internal capital structure alignment. Other relationships are statistically insignificant. Similarly, the debt-

to-equity ratio shows a weak negative correlation with GDP growth (95% confidence), but no significant correlation with the remaining variables. Finally, the All-Property Index return is moderately and positively correlated with GDP growth at a 99% confidence level, underscoring the dependence of property market performance on macroeconomic conditions.

Regression Results and Model Diagnostics

This section estimated four panel regression models to examine the influence of ESG disclosure on the investment performance of South African REITs, using ROA, ROE, Sharpe Ratio, and Dividend Yield as dependent variables. The models incorporated ESG Score as the independent variable, with macroeconomic and firm-specific controls, including a COVID-19 dummy.

The model was estimated with ROA as the dependent variable and ESG Disclosure Score as the independent variable. The other variables are selected as constant variables. The table below illustrates the goodness of fit of the model.

Table 13: Adjusted R square results - ROA

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	0.755	0.570	0.517	0.06335	2.004

The ROA model achieved an adjusted R² of 51.7%, indicating a moderate model fit. The F-test result (F = 10.822, p < 0.001) confirms joint significance of the predictors.

The table below illustrates the F-test and the level of significance.

Table 14: F-test - ROA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	0.261	6	0.043	10.822	<0.001
	Residual	0.197	49	0.004		
	Total	0.457	55			

Source: Compiled by Author using SPSS

The F-test result (F = 10.822, p < 0.01) confirms that the independent and control variables are jointly significant in predicting ROA. Combined with an adjusted R² of 51.7%, this indicates a moderate model fit, justifying further interpretation of the regression results.

The table below illustrates the results of the model, with ROA as the dependent variable.

Table 15: Regression results - ROA

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95,0% Confidence Interval for B		Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	-0.385	0.283		-1.360	0.180	-0.955	0.184		
ESG Score	-0.234	0.098	-0.260	-2.374	0.022	-0.432	-0.036	0.731	1.367
GDP Growth rate	1.767	0.780	0.303	2.267	0.028	0.201	3.334	0.490	2.042
Covid-19 Dummy	-0.103	0.025	-0.492	-4.125	<0.001	-0.153	-0.053	0.618	1.619
Log Market Cap	0.020	0.012	0.181	1.654	0.105	-0.004	0.045	0.731	1.368
All-Property Index Return	0.102	0.060	0.204	1.705	0.094	-0.018	0.221	0.615	1.625
Debt-to-equity ratio	0.088	0.051	0.190	1.700	0.096	-0.016	0.191	0.703	1.423

Source: Compiled by Author using SPSS

The regression analysis identifies ESG disclosure ($p = 0.022$) and GDP growth rate ($p = 0.028$) as significant predictors of ROA at the 95% confidence level, with respective t-statistics of -2.374 and 2.267. The Covid-19 dummy is highly significant at the 99% confidence level ($p < 0.001$; $t = -4.125$), further affirming its explanatory power. Conversely, market capitalisation ($p = 0.105$), All-Property Index return ($p = 0.094$), and debt-to-equity ratio ($p = 0.096$) are statistically insignificant, offering weak support for explaining ROA variability. All VIF values are under 5, indicating no multicollinearity concerns.

The ROE model was estimated using ESG disclosure as the main independent variable, alongside selected control variables. The adjusted R^2 of 57.1% indicates a moderate fit, suggesting the model explains over half of the variation in return on equity across South African REITs.

Table 16: Adjusted R square results – ROE

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	0.786	0.618	0.571	0.07632	2.129

Source: Compiled by Author using SPSS

The table below illustrates the F-test to indicate whether the model can significantly explain the dependent variable.

Table 17: F-test – ROE

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	0.462	6	0.077	13.214	<0.001
	Residual	0.285	49	0.006		
	Total	0.747	55			

Source: Compiled by Author using SPSS

The F-statistic of 13.214, significant at the 1% level, confirms that the independent and control variables are jointly significant in explaining ROE. Given the strong model fit and significance, further interpretation of the regression results is warranted.

The table below illustrates the results of the model, with ROE as the dependent variable.

Table 4.18: Regression results – ROE

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	-0.036	0.342		-0.107	0.916	-0.723	0.650		
ESG Score	-0.170	0.119	-0.148	-1.429	0.159	-0.408	0.069	0.731	1.367
GDP growth rate	2.310	0.939	0.310	2.460	0.017	0.423	4.197	0.490	2.042
Covid-19 Dummy	-0.119	0.030	-0.445	-3.964	<0.001	-0.179	-0.059	0.618	1.619
Log Market Cap	0.009	0.015	0.065	0.633	0.530	-0.020	0.039	0.731	1.368
All-Property Index Return	0.139	0.072	0.218	1.937	0.058	-0.005	0.283	0.615	1.625
Debt-to-equity ratio	-0.049	0.062	-0.084	-0.798	0.429	-0.174	0.075	0.703	1.423

Source: Compiled by Author using SPSS

The regression results reveal that only the GDP growth rate ($p = 0.017$) and the Covid-19 dummy variable ($p < 0.001$) are significant predictors of ROE at the 1% confidence level. In contrast, the ESG score ($p = 0.159$), market capitalisation ($p = 0.530$), All-Property Index return ($p = 0.058$), and debt-to-equity ratio ($p = 0.429$) show no statistical significance, offering limited explanatory power for ROE variability. Additionally, all VIF values fall below the threshold of 5, indicating no multicollinearity concerns among the independent variables.

Sharpe Ratio

The Sharpe ratio model, a widely accepted measure of investment performance, was estimated using ESG disclosure as the independent variable alongside selected control variables. The table below presents the model's goodness-of-fit statistics.

Table 19: Adjusted R square results - Sharpe Ratio

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	0.907	0.823	0.802	0.42331	2.044

Source: Compiled by Author using SPSS

The model's adjusted R² of 0.802 indicates that 80.2% of the variation in the Sharpe ratio is explained by the independent and control variables, reflecting a strong model fit. This is further supported by the F-statistic, confirming the model's overall significance in explaining Sharpe ratio performance.

Table 20: F-test results - Sharpe Ratio

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	40.919	6	6.820	38.060	<0.001
	Residual	8.780	49	.179		
	Total	49.700	55			

Source: Compiled by Author using SPSS

The F-statistic of 38.060, significant at the 99% confidence level, confirms that the ESG score and control variables are jointly significant in predicting the Sharpe ratio. Given the strong model fit and joint significance, the regression results can be meaningfully interpreted.

Table 21: Regression results - Sharpe Ratio

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	2.315	1.894		1.222	0.228	-1.492	6.121		
ESG Score	-.269	0.658	-0.029	-.409	0.684	-1.592	1.053	0.731	1.367
GDP growth rate	-1.760	5.209	-0.029	-.338	0.737	-12.228	8.709	0.490	2.042
Covid-19 Dummy	0.379	0.166	0.174	2.283	0.027	0.045	0.714	0.618	1.619
Log Market Cap	-0.099	0.081	-0.085	-1.214	0.230	-0.262	.065	0.731	1.368
Debt-to-equity ratio	-0.008	0.344	-0.002	-.025	0.981	-0.700	.683	0.703	1.423
All-Property Index Return	4.590	0.398	0.883	11.541	<0.001	3.791	5.390	0.615	1.625

Source: Compiled by Author using SPSS

The model results show that the All-Property Index Return is a strong predictor of the Sharpe ratio at the 99% confidence level ($p < 0.001$; $t = 11.541$), while the Covid-19 dummy is also statistically

significant at the 95% level ($p = 0.027$; $t = 2.283$). These are the only two variables with a significant effect on the Sharpe ratio. The ESG disclosure score, used as the independent variable, is statistically insignificant ($p = 0.684$; $t = -0.409$), indicating weak explanatory power for investment performance. Similarly, GDP growth rate ($p = 0.737$; $t = -0.338$), log of market capitalisation ($p = 0.230$; $t = -1.214$), and debt-to-equity ratio ($p = 0.981$; $t = -0.025$) show no significant impact. All VIF values are below the threshold of 5, suggesting no multicollinearity concerns among the explanatory variables.

Dividends Yield

The dividends yield model was estimated using ESG disclosure score as the primary independent variable, with GDP growth, Covid-19 dummy, log of market capitalisation, debt-to-equity ratio, and All-Property Index Return as control variables. The adjusted R-squared value is 0.066, indicating that only 6.6% of the variability in dividends yield is explained by the model. This reflects a very weak goodness of fit and suggests that the explanatory power of the model is limited in the context of dividend performance.

Table 22: Adjusted R square results – Dividends Yield

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	0.410	0.168	0.066	0.03405	1.391

Source: Compiled by Author using SPSS

To further assess the validity of the model, the F-test was conducted. The F-statistic is 1.649 with a p-value of 0.154, indicating that the model is not statistically significant at either the 95% or 99% confidence level. This suggests that the ESG score and control variables do not jointly explain variations in dividends yield.

Table 23: F-test results - Dividends Yield

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	0.011	6	0.002	1.649	0.154
	Residual	0.057	49	0.001		
	Total	0.068	55			

Source: Compiled by Author using SPSS

In order to further evaluate the insignificance of estimated model, the t-test was analysed. The table below illustrates the results of the t-test.

Table 24: Regression results - Dividends Yield

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95,0% Confidence Interval for B		Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	0.088	0.152		0.580	0.564	-0.218	0.395		
ESG Score	0.076	0.053	0.218	1.432	0.159	-0.031	0.182	0.731	1.367
Annual GDP	-0.340	0.419	-0.151	-0.811	0.421	-1.182	0.502	0.490	2.042
Covid-19 Dummy	0.005	0.013	0.061	0.367	0.715	-0.022	0.032	0.618	1.619
Log Market Cap	-0.002	0.007	-0.037	-0.243	0.809	-0.015	0.012	0.731	1.368
Debt-to-equity ratio	0.000	0.028	-0.001	-0.007	0.995	-0.056	0.055	0.703	1.423
All-Property Index Return	-0.049	0.032	-0.253	-1.523	.134	-0.113	0.016	.615	1.625

Source: Compiled by Author using SPSS

The results show that all explanatory variables in the dividends yield model—including ESG score ($t = 1.432$, $p = 0.159$), log of market capitalisation ($t = -0.243$, $p = 0.809$), debt-to-equity ratio ($t = -0.007$, $p = 0.995$), GDP growth rate ($t = -0.811$, $p = 0.421$), All-Property Index return ($t = -1.523$, $p = 0.134$), and the Covid-19 dummy ($t = -0.811$, $p = 0.715$)—are statistically insignificant at both the 95% and 99% confidence levels. These results confirm that the model offers limited explanatory power in accounting for variations in dividends yield. Additionally, all VIF values are below the threshold of 5, indicating minimal risk of multicollinearity.

Model Residual Diagnostics

This section presents residual diagnostics for the four estimated models, focusing on tests for normality and autocorrelation. Histograms of the regression residuals are used to assess whether the residuals approximate a normal distribution.

Figure 6: Histograms of the residuals of regression models

Source: Compiled by Author using SPSS

To assess autocorrelation, the Durbin-Watson (d) test was applied across all four models. Values close to 2 indicate minimal autocorrelation. The ROA, ROE, and Sharpe ratio models produced d-values of 2.004, 2.129, and 2.044 respectively suggesting no significant autocorrelation. Although the dividends yield model yielded a lower d-value of 1.391, this still indicates only mild evidence of autocorrelation. Overall, the residual diagnostics confirm that the models adhere reasonably well to regression assumptions. The histograms suggest that residuals are approximately normally distributed, and scatterplots of residuals versus predicted values reveal no clear patterns, indicating homoscedasticity across all models.

Figure 7: Scatterplots of Residual against Predictable values

Source: Compiled by Author using SPSS

Scatterplots were used to assess whether the error terms exhibit homoscedasticity—a key assumption of OLS regression. The absence of any discernible pattern in the scatterplots across all models confirms that the residuals are homoscedastic, supporting the reliability of the regression results.

Conclusion

This study examined the impact of ESG disclosure on the investment performance of South African Real Estate Investment Trusts (REITs) listed on the Johannesburg Stock Exchange (JSE) over the period 2016–2024. As ESG integration continues to gain prominence globally, particularly in developed markets, this paper provides a crucial emerging market perspective where ESG adoption remains uneven and under-researched.

The findings revealed that ESG disclosure among South African REITs is still limited, with only 7 out of 27 REITs disclosure ESG scores on Bloomberg—approximately 26% of the market. Most REITs had average scores below 50%, especially in the Environmental and Social components, suggesting a skewed focus towards Governance. These results align with existing literature noting that governance remains the most disclosed ESG pillar in developing economies (Ellili, 2022). The

lag in environmental and social disclosure may reflect systemic challenges such as water scarcity, inequality, and legacy issues of social exclusion in South Africa.

To assess the financial implications of ESG disclosure, the study employed a robust panel data framework using four investment performance measures—Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), Sharpe Ratio, and Dividend Yield. Regression analyses showed mixed outcomes. ROA was significantly and negatively associated with ESG disclosure, suggesting that ESG integration may introduce short-term costs that weigh on operational efficiency. ROE demonstrated an inverse but statistically insignificant relationship with ESG scores, while both the Sharpe Ratio and Dividend Yield showed no significant associations.

These findings contrast with previous international studies (e.g., Chen & Xie, 2022; Almeyda & Darmansya, 2019) which found a positive relationship between ESG disclosure and financial performance, particularly in developed markets. This contrast may stem from differing investor expectations, regulatory maturity, and prevailing theoretical frameworks. South African REITs may still be shaped by shareholder-centric governance models, while ESG's full value remains unrealised in investor pricing behaviour—reflecting a misalignment between corporate ESG efforts and capital market responses.

The models demonstrated high internal validity, passing key diagnostic tests for autocorrelation, homoscedasticity, and multicollinearity. However, the Dividend Yield model lacked significance, reinforcing the notion that market-based metrics in this context are not yet sensitive to ESG transparency. Additionally, REITs with higher market capitalisations exhibited faster ESG adoption, possibly due to stronger resource capacities and pressure from institutional investors.

This study contributes to the growing body of literature exploring ESG-financial linkages in underrepresented regions and industries. It underscores the urgent need for a formal ESG disclosure framework tailored to the South African REIT sector. Such a framework could help standardise disclosure practices, drive capital flows toward more sustainable entities, and align investor incentives with long-term value creation.

Future research should extend this analysis to other emerging REIT markets and incorporate alternative performance measures. A cross-country comparative framework could enrich insights into how ESG disclosure maturity interacts with capital market structures and stakeholder expectations in diverse socio-economic settings.

Ultimately, this research advocates for more deliberate policy and industry collaboration to embed ESG as a value driver—not just a compliance tool—in the evolving investment landscape of Africa.

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Mining, environmental impacts and residential property values: A case of former mining townships in the Copperbelt Province of Zambia *Malekano Phiri*¹; *Nelly Chunda Mwango*²; and *Ephraim Kabunda Munshifwa*³

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Abstract

This study sought to investigate the effects of mining operations on residential property values in Nkana West and Nkana East in the city of Kitwe. It is largely based on lived-experiences and perceptions of communities in the two areas. It was premised on the observed deterioration of townships after mining operations in Copperbelt towns. The study thus provided a comprehensive analysis of the relationship between environmental factors, including ground vibrations, proximity to mining operations, pollution and waste management, and property values. It employed a mixed-methods comparative research approach whereby regression analysis was used for quantitative data and thematic analysis for qualitative data. The study found that residential property values in both areas were affected negatively by mining operations, with Nkana West more affected due to its close proximity. An important point for policy makers to note is that they should consider long term effects of mining operations on neighbouring communities in newly opened mining sites.

Key words: Mining; Environmental impacts; Residential Property Values; Kitwe

Introduction

Zambia's mining industry has historically played a pivotal role in shaping the socio-economic landscape of the Copperbelt region. However, while mining has contributed significantly to the nation's economy, its operations have had notable implications for residential properties. This is especially so as Zambia's major cities of Lusaka, Ndola and Kitwe face myriads of challenges related to urban growth, land use and environmental impacts (Munshifwa et al., 2021; Chileshe et al., 2023; Mwiinde and Munshifwa, 2024). Former mine townships in the Copperbelt Province are emblematic of the tension between industrial activity and residential well-being, after decades of mining operations. The proximity of mining operations to residential zones raises concerns about environmental degradation, infrastructure damage, and the resultant declining residential property values. This paper seeks to examine these effects through a case study of Nkana West and Nkana East, two former mine townships in the city of Kitwe, and a former hub of mining activities.

Mining activities have long been associated with environmental challenges that significantly impact residential property values, (Zhang and Chen, 2019; Cheng et al., 2020; Chen and Zhou, 2021; Jain et al., 2021; Zhao et al., 2022; Li et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2023). For instance, mining has been associated with what is called "acid rain", which results from the emission of sulphur dioxide (SO₂) and nitrogen oxides (NO_x) into the atmosphere during industrial processes such as ore smelting and fossil fuel combustion (Zhao et al., 2021). These emissions react with atmospheric moisture to form acidic precipitation, which gradually deteriorates buildings, corrodes

metal structures, and contaminates water sources, thereby affecting residential property values in the areas (Zhao et al., 2021).

This paper investigates the effect of mining activities on residential property values in two former mining residential areas of Nkana West and Nkana East, in Kitwe. Once thriving residential areas, they are now emblematic of the socio-economic challenges posed by proximity to large-scale mining operations. Ideally, residential properties in these areas should appreciate in value, supported by well-maintained infrastructure, minimal environmental hazards, and an overall enhancement of the quality of life for their inhabitants. Such a scenario would reflect a harmonious coexistence between industrial growth and urban development, ensuring sustainable living conditions for residents while fostering economic stability in the Copperbelt region. However, the current reality starkly contrasts with this ideal. Mining operations have introduced significant environmental, structural, and economic challenges, eroding the viability of Nkana West and Nkana East as residential communities.

After this introductory section, the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents a literature review on mining, environmental impacts and residential property values while Section 3 discusses the research methodology for the study. Section 4 presents the findings which are discussed in Section 4. Section 5 concludes the paper.

Mining, environmental impacts and residential property values: a literature Review

This paper was conceptualised from a hedonic pricing theory lens. Originally postulated by Rosen (1974), the theory argues that the market price of a good (property) is a function of its bundle of characteristics or attributes. Alternatively, it argues that house price is a sum of the values of its characteristics. These characteristics could include structural (design, age, size, etc), neighbourhood (social amenities, school quality, etc.) or environmental (air quality, noise level, proximity to industrial areas, etc.). Thus, over the years, a number of studies have applied the theory in the subareas of valuation and environmental impacts (Jain et al., 2019; Neelawala et al., 2013; Gonzalez et al., 2021; Jain et al., 2021).

As already noted, mining operations, despite their overall positive economic contributions, often have negative effects suffered by the hosting community. In other words, while the gains are often national and global, the costs are largely local and suffered by a few. For instance, mining operations are reported to trigger ground vibrations, emit gases in the atmosphere, spill acidic waste on land and into water bodies, and generally impact on the environment (Kumar and Li, 2020; Ahmed and Patel, 2021; Mwale and Chanda, 2021; Mkhize, 2020; Chileshe and Banda, 2021; Mwansa and Phiri, 2022; Chileshe et al., 2023). Mkhize (2020) reported of houses in South Africa located within two kilometres of active mines exhibiting foundation cracks, wall distortions, and occasional roof collapses.

A similar study by Chileshe and Banda (2021) in Kitwe also found that over 65% of surveyed houses displayed visible signs of damage, including diagonal cracks, shifted walls, and destabilised

roofs. The study employed seismic wave analysis and structural modelling to assess the correlation between mining activities and building damage. These effects were most pronounced in low-cost housing units constructed without adequate reinforcement to withstand ground vibrations. Mwansa and Phiri (2022), too, undertaking a similar study in Solwezi, found that households located within a one-kilometre radius of Kansanshi mine experienced up to 70% more structural issues compared to those farther away. Despite these findings, the focus of these studies were not on their further effects on the residential property values.

Air and water pollution caused by mining operations was another pervasive issue that has significant implications for residential property values near mining areas. Globally, studies have consistently shown that environmental degradation caused by mining activities diminishes the desirability of nearby residential areas, leading to a decline in property values (Mensah 2016; Gonzalez et al., 2021). For instance, a study in Peru's mining regions utilised hedonic pricing models to analyse property value trends and revealed that homes within a two-kilometre radius of mining operations experienced an average price reduction of 20% due to persistent air pollution and contaminated water sources (Gonzalez et al., 2021). These findings highlighted that environmental quality is a critical determinant of residential property values, influencing buyers' willingness to invest in such areas.

In Africa, the impact of mining pollution on property markets has been documented in countries such as Ghana, Zambia and South Africa (Mensah 2016; Mwale and Chanda, 2021; Banda and Phiri, 2022). For instance, Mensah (2016) reported that over 65% of residents perceived significant depreciation in their property values due to the contamination of nearby rivers and streams by cyanide and other mining by-products in the Tarkwa mining region. The combined effects of air and water pollution also have long-term socio-economic implications (Nachalwe, 2020; Chileshe et al., 2023; Mukuka and Tembo, 2023). For example, households in Kitwe reported spending more on healthcare due to respiratory and waterborne diseases linked to mining pollution, further straining household budgets and reducing disposable income for property investments (Chileshe et al., 2023). This financial burden, coupled with the perceived environmental risks, exacerbates the decline in property values, as fewer individuals are willing to purchase homes in these affected areas.

The proximity factor of residential areas to mining activities also has a significant impact on the desirability of properties, driven by environmental, social, and economic factors (Neelawala et al., 2013; Robert and Lee, 2021; Mwale and Banda, 2022). Globally, mining activities often create externalities such as noise, dust, vibrations, and pollution, which diminish the appeal of nearby residential properties. For instance, Neelawala et al., (2013) used hedonic pricing models to examine how property values change with distance from mining and smelting sites.

In Africa, the problem of air and water pollution is particularly pronounced in countries with high mining activity, such as South Africa and Ghana (Mkhize, 2020; Mensah and Okyere. 2014). For

instance, Mkhize (2020) revealed that 78% of residents near mines in Gauteng, South Africa, expressed dissatisfaction with their living environment, citing poor air quality and regular blasting-induced vibrations as major deterrents. Similarly, in Ghana’s Obuasi mining community, Mensah and Okyere (2014) showed that residents near mining operations were significantly more likely to consider relocating, driven by concerns over noise pollution and contamination of water sources.

Effective waste management practices are critical in mitigating the negative effects of mining operations on the liveability of residential areas (Banda et al., 2021; Nkosi and Mahlangu, 2021; Mwansa and Chanda, 2022; Mukuka et al., 2023). Globally, poor management of mining waste has been linked to declining environmental quality and increased health risks in communities. For instance, a study in Chile’s copper mining regions revealed that inadequate containment of tailings dams led to toxic leachate seeping into surrounding water bodies, causing a 25% decrease in water quality indices and forcing residents to rely on alternative, often costly, water sources (Gonzalez et al., 2021). The study further showed that contamination significantly reduced the liveability of nearby areas due to compromised access to clean water and heightened health risks.

The conceptual framework in Figure 1 captures the relationship between mining activities, environmental impacts and property value effects. For this paper, it is argued that the combination of air and water pollution, ground vibrations, close proximity to mining operations and inadequate mine waste management leads to a substantial decline in residential property values in former mining townships. Buyers and tenants tend to avoid areas with visible environmental degradation, increased health risks, and excessive property maintenance costs, further reducing demand for properties in such locations (Jain et al., 2021; Mulenga et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2022).

Figure 1: Conceptual framework of Mining activities, environmental impacts and property values

Source: Authors (2025)

Research method

This study sought to investigate the effects of mining activities on residential property values in Nkana West and Nkana East (Figure 2). It employed a mixed-methods research approach by integrating both quantitative and qualitative data. The research aimed to provide a comprehensive analysis of the relationship between environmental factors, including ground vibrations, pollution, proximity to mining operation and waste management and property values. The quantitative component involved structured questionnaires distributed to 120 residents across the two areas, while the qualitative aspect consisted of semi-structured interviews with 15 key informants, including government officials and real estate professionals. This mixed approach allowed the study to measure the extent of property devaluation from residents' lived experiences. The mixed-methods approach ensured validation of findings, aligning numerical trends with qualitative insights.

Nkana West and Nkana East were selected for their proximity to mining operations and their historical role as residential hubs for mining workers. These locations experience significant environmental impacts, making them ideal for assessing the broader implications of industrial activity on urban sustainability.

Nkana West, Kitwe

Nkana East, Kitwe

Figure 2: Map of Kitwe
Source: Google Maps (2024)

A cross-sectional research design was used, allowing the collection of data at a single point in time to provide insights into ongoing challenges. This approach helped establish a snapshot of property values in relation to environmental and socio-economic influences. The study utilised both primary and secondary data sources. Primary data were obtained through structured questionnaires and semi-structured interviews, offering firsthand insights from residents and key informants.

Secondary data included government reports, environmental assessments, academic journals, and real estate analyses, which provided broader context and validation for the findings. Triangulating these data sources ensure reliability and a well-rounded understanding of the research problem.

Quantitative data were processed using SPSS (version 27), with descriptive statistics like means and percentages summarizing respondents' perceptions. Inferential statistics, including regression analysis, identified relationships between environmental factors (such as ground vibrations and pollution) and residential property values. Qualitative data were analysed through thematic analysis, where responses were coded and categorized into key themes to highlight recurring patterns and insights regarding residents' experiences and market trends. Triangulation analysis, that is comparing patterns across surveys, interviews and observations, assisted in testing the reliability and validity of data collected.

Findings

Socio-economic characteristics: Understanding the demographic characteristics of respondents, such as gender, education level, residence duration, and employment status, is essential in contextualizing their perceptions of mining activities and their impact on residential property values. These factors influence how individuals assess environmental and economic challenges, shaping their perspectives on the desirability, liveability, and value of residential properties in Nkana West and Nkana East. As shown in Figure 3, the age distribution of respondents revealed a balanced mix across different age groups. In Nkana West, the largest proportion of respondents falls in the 51 years and above category (31.1%), followed closely by the 31–40 years group (27.8%). This indicates that a significant portion of the population has lived in the area long enough to observe changes in property values and environmental conditions caused by mining. Conversely, in Nkana East, the highest representation is in the 31–40 years group (28.9%), with a higher percentage of younger residents (22.2% aged 18–30 years) compared to Nkana West. This suggests that Nkana East is attracting a relatively younger demographic, which may be linked to different socio-economic dynamics, including employment opportunities and housing affordability.

Figure 3: Age Distribution of Respondents

Source: Authors (2025)

As shown in Figure 4, the gender distribution indicated a male-dominated respondent base in both areas, with 58.9% in Nkana West and 55.6% in Nkana East being male. This pattern suggests that men may have a greater influence in household decision-making, especially concerning property ownership and investment decisions. However, the notable presence of female respondents (42.5%) highlights women's active role in housing and environmental matters, which is critical for understanding the broader impacts of mining activities on family and community well-being.

Figure 4: Gender Distribution

Source: Authors (2025)

In terms of the education profile of respondents, Figure 5 indicates relatively high levels of education in both areas. In Nkana West, 28.9% hold postgraduate qualifications, followed by 25.6% with college/university education, which may influence their awareness and perspectives on mining-related environmental and economic issues. Similarly, Nkana East exhibits a comparable trend, with 28.3% having postgraduate qualifications and 25.0% holding a college/university degree. The presence of educated respondents suggests that opinions on property values and environmental degradation are likely based on informed assessments, enhancing the credibility of the responses.

Figure 5: Education Levels

Source: Authors (2025)

Figure 6 reveals the years of residence in the respective areas. The analysis indicates that a significant proportion of respondents in Nkana West (38.3%) have lived in the area for more than 10 years, compared to 30.0% in Nkana East. This suggests that long-term residents in Nkana West may have more extensive knowledge of the impact of mining activities on property values. Meanwhile, Nkana East has a higher percentage of newer residents (26.7% with less than one year of residence), which might indicate increased migration into the area due to relatively better environmental conditions or economic opportunities.

Figure 6: Years of Residence
Source: Authors (2025)

Ground vibrations. Table 1 below shows that ground vibrations were a concern for residents of Nkana West and Nkana East, with significant effects on residential property values in the two areas. For instance, 35.3% of respondents in Nkana West and 32.9% in Nkana East strongly agreed that ground vibrations caused depreciation in their properties, which is later reflected in market values. Many (49.9% strongly agreeing in Nkana West and 44.1% in Nkana East) pointed to structural damages caused by mining vibrations. This suggests that the majority of residents are experiencing visible cracks and deterioration in their buildings, which could be attributed to frequent exposure to tremors from blasting activities. Noise and discomfort from ground vibrations are also prevalent, as strongly agreed by 35.3% respondents in Nkana West and 31.4% in Nkana East. This reflects the intrusiveness of mining activities in daily life, where residents report disturbed sleep, stress, and overall discomfort due to frequent vibrations. This aligns with studies, such as Kumar and Li (2020), Mkhize (2020) and others, showing that prolonged exposure to ground tremors can contribute to stress-related illnesses and reduced quality of life. These vibrations are perceived as serious risks to the long-term integrity of their homes. The presence of visible damage over time suggested that houses may require frequent repairs, which added to the financial burden on homeowners. Ground vibrations are therefore seen as a notable economic impact, which is reflected in residential property values as potential buyers avoid areas prone to ground vibrations due to structural risks.

Table 1: Perceptions of Ground Vibrations

Statements	Nkana West			Nkana East		
	Strongly agreed	Mean	SD	Strongly agreed	Mean	SD
Ground vibrations from mining operations have caused structural damage to my property.	49.9%	3.74	1.489	44.1%	3.62	1.521
I frequently experience noise and discomfort due to mining-related ground vibrations.	35.3%	3.42	1.472	31.4%	3.30	1.496
Ground vibrations have negatively impacted my property's stability and durability.	48.3%	3.81	1.358	42.4%	3.67	1.389
Ground vibrations from mining activities have created safety concerns for my household.	57.0%	3.89	1.398	47.1%	3.75	1.421
My property's value has decreased due to ground vibrations in this area.	35.3%	3.62	1.482	32.9%	3.44	1.512

Source: Authors (2025)

Air and water pollution: Table 2 presents findings on the perceptions of residents' concerning air and water pollution by mining operations, with many linking it to depreciation in residential property values. For instance, 41.5% in Nkana West and 37.2% in Nkana East strongly agreed that air and water pollution had an economic effect on their properties as reflected in lower selling prices, especially in Nkana West. The most significant impact was observed in water contamination, where 53.3% in Nkana West strongly agreed that mining had negatively affected access to clean water. Those closest to mining tailings or effluent discharge experienced severe water pollution compared to those farther away. Similarly, air pollution was identified as a major factor reducing quality of life in the two areas, with 48.1% of respondents in Nkana West strongly agreeing and 39.8% in Nkana East. Many residents are directly affected, experiencing dust accumulation, respiratory issues, and general discomfort. The economic effects of pollution was thus evident, with 43.9% of respondents in Nkana West and 35.6% in Nkana East strongly agreeing that property desirability has decreased due to mining pollution. They indicated that pollution plays a role in limiting the demand for homes in the area, discouraging potential buyers.

Health risks, thus, remained a pressing concern, as strongly agreed 47.8% of respondents in Nkana West and 42.5% in Nkana East. This aligns with previous studies, such as Chileshe et al. (2023) and Mukuka and Tembo (2023) and others, indicating that even distant exposure to mining pollution can lead to long-term respiratory illnesses and waterborne diseases. This reinforces concerns over exposure to airborne pollutants and contaminated water sources, which are linked to respiratory diseases, skin conditions, and other health complications.

Table 2: Perceptions on Air and Water Pollution

Statements	Nkana West			Nkana East		
	Strongly agreed	Mean	SD	Strongly agreed	Mean	SD
Air pollution from mining activities has worsened the quality of life in this area.	48.1%	3.72	1.435	39.8%	3.52	1.470
Water contamination caused by mining has affected access to clean water for household use.	53.3%	3.77	1.510	45.7%	3.61	1.498
Pollution from mining operations has decreased the desirability of properties in this area.	43.9%	3.69	1.420	35.6%	3.47	1.438
I am concerned about health risks associated with air and water pollution from mining activities.	47.8%	3.81	1.389	42.5%	3.66	1.418
The presence of mining pollution has contributed to a decline in my property's value.	41.5%	3.72	1.396	37.2%	3.58	1.412

Source: Authors (2025)

Proximity to mining operations: Table 3 reveals heightened concerns on proximity to mining operations, and its link to desirability, noise pollution, and devaluation in residential property values. At least 49.3% of respondents in Nkana West and 43.3% strongly agreed that living near mining operations has made the area less desirable for residential purposes. The issue of noise and dust pollution from mining operations received the highest response, with 56.2% of respondents strongly agreeing in Nkana West and 51.9% in Nkana East. This indicates that environmental disturbances from mining activities significantly affected daily life. The economic consequences of proximity to mines are also evident, with 36.0% of respondents in Nkana West and 32.2% in Nkana East strongly agreeing that property values have declined due to mining activities. Safety concerns were a dominant theme in Nkana West, as 55.1% of respondents strongly agreed that living near mining operations has made the area less liveable. This underscores the significant risks associated with mining activities, including increased accidents, dust exposure, and unstable land conditions. Thus, many residents see relocating as an alternative strategy.

Table 3: Perceptions on Proximity to Mining Operations

Statements	Nkana West			Nkana East		
	Strongly agreed	Mean	SD	Strongly agreed	Mean	SD
Living close to mining operations has made this area less desirable for residential purposes.	49.3%	3.84	1.320	43.3%	3.72	1.340
Noise and dust from nearby mining operations have negatively impacted my quality of life.	56.2%	3.79	1.462	51.9%	3.69	1.470
Proximity to mining sites has reduced the market value of residential properties in this area.	36.0%	3.46	1.505	32.2%	3.38	1.500
Safety concerns due to mining operations have made this area less liveable.	55.1%	3.86	1.428	51.1%	3.74	1.433
I would consider relocating due to the challenges of living near mining operations.	40.9%	3.73	1.382	37.2%	3.64	1.380

Source: Authors (2025)

Waste generation and management: Mining operations are known to generate large amounts of waste, which if not properly managed, result in serious environmental impacts. Table 4 shows that the majority of respondents (53.1% in Nkana West and 51.3% in Nkana East) strongly agreed that mining waste was a serious concern in the two areas due to poor management practices by firms. This is perceptive to impacts on the environment, health, and residential property values. These findings underscore the significant and visible environmental harm caused by ineffective waste disposal. The health risks associated with mining waste were also widely acknowledged, with 44.4% strongly agreeing in Nkana West and 42.4% in Nkana East. The economic impact of waste mismanagement is evident in the perceived decline in property values in the two areas. s who strongly agreed, compared to 44.4% in Nkana West. These findings reinforce the effect of mining activities, residential property value impact, with 53.7% of respondents in Nkana West and 50.8% strongly agreeing that ineffective waste management had contributed to property devaluation.

Table 4: Perception on Waste Generation and Management

Statements	Nkana West			Nkana East		
	Strongly agreed	Mean	SD	Strongly agreed	Mean	SD
Poor waste management by mining companies has led to environmental degradation in this area.	53.1%	3.97	1.302	51,3%	3.91	1.312
Mining waste disposal has caused health risks for residents in this area.	44.4%	3.74	1.438	42.4%	3.69	1.452
Ineffective waste management has contributed to the decline in property value.	53.9%	3.94	1.308	50.8%	3.88	1.320
Dust from mining waste sites has negatively affected the air quality in my area	32.5%	3.39	1.387	30.9%	3.34	1.395
Mining companies have not implemented adequate measures to manage waste in this area.	53.7%	3.79	1.457	50.8%	3.74	1.462

Source: Authors (2025)

Perceptions on effects on residential property value: Table 5 captures the overall perceptions of residents on the effects of mining, environmental impacts and residential property values. These findings revealed substantial concerns in Nkana West regarding property devaluation due to mining-related environmental impacts. For instance, most respondents (30.5% and 34.6% in Nkana West compared to 29.2% and 31.7% in Nkana West), agreed or strongly agreed, respectively, that their residential property values had decreased due to environmental challenges. The relatively low proportion of disagreement (13.2% in Nkana West and ... Nkana East) suggested that this perception is widely shared, despite some variability, possibly influenced by property location or structural resilience. Table 5 further reinforced earlier findings with regards to proximity to mining operations and reduced property desirability, in turn impacting its market value. Pollution is also re-emphasised as an investment concern as prospective buyers are reluctant to invest in properties in the area. Thus, residents agreed that mining-related challenges made the two areas less liveable, ultimately hindering property value appreciation.

Table 5: Perceptions on impacts on Property Value

Statements	Nkana West			Nkana East		
	Strongly agreed	Mean	SD	Strongly agreed	Mean	SD
My property's market value has decreased due to environmental challenges caused by mining.	34.6%	3.67	1.382	28.4%	3.42	1.401
The desirability of residential properties in this area has declined due to proximity to mining activities.	44.5%	3.77	1.401	39.9%	3.62	1.395
Prospective buyers are reluctant to invest in properties in this area because of pollution concerns.	38.7%	3.78	1.375	36.2%	3.63	1.382
The overall liveability of this area has affected the appreciation of property values.	46.5%	3.81	1.336	42.6%	3.69	1.342
Environmental degradation from mining has caused long-term reductions in property values.	29.9%	3.36	1.365	24.7%	3.19	1.351

Source: Authors (2025)

Statistical interpretations of findings

Table 6 presents the statistical interpretation of resident's perceptions on residential property values, as dependent variables, with environmental effects, as independent variables. Results show that nearly half ($R^2 = 0.460$) of the variability in residential property values can be explained by the combined effects of ground vibrations, air and water pollution, proximity to mining operation and waste management practices. These findings underscore the importance of these environmental and operational factors in shaping perceptions of residents on property value.

Table 6: Regression Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.678 ^a	0.460	0.447	0.29011
a. Predictors: (Constant), Ground vibrations, Air and Water Pollution, Proximity to Mining Operation, Waste Management Practices				

Source: Authors (2025)

Regression coefficients, in Table 7, provide further insights into the individual contributions of each predictor to residential property values. Ground vibrations are a significant predictor, with a standardized beta coefficient of 0.288, indicating a moderate contribution to the model (t -value = 5.028 and a p -value = 0.000). Air and water pollution also exerted strongest influence, as indicated by the standardized coefficient beta of 0.430 (t -value = 7.517 and p -value = 0.000). This reveals the critical role air and water pollution plays in shaping perceptions on property values, reflecting the significant impact of environmental factors on marketability of properties. Proximity to mining operations had a smaller but statistically significant effect on property values, with a standardized coefficient beta of 0.129 (t -value = 2.242 and p -value = 0.026). The results revealed that differentials in proximity to mining sites pose challenges, which may not be immediately apparent to residents. Waste management practices also came out as strong influencers of property values, with a standardized beta value of 0.408 (t -value = 7.116 and p -value = 0.000). The findings highlight the importance of effective waste management in mitigating property value depreciation and fostering positive perceptions of environmental stewardship.

Table 7: Regression Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized B	Coefficients Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
1 (Constant)	1.652	0.233		7.077	< 0.001
Ground vibrations	0.154	0.031	0.288	5.028	< 0.001
Air and Water Pollution	0.271	0.036	0.430	7.517	< 0.001
Proximity to mining operations	0.077	0.035	0.129	2.242	0.026
Waste management	0.224	0.032	0.408	7.116	< 0.001

Source: Authors (2025)

Triangulation with Qualitative data

Quantitative findings were re-confirmed through in-depth interviews with key informant

Ground vibration: One resident remarked that “... *constant vibrations have weakened the foundation of my house, and I’m afraid it will not withstand another year*”. This underscores the physical impacts of ground vibrations on property integrity. Another resident commented that “*The tremors are not just annoying; they make us feel unsafe in our own homes.*”

Air and water pollution: One resident remarked that “*The roofs need frequent cleaning or replacement because the chemicals in the air corrode the materials.*” This demonstrated the economic burden placed on residents to repair or replace damaged infrastructure caused by airborne contaminants. The discolouration of the roof serves as a visible reminder of these ongoing

expenses. Another resident pointed out that *"My children often have coughs and breathing problems, which doctors say could be due to the poor air quality in our area."* Such sentiments, echoed by many participants, pointed to the dust and fumes from mining operations as a source of concern.

Proximity to mining operation: One participant remarked that *"It feels like we're living in a construction site that never ends."* Such comments reflect the relentless nature of mining-related disturbances and their impact on daily life. Safety concerns also featured prominently, with participants describing fears of accidents and hazardous conditions. One respondent pointed out that *"We worry about explosions or equipment malfunctions. It's always in the back of our minds."*

Waste management: Many residents voiced concerns about the health risks associated with waste sites like the slag dump. One resident stated that *"The air feels heavy, and we constantly worry about the dust and toxic substances we might be breathing in."* The slag dump also serves as a source of dust storms during windy periods, further affecting air quality. One respondent shared that *"Every time the wind picks up, the dust from the dump spreads everywhere, covering our homes and making it hard to keep our surroundings clean."*

Overall, the perception of residents of Nkana East and Nkana West was that mining activities have an effect on residential property values, with respondents describing significant depreciation in their assets. One participant stated that *"Our houses are worth nothing now. Who would want to live here?"* Pollution and environmental degradation were frequently cited as the main drivers of declining property values. Another respondent remarked that the *"... air and water pollution have made this area undesirable. Buyers are not interested."* Another mentioned that the *"... cracks in our walls make it impossible to sell the house. People are afraid to invest here"*. This highlights the interplay between environmental factors and marketability. Such comments reflect the economic consequences of mining-related environmental challenges. This underscores the role of perceived safety in property valuation.

Discussion

This paper investigated the effects of mining and its environmental impacts on residential property values in two former mining townships of Nkana West and Nkana East in Kitwe. The findings presented above revealed a clear disparity of these effects on residential property values. For instance, the severity of ground vibrations was more in Nkana West due to its close proximity to active mining operations and less in Nkana East. Thus, Nkana West experienced stronger and more frequent tremors, leading to higher concerns about structural damage, noise, and safety risks. In contrast, Nkana East also felt the tremors, although these were less severe. This study revealed that residential desirability was lower in Nkana West due to these concerns, including noise and dust pollution, which ultimately impacted market values. Overall, devaluation concerns were stronger in Nkana West compared to Nkana East.

These findings are supported by similar studies such as Ngoma et al. (2021), Mwansa et al. (2023) and Tembo et al. (2023). These environmental hazards have directly contributed to declining property values and heightened health risks for local populations.

Furthermore, infrastructure in these residential areas has suffered significant degradation. Roads, initially designed to accommodate local traffic, now bear the brunt of heavy mining machinery, resulting in potholes and frequent closures. Studies, such as Phiri and Banda, (2023) reported that over 45% of roads in Nkana West were in a state of disrepair, with no immediate plans for rehabilitation. Compounding these challenges is the issue of waste management. Mwansa et al. (2023) found that poor disposal of mining waste had led to the contamination of water sources, with 58% of boreholes in Nkana East said to be contaminated with heavy metals such as lead and cadmium, making the water unsafe for human consumption. The compound effect of all these factors is depreciation in market values as the areas become unattractive.

Conclusion

This paper investigates the impacts of mining operations on the environment and its concomitant effects on residential property values in Nkana East and Nkana West in Kitwe. The paper isolated ground vibrations, pollution, proximity to operations and waste generation and management as key factors affecting residential property values. Overall, the paper concludes that mining operations have long term negative effects on neighbouring residential communities. This paper isolated residential property values as one variable. Furthermore, the study highlights key concerns of communities living near mining operations. This is especially important for the government to note, as new mining areas are opened, such as in North-Western Province. For instance, the licensing process should not only be concerned with job creation and the contribution of mining to the overall state treasury. but should go beyond to factor in the micro effects on local communities. These are the ones that bear the long-term costs, even after mining operations have ceased, as is the case for Kitwe.

This study faced several limitations. Firstly, the sample size, though adequate for statistical analysis, may not fully capture the diversity of experiences across all mining-affected areas. Secondly, the reliance on self-reported data in qualitative responses introduces the possibility of bias. Thirdly, the study focused on a single geographical context, which may limit the generalisability of findings to other regions. Despite these limitations, the study provides valuable insights into the impact of mining activities on residential property values, forming a strong foundation for further research. Future research should explore the long-term impact of mining activities on property values, considering factors such as market recovery after environmental restoration. Studies should also focus on developing predictive models to estimate the economic costs of environmental degradation on residential properties. Comparative analyses of mining-affected areas with and without mitigation measures could provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of different strategies.

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Disclosure Statement

No potential conflict of interest.

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**Peer Reviewed*

Exploring Technology Adoption in Property Valuation Data Collection in South Africa *Rumbidzayi Taruvinga¹; Chioma Okoro¹; and Ntwanano Hlekane¹*

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Abstract

The lack of up-to-date and reliable data is a problem in property valuation, raising concerns about the current data collection methods. This study proposed using technology to mitigate these challenges and ensure more credible valuations in South Africa. The research investigated technology adoption in property valuation data collection, identifying current technologies and their influencing drivers. Drivers were identified through a literature review on technology adoption theories and data collection technologies in the built environment. A quantitative research approach was employed, and data were collected using a questionnaire survey distributed to valuers using a purposive sampling approach, yielding 103 responses. Data was analysed using descriptive statistics. Findings showed that mobile technology, geographical information systems, and the Internet of Things were the most frequently used technologies. Key drivers were also revealed, including enhanced efficiency, increased productivity, and the ability to use technology. Due to the limited sample size, a broader representation is recommended for future research, as well as an investigation into technology adoption in other phases of the valuation process. This study contributes to the theoretical framework on technology adoption in property valuation. It also provides valuable insights to guide valuers in integrating technology into data collection.

Key words: Property valuation; Technology adoption; Data collection; Valuers; South Africa

1. Introduction

Property valuation plays a significant role in the real estate market as it is performed for various purposes such as financial reporting, mortgage, litigation, rent determination, rates assessments, expropriation, property investment, and for sale valuation (SAIV, 2025). However, the property valuation practice has been plagued by numerous valuation problems and challenges. Globally, common valuation problems have been identified, including valuation inaccuracies, variations, client influence, unethical practice by valuers, and inexperienced valuers (Abidoye et al., 2021). Valuation inaccuracies or variations, client influence, and the use of heuristics constitute the primary valuation challenges in developing countries. These issues are primarily attributed to limited and unreliable property data, largely due to the absence of centralised data systems, and further exacerbated by institutional corruption, inadequate land information management systems, and professional misconduct among valuers (Cheloti & Mooya, 2021). Lack of documented transactions, poor record keeping, and non-disclosure of transaction details have also been reported as major issues affecting access to reliable property market data in valuation practice (Gyamfi-Yeboah & Awuah, 2020).

Given these challenges, ensuring access to reliable and high-quality property market data is critically important. Such data is essential for credible valuations and forms the foundation of the valuation process (Mills, 2019; Simpson & Simpson, 2022). For this reason, valuers must gather accurate and reliable data on the subject property, comparable property, and market data (Mills, 2019). The demand for valuation credibility underscores the need to adopt more effective and systematic approaches to data collection. As a

result, the integration of technology into the property valuation data collection process has become increasingly vital.

Over the years, technology has been used to enhance data collection, resulting in more accurate valuation outcomes. Previous studies in the field of property valuation have explored the potential benefits of adopting innovative technologies (Akindele et al., 2021; Koeva et al., 2021; Mohammed & Bello, 2021; Ogunnowo et al., 2021). A study by Nena et al. (2022) highlighted that the implementation of technologies such as drones, robotics, and building information modelling (BIM) can facilitate several benefits, including safer, more accurate, and effective inspections, reduced resource requirements, improved time efficiency, and flexible and cost-effective inspections. Other benefits for using technology in the data collection process include more reliable data collection and increased productivity (Mohammed & Bello, 2021; Tan et al., 2022).

Although developed countries have adopted current approaches, which include innovative tools and advanced valuation methods, traditional methods are still being used in Australia (Abidoeye et al., 2021; Ullah et al., 2021) and Asia (Abidoeye et al., 2018). Developing countries are still behind in the use of technology for property valuations. In Rwanda, Malawi, Nigeria, Ghana, and South Africa, traditional methods such as physical property inspections are still being used (Boshoff & De Kock, 2013; Abidoeye & Chan, 2016; Koeva et al., 2021; Namangale & Chimalizeni, 2021). In South Africa, in terms of the Municipal Property Rates Act (MPRA) s45(2)(b), a municipal valuer may use 'comparative, analytical and other systems or techniques, including aerial photography and computer-assisted mass appraisal systems (CAMA) or techniques, when carrying out desktop valuations (research). The Act also reckons changes in technology, valuation systems, and methods. However, the way users perceive the benefit of using new technology depends on the extent to which they think technology use improves performance (Dowelani et al., 2022).

The depth of the data to be collected, the type of property to be valued, and the use of the property are determinants of the valuation approach selected (Koeva, 2021). For example, single property valuations require in-depth data compared to mass valuations (Grover, 2016). Other studies argue that perceived ease of use and usefulness, among other perceptions, influence the full adoption of technology in real estate (Namangale & Chimalizeni, 2021; Adegoke et al., 2022). Therefore, although studies exist on the use of technology, little is known about the areas where technology has been used and how valuers perceive its use in the valuation practice in South Africa.

There is limited research on the integration of innovative technologies for data collection in the valuation process in South Africa, revealing a significant gap in the published literature streamlining these technologies to ensure accurate and reliable data. Despite advancements in data collection tools, the practical implementation in property valuation lags. Therefore, this study investigated the adoption of technology in property valuation data collection in South Africa. This study argues that adoption of technology is crucial for credible valuations, given that limited and unreliable data (Effiong, 2015; Abidoeye et al., 2021) has been shown to compromise valuation outcomes. To achieve the main objective, the study examined what technologies are predominantly used by valuers in the data collection process and what drives valuers to use technology.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Use of Technology in Property Valuation Data Collection Process

While technology may help address the problem of unreliable data and valuation inaccuracies in the valuation process, its adoption by valuers has been met with varied perspectives. Existing literature (Ullah

et al., 2018; Koeva et al., 2021; Mohammed & Bello, 2021; Ogunnowo et al., 2021; Nena et al., 2022) has examined various innovative data collection technologies, which are further reviewed in the following sections.

2.1.1 Mobile Technology

Mobile technology comprises various applications and software specifically developed for smartphones, tablets, and other mobile devices. Mobile technology can be utilised to advertise properties for sale, conduct virtual inspections, and perform valuations using software applications such as Google Apps, Virtual Inspection Apps, Argus Software, and other available software (Akeju et al., 2021). Another form of mobile device, a handheld GPS, has also been used by valuers during site visits to collect data (Koeva et al., 2021).

2.1.2 Wearable Technology

Wearable technologies are electronic devices used for data collection that can be worn, such as smartwatches, eyewear, walkie-talkies, and helmets. In real estate, these technologies can be implemented to track maintenance, detect faults, and provide visuals of building components (Ullah et al., 2018). During on-site visits, valuers can also use wearable technology to capture visuals of a property and its surroundings, enabling them to access data in real-time (Ullah et al., 2018).

2.1.3 Digital Camera (Photogrammetry) and Video Camera (Videogrammetry)

Photogrammetry can be used for collecting data on a property. Per Alaloul et al. (2022), “it is the generation of a 3D point cloud model, known as the as-built model, of any object from digital photographs”. On the other hand, videogrammetry is a technique that extracts features from video recordings, and it has proven to be effective in detecting damage and evaluating safety in various buildings (Omar & Nehdi, 2016). A video camera can be used for data capturing and can produce more accurate, quality, time-efficient, and cost-effective results (Omar & Nehdi, 2016). However, videogrammetry techniques have lower accuracy when compared with photogrammetry (Dai et al., 2013, cited in Alaloul et al., 2022).

2.1.4 Drones/ Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV)

An Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) has the highest potential for data collection compared to a digital camera and satellite (Koeva et al., 2021). According to Mohammed and Bello (2021), the use of drones offers a range of potential benefits, including improving the valuation process, simplifying property inspections, especially for high-rise buildings, and streamlining the measurement process. Drones can be used to capture aerial imagery, conduct surveys, and gather data on properties. Furthermore, Nena et al. (2022) reported that drones/UAVs were being used as inspection tools in construction.

2.1.5 Geographic Information System (GIS)

The use of GIS technology, which primarily relies on satellite imagery, enables valuers to gather property location data, geographical boundaries and to inspect the condition of the subject property. Saraf et al. (2024) suggest that the four main possible GIS applications in the valuation process are data visualisation, mass valuation, cloud application, and price prediction. In valuation, data visualisation assesses terrain factors, site suitability, and property information, and mass valuation streamlines large-scale property assessments. Cloud applications provide data storage and management, and price prediction models analyse the property surroundings amenities for valuations (Saraf et al., 2024).

2.1.6 3D Laser Scanner

Hand-held scanners and mobile laser scanners are disruptive data collection technologies that can be used in real estate (Ullah et al., 2018). Takin et al. (2017) argue that 3D hand-held scanners can capture interior space, measure interior rooms, while heavier scanners can be used to collect spatial data, create 3D maps and models, and offer a virtual experience to consumers. Valuers can collect scanned as-built drawings and images that show a realistic layout of the subject property, providing more credible and reliable property information (Ullah et al., 2018).

2.1.7 Cloud Computing

Cloud computing provides solutions for data storage, access, and processing over the internet, unlike a traditional desktop computer and hard drive (Ullah et al., 2018). Valuers can store and analyse information through cloud storage, offering a secure and cost-effective virtual platform, enhancing the valuation process (Mohammed & Bello, 2021). Saraf et al. (2024) contend that cloud computing applications in other technologies, such as GIS, also provide data storage and computing capabilities.

2.1.8 Internet of Things (IoT)

According to Maqbool et al. (2022), the IoT is a system of devices that are connected and communicate together using the internet or a private network. The IoT system comprises four elements: sensors, a user interface, an internet connection, and information handling (Akindele et al., 2021). Therefore, IoT-based applications or devices, such as maintenance and monitoring systems, can be installed in buildings to collect data. These buildings, also referred to as smart buildings, are an example of how IoT can be applied for purposes of property management and valuation, by connecting sensors to walls, doors, or the roof to gather data from the building and send it to a server where the valuers can access it remotely (Mohammed & Bello, 2021).

2.1.9 Virtual (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR)

Virtual reality devices are computer-generated, interactive, real-time 3D simulators, whereas AR uses cameras and sensors to combine physical surroundings and computer-generated content, creating a mixed reality (Okoro et al., 2023). Through image capture software, VR and AR enable a valuer to conduct remote assessments, interactive inspections, and viewings instead of physical site visits, revolutionising data collection methods (Saull et al., 2020). A virtual tour can offer a realistic view of the subject property, enabling valuers to inspect the property remotely without physically visiting the property (Miljkovic et al., 2023).

2.1.10 Artificial Intelligence (AI)

According to Saull et al. (2020) AI, such as machine learning image recognition software, can be used to extract and digitalise lease information from transaction documents, streamlining paperwork and speeding up real estate transactions. AI-powered real estate applications can also be used to automate property inspections, forecast market trends, and estimate property values, improving time efficiency, cost savings, and user experience (Miljkovic et al., 2023). Additionally, Abidoye and Chan (2016) argued that the use of AI valuation techniques can provide more reliable and accurate property valuation estimates.

2.1.11 Robotics

According to Wang and Luo (2019), robotics can be employed in building inspection to detect wall defects in construction. Robotic-based inspections are time-saving, cost-effective, and flexible. They also improve productivity and enhance inspection accuracy (Nena et al., 2022; Wang & Luo, 2019). Furthermore,

robotics is seen to transform the valuation profession into a more efficient and data-driven industry (Mohammed & Bello, 2021). Therefore, robotics can also be used to inspect the condition of a property for valuation purposes.

2.1.12 Building Information Modeling (BIM)

Building information modelling is a technology that provides in-depth information at each stage throughout the building's lifecycle (Jafary et al., 2022). BIM can also be used to automatically generate inspections (Nena et al., 2022) and can be applied in various domains in valuation, such as 3D visualisation and 3D modelling, providing detailed property information, and can be integrated into the cost approach-based valuation by providing the data needed to calculate the depreciated replacement cost (DRC). Jafary et al. (2022) argue that BIM can also be utilised when developing machine learning-based valuation models, and to assess how efficiently 3D factors extractable from BIM and GIS improve valuation accuracy.

2.2 Technology Adoption Theories

Technology adoption can be described as a user's willingness to use a particular innovation when performing a task (Oyetade et al., 2020). This is often seen as a form of user acceptance, which refers to the user's behavioural intention or willingness to use, purchase, or experiment with a product or service (Kelly et al., 2023). To fully understand the factors that influence technology adoption, this study identified key drivers from various theories.

2.2.1 Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA)

Taherdoost (2018) reported that TRA seeks to investigate an individual's information technology usage behaviour. The TRA consists of three primary cognitive components used to explain a user's behaviour, which are attitudes, social norms (beliefs), and behavioural intentions (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1977). Thus, the model suggests that valuers' intention to use technology is influenced by their attitude and social influences (Taherdoost, 2018) within the valuation industry.

2.2.2 Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB)

Similar to TRA, TPB identifies the same key factors that affect one's behaviour: behavioural intention and attitude, and subjective norm. Additionally, TPB includes perceived behavioural control. According to Lai (2017), perceived behavioural control refers to the restrictions that users perceive may limit their behaviour. Although the model acknowledges that the latter three factors affect behavioural intention, it is criticised because if the information technology is not accessible, then the user's attitude will not be relevant (Taherdoost, 2018). Another study by Okoro et al. (2023) argues that attitude and perceived behavioural control significantly influence the intention to use immersive technology. This suggests that if valuers feel confident in their capability to use a new technology, they are far more likely to intend to use it (Adegoke et al., 2022).

2.2.3 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The TAM, derived from the psychological theories of TRA and subsequently the TPB (Marangunić, & Granić, 2015), seeks to explain the key determinants of technology acceptance by users (Davis, 1989). Its five key components are perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, user satisfaction, behavioural intention to use, and actual use (Davis, 1989; Nnaji et al., 2023). Previous research in the built environment has applied the TAM core components to examine the drivers and barriers to the adoption of technology (Ullah et al., 2018).

TAM was subsequently extended to TAM 2, which incorporates some antecedents of perceived usefulness, including social influence (subjective norms) and cognitive beliefs (result demonstrability, job relevance, and output quality) (Oyetade et al., 2020). Furthermore, in TAM 3, perceived ease of use incorporates enjoyment, objective usability, computer self-efficacy, computer anxiety, computer playfulness, and perceptions of external control (Taherdoost, 2018; Venkatesh & Bala, 2008).

2.2.4 Social Cognitive Theory

Another technology adoption theory, the SCT, is based on behaviour, personal, and environmental factors (Taherdoost, 2018). The behaviour factor explores usage, performance, and adoption issues, whereas personal factors focus on personality, cognitive, and demographic characteristics, and the environmental factors focus on the external physical and social factors. Therefore, the SCT provides a framework to help us understand the reasons behind why valuers may adopt technology by considering actions, social influences, and external factors.

2.2.5 Theory of Interpersonal Behaviour (TIB)

The TIB primarily focuses on human behaviour, which is influenced by social and emotional factors. According to Taherdoost (2018), the primary factors that form intention in the TIB are emotions, social factors, and habits, whereas attitudes, personal beliefs, and social factors influence behaviour. The study highlights that individual characteristics and past experiences shape an individual's behaviour. Similarly, Abidoeye et al. (2018) opined that valuers in Hong Kong regularly adopted traditional methods of valuation as opposed to advanced methods, and this was mainly attributed to factors such as educational qualifications and experience.

2.2.6 Motivation Theories

Two models, Igbaria's Model (IM) and Motivational Model (MM), suggest that intrinsic and extrinsic motivation influence the decision to adopt technology. According to Taherdoost (2018) the motivational determinants to use a particular system are intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation. Extrinsic motivation refers to the belief that users will perform a task because they believe that by doing so, they can achieve valued outcomes, and intrinsic motivation refers to the belief that a user will perform the task because of the fulfilling process of performing that task. Igbaria's model (IM) describes perceived fun as an intrinsic motivator, whereas perceived usefulness is an example of an extrinsic motivator, which both have a significant influence on adoption (Taherdoost, 2018).

2.3 Empirical Drivers

A literature review identified drivers of technology adoption in the built environment. In a study in Australia, a developed country, Abidoeye et al. (2021) noted that the most effective drivers for adopting AI in valuation methods are professional bodies, close cooperation between AI valuation software firms, and property firms, easier access to market data, a valuer's personal decision (willingness) to try new technology, and more user-friendly software. Additionally, Abidoeye et al. (2021) noted that cooperation between AI software firms and property firms is an important driver, as software firms need to design software that meets the needs of users.

Conversely, in South Africa, van Wyk et al. (2024) found that the highly ranked drivers influencing the adoption of innovative technology were competition, globalisation, and good relations between firms and individuals, as well as between firms and external parties. According to van Wyk et al. (2024), companies were aware of the available technologies; however, they had limited knowledge of what they involve.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Research Approach

This study reviewed existing knowledge on technology adoption theories and technologies used for data collection in property valuation. A quantitative survey method was employed, using questionnaires to collect quantifiable data for descriptive statistics (Saunders et al., 2009), consistent with previous studies (Abidoye et al., 2021; Ullah et al., 2021; Oluwunmi & Agara, 2023).

3.2 Data Collection

The purposive sampling method was used to select valuers with specific traits relevant to the study objectives: candidate valuers, professional associated valuers, and professional valuers in South Africa, targeting those with property valuation experience (Champ, 2017). Respondents were identified from the South African Council of Property Valuers Profession (SACPVP) database, a statutory body with approximately 2 226 valuers registered at the time of the study (SACPVP, 2024). However, contact details were withheld due to data privacy (POPI Act, 2013).

Questionnaires were distributed to a minimum of 338 recipients through LinkedIn invitations, emails, and physical requests, the South African Institute of Valuers (SAIV) website, and the valuers' WhatsApp groups. Reminders were sent once every two weeks to encourage participation in the study. The data collection process spanned over four months, resulting in 104 questionnaires being completed. After review, 1 questionnaire was excluded due to multiple errors, and 103 responses were captured for data analysis. This aligns with similar studies, which reported response rates of 102 (Ullah et al., 2021), 76 (Oluwunmi & Agara, 2023), and 64 (Abidoye et al., 2021).

3.3 Data Analysis

The data was analysed using IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (IBM SPSS Statistics, version 28.0). Descriptive analysis, using frequencies and tables, provided an understanding of the central tendencies, variability, and distribution of the data (Pallant, 2016). Mean scores (MS) and standard deviation (SD) were used to analyse and rank the technologies, application areas, and drivers of technology adoption, consistent with a previous study by Abidoye et al. (2021).

3.4 Reliability and Validity

The questionnaire's reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, which scored 0.947 on the drivers, demonstrating adequate internal consistency and reliability (Hair et al., 2013). Additionally, content validity was established through a comprehensive literature review, and face validity through a review by the research supervisors, both of which confirmed that the questionnaire adequately measured the intended constructs (Saunders et al., 2009).

4. Findings and Discussion

Table 1 shows the demographics of the respondents, indicating their gender, qualification, professional membership, designation, experience, area of practice, valuation undertaken, and location. The majority of the respondents were male (57.28%), while 41.75% were female, and 0.97% chose not to disclose their gender. Table 1 also shows that most respondents hold a bachelor's (or honours) degree (47.63%), while 33.01% have a diploma (national and advanced), 20.39% a master's degree, and 0.97% a doctorate. This shows an improvement in academic qualification compared to Mooya's (2015) findings, which reported that most South African valuers did not have a university degree.

Table 1: Demography of the Respondents

Demographics	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	59	57.28
	Female	43	41.75
	Other	1	0.97
	Total		100.0
Qualification	Diploma	34	33.01
	Bachelor's Degree	47	45.63
	Master's Degree	21	20.39
	Doctoral Degree	1	0.97
	Total		100.0
Membership of professional bodies	South African Council for the Property Valuers Profession (SACPVP)	94	71.76
	Royal Institute of Chartered Surveyors (UK) (RICS)	16	12.21
	Other	21	16.03
	Total		100.0
Designation of Valuer	Candidate Valuer	44	42.72
	Professional Associated Valuer	20	19.42
	Professional Valuer	39	37.86
	Total		100.0
Valuer Experience	0-5 Years	47	45.63
	6-10 Years	16	15.53
	11-15 Years	13	12.62
	16 Years and above	27	26.21
	Total		100.0
Area of practice	Private Organisation	58	51.79
	Public/Government Institution	32	28.57
	Own private practice	22	19.64
	Total		100.0
Valuation type undertaken	Residential Property	91	24.14

Demographics	Category	Frequency	Percentage
	Commercial Property	89	23.61
	Industry Property	79	20.95
	Specialised Valuations	61	16.18
	Farm Valuations	57	15.12
	Total		100.0
Location/Province	Gauteng	66	34.92
	Western Cape	26	13.75
	Eastern Cape	19	10.05
	KwaZulu Natal	17	8.99
	Free State	16	8.47
	Limpopo	13	6.88
	Mpumalanga	12	6.35
	North West	11	5.82
	Northern Cape	9	4.76
	Total		100.0
Country	South Africa	98	95.15
	Other	5	4.85
	Total		100.0

Source: (Author's field survey, 2025)

Professionally, 71.76% are registered with SACPVP, 12.21% with the Royal Institute of Chartered Surveyors (UK) RICS, and 16.03% with other professional bodies. Multiple responses were recorded due to some having dual affiliations.

The respondents were primarily candidate valuers (42.72%), professional valuers (37.86%), and professional associated valuers (19.42%). Most valuers had 0 – 5 years of experience (45.63%), followed by 16+ years (26.21%), 6 – 10 years (15.53%), and 11 – 15 years (12.62%). Most respondents worked in private organisations (51.78%), followed by public/government institutions (28.57%), and private practice (19.64%). Furthermore, they performed various types of valuations, including residential (24.14%), commercial (23.61%), industrial (20.95%), specialized properties (16.18%), and farm (15.12%). These demographics confirm that the respondents possessed sufficient knowledge and experience, ensuring the reliability and validity of the data provided.

Geographically, many respondents conducted valuations across all nine provinces of South Africa. The highest concentration was in Gauteng (34.9%) followed by Western Cape (13.8%), Eastern Cape (1.01%),

KwaZulu-Natal (9%), Free State (8.5%), Limpopo (6.9%), Mpumalanga (6.3%), North West (5.8%) and Northern Cape (4.8%). While 95.15% were practicing in South Africa, 4.85% were also practicing internationally (including Dubai, Zimbabwe, and Saudi Arabia). These comprehensive demographics are a representation of the South African valuer population, which increases the generalisability of the study and provides relevant insights applicable to the property valuation industry.

To determine the frequency of technology use by valuers for data collection, respondents scored items on a 5-point Likert scale, and the MS and SD values for each technology are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Ranking of technologies frequently used

Tools	Mean	Std. Dev	Rank
Mobile Technology	4.54	0.751	1
Geographic Information System (GIS)	4.40	0.953	2
Internet of Things	4.40	1.123	3
Digital Camera	3.36	1.514	4
Cloud Computing	3.00	1.621	5
Artificial Intelligence	2.11	1.298	6
Building information modelling (BIM)	2.05	1.263	7
Video Camera	2.03	1.216	8
3D Laser Scanner	2.03	1.317	9
Augmented Reality	1.66	1.025	10
Drones/UAV	1.61	1.031	11
Wearable Technology	1.60	1.032	12
Virtual Reality	1.59	0.954	13
Robotics	1.24	0.633	14

Source: (Author's field survey, 2025)

Table 2 shows that the most frequently used technologies were mobile technology (MS=4.54; SD=0.751), GIS (MS=4.40; SD=0.953), and IoT (MS=4.40; SD=1.123).

In contrast, the lowest scores were observed in robotics (MS=1.24; SD=0.633), VR (MS=1.59; SD=0.954), and wearable technology (MS=1.60; SD=1.032), suggesting infrequent use. Robotics, with the lowest mean score and standard deviation, was consistently rated lowest. Although this study found wearable

technology, VR, and robotics were the least used, previous studies (Wang & Luo, 2019; Saull et al., 2020; Nena et al., 2022) argue that integration of these technologies can improve the property inspection process.

The results illustrated in Table 3 show the adoption of identified data collection technologies in various areas.

Table 3: A comparative ranking of technology application areas based on usage

Area	Tools	Frequency	Percentage	Ranking
Property inspection	Mobile Technology	88	19.47	1
	Digital Camera	76	16.81	2
	Geographic Information System	61	13.50	3
	Video Camera	43	9.51	4
	Internet of Things	35	7.74	5
	3D Laser Scanner	28	6.19	6
	Drones/UAV	27	5.97	7
	Wearable Technology (smart watch, eyewear)	17	3.76	8
	Cloud Computing	17	3.76	8
	Building Information Modelling	16	3.54	9
	Artificial Intelligence	12	2.65	10
	Augmented Reality	11	2.43	11
	Virtual Reality	11	2.43	11
	Robotics	10	2.21	12
Total		100		
Property owner interviews	Mobile Technology	49	38.58	1
	Internet of Things	26	20.47	2
	Cloud Computing	11	8.66	3
	Geographic Information System	9	7.09	4
	Digital Camera	6	4.72	5
	Building Information Modelling	6	4.72	5
	Video Camera	5	3.94	6
	3D Laser Scanner	4	3.15	7
	Artificial Intelligence	4	3.15	7

Area	Tools	Frequency	Percentage	Ranking
	Augmented Reality	3	2.36	8
	Virtual Reality	3	2.36	8
	Robotics	1	0.79	9
	Wearable Technology	0	0	10
	Drones/UAV	0	0	10
	Total		100	
Market Area Research	Mobile Technology	74	20.0	1
	Geographic Information System	73	19.73	2
	Internet of Things	66	17.84	3
	Digital Camera	32	8.65	4
	Cloud Computing	31	8.38	5
	Artificial Intelligence	23	6.22	6
	Building Information Modelling	23	6.22	6
	Drones/UAV	13	3.51	7
	Video Camera	11	2.97	8
	Virtual Reality	8	2.16	9
	Wearable Technology	6	1.62	10
	Augmented Reality	4	1.08	11
	3D Laser Scanner	3	0.81	12
	Robotics	3	0.81	12
	Total		100.0	
Desktop Research	Mobile Technology	73	25.35	1
	Internet of Things	59	20.49	2
	Geographic Information System	57	19.79	3
	Cloud Computing	27	9.38	4
	Artificial Intelligence	21	7.29	5
	Building Information Modelling	17	5.90	6
	Digital Camera	9	3.13	7
	Video Camera	5	1.74	8
	Drones/UAV	5	1.74	8

Area	Tools	Frequency	Percentage	Ranking
	Wearable Technology	4	1.39	9
	Augmented Reality	4	1.39	9
	3D Laser Scanner	3	1.04	10
	Virtual Reality	3	1.04	10
	Robotics	1	0.35	11
	Total		100.0	

Source: (Author’s field survey, 2025)

In the application areas, mobile technology, digital cameras, and GIS were mostly used during property inspection. These findings are consistent with a previous study by Koeva et al. (2021), which highlighted that although UAVs were more effective for collecting data, digital cameras were still being used to take pictures of the subject property during field inspection in Rwanda. Valuers primarily used mobile technology, GIS, and IoT for market area research and desktop research. Furthermore, mobile technology, IoT, and cloud computing were mostly used for property owner interviews.

In another previous study, Alaloul et al. (2022) also found that traditional methods (manual observations and statistical methods) were the most adopted data collection methods for monitoring construction activity. Computer vision-based methods (including 3D models and object detection tools) and photogrammetry (cameras) were ranked second and third, respectively. Technologies such as GPS, smartphone sensors, Bluetooth, and accelerometers were less used; however, they formed part of mobile technology tools or applications, including laptops, mobile phones, and Bluetooth/Wi-Fi routers, which this study found as the most used data collection devices.

This current study’s findings also revealed that valuers often use AI for market and desktop research, data analysis, and the valuation report phase in the valuation process. This aligns with a recent study by Amidu et al. (2024), which recommended efficient use of multimodal tools (advanced AI systems) for report writing. Similarly, valuers also reported using mobile technology for AI assistance in report writing and sending or loading reports. GIS was used for town planning searches, wearable technology for AI assistance, and GPS location, and cloud computing for data storage.

The results in Table 4 illustrate the valuers’ opinion on the importance of drivers influencing data collection technology adoption.

Table 4: Drivers of Influencing Technology Adoption in Property Valuation

Drivers	Mean Score	Std. dev	Rank
Using technology enhances efficiency	4.42	0,880	1
Using technology will increase productivity	4.37	0,907	2

Drivers	Mean Score	Std. dev	Rank
Ability to use technology	4.31	0,929	3
Willingness/intention to adopt technology in valuation data collection	4.19	0,950	4
How easy/simple it is to use technologies	4.17	0,868	5
Price value (the benefits outweigh the cost)	4.13	0,915	6
Relative advantage compared to existing system (e.g. simplified work, improved quality data)	4.07	0,866	7
Job-fit technology (e.g. valuation specific innovative features)	4.07	0,932	8
The type of market area a valuer operates in (e.g. urban markets)	4.00	0,990	9
Free-trial use before purchase (e.g. test run on valuation software packages)	3.96	1,009	10
An individual's sense of control over the technology	3.95	0,912	11
High quality system	3.93	1,096	12
Availability of supportive technical resources	3.92	0,977	13
Trust in technology and its providers	3.89	0,938	14
Availability of supportive organisational structures (management support)	3.89	0,999	15
Competition (competitive pressure will influence firms to adopt innovative technology)	3.89	1,019	16
Actual number of times one uses technology	3.88	1,003	17
Globalisation (Increased interconnectedness of world economies)	3.82	0,926	18
Close cooperation with technology providers	3.80	1,032	19

Drivers	Mean Score	Std. dev	Rank
Product/System demonstration (e.g. suppliers can provide free demo sessions on how to operate new technologies)	3.78	1,028	20
Collaboration with professional regulatory bodies (SACPVP and RICS)	3.71	1.210	21
The enjoyment derived from using technology	3.65	1.109	22
Societal pressure or influence to use technology	3.59	0,964	23
Playful use of technology (e.g. immersive technology such as augmented and virtual reality)	3.17	1,014	24

Source: (Author’s field survey, 2025)

The study found that the three highest-ranked drivers were “using technology enhances efficiency” (MS=4.42; SD=0.880), “using technology will increase productivity” (MS=4.37; SD=0.907), and “ability to use technology” (MS=4.31; SD=0.929). This suggests there is a strong belief that technological benefits and individual factors, such as the ability to use technology, are the most important drivers for technology adoption. In contrast, van Wyk et al. (2024) found that the top drivers in the South African construction industry were globalisation, competition, procurement processes, and a firm’s relationship with both individuals and external parties, whereas, in this study, these drivers were ranked lower.

Additionally, the study found that “playful use of technology” (MS=3.17; SD=1.014) was the lowest-ranked driver, followed by “societal pressure or influence to use technology” (MS=3.59; SD=0.964) and “enjoyment derived from using technology” (MS=3.65; SD=1.109). While these drivers are not perceived as primary drivers for the adoption of technology in the property valuation data collection, all the identified drivers are considered significantly important, as evidenced by the consistently moderate to high mean score values. A recent study by Marikyan et al. (2023) asserts that social influence, perceived playfulness, and enjoyment are significant predictors of technology acceptance.

5. Conclusion

This study explored the adoption of technology in property valuation data collection in South Africa, focusing on the drivers and technologies that can improve data quality and ultimately valuation outcomes. The study identified fourteen technologies and twenty-four drivers. The study found a widespread use of traditional technologies, including mobile technology, GIS, IoT, and digital cameras, but limited adoption of emerging technologies such as AI, BIM, 3D laser scanners, drones, AR, VR, and robotics. Notably, despite robotics being utilised in the construction industry, it has not been fully adopted in valuation. This suggests that emerging technologies may be less accessible, costly, or complex. Further research could explore the underlying barriers to low adoption rates of these technologies among valuers.

The study revealed that the primary drivers of technology adoption were enhanced efficiency, increased productivity, and the ability to use technology. While other factors were considered significant, they were deemed secondary; notably, playful use, social influence, and enjoyment were perceived to be less

influential in the adoption of technology. The findings suggest a strong focus on functional benefits and ease of use.

The interpretation of the study's findings should be approached with prudence, given the limitations of the sample size; a broader sample is recommended. The study further recommends future research on technology adoption in other phases of the valuation process and its impact on valuation outcomes. This study adds to the body of knowledge on the adoption of technology in property valuation. To promote adoption, this study recommends practical training workshops, product demonstrations by suppliers, and collaborations with higher education institutions and regulatory bodies to integrate practical sessions into the valuation curriculum.

Disclosure Statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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Abstract

Land boundary disputes remain one of Nigeria's most persistent governance and security challenges, often escalating into violence, displacement, and weakened inter-community relations. The Oyo–Ogun boundary dispute exemplifies the gaps in effective land administration and the failure of conflict resolution mechanisms. This study addresses the gap in empirical understanding of the specific socio-political, cultural, and governance drivers of interstate boundary conflicts in Nigeria. By focusing on Oyo–Ogun, the study provides context-specific insights that can guide both theory and practice in land governance. A descriptive survey research design was employed, drawing data from six affected boundary communities. The analysis combined descriptive statistics with Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to identify and group the most critical drivers of disputes. Descriptive findings showed that inheritance disputes, ownership conflicts, and boundary demarcation problems were the highest-ranked drivers of conflict across the study communities. PCA further grouped the underlying causes into four broad components: (1) governance and resource-use conflicts, (2) land allocation and management disputes, (3) boundary demarcation and family disagreements, and (4) cultural-historical narratives. The study concludes that disputes in Oyo–Ogun are not only products of weak governance and policy gaps but are also deeply rooted in cultural and historical contestations. Theoretically, this study extends the discourse on land governance and conflict theory by integrating institutional, socio-cultural, and historical perspectives. Practically, it highlights the need for multi-dimensional interventions: adoption of geospatial technologies for accurate demarcation, establishment of joint boundary management institutions, harmonization of land administration systems, and inclusion of traditional leaders in dispute resolution. These strategies are critical for policymakers, particularly the Nigerian government and National Boundary Commission, in designing sustainable approaches to land boundary conflict management.

Keywords: Land Boundary, Dispute, Interstate

1. Introduction

Land boundary disputes have been a recurring challenge in Nigeria since before independence, largely due to the economic and social importance of land resources, particularly those located along state boundaries (Bamidele & Idowu, 2023). These disputes often result in loss of lives, destruction of property, forced displacement, and disruption of socio-economic activities (Musa, 2020). Land boundaries, as Sajini (2021) observed, are human constructs shaped by the quest for self-determination and resource control. While intended to maintain order, they have frequently generated disputes, conflicts, and violence among communities.

In many parts of Nigeria, communities that once existed as large cohesive settlements have been fragmented into smaller entities due to colonial amalgamations and post-independence

administrative restructuring. These imposed boundaries often disregarded historical, cultural, and economic linkages, thereby sowing seeds of recurrent disputes (Sajini, 2021). As Calabar (2018) note, land disputes arise when competing interests, values, and aspirations clash in the struggle to access and control scarce land resources. Despite numerous governmental and institutional interventions, many boundary conflicts remain unresolved, underscoring the need for more context-specific investigations.

A prominent example is the long-standing interstate land boundary dispute between Oyo and Ogun States in Southwest Nigeria. These two states, which share cultural similarities and economic interdependence, continue to experience recurring tensions over contested boundary settlements. The dispute is significant because the affected areas are agriculturally productive, economically strategic, and demographically dense. Unlike national-level analyses that broadly examine land disputes across Nigeria, this study narrows its focus to Oyo and Ogun States to uncover localized drivers of boundary conflicts and their socio-economic implications.

This study is therefore justified on three grounds. First, boundary disputes between Oyo and Ogun States have direct consequences on land administration, agricultural productivity, and inter-communal relations. Second, the persistence of the conflict despite government interventions highlights a gap in context-specific research that could inform sustainable solutions. Third, the study contributes to the broader discourse on land governance by providing empirical evidence that can guide policymakers in designing more effective land administration systems at the state level.

Accordingly, the objective of this study is to examine the factors responsible for the interstate land boundary dispute between Oyo and Ogun States, Southwest Nigeria, with a view to providing insights that will improve land administration and promote conflict resolution.

The study seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the underlying factors driving land boundary disputes between Oyo and Ogun States?
2. What strategies can be recommended to mitigate and sustainably resolve land boundary disputes between the two states?

2. Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Review

Dispute/Boundary Dispute

Given the nature and characteristics of humanity, conflict or dispute is an essential part of human existence. It is as old as man and will always exist. In fact, despite its detrimental effects on the advancement of society, conflict or dispute is one of the fundamental tenets of humanity (Ekeke, 2024) and is a ubiquitous and complex aspect of human interaction that affects individuals, communities, businesses, and nations. Disputes arise when divergent interests, values, or

interpretations lead to disagreement, confrontation, or conflict. To understand disputes, one must examine their types, dynamics, and methods of resolution.

A dispute is fundamentally an argument or disagreement between two or more parties regarding opposing views or interests that cannot be resolved by mutual understanding or negotiation. Disputes can take many different forms, such as arguments or disagreements that are verbal, legal battles, or even violent conflicts. The nature of disputes can vary greatly depending on the circumstances, the parties involved, and the issues at hand (Menkel-Meadow, 2004).

Boundary disputes between states often stem from a multiplicity of interrelated factors that can be broadly categorized into political, historical, socio-cultural, economic, and administrative dimensions (Paasi, 1998). These factors represent the independent variables that explain the persistence and intensity of interstate land boundary conflicts, particularly in the Nigerian context. Understanding these determinants is crucial to unpacking the underlying causes of disputes such as the one between Oyo and Ogun States in Southwest Nigeria.

One of the most prominent factors responsible for interstate land boundary disputes is historical antecedents. Many boundaries in Nigeria, including those between Oyo and Ogun States, were inherited from colonial demarcations that did not adequately consider the realities of indigenous communities. The colonial practice of drawing arbitrary lines often ignored ethnic affiliations, cultural ties, and local administrative systems, thereby sowing seeds of conflict that have persisted in the post-independence era. These historical boundaries, which sometimes split communities or lumped them together without consultation, continue to fuel disagreements whenever questions of land ownership and jurisdiction arise (Abramson & Carter, 2016).

Closely linked to historical factors are socio-cultural factors. Nigeria's diverse ethnic composition often translates into disputes where communities on either side of a boundary share common heritage, language, and traditions (Omotosho, Ihekuna & Fakoya, 2020). Such communities may lay competing claims to land based on ancestral ownership or customary rights, disregarding the official boundaries recognized by government authorities. In Oyo and Ogun States, where the Yoruba ethnic identity is shared but fragmented into sub-groups with localized identities, socio-cultural attachments to land and territory have frequently shaped claims and counterclaims. Land is not merely an economic resource; it also carries symbolic and cultural value, making disputes over territory highly sensitive and emotionally charged.

Another factor that significantly influences interstate land disputes is the political dimension. Boundary conflicts are often exacerbated by political elites who exploit them to gain local support or advance broader political interests. Political actors may fuel community grievances, contest administrative boundary adjustments, or resist federal and state interventions that appear unfavorable to their constituencies. In some cases, political interference delays peaceful resolution, as leaders prioritize electoral advantage over long-term conflict management. The political factor is especially relevant in Southwest Nigeria where control of land translates into political influence, voter mobilization, and legitimacy in governance (Zhang et al., 2024).

Equally important are economic factors, particularly the struggle over natural resources and land-related revenues (Sietchiping, 2010). Land disputes are not just about demarcation; they also involve competition for fertile farmland, markets, mineral deposits, and revenue-generating opportunities. The economic value of land can drive communities and state governments to contest boundaries vigorously, especially in densely populated and agriculturally productive regions such

as Oyo and Ogun States. With land being a source of livelihood, food security, and local taxation, the economic stakes tied to land ownership intensify the struggle for territorial control.

Finally, administrative and institutional weaknesses represent a critical factor responsible for boundary disputes. Ineffective land governance systems, poor record-keeping, and overlapping jurisdictional authority often complicate efforts to resolve conflicts (Kochan, 1975). In Nigeria, agencies responsible for boundary management, such as the National Boundary Commission, frequently face bureaucratic bottlenecks, limited funding, and political resistance, which undermine their effectiveness (Oji & Mustapha, 2020). Similarly, inconsistencies in land tenure laws, coupled with inadequate community participation in boundary delineation processes, contribute to recurring disputes. The absence of effective conflict resolution mechanisms at the local level further aggravates the situation, allowing disputes to escalate into violent confrontations (Kansanga, Arku & Luginaah, 2019).

Interstate Land Boundary Disputes

Interstate land boundary disputes represent a major socio-political and economic challenge in many developing nations, and Nigeria is no exception (Otor, 2022). These disputes typically emerge from disagreements between two or more states over the precise delineation of territorial limits. Boundaries, though human constructs, hold significant implications for governance, social relations, and economic development, as they often determine the control and distribution of land resources. In the Nigerian context, boundary disputes are not only historical but have also persisted into the contemporary period, reflecting the interplay between colonial legacies, socio-cultural diversities, and the contest for resources. The dependent variable in this study, interstate land boundary disputes, thus refers to the incidence, recurrence, and intensity of land-related conflicts occurring between Oyo and Ogun States in Southwest Nigeria.

Theoretically, boundary disputes are rooted in competing claims over land ownership, usage rights, or territorial sovereignty. These conflicts are heightened in societies where land plays a central role in livelihoods, community identity, and state revenue generation. Scholars such as Kansanga, Arku & Luginaah (2019) argue that boundary conflicts often arise when interests, values, and aspirations between communities overlap within contested territories. In Southwest Nigeria, boundaries were largely demarcated without full consideration of ethnic affiliations and communal ties, resulting in ambiguous land ownership structures. This ambiguity has fueled recurring disputes, as communities and state actors continuously contest historical claims and legal boundaries. Consequently, interstate land boundary disputes are not isolated incidents but recurring outcomes of structural and institutional weaknesses in land administration.

At the practical level, the consequences of unresolved boundary disputes are far-reaching. First, they often result in violent clashes, leading to loss of lives, destruction of property, and displacement of populations. These social disruptions undermine community cohesion and erode trust in governmental institutions responsible for conflict resolution. Second, boundary disputes disrupt economic activities, particularly agriculture, trade, and small-scale enterprises that thrive in border communities. When farmers are denied access to land or markets due to insecurity, livelihoods are threatened, exacerbating poverty and fueling further grievances. Third, these disputes frequently strain intergovernmental relations, as states expend resources on litigation, security interventions, and negotiations rather than on development initiatives. In the case of Oyo and Ogun States, recurring conflicts along contested boundary lines have created a climate of mistrust that undermines cooperative governance in the region (Birhan, 2024).

Interstate land boundary disputes also have implications for broader national development. Nigeria's economic growth and stability are closely linked to equitable land administration and secure tenure systems. However, disputes create uncertainty, discourage investment, and weaken tenure security. As Uwakwe (2021) observes, boundary-related conflicts perpetuate instability, making land one of the most contested resources in Nigeria. Moreover, these disputes are not merely about territorial demarcation but symbolize deeper struggles over identity, autonomy, and access to scarce resources. Communities in Oyo and Ogun states often frame the disputes as existential struggles, which magnify tensions and complicate peaceful resolution. Thus, the persistence of boundary disputes is both a symptom and a driver of underdevelopment in affected regions.

It is important to emphasize that interstate boundary disputes are often perpetuated by weak institutional frameworks for conflict resolution. Although Nigeria has established mechanisms such as the National Boundary Commission (NBC) to manage disputes, bureaucratic inefficiencies, political interference, and limited local participation undermine the effectiveness of such institutions. For example, when adjudication processes fail to fully address the concerns of affected communities, parties resort to self-help measures, often escalating into violent confrontations. The inability of formal institutions to enforce binding resolutions thus sustains a cycle of disputes, making them more intractable. In the Oyo-Ogun case, the delay in clarifying and implementing agreed boundaries has prolonged hostilities and further entrenched mistrust between the two states (Nwosu, 2024).

From a socio-cultural perspective, boundary disputes are also fueled by strong attachments to ancestral land and heritage. Land is often seen not merely as an economic asset but as a symbol of identity and legacy passed from one generation to another. Therefore, when boundaries are contested, communities perceive it as a direct attack on their collective identity and survival. This explains why disputes are often met with strong resistance and why negotiations frequently stall. In Oyo and Ogun States, competing narratives of history and settlement patterns serve as the foundation for conflicting territorial claims, making reconciliation difficult. Such dynamics underscore the complexity of the dependent variable, as it embodies not only material struggles but also deep-seated emotional and cultural dimensions (Gwerevende, 2023).

Theoretical Underpinning

This study is anchored on Marxist theory of conflict and Pluralist theory of conflict, both of which provide analytical lenses for understanding interstate land boundary disputes.

The Marxist perspective views land disputes as a struggle over material resources and economic power. According to Marxist theory, land is a key means of production, and conflicts over boundaries often reflect deeper struggles between social classes, elites, and marginalized groups who compete for control of resources (Lachmann, 1990; Giddens & Held, 1982). Within the context of Oyo and Ogun States, the Marxist lens highlights how political elites, local landowners, and communities may mobilize around boundary disputes to assert dominance, secure economic opportunities, or control rents derived from land. This perspective suggests that the root causes of the interstate boundary disputes are not merely geographical or administrative, but deeply tied to economic interests, inequality, and contestation over resource control.

On the other hand, the Pluralist theory emphasizes the multiplicity of actors, interests, and values within society. Unlike the Marxist approach that foregrounds economic power, pluralism argues

that conflicts arise because diverse groups; ethnic communities, traditional rulers, local governments, and state authorities, have competing but legitimate claims and aspirations (Grillo, 1998; Jalali & Lipset, 1998). From this perspective, boundary disputes between Oyo and Ogun States can be understood as the outcome of competing demands among multiple stakeholders, each advancing their own political, cultural, or economic interests. The pluralist lens stresses the importance of negotiation, compromise, and institutional mechanisms in resolving such conflicts, since no single actor has a monopoly of power.

By integrating these two theoretical perspectives, the study benefits from a dual lens. While Marxism highlights the structural inequalities and economic dimensions underlying the disputes, pluralism draws attention to the diverse stakeholders and the need for inclusive governance mechanisms in conflict resolution. Together, they provide a holistic framework for analyzing the factors responsible for the Oyo–Ogun interstate land boundary dispute, offering both a structural and institutional explanation of its persistence and complexity.

Thus, this theoretical framework guides the study by framing land boundary disputes not only as resource-driven struggles but also as multi-actor competitions that require balanced management approaches. It also helps to interpret the literature and empirical findings, linking them to broader theoretical debates in conflict and land governance studies.

Empirical Review

Recent empirical work confirms that boundary conflicts in Nigeria are multi-causal, blending material interests with identity politics. In Oyo State, a mixed-methods study finds that land conflicts are driven by competing stakeholder interests; including customary owners, local elites, and state actors, alongside weak documentation and contestation over rents and livelihood space. The study further demonstrates how stakeholder beliefs and roles influence whether conflicts escalate or de-escalate (Shiyanbola, Todorovski & Zevenbergen, 2024). A follow-up analysis reveals that the effects of these conflicts extend beyond casualties to the erosion of trust, the souring of relationships, and the entrenchment of recurrent hostilities, reinforcing cycles of remobilisation around land disputes (Shiyanbola, Todorovski & Zevenbergen, 2024). Outside the Southwest, distributive-justice research in Nasarawa State shows that perceived inequities in access and adjudication of land rights intensify tensions, indicating that grievances about fairness are as consequential as absolute scarcity (Nwaneri, 2016). Large-scale regional analyses also link land and resource competition to violent communal disputes across West Africa, situating Nigerian cases within broader spatial patterns of conflict clustering (Adigun, 2023). These findings resonate with Marxist perspectives that emphasize the salience of resource control, land rents, and class-mediated access, while pluralist theory helps to explain why multiple legitimate claimants; customary authorities, local governments, state agencies, and farmer groups, produce institutional deadlock in the absence of inclusive mechanisms.

The socio-economic and governance costs of boundary disputes are consistently documented across studies. In Oyo State, the impacts include disrupted markets, constrained agricultural activities, and long-term relationship damage that fuels recurrence (Akinola, 2018). A qualitative study of Erinle–Offa in Kwara State shows that settlements often produce only “negative peace,” with periodic relapses into violence reflecting incomplete reconciliation and weak local peace infrastructures (Bamidele & Idowu, 2023). Broader Nigerian and Delta-focused assessments further link land and boundary disputes to lethal communal volatility and economic disruption, underscoring the destabilising role of such conflicts for development (Amenaghawon, 2016).

These outcomes align with Marxist interpretations of livelihood precarity and competition over the means of production, while the persistence of “negative peace” highlights the pluralist insight that diverse actors cannot sustain stability unless accommodated within durable institutional frameworks.

Policy responses have sought to address these disputes, though progress remains partial. The National Boundary Commission (NBC) reported resolving fifteen interstate disputes in 2023, signalling institutional capacity but also underscoring the scale of the backlog (Changullah, 2024). NBC’s own departmental brief highlights its research and policy analysis function to support evidence-based demarcation and dispute resolution, though uptake at sub-state levels remains uneven. Official communications from the Federal Ministry of Information and NBC further reaffirm reliance on legal instruments such as gazettes, decrees, and maps as the basis for interstate demarcation. While important, such legalistic measures are often insufficient without meaningful community participation. Micro-level studies propose hybrid arrangements combining traditional rulers, local committees, and civil society facilitation to shift contexts like Erinle–Offa from negative to positive peace (Bamidele & Idowu, 2023). In the Southwest, stakeholder-centred reforms, including clearer land records, participatory mapping, and accessible grievance-redress mechanisms, are emerging as promising pathways for reducing disputes (Akinola, 2018). Complementary policy evaluations also warn that strictly legal solutions, such as verdicts in international disputes like the Bakassi Peninsula case, often falter without robust political and social enforcement mechanisms, a lesson that carries direct relevance for Nigeria’s internal boundary disputes. From a theoretical standpoint, pluralism supports such multi-stakeholder, negotiated approaches to mitigation, while Marxism cautions that unless reforms address structural imbalances in tenure security and benefit-sharing, conflicts are likely to resurface (Abubakar, 2022).

Among the most relevant empirical studies for the Southwest are those of Shiyambola, Todorovski and Zevenbergen (2024), which document the causes, stakeholder dynamics, and impacts of land conflicts in Oyo State through mixed-methods analysis, offering actionable recommendations for management. While Erinle–Offa lies in Kwara rather than Oyo or Ogun, its boundary-dispute dynamics; customary authority involvement, episodic violence, and fragile reconciliation, are analogous to those along the Oyo–Ogun line, making its lessons transferable (Bamidele & Idowu, 2023). Policy baselines established by NBC outputs in 2023–2024 further provide an institutional context against which localised Oyo–Ogun disputes and possible remedies can be evaluated (Changullah, 2024).

Despite this growing body of evidence, significant gaps remain. Community-level and comparative data specifically focused on Oyo–Ogun interstate flashpoints are sparse, as most Oyo studies adopt a state-wide perspective without disaggregating local boundary disputes. The linkage between policy and practice also remains weak, with NBC’s reliance on legal instruments rarely matched by sustained participatory demarcation, grievance redress, or equitable benefit-sharing at border communities. Moreover, longitudinal impacts are under-measured; beyond event counts, few studies trace post-agreement social healing, livelihood recovery, or the risks of recurrence over time, as illustrated by the Erinle–Offa case of “negative peace.” Finally, theoretical integration is limited, as empirical studies seldom test how material incentives, emphasized by Marxism, interact with the multi-actor bargaining dynamics highlighted by pluralism to explain conflict persistence or resolution.

A focused study of the Oyo–Ogun interstate boundary therefore becomes necessary. By concentrating on this specific context, it contributes granular, community-level evidence to an under-researched area, bridging the gap between policy frameworks and lived realities. It also integrates Marxist and pluralist theoretical lenses to capture both the material and institutional dynamics of conflict. In practical terms, it proposes a context-sensitive mitigation framework centred on participatory mapping, tenure clarification, localized benefit-sharing, and the institutionalisation of joint boundary committees. Such a study contributes empirically by supplying detailed evidence from the Southwest, theoretically by showing how material interests and multi-actor negotiations jointly shape conflict trajectories, and practically by aligning community-based solutions with the current procedures of the NBC, thereby improving the prospects of sustainable peace.

3. Methodology

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study in order to systematically gather data from residents of selected border communities affected by land boundary disputes between Oyo and Ogun States. The study population comprised all adult residents of six identified communities where boundary disputes are recurrent: Ijilo, Bakatari, Ilugun, Moriwi, Bansa, and Eleso. According to preliminary reconnaissance visits, these communities have populations ranging from approximately 250 to 600 residents each, with farming and trading as the dominant occupations.

Purposive sampling was employed to select residents with direct knowledge and experience of the boundary disputes. This approach was justified because not all residents may have been directly involved in, or knowledgeable about, the disputes. Twenty respondents were selected from each of the six communities, based on their availability and willingness to participate, giving a total sample size of 120. While this sample does not represent the full numerical population of each community, it provides a cross-section of adult residents with relevant lived experiences and perspectives on the disputes.

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire designed by the researcher after reviewing prior literature on land and boundary disputes in Nigeria. The instrument covered four main domains: (1) demographic and socio-economic characteristics, (2) perceptions of causes of boundary disputes, (3) impacts of the disputes on livelihoods and social relations, and (4) mechanisms of conflict resolution. Items included both closed-ended questions (Likert-type and categorical) and open-ended questions to allow for nuanced responses. The questionnaire was pre-tested in a nearby but non-sample community (Onidundu) to check clarity, reliability, and face validity, and minor modifications were made accordingly.

The questionnaires were administered face-to-face by the researcher with the assistance of a trained research assistant who was fluent in Yoruba and English. This approach ensured inclusivity for less literate respondents and allowed clarifications to be provided during administration. Ethical considerations such as informed consent, confidentiality, and voluntary participation were observed throughout the process. Of the 120 questionnaires administered, 95 were retrieved and found usable, representing a 79.2% response rate. Data were coded and entered into SPSS (version 26) for analysis. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, and cross-tabulations) were used to summarise socio-demographic characteristics and response patterns, while qualitative data from

open-ended responses were analysed thematically to capture local perceptions and narratives on conflict dynamics.

Table 1 Numbers of questionnaires administered and retrieved

S/N	Communities	Purposive Sample
1	Bakatari	20
2	Ilugun	20
3	Ijilo	20
4	Moriwi	20
5	Bansa	20
6	Eleso	20
	Total	120

Field Survey, 2024

4. Results

This section of the paper is concerned with the results and findings that emanates from the survey.

Table 2 Numbers of questionnaires administered and retrieved

S/N	Community	Population Considered for the Study	Questionnaires Administered	Questionnaires Retrieved	Percentage of Questionnaires Retrieved
1	Bakatari	20	20	17	85%
2	Ilugun	20	20	13	65%
3	Ijilo	20	20	16	80%
4	Moriwi	20	20	17	85%
5	Bansa	20	20	18	90%
6	Eleso	20	20	14	70%
	Total	120	120	95	79.2%

Field Work, 2024

The six study communities recorded varying levels of questionnaire retrieval, as shown in Table 2. Response rates ranged from 65% in Ilugun to 90% in Bansa, reflecting both availability and willingness of participants. The overall retrieval rate of 79.2% is acceptable for community-based field surveys and provides sufficient data for analysis.

Table 3: Socio-demographic Characteristics of Respondents

		N	%
Sex	Male	62	65.3
	Female	33	34.7
Age	18-30years	16	16.8
	31-45 years	8	8.4
	46-59years	34	35.8
	60years & above	37	38.9
Marital Status	Single	16	16.8
	Divorced	6	6.3
	Married	49	51.6
	Widowed	24	25.3
Religion	Christian	53	55.8
	Islam	38	40.0
	Traditional Worshipper	4	4.2
Occupation	Farmer	41	43.2
	Trader	36	37.9
	Self-Employed	18	18.9
Education	Educated	74	77.9
	Not Educated	21	22.1
Level of Education	Primary	32	42.7
	Secondary	25	33.3
	Post-Secondary	18	24.0
Length of Stay in community	<=5years	21	22.1
	>5years	74	77.9
Household Size	<=5years	30	31.6
	>5years	65	68.4

Field Work, 2024

Table 3 presented demographic and socio-economic characteristics of the respondents. The majority of the respondents were male, comprising 62 (65.3%) respondents, while females were 33 (34.7%). In terms of age distribution, the largest group was those aged 60 years and above, accounting for 37 (38.9%) respondents, followed by the 46-59 years age group with 34 (35.8%)

respondents. Those aged 18-30 years were 16 (16.8%), and those aged 31-45 years were the smallest group, with 8 (8.4%). It then presupposes that across the communities, there are more male population than their female counterpart. This may largely be due to the fact that most men in rural communities of this nature are giving to agricultural farming, and while some may believe in the idea of an ancestry land and thereby limiting their migration and making them stay put for the rest of their lives in the land of their ancestors.

Marital status data revealed that most respondents were married, with 49 (51.6%) respondents, while 24 (25.3%) were widowed. Single respondents constituted 16 (16.8%), and the divorced group was the smallest at 6 (6.3%). In terms of religious affiliation, Christians formed the majority with 53 (55.8%), followed by Muslims 38 (40.0%). Traditional worshippers were the smallest group, accounting for 4 (4.2%). The reason that could be adjudged for this could be that divorce rate in the communities is not pronounced as we have in urban centres and among urban population. This could be the reason for the low divorce rate. Also, because of the age bracket of the respondents, it would not be out of place to discover that either of the spouses may have transitioned, hence, the reason for the high number of widowed respondents, and those who may have been married to their spouses in the traditional village custom accounted for the high number of folks who claimed they are married.

Occupation-wise, the largest group consisted of farmers, totalling 41 (43.2%). Traders followed closely with 36 (37.9%), while self-employed respondents accounted for 18 (18.9%). Regarding education, a significant majority of 74 (77.9%) were educated, whereas 21 (22.1%) were not educated. Among the educated, 32 (42.7%) had primary education, 25 (33.3%) had secondary education, and 18 (24.0%) had post-secondary education. It is not out of place to discover that most rural communities are engaged primarily in agricultural practices, hence, the reason for the high number that chooses farming activities. Also, traders usually sell in boundary communities selling their farming produce to boundary travellers and crossers. This could also be mostly, the trade of the women in the study area. Also, the most educated among the respondents as seen from the table have just primary education, which is education at the lowest level. Those who have secondary and post-secondary education when summed up are in the majority. But this does not negate the fact that those with just the primary education are in the majority.

Most respondents had resided in the community for more than 5 years, totalling 74 (77.9%), while 21 (22.1%) had lived there for 5 years or less. This means that the respondents would be in the know if there are or had been land dispute between their communities and that of the neighbouring state in the course of their stay in the village. Also, Household size data showed that 65 households (68.4%) had more than 5 members, whereas 30 households (31.6%) had 5 members or fewer. The reason for the household size being what it is might reflect cultural norms around family size and living arrangements, and could impact community resource needs and planning.

4.1 Awareness of land boundary dispute

The respondents were asked to about whether they are aware of land boundary disputes in the study area. It is pertinent to examine the level of their awareness before asking them what type of land boundary dispute it is, hence, this particular question. The result of the finding is presented in the Table below, and also depicted by the Pie Chart that follows it.

Table 4.4: Awareness of Land Boundary Disputes

	Frequency	Percent
Yes	83	87.4%
No	12	12.6%
Total	95	100.0

Field Work, 2024

Table 4 provided information on the awareness of land boundary disputes between the respondents' community and another one. 83 (87.4%) of the respondents said that they are aware of land boundary disputes in the communities that they reside with another one, while 12 (12.6%) said they are not aware of any land boundary dispute. The total number of respondents surveyed was 95 (100.0%), making this data comprehensive and reflective of the community's awareness level regarding land boundary issues. This finding is in tandem with the findings of Baywood, Fagbamigbe, Igbokwe, and Udo (2020) that shows that majority of their respondents were aware of one form of boundary dispute or the other between their community and other communities. The possible scenario for those who aren't aware of any land boundary dispute could be tilted toward those respondents who are probably less than five years old residing in the community. They may also be younger generations of residents who peradventure have not witnessed any of these conflicts happen in their lifetime. Hence, it can be inferred that respondents sampled had the requisite awareness and experience to make quality and valid contributions to research questions posed.

Figure 1: Proportion of respondents who were aware of land boundary disputes

4.2 Types of Land-related disputes in study community

The table lists different types of land disputes, each evaluated on a frequency scale: "Never," "Rarely," "Sometimes," "Often," and "Always." Each type of dispute is followed by the number (N) and percentage (%) of respondents for each category. The table also includes the mean (M) and standard deviation (SD) for each dispute type, indicating the average frequency and variability in responses.

Table 5: Types of Land Dispute

	Never N (%)	Rarely N (%)	Sometimes N (%)	Often N (%)	Always N (%)	M±SD
Inheritance Dispute	6 (6.3)	5 (5.3)	23 (24.2)	26 (27.4)	35 (36.8)	3.83±1.17
Ownership Dispute	5 (5.3)	7 (7.4)	15 (15.8)	40 (42.1)	28 (29.5)	3.83±1.1
Boundary Dispute	6 (6.3)	5 (5.3)	15 (15.8)	46 (48.4)	23 (24.2)	3.79±1.07
Land grabbing by “Omo Onile”	12 (12.6)	16 (16.8)	19 (20)	19 (20)	29 (30.5)	3.39±1.4
Ownership conflicts due to lack of land registration	3 (3.2)	11 (11.6)	31 (32.6)	35 (36.8)	15 (15.8)	3.51±1.4
Market evictions and distortion of local land market/values	13 (13.7)	21 (22.1)	23 (24.2)	18 (18.9)	20 (21.1)	3.12±1.34
Conflicts between human/cultural and natural use (flora and fauna)	12 (12.6)	22 (23.2)	28 (29.5)	18 (18.9)	15 (15.8)	3.02±1.25
Destruction of property	6 (6.3)	23 (24.2)	31 (32.6)	23 (24.2)	12 (12.6)	3.13±1.11
Ownership conflicts between state and private/common/collective owners	5 (5.3)	18 (18.9)	36 (37.9)	27 (28.4)	9 (9.5)	3.18±1.02
Multiple sales/allocations of land	7 (7.4)	26 (27.4)	23 (24.2)	31 (32.6)	8 (8.4)	3.07±1.11
Violent land acquisitions, incl. clashes and wars over land	10 (10.5)	23 (24.2)	34 (35.8)	17 (17.9)	11 (11.6)	2.96±1.15
Limited access to land due to discrimination by law, custom or practice	14 (14.7)	24 (25.3)	28 (29.5)	21 (22.1)	8 (8.4)	2.84±1.18
Evictions by land owners	13 (13.7)	21 (22.1)	35 (36.8)	17 (17.9)	9 (9.5)	2.87±1.15
Peaceful, informal land acquisitions without evictions	15 (15.8)	25 (26.3)	26 (27.4)	23 (24.2)	6 (6.3)	2.79±1.17
Illegal evictions by state officials acting without mandate	15 (15.8)	32 (33.7)	22 (23.2)	16 (16.8)	10 (10.5)	2.73±1.22
Illegal sales of state land	17 (17.9)	29 (30.5)	28 (29.5)	18 (18.9)	3 (3.2)	2.59±1.09
Disputes over the value of land	17 (17.9)	33 (34.7)	24 (25.3)	17 (17.9)	4 (4.2)	2.56±1.11

Land grabbing by high-ranking public officials	14 (14.7)	31 (32.6)	32 (33.7)	16 (16.8)	2 (2.1)	2.59±1.01
Disputes over the payment for using/buying land	23 (24.2)	32 (33.7)	27 (28.4)	10 (10.5)	3 (3.2)	2.35±1.06

Field Survey, 2024

Table 5 details the types of land disputes, categorized by their frequency of occurrence as indicated by the mean (M) and standard deviation (SD). The most common types of land disputes were inheritance disputes and ownership disputes, with both mean and standard deviation of 3.83 ± 1.17 and 3.83 ± 1.1 , respectively. This then mean that inheritance and ownership disputes over land is more pronounced in the communities surveyed than any other type of land dispute. With respect to inheritance dispute, this finding is in tandem with Azeez and Aluko (2019) study on the causes of land conflict in the forest reserves of Ondo state. These disputes often arise from unclear wills, inadequate legal frameworks, family conflicts, patriarchal inheritance systems, lack of awareness about inheritance rights, and discrepancies in land registration systems. Ownership issue on the hand, are commonly due to unclear land titles, fraudulent land sales, and historical land claims. Discrepancies in land registration systems and corruption exacerbate the problem. Boundary disputes followed closely with a mean of 3.79 ± 1.07 . These disputes arise from inaccurate or out-dated land surveys, conflicting land use practices, and lack of clear demarcation of land boundaries. Encroachment and urban expansion also contribute. It then presupposes that the communities under consideration witnesses boundary dispute, howbeit, not as frequent as inheritance and ownership disputes.

Land grabbing by “Omo Onile” had a mean of 3.39 ± 1.4 , while ownership conflicts due to lack of land registration had a mean of 3.51 ± 1.4 . Even though the practices of "Omo Onile" often involve illegal demands for money or property is more pronounced especially in urban areas undergoing rapid development, the findings however show their occurrence in rural communities cannot be ruled out as well. Usually and most of the times, weak legal enforcement and corruption enable such practices. Market evictions and distortion of local land market/values were also frequent, with a mean of 3.12 ± 1.34 , followed by conflicts between human/cultural and natural use (flora and fauna) with a mean of 3.02 ± 1.25 . Destruction of property disputes had a mean of 3.13 ± 1.11 , and ownership conflicts between state and private/common/collective owners were reported with a mean of 3.18 ± 1.02 . Multiple sales/allocations of land had a mean of 3.07 ± 1.11 .

Less common disputes were shown by the respondents to include violent land acquisitions, including clashes and wars over land, with a mean of 2.96 ± 1.15 , and limited access to land due to discrimination by law, custom, or practice, with a mean of 2.84 ± 1.18 . Evictions by landowners had a mean of 2.87 ± 1.15 , and peaceful, informal land acquisitions without evictions had a mean of 2.79 ± 1.17 . Illegal evictions by state officials acting without mandate had a mean of 2.73 ± 1.22 , while illegal sales of state land had a mean of 2.59 ± 1.09 . Disputes over the value of land had a mean of 2.56 ± 1.11 , and land grabbing by high-ranking public officials had a mean of 2.59 ± 1.01 . The least frequent disputes were over the payment for using/buying land, with a mean of 2.35 ± 1.06 .

4.3 Categories of Factors responsible for land boundary dispute in respondents’ communities

A factor analysis was carried out to evaluate the Factors responsible for land boundary disputes in the study communities.

A. Test of Data Suitability

To assess the suitability of the data for factor analysis, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure of Sampling Adequacy and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity were conducted (Table 6).

Table 6: KMO and Bartlett's Test

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Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.636
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	615.434
	df	153
	Sig.	.000
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Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure of Sampling Adequacy

With a numerical value of 0.636, this KMO score suggests a moderate level of sampling adequacy. In essence, it indicates that the variables under scrutiny may possess some intercorrelations, rendering them potentially suitable for further analysis through techniques like factor analysis.

Bartlett's Test of Sphericity

Bartlett's Test of Sphericity provides a complementary assessment, probing the hypothesis that the correlation matrix is an identity matrix, implying that variables are uncorrelated. The statistical evaluation yields an approximate ($\chi^2(153) = 615.434, p < .001$), denoting a highly significant departure from sphericity. In practical terms, this result suggests that the variables in the dataset are indeed correlated to a significant degree, validating the need for more sophisticated analytical approaches beyond simple correlation analysis.

Based on these assessments, the data is deemed suitable for factor analysis. The KMO value (0.636) indicates mediocre but acceptable sample adequacy, while Bartlett's Test of Sphericity ($\chi^2(153) = 615.434, p < .001$) strongly supports the factorability of the correlation matrix. Therefore, proceeding with factor analysis is appropriate and likely to yield meaningful insights.

Table 7: Pattern Matrix of factors loading

	Component			
	1	2	3	4
Poor political Governance	.827			
Agricultural product/Farmland encroachment	.687			
Loopholes in land management systems	.626			
Changes of Customary tenure	.567			

Resource Control	.546	
Family Rift	.375	
Multiple land allocations	.822	
Poor land governance	.714	
Ineffective land policies	.559	
States and traditional institution factor	.523	
Land acquisition for public use	.463	
Unsettled rift between communities over land	.716	
Land Encroachment	.661	
Inappropriate Boundary demarcation	.611	
Family disagreement	.592	
Cultural/Tradition differences	.858	
Historical Inaccuracy	.828	
Inconsistent and inaccurate surveys	.677	

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Promax with Kaiser Normalization.^a

a. Rotation converged in 9 iterations.

Figure 2: Scree plot showing the proportion of respondents Factors Loading and Components the Factors Analysis

Factor Names

Based on the factor loadings on the Principal Component Analysis (Table 8), the factors loaded into the data were (Table 4.9, Figure 4.4 & 4.5):

Figure 3: Radar Map showing scores distribution of factors responsible for land boundary dispute in respondents' communities.

1. Political Governance and Resource Use Conflicts
2. Land Allocation and Management Conflicts
3. Land Disputes and Conflicts
4. Cultural and Historical Factors in Land Use and Management

Factor 1: Political Governance and Resource Use Conflicts

This factor captures issues predominantly related to political governance and resource use. High loadings on this factor include: Poor political governance (.827), Agricultural product/farmland encroachment (.687), Loopholes in land management systems (.626), Changes of customary tenure (.567), and Resource control (.546). These variables highlight the broad spectrum of conflicts and disputes arising from political governance issues, including encroachment on agricultural land and natural resources, inadequate land management systems, and changes in customary tenure.

Factor 2: Land Allocation and Management Conflicts

This factor captures issues predominantly related to land allocation and management. High loadings on this factor include: Multiple land allocations (.822), Poor land governance (.714), Ineffective land policies (.559), States and traditional institution factor (.523), and Land acquisition for public use (.463). These variables highlight the broad spectrum of conflicts and disputes arising

from land allocation and management issues, including multiple allocations of the same land, inadequate land governance, and ineffective land policies.

Factor 3: Land Disputes and Conflicts

This factor captures issues predominantly related to land disputes and conflicts. High loadings on this factor include: Unsettled rift between communities over land (.716), Land encroachment (.661), inappropriate boundary demarcation (.611), and Family disagreement (.592). These variables highlight the broad spectrum of conflicts and disputes arising from land disputes and conflicts, including encroachment on other people's land, inappropriate boundary demarcation, and family disagreements over land. This finding corroborates the work of Okoli and Ukwuandu (2022) that communal conflicts is often both dynamic and opportunistic, feeding into the existing primordial and structural fault-lines to assume multiple complications.

Factor 4: Cultural and Historical Factors in Land Use and Management

This factor captures issues predominantly related to cultural and historical factors in land use and management. High loadings on this factor include: Cultural/tradition differences (.858), Historical inaccuracy (.828), and Inconsistent and inaccurate surveys (.677). These variables highlight the broad spectrum of conflicts and disputes arising from cultural and historical factors in land use and management, including differences in cultural and traditional practices, inaccuracies in historical records, and inconsistent and inaccurate surveys.

5. Discussion of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendation

The findings from this study revealed that land boundary disputes in the Oyo–Ogun axis are multi-dimensional, shaped by inheritance practices, ownership conflicts, weak governance systems, and cultural-historical differences.

From the descriptive analysis, the highest-ranked disputes were inheritance disputes (M=3.83) and ownership disputes (M=3.83), followed closely by boundary disputes (M=3.79). These results indicate that conflicts over inheritance and ownership are the most pronounced forms of land disputes in the study communities. This aligns with the findings of Azeez and Aluko (2019), who observed that inheritance disputes in Ondo State Forest reserves were often driven by inadequate legal frameworks, patriarchal systems, and family rifts. Similarly, ownership disputes mirror the conclusions of Adepoju, Audu & Adewoyin (2024), where unclear land titles and fraudulent sales were major sources of community land conflicts in Nigeria.

By contrast, the lowest-ranked disputes were those relating to payment for using/buying land (M=2.35), illegal sales of state land (M=2.59), and land grabbing by high-ranking officials (M=2.59). While these issues are critical at national and urban levels, their relatively lower frequency in the rural Oyo–Ogun boundary communities suggests that local disputes are less about state-level political manipulation and more about immediate livelihood, inheritance, and family ownership structures. This diverges from the findings of Orimaye et al. (2025), who argued that political elite capture often drives boundary conflicts in urbanizing regions.

The Principal Component Analysis (PCA) grouped the underlying causes into four distinct factors:

1. **Political Governance and Resource Use Conflicts:** driven by poor governance, farmland encroachment, loopholes in land management, and resource control. This supports Yusuf

(2025), who highlighted weak governance and political interference as persistent triggers of land disputes in Nigeria.

2. **Land Allocation and Management Conflicts:** explained by multiple land allocations, poor governance, and ineffective policies. This finding resonates with Adepoju, Audu & Adewoyin (2024), who emphasized the role of institutional weaknesses in perpetuating unclear and conflicting land claims.
3. **Land Disputes and Conflicts:** centered on boundary demarcation, land encroachment, and family disagreements. This corroborates Okoli and Ukwandu (2022), who stressed that communal conflicts often build on existing primordial and structural fault lines.
4. **Cultural and Historical Factors in Land Use:** shaped by cultural/traditional differences, historical inaccuracies, and inconsistent surveys. These findings reinforce earlier works such as Liman (2015), which stressed the deep-rooted nature of cultural and historical narratives in shaping Nigerian land disputes.

Conclusion

This study concludes that the persistence of land boundary disputes between Oyo and Ogun States is primarily driven by a combination of inheritance and ownership-related conflicts, weak land governance systems, and cultural-historical narratives. While inheritance and ownership disputes are the most prevalent, boundary demarcation issues and weak policy frameworks amplify tensions across communities. The PCA findings further reveal that disputes can be grouped into four categories: governance-resource conflicts, land allocation/management issues, land disputes, and cultural-historical factors.

Without effective intervention, such disputes will continue to undermine social cohesion, economic development, and inter-community relations in boundary zones. However, multi-dimensional approaches; technological (GIS mapping), institutional (joint boundary commissions), and socio-cultural (community engagement), offer a path toward sustainable peace and clarity in land governance.

Contribution of the Study

Theoretical Contribution: The study contributes to the literature on land governance and conflict theory by integrating socio-cultural and historical dimensions with governance and policy frameworks. It shows that land disputes cannot be explained solely by institutional weaknesses, but must also account for deep-rooted cultural and historical narratives.

Practical Contribution: For policymakers, especially the Nigerian government and the National Boundary Commission, the findings highlight the urgent need for:

1. Adoption of geospatial technologies for accurate boundary demarcation.
2. Strengthening of land administration systems to prevent multiple allocations and fraudulent sales.
3. Inclusion of traditional rulers and community leaders in mediation frameworks to enhance trust and legitimacy.

4. Joint socio-economic development projects in contested areas to reduce rivalry and foster cooperation.

Limitations of the Study

This study is not without limitations. First, the research is limited to six boundary communities between Oyo and Ogun States, which may restrict generalizability to other parts of Nigeria. Second, the study relied on self-reported data, which could be influenced by recall bias or social desirability bias. Third, while PCA provided meaningful groupings of factors, a larger sample size could yield even more robust factor structures.

Recommendations

For Stakeholders:

1. The governments of Oyo and Ogun States, in partnership with the National Boundary Commission, should establish a joint boundary management framework equipped with modern GIS and cadastral mapping systems.
2. Harmonization of land titling and registration processes is critical to reduce overlapping claims and prevent political manipulation.
3. Community stakeholders, especially traditional rulers, should be institutionalized as mediators through alternative dispute resolution (ADR) mechanisms.
4. Socio-economic investments, such as shared infrastructure, local markets, and agricultural support, should be prioritized to reduce economic rivalries among boundary communities.
5. Legal reforms, particularly an update of the Land Use Act, should be undertaken to strengthen institutional capacity and discourage illegal practices fueling disputes.

For Future Research:

1. Comparative studies of boundary disputes in other Nigerian states to identify patterns and divergences.
2. Longitudinal research to track the effectiveness of GIS and cadastral mapping technologies in reducing disputes.
3. Mixed-methods approaches that combine spatial analysis (maps, surveys) with ethnographic insights to capture the socio-cultural depth of land conflicts.

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**Peer Reviewed*

Mapping the Relationship between Energy Inflation and Real Estate Asset Performance: A Scoping Review Marius Muller¹; Sibongile Zwane²; and Timothy Oluwafemi Ayodele³

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Abstract

The intersection of energy markets and the real estate sector represents a critical area of economic research, with significant implications for household wealth, financial stability, and macroeconomic policy. However, while the impact of energy price shocks on the broader economy is well-documented, their specific effects on real estate financial performance are complex and merit focused investigation. This study seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of the patterns, divergences, and evidence gaps on the impact of energy fluctuation on real estate investment. The study adopts a scoping review that synthesizes and analyses the existing academic literature on the impact of energy inflation, primarily measured through oil price fluctuations and volatility, on the financial performance of real estate markets. A systematic review of 39 academic studies was performed using the PRISMA-ScR. The analysis focused on empirical quantitative studies examining the relationship between energy costs and measurable real estate financial outcomes, such as property values, rental rates, market volatility, and returns. Data on the study design, market context, key variables, quantitative impacts, market dynamics, and policy recommendations were extracted and synthesized. The review reveals a consistent and statistically significant relationship between energy inflation and real estate financial performance in the short run. However, the magnitude and nature of this impact are highly context dependent. By mapping the evidence from 39 distinct studies, this review provides a comprehensive overview of the transmission channels linking energy markets and real estate performance. It identifies key thematic findings, highlights significant research gaps related to data availability and methodological limitations, and consolidates policy recommendations. The review concluded that the financial performance of real estate is intricately intertwined with energy inflation. This connection, however, is not a straightforward, fixed principle but rather an emergent characteristic of a complex adaptive system, shaped by national economic frameworks, the extent of market financialization, and the proactive influence of policy and information.

Keywords: *Energy Inflation, Oil Prices, Real Estate Performance, Housing Prices, Scoping Review, Market Volatility, REITs*

Introduction: The Energy-Real Estate Nexus in an Era of Volatility

The intersection of energy markets and the real estate sector represents a critical area of economic research, with significant implications for household wealth, financial stability, and macroeconomic policy. Energy, as a fundamental input to economic activity, and real estate, as a cornerstone asset class, are intrinsically linked. Fluctuations in energy prices, a phenomenon often termed energy inflation, can ripple through an economy, influencing everything from construction costs and household disposable income to investment sentiment and monetary policy responses. While the impact of energy price shocks on the broader economy is well-documented, their specific effects on real estate financial performance are complex and merit focused investigation. Real estate assets are often considered a hedge against inflation due to their tangible nature and ability to generate income. Thus, from a theoretical standpoint, this study leans on the foundational

work of Fama and Schwert (1977) to assess the performance behaviour of real estate assets to fluctuations in energy prices across different markets. It examines whether there is supporting evidence to show that property investment performance adjusts sufficiently to offset fluctuating energy costs, thus preserving or enhancing real returns for investors.

Several reviews have sought to synthesize this complex relationship. However, the present study builds upon this work by conducting a systematic and granular scoping review of a specific body of 39 recent empirical papers. This focused approach allows for a deeper analysis of the underlying methodologies, quantitative effects, and context-specific dynamics that shape these interactions. The objectives of the study are to: (1) synthesize the key quantitative findings on how energy inflation affects real estate prices, rents, and volatility; (2) analyze the dynamics of market responses, including asymmetries and regional variations; and (3) identify policy recommendations, research gaps, and directions for future inquiry. By collating and analysing these studies, this review seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of the patterns, divergences, and evidence gaps on the impact of energy fluctuation on real estate investment.

Methodological Approach: A Scoping Review of the Empirical Landscape

This study employs a scoping review methodology to clarify and synthesise the existing empirical literature about the relationship between energy inflation and real estate financial performance. The review was conducted and recorded in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) standards. The fundamental purpose of this structured method is to make sure that the process is transparent, can be repeated and delivers a thorough and fair image of the topic of research.

To ensure the relevance and quality of the synthesised evidence, a predetermined set of inclusion and exclusion criteria was established.

Requirements for Inclusion:

- **Scope:** Research that empirically investigated the relationship between measures of energy price volatility (e.g., oil prices, energy indices, gasoline expenses) and the real estate market.
- **Outcomes:** The review included studies that had either: Quantitative outcomes that encompass impacts on property values, REIT returns, housing prices or market volatility, or Qualitative results that encompass examinations of stakeholder perspectives, socio-economic ramifications or challenges in home affordability attributable to energy costs.
- **Type of Publication:** Only research that had been peer-reviewed was included.
- **Language:** The review only looked at articles that were written in English.
- **Timeframe:** The search looked for research published between January 1978 and June 2025 to highlight how modern energy and financial markets have transformed, especially since the energy crises of the 1970s.

The criteria for exclusion ensure was based on article type and source. Non-empirical works, such as editorials, commentaries, book reviews, and conference abstracts, were excluded. Also, non-peer-reviewed sources, such as dissertations, white papers, and news articles, were removed.

Regarding the information sources and search strategy, this scoping study is the first stage of a comprehensive systematic literature review. It is for this reason that the search was limited to a single large database. Scopus was chosen as it has an extensive collection of papers on economics, finance and social sciences. Its search functions have also proven useful. A detailed search was carried out in June 2025. A long search string was created by combining keywords from three major topics: real estate, energy and financial/economic implications.

The search term: TITLE-ABS-KEY(("real estate" OR "property market" OR "housing market" OR "commercial real estate" OR "residential real estate" OR REIT* OR "real estate investment trust*" OR "property investment*" OR "real property") AND ("energy inflation" OR "energy price inflation" OR "energy price*" OR "energy cost*" OR "utility cost*" OR "electricity price*" OR "natural gas price*" OR "fuel price*" OR "oil price*" OR (inflation AND energy)) AND (impact OR influence OR effect OR affect OR consequence OR implication OR relationship OR correlation OR "market dynamics"))

Selection of Sources: The initial search query produced 208 documents. After a careful two-step screening process to avoid selection bias, 39 studies were chosen for final inclusion. Step 1 screening focused on the titles and abstracts. Three researchers independently assessed the titles and abstracts of all identified records against the eligibility criteria. We debated any differences in opinion until consensus was reached. For Step 2, a complete text review was done by the same three researchers, looking at and reviewing the full texts of all the publications identified from Stage 1 to assess whether it could be beneficial for ultimate inclusion.

The PRISMA flowchart (Figure 1) explains how the complete process of selection was undertaken.

Figure 1: PRISMA Flow Diagram of the Study Selection Process

Sources: Authors construct (2025)

Overview of Literature

Using Scopus export data, a descriptive analysis of the 39 included publications was done to map the broad characteristics of the research environment. The trend in the yearly distribution of publications showed an ever-increasing number of scholars who showed interest in the research topic. Limited research was undertaken in 2006, but in recent years, there has been a significant increase in research output, especially from 2017 onwards. This trend shows how important the energy-real estate nexus has become. Much of the research in the literature is clustered around a few key geographic regions. The USA, UK, Russia, Germany and China are the countries with highest number of total publications. The research mostly exists within the fields of Economics and Finance, Energy and Engineering, and Business and Environmental Sciences. This highlights the inter-disciplinary nature of the subject while retaining a central emphasis within an economic context.

The approach to handling the data from the selected studies involved two distinct stages: data extraction and narrative synthesis. Regarding the data extraction, data was collected from all 39 included studies and was subsequently examined in the following manner: The name(s) of the author(s) and the year it was published; the study's setting is the country or place where the real estate is located; methodology, i.e., research design (for example, VAR or case study); and key findings, i.e., the principal outcomes, include statistical correlations from quantitative research and thematic insights from qualitative studies.

A narrative synthesis was employed to integrate the findings from the diverse studies. This method employs a documented narrative to explain the outcomes of both qualitative and quantitative research. The synthesis involved two steps: Thematic Analysis, where the information from all 39 studies was used to identify recurring concepts which were then grouped into broader, descriptive themes. Narrative Structuring, the results were arranged into a narrative focused on these main topics (e.g., transmission paths, market dynamics), thereby allowing for the integration of quantitative and qualitative data.

In alignment with the primary aim of a scoping review, which is to outline the complete range of existing evidence, a formal assessment of methodological quality was not conducted. The goal was to provide a complete overview of the literature, no matter how good or bad it was. Furthermore, due to the significant heterogeneity of the included methodologies and outcome measures, a statistical meta-analysis was not performed as it would have been inappropriate and statistically invalid.

The Empirical Evidence and Transmission Channels

The accumulated evidence outlined in the examined literature demonstrates a strong, though intricate, agreement: energy inflation serves as a significant, non-neutral factor influencing real estate financial performance. Across various methodologies and market conditions, a statistically significant connection is reliably observed. Nonetheless, a superficial interpretation of these results would obscure a far more complicated and subtle reality. The essential understanding lies not merely in the existence of a relationship, but in how its nature is influenced by the dynamics of economic structure, market financialization, and the current policy landscape.

i. The Direct Impact of Energy Inflation on Real Estate Valuations and Volatility

At the most fundamental level, literature establishes a distinct, positive relationship between energy price shocks and metrics related to real estate prices or volatility. Research conducted in China, for instance, indicated that a 1% increase in energy price volatility can result in a 0.03% increase in housing price volatility (Wang *et al.*, 2024), whereas a 1% change in oil prices can enhance housing prices by as much as 0.451% in a short timeframe (Ali *et al.*, 2024). In Kuwait, a 1% hike in oil prices corresponds to a boost of about 0.138-0.16% in property values (Sharaf and Shahen, 2025). A more comprehensive analysis uncovers that the pathways for these effects are varied and complex. On one side, energy inflation impacts the real economy through direct cost mechanisms, including heightened construction costs and a decrease in household disposable income, consequently affecting the fundamentals of housing supply and demand (Wang *et al.*, 2024). Conversely, especially in more financially integrated markets, the repercussions are conveyed through more intricate channels, such as the influence of oil market risk on the volatility

of U.S. Real Estate Investment Trusts (REITs) (Bonato *et al.*, 2021). Zaki and Isakson (1983) provide early empirical evidence on the impact of energy prices on housing markets, highlighting how rising energy costs influence housing demand, location preferences, and affordability. Their findings suggest that energy price shocks can lead to significant shifts in housing consumption patterns, particularly in energy-intensive suburban developments. This is echoed in Rodriguez (2013), who finds that high gasoline prices disproportionately affect low-density housing markets, leading to reduced demand and price corrections in car-dependent suburban areas.

Energy inflation exerts a profound influence on housing markets, particularly through construction costs and household energy expenditures. Breitenfellner *et al.* (2015) highlights how energy price shocks can trigger house price corrections, especially in overheated markets. Dodson and Sipe (2008) further emphasize the spatial dimension of energy inflation, noting that suburban households are disproportionately affected due to higher transportation and energy costs. This spatial disparity influences housing market dynamics and REIT performance, particularly for residential and suburban-focused REITs.

Housing markets, particularly in oil-exporting nations, have experienced construction cost escalations due to inflationary pressures in energy and raw materials. Alfouzan and Khalafallah (2014) highlighted how cost escalations affect housing affordability and the viability of real estate projects. Le (2015) finds that in Malaysia, oil price shocks significantly influence housing prices through wealth and labour market channels. Akinjare *et al.* (2018), assessing the risk factors on Nigerian portfolios of stock and bonds, identified “crash in oil prices” as a significant post-2008 risk factor for stock investments. Similarly, Alkali *et al.* (2018), also focused on Nigeria, identified crude oil price as a major macroeconomic determinant of residential property prices. Grossman *et al.* (2019) analysed evidence from Texas MSAs (1975-2016). The study found real oil price shocks significantly impacted local house prices, especially in oil-sensitive areas, with effects comparable in magnitude to income shocks. The study underscores the need to account for oil price spillovers when analysing the effects of real income on housing markets

ii. Asymmetries, Lags, and the Dynamics of Market Response

The connection between energy and real estate is inherently non-linear and fluid. Asymmetric effects frequently emerge, with evidence indicating that increasing energy prices tend to exert a more pronounced influence than decreasing prices (Wang *et al.*, 2024), reflecting a classic characteristic of risk aversion and loss amplification within financial systems. The market's reaction is also contingent on historical context, as research has revealed delays in the shock transmission process (Ali *et al.*, 2024) and regime-switching patterns, where the effects depend on the market's prior volatility state (Alola, 2021). This fluidity is significantly highlighted by the discovery that the information landscape can be influenced by policy measures. The field study conducted in Ireland, which illustrates that monetized energy-cost labels can enhance the incorporation of energy efficiency into property valuations, represents a noteworthy finding (Carroll *et al.*, 2024). It implies that the effects of energy inflation are not fixed laws but are, at least to some extent, influenced by the relevance of information and the structuring of policy. Wen *et al.* (2019) found no linear cointegration but significant bidirectional nonlinear Granger causality between oil prices and several sectoral stock indices; including Real Estate. The result suggests

complex, nonlinear predictive relationships. Rehman *et al.* (2020) used a Nonlinear Autoregressive Distributed Lag (NARDL) model to assess asymmetric effects of oil prices, interest rates, inflation, and GDP on residential prices from 1975 to 2017, in the U.S., UK, and Canada. The study found significant short-run effects of oil prices, with varying long-run dynamics across the countries. Al Refai *et al.* (2021), studying Qatar's real estate-stock market linkages, the study found asymmetric short-run and symmetric long-run relationships between oil prices and real estate. Mohan *et al.* (2019) assessed the effects of macroeconomic indicators, including crude oil prices, on US housing prices over 1999 to 2017. The study showed that while oil prices contribute to housing price variance, though to a lesser extent, mortgage interest rate and housing price index (HPI) exerted more influence on housing prices. The results show that macroeconomic shocks, including those stemming from energy markets, significantly influence housing market price.

iii. The Moderating Role of Economic Structure and Local Factors

The distinction between real and financial transmission channels helps to explain the heterogeneity of outcomes observed across the literature. The impact of energy inflation appears to be contingent on at least two primary axes: the economy's structural dependence on energy and the nature of the real estate asset itself. In resource-rich nations like Ghana or Saudi Arabia, the linkage is direct and cyclical, with real estate performance acting as a derivative of the global energy cycle (Issah, 2021; Alola, 2021). In contrast, for large, diversified economies like the UK and Norway, stock market shocks can be a greater determinant of housing prices, suggesting energy inflation is but one of many influencing factors (Büyükkara *et al.*, 2023). Furthermore, a distinction is evident between financialized assets like REITs, which respond primarily to volatility and risk (Bonato *et al.*, 2021), and physical housing, which is more sensitive to direct affordability pressures (Čermáková & Hromada, 2022).

Saadaoui *et al.* (2020) examined the responsiveness of oil prices to disruptions in the bond market, especially during financial crises. The findings suggest that oil prices are sensitive in the short term to financial market shocks, with the relationship increasing over extended periods. The study found the financial market significantly affects oil prices only during severe crises, such as the subprime mortgage and sovereign debt crisis. Though the study does not directly address real estate, it highlights the importance of oil price volatility, and its effect on real estate markets through broader economic means.

Emerging Themes and Deeper Implications

Beyond the direct evidence of transmission, a closer reading of the literature reveals deeper thematic implications of the energy-real estate nexus, particularly concerning portfolio behaviour and societal outcomes.

i. Inter-Asset Dynamics: Real Estate in a Competitive Capital Environment

A vital aspect highlighted in literature is the significance of inter-asset interactions and capital reallocation. The reaction of the real estate sector to energy shocks cannot be analysed in isolation; it takes place within a larger ecosystem of rival investment assets. Büyükkara *et al.* (2023) provide a compelling analysis, indicating that in both the UK and Norway, the behaviour of the stock market plays a more crucial role in shaping housing costs than the changes in oil prices. Additional support for the idea of asset reallocation is evident in China, where shocks in gold prices have been

shown to adversely affect housing prices, indicating that investors tend to shift their capital towards gold as a safe-haven asset when its price rises (Ali *et al.*, 2024). This concept is central to the research conducted by Nasreddine and Essafi-Zouari (2025), who evaluate the inflation-hedging effectiveness of real estate in direct comparison to assets such as oil and gold. This collection of evidence suggests that energy inflation does not simply adjust asset prices in a vacuum; it reorganizes them within investment portfolios, and the overall effect on real estate is influenced by its perceived worth in relation to alternative asset categories.

ii. Socio-Economic Consequences: Energy Inflation and Housing Affordability

Beyond financial mechanics, the literature reveals that energy inflation acts as a powerful driver of housing affordability crises and socio-economic stratification. The study of the Czech Republic by Čermáková and Hromada. (2022) is a stark illustration, documenting how sharp rises in energy prices have deteriorated housing affordability to the point of creating a "new dimension of poverty." This macroeconomic shock is shown to have direct, tangible consequences on the social structure. A similar narrative emerges from the mixed-methods study of Ghana's oil city, where an oil boom led to the eviction of lower-paid tenants as landlords refurbished properties to cater to higher-income oil workers (Issah, 2021). This is a clear case of energy-driven development directly causing socio-economic displacement. The policy recommendations in the Kuwaiti study, which urge policymakers to address affordability concerns (Sharaf and Shahen, 2025), further cement this conclusion. Taken together, these studies demonstrate that energy inflation is not a socially neutral event; it is a regressive force that disproportionately impacts lower and middle-income groups and can fundamentally alter the social fabric of cities and regions. Wu *et al.* (2019) examined the U.S. suburban housing market. The study revealed that gasoline price shock increases commuting costs, decreases suburban property values, and increases foreclosure rates. The findings suggest that energy costs disproportionately affect lower-income and suburban households, thereby making mortgages less affordable.

The Research Frontier: A Proposed Agenda for Future Inquiry

The examined literature establishes a robust basis, yet its synthesis reveals significant gaps and suggests a more ambitious and cohesive research agenda. The constraints identified by the authors are not just technical flaws; they reflect the boundaries of the existing paradigm's explanatory power. Consequently, a genuinely forward-thinking research agenda should transcend mere incremental advancements and adopt fresh conceptual frameworks.

First, the real estate discipline must confront the issue of data scarcity and the challenge of granularity. The persistent demands for improved local-level energy price data (Wang *et al.*, 2024), more thorough metrics for unlisted assets (Gupta *et al.*, 2023), and comprehensive transactional data (Sharaf and Shahen, 2025) reflect a more extensive concern. Second, a crucial shift in methodological approach is evident. The prevalence of linear VAR and ARDL models may fall short in capturing the intricate dynamics that have been uncovered. Future research should focus on models that explicitly incorporate non-linearities (Michieka *et al.*, 2024), threshold effects, and asymmetries (Wang *et al.*, 2024) that seem to be pervasive in this relationship. Third, and most importantly, upcoming research must explore uncharted conceptual intersections, thereby reframing the fundamental research question. We suggest three promising paths:

i. The Energy Transition Nexus: The existing literature primarily focuses on fossil fuel prices. The research question should shift from “What is the effect of oil price volatility?” to “In what ways does the global energy transition, comprising a complex interplay of technological advancements, carbon pricing, and green finance, comprehensively alter real estate valuation, investment and associated risks?”

ii. Behavioural Real Estate Finance and Energy Salience: Building upon the Irish study (Carroll *et al.*, 2024), it is essential for research to explicitly link energy economics with behavioral finance in order to comprehend how cognitive biases influence the integration of energy costs into property valuations.

iii. Geopolitical Risk, Capital Flows, and Real Estate as a Safe Haven: A focused research avenue is necessary to explore how geopolitical risks, transmitted via energy markets, affect global capital movements toward real estate and the function of property as a “safe haven” investment.

Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

The body of work examined here leads to a clear conclusion that the financial performance of real estate is intricately intertwined with energy inflation. This connection, however, is not a straightforward, fixed principle but rather an emergent characteristic of a complex adaptive system. Its essence is shaped by national economic frameworks, the extent of market financialization, and the proactive influence of policy and information. The consistent observations of heterogeneity, asymmetry, and non-linearity strongly indicate that efforts to identify a single, universal beta for real estate's exposure to energy risk are likely to be unsuccessful. The impact is contextual, fluid, and continually changing. This nuanced understanding demands a corresponding evolution in policy and investment strategy, moving beyond traditional views to adopt more dynamic and forward-thinking approaches.

Recommendations for Policy and Investment Strategy

For Policymakers: there is the need to establish energy-conscious financial stability frameworks. Policymakers and financial regulators should create formal Energy-Conscious Real Estate Stress Tests, which simulate the systemic effects of specified energy shock scenarios on the financial system. By translating this broad recommendation into a concrete, actionable framework, the aim is to connect academic insights with regulatory implementation.

Also, there is the need to leverage information to enhance market efficiency. Building upon insights from Carroll *et al.* (2024), policy should focus on making energy efficiency a clear and liquid asset characteristic by nurturing ecosystems that deliver dynamic, real-time energy cost and carbon footprint information directly into property listings and mortgage underwriting platforms. In addition, risk mitigation in green construction through industrial strategy could be considered. The discovery that fluctuations in oil prices impede green real estate development (Eje *et al.*, 2023) poses a significant policy challenge. An effective response necessitates an industrial strategy designed to mitigate risks in the supply chains for green construction materials through public-private partnerships, subsidies, or price stabilization funds.

For Investors: there is the need to consider an energy risk factor strategy. Investors ought to view energy as a systematic risk element that requires management throughout the entire portfolio. This

means creating quantitative models, inspired by the disaggregated shock analysis conducted by Bonato *et al.* (2021), to assess how sensitive a portfolio is to various types of energy shocks. Also, the review suggests the need to capitalize on local-global arbitrage opportunities. The notable observation that local factors can overshadow global energy patterns (Fetais *et al.*, 2024) offers a significant chance for astute investors to generate alpha by pinpointing markets where the effects of global energy inflation are inaccurately valued.

While this study has provided a comprehensive understanding of the patterns, divergences, and evidence gaps on the impact of energy fluctuation on real estate investment, this study acknowledges its peculiar limitations. First, despite a rigorous database search, relevant studies not indexed in the Scopus repository or published in non-English languages were overlooked, besides expanding the database search to include other repositories might be considered for a broader context and implication. Also, direct comparison of findings across markets with different exposure to energy fluctuations may be limited. Thus, limiting the transferability of conclusions across global markets.

Disclosure Statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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**Peer Reviewed*

Green Finance Instrument and Product Awareness In South Africa: Characteristics, Risks, and Stakeholders. *Thobile Ntombela*¹, *Chioma S. Okoro*², *Jonathan D. Oladeji*³.

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Abstract

Green finance has been identified as a crucial vehicle for achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), specifically SDGs 3, 6, and 7. An integrative literature review was employed to examine green finance products available to retail consumers and their associated risks. In addition, a semi-structured interview was conducted to determine relevant stakeholders, beyond the issuing financial institutions, who can drive GF products awareness, towards increasing usage. Findings revealed that green finance instruments can be categorised into bank lending, corporate finance, green insurance, and green funds for various uses. These uses include construction, waste management, water management, residential housing development, renewable energy, clean transportation, and climate change and adaptation projects. Multi-stakeholder and multisectoral collaborations between the government, regulatory bodies, multilateral and international finance institutions, private sector organisations, non-profit organisations, academic institutions, retail consumers, advocacy groups, and community organisations can drive awareness and increased usage of GF products. This study provides insights for GF stakeholders on access challenges that result in involuntary exclusion for consumers. As well as discussing strategies that can be implemented to arrive at an accessible GF market, and the stakeholders responsible for implementing such strategies.

Keywords: Green finance, housing infrastructure, real estate investment, SDGs, South Africa, sustainability.

1. Introduction

Green Finance (GF) has become a fundamental concept in the financial sector due to its ability to meet the United Nations Paris Agreement targets and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (UN, 2021). Lindeberg (2014) defined GF as “components of the financial system that deal specifically with green investments, such as the Green Climate Fund or financial instruments for green investments (e.g. green bonds and structured green funds), including their specific legal, economic and institutional framework conditions”. The terms “green”, “sustainable”, “climate”, “impact” and “social” have been used interchangeably in literature, but they are not synonymous (Zairis et al., 2024). However, the interrelation of these terms lies in their objective of incorporating Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) considerations in financial and investment decisions of institutions.

Preluding from the definition and goals of GF, much literature has investigated the relationship between GF and environmental performance and has found that for the broader economy, GF leads to a greener environment (Zakari and Khan, 2022). Yet, without sufficient awareness of the characteristics, associated risks, and stakeholder involvement, GF adoption in developing economies might seem less attractive to consumers. Although GF products exist, there’s a perception that they are not typically tailored to household consumers. Bethlendi, Nagy, and Póra (2022) observe that the study of GF has been limited to focus on green instruments (e.g., green bonds, green funds) and has not comprehensively covered green products (e.g., green mortgages). Much of literature on GF has limited the definition and application of GF to green bonds, green/climate funds, and other financial instruments or platforms mobilizing capital and has

excluded the definition of GF that includes debt-financing and financing for household systems such as solar panels and clean cookstove technology, which indicates that GF awareness has not been widely designed to address household end-users (Volz, Knaack, Nyman, Ramos and Moling, 2020; Martin 2022; Debrah et al., 2022).

Green finance has at its core the aim of merging environmentally friendly practices into business and finance operations. GF is, therefore, a component of sustainable living, focusing mainly on environmental issues and preserving the environment using financial tools (Zairis, Liargovas, and Apostolopoulos, 2024). However, countries differ on what types of financial products are defined as green, creating limited awareness and lower adoption (Gilchrist, Yu, and Zhong, 2021). The reason for this difference could be that countries are at different levels of development, and their priorities are different, leading to different GF standards and goals. Based on this, the current study is anchored in the resource theory, which explains why the sustainable finance progress of some countries is more advanced than that of others. The theory provides that competitive advantage resulting from a difference in human-made resources is one of the reasons for the variance in progress (Ozili, 2022). Such human-made resources include a better education system, a developed financial sector, advanced technology, financial regulation and supervision, and a sustainably conscious population, amongst others. Countries that have these resources can achieve their sustainable finance goals with ease and seamlessly transition from traditional finance systems.

As a developing country, South Africa is uniquely positioned to lead in the awareness and uptake of GF products. Yet, limited data is demonstrating that the consumer appetite aligns with expectations. South Africa has witnessed its surge in GF instruments such as green bonds issued by Growthpoint, African Development Bank, Standard Bank and Investec Bank, to name a few. Similarly, GF products have emerged to serve end users, including the Absa Eco Home Loan in partnership with Balwin Properties, and the Balwin Properties Green Mortgage in partnership with South African banks (Absa, n.d.; Balwin Properties, 2022). As a developing country, South Africa has been highlighted as a pioneer of GF in Africa, evidenced through the development and launch of the South African Green Finance Taxonomy in April 2022 (Kwanhi and Mago, 2024). The South African government has also been progressive in adopting climate change mitigation and adaptation agreements, such as the Paris Agreement and inclusion of sustainable goals in its nationally determined contributions (NDCs) (Elsner and Neumann, 2023). Yet, there remains a lack of evidence regarding the awareness levels, risks, and engagement of stakeholders in the uptake of GF products. This creates a gap in understanding if the level of development of GF is matched by market readiness and awareness, which constrains policy development targeted at increasing uptake.

Therefore, the overarching question in this study was: What are the predominant green finance products and instruments for sustainable real estate development and investment in South Africa? The objectives were to identify the predominant types and categories of GF products or instruments, the characteristics and associated risks, focusing on the South African products and the roles that stakeholders play in GF awareness level, and addressing the related challenges. The study's findings on the characterisation of green finance products and instruments and stakeholders' roles in increasing awareness and accessibility will contribute to sustainable real estate development and investment policy in South Africa.

2. Literature Review

In this section, a literature review is conducted to provide a conceptual and theoretical framing for the research. The study aims to characterise green finance products and instruments for sustainable real estate development and investment in South Africa. Therefore, this literature review provides a thematic synthesis of extant literature, highlighting the research gaps that the study addresses.

2.1 GF Instruments

A systematic literature review study by Akomea-Frimpong, Adeabah, Ofosu and Tenakwah (2022) aimed to analyse literature on banks' GF in terms of products or instrument characteristics, publishing journals, research methodology used, identify relevant themes addressed in different studies and identify research gaps and future directions of most studies. The study found that the following GF products and instruments were reported by banks, arranged from most to least reported: green credit/loan; green long-term investment account; carbon finance; climate finance; green traded stocks and bonds; green bancassurance and green infrastructural finance. A study by Martin (2022) provided a comprehensive literature review of GF instruments that exist worldwide and looked at the regulatory developments that have been made. It found the following GF instruments in the Serbian market: green bonds, renewable and sustainable equity, green mutual funds, solar bonds, green stocks, and renewable energy credits. This study took a different direction by focusing specifically on GF products on offer (and those previously offered) in the South African GF market. An analysis of the GF instruments described by the author revealed that only two of the instruments were linked to products specifically designed for retail consumers, these being the renewable and sustainable equity and green mortgage. This shows that most GF instruments have limited relevance to retail consumers.

2.1.2 Characterising GF Instruments

From these studies (Mudalige 2024; Akomea-Frimpong et al 2022; and Martin 2022), it can be observed that there is no consensus yet in terms of the categories of GF instruments, with some identifying green credit and green loans as GF instruments, while others maintain that these are different products. Some of these studies (Bogacheva and Smorodinov, 2017; Gujadhur and Ansaram, 2021; Gilchrist, Yu, and Zhong, 2021) make a distinction between GF instruments and solar/renewable energy instruments, while others maintain that both are classified as GF instruments. These differences highlight and amplify the need for unanimity in the classification of GF instruments.

2.2 GF Products

Ahmed (2019) looked at the concept, scope, history, and types of GF products as well as the status and barriers to GF in Bangladesh. Like other authors, this author categorised GF products into the following types: retail banking, corporate and investment banking, asset management, and insurance. Under retail banking, the following products were included, and the products were briefly described in terms of key product design: green home mortgage, green commercial building loans, green auto loan, and green credit card. Ghahroud, Rezania, Oryani and Tajdini (2020) collaborated on an interesting study that expands on the GF products' categorisation and GF products listed by Ahmed (2019). These studies are limited in that they do not address the gap in the developing country context compared to more developed countries.

2.2.1 GF Product Demand and Accessibility

Bethlendi et al. (2022) investigated the under-researched area of retail consumer demand for GF products, using a survey of 2500 Hungarian citizens using the computer-assisted Telephone Interviewing (CATI) method. The study found that consumer preference and behaviour are not the same for all consumers and can be grouped, in terms of shared characteristics, into 4 clusters.

Gujadhur and Ansaram (2021), who focused solely on GF solutions offered by commercial banks, found that businesses demonstrated higher knowledge of green leasing and green mortgages, especially with products supplied by banks. The energy sector was perceived as the main beneficiary, followed by transportation, agriculture, and construction. Similarly, Unnikrishnan et al. (2019) explored the awareness of the GF concept and the willingness to invest in GF instruments in India. While there is some indication of awareness of GF products as evidenced in the literature, a greater concern is the accessibility of the products, as observed by Claessen (2006), Hattingh and Appies (2022), Gujadhur and Ansaram (2021), and Khan et al. (2022). Some studies also highlight that accessibility is greater in developed countries than in developing countries (Wasan et al., 2024). This study, therefore, assessed accessibility characteristics of green finance products in South Africa to increase awareness, accessibility, and use.

2.2.2 GF product awareness and knowledge

Another study by Bethlendi and Póra (2021) investigated how households' environmental and financial knowledge and attitudes affect demand for green financial products, and how significantly price support can be used to channel citizens towards more sustainable financial products. Additionally, the study explored households' green and financial knowledge and attitudes. The study used a pre-established survey by BME-NMB, which was conducted using the CATI methodology of 2500 Hungarian citizens. The study found that Hungarian residents tend to undermine their green and financial knowledge. However, the authors did not first look at consumers' awareness about GF products, which is what this study will do. The studies by Ahmed (2019) and Ghahroud et al. (2020) focused only on GF products provided by financial institutions. This study sought to investigate the role of stakeholders in addressing challenges affecting GF awareness levels in South Africa.

3. Methods

This study employed a qualitative research approach that incorporates an integrative literature review and semi-structured interviews to address the research gaps. The emerging themes and information derived from the literature review provided a conceptual framing of the current understanding of GF and a basis for the data collection and analysis. The combination of these qualitative approaches allows for a real-world understanding of the established trends in GF products and instruments. The study's aim is achieved through the systematic synthesis of literature, as well as interviews with 8 industry experts identified through a purposive sampling. Participants were selected and contacted through LinkedIn. A total of 33 connection invites were sent to potential participants, and this achieved a 38.9% turnover rate. The participants were selected using the criteria that they are knowledgeable about the green industry, own or lease property other than a state-subsidised house, are currently employed, earn an income, and are South African residents. Sandelowski (1995), cited in Boddy (2016), posits that a sample size of ten is suitable when sampling from a homogeneous population. The study applied further snowball sampling to identify other relevant stakeholders and ensured data saturation, which has been described as critical to the robustness and validity of data (Hennink and Kaiser, 2022). The data

from the Microsoft Teams interviews were transcribed by the researcher and then analysed using ATLAS.ti.

4. Findings

4.1 Categorisation of Green Finance Instruments and Products

According to Cheberyako et al. (2021), GF instruments can be categorised into 4 groups, namely bank lending, corporate finance, green insurance and green funds. This section of the literature reviewed GF instruments according to the abovementioned categorisation and briefly described each GF instrument.

4.1.1 Bank Lending

Green Credit

The majority of studies agree that green credit takes the form of policies that mandate financial institutions to consider more than economic indicators, but also environmental indicators when allocating capital and resources to industries that have low energy consumption and pollution (Lyu, Da, Ostic and Yu, 2022; Wu, Zhou and Zhu, 2023). The overarching aim of green credit is to reduce carbon emissions by directing capital away from companies that are heavily polluted and energy-consuming (Lyu et al., 2022). Theoretically, green credit is an innovative solution for present environmental goals; however, much literature has also highlighted the shortcomings of this GF instrument. Other authors have also criticised green credit on the grounds of long-term sustainability and impact on industries (Sun, Wang, Yin and Zhang, 2019; Liu, Wang and Cai, 2017).

Green Loans

Green loans are described as credit products that are issued to finance or refinance projects with positive environmental benefits (Gulzhan, Kerimkulova, Yessymkhanova, Orazbayeva, and Alibekova, 2023). Green loans are designed for retail and corporate bankers to cover their financial needs, provided those needs will not result in a negative impact on the environment (Mirovic, Kalas, Djokic, Milicevic, Djokic, and Djakovic, 2023).

Other forms of green loans mentioned in studies include green car loans, green mortgages, and green home equity loans. These GF products are designed and suited for retail consumers and their needs. Green home equity loans offer lower interest rates to customers who install renewable energy technologies in their homes.

4.1.2 Corporate Finance

Green Bonds

Green bonds are debt financial instruments used to finance projects with a positive impact on the environment (Cheberyako et al., 2021). Green bonds are widely proliferated green financial instruments. Green bonds are issued by governments, financial institutions, corporations and other entities. The largest issuers of green bonds are the International Finance Corporation (IFC) and World Bank (Cheberyako et al., 2021). Before an entity can issue a bond and qualify it as 'green', the issuers need to undergo verification by a third party (Flammer, 2021). The verification process will also ensure that the proceeds will be used to finance environmentally beneficial projects.

Green securitisation

According to Agliardi (2022), green securitisation has two different meanings in the literature. One definition sustains that securitisation is green when the proceeds from it are used to finance environmentally friendly assets or activities. The other definition maintains that a securitisation is said to be green if the underlying collateral assets are green. This difference in definition is supported by other authors such as Li, Zhu and Zhang (2024). Green securitisation has been highlighted as more impactful than green loans and green bonds, especially in developing countries (Li et al., 2024). However, the growth of green securitisation has not been without challenges. One raising concern about the plight of green securitisation is the greenwashing of the underlying collateral pool and that of projects or assets to which proceeds are directed. Against the issue of greenwashing, this study by Li et al. (2024) investigated the role of external certification of assets and projects in green securitisation.

Green Leasing

A green lease is defined as an agreement between an owner and occupier agreeing to the sustainable operation and management of the green property (Hettige, Perera and Mallawaarachchi, 2017; Collins, 2019). According to these authors, green leasing has previously mainly been used for the leasing of residential space and has been widely used in developed countries. Cheberyako et al. (2021) posit that green leasing can also be used on other asset types, such as cars, mortgages and energy-efficient products. A green lease is different from a traditional lease in that the owner and tenant mutually agree on which obligations to include in the contract (Rameezdeen, Zuo, Paniagua, Wood, and Do, 2019). Green Venture Capital (GVC)

Green Venture Capital is described by Randjelovic, O'Rourke and Orsato (2003) as being “a high-risk capital provision for eco-innovative ventures, which offers the potential for financial returns as well as contributing to sustainable development.” A study by Wei, Yuguo and Jiaping (2015) found that studies on green venture capital were, at the time of publishing, very limited in defining what GVC is. Presently, that is still the case, with GVC being defined using literature from 2003. However, other studies on GVC have systematically reviewed the significance of GVC for sustainable development (Dhayal, Giri, Esposito and Agrawal, 2023).

Green Private Investment

Green private investment is described as investment into activities that promote sustainability within an economy (Bowen, 2021). Green private investment can also be in the form of banks establishing a private equity fund to provide capital for environmental projects.

4.1.3 Green Insurance (GI)

GI is defined as an innovative financial product that combines environmental protection and the financial sector (You, Wu and Li, 2024). There are varying definitions of the mechanism of GI. Nobanee, Alqubaisi, Alhameli, Alqubaisi, Alhammadi, Almarshli and Wazir (2021) define GI as “environmental pollution liability insurance”, which necessitates environmental polluters to pay affected parties and encourages corporations to account for environmentally-detrimental acts. While Wu and Chiu (2023) define GI as a form of economic payment that incentivises behaviour change or encourages the development of carbon-reductive innovations by providing insurance specifically catered for the environmental benefits of these products. Noh (2018) provides that GI

can also be in reference to insurance products that provide different insurance premiums according to the environmental benefit of the asset under cover.

According to Nobanee et al. (2021), there are different GI products such as green building insurance, “global weather insurance”, green car insurance, and renewable energy insurance. According to Wu and Chiu (2023), GI can be categorised into green property insurance, environmental liability insurance, and carbon insurance.

4.2 South African Green Finance Products

Table 1 identifies 14 GF products that have been developed specifically for South African retail consumers. Each GF product is listed, as well as its categorisation according to the above-discussed categorisation of financial instruments. A worldwide overview of GF products that have been addressed by authors in previous studies is presented. This section funnelled down the focus of GF from broad to specifically look at GF at the level of the retail consumer in South Africa. The authors illustrate the GF products that participants are surveyed about during the interview process. Publicly available documents about institutional GF products were analysed using content analysis.

There are three categories of providers, including development banks, commercial banks, and commercial real estate companies. In line with Bethlendi et al. (2022), consumer behaviour and intent for GF products differ across the board. The findings also demonstrate that GF products are available in developing countries like South Africa, which adds to the understanding of accessibility.

Table 1: South African Green Finance Products

No.	GF Product	Type of GF Instrument	Dates of issue	Types of eligible projects	Examples of eligible projects	Users	Reference
1.	African Development Bank (AfDB) green bond	Corporate Finance	23 August 2022- 06 September 2023 (maturity)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate change mitigation projects • Climate change adaptation projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Greenfield renewable energy generation • Demand-side brownfield and greenfield energy efficiency • Vehicle energy efficiency fleet retrofit or urban transport modal change • Biosphere conservation projects • 	Not available	African Development Bank (2022).
2.	Development Bank of Southern Africa (DBSA) green bond	Corporate Finance	February 2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mitigation of climate change projects • Adaptation to climate change projects. • Environmental sustainability projects. • Social sustainability projects. • 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Renewable energy generation, distribution and/or transmission. • Energy efficiency construction and development. • Manufacturing, acquisition and maintenance of low-carbon public transportation. • 	Not available	DBSA (2021).
3.	Standard Bank green bond	Corporate Finance	10.5-year term loan issued in 2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction, generation, maintenance or acquisition of renewable power sources and infrastructure. • Manufacturing of components for renewable energy technology • Transmission and distribution of 	-	Not available	Standard Bank Group (2024).

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> renewable energy to the grid Climate change mitigation 			
4.	Rand Merchant Bank (RMB) sustainability-linked bonds	Corporate Finance	Not available	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Renewable energy. Water efficiency performance. Water infrastructure. Reduced carbon/greenhouse gas emissions 	Not available	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Redefine Properties (REIT) Rand Water (SOC) Emira Property Fund (REIT) 	RMB (n.d)
5.	Investec green bond	Corporate Finance	Issued on 23 February 2023-23 February 2026 (Redemption Date)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Renewable energy Energy efficiency Sustainable water and wastewater management Green buildings Clean transport 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Renewable energy projects such as wind, solar, hydro, biomass and associated components. Grid expansion with a minimum of 85% renewable energy. Smart grids and meters. Water treatment facilities Water savings systems 	As of August 2021, the following projects were considered for funding through the Investec Green Bond. All the projects included focused on renewable energy and were mega-projects of massive power generation, ranging from 50MW-100MW capacity.	Investec, November 2021. JSE Client Portal, 23 February 2023.
6.	Growthpoint green bond	Corporate Finance	10-year bond issued 7 February 2024.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Green buildings Energy efficiency Sustainable water and wastewater management Renewable energy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Projects financing or refinancing new or existing properties that meet any of the following requirements: 4-star or higher green rating; 6 or higher Energy Water Performance (EWP); WELL Building Standard; Excellence in Design for 	Not available	Growthpoint, April 2024. Growthpoint Properties, February 2024.

					<p>Greater Efficiencies (EDGE) certification by IFC partners.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financing or refinancing of projects or equity investments that improve energy efficiency in new or refurbished buildings. • Financing or refinancing of projects or equity investments that improve water efficiency in new or refurbished buildings. • Financing or refinancing of projects or equity investments in renewable energy transition and/or generation. 		
7.	Redefine Properties green bond	Corporate Finance	29 August 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Renewable energy • Energy efficiency • Green buildings • Sustainable water and wastewater management • Waste management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction, generation, transmission and maintenance of renewable energy and associated infrastructure. • Manufacturing or importation of renewable energy technology components. • Manufacturing and/or installation of components of technologies for energy efficiency. • 		Redefine Properties, December 2023. Redefine Properties, 2022.
8.	Nedbank green residential development bond	Corporate Finance	10 December 2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Green residential developments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financing projects that develop IFC EDGE-certified residential housing developments. • Provide performance-based incentives to developers financed by the bond to 	Green residential developers.	JSE, 10 December 2021. Nedbank, 2021. IFC, 2021.

					offset green certification costs.		
9.	Absa Eco-home loan in partnership with Balwin properties	Bank Lending	12 March 2020.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmentally friendly homes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Customers who purchase Absa-approved EDGE-certified residential developments. 	First-time homebuyers, repeat buyers and investors purchasing Absa-approved EDGE-certified homes directly from the developer.	Absa, n.d. Balwin Properties, 2020.
10.	Balwin Green Mortgage in partnership with Absa, Nedbank, Standard Bank, FNB and SA Home Loans	Bank Lending		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Green certified residential buildings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GBCSA EDGE certified homes/buildings GBCSA 6-star rated buildings GBCSA Net Zero Carbon-rated buildings 	Homeowners wishing to access lower interest rates and utility costs homes.	Balwin Properties, 2022.
11.	Standard Bank LookSee Solar Loan	Bank Lending		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Solar energy for homes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Financing and installation of solar energy systems in homes 	Homeowners wishing to finance solar energy for their homes	Guest, 2023.
12.	Nedbank Green Housing Bond	Bank Lending	29 July 2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Financing EDGE-certified homes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Financing consumers' green mortgage bonds for EDGE-certified homes. 	Homeowners looking to purchase an EDGE-certified house	Nedbank, 2021.
13.	Nedbank renewable energy bond	Corporate Finance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 30 April 2019- 30 April 2022/24/26 (maturity dates) 25 October 2019 – 25 October 2022/24 (maturity dates) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Financing renewable energy projects 	Proceeds allocated to financing renewable energy projects undertaken by four Proprietary companies for renewable energy facilities located in South Africa.	Nedbank, 2021.

14.	City of Cape Town Green Bond	Corporate Finance	2017	Funding and refinancing of projects focused on infrastructure, water supply shortages and mobility challenges.		It was used to finance projects focused on water capture, storage and distribution infrastructure, alternative water treatment plants and flood defence.	Cities Climate Finance Leadership Alliance, n.d. Sullivan, 2020.
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Figure 1: GF Products Categories and Types in South Africa

4.3 GF Risks

Despite the benefits of GF, it is not without risks. The findings of this study revealed that consumers' perception about GF is that it is risky, which is a deterring factor to consumers considering GF products. The products available under GF have also been highlighted as being expensive, which is a risk and a limiting factor for consumers. Consumers are also of the opinion that the disadvantages of GF presently outweigh the advantages, which deters them from making use of GF products.

In contrast with Sachs et al. (2019), GF is noticeably provided for short-term, long-term, high-risk and low-risk projects in South Africa. This suggests that GF products are potentially extending in their applicability and there is a more favourable perception despite the inherent risks. The use of standards like IFC Edge and Green Certification demonstrates a growing effort to address risks such as greenwashing, implementation and regulation, and a lack of information. It is important to highlight that an important challenge to GF accessibility is the risk perception that inhibits providers like the bank lenders. These findings demonstrate that specific retail consumer products have been developed in South Africa, including those for first-time homeowners or homeowners interested in Edge-certified buildings. Therefore, institutions are addressing the perceived risk of the products with consumers in mind.

4.4 Stakeholder Responsibilities

As part of the objectives, this study also highlighted the roles and responsibilities of different stakeholders in developing the accessible GF market. The participants in this study suggested a bottom-up approach to be adopted for further promulgation of GF for retail consumers. This agrees with Ozili (2021), who provided that to grow the sustainable finance sector, it is necessary to adopt a bottom-up approach. This change in approach requires partnership between multiple stakeholders, such as stakeholders that will develop GF products for lower-income consumers, those that will educate these consumers about GF and GF products, those that will equip them with skills to access and use GF products, and those that will continually research to improve these product offerings.

Figure 2. GF Stakeholder Cycle of Awareness and Accessibility

The following stakeholders were considered to have a paramount role in GF awareness and accessibility:

- *Government* - Government was recognised as the main stakeholder responsible for driving awareness and information sharing initiatives to consumers and communities. Government was also recognised as a policymaker that has the right tools to effect change by providing policy direction, developing macroeconomic policies and providing incentives (financial and non-financial) to encourage participation of different parties.
- *Regulatory Bodies* - The main regulatory body identified by participants was the Johannesburg Stock Exchange (JSE), and their role was the enforcement, mandatory frameworks and regulation of companies. The JSE could also regulate the sharing, availability and quality of information provided by companies. The JSE could also work in conjunction with government departments to put in place a blanket approach that covers all types of consumers.
- *Multilateral and International Finance Institutions* - These institutions were identified as key players in increasing the uptake of GF at the granular level through partnerships with community-based organisations that will inform and increase awareness at the community level.
- *Private Financial Institutions* - Financial institutions were highlighted as suitable bodies to lead the development of financial products that cater to multiple-income households.
- *Private Sector Companies* - Private companies as institutions that employ were highlighted as necessary for the deployment of a blanket approach that makes sure that everyone is exposed to GF. Additionally, companies that operate in the private sector and have significant emissions and other negative externalities should be the ones mandated to increase awareness about GF products and sustainability issues.
- *Non-Profit Organisations (NPOs), Advocacy Groups, Community Organisations* - Community-based organisations and community leaders' role is highlighted as the bodies that directly engage with the community or bring in institutions that will inform and educate the community about GF and the products available to them and how these can be attained.

- *Academic Institutions* - The role of academic institutions was highlighted as producers of knowledge and the bodies that research into problems and provide insights and recommendations for those problems. Academic institutions, as bodies that house a large demography of students, were highlighted as the right bodies to educate and instil GF in students.
- *Retail Consumer* - The role of the consumer was highlighted as the individuals who must change their perceptions and reevaluate their priorities when it comes to sustainability. Consumers need to self-educate about GF, and when presented with the opportunity to choose between green and non-green products, make the informed decision to choose green because of its positive contribution to the environment.

5 Conclusion

Regarding the previously identified GF neglect of retail consumers, this study has reviewed literature that focused on these consumers and identified gaps in these studies. The overarching aim of the study was to characterise GF products and instruments for sustainable real estate development and investment in South Africa. This study used an integrative literature review and interview data to identify the types and categories of GF products or instruments that have dominated sustainable real estate literature; characterise GF products and instruments available in South Africa; and explore the role of stakeholders in addressing challenges affecting GF awareness levels in South Africa. Through this current study, some of these gaps were bridged by detailing GF products that cater to the needs of retail consumers, and interviewing only retail consumers, both those who have used and not used GF products. Lastly, the study presented and discussed strategies to improve consumers' access to GF products, some of which had previously been identified but not in the context of retail consumers.

The study identified 14 GF products available to South African retail consumers, including climate change mitigation projects, Edge-Certified homes, solar energy projects, green residential developments, waste management, and sustainable water and waste management. The results also demonstrate that the risk perception of GF products continues to be addressed in the South African market, which contributes to accessibility. It also highlighted critical stakeholders for improving GF Awareness, including the Government, Regulatory Bodies, Multilateral International Finance Institutions, Non-Profit Organisations, Private Sector Companies, Private Financial Institutions, Academic Institutions and Retail Consumers. Stakeholders must be motivated to contribute to knowledge and awareness about GF products. It contributes to behavioural theory, demonstrating that stakeholders like regulatory bodies (IFC EDGE, and Green Building Council of South Africa) influence consumer intention towards GF products. It also highlights the potential for the application of GF products across varying project types, from solar energy, wastewater management, and home buying.

GF has had an immeasurable impact on literature, practice and attainment of sustainability goals. As much as there has been a surge in literature about GF, much of this literature is still very broadly focused. This study, by delving directly into a neglected group of consumers and GF, has provided distinct insights into a rarely explored issue. Future research could adopt a similar approach and investigate refined topics of GF that have not been explored before. Further exploration of the perceptions of the identified stakeholders could reveal more insights into GF accessibility and how to uncover and handle future uncertainties and risks regarding green finance.

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**Peer Reviewed*

The framework for the development of a standard for mass valuation in South Africa *Ngubeni Steven*¹; *Benita Zulch*²; *Joseph Awoamim Yacim*³ and *Partson Paradza*⁴

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Abstract

The valuation disputes associate to valuation inconsistencies and inaccuracies, suggest that South Africa urgently needs either a renewed commitment in implementing the international mass valuation standards or developing a localized standard. The objective of the study is to investigate the application of the international mass valuation standards in South Africa, and to propose a framework for the development local mass valuation standards. The study approach is qualitative, underpinned by interviews and focused group discussions. With the aid of purposeful sampling and snow balling, the study targeted the mass valuation practitioners and valuation regulators, which were. The results of the study were subjected to thematic analysis. After establishing that there is little or non-use of the international standards during mass valuation standards in South Africa, the study proposed a practical framework for the development of the mass valuation standard, which provides guidance on both procedural and substantive aspects of developing a mass valuation standard. Legal reforms are recommended to make adoption of the standard mandatory and effective. Although designed for South Africa, the framework can be useful for other developing countries without their own mass valuation standards.

Key words: Mass valuation; valuation standard; framework; accuracy; consistency

Introduction

The growing frequency of valuation disputes in South African municipalities has raised serious concerns about the consistency and accuracy of mass property valuations in general and municipal valuations in particular. These disputes often stem from a lack of a robust mass valuation standard aimed at preventing or minimizing valuation irregularities and the lack of uniformity, which undermines public confidence in, and the legal defensibility of, valuation rolls. Although international standards, such as the IAAO's Standard on Mass Appraisal of Real Property (IAAO, 2013), provide useful benchmarks, direct application to South Africa is constrained by significant contextual and regulatory differences. The gap between international best practice and South African realities highlights the need for a bespoke mass valuation standard that addresses the local legal and institutional context.

In response, South Africa introduced the Standard on Municipal Valuation for Property Rating (sMVPR), approved by the South African Council for the Property Valuers Profession (SACPVP). However, its impact is limited. It is primarily seen as an administrative guideline for implementing the Municipal Property Rates Act (MPRA) rather than a valuation-driven standard focused on technical issues such as accuracy, market alignment, or uniformity. Critically, the development process lacked broad-based consultation with valuation professionals and statutory bodies, resulting in limited sector buy-in and recognition. Additionally, the rapid urbanization and economic changes affecting the real estate market make it even more imperative for a standard.

Accordingly, this study responds to this gap by asking: What would a robust, context-specific framework for developing a South African mass valuation standard look like? Previous research on the subject, especially Erasmus et al. (2012); Foryś & Putek-Szeląg (2018) in South Africa, and

Ludiema et al. (2018) in Kenya, has made enormous contributions towards resolving the problems of accuracy and consistency; unfortunately, it failed to provide a framework leading to the development of country-specific mass valuation standards.

Literature Review

Mass valuation standards are essential for enhancing the accuracy, transparency, and fairness of property assessments across jurisdictions practicing ad valorem property taxation. The demand for such standards is most urgent in countries like South Africa, where inconsistencies in municipal valuation rolls have been attributed to the absence of localized mass valuation standards (Ngubeni, 2022). Developing countries often lack reliable sales data, regulatory control, and consistent methodologies, which further exacerbate inaccuracies in mass appraisal (Ayedun et al., 2012).

The absence of a mass valuation standard specific to these countries, including South Africa, highlights the pressing need to develop such a standard. It also follows that there is a need for a framework to guide the development of the localized mass valuation standard. According to Channing and Erasmus (2024), Dugeri (2011) and Babawale (2012), the international valuation standards like those from the IAAO or IVS are not tailor-made to fully respond to South Africa's unique property market conditions and thus must be adapted. The global practices where other countries modify international standards to meet their local requirements attest to this assertion (Dugeri et al, 2012; Smith & Johnson, 2018).

Several studies attribute valuation inaccuracy to systemic issues, such as outdated methods, lack of experience among valuers, and insufficient market data (Smith, 1986; Ayedun et al., 2012). These shortcomings have led to mistrust in the valuation profession and widespread public dissatisfaction with property tax assessments. In response, jurisdictions like the United States and Canada have developed and implemented mass valuation standards that stress quality assurance, transparency, and statistical validity (IAAO, 2013).

As described by Fayad et al. (1999), a framework is a reusable design component that defines abstract entities and their interactions to provide structure. In practical terms, frameworks serve as foundational structures to construct systems. The Cambridge Dictionary (2018) supports this view by defining a framework as "a supporting structure around which something can be built." In valuation contexts, this implies that a framework serves as a skeleton on which a standardized valuation model can be developed and implemented.

Moreover, stakeholder consultation has emerged as a critical factor in developing such frameworks. Experts caution against including non-professional stakeholders whose inputs might dilute the standard's technical integrity. Instead, professional bodies such as SACPVP, SAIV, and OVG are recommended as primary participants in the consultation process (IAAO, 2017). Their input is crucial in ensuring the standard prioritizes value accuracy, model transparency, and robust data governance.

Literature establishes a compelling case for developing a national mass valuation framework tailored to South Africa. Such a framework should improve valuation accuracy, promote uniformity, and increase public confidence. It must also provide guidance on stakeholder participation, valuation methodologies, data handling, and statistical testing, thus ensuring valuations align closely with market values (Smith, 1986; Ayedun et al., 2012; IAAO, 2013).

Mass valuation is the valuation of a group of real estate properties at the same valuation date, objectively, equitably and subject to statistical testing (IAAO, 2017; Gnat, 2020). Such a property group could refer to a property portfolio belonging to a person, company, government, or government

entity. In the context of municipal property rating and taxation, it relates to the valuation of all properties under a municipal jurisdiction on the same valuation date (IAAO, 2017). Mass valuation can be distinguished from the valuation of individual properties based on the mass valuation techniques and models employed. In the case of the latter, five traditional valuation methods are used, whilst for the former, models such as regression models, spatial models, automated valuation models, and recently, artificial intelligence-based models are employed (Yacim, 2020).

The need for standards in valuation cannot be overemphasized. Babawale (2012) cautions that professionalism cannot exist without standards, and runs the risk of abuse, mediocrity, complacency and conflict. A standard refers to a collection of rules, guidelines and characteristics established by consensus and approved by a recognized body, intended for common and repeated use to achieve the optimum degree of order in each context (ISO, 2024). Standards may be developed in consultation with stakeholders and take the form of technical specifications, test methods, management system frameworks, or codes of practice to ensure consistency, interoperability, quality, and safety across goods, services, and processes (ISO, 2024). Standards are voluntary, but may be incorporated into legislation or contracts, thus acquiring binding force in legal or commercial contexts. Standards may be subject to regular reviews to ensure their relevance amid technological, economic, and societal changes (ISO, 2024).

Mass valuation standards are thus concerned with the rules, guidelines, and characteristics commonly agreed upon by the valuation fraternity, such as simultaneously valuing a group of properties (IAAO, 2017; ISO, 2024). The valuation standards seek to ensure consistency in practices and accuracy in the value estimates, especially regarding ad valorem taxation. Learning from the standard on mass appraisal of real estate, mass valuation can be designed such that it can be used in the valuation of large property portfolios of various properties, including residential, farms, commercial, or institutional, required for financial statements and other reasons (IAAO, 2017).

Theoretical Framework

The theory guiding the study is the stakeholder theory advanced by Freeman (1984), which highlights that policies and standards gain legitimacy and sustainability when shaped by the active involvement of all groups who affect or are affected by them. This is because the mass valuation process involves multiple stakeholders with potentially conflicting interests. Accordingly, understanding the complex interplay of the contributions of different actors is essential for making decisions and building a framework that could be used to midwife a guideline. The guideline in this case is the framework that valuers, municipal officials, and ratepayer associations, as integral participants, must design for effective development of a valuation standard. Therefore, the different interests and perspectives of the participants above must be harnessed together to ensure that the valuation standards are technically robust and socially acceptable. This participatory process reinforces fairness and strengthens the accountability of institutions implementing the standards.

Governance theory complements the stakeholder theory by acknowledging that public goods are increasingly delivered through collaboration between state and non-state actors (Stoker, 1998). Within South Africa's democratic framework, valuation standards cannot be solely imposed by government or technical experts; they must reflect shared ownership across multiple actors. The process balances competing interests by structuring engagement based on stakeholders' legitimacy, power, and urgency. This helps prevent dominance by powerful groups while ensuring weaker but affected stakeholders, such as vulnerable communities, have a meaningful voice in shaping the standards.

Applying stakeholder and governance theories together provides a normative and practical guide for developing mass valuation standards that are both effective and equitable. Theories suggest that mapping and categorizing stakeholders according to their influence and stakes allows for strategic inclusion at each stage of standard development. This systematic participation builds trust, reduces resistance, and enhances democratic responsiveness. Furthermore, by embedding governance principles such as transparency, inclusivity, and accountability, the standards gain technical legitimacy from experts and social legitimacy from communities, leading to long-term stability and compliance in their application.

Methods

The study adopted a qualitative approach, drawing on expert insights from property valuers, regulators, and practitioners directly involved in municipal valuations. A combination of purposive and snowball sampling was used to select the participants for the interviews and focus-group discussions. For the interviews, thirteen municipal valuation experts were interviewed. These experts are known in at least one of the eight South African metropolitan municipalities or are involved with the valuation regulatory bodies and voluntary associations. All participants had at least ten years' experience in municipal valuation and valid professional registration with the SACPVP. The data was subjected to systematic coding, categorisation, and theme development. (Leedy and Ormrod, 2010)

Furthermore, two expert focus-group discussions were conducted to test the proposed framework. The first group discussion targeted the thirteen interview participants, of which only seven eventually availed themselves. The second focus group discussion included four additional participants from SAIV, SACPVP and OVG. In both the sessions a structured presentation which covered the framework's rationale, components, and expected outcomes, was presented. The proposed framework was subjected to probing and critical yet constructive discussions. The focus of the discussions was placed on statistical benchmarks, valuation education, and stakeholder inclusion. The feedback from the first session was used to revise and refine the proposed framework, which was then re-tabled in the second focus group discussion for final validation.

The validation of the framework, pursued in both focus group discussions, is grounded in Pidd's (2009) belief that a framework is a structured abstraction of real-world conditions that must be tested for real-world applicability. (Oberkampff and Trucano, 2008:717; Miser, 1993)

Findings

Out of the thirty experts invited to participate in the interviews, only thirteen experts participated in the interviews. Two of which are specialists who often represent ratepayers during objections to the valuation rolls were coded as Property Rates Expert (PRE). Seven participants are practicing professional valuers and are coded as Property Valuer in the Private Sector (PVPS). These participants also participated in the first focus group. The last four participants are employed in government as valuation experts and accordingly coded as Property Valuer in Government (PVG). Table 1 depicts the list of interview participants and their codes for anonymity.

Table 1: Interview and First Focus Group Participants

Professional Status	Academic Qualifications	Experience	Municipalities	Coding
Valuation Experts Government	ND, BSc	23 years	CoJ, CoT,	PVG001
	inND, BSc	26 years	CoCT, NMB	PVG004
	ND Real Estate, BSc	21 years	BC	PVG002
	MSc Real Estate	20 years	CoJ, CoT, EMM	PVG003
Valuation Expert Private Sector	ND	24 years	BC, NMB	PVPS001
	MSc Real Estate	22 years	CoJ, CoT	PVPS002
	MSc Building	28 years	CoJ	PVPS003
	ND	21 years	CoT, BC	PVPS004
	ND	21 years	NMB, EMM	PVPS005
	ND	23 years	CoJ, CoCT, eThekweni, EMM, BC, NMB	PVPS006
	ND	24 years	EMM, eThekweni, Mangaung, CoJ	PVPS007
Property Rates Expert	ND Real Estate	23 years	All metros	PRE001
	ND Real Estate, BSc	21 years	All metros	PRE002

Source: Ngubeni (2022)

The Use of Mass Valuation Standards

When participants were asked whether valuers in South Africa use international mass valuation standards, or any standards at all, particularly during municipal valuations, the general response indicated that standards are seldom applied in practice. For example, PVPS001 remarked:

"In my experience and knowledge, SA has never had a standard. Even the one published by the SACPVP only came to the fore in late 2021. Other values only mentioned the international standards. However, we have no proof that they used those standards in municipal valuations."

This position was reinforced by PRE001, who argued:

"I understand that the IVSC and the RICS do not have a mass valuation standard. I have also heard from some valuers who may know about the mass valuation standard of the IAAO. However, I doubt they ever use the standard during municipal valuation."

Contrary to this general view, PVPS007 suggested that some indirect reliance on international standards does occur:

"In the municipalities where we assist the municipal valuers in carrying out the general valuations, we integrate the IAAO standards. In fact, I was part of the IAAO committee that revised the international standards. However, the municipal valuers do not read the closeout reports we submit after completing our projects. This is why they would not know about the standards we used."

Overall, the evidence suggests a fragmented and inconsistent application of mass valuation standards in South Africa.

International versus Local Mass Valuation Standards

Whether South Africa should develop its own localized mass valuation standard or adopt international standards such as the IAAO's Standard on Mass Appraisal of Real Property, most respondents (80%) preferred a localized, tailor-made approach. However, some dissenting opinions emphasized the adequacy of international frameworks. PVPS007 stated:

"As private valuers, we have used the IAAO standards in metros such as the City of Johannesburg, eThekweni Metro, City of Cape Town, Ekurhuleni Metro and Mangaung. I really think that the IAAO standards are adequate for SA. All that needs to be done is to up-skill the municipal valuers in using standards. However, for acceptability, the standards must be adapted to the South African legal framework."

Support for a localized approach was strongly expressed by PVPS001:

"This is a difficult philosophical question; it must consider the nature of standard imposition. It is known that standards are a product of the societal value system. Generally, standards are developed somewhere for a particular purpose. Take, for instance, the RICS valuation standards. The English developed them for their societies, including the former colonies. By so doing, they get to impose their values on the rest of the world. So, because SA is trying to define its societal values in an African context, it must develop its own standard. However, the fact is that the real estate in SA is defined in Western terms. Western values inform selling and buying; adapting the IAAO's international standards may be realistic. Of course, SA should develop its own valuation standard, informed by its real estate values."

While this view was widely shared, pragmatic perspectives also emerged. For instance, PRE001 remarked:

"It will be foolish to reinvent the wheel. South Africa should adopt and adapt the IAAO's standard to the SA context. Even the SACPVP did exactly that when developing the newly adopted standard."

The findings, therefore, highlight a dual perspective. While most valuers support a localized standard aligned with South African socio-economic realities, there remains recognition of the practicality of adapting existing international models.

Procedural Concerns in Developing a Mass Valuation Standard

Participants expressed concern about the process followed in developing the Standard on Municipal Valuation for Property Rating (sMVPR), arguing that it lacked inclusivity and transparency. PRE002 stated:

"In relation to the development of the standard now published by the SACPVP, consultations were a one-way communication stream. We were never informed whether our views are acceptable or not."

Similarly, PVG004 raised concerns about the exclusion of key stakeholders:

"I have not seen the standard published by the SACPVP or SAIV. I am concerned that they went ahead and compiled a standard without consulting with us [municipal valuers], the valuers in the big municipalities. The metropolitan municipalities such as the City of Johannesburg, City of Cape Town and eThekweni, are responsible for valuing and rating 600,000 properties worth over R1 trillion."

When asked who should have been consulted in developing the sMVPR and future processes, participants (45%) called for wider consultation, including regulators, municipal valuers, and professional associations. PVG001 emphasized:

"All stakeholders must be invited. This includes all in the profession, municipalities, business owners, property owners, civic organizations, the council and the OVG."

Echoing this, PVG004 advocated genuine engagement:

"The envisaged participation or consultation process should allow for a two-way conversation between the stakeholders. Such a consultation should promote a meaningful dialogue geared towards reaching a consensus. Remember, SA is a constitutional democracy"

These insights underscore the need for participatory, inclusive, and dialogic approaches in developing valuation standards in South Africa.

Substantive Components of a Mass Valuation Standard

Participants identified key technical components that a mass valuation standard in South Africa should prioritize. These included: data collection, storage and maintenance; property classification; valuation approaches; modelling techniques; sales sampling; and market analysis. However, concerns were raised about the current standard. As PVG002 commented:

"I welcome the effort that was put into compiling the standard. However, the authors have confused a standard with procedure manuals. The standard does not address the issues a standard should address. Rather, it deals, for example, with the appeals board processes. It deals with the issues of the municipal rating policy. All these are not value-determining standards."

Aligning with international practice, PRE001 emphasized the relevance of adapting existing models:

"It is my thinking that the components of the IAAO standard remain relevant for SA's standard for mass valuation. The sMVPR includes more than what a mass valuation standard should contain, guided by the very reason for its existence. The reason for a mass valuation standard should be to guide the valuers in producing reliable, accurate and acceptable value estimates. Other issues covered in the sMVPR, such as rating policy, valuation appeals board, etc., can only make practical the MPRA, and not the main reason for the existence of mass valuation standard."

Thus, while consensus exists on the essential technical elements of a mass valuation standard, divergent views on scope exist, with some valuers cautioning against conflating technical valuation guidelines with broader administrative processes.

First Focus Group Discussion (Framework Validation)

Reaction to the Proposed Framework

Participants expressed approval when presented with the proposed framework for developing a mass valuation standard in South Africa. They considered the framework a sound basis for addressing the normative concerns that have historically contributed to valuation inaccuracy in mass appraisals. Both the procedural and substantive aspects were commended. The procedural framework was valued for its emphasis on intensified public consultation. In contrast, the substantive framework was applauded for its focus on technical elements necessary to produce more accurate market-related valuations. Importantly, there was consensus that the framework offers a credible foundation for improving valuation practice in the country.

As PVPS001 remarked during the discussion:

"This framework finally speaks to the gaps we highlighted during the interviews. The procedural clarity and substantive depth assure us that accuracy in municipal valuations can improve."

Solutions to Challenges of Valuation Inaccuracy

Participants agreed that the framework provides adequate direction for confronting the challenges associated with valuation inaccuracy. Although the framework did not elaborate on the precise content of the standard, it offered sufficient guidance on the envisaged process and on identifying the relevant problems confronting the mass valuation industry. The framework was seen as fertile ground for developing meaningful solutions to challenges such as poor consultation, legislative gaps, and procedural inconsistencies.

PRE001 added:

"Even if the details of the standard are not in the framework yet, the structure is there to ensure we can address accuracy challenges. For me, the emphasis on legislative support is crucial; otherwise, the standard will remain toothless."

Responsiveness to Public Participation Concerns

In reflecting on the weaknesses of the Standard on Municipal Valuation for Property Rating (sMVPR), most participants acknowledged that the proposed framework provides a corrective by enhancing opportunities for stakeholder engagement. They recommended greater inclusivity in future processes. However, an important caveat was raised: valuation standards are a specialized domain, and therefore, participation should primarily involve valuation professionals. Participants warned that involving non-valuation actors could dilute the technical focus and reproduce problems observed in the sMVPR.

PVG004 expressed concern:

"Consultation is vital, but it must be meaningful. We cannot have a repeat of the sMVPR, where comments were requested but not considered. This framework must create a true two-way conversation."

Similarly, PVPS007 observed:

“The consultation should be open, but technical valuation issues must remain in the hands of professionals. Otherwise, we risk having a standard that again drifts into rating policy and political issues.”

Coverage of Substantive Aspects of Mass Valuation

Participants agreed that the substantive components of the proposed framework broadly cover the major aspects required to guide valuers in determining market values in mass valuation. For example, the framework's proposals on property registers were supported, although it was noted that the Municipal Property Rates Act (MPRA) already provides for property registers. Participants emphasized the need to standardize property characteristics within the registers to ensure accuracy and consistency.

PV002 explained:

"The substantive Section is on the right track, but we must be careful not to confuse standards with procedure manuals. The focus must remain on data collection, modelling, and classification."

Additionally, participants stressed the need to dedicate attention to the mass valuation of non-residential properties, particularly commercial properties. PRE001 reinforced this by stating:

"The commercial property sector poses different challenges. If the framework does not explicitly address these, we will again have disputes undermining confidence in municipal valuations."

Workability and Adaptability of the Framework

Finally, participants were asked whether the proposed framework is workable in South Africa and adaptable for use in other developing countries. They expressed dissatisfaction with the process followed during the development of the sMVPR, describing it as exclusionary and tokenistic. Against this backdrop, they welcomed the proposed framework's emphasis on wide and genuine consultation consistent with South Africa's democratic ethos.

PVG001 commented:

“This framework would work in South Africa precisely because it is built on inclusivity and transparency. It acknowledges our democratic context, which was ignored during the sMVPR process.”

Moreover, PVPS007 linked its broader relevance to international practice:

“Other developing countries with similar markets can adapt this framework. We used IAAO standards before, but without local context, they fall short. This framework balances international practice with local realities.”

Second Focus Group Discussion (Framework Validation)

The second focus group discussion involved seven valuation experts who had not participated in the interviews or the first focus group. This cohort included practitioners from the Office of the Valuer-General (OVG) and the South African Council for the Property Valuers Profession (SACPVP). The revised framework, which incorporated the recommendations from the first focus group, was presented for further validation. The discussions were guided by three open-ended questions and sought to elicit

critical reflections on the second draft of the framework. Table 2 depicts the list of participants in the second focus group.

Table 2 depicts the list of participants in the second focus group discussion, by qualification, years of experience, and affiliation. They are coded (Focus Group Participant) FGP, followed by the participant number.

Table 2: Second Focus Group Participants

Professional Status	Academic Qualifications	Experience	Municipalities	Coding
Valuation Experts in Government	BSc, MBA	21 years	SACPVP	FGP001
	ND	15 years	OVG	FGP002
	BSc	10 years	CoGTA	FGP003
	BCom	22 years	SAIV	FGP004

Source: Research findings

Reaction to the Second Draft of the Framework

Participants confirmed that the revised framework was comprehensive and addressed the substantive concerns typically associated with developing a mass valuation standard. The group particularly commended the framework's emphasis on stakeholder participation, which they perceived as a corrective to the shortcomings of the Standard on Municipal Valuation for Property Rating (sMVPR).

FGP001 affirmed this position:

"The revised framework reflects the key issues raised earlier. It is broad enough to deal with valuation accuracy yet detailed enough to guide how we approach uniformity. It is a good step forward for South Africa."

Similarly, FGP004 observed:

"What I appreciate is the structure. It acknowledges the substantive and procedural aspects, which have been missing in the current standard."

Overall, participants unanimously endorsed the second draft as a solid foundation for the finalization of the framework.

Additional Issues to be Addressed in the Final Draft

Although broadly supportive, the participants identified areas that required further consideration. A central theme was the need to establish compulsory requirements for valuers conducting mass valuations, which they argued should include training in statistics and mass valuation methods. However, participants agreed that such requirements would necessitate amendments to the Municipal Property Rates Act (MPRA) rather than being embedded directly within the framework.

FGP002 explained:

“We cannot ignore the skills gap. Anyone conducting mass valuations should demonstrate competency in statistics and modelling. Otherwise, the framework will not achieve its goals.”

Linked to this concern, participants recommended enhancements to the valuation curriculum in South Africa. They suggested the introduction of specialised training modules, like the land reform valuation programme offered at the University of Cape Town.

FGP003 remarked:

"If we are serious about mass valuation, the universities must introduce a dedicated module. We are currently training valuers for single-property work, not mass valuation."

These proposals underscored the importance of aligning professional education and statutory regulation with the framework.

Scope of Stakeholder Participation

Building on debates from the first focus group, the participants revisited the question of whether the development of the mass valuation standard should extend beyond valuation professionals. While affirming the need for consultation, they cautioned against overextending participation to include non-specialists, arguing that such involvement could dilute the standard's technical focus.

FGP003 cautioned:

“The risk is that non-valuation stakeholders will push for issues unrelated to valuation accuracy. That is exactly what happened with the sMVPR. The focus shifted away from core valuation practice.”

Accordingly, the group advocated that participation be confined to professional valuers, voluntary valuation associations, and statutory bodies such as the SACPVP and the OVG.

FGP004 emphasized:

“Public participation is necessary, but the technical content of a valuation standard should remain in the hands of experts. We must learn from the mistakes of the past.”

This reinforced the findings of the first focus group, highlighting the need for a balance between inclusivity and technical rigor.

Overall Endorsement and Finalization

After rigorous discussion, the second focus group accepted and approved the revised framework. The participants agreed that the framework is workable and relevant to the South African context and provides a model that could be adapted for similar property markets in developing countries.

FGP002 concluded:

"The framework is practical and implementable. It sets South Africa toward international best practice while remaining locally relevant."

The interview results and two focus-group discussions reveal a broad consensus on the need for a structured framework to guide mass valuation in South Africa. Participants confirmed that the proposed framework adequately captures substantive and procedural dimensions, including stakeholder engagement, statistical standards for accuracy and uniformity, and legal defensibility.

While valuers emphasize that participation in framework development should remain confined to professional valuers and statutory bodies to safeguard technical integrity.

Discussion

The study found that international mass valuation standards are rarely applied in South African municipalities, echoing Ayedun et al.'s (2012) concerns about inconsistent methodologies in developing contexts. Limited uptake undermines transparency, confirming Smith's (1986) argument that poor practices erode trust. While some valuers use IAAO standards indirectly, broader adoption remains weak. Babawale (2012) stresses that professionalism cannot thrive without codified rules, and IAAO (2017) highlights statistical safeguards. A national framework is thus essential to enforce procedural clarity and quality assurance.

Participants preferred a localized framework but supported adapting international models such as IAAO. This aligns with Babawale (2012) and Dugeri (2011), who argue international standards are insufficiently tailored, while Smith and Johnson (2018) advocate hybrid models. Concerns over external imposition reflect ISO's (2024) view that standards embody societal values, while others stressed efficiency through adaptation. These insights suggest that South Africa must balance legitimacy with technical adequacy, developing its framework while leveraging global practices through contextualization.

In agreement with the stakeholder theory, Participants criticized the sMVPR process for excluding key municipal valuers and lacking reciprocal consultation, reflecting IAAO's (2013) and ISO's (2024) emphasis on consensus-based legitimacy. As Smith and Johnson (2018) show, exclusion weakens professional acceptance, while Babawale (2012) warns that professionalism risks mediocrity without collective ownership. However, participants stressed the need to restrict input to technical experts to preserve rigor. The findings highlight the importance of balanced consultation, ensuring inclusivity without compromising technical integrity in developing a framework.

Key substantive issues raised included property registers, data governance, modelling, and statistical testing, with criticism that sMVPR conflates technical standards with administrative processes. This contrasts with IAAO's (2017) guidance, distinguishing governance from valuation accuracy. Participants supported contextualized use of IAAO benchmarks, echoing Smith and Johnson (2018), while emphasizing statistical validity, consistent with Ayedun et al. (2012). Concerns about commercial property valuations reaffirm Smith's (1986) caution that inaccuracies are most damaging in complex markets. Technical rigor is therefore critical.

The framework was widely endorsed for addressing procedural and substantive concerns. Its inclusivity aligns with ISO's (2024) principles, while its statistical testing and calibration provisions reflect IAAO (2013) and Ayedun et al. (2012). Participants stressed legislative backing, echoing Babawale's (2012) concern that unenforceable standards weaken professionalism. Though valuers preferred restricting technical input to experts, they also advocated consultation for legitimacy, consistent with Smith and Johnson (2018). The framework aligns with the best global practice while addressing South Africa's systemic weaknesses.

The second group endorsed the framework but stressed professional competence, recommending statutory training and curriculum reforms. This reflects Ayedun et al. (2012) and Smith (1986), who link inaccuracies to poor training. Calls for a mass valuation curriculum support Babawale's (2012) emphasis on continuous development, while IAAO (2017) highlights professional capacity as critical. Participants cautioned against diluting technical focus, echoing Smith and Johnson (2018).

Acknowledging the framework's adaptability, they confirmed its relevance for South Africa and broader regional contexts.

The Purpose of the Framework

The findings laid the path for a proposal for the framework, which serves as a response to the gaps and challenges identified. The proposal seeks to provide a platform upon which the SA mass valuation practices may be standardized.

Figure 1 depicts the proposed framework, with major aspects highlighting the procedure for developing the mass valuation standard. The procedural aspects are then explained in detail. The diagram has nine main procedural aspects.

Figure 1: The Proposed Framework (Emphasis on Procedural Aspects)
Source: Ngubeni (2022)

Initiation of the Standard Development Process

The initiation of a mass valuation standard should be led by the Office of the Valuer-General (OVG), in partnership with the South African Council for the Property Valuers Profession (SACPVP) and the Department of Cooperative Governance and Traditional Affairs (CoGTA). This collaboration aligns with Section 45 of the MPRA, combining OVG's expertise, SACPVP's standards, and CoGTA's oversight, ensuring a comprehensive foundation for consistent national valuation practices.

Legislative Framework Review and Amendments

Developing a mass valuation standard requires legislative clarity to establish authority, scope, and accountability. Currently, the MPRA and PVA provide limited guidance, necessitating amendments to Section 7 of the PVA and Section 45 of the MPRA to empower the OVG. These changes would formalize oversight, mandate the standard's development, and enhance legitimacy, strengthening the legal framework for transparent and accountable municipal valuation practices across South Africa.

Development of the Mass Valuation Standard

A specialized team of valuation experts and policy drafters should develop the mass valuation standard, drawing insights from IAAO guidelines while tailoring it to South Africa's diverse property market. The standard must balance detailed technical specifications with broad applicability to address inconsistent practices. By incorporating enabling actions, procedures, and stakeholder engagement, the standard can ensure effectiveness, fairness, and consistency in guiding valuation practices nationwide.

Stakeholder Consultation and Participation

Defining the standard's scope requires structured consultation with key stakeholders, including valuers, professional bodies, municipalities, ratepayer groups, and CoGTA. Meaningful engagement ensures the standard reflects technical realities, addresses stakeholder concerns, and aligns with democratic principles of participation. Inclusive involvement strengthens legitimacy, minimizes conflicts, and builds collective ownership, thereby enhancing the credibility and broad acceptance of the standard in municipal valuation practices across South Africa.

First Revision of the Draft Mass Valuation Standard

After drafting, the mass valuation standard undergoes stakeholder review to incorporate diverse inputs and refine technical clarity. The revision process ensures compliance with the MPRA, addresses practical challenges, and integrates improvements for broader acceptance. This iterative review strengthens the technical and legal robustness of the standard while building confidence among practitioners and stakeholders, preparing it for public consultation and further refinement.

Invite Written Public Comments on the Draft Mass Valuation Standard

The revised draft should be released for a minimum 60-day public comment period, ensuring inclusivity and transparency. Feedback from individuals, organizations, and professional groups must be systematically considered when refining the standard. Publicity through government websites, professional bodies, and media will encourage widespread participation. This process strengthens trust and accountability and ensures the standard addresses practical realities while fostering broad-based legitimacy and support.

Second Revision of the Draft Mass Valuation Standard

Public feedback must be integrated into a second draft revision, which is then submitted to the OVG and SACPVP for review and approval. This process guarantees the standard's compliance with legal and professional requirements while reflecting stakeholder priorities. Upon completion, the document evolves into an authoritative and practical guideline, ensuring consistency, fairness, and credibility in mass valuation across South Africa's municipalities.

Publication of the Final Mass Valuation Standard

The final mass valuation standard should be published following approval, with a clear implementation timeline. Dissemination via government platforms, professional bodies, and workshops will ensure accessibility and readiness. Offering training and multilingual resources can support municipalities and valuers, ensuring effective application. Publication establishes the standard as an official reference point for reliable, transparent, uniform valuation practices nationwide, strengthening credibility and compliance.

Commencement of the Implementation of the Final Standard

On the effective date, all municipalities and valuation bodies must comply with the new standard, ensuring uniformity in property valuations. Implementation should be supported by training, technical assistance, and resource tools. Monitoring mechanisms and feedback channels will address challenges, promote accountability, and allow timely updates. This approach ensures the standard remains responsive, effective, and aligned with evolving valuation practices and legislative requirements.

Substantive Aspects of the Framework

Based on the literature, document review, and empirical study conducted, the proposed framework addresses seven aspects. Figure 2 illustrates these aspects in their order. To the substantive issues in the mass valuation standard.

Figure 2: Proposed Substantive Framework

Source: Ngubeni (2022)

Compilation of Property Register

The MPRA (2004) mandates municipalities to compile complete property registers, covering land parcels and sectional titles. These registers, containing zoning, ownership, erf numbers, and LPI codes, underpin planning, analysis, and mass valuation. Consistency enhances transparency, accuracy, and efficient updates, fostering trust (CoGTA, 2020).

Property Data Collection and Maintenance

Accurate data collection and maintenance are crucial for mass valuation. A centralized repository with quality assurance protocols ensures accuracy, timeliness, and consistency (CoGTA, 2020). Standardized formats reduce costs and improve efficiency (SACPVP, 2021). Clear update protocols enhance transparency while protecting privacy, enabling robust collaboration.

Market Analysis Reports

Comprehensive market analyses are vital for statutory mass valuations (MPRA, 2004). A standard should mandate publicly disclosed reports detailing sales samples, timeframes, and methodologies

(SACPVP, 2021). Standardized formats deter outdated data use, enhance comparability, and ensure transparency, strengthening confidence in valuation practices (CoGTA, 2020).

Developing and Calibrating Mass Valuation Models

Mass valuation must reflect market values using efficient, transparent models (MPRA, 2004). Guidance should support multiple approaches, CAMA, MRA, or ANN, depending on data and property types (SACPVP, 2021). Standards must address calibration, depreciation, and income data collection, ensuring fairness and applicability (CoGTA, 2020).

Valuation Testing and Validation

Validation ensures accuracy and fairness in mass valuations. Standards should prescribe diagnostics and sales-ratio analysis (SACPVP, 2021). Tools such as COD, RMSE, and MAPE define acceptable thresholds (CoGTA, 2020). Transparent validation enhances accountability and provides defensible outcomes for legal and administrative reviews.

Valuation of the Properties

Validated models must be applied to all registered properties, including sectional titles, farms, and commercial premises (MPRA, 2004). Values must reflect the legislated valuation date, with quality checks for anomalies. Final outputs underpin General Valuation Rolls for municipal revenue (IAAO, 2013; SACPVP, 2021).

Valuation Resources Management

Mass valuations require coordinated human, technological, and financial resources. Standards should guide staffing, outsourcing, and technological integration with CAMA, GIS, and finance systems (CoGTA, 2020; SACPVP, 2021). Strong data protection measures involving encryption, access controls, and backups to safeguard information while ensuring efficient and resilient valuation processes.

Conclusion

The proposed framework may not immediately resolve accuracy and reliability issues in mass valuation, but it establishes a solid foundation for developing national valuation standards in South Africa. Although tailored to South Africa's municipal valuation context, it can be adapted for other developing countries with similar real estate maturity. While valuation standards should guide rather than prescribe practice, enforceability is essential, particularly in municipal valuations and their use in financial reporting.

Regulatory and oversight bodies must use the standard as a benchmark for assessing valuation accuracy. For this to be effective, laws such as the Property Valuation Act (PVA) and Municipal Property Rates Act (MPRA) must explicitly mandate the standard's use. Therefore, legal and policy reforms are necessary to define the standard's authority. The proposed framework provides a solid basis for initiating these critical discussions among stakeholders, supporting the creation of a credible, enforceable, and contextually relevant mass valuation standard for South Africa.

Disclosure Statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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Does ESG Still Signal Value When the Lights Go Out? A Machine Learning Analysis of REIT Behaviour Under Load Shedding *Oluwaseun Damilola Ajayi¹; Emmanuel Kofi Gavu², Bamidele Tosin Owosuyi³; Cyril Ayodele Ajayi⁴*

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Abstract

South Africa's persistent load shedding crisis has introduced a distinct form of systemic infrastructure risk into its capital markets, yet the role of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) signals in mediating investor behaviour under such extreme energy stress remains theoretically and empirically underdeveloped. This study interrogates whether ESG indicators influence real estate investment trust (REIT) performance during episodic and chronic power disruptions, and how investors recalibrate expectations in response to signal variance across ESG dimensions. Drawing on a longitudinal dataset of over 48,000 daily observations, we employ an integrated methodological approach encompassing wavelet coherence, event study regression, difference-in-differences estimation, quantile regression, machine learning models (Random Forest, XGBoost), and reinforcement learning-based portfolio simulations. Results demonstrate that ESG signals exhibit time-frequency dependence with REIT returns, but investor receptivity is context-contingent: environmental signals are positively priced during crisis episodes, whereas governance signals attract discounting. Machine learning models significantly outperform conventional approaches in forecasting return patterns under stress, and adaptive portfolio strategies increasingly converge toward ESG alignment as load shedding severity escalates. This paper contributes novel empirical evidence that ESG signals function as conditional risk-mitigation instruments in frontier markets, with implications for investor strategy, ESG regulation, and infrastructure-responsive financial policy.

Keywords: South African REITs; Load Shedding; ESG Performance; Investor Attention; Machine Learning Forecasting; Infrastructure Risk.

Introduction

South Africa's real estate investment landscape is increasingly characterised by exposure to deep infrastructural fragilities; none more pronounced than its enduring energy crisis. Load shedding, once an episodic inconvenience, has metastasized into a systemic economic threat, with over 300 days of power cuts recorded in 2023 alone (Montmasson-Clair & Moilwa, 2023). For listed real estate investment trusts (REITs), which rely on uninterrupted utility supply to maintain occupancy, income stability, and operating efficiency, the consequences are profound and persistent. In a market where asset values are anchored to long-term cash flows, energy insecurity disrupts valuation fundamentals, compresses yields, and introduces new layers of tenant and operational risk (Jackson & Berrisford, 2022). Within this context, environmental, social, and governance (ESG) metrics have been widely promoted as instruments of resilience and long-term value preservation. Yet, the mainstreaming of ESG in emerging capital markets has often outpaced its empirical validation, especially under conditions of systemic infrastructure stress. ESG is frequently invoked as a "signal of sustainability," but its credibility in periods of infrastructural breakdown remains uncertain. Therefore, we ask: Do investors still price ESG when markets are driven by rolling blackouts, failing public utilities, and macro-level grid failure? Do ESG signals buffer risk, or do they collapse under pressure?

This paper critically examines how REIT investors in South Africa respond to ESG signals during escalating phases of load shedding. Specifically, it interrogates whether ESG attributes, disaggregated into environmental, social, and governance components retain explanatory power under crisis conditions, and whether investor attention adapts as infrastructure failure becomes chronic. It further examines whether ESG indicators serve as return predictors, resilience signals, or merely reputational artefacts when market stress peaks. To address this, we employ a multi-method empirical framework that combines wavelet coherence analysis, event study regression, quantile modelling, causal interaction estimation, machine learning forecasting, and reinforcement learning portfolio simulation. This approach allows us to uncover when, how, and under what crisis intensities

ESG is priced. This paper tells the story of ESG's behavioural and financial relevance when the lights go out (literally). The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews literature on ESG, REITs, and load shedding risks. Section 3 explains the data and methods, including econometric and machine learning models. Section 4 presents and discusses the results with implications for investors, regulators, and policymakers. Section 5 concludes with key findings and future research directions.

2. Literature Review

2.1 ESG and REIT Performance: The Evidence So Far

The intersection between ESG performance and REIT returns has attracted growing academic interest, particularly as investors increasingly demand sustainability-integrated financial strategies. In developed markets, studies suggest that ESG-aligned REITs benefit from reduced cost of capital (Derwall et al., 2011), superior risk-adjusted returns (Fuerst et al., 2020), and resilience during downturns (Devine & Yates, 2023). ESG-focused real estate portfolios are also associated with higher tenant retention and lower vacancy risks, especially for green-certified buildings (Eichholtz et al., 2010; Chegut et al., 2014). However, much of this literature is grounded in stable, mature markets with reliable institutional infrastructure. Empirical results from emerging markets remain scarce, fragmented, and often inconclusive. Moreover, most studies examine ESG as a static factor without accounting for its dynamic interactions with exogenous shocks such as infrastructure collapse or regulatory instability.

2.2 ESG Signals in Emerging and Frontier Markets

Emerging market contexts introduce significant noise into the ESG-return relationship due to volatile macroeconomic conditions, weak enforcement of sustainability standards, and variable data quality (Arayssi et al., 2020; Amidu et al., 2022). In Africa, ESG disclosures are often driven by reputational signalling rather than substantive governance change (Tariq & Abbas, 2021). This weakens the credibility of ESG signals, especially in markets where investor trust in institutional integrity is low. Yet, paradoxically, it is in these high-volatility environments that ESG may matter most. When conventional financial metrics are distorted by externalities such as power outages or corruption, ESG could serve as a compensatory heuristic for investors seeking long-term stability. The challenge lies in establishing whether and under what conditions ESG signals retain explanatory power amidst systemic dysfunction.

2.3 Load Shedding as Systemic Investment Risk

Load shedding in South Africa is an enduring systemic threat that permeates virtually all sectors of the economy. Research has shown that electricity insecurity reduces productivity (Altieri & Nicholls, 2021), depresses firm valuations (Liedtke, 2022), and increases investor uncertainty (IMF, 2023). For REITs, the effects are particularly severe: increased operating costs, reduced net operating income, disrupted rental flows, and heightened tenant risk all undermine portfolio stability (Berrisford & Kaggwa, 2022). Yet few studies have explicitly examined the capital market consequences of chronic infrastructure failure, especially how it interacts with ESG signalling in listed property markets. This paper addresses this void by focusing on the ESG-REIT-load shedding nexus using South Africa as a living case of grid instability meets financial exposure.

2.4 Theoretical Framing: Signals, Risk, and Investor Adaptation

This study draws on signalling theory (Spence, 1973) to conceptualise ESG scores as market signals through which firms attempt to communicate non-observable attributes such as resilience, governance quality, or environmental stewardship. However, the efficacy of such signals depends on market trust, noise, and interpretive context. In times of systemic stress, investors may reassess the credibility or materiality of ESG dimensions (Giese et al., 2021). In parallel, we engage with risk pricing theory, particularly under market incompleteness. Here, ESG is treated not merely as a reputational tool, but as a latent factor influencing perceived tail risk exposure. Under load shedding, we hypothesize that environmental ESG scores may act as downside buffers, while governance scores are scrutinized for institutional competence.

3. Methodology

3.1 Data and Variable Construction

This study utilizes high-frequency panel data on South African Real Estate Investment Trusts (REITs), ESG scores, and load shedding indicators from 2013 to 2024. REIT price and return data were sourced from the JSE Top 40 Index constituents, while ESG scores were obtained from Bloomberg ESG Disclosure Scores, disaggregated into E, S, and G dimensions. Load shedding intensity was proxied using two novel measures: (i) *LSSI-smooth*, a smoothed severity index reflecting Eskom stage-level declarations; and (ii) *Stage Max*, capturing daily blackout ceiling levels. Additional control variables include 5-day and 10-day realized volatility, abnormal returns, dividend yield, and sentiment-based investor attention indices. All variables were tested for stationarity using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test, confirming $I(0)$ properties. Table 1 provides a detailed summary of the variables used, including descriptions, data sources, and measurement frequency.

Table 1: Variable Definitions and Data Sources

Variable	Description	Source	Frequency
RET	Daily REIT return (%)	JSE Top 40 Index	Daily
ESG	Composite ESG score (0–100)	Bloomberg ESG Dataset	Daily
ENV	Environmental score component of ESG	Bloomberg ESG Dataset	Daily
GOV	Governance score component of ESG	Bloomberg ESG Dataset	Daily
LSSI	Load Shedding Severity Index (smoothed)	Constructed from Eskom Stage Logs	Daily
StageMax	Maximum load shedding stage per day	Eskom Daily Reports	Daily
AbnRET	Abnormal return (market-adjusted)	Author's computation using market model	Daily
RealVol_5D	5-day realised volatility of REIT returns	Computed from intraday squared returns	Daily
RealVol_10D	10-day realised volatility of REIT returns	Computed from intraday squared returns	Daily
GoogleTrend	Investor attention index derived from Google search volume	Google Trends API	Daily

3.2 Empirical Strategy and Model Development

To examine the multidimensional dynamics between ESG signalling, load shedding, and REIT performance, we adopt a six-pronged methodological framework:

3.2.1 Wavelet Coherence Analysis

To capture co-movement in the time–frequency domain, wavelet coherence analysis was employed to explore how ESG signals and REIT returns evolve together under different temporal resolutions and market regimes (Torrence & Compo, 1998). This method enables us to disentangle short-term from long-term investor sensitivity, crucial in unstable energy contexts.

3.2.2 Event Study Regression

A modified event study design was applied to isolate the abnormal return response of REITs during scheduled load shedding windows, controlling for ESG levels and regime shifts. Regression models interact ESG categories with event windows and crisis indicators, revealing conditional return patterns across governance and environmental dimensions (MacKinlay, 1997).

3.2.3 Difference-in-Differences (DiD) Models

To examine shifts in investor attention post-load shedding crises, DiD models were estimated, with interaction terms capturing the moderating role of ESG quality. Market liquidity and short-run volatility served as dependent proxies for sentiment-driven trading, offering insights into behavioural asymmetries and post-crisis convergence patterns.

3.2.4 Quantile Regression Modelling

Recognising the nonlinear and heterogeneous effects of ESG under stress, quantile regression was employed to model tail-dependent impacts of load shedding and ESG interaction on REIT returns. This approach identifies asymmetric effects that traditional mean-based models would obscure (Koenker & Bassett, 1978).

3.2.5 Machine Learning Forecasting

To assess predictive efficacy, we implemented Random Forest, XGBoost, ElasticNet, and LSTM to forecast REIT returns, incorporating ESG and load-shedding features. Model performance was benchmarked using R^2 , RMSE, and MAE. SHAP values were used to interpret feature importance, offering explainable AI insights into variable influence.

3.2.6 Reinforcement Learning Portfolio Strategy

We further developed a reinforcement learning (RL) agent trained to adaptively allocate weights to ESG-tilted REITs under varying load shedding stages. Using Q-learning, we modelled cumulative reward trajectories and optimal ESG decile-stage pairings, demonstrating real-time adaptability under systemic energy shocks.

3.3 Variable Definitions and Descriptions

All variable definitions, summary statistics, correlation matrices, and stationarity tests are provided in the Appendix. ESG scores are expressed as percentile-based continuous variables. Load shedding is encoded via both discrete categorical and continuous smoothed indices. Investor attention is derived from Google Trends and sentiment-weighted financial discourse. Abnormal returns are calculated using a market-adjusted model, while volatility is derived from intraday squared returns.

4. Results

4.1. Descriptive statistics

Table 2 reports detailed descriptive and distributional statistics for the study's key variables across 48,768 daily observations. As expected in a turbulent emerging market context, REIT daily returns and abnormal returns are centred around zero with high dispersion ($SD = 2.7\%$ and 2.5% respectively) and exhibit extreme tails (min: -37.1% , max: $+76.5\%$), indicating the presence of sharp drawdowns and infrequent large gains. High kurtosis and positive skewness in returns affirm the presence of non-normal, event-driven market behaviour and this proves the importance of applying non-linear and tail-sensitive modelling techniques later in the analysis. This return structure aligns with earlier findings on African REIT volatility and asymmetric reactions to crisis events (see Yartey & Adjasi, 2023; Ndlovu & Sibanda, 2020). Volatility measures (5-day and 10-day realised volatility) are positively skewed with long right tails (max values: 7.06 and 4.86 respectively), signalling clustered risk and persistent uncertainty over short horizons; particularly during blackout periods. The coefficient of variation ($CV > 1$) confirms significant relative volatility, reinforcing the view that REITs in load-shedding-prone markets require risk-adjusted performance diagnostics beyond traditional metrics.

ESG scores reveal informative asymmetries. While the mean overall ESG score is moderately high (60.0), disaggregation shows governance (mean = 69.9) outperforms environmental (65.0) and social (55.1) dimensions. The wide dispersion and high CV in the social pillar, coupled with a floor of 0, suggest large inconsistencies in disclosure or performance in that domain with a view to validating prior critiques of fragmented ESG integration in African listed property firms (Mnguni & Groenewald, 2022). The rolling beta of REITs to ESG trends is statistically near-zero but varies enough to motivate the modelling of conditional ESG sensitivity under crisis conditions. Load shedding metrics exhibit stark right-skewness: Stage Max (mean = 0.51, skew = 2.54) and LSSI (mean = 0.61, max = 10.86) highlight the dominance of extreme energy events. Their fat-tailed structure implies systemic, not cyclical risk which focuses on gradual climate transitions (Campiglio et al., 2018). The Load Shedding Shock dummy (mean = 0.109) shows blackout shocks occur in approximately 11% of trading days, confirming their non-trivial market influence. The Attention Index (Google-based sentiment) is mean-zero by construction but positively skewed (skew = 1.396), and this suggests that investor attention intensifies disproportionately in response to shocks, with implications for ESG signal

reception under stress. Table 2 provides foundational evidence of asymmetric risk exposure, ESG reporting gaps, and the behavioural nature of investor reactions. For investors, it highlights the unreliability of ESG scores as standalone risk shields, especially when structural disruptions like energy crises dominate. For regulators, the data reveal the need for enhanced granularity in ESG reporting; particularly in the social dimension. For government, the concentration of risk during blackout events directly links energy governance to asset pricing dynamics, reinforcing the urgency of infrastructure stability as an economic priority.

Table 2: Summary Statistics of Key Variables

Variable	Obs	Mean	StdDev	Min	5%	Q1	Median	Q3	Max	Skewness	Kurtosis	CV
Return	48752	0.000	0.027	-0.371	-0.033	-0.006	0.000	0.006	0.765	1.338	41.662	0.000
Abnormal Return	48272	0.000	0.025	-0.363	-0.032	-0.008	0.000	0.007	0.457	0.774	26.355	0.000
Volatility_5d	48688	0.286	0.325	0.000	0.000	0.111	0.201	0.343	7.056	3.857	29.258	1.136
Volatility_10d	48608	0.307	0.300	0.000	0.000	0.145	0.224	0.361	4.860	3.291	19.871	0.977
Rolling Beta-ESG	48272	0.000	0.001	-0.005	-0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.005	0.404	12.360	0.000
ESG-Overall	48768	60.028	9.958	15.370	43.701	53.327	60.014	66.727	99.262	-0.003	-0.018	0.166
ESG-Environmental	48768	65.027	12.041	20.286	45.191	56.937	65.063	73.190	100.000	-0.019	-0.074	0.185
ESG-Social	48768	55.062	14.939	0.000	30.410	44.924	55.150	65.239	100.000	-0.021	-0.044	0.271
ESG-Governance	48768	69.955	8.005	35.008	56.827	64.555	69.932	75.298	100.000	0.004	-0.002	0.114
Stage Max	48768	0.512	1.241	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	6.000	2.538	5.842	2.424
LSSI smooth	48768	0.605	1.444	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.286	10.857	3.297	12.404	2.387
Load Shedding Shock	48768	0.109	0.312	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.000	2.505	4.276	2.862
Attention Index	48768	0.000	1.500	-2.152	-1.629	-1.101	-0.318	0.589	6.766	1.396	2.250	0.000

4.2. Pairwise Correlations among REIT Returns, ESG Scores, Load Shedding Indicators, and Market Risk Variables.

Table 3 presents the Pearson correlation matrix capturing the linear relationships between REIT returns, ESG scores, load shedding indicators, and associated control variables. As expected, REIT returns exhibit a strong positive correlation with abnormal returns (0.835), reinforcing the validity of abnormal return construction in this high-frequency context. However, the correlation between REIT returns and realised volatility is weak (0.055 for 5-day, 0.036 for 10-day), suggesting a disconnect between price fluctuation intensity and contemporaneous return levels. Volatility measures are highly interrelated (0.855), confirming temporal persistence of risk exposure. Strikingly, correlations between ESG scores and financial performance variables are uniformly weak. The composite ESG score has near-zero correlation with returns (0.006), and its subcomponents (Environmental, Social, and Governance) display equally muted or negative associations. These results align with critiques in the African ESG literature that suggest a disconnect between reported ESG performance and real financial resilience (Mnguni & Groenewald, 2022). The weak correlations also reflect a broader limitation of ESG as a signal in high-friction markets where disclosure quality, enforcement, and investor interpretation vary considerably (Capelle-Blancard & Petit, 2019). Moreover, the low correlation between ESG scores and the rolling beta to ESG trends suggests that market sensitivity to ESG narratives may be structurally absent or episodic rather than systematic.

The load shedding indicators (*StageMax*, *LSSI*, and *Load Shedding Shock*) exhibit strong internal alignment (*StageMax* and *LSSI*: 0.785) and this confirms their validity as proxies for blackout severity. Their negligible or negative correlations with ESG scores suggest that energy resilience is not embedded within ESG frameworks in this setting. Importantly, the Attention Index shows moderate correlation with blackout variables (*0.440 with StageMax*, *0.474 with LSSI*), but remains weakly associated with returns (*-0.004*), and this indicates that spikes in investor attention during crises do not necessarily translate into market performance. This highlights the behavioural and informational inefficiencies within ESG signalling under infrastructure stress. Table 3 reveals a disconnection between ESG ratings and both REIT performance and systemic risk exposure. For investors, the table invites caution in interpreting ESG scores as protective during blackouts or volatility spikes. For regulators, it raises concerns about the superficiality of ESG metrics when decoupled from operational resilience. For government stakeholders, the evidence reflects a broader policy gap that blackout risk remains financially material, but ESG frameworks fail to meaningfully internalise or communicate this risk to capital markets.

Table 3: Correlation Statistics

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M
Return	1.000												
Abnormal Return	0.835	1.000											
Volatility_5d	0.055	0.042	1.000										
Volatility_10d	0.036	0.023	0.855	1.000									
Rolling Beta-ESG	0.001	-0.010	0.065	0.084	1.000								
ESG-Overall	0.006	0.005	-0.005	-0.003	-0.002	1.000							
ESG-Environmental	-0.004	0.000	-0.001	-0.005	-0.002	0.001	1.000						
ESG-Social	-0.005	0.000	0.006	0.008	0.013	-0.007	0.003	1.000					
ESG-Governance	0.000	-0.001	-0.002	-0.002	0.006	-0.002	-0.003	-0.005	1.000				
Stage Max	0.000	0.000	0.028	0.028	0.015	-0.003	-0.001	0.001	0.001	1.000			
LSSI smooth	-0.008	0.000	0.024	0.023	0.025	-0.001	-0.001	0.002	0.000	0.785	1.000		
Load Shedding Shock	-0.004	0.000	0.029	0.024	0.008	-0.007	-0.002	0.000	0.002	0.656	0.423	1.000	
Attention Index	-0.004	0.000	-0.023	-0.029	-0.003	-0.006	0.003	0.000	-0.001	0.440	0.474	0.302	1.000

4.3. Time-Varying Investor Attention to Load Shedding: Sentiment Shocks and Structural Persistence

Figure 1 presents an empirical validation of a rarely quantified but critical behavioural mechanism in ESG finance of the dynamic co-evolution of investor attention, ESG salience, and blackout severity in South Africa's REIT market. The figure plots a daily time series of the Google-based Attention Index (mean-zero, $SD = 1.50$), alongside the Load Shedding Stage Max and LSSI metrics from 2013 to 2024. Three distinct behavioural regimes emerge: (1) a latent low-attention plateau from 2013–2018, (2) an episodic spike era from 2019–2021, and (3) a high-attention volatility regime from 2022 onward. This trajectory is structurally tethered to the intensification of Eskom's failures and the market's evolving cognitive association between load shedding and ESG relevance. Attention surges, particularly those breaching the $+2$ SD threshold (for example July 2020, June 2022, March 2023), align tightly with prolonged Stage 4+ load shedding events and coincide with major ESG disclosure periods, as confirmed by event data. These peaks exhibit slow decay rates which often requires 15–20 trading days to revert to baseline. This prolonged attentional half-life is analytically significant. It suggests that investors recalibrate ESG interpretability windows, with a view to scrutinising environmental and governance disclosures more acutely in the wake of infrastructure failure. The attention curve's positive skew (1.396) and excess kurtosis (2.250) affirm the tail-driven nature of sentiment that ESG becomes salient through shock-triggered narrative anchoring.

This pattern introduces an urgent theoretical update to ESG signalling models that in high-volatility contexts, investor attention operates as a nonlinear amplifier. Importantly, during the 2022–2024 period, we observe attention spikes even in the absence of actual load shedding escalations. This decoupling points to a memory effect: the market begins to anticipate blackout consequences, pricing in ESG narratives in a pre-emptive, reflexive manner. The Attention Index, once reactive, becomes anticipatory, indicating a maturation of investor heuristics and an evolving belief system around ESG's predictive value under state failure. The figure's juxtaposition of Stage Max (mean = 0.51, max = 6.0) and LSSI (mean = 0.61, max = 10.86) with attention peaks reveals a critical asymmetry: investor response is not proportional to load shedding levels, but to their duration and perceived mismanagement. For instance, the July 2020 spike occurred during sustained Stage 2 outages; less severe in numeric stage, but prolonged and poorly communicated. This underscores the informational and governance dimensions of ESG interpretation: markets do not merely react to electricity loss but to signals of state incapacity and firm-level preparedness.

For investors, this figure shows a new pricing logic which is attention-adjusted ESG. Portfolios that ignore sentiment volatility risk mistiming exits and mispricing resilience. ESG must be curated for attention-aligned moments. For regulators, the figure demonstrates that high ESG scores are not credible unless disclosures align with behavioural inflection points; particularly during energy and governance crises. Mandating ESG reports without structuring them around public sentiment dynamics will dilute their market relevance. For government, the persistent elevation in attention following load shedding surges exposes a reputational crisis: state failure is now embedded in investor cognition and conditions the interpretive power of ESG itself. This invites a reframing of energy governance as a key determinant of national asset pricing narratives. We opine that these results show a deeper truth that ESG's value is modulated by when and how the market pays attention. In South Africa's REITs space, ESG becomes most meaningful precisely when the grid fails, the news cycle intensifies, and investors search for stabilising signals. This chart, therefore, is a visualisation of how financial meaning is constructed, broken, and reconstructed under crisis.

Figure 1: Co-Evolution of Investor Attention, ESG Importance, and Load Shedding Severity in South Africa (2013–2024)

4.4. Investor Attention, Energy Crises, and the Limits of ESG Signalling: A Post-Load Shedding Market Response Analysis

Table 4 offers deep insights into how investor attention, ESG profiles, and post-load shedding crises interact to influence market dynamics in South African REITs. Notably, the attention index is significantly negative across liquidity (-0.125 , $p = 0.013$) and volatility dimensions (-0.036 , -0.033 ; $p < 0.001$), suggesting that heightened investor attention often a proxy for fear, uncertainty, or noise trading (Da et al., 2011; Vlastakis & Markellos, 2012) coincides with destabilised trading conditions, reduced liquidity, and elevated turbulence. This contradicts traditional views that attention inherently signals confidence or stability and instead supports the view that in emerging markets, attention surges may represent speculative herding or reflexive panic. The post-crisis coefficient is negative and significant across all models, reinforcing that market conditions deteriorate in the aftermath of energy crises, with reductions in liquidity (-0.755 , $p = 0.049$) and sustained volatility. This is consistent with studies showing how infrastructure shocks and energy insecurity can have long-lasting financial repercussions (Asongu et al., 2022). However, a more nuanced dynamic is revealed through the interaction term: the positive coefficients on Attention Index \times Post-Crisis (0.333 for liquidity, $p = 0.067$) suggest that investor attentiveness in crisis recovery phases may attenuate volatility and improve liquidity, possibly through anticipatory repositioning or a recalibration of perceived REIT risk premia. This mirrors adaptive expectation theory (Evans & Honkapohja, 2001), where informed investors adjust more rationally during persistent macro stress.

Interestingly, high ESG quality; measured by High ESG–Overall and its interactions is not significantly associated with liquidity or volatility, nor does it significantly mediate post-crisis sentiment. This suggests that despite ESG’s conceptual role in enhancing resilience (Krüger, 2015; Fatemi et al., 2018), it is not (yet) priced as a protective factor in South Africa’s REIT market during systemic energy shocks. Possible explanations include ESG score opacity, greenwashing concerns, or a weak link between ESG narratives and bottom-line performance during crises. This challenges assumptions that ESG-aligned REITs will be automatically rewarded in periods of elevated systemic risk, especially in frontier markets where ESG data is thinner and investor trust is nascent. The LSSI-smooth variable is significantly positive with volatility ($p = 0.002$ – 0.001), affirming that energy instability is a critical macrofinancial risk. This finding aligns with recent literature suggesting that load shedding not only distorts real estate operations but also amplifies market-wide uncertainty and capital allocation inefficiencies (Boako & Alagidede, 2017). From an integrated stakeholder perspective, the findings urge investors to be cautious in interpreting attention as a stabilising force. They must also re-evaluate the role of ESG in portfolio hedging during energy crises. REIT managers should not assume ESG ratings alone will cushion them in volatile environments; rather, they must adopt deeper crisis-preparedness and disclosure frameworks. For policymakers, the disconnect between ESG and market behaviour underscores the

need for more credible, stress-sensitive ESG reporting regulations. Finally, ESG rating agencies and academic researchers must reconsider the static nature of ESG scores in contexts of recurring infrastructure shocks and evolve toward more dynamic, context-aware ESG metrics that capture resilience beyond branding.

Table 4: DiD Regression of Investor Sentiment towards ESG Signals During Post Load Shedding Crisis

Variable	Liquidity Volume		Volatility (5-Day)		Volatility (10-Day)	
	Coef.	p	Coef.	p	Coef.	p
Intercept	10.778	0.000***	-1.390	0.000***	-1.341	0.000***
Attention Index	-0.125	0.013**	-0.036	0.000***	-0.033	0.000***
Post Crisis	-0.755	0.049**	-0.517	0.000***	-0.493	0.000***
Attention Index × Post Crisis	0.333	0.067*	0.073	0.070*	0.073	0.062*
High ESG – Overall	0.081	0.102	-0.004	0.700	0.001	0.952
Attention Index × High ESG – Overall	-0.022	0.394	0.007	0.150	0.009	0.077*
Post Crisis × High ESG – Overall	0.213	0.753	-0.047	0.687	-0.017	0.820
Attention × Post Crisis × High ESG Overall	-0.169	0.603	0.041	0.487	0.020	0.611
Return	-0.192	0.608	0.689	0.000***	0.456	0.000***
LSSI – Smooth	-0.032	0.834	0.092	0.002***	0.088	0.001***

*NOTE: Significance levels – ***p < 0.01, **p < 0.05, p < 0.10. “Post Crisis” is defined as the period following Stage 6 load shedding events. Standard errors are robust.

4.3. Time-Frequency Relationship between ESG Signals and REIT Returns During Scheduled Load-Shedding Periods

Figure 2 illustrates the wavelet coherence between REIT returns and ESG signals across different frequencies and market regimes. Across all dimensions (ESG), the coherence remains consistently high, exceeding 0.90 and approaching unity as time scales lengthen. This suggests a robust long-term co-movement between ESG performance and REIT returns in South Africa, supporting the view that ESG is priced into REIT valuations, albeit slowly. Such coherence patterns affirm findings by Bouri et al. (2022) on ESG's delayed but persistent informational content in thin and volatile emerging markets. However, regime differentiation reveals subtle but critical insights. Under normal market conditions, ESG signals especially governance, achieve high coherence levels more rapidly. In contrast, during crisis periods induced by load shedding, the coherence trajectories for all ESG dimensions flatten in the short term, implying that systemic shocks suppress or delay the pricing response to ESG information. This is consistent with signalling theory's assertion that under conditions of noise or stress, informational signals (like ESG) lose salience or become ambiguous (Connelly et al., 2011). Particularly notable is the governance channel, which shows faster integration during stable periods, implying investor preference for institutional clarity and board-level accountability when markets function predictably.

From a policy and investor perspective, this figure delivers nuanced implications. For institutional investors, it highlights that ESG strategies may retain value over long horizons but are unlikely to offer insulation during acute grid failures. For regulators, it underscores the need to reform ESG disclosure architecture to ensure that signals retain interpretability in volatile regimes. For government, the flatness of ESG response during blackouts challenges the assumption that sustainability frameworks inherently build market confidence unless they are explicitly tied to operational risk metrics like energy continuity. Ultimately, the data invite a sobering question: if ESG scores remain coherent but muted in crisis, are they informative, or merely consistent?

Figure 2: Wavelet Coherence between Return and ESG Signals across Regimes

4.4. Event Study Regression Results: REIT Abnormal Returns Around ESG Disclosure Events During Load Shedding

Event regression estimates of Table 5 measure the response of REIT abnormal returns to ESG signals during load shedding. The results show that the event window period itself is positively associated with returns, confirming that load shedding events elicit strong market responses. Aggregate high ESG ratings are in negative connection with returns, and it may imply an investor discount on highly ESG-rated REITs, which could be due to perceived underperformance or defensive positioning. Interestingly, during periods of crisis, governance and environmental signals are important: environmental ESG is positively related with returns, suggesting investors reward green-focused REITs during periods of energy pressure; governance ESG, by contrast, is very highly negatively related with returns, possibly reflecting concerns regarding governance arrangements that fail to protect against crisis risk. These findings suggest that in load shedding, South African REITs (SAREITS) investors are subtly and selectively ESG sensitive.

Table 5: Event Study Regression Results – Abnormal Returns and ESG Interactions During Load Shedding

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	p-value
Intercept	0.0001	0.0001	-0.6265	0.5310
Event Window [-3, +3]	0.0004**	0.0002	2.1645	0.0304
Crisis Regime (Load Shedding)	0.0001	0.0001	0.1320	0.8950
High ESG – Overall (vs. Low ESG)	-0.0001**	0.0001	-2.0183	0.0436
High ESG – Environmental	0.0001	0.0001	0.7053	0.4806
High ESG – Governance	0.0001	0.0001	-0.3621	0.7173
Event × High ESG – Overall	-0.0005	0.0004	-1.2459	0.2128
Event × High ESG – Environmental	-0.0003	0.0003	-0.8683	0.3852
Event × High ESG – Governance	0.0005	0.0004	1.3307	0.1833
Event × High ESG – Overall × Crisis	-0.0005	0.0021	-0.2642	0.7916
Event × High ESG – Environmental × Crisis	0.0025**	0.0012	2.1823	0.0291
Event × High ESG – Governance × Crisis	-0.0024**	0.0007	-3.3329	0.0009

NOTE: $p < 0.10$ (ρ), < 0.05 (ρ), < 0.01 (ρ). High ESG categorisation defined by top 33rd percentile of ESG scores. Load shedding regime coded as binary dummy using Eskom Stage Max ≥ 2 threshold. CARs computed around [-3, +3] event window using market-adjusted model.

4.5. Comparative Forecast Accuracy of Machine Learning Models Against Actual South African REIT Returns

Figure 3 reveals actual South African REIT returns with forecasts from advanced machine learning models (Random Forest (RF), XGBoost, and Long Short-Term Memory networks (LSTM)) over a two-year horizon. Notably, RF achieves the highest explanatory power, capturing 72.8% of return variance ($R^2 = 0.728$), followed

by XGBoost at 67.0%, underscoring the remarkable ability of ensemble tree-based algorithms to distill nonlinear and interactive effects of ESG factors and load shedding severity on price dynamics. These models' low RMSE and MAE values indicate precise and stable predictive accuracy, critical for investors navigating the volatility endemic to emerging markets with infrastructural fragility (Zhang et al., 2023; Nguyen & Zhao, 2022). In contrast, ElasticNet and LSTM yield negligible or negative R^2 , signaling their relative inadequacy in capturing complex high-frequency interactions inherent in the South African REIT market. The underperformance of LSTM, despite its sequential modeling capacity, suggests that temporal dependencies may be overshadowed by abrupt systemic shocks such as load shedding, which introduce noise and disrupt traditional time-series patterns (Chen & Pan, 2021). This aligns with recent critiques emphasizing the limits of deep learning in structurally unstable financial environments (López de Prado, 2018).

For practitioners and portfolio managers, these findings advocate prioritizing robust nonlinear models that can integrate multifaceted ESG signals and systemic risk indicators to anticipate market shifts with enhanced fidelity. Regulators should heed the demonstrated value of advanced analytics in refining ESG disclosure frameworks and systemic risk monitoring, thereby fostering more resilient capital markets amid chronic infrastructural challenges. Policymakers are reminded that machine learning insights can expose critical inflection points where energy crises materially impact asset valuations, reinforcing the imperative to bolster grid reliability for sustainable financial market functioning.

Figure 3: Forecast and Actual REIT Returns

4.5. Quantile Result of the Dynamic Interaction between ESG and Load Shedding on REITs Return

Table 6 captures the conditional and asymmetric behaviour of ESG performance in shaping REIT returns across different market states, operationalised through a quantile regression framework. Rather than treating ESG as a uniformly priced attribute, the results demonstrate that its financial materiality is profoundly shaped by tail risk dynamics and macro-instability; specifically, infrastructure stress induced by South Africa's chronic load shedding. At both the 10th and 90th quantiles, ESG Overall scores are significantly and negatively associated with REIT returns. This indicates that during deep drawdowns or irrational exuberance, ESG is discounted possibly due to investors' flight to liquidity, a preference for operational resilience over long-term sustainability, or scepticism about ESG's short-term buffering value. Yet at the 75th quantile, ESG performance is rewarded, suggesting that under moderate optimism and relative macro calm, ESG enhances investor confidence and signals strategic competence. This nonlinear valuation arc deviates from the traditional ESG premium narrative (Devine & Yao, 2020; Fatemi et al., 2018), which assumes ESG yields stable risk-adjusted benefits across the return spectrum. More critically, the $ESG \times Load\ Shedding$ interaction term is significant at the extremes with a view to reinforcing ESG's role as a conditional hedge but only when systemic pressures are most acute. In

other words, ESG is not a static signal of virtue, but a dynamic resilience proxy, whose value crystallises only when infrastructure collapses introduce exogenous stress to REIT operations, tenant risk, and portfolio stability.

This finding is especially salient for investors, who must rethink ESG as a non-linear factor; highly relevant in crises, but less so in stable regimes. For regulators, the results point to the need for dynamic ESG disclosure frameworks that account for contextual and regime-sensitive performance rather than static scorecards. For governments, particularly in emerging economies, the evidence calls attention to a dangerous misalignment: ESG ambitions without infrastructure reliability may weaken capital flows, disincentivise long-term green allocation, and erode public trust in sustainability commitments. Theoretically, Table 6 advances the ESG–REIT literature by operationalising market state dependence within a high-frequency, emerging market infrastructure crisis (Brounen & Marcato, 2019; Hartzmark & Sussman, 2019). It brings signalling theory into confrontation with crisis realism, asking whether ESG’s promise holds when foundational systems like electricity break down. In doing so, this paper equips market participants with a more adaptive lens for interpreting ESG in fragile, high-volatility environments.

Table 6: Quantile Result of the Dynamic Interaction between ESG and Load Shedding on REITs Return

Variable	Q0.10	Q0.25	Q0.50	Q0.75	Q0.90
Intercept	−0.0042***	0.0001	0.0001	−0.0002***	0.0179***
ESG-Overall	−0.0001***	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001***	−0.0002***
LSSI-smooth	−0.0028***	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	−0.0031***
Attention Index	−0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	−0.0001***	−0.0003***
Weather Stress Index	0.0007***	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	−0.0013***
Volume / Liquidity	0.0001***	0.0001***	0.0001	0.0001***	0.0001***
Volatility (5D)	−0.0257***	−0.0263***	0.0001	0.0055***	0.0440***
ESG × Load Shedding	0.0001***	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001***

NOTE: $p < 0.10$ (*), < 0.05 (**), < 0.01 (***). Standard errors in parentheses. Source: Authors’ computations using South African REITs (2013–2024), Bloomberg ESG scores, and Eskom load shedding data. LSSI-smooth captures blackout severity; ESG × Load Shedding interaction tests conditional ESG value under energy crisis.

4.6. Predictive Modelling of ESG–REIT Interactions: Machine Learning Evidence

The predictive performance of ESG signals and load shedding indicators is benchmarked using four modelling approaches in Table 7. The Random Forest model outperforms all others, yielding the highest R^2 (0.728) and the lowest RMSE (0.016), followed closely by XGBoost ($R^2 = 0.670$). These results highlight the importance of nonlinear feature interactions and high-dimensional tree-based learning in capturing ESG-return dynamics under South Africa’s energy volatility. Traditional linear models (Elastic Net) perform substantially worse, with near-zero explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.000$), while the LSTM neural network, often favoured in high-frequency time series contexts, underperforms ($R^2 < 0$), likely due to limited sequential dependence or insufficient temporal structure in ESG-return relationships. This challenges the common assumption in financial forecasting that deep learning models are universally superior, particularly in structurally noisy emerging markets with systemic shocks. The superior accuracy of tree-based models underlines the contextual salience of ESG and load shedding features when modelled non-parametrically. For investors, this suggests that ESG integration benefits from machine learning techniques that uncover latent interactions missed by linear methods. For regulators, the performance gap reaffirms the need for algorithmic transparency and governance in ESG analytics. And for governments, the finding signals that machine learning can serve as a diagnostic lens for identifying where ESG commitments are most financially credible under infrastructure strain. Table 5 thus extends existing work by explicitly comparing traditional and frontier models in a crisis-prone African real estate market. It situates ESG as a predictive asset whose signal strength depends on algorithmic sensitivity and economic context.

Table 7: Model Performance

Model	R2	RMSE	MAE	Residual Std.
XG Boost	0.670	0.017	0.007	0.017
Random Forest	0.728	0.016	0.006	0.016
Elastic Net	0.000	0.030	0.014	0.030
LSTM	-0.024	0.030	0.015	0.030

NOTE: Model performance metrics for REIT return prediction using ESG and load shedding variables. Random Forest and XGBoost outperform Elastic Net and LSTM, highlighting the strength of nonlinear models in capturing return dynamics under systemic stress. Metrics are based on out-of-sample test sets. Source: Authors' computations.

4.7. Interpretable ESG Intelligence: SHAP-Based Feature Attribution for REIT Return Dynamics Amid Load Shedding

Figure 4 reveals the internal logic of the XGBoost model using SHAP values, offering granular insight into which predictors most influence REIT return forecasts under load-shedding stress. The dominant variables (*Volatility_5d*, *LSSI_smooth*, and *AbnormalReturn_t*) signal that investor behaviour is shaped more by systemic instability and short-run market tremors than by long-term ESG credentials. This directly challenges the assumption in much of the ESG literature (Fatemi et al., 2018; Krüger, 2015) that ESG integration holds constant predictive power in turbulent markets. Volume and attention indices, proxies for investor sentiment and herding, play secondary but significant roles, reinforcing findings from emerging market behavioural finance (Nassirtoussi et al., 2015). While ESG variables appear in the lower tier of influence, their non-zero impact suggests they are simply overridden by immediate risk signals in predictive hierarchies. For investors, this implies ESG sentiment alone cannot hedge portfolio exposure to energy infrastructure fragility. Regulators must reconsider mandatory ESG disclosures as insufficient buffers without complementary systemic risk assessments. Governments, in turn, are urged to internalise energy reliability as part of national ESG scoring systems.

Figure 4: SHAP-Based Feature Importance in Predicting REIT Returns under Load Shedding Conditions

4.8. Reinforcement Learning under Load Shedding: ESG as a Dynamic Decision Signal

To interrogate the real-time strategic value of ESG during infrastructure breakdowns, we developed a reinforcement learning (RL) framework that models investor decision-making under South Africa's chronic load shedding in Table 8. Using Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO), the ESG-aware agent dynamically reallocated capital across REITs using a high-frequency state space of ESG scores, market returns, load shedding intensity (LSSI), volatility, liquidity, and investor attention metrics. The agent learned to optimize

cumulative return, conditioned on energy stress and market noise. Table 8 compares the ESG-aware policy with two baselines: an ESG-blind agent and a passive REIT-holding strategy. The ESG-informed agent outperformed both on cumulative return (+12.5%), Sharpe ratio (1.34), and maximum drawdown (-6.8%), especially during acute load shedding episodes. This suggests that ESG information, when embedded in a learning environment, confers adaptive financial resilience; not just reputational value. For investors, this reinforces ESG’s utility as a dynamic alpha signal under volatility. For regulators, the result affirms that market actors equipped with sustainability signals respond more prudently to systemic risk. And for government, it illustrates the tangible economic value of ESG transparency and policy enforcement, particularly in crisis-prone sectors like real estate and energy. With a view to simulating investor behaviour in a broken grid economy, this RL model shifts ESG from a passive score to an active strategic input and this illustrates how sustainability considerations can materially shape capital under duress.

Table 8: Reinforcement Learning Performance Metrics of ESG-Aware vs ESG-Agnostic REIT Investment Policies under Load Shedding Stress

Metric	ESG-Aware Agent	ESG-Agnostic Agent	Baseline Strategy
Cumulative Return	12.5%	7.8%	5.2%
Sharpe Ratio	1.34	0.89	0.63
Max Drawdown	-6.2%	-8.5%	-10.4%
Volatility	2.1%	2.8%	3.2%
Win Rate	63%	55%	49%
ESG Exposure Score (Avg)	High	Low	None

4.9. ROC Curve Analysis for ESG-Sensitive REIT Market Reaction under Load Shedding Risk

Figure 5 captures the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve evaluating the ability of a machine learning classifier to distinguish significant abnormal return movements in South African REITs triggered by ESG signal events during load shedding periods. The Area Under the Curve (AUC) value of 0.583, while modest, is analytically revealing. It implies that ESG disclosures even when aligned with energy risk contexts possess limited standalone predictive power for classifying sharp market reactions. This performance must not be hastily dismissed. Instead, it speaks to a more intricate market truth: investor responses to ESG disclosures in REIT markets are deeply probabilistic, temporally conditional, and behaviorally noisy, particularly under infrastructure volatility like load shedding. The slightly elevated AUC above 0.5 suggests that ESG indicators offer some signal but it is likely nonlinear, confounded, or diluted by competing information streams such as crisis salience, firm fundamentals, or liquidity distortions.

Crucially, this figure affirms a core methodological contribution of the paper: the necessity of hybrid approaches. Simple classifiers may falter in regimes of high uncertainty, but machine learning, when paired with event structures and volatility-aware features, begins to unearth conditional ESG sensitivities in investor behaviour. This is particularly relevant for South Africa’s real estate market, where systemic energy instability and climate governance vacuums intersect with global ESG mandates. For investors, the figure warns against overreliance on ESG announcements as trading signals unless contextually weighted. For regulators and policymakers, it stresses the urgent need to enhance ESG data quality, promote contextual ESG education, and embed ESG responses into pricing models not merely compliance frameworks. And for REIT executives, it suggests that ESG signalling must evolve from generic disclosure to crisis-resilient, investor-relevant narratives that shape capital flows in times of infrastructural disruption.

Figure 5: ROC Curve Analysis for ESG-Sensitive REIT Market Reaction under Load Shedding Risk

4.10. Temporal Evolution of Cumulative Returns for an ESG-Aware Reinforcement Learning Investor under Load Shedding Stress

Figure 6 vividly illustrates the dynamic evolution of cumulative rewards generated by an ESG-aware reinforcement learning (RL) investor navigating South Africa's increasingly unstable load shedding landscape from 2013 to 2025. The initial phase (2013–2020) is marked by significant fluctuations and prolonged intervals of negative cumulative returns, reflecting the RL agent's limited ability to consistently identify and capitalize on ESG signals when energy insecurity and investor awareness were comparatively low. This volatility underscores the challenges of leveraging ESG factors in an environment where systemic risks were not fully priced or embedded into market behaviour. A pronounced inflection point emerges around 2021 with a view to coinciding with the escalation in load shedding intensity and wider recognition of ESG materiality in real estate investment decisions. From this juncture, the RL agent's reward trajectory sharply ascends, culminating in a sustained positive cumulative return exceeding 2.5 units by 2025. This trend evidences a regime shift whereby ESG attributes, particularly those related to environmental and governance robustness, become increasingly salient and financially rewarding amidst infrastructural disruption.

Crucially, the convergence in cumulative rewards post-2021 signals the RL framework's successful adaptation to evolving market regimes, dynamically reallocating portfolio weights toward ESG-aligned REITs that demonstrate resilience under power outage stress. This adaptation embodies a sophisticated learning process: the agent effectively discriminates between superficial ESG claims and substantive sustainability performance that buffers downside risk during energy crises. This figure substantiates the thesis that static ESG scores are insufficient proxies in volatile emerging markets; instead, an interactive, reinforcement-based approach capturing temporal shifts and infrastructure shocks unlocks alpha-generating opportunities. For investors, the findings highlight the necessity of integrating adaptive machine learning strategies to harness ESG insights contextually. Policymakers and regulators should interpret this as an empirical call for ESG disclosure frameworks that emphasize operational continuity and energy risk mitigation.

Figure 6: Reward Convergence for ESG-Aware REITs Investors under Load Shedding

5. Conclusion

This study provides an urgent and rigorous investigation into the conditional pricing and behavioural relevance of ESG signals within South Africa's REIT market, amid the systemic shock of escalating load shedding (Montmasson-Clair & Moilwa, 2023). Our findings decisively challenge the prevalent ESG premium assumption by revealing that ESG's financial influence is neither stable nor universal; rather, it exhibits regime-dependent variability thereby gaining significant traction only during intense infrastructure stress. Specifically, the environmental and governance dimensions emerge as critical risk buffers during blackout crises (Devine & Yao, 2020; Hartzmark & Sussman, 2019). This nuance compels a paradigm shift away from static ESG scoring toward a contextual understanding of ESG as a crisis-sensitive signal. Employing a multi-method approach (combining wavelet coherence, event study regressions, quantile models, and cutting-edge machine learning including reinforcement learning), our analysis exposes the dynamic evolution of investor behaviour and market adaptation to infrastructure fragility (Bouri et al., 2022; Nassirtoussi et al., 2015). The reinforcement learning framework notably demonstrates superior portfolio performance by dynamically reallocating capital toward ESG-aligned REITs as load shedding intensifies with a view to illustrating the limitations of traditional, static ESG assessments in volatile emerging markets. This finding advances the frontier of ESG finance by highlighting the value of adaptive, AI-driven strategies in managing sustainability risk under infrastructural duress (Fatemi et al., 2018; Campiglio et al., 2018).

For investors, ESG should be integrated as a temporally sensitive alpha source, with investment decisions calibrated to regime-specific energy risks rather than generalized ESG ratings. Regulators and policymakers must urgently reform ESG disclosure protocols to embed granular operational risk metrics such as energy continuity and governance resilience that materially influence market valuations in energy-stressed economies (Capelle-Blancard & Petit, 2019). Without such reform, ESG ratings risk becoming superficial reputational tools disconnected from true financial risk exposure. Ultimately, this paper bridges a critical gap in sustainability finance literature by empirically linking ESG performance, systemic infrastructure failure, and sophisticated computational modeling in an emerging market context that typifies structural fragility. As climate change and energy insecurity become ever more intertwined with economic stability globally, the study's insights serve as a foundation for future research extending dynamic ESG frameworks across sectors and geographies which adopts machine learning to enhance truly resilient investment paradigms (Brounen & Marcato, 2019; Krüger, 2015).

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Appendix:

Table A1: ADF Stationarity Test

Variable	TestStat_Level	p-value_Level	TestStat_FirstDiff	p-value_FirstDiff	Stationary_Level	Stationary_FirstDiff
Return	-32.288	0.000	-47.048	0.000	Yes	Yes
Abnormal Return	-38.364	0.000	-55.592	0.000	Yes	Yes
Volatility_5d	-12.935	0.000	-45.241	0.000	Yes	Yes
Volatility_10d	-12.748	0.000	-43.859	0.000	Yes	Yes
Rolling Beta-ESG	-27.634	0.000	-40.444	0.000	Yes	Yes
ESG-Overall	-220.562	0.000	-50.225	0.000	Yes	Yes
ESG-Environmental	-221.215	0.000	-50.199	0.000	Yes	Yes
ESG-Social	-221.098	0.000	-48.777	0.000	Yes	Yes
ESG-Governance	-218.371	0.000	-50.203	0.000	Yes	Yes
Stage Max	-8.622	0.000	-42.276	0.000	Yes	Yes
LSSI smooth	-9.136	0.000	-43.690	0.000	Yes	Yes
Load Shedding Shock	-14.078	0.000	-43.045	0.000	Yes	Yes
Attention Index	-13.988	0.000	-39.511	0.000	Yes	Yes

A Systematic Review on Factors Influencing Technological Innovation Adoption in Real Estate Valuation

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Abstract

The real estate industry is undergoing rapid technological transformation driven by innovations such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Automated Valuation Models (AVMs), and Geographic Information Systems (GIS), all of which enhance valuation accuracy, transparency, and efficiency. Despite their potential, adoption remains slow in many developing contexts.

This study systematically reviews the factors influencing technological innovation adoption in real estate valuation using the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) framework. Scholarly databases including Scopus and Google Scholar were searched, yielding 656 records, of which 17 peer-reviewed studies (2011 – 2025) met the inclusion criteria - studies published in English and specifically address the use of technologies in real estate valuation between 2011 and 2025. Studies that address technological innovations in other aspects of real estate practice and existing systematic reviews were excluded. Selected studies were synthesised to provide an insight on the focus of technological innovations in enhancing valuation accuracy and reliability.

The study integrates Rogers' Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) theory and the PEST (Political, Economic, Social, and Technological) analytical framework to examine both behavioural and contextual determinants of adoption. Findings reveal that AVMs (35%) and Artificial Neural Networks and ML (23%) are the most widely adopted technologies, followed by GIS (18%) and blockchain (12%). The key drivers of adoption include regulatory support (political), operational efficiency, pressure from institutional clients (economic) and transparency (technological). Conversely, identified barriers were high implementation costs (economic), lack of digital infrastructure, training barriers (technological), low professional awareness, resistance to change, regulatory, economic constraints (political and economic).

The study concludes that strengthening digital infrastructure, regulatory modernization, and professional capacity building are critical to accelerating technology adoption in valuation practice. Also, policymakers and professional institutions should collaborate to create enabling environments that foster innovation diffusion and support sustainable, data-driven real estate valuation systems.

Keywords:

Artificial Intelligence, AVMs, GIS, Real Estate Valuation, Technology Adoption

1.0 Introduction

Valuation, as a crucial aspect of the real estate industry, aids in various transactions including purchases, sales, mortgage, and investment decisions (Yasnitsky et al., 2021). The growing need for property valuation by stakeholders in the real estate market necessitates decreasing overdependence on subjective judgment while increasing objectivity to enhance accuracy. Informed decision-making requires reliable and accurate property value estimates, yet ensuring valuation accuracy has long been a concern in global property markets, especially after the 2008 Global Financial Crisis, which was caused in part by inflated and inaccurate property valuations (Mishkin, 2011).

Property valuation has been widely criticized for inaccuracies and their adverse effects on real estate transactions, investment decisions, and financial reporting. Studies have revealed discrepancies of up to 30% between valuations and market prices, often due to inconsistent methodologies, inadequate data, and human subjectivity (Ajibola & Oletubo, 2011; Babawale & Omirin, 2011). The continued reliance on traditional valuation techniques such as the comparative sales approach, without proper adjustment for dynamic market conditions, has exacerbated valuation inaccuracies (Aluko, 2007). Moreover, the lack of a standardized property database and weak regulatory enforcement contribute to variation among practitioners (Adegoke, 2016; Babawale & Omirin, 2011), leading to disputes in transactions, reduced investor confidence, and challenges in mortgage financing (Ayedun et al., 2011). Such inefficiencies underscore the urgent need for modernization through the adoption of technological innovations in valuation practice (Dangana & Udoekanem, 2024).

With the rise of globalization and digital transformation, the real estate profession is undergoing a profound technological shift. The availability of data and advances in information and communication technology (ICT) have challenged the traditional role of valuers and expanded access to market information (Wilkinson et al., 2017). Valuation, once grounded purely in professional judgment and manual processes, is increasingly shaped by technological innovations that enhance accuracy, speed, and transparency. Technological tools such as Geographic Information Systems (GIS), Automated Valuation Models (AVMs), Building Information Modelling (BIM), Artificial Intelligence (AI), blockchain, and drones are now transforming valuation processes by automating data analysis, improving objectivity, and reducing turnaround times (Droj et al., 2024). For instance, Namangale (2021) found that speed, accuracy, and reduced cost ranked highest among valuers' perceived benefits of AVM adoption.

Conceptually, technological innovation refers to the process of developing, adopting, and diffusing new technologies or methods that improve efficiency and performance (Rogers, 2003; Adair et al., 2020). In real estate valuation, it involves integrating digital tools and data-driven systems to enhance analytical precision and transparency (French et al., 2021). The adoption of technological innovation thus represents valuers' decision to integrate and institutionalize these technologies in their workflow, influenced by factors such as perceived usefulness, organizational support, and policy environment (Davis, 1989; Alkhaffaf & Hassanain, 2022). Meanwhile, digital technologies including AVMs, GIS, BIM, AI, and blockchain constitute the tangible expressions of such innovations, enabling a transition from traditional, manual valuation approaches to automated and data-driven systems (Li et al., 2021; Oloke et al., 2023).

The adoption of technological innovations in real estate valuation, however, remains uneven and underexplored in many developing contexts, particularly in Nigeria. While some studies have examined awareness and willingness to adopt specific technologies such as GIS and Automated Valuation Models (AVMs), few have systematically synthesised the broader environmental and institutional factors that influence their adoption (Adegoke, 2016; Ayedun et al., 2011). Despite growing research interest, existing works remain fragmented and region-specific, often focusing on single technologies or isolated determinants without critically comparing the political, economic, social, and technological contexts that shape adoption. This fragmentation limits policymakers, professional institutions, and researchers from drawing generalisable insights or designing informed interventions to foster innovation uptake in

valuation practice. Consequently, valuers in developing markets risk being left behind in the global transition toward digitalised and sustainable real estate systems.

In response to these gaps, this study conducts a systematic literature review to consolidate and critically appraise the current state of knowledge on technology adoption in real estate valuation. Specifically, the study seeks to answer the following research questions:

- (i) What are the types of technological innovations adopted in real estate valuation?
- (ii) What are the drivers of technological innovation adoption in real estate valuation?
- (iii) What are the barriers to technological innovation adoption in real estate valuation?

To anchor this inquiry, the study draws upon **Rogers' Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) Theory** (1962, 2003), which explains how new ideas and technologies spread within a social or professional system over time. The DOI theory identifies innovation attributes such as relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability, and observability as critical factors influencing adoption decisions (Rogers, 2003; Bryan & Zuva, 2021). This framework is particularly useful for understanding how valuers perceive, interpret, and integrate technological tools within established professional norms. However, while DOI effectively captures behavioural and organisational dynamics, it gives limited attention to the broader macro-environmental conditions that enable or constrain adoption.

To complement DOI, this study employs the **PEST analytical framework** – Political, Economic, Social, and Technological, which provides a macro-level lens to examine the external forces shaping technological innovation adoption (Tornatzky & Fleischer, 1990; Davis, 1986, 1989). PEST helps to contextualise how government policies, economic incentives, societal readiness, and technological infrastructure collectively influence adoption in the Nigerian real estate sector. By integrating DOI and PEST, the study achieves both **theoretical depth** and **contextual breadth**, offering a holistic understanding of the **factors influencing technological innovation adoption in real estate valuation**.

2.0 Literature Review

The integration of technological innovations into real estate valuation such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Automated Valuation Models (AVMs), and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) has the potential to reduce valuation errors, enhance analytical precision, and improve methodological consistency (Akinjare et al., 2013). Studies have demonstrated that AI and Machine Learning (ML) significantly enhance the accuracy and efficiency of valuation processes by enabling the analysis of large and complex datasets, including historical sales, property attributes, and market trends (AlZaidan et al., 2025; Topraklı, 2024). By automating repetitive and data-intensive tasks, these technologies minimize human bias and accelerate the valuation process (Alsahan & AlZaidan, 2023; Xu, 2025). Similarly, GIS technology improves spatial analysis and allows valuers to account for locational variables such as proximity to amenities and environmental risks (Liu et al., 2011), while Blockchain enhances data integrity and transparency by providing tamper-proof property transaction records. Collectively, these innovations promise greater accuracy, efficiency, and transparency in real estate valuation.

Although literature on the digital transformation of real estate practice is growing, comprehensive evidence on the types and determinants of technological innovation adoption in valuation remains limited. Advanced economies have demonstrated higher adoption rates

and institutional support for technological tools. In Australia, for instance, real estate firms such as CoreLogic and APM Price Finder have integrated AVMs and big data analytics to generate real-time subscription-based valuation reports (Wilkinson et al., 2017). Similarly, financial institutions in developed countries are building proprietary databases for mortgage valuations to reduce reliance on external valuers (Blass, 2016). In contrast, adoption in emerging economies remains fragmented and slow. While professionals acknowledge the benefits of AI and GIS, practical uptake is constrained by inadequate training, weak institutional promotion, and the absence of digital infrastructure (Abidoye, 2017; Abidoye & Chan, 2017).

This disparity underscores the importance of examining why technological diffusion in valuation remains uneven across global contexts. The Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) theory (Rogers, 1962, 2003) provides a useful lens for understanding this phenomenon. DOI explains how innovations are communicated and adopted within a social system over time, emphasizing factors such as relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability, and observability. Within the valuation profession, these constructs manifest through valuers' perceptions of a technology's usefulness, ease of integration, and alignment with professional norms (Davis, 1989; Bryan & Zuva, 2021). For instance, AI and AVMs may offer superior predictive accuracy (relative advantage) but be resisted due to interpretability concerns (complexity) or perceived threat to professional autonomy (compatibility). Thus, behavioural and perceptual factors play a central role in shaping the pace of innovation adoption.

Apart from the benefits offered by DOI theory, broader macro-environmental factors also influence diffusion outcomes. The PEST framework encompassing Political, Economic, Social, and Technological dimensions captures these external determinants. Political and regulatory support, for example, determine whether technologies like AVMs and blockchain gain official recognition (Stang, 2023). Economic conditions affect firms' financial capacity to invest in digital infrastructure (Ogunnowo et al., 2020; Adilieme et al., 2024). Social attitudes, including professional resistance and cultural attachment to traditional methods, influence acceptance (Jie, 2022; Gardes, 2025), while the availability and maturity of digital tools shape technological readiness (Adewusi, 2022). Combining DOI and PEST frameworks, therefore, enables a comprehensive analysis of both micro-level behavioural drivers and macro-level contextual enablers or constraints of technological innovation adoption.

By systematically synthesizing existing evidence, this paper consolidates scattered insights into a coherent framework that highlights both behavioural and contextual dimensions of adoption. Anchored on DOI theory and structured through the PEST framework, the study provides a theoretically robust and contextually grounded synthesis of technological innovation in valuation practice. This approach aligns with the PRISMA guidelines (Page et al., 2020) and situates the discussion within the global movement toward digital transformation, offering practical implications for training, policy design, and institutional capacity-building in the real estate sector.

Although prior studies are fragmented and vary in methodological rigour, this review does not merely aggregate their findings. Instead, it applies a systematic and comparative synthesis that critically evaluates the strength, context, and consistency of available evidence. By assessing methodological differences such as data sources, analytical techniques, and geographic coverage the review identifies both convergence and divergence in existing research outcomes.

This approach ensures that the study contributes not only a summary of what is known but also a deeper understanding of how and why findings differ across contexts. Anchored on DOI and structured through the PEST framework, this review provides a robust and critically informed synthesis to guide both scholarly inquiry and professional practice.

3.0 Methods

This study adopted a **systematic literature review (SLR)** methodology to investigate the drivers and barriers influencing the adoption of technological innovations in real estate valuation. The review followed the **PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses)** guidelines to ensure transparency, replicability, and methodological rigour. The review process began with identification of related articles on the subject. A comprehensive search was conducted across scholarly databases such as Scopus and Google Scholar and Journal of African Real Estate targeting peer-reviewed journal articles published between 2011 and 2025 in both developed and emerging markets.

The study was guided by two frameworks: Rogers' Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) theory (1962, 2003) and the PEST analytical framework (Political, Economic, Social, and Technological). The DOI theory provides the behavioural and organizational lens, explaining how valuers and real estate firms perceive and adopt innovations based on attributes such as relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability, and observability. Meanwhile, the PEST framework offers a macro-contextual perspective, identifying the broader environmental and institutional forces that facilitate or hinder innovation adoption. Together, these frameworks establish both the micro-level (behavioural) and macro-level (contextual) bases for understanding the adoption of technological innovation in valuation practice.

A combination of keywords and Boolean operators used for search were ("technology innovation" OR "technological innovation" OR "digital innovation" OR "proptech" OR "real estate technology" OR "information technology" OR "IT adoption" OR "smart technology") AND ("adoption" OR "acceptance" OR "implementation" OR "use" OR "utilization" OR "diffusion") AND ("real estate valuation" OR "property valuation" OR "real property appraisal" OR "real estate appraisal" OR "land valuation") AND ("factors" OR "determinants" OR "barriers" OR "drivers" OR "challenges" OR "influencing factors").

Inclusion criteria required that studies be written in English; peer-reviewed journal articles, conference papers, and policy reports published between 2011 and 2025; and specifically address the use of digital, automated technologies, AVMs or AI in real estate valuation. On the other hand, exclusion criteria included studies not related to real estate valuation or digital innovation; grey literature or unverified sources lacking empirical or conceptual rigours as well as papers focused solely on construction technology without valuation implications.

Data from selected studies were extracted based on type of technological innovation as well as identified factors influencing adoption. The review followed the four PRISMA stages: Identification, Screening, Eligibility, and Inclusion (Moher et al., 2009). A total of 656 papers extracted from the scholarly databases were screened by the authors which enabled removal of duplicates and irrelevant records. Afterwards, titles and abstracts were further screened for relevance. Only studies published in English within the stipulated period, focusing on the adoption of technology in real estate valuation, were eligible for the review. The final selection

comprised 17 empirical and conceptual studies covering regions such as Sub-Saharan Africa, Southeast Asia, Europe, and North America. PRISMA diagrams showing the selection process is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: PRISMA diagram
Source: Author’s Construct (2025)

To enhance methodological transparency and reliability, the screening process was conducted in two independent stages by separate reviewers. Each reviewer assessed the studies against inclusion criteria using a coding sheet. Disagreements were resolved through discussion to reach consensus and final decision. This approach ensured inter-rater reliability and minimized selection bias.

The relatively small final sample size (17 studies) reflects the specificity of the inclusion criteria and the nascent nature of empirical research on technological adoption in valuation, especially in developing contexts. Most studies from Africa (esp. Nigeria, Malawi, South Africa) met inclusion criteria due to a recent surge in valuation technology research in these regions. Western and Asian studies were fewer but more methodologically robust. Each retained paper met the minimum quality threshold of peer-reviewed status and explicit methodological clarity.

To achieve conceptual depth and contextual clarity, the study employed a dual-framework integration of DOI and PEST. The DOI theory informed analysis of micro-level behavioural determinants, such as valuers’ perception of usefulness, compatibility, and ease of use, as well as organizational readiness and professional culture. The PEST framework structured macro-level environmental determinants, including Political factors (government digitalization

policies, national ICT strategies, and professional regulation of valuation standards); economic factors (market conditions, cost of technology adoption, and availability of funding for digital transformation); social factors (professional attitudes, generational differences among valuers, and client demand for transparency and faster service delivery); and technological factors (availability, accessibility, and maturity of digital tools such as GIS, AVMs, AI, and blockchain systems). This integration allowed the study to capture both the internal behavioural enablers (DOI) and external systemic influences (PEST) that shape technological innovation adoption in real estate valuation.

A structured **data extraction matrix** was developed to summarise author(s), year, country, technology type, study design, and key findings. The extracted data were then **coded deductively** under the **PEST categories**. The **DOI theory** informed how the review interpreted these categories. For instance, relating political legitimacy to **compatibility**, economic incentives to **relative advantage**, social awareness to **observability**, and technological usability to **complexity** (Rogers, 2003). This deductive-theoretical approach ensured that findings were not merely descriptive but linked conceptually to innovation diffusion logic.

The synthesis followed the narrative synthesis approach outlined by Pope et al. (2006). Findings from the selected studies were coded into thematic clusters according to PEST dimensions and then compared across geographies and methodologies to identify convergence and divergence in results. This process emphasized explanation building rather than statistical aggregation, appropriate for the heterogeneity of data and study designs in the reviewed literature.

To complement the qualitative synthesis, **frequency counts** were used to quantify the proportion of studies that examined each technology type. These percentages were derived from **frequency analysis**, calculated by dividing the number of studies addressing a given technology by the total sample (17). For example, 6 studies that focused primarily on Automated Valuation Models (AVMs), represented 35% of the reviewed studies. The analysis allowed for multiple counting where a single study examined more than one technology type. Similarly, a frequency count analysis was conducted to identify the most recurring drivers and barriers to technological innovation adoption in real estate valuation. Each study was coded deductively according to the PEST framework (Political, Economic, Social, and Technological factors). The frequency of each factor's appearance across the 17 included studies was tallied to determine dominance patterns, which were summarized in tabular form.

Although some empirical studies (e.g., Stang, 2023; Adewusi, 2022; Babtan, 2025) reported quantitative measures of model accuracy, such as Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), or R^2 , these metrics were not consistently reported across all studies. Therefore, the reported improvements in valuation accuracy (ranging between 20–40%) should be interpreted as indicative of performance gains observed in modelling-based studies, rather than standardized cross-study comparisons.

For the majority of studies, particularly those conducted in developing economies, the findings were qualitative or descriptive, focusing on awareness levels, perceived benefits, and barriers to adoption. Consequently, the overall synthesis prioritised narrative integration rather than statistical meta-analysis, ensuring that both empirical and perceptual insights were meaningfully captured.

For analytical rigour, a **PEST** (Political, Economic, Social, and Technological) **framework** was employed to categorise and interpret the barriers and drivers identified in the literature. A **PRISMA literature matrix** was constructed to summarise key data including technologies studied, methodological approach, study area, key findings, and contextual relevance. This structured synthesis enabled the comparison of trends across geographies and valuation practices. Findings are presented in the next section.

4.0 Results

The systematic literature review (SLR) was conducted to identify the types of technological innovations adopted in real estate valuation and to analyze the key factors influencing their adoption. Following PRISMA procedures, 17 studies that met the inclusion criteria were reviewed, revealing a rapidly expanding body of evidence highlighting how technological innovations are transforming valuation practice globally.

As indicated in figure 2, the review identified three dominant categories of innovations – Automated Valuation Models (AVMs) (35%), Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) (23%), and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) (18%) alongside emerging tools such as blockchain (2%), valuation software (6%), and big data analytics (6%).

Figure 2: Technology Innovations Adopted in Real Estate Valuation
Source: Author's Construct (2025)

Empirical studies reported improvements in valuation accuracy ranging from 20% to 40% with the application of advanced machine learning techniques. For example, **XGBoost** and **Extra Trees Regressors** achieved superior predictive power compared to traditional hedonic models, particularly in large datasets (Stang, 2023; Adewusi, 2022). GIS has been widely appreciated for its potential to improve spatial analysis in urban and high-density areas, though adoption remains modest due to cost and training challenges (Ayedun et al., 2022; Fasteen, 2016). The summary of various technological innovations adopted and their application in real estate valuations are presented in Table 1 for clarification.

Table 1: Type of Technological Innovation in Real Estate Valuations

Sources	Technological Innovation	Description	Application in Real Estate Valuation
Bäbţan (2025); Zhang (2018); Khalilov (2021); Adewusi (2022)	Artificial Neural Networks (ANN)	Mimics human brain for modeling non-linear data relationships.	Predicts property value using complex input features.
Bäbţan (2025); Stang (2023)	Regression Models (OLS, GAM)	Statistical models to identify variable relationships.	Used for hedonic price modeling and AVMs.
Bäbţan (2025); Adewusi (2022)	Decision Trees / Random Forest	Tree-based ML models with rule-based predictions.	Provides interpretable and stable valuation results.
Bäbţan (2025); Stang (2023)	XGBoost (Extreme Gradient Boosting)	Ensemble ML method for predictive analytics.	High-accuracy valuation across German datasets.
Adewusi (2022)	Bagging and Extra Trees Regressor	Ensemble techniques for regression tasks.	Used for faster and more accurate valuation predictions.
Mooya (2011); Thebe (2024); Bidanset & Rakow (2022); Jie (2022); Namangale (2021)	AVMs (Automated Valuation Models)	Automated models using statistics/ML.	Cost-efficient, rapid property valuation; useful in mass appraisal.
Ogun (2024); Ayedun et al. (2022); Fasten (2016)	GIS (Geographic Information Systems)	Integrates spatial/geographic data.	Location-based valuation enhancements and land record visualization.
Ogun (2024); Adilieme et al. (2024)	Blockchain	Distributed ledger ensuring secure records.	Transparent property databases, client influence reduction.
Ogun (2024)	Big Data Analytics	Analyzes large datasets for trends.	Supports informed property decisions and market analysis.
Ogunnowo et al. (2020)	Valuation Software (e.g., Argus, MRI)	Digital tools for valuation processes.	Improves valuation efficiency and reduces manual errors.
Xu (2025)	Vision Language Models (VLMs) & Generative AI	AI models assessing visual data (photos).	Augments hedonic models with photo-based

Source: Author's Construct (2025)

Having identified the dominant technological innovations, the study proceeds to examine the broader political, economic, social, and technological factors influencing their adoption in the next section.

Table 2 indicated a frequency count of influencing factors categorized under the PEST framework indicated that technological and economic dimensions were the most dominant across studies. Accuracy improvement (n=9) and cost efficiency (n=8) emerged as the leading drivers, while high implementation costs (n=7) and poor data quality (n=7) were the most frequent barriers. These findings demonstrate that technological innovation adoption in valuation is primarily shaped by a trade-off between perceived performance benefits and resource constraints, consistent with diffusion of innovation theory.

Table 2: Frequency Count of Dominant Drivers and Barriers based on PEST/DOI Coding

PEST Category	Drivers	Barriers
Political	Supportive regulation (3), government endorsement (2)	Lack of regulation/policy gaps (5), institutional inertia (3)
Economic	Cost efficiency (8), profitability and time savings (5)	High implementation cost (7), lack of funding/resources (5)
Social	Professional awareness (6), perceived usefulness and motivation (4), transparency and trust (3)	Resistance to change (6), fear of job loss (3), limited training (5)
Technological	Accuracy improvement (9), data-driven decision making (7), innovation advantage (5)	Poor data quality/access (7), technical complexity (6), lack of expertise (5)

Source: Author’s Construct (2025)

In analysing the factors influencing technological innovation in real estate valuation, **PEST framework** indicates complex adoption dynamics. Politically, support varies across different markets – European regulators are moving toward supervised AVM use, while African and Southeast Asian markets suffer from regulatory ambiguity and enforcement gaps. Economically, the high cost of implementation particularly for GIS and proprietary software emerges as a universal constraint. Socially, entrenched professional norms and fear of job displacement continue to obstruct innovation. Technologically, while most tools show strong theoretical potential, concerns persist around data quality, explainability of AI outputs, and infrastructure compatibility. Importantly, studies in Malaysia, Nigeria, and Malawi revealed localised barriers that differ substantially from those in mature economies, emphasising the need for contextual policy design. These factors are discussed in detail in the preceding section.

The PRISMA literature review matrix is presented in Table 3 to summarise the drivers and barriers influencing the adoption of technological innovation in real estate valuation.

Table 3: PRISMA Literature Matrix

Author(s)/ Year	Country	Technological Innovations	Methodology	Key Findings	Barriers/Drivers (PEST/DOI)
Bäbjan (2025)	Europe	ANN (AI)	Conceptual & Comparative Review	AI models enhances valuation reliability, speed and accuracy, improving audit credibility	Drivers: Efficiency, accuracy, data availability (Tech/Eco). Barriers: Data quality, need for skilled users (Tech/Social)
Gardes (2025)	France	AI (General AI adoption)	SEM & Survey	AI adoption influenced by emotion, motivation, and autonomy threat	Drivers: Positive emotions, performance expectations (Social/Tech). Barriers: Fear of autonomy loss, emotional resistance (Social).
Xu (2025)	Global	Vision Language Models (VLMs) & Generative AI	Experimental modeling (AI-enhanced hedonic model)	Visual features improve valuation accuracy and buyer-price alignment.	Drivers: Price transparency, visual realism (Tech). Barriers: Data requirements, AI explainability (Tech)
Adilieme et al. (2024)	Nigeria	Blockchain	Interview-based qualitative	Blockchain improves trust and transparency in valuation; low adoption due to secrecy and lack of regulation.	Drivers: Regulation, transparency (Pol/Soc). Barriers: Low awareness, poor digitization, corruption (Pol/Soc).
Adilieme et al. (2024)	Nigeria	Blockchain (PropChain App)	Focus group simulation (valuers, bankers, clients)	Blockchain reduces client influence and increases transparency.	Drivers: Stakeholder collaboration, trust (Soc).
Ogun (2024)	Nigeria	AI, GIS, Blockchain, Big Data	Mixed methods	AI improves valuation accuracy by 25% and reduces assessment time by 40%.	Drivers: Technologies improve valuation accuracy and efficiency.
Thebe (2024)	South Africa	AVMs	Quantitative Survey	AVMs viewed as faster but limited due to lack of physical inspections	Drivers: Cost efficiency, transparency (Eco/Tech). Barriers: High cost, data gaps (Eco/Tech).
Nielsson & Simper (2024)	Denmark	Random Forest (AI)	ML experimentation	RF model outperforms national system in accuracy	Drivers: Cost efficiency, predictive accuracy (Eco/Tech). Barriers: Institutional resistance (Soc).

Author(s)/ Year	Country	Technological Innovations	Methodology	Key Findings	Barriers/Drivers (PEST/DOI)
Stang (2023)	Germany	AVMs, ML (XGBoost, OLS, GAM, EXF)	AVM benchmarking (big data)	XGBoost offers highest accuracy; AVMs suitable for lending if auditable.	Drivers: Regulatory debate, data robustness (Pol/Tech). Barriers: Regulatory uncertainty, explainability (Pol/Tech).
Adewusi (2022)	Nigeria	ANN, Random Forest, Bagging, Extra Trees	AI model benchmarking	ML models improve predictive accuracy; Extra Trees Regressor performs best.	Drivers: Speed, accuracy (Tech). Barriers: Data size, expertise needs (Tech).
Ayedun et al. (2022)	Nigeria	GIS	Survey (RII)	Low GIS adoption despite high awareness	Drivers: Awareness, efficiency potential (Soc/Tech). Barriers: Cost, low training, data access (Eco/Tech).
Bidanset & Rakow (2022)	USA	AVMs	Survey (IAAO, 2019)	16% adoption; improves accuracy and cost-efficiency; regulatory barriers persist.	Drivers: Accuracy, efficiency (Tech). Barriers: Lack of budget, expertise, legislative limits (Pol/Eco).
Jie (2022)	Malaysia	AVMs	Mixed methods (RII + survey)	Accuracy & speed are key; AVMs pose low job threat now but may rise	Drivers: Accuracy, efficiency (Tech/Eco). Barriers: Training gaps, cost, job insecurity (Soc/Eco)
Namangale (2021)	Malawi	AVMs	Qualitative Interviews	Mixed views; AVMs may augment but not replace traditional practice	Drivers: Efficiency (Tech). Barriers: Fear of obsolescence, data gaps (Soc/Tech).
Ogunnowo et al. (2020)	Nigeria	Valuation Software (Argus, MRI, BOE, ValuePro)	Descriptive Survey	65% of firms never use valuation software; Argus most used among adopters.	Drivers: Belief in efficiency gains (Soc). Barriers: Cost, low awareness, lack of training (Eco/Soc).
Fasteen (2016)	USA	GIS	Structural Equation Modeling	Perceived usefulness, training, and efficiency predict GIS adoption.	Drivers: Perceived usefulness, training (Soc/Tech). Barriers: Age, complexity (Soc/Tech).
Mooya (2011)	Global	AVMs	Theoretical / Ontological analysis	Argues AVMs could replace valuers if social processes allow	Drivers: Objectivity (Soc). Barriers: Professional resistance (Soc).

Source: Author's Construct (2025)

5.0 Discussion

The real estate valuation profession is undergoing a transformative shift driven by rapid advancements in technology. Innovations such as AI, AVMs, GIS, and blockchain are redefining traditional approaches to property valuation. These tools promise increased accuracy, operational efficiency, and data transparency, yet they also introduce challenges that may hinder widespread adoption. This systematic literature review synthesises findings from relevant academic sources to examine the types of technological innovations currently adopted in real estate valuation and analyses the drivers and barriers to adoption using the Political, Economic, Social, and Technological (PEST) framework.

5.1 Types of Technological Innovations adopted in Real Estate Valuation

The literature presents a broad spectrum of technological innovations reshaping property valuation practice. The 17 reviewed studies highlight several key technologies including Automated Valuation Models (AVMs), Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), Geographic Information Systems (GIS), blockchain, valuation software, and big data analytics. Each of these innovations contributes uniquely to the transformation of valuation processes through enhanced accuracy, efficiency, and transparency.

AI techniques such as regression models, decision trees, random forests, and XGBoost are increasingly employed to improve valuation accuracy and efficiency (Băbțan, 2025). These methods underpin the development of AVMs, which automate property appraisal processes by integrating large datasets and advanced algorithms.

5.1.1 *Automated Valuation Models (AVMs)*

Automated Valuation Models (AVMs) remain among the most widely adopted innovations in property valuation. They offer standardized, real-time valuation outputs that help reduce human subjectivity and enhance efficiency (Mooya, 2011; Thebe, 2024). AVMs utilize statistical and machine learning techniques to estimate property values without physical inspection, making them particularly suitable for mass appraisals and mortgage underwriting.

Empirical studies demonstrate their benefits for improving valuation accuracy, consistency, and cost-effectiveness. Bidanset and Rakow (2022) report that regression-based AVMs have improved uniformity and equity in property tax assessments, while Namangale (2021) and Jie (2022) highlight their growing use in both African and Asian contexts. However, challenges remain regarding transparency, data quality, technical expertise, and professional acceptance.

Some AVM frameworks, such as the Expert Function (EXF) model discussed by Stang (2023), employ similarity functions and rule-based filters to automate the traditional sales comparison approach. These functions identify comparable properties using predefined statistical and spatial criteria, ensuring transparency, consistency, and regulatory auditability. Although such models are less flexible than modern machine learning algorithms, they enhance objectivity and remain valuable for standardized valuation tasks where data reliability is high.

5.1.2 *Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs)*

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) and other AI tools including Random Forest, Bagging Regressor, Extra Trees Regressor, and XGBoost, are transforming valuation modelling by capturing nonlinear relationships between property attributes and market values. These algorithms often outperform traditional statistical models. For instance, XGBoost achieved superior predictive accuracy in Germany's nationwide datasets (Stang, 2023), while studies by Adewusi (2022) and Xu (2025) demonstrate the efficacy of Random Forest and Extra Trees Regressor in local contexts. These models support data-driven decision-making by enhancing precision, scalability, and adaptability in diverse market conditions.

5.1.3 *Geographic Information Systems (GIS)*

Geographic Information Systems (GIS) integrate spatial data into property valuation processes, enabling valuers to incorporate location-based variables and visual land-use patterns. GIS can significantly enhance the accuracy and contextual relevance of valuations, particularly in urban planning and assessment roles. GIS technologies were investigated by Ayedun et al. (2022) and Fasteen (2016) for their spatial analytical power and potential to improve decision-making. Despite high awareness among estate valuers, limited adoption is recorded due to barriers such as high cost of software, limited technical expertise, and limited institutional support (Ayedun et al., 2022; Fasteen, 2016; Ogun, 2024). However, the efficiency and decision-making capacity afforded by GIS tools continue to drive interest in their broader adoption in real estate valuation.

5.1.4 *Blockchain Technology*

Blockchain technology is emerging as a tool for promoting transparency, security, and efficiency in property valuation. It enables tamper-proof records, fosters trust in property transactions, and can reduce undue client influence in the valuation process. For instance, PropChain, a blockchain-based mobile application tested in Nigeria, has the potential to improve information transparency and reduce external pressures during valuations (Adilieme et al., 2024; Ogun, 2024). Challenges to adoption include regulatory uncertainty, lack of awareness, and infrastructure limitations (Adilieme et al., 2024). Nonetheless, stakeholders advocate for education, policy support, and early adoption by major industry players to drive blockchain integration in valuation practices.

5.1.5 *Valuation Software Tools*

Valuation software tools such as Argus, MRI, BOE, and ValuePro support the digitization and automation of the valuation process. These tools can improve accuracy, streamline reporting, and enhance operational efficiency in valuation firms. Despite their benefits, valuation software, such as ARGUS and MRI, are underutilised – only about 35 percent of valuation firms in Lagos using such tools, with Argus being the most common, as reported by Ogunnowo et al. (2020). This is attributed to high licensing costs, low level of awareness, and inadequate training on software use (Ogunnowo et al., 2020). Nonetheless, where implemented, these tools have demonstrated the potential to significantly boost productivity and reduce manual errors, making them a viable complement to traditional valuation methods.

5.1.6 *Big Data Analytics*

Big Data Analytics supports decision-making by enabling the processing and analysis of vast quantities of property-related data. It underpins many other innovations such as AVMs and AI by facilitating real-time insights and long-term trend analysis. Big data allows for a more comprehensive understanding of market dynamics, risk assessment, and investment planning (Ogun, 2024). However, its adoption depends on access to reliable data sources, data infrastructure, and analytical capabilities. As the volume and variety of property data grow, big data analytics will become increasingly integral to informed and strategic real estate valuation.

5.2 **Factors influencing technological innovation adoption in real estate valuation**

The systematic review reveals that although several technological innovations such as AVMs, AI and machine learning models, GIS, blockchain, and valuation software have emerged in valuation practice, their adoption remains inconsistent. To understand the underlying dynamics, this study applies a **deductive PEST framework (Political, Economic, Social, and Technological)**, complemented by insights from **Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) theory**, which explains how institutional legitimacy, perceived advantage, and complexity influence adoption (Rogers, 2003; Tornatzky & Fleischer, 1990). Each factor category was coded from the included studies according to its primary emphasis, allowing the identification of dominant **drivers** and **barriers**.

The reviewed studies varied considerably in their methodological orientation and data sources, which partly explains the divergence in reported findings. For instance, studies employing machine learning models on large datasets (e.g., Stang, 2023; Adewusi, 2022; Xu, 2025) reported substantial gains in valuation accuracy, whereas survey-based or case study approaches (e.g., Ayedun et al., 2022; Namangale, 2021) emphasized perceptual and institutional barriers rather than quantitative outcomes. Similarly, regional differences shaped results: research from Europe and Australia generally reflected mature digital infrastructures and stronger regulatory support, while studies from Nigeria, Malawi, and Malaysia revealed constraints tied to resource scarcity, skill deficits, and weak policy environments.

By comparing findings across these methodological and contextual variations, the review demonstrates that adoption barriers are not universal but are influenced by each study's analytical approach and socio-economic setting. This critical synthesis moves beyond mere aggregation to provide a nuanced understanding of how technology adoption unfolds differently across contexts and research traditions. The PEST factors are discussed in the following section.

5.2.1 ***Political Factors***

Government regulation and policy frameworks can either enable or impede the adoption of valuation technologies. In advanced economies, political frameworks increasingly support digital transformation. For example, the European Banking Authority has initiated regulatory discussions around permitting AVMs like XGBoost for lending, contingent on auditability and transparency (Stang, 2023). However, lack of enabling regulatory frameworks is a recurring barrier identified across the studies in emerging markets such as Nigeria and Malaysia. This include weak institutional capacity, outdated legal frameworks, and inconsistent enforcement significantly

which hinder technology diffusion (Ayedun et al., 2022; Jie, 2022). In Nigeria, for instance, Adilieme et al. (2024) found that blockchain technology, despite its potential to enhance transparency and trust in property transactions, faces resistance due to corruption, secrecy in property transactions, and an absence of clear legal backing.

Similarly, the study by Bidanset and Rakow (2022) on AVMs revealed that legislative restrictions in some jurisdictions prevent the widespread use of automated valuation models, despite their advantages in accuracy and efficiency. Moreover, political inertia often leaves technological adoption in a regulatory vacuum. For instance, the failure to formally recognise AVMs or machine learning algorithms as credible tools for property lending valuations (Stang, 2023) reflects how slow regulatory reforms can stall innovation. In Nigeria, blockchain adoption is hindered by corruption, secrecy in transactions, and lack of legal recognition, even though the technology could improve transparency and trust (Adilieme et al., 2024; Ogun, 2024). However, early government involvement such as through digital land registries and tax reforms can also be a powerful driver which acts as a catalyst for diffusion.

Conversely, the lack of political commitment and formal recognition of AVMs and AI tools creates uncertainty that discourages investment in technology. Therefore, from the DOI perspective, political endorsement provides **institutional legitimacy**, enhancing perceived compatibility and reducing uncertainty. Hence, **policy reforms, regulatory clarity, and public sector adoption** are powerful diffusion enablers that can accelerate professional acceptance. Studies emphasise that early government adoption particularly by large public institutions can promote confidence among private players (Adilieme et al., 2024). Where governments mandate mass appraisal systems using AVMs, as observed in some U.S. jurisdictions (Bidanset and Rakow, 2022), adoption rates will improve significantly.

5.2.2 *Economic Factors*

Economic considerations critically affect the decision to adopt technology. Across the reviewed studies, high costs of acquisition, implementation, and maintenance emerged consistently as major barriers. Technologies like blockchain (Adilieme et al., 2024), GIS (Ayedun et al., 2022), and valuation software (Ogunnowo et al., 2020) require substantial capital investment, both in hardware/software and in specialised training for staff. In emerging economies like Nigeria and Malawi, valuation firms are small-scale operators with limited capital reserves, making it difficult to justify such expenditures. Additionally, ongoing costs such as subscription fees for AVM platforms or costs for regular system upgrades pose long-term financial burdens (Jie, 2022).

Nonetheless, economic benefits are equally highlighted as strong drivers. Once adopted, technologies like AVMs and machine learning (ML) models significantly reduce operating costs, increase valuation throughput, and improve profitability. Nielsson and Simper (2024), for instance, demonstrated that machine learning models, such as Random Forest, outperformed traditional valuation systems in Denmark while operating with fewer input variables and at lower cost, suggesting a pathway to cost-effective valuation at scale. Moreover, automation technologies allow firms to handle more assignments in less time (Bidanset and Rakow, 2022; Adewusi, 2022),

directly translating into revenue growth. Firms that overcome the initial cost hurdles often realize substantial long-term economic gains.

The review also indicates regional contrasts in cost dynamics: while high initial costs deter adoption in Africa and Asia, these are often offset by long-term savings in Europe and North America. The findings suggest that where cost-benefit awareness is low, institutional incentives or government subsidies could help reduce the financial burden of innovation uptake.

5.2.3 *Social Factors*

Professional culture and user perceptions are among the most significant factors shaping the pace of innovation adoption. Several studies report a prevailing resistance to change among valuers, rooted in concerns about job displacement, reduced autonomy, and distrust of algorithmic outputs (Lim Zheng Jie, 2022; Fasteen, 2016; Gardes, 2025; Thebe, 2024). Gardes (2025) explored this directly, demonstrating that real estate professionals often perceive AI as a threat to their autonomy, leading to emotional resistance toward its adoption. Professionals highly value their judgment, and fear that technology could devalue or replace their expertise. Similarly, Namangale (2021) found that valuers in Malawi viewed AVMs with suspicion, fearing they might erode the prestige and necessity of human appraisers. Even when technology is framed as an assistive tool (e.g., AVMs supplementing rather than replacing traditional valuations), scepticism is still high. Low awareness levels and inadequate digital literacy further hinder adoption, particularly in emerging markets like Nigeria (Ayedun et al., 2022; Ogunnowo et al., 2020). The study on valuation software usage revealed that even among firms aware of technological tools, the majority rarely used them due to limited knowledge and training opportunities.

Apart from barriers, social drivers exist too. Technologies that enhance transparency and reduce client manipulation such as the blockchain-based Propchain solution proposed by Adilieme et al. (2024) are viewed positively by professionals and clients alike. Social influence particularly from industry leaders, regulatory bodies, and client expectations can also accelerate technological transitions. For instance, Xu (2025) shows that integrating AI-based visual modelling meets consumer demands for price transparency and can shift stakeholder expectations. Transparent processes foster trust in property markets, and in contexts where data secrecy undermines market integrity (like Nigeria), blockchain adoption could be transformative. Furthermore, growing societal acceptance of digital solutions in broader industries (e.g., fintech, e-commerce) is gradually influencing expectations in real estate. Younger professionals entering the field are more technologically savvy and may drive future adoption.

5.2.4 *Technological Factors*

Technological factors encompass the inherent features, limitations, and readiness of existing innovations. Across the reviewed studies, technical complexity is a consistent hurdle. Blockchain implementation requires significant data standardization and secure data-sharing protocols, which are often missing in fragmented property markets (Adilieme et al., 2024). AVMs and AI models, while offering high predictive accuracy, often suffer from the “black box” problem wherein users

and regulators cannot easily understand how outputs are generated (Stang, 2023; Xu, 2025). This opacity undermines trust, especially in sensitive applications like property lending. Another significant barrier is data quality and availability. Effective machine learning models require large, clean, and well-structured datasets (Adewusi, 2022; Nielsson & Simper, 2024). In developing markets, property databases are either incomplete, inaccessible, or riddled with inconsistencies, limiting the full potential of data-driven technologies.

Despite these challenges, technological advancements are steadily improving adoption prospects. More user-friendly platforms, advances in explainable AI (XAI), and the integration of computer vision such as vision-language models in real estate valuation (Xu, 2025) are making technologies more accessible to non-technical users. GIS technologies are increasingly simplified through intuitive interfaces, and hybrid AVM models now combine traditional sales comparison approaches with machine learning (Stang, 2023), striking a balance between interpretability and predictive power. In sum, technology's evolution toward greater accuracy, efficiency, and usability acts as a catalyst for its increasing incorporation into valuation practice. Under DOI, technologies with high **relative advantage**, **trialability**, and **observability** spread faster. Thus, continuous refinement and localisation of valuation technologies are crucial to building user trust and institutional integration.

From the foregoing, it is worthy of note that institutions such as the **Nigerian Institution of Estate Surveyors and Valuers (NIESV)** and the **International Valuation Standards Council (IVSC)** are vital intermediaries in legitimising digital valuation tools. The reason is that updated standards, training, and certification pathways enhance professional confidence and guide ethical application (IVSC, 2021). While high upfront costs remain barriers, multiple studies show that efficiency gains, scalability, and data reusability offset long-term expenses (Stang, 2023; Nielsson & Simper, 2024). However, in low-income markets, cost recovery mechanisms remain underdeveloped, limiting scalability.

Globally, valuation standards are shifting to accommodate algorithmic transparency and hybrid valuation methods. Europe and Australia demonstrate high adaptation, while Africa and parts of Asia remain at early diffusion stages. Also, chronological mapping reveals an evolution from conceptual discussions (2011–2016) to experimental applications (2018–2025), suggesting accelerating technological maturity and growing institutional openness to digital transformation.

In summary, the adoption of technological innovations in real estate valuation is shaped by **interdependent political, economic, social, and technological dimensions**, interacting through institutional legitimacy (DOI) and contextual readiness (PEST). Political support and regulation underpin legitimacy; economic capacity drives feasibility; social attitudes affect willingness; and technological features determine usability. The evidence shows that while barriers persist especially in developing economies, technological diffusion is steadily progressing as regulatory clarity, digital literacy, and professional adaptation improve.

6.0 Conclusion

This systematic literature review has identified the diverse types of technological innovations and determinants of technological innovation adoption in real estate valuation through an integrated

Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) and PEST (Political, Economic, Social, and Technological) framework. The review identified a growing diversity of digital tools including Automated Valuation Models (AVMs), Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithms, Geographic Information Systems (GIS), blockchain, and big data analytics, that are transforming valuation practice globally. These innovations collectively enhance valuation accuracy, efficiency, transparency, and scalability, signalling a paradigm shift in how property value is assessed and reported.

Adoption, however, is neither uniform nor unchallenged across markets. Findings reveal that adoption is shaped by both behavioural factors (as explained by DOI) and contextual enablers or constraints (as captured by PEST). Political and regulatory support emerged as pivotal, with enabling policies accelerating adoption in advanced economies, while regulatory ambiguity and weak institutional frameworks hinder diffusion in developing contexts. Economically, high implementation and maintenance costs remain major barriers, particularly among small and medium-sized valuation firms. Social factors including professional resistance, low digital literacy, and perceived threats to expertise further constrain uptake. Technologically, data limitations, interoperability issues, and model transparency challenges persist despite rapid innovation.

The findings suggest that while technological integration can enhance the valuation profession, its success depends on addressing the systemic barriers that constrain adoption. Ultimately, the profession must strike a balance between embracing technological precision and preserving the contextual judgment that human expertise provides. This is because the future of valuation lies in augmenting human expertise with intelligent systems. Therefore, stakeholders must work together to create ecosystems that are technologically advanced, socially inclusive, and institutionally resilient. For successful integration, coordinated efforts across policy reforms, professional retraining, technology standardization, and infrastructure investments are crucial.

The foundation of this review was based PEST framework and DOI theory. However, PEST is limited because it does not account the growing significance of sustainability regulations, environmental risk assessment, and ESG reporting in valuation practice recognised globally. Therefore, future studies using PEST(LE) framework might be necessary to offer a more comprehensive analytical lens by incorporating legal and environmental factors into the review. Furthermore, future research could explore longitudinal and comparative analyses of technology diffusion across jurisdictions to better understand how cultural, economic, and regulatory contexts shape adoption trajectories. Such inquiry will deepen theoretical understanding and guide evidence-based policy for a sustainable and technologically adaptive valuation profession.

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Abstract Only (Non-Peer-Reviewed)

Risk Analysis and Management Practices of Types of Real Estate Developers *Ezinne Ifeoma Onyekwelu¹; Obinna Collins Nnamani^{1*}*

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to determine if there is any relationship between risk analysis and management practices and types of real estate developers in Nigeria, specifically mainly-trader developers and mainly-investor developers. An explanatory sequential mixed-methods design was employed, involving a quantitative survey of 250 experienced developers across the six geopolitical zones in Nigeria, yielding 84 valid responses. Also 13 experienced developers were purposively selected for oral interview. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for the data analysis. Overall, findings show that the most common risk management techniques adopted by the developers were brainstorming (71.4%), checklist (67.9%), experience/judgement/intuition (64.5%), and risk avoidance (63.1%). On the other hand, mainly-trader developers showed a higher likelihood of using checklist ($p = 0.016$), sensitivity analysis ($p = 0.040$), scenario technique ($p = 0.045$), and expected monetary value ($p = 0.003$). This study enhances understanding of how different developer types assess and mitigate risks, offering valuable insights for industry practitioners and academia. While limited to Nigeria, its findings may be applicable to other emerging markets. Notably, this is the first study to investigate risk management practices across all six geopolitical zones of Nigeria, contributing to the broader discourse on real estate development risk analysis.

Key words: Risk analysis; Risk management; Real estate development; investment decision-making; Nigeria

Prospect of Blockchain Technology Adoption in Lagos Property Market, Nigeria *Sulaimon Olawale Olaleye¹; and Timothy Oluwafemi Ayodele²*

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Abstract

Currently, the Lagos Property Market is inefficient due to several issues such as data-related challenges, lack of transparency, and delay in property documentation. Blockchain Technology (BCT) is asserted to provide a promising solution for solving the issues facing real estate practices in Lagos State. However, the prospect of the adoption of BCT in the Lagos Property Market needs to be understood. Therefore, this study examined the prospect of Blockchain Technology (BCT) in the Lagos Property Market in Nigeria. To achieve the objectives, the research adopted a quantitative research approach. Data were collected using a closed-ended questionnaire administered to 252 real estate firms, and 139(55.2%) were retrieved. Data was analysed using mean, frequency, and percentages. The results revealed that BCT adoption is high across real estate practices, including agency, property and facility management, valuation, land administration, property development and finance. The result showed that BCT would streamline property transactions and document verification for agency practice. It will also facilitate data management and data sharing, which could solve challenges faced by property valuation. BCT will be helpful in facility management practices, especially for access control and security, building system monitoring, and service records. In property management practices, BCT would streamline tenant verification and background checks, management of tenants, and rental contracts. Security and transparent record-keeping, digital identity and authentication, and secure land titles

and ownership records, transparency and trust, and access to land information could be improved with the use of BCT for property development and land administration, respectively. This study offers insight into the potential of BCT in real estate practice. The results are useful to real estate practitioners and professional bodies in determining possibilities of implementing BCT in real estate practices.

Key words: *Blockchain Technology, Adoption, Property Market, Real Estate Practice, Property Transaction*

Risk Analysis and Management Practices of Types of Real Estate Developers *Ezinne Ifeoma Onyekwelu¹; Obinna Collins Nnamani^{1*}*

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to determine if there is any relationship between risk analysis and management practices and types of real estate developers in Nigeria, specifically mainly-trader developers and mainly-investor developers. An explanatory sequential mixed-methods design was employed, involving a quantitative survey of 250 experienced developers across the six geopolitical zones in Nigeria, yielding 84 valid responses. Also 13 experienced developers were purposively selected for oral interview. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for the data analysis. Overall, findings show that the most common risk management techniques adopted by the developers were brainstorming (71.4%), checklist (67.9%), experience/judgement/intuition (64.5%), and risk avoidance (63.1%). On the other hand, mainly-trader developers showed a higher likelihood of using checklist ($p = 0.016$), sensitivity analysis ($p = 0.040$), scenario technique ($p = 0.045$), and expected monetary value ($p = 0.003$). This study enhances understanding of how different developer types assess and mitigate risks, offering valuable insights for industry practitioners and academia. While limited to Nigeria, its findings may be applicable to other emerging markets. Notably, this is the first study to investigate risk management practices across all six geopolitical zones of Nigeria, contributing to the broader discourse on real estate development risk analysis.

Key words: Risk analysis; Risk management; Real estate development; investment decision-making; Nigeria

Effects of Deficient Housing Maintenance on Rental Values in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria *Rukayat Bewaji ADEYINKA*

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Abstract

Deficient housing maintenance is a significant challenge in some regions within Ibadan. This has led to several challenges, including rental value depreciation, tenant dissatisfaction, and reduced investment returns. This study examines the impact of inadequate housing maintenance on rental value in the selected regions of Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. The research explores key factors such as rapid urbanization, lack of maintenance culture, financial constraints, obsolesces and weak enforcement of building regulations, which contribute to declining property

conditions and market value. A mixed-method research approach was adopted, integrating both qualitative and quantitative data. Primary data were collected through structured interviews and surveys with property owners, tenants, and real estate professionals, while secondary data were obtained from government reports, academic literature, and market analyses. Descriptive and inferential statistical methods were employed to analyse the relationship between housing maintenance and property value depreciation. Pearson's correlation analysis revealed a strong negative correlation ($r \approx -0.75$, $p < 0.01$) between inadequate maintenance and declining property value, highlighting the significant impact of poor maintenance on property degradation, high tenant turnover, and lower market desirability. The findings emphasize the need for proactive maintenance strategies, stricter regulatory enforcement, and increased awareness of sustainable housing practices. Strengthening maintenance policies and investment in property upkeep will be crucial in preserving real estate value and ensuring long-term economic sustainability in the study area.

Keywords: Deficiency, Housing, Maintenance, Value, rentals.

COVID-19 and the Real Estate Market – A PAGER Systematic Review Rotimi B. Abidoye¹ & Chibuikem M. Adilieme¹

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Abstract

The real estate market has been dominated by high prices, limited access and affordability, especially for young people and first-home buyers. The issues plaguing the market have been attributed to supply chain, migration, and COVID-19, to name a few. This study focuses on COVID-19 as a black swan event that has impacted the real estate market to draw insights that can help policymakers in Australia. Accordingly, through a systematic manner, 101 journal articles on the Covid-19 pandemic and the real estate market were extracted from the Scopus database and reported using the Patterns, Advances, Gaps, Evidence for practice and Research recommendations (PAGER) framework to report the findings from the literature. The observable patterns include the impact of the pandemic on real estate prices and values, rent and investment return, the impact on indirect real estate and the interrelationship with market fundamentals such as transaction patterns, time on the market, and demand, among others. Overall, there were mixed (positive and negative) impacts on different markets, with attempts to model and predict property prices to help investors and policymakers.

Keywords: COVID-19, Real Estate Market, PAGER, Prices, Rent, Australia

The Economic Impact of Real Estate in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Case for Greater Francophone Inclusion in the African Real Estate Society *Fiona Toliva*¹

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Abstract

The real estate sector which plays a major role in economic development in all regions of Sub-Saharan Africa. The real estate sector plays a crucial role in economic development across Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), leads to GDP growth, infrastructure development and employment. Also, its full potential is inhibited by factors such as market fragmentation and institutional barriers, especially in Francophone Africa with significantly different legal frameworks, regulatory environments and legal frameworks. This study draws from the Network and Institutional Theories in examining how formal institutions and professional networks influence market performance in the Anglophone and Francophone SSA.

By analysing a representation of either market in Kenya and Senegal, the study evaluates regulatory differences, GDP contributions, FDIs and professional representation, in a comparative study. The study employs descriptive statistics, including means and proportions, to analyze key economic indicators across Anglophone and Francophone African countries. A comparative analysis using t-tests, ANOVA, and Chi-square tests is conducted to assess significant differences between these markets, examining variations in economic performance and real estate sector contributions. Furthermore, regression analysis is utilized to determine the impact of real estate on GDP growth, identifying the extent to which the sector drives economic expansion in both linguistic regions. Preliminary findings show that Anglophone countries attract more foreign investment, as a benefit of decentralized governance and common law frameworks, while their Francophone counterparts experience higher transaction costs and less liquidity stemming from the more centralized regulations resulting from civil law systems.

Affordable smart housing initiatives for a successful smart city development in Akure, Nigeria *Priscilla Oyebola Bello¹ and Princebell Oyewande Bello²*

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²Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba-Akoko, Nigeria (princebellbello@gmail.com)

Abstract

Smart cities have emerged as innovative responses to urbanisation challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, traffic congestion, insecurity, and social inequality. However, affordable housing, a critical component of a city, is often neglected in the pursuit of smart city development. This study investigates how innovative construction techniques can facilitate the integration of affordable housing into smart city development. Data was collected from architects practising in Akure and analysed with descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings revealed the potential of locally sourced construction materials to reduce the cost of smart housing in Nigeria significantly. The study contributes to the academic discourse on affordable smart housing and provides practical insights for policy and urban development stakeholders driving for inclusive and sustainable smart cities in Nigeria.

Key words: Affordable housing; Smart city; Smart housing; Sustainable urban development; Smart building

Factors Influencing Female Accessibility to Mortgage Facilities in Lagos, Nigeria *Abiodun Oduntade Adejumo¹, Mathew Oluwole Oyewole²; and Funmilayo Moyinoluwa Araloyin³*

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Abstract

This study investigates female access to residential mortgage facilities on Lagos Island and the mainland, aiming to determine access levels and key influencing factors, with a primary objective of reducing gender gaps in mortgage availability. A total of 105 buildings were surveyed in three randomly chosen gated estates from each area. Descriptive and inferential statistics were employed to analyze the respondents' general indifference towards mortgage availability in Nigeria. The study revealed that high interest rates, bureaucratic red tape, strict mortgage terms, and gender-based restrictions are among the contributing factors. Although the study concludes that women are predominantly unable to obtain mortgage facilities, it argues that reforms such as lower interest rates, more efficient procedures, flexible terms, and socioeconomic empowerment could increase the number of mortgage options available to women.

Keywords: Mortgage Facility, female accessibility, Gender equality, and Policy Reforms

Re-evaluating the Importance of Health and Wellbeing in the UK Office Market: A research agenda

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Abstract

In light of evolving workplace expectations and post-pandemic priorities, there is an increasing demand for office spaces that support occupant health, productivity and overall wellbeing. This research explores the growing emphasis on health and wellbeing in the UK office market, with a particular focus on WELL-certified buildings. The study began by synthesising web-based information and literature to identify and summarise the key drivers behind the adoption of WELL certification in the office sector. CoStar data was also adopted to evaluate the performance of WELL-certified offices in comparison to non-certified buildings with a view to establishing a measurable link between certification and market performance. Initial findings indicate that the demand for WELL certification is primarily driven by ESG agendas, employee health and wellbeing, talent attraction and retention, productivity and operational cost goals, the need to future-proof against regulatory changes, and the desire to enhance marketability and asset value. WELL-certified buildings also frequently hold other sustainability certifications. This presentation provides an update on the research to date and outlines the agenda for the next phases of the study.

Key words: ESG; health and wellbeing; office market; real estate; WELL-certified

Developing Sustainable Investment Structures - The case of housing price indices in the East African region *Henry Muyingo¹; Frank Nyanda²*

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Abstract

The African real estate market still lags behind many other regions in the struggle to attract investment capital especially within the elements related to sustainable financing mainly due to opaqueness. A PhD dissertation

defended in May 2025 at Ardhi University in Dar es Salaam pointed to various ways in which a housing price index could be created for nascent markets similar to that in Tanzania.

This paper provides a brief summary of the main findings from the dissertation together with an overview of the current status and development potential of housing price indices within the East African region. The study primarily covers the real estate markets in Kenya, Uganda, Tanzania, Rwanda, Ethiopia and Somalia. Given the nature of the markets and the degree of informality, a key element is the analysis of how the property transaction data is captured, reported and shared among key stakeholders within the public and private sectors.

The paper aims to contribute to the process of standardised data collection within the region with the purpose of highlighting the importance of taking into account all sources of information that can lead to an increase in the efficiency and transparency of the markets under question.

Key words: Housing price index, data availability, housing markets, East Africa, property valuation

Evaluating Travel Distance Versus Linear Distance as Predictors of Retail Rental Value *Oluwatayo Ogunjobi*¹; *Adejimi Ali Adebayo*²

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Abstract

This study employs vector GIS to evaluate how different measures of location distance, linear and travel distances, affect retail rental values in a monocentric city. It investigates how the effect of location on retail rents varies depending on which distance measurement approach is used, offering insights into urban spatial dynamics. Using the GIS, the research generates locational parameters for both linear and travel distances to the city centre, transport nodes, and the agglomeration effect of surrounding retail properties in York, United Kingdom. These were then incorporated into a retail rent model to assess their influence on rental values.

Results indicate that proximity to transport nodes plays a crucial role, with linear distance showing the most significant negative impact (34%) on retail rent. Interestingly, linear distance to the city centre has a strong positive effect (6.7%) on rent values, whereas travel distance to the centre negatively impacts rent (4.4%). These findings highlight the importance of how location is measured when analysing retail rents. The study introduces an innovative method for generating locational metrics for rent analysis and emphasises the nuanced effects of spatial proximity. These insights are valuable for urban planners, real estate investors, and town centre managers making location-based decisions.

Which Is a Stronger Indicator of Retail Rental Value—Travel Distance or Linear Distance *Oluwatayo Ogunjobi¹; Adejimi Ali Adebayo²*

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Cultural Attachment to Land and its Implications on the Economic Development of African Nations *Ogunsanya Kehinde Abraham and Shehu Janeth*

Abstract

Cultural attachment to land in Africa significantly shapes its economies, often creating a complex interplay between tradition and modernity. While land provides essential livelihoods and is a source of wealth, traditional land tenure systems can hinder economic development due to factors like limited access, inefficient land use, and disputes. Conversely, traditional practices can also offer valuable insights into sustainable resource management and biodiversity conservation. According to Shipton “land is not merely a physical resource but also a source of identity, cultural heritage, and profound symbolic meaning”. Based on this concept, the research work explores the intricate relationship between land, culture, and its roles in the development of the economy of African nations. The work x-rays the separation of seemingly disparate domains – religion, ritual, cognition, adaptation, sustenance, and production – depicting on how they are intertwined within the context of land ownership and access. The work also examined how land in Africa is not just a commodity but also carries rich symbolic connotations and intricate legal philosophies. It's a focal point for cultural identity and heritage, where concepts of ownership, tenancy, and access are deeply embedded in social structures and belief systems. In order to satisfactorily address the issues raised by the research topic, the research strategy used in this study was the qualitative method. This method employed a tripartite data collection mechanism involving in-depth Semi-Structured Interviews, Focus Group Discussion and Questionnaire. The result shows that cultural attachment to land in the African context have both positive and negative connotations. The positive connotations are land serves as a source of livelihood and food security; it also connotes cultural identity and social symbol; land contributes to sustainable resource use and biodiversity conservation as well

as traditional markets, where social relationships influence economic transactions, play a role in local economies. On the other hand, the negative impact are there is Land Tenure Insecurity – where colonial legacy, unequal land distribution, and unclear land ownership rights can lead to disputes and hinder investment in land development. In the same vein, disparities in access to land and control over resources can exacerbate poverty and inequality. Traditional land tenure systems can sometimes be a barrier to modernizing agriculture and other land-based industries. While in some cases, traditional practices may contribute to environmental degradation if not adapted to changing circumstances. Land ownership issues and traditional land use patterns can sometimes hinder infrastructure development. The devaluation of traditional knowledge and practices can lead to a loss of cultural identity and heritage.

Key Words: African nations, cultural attachment, economic development, land, land tenure system.

Impacts of Statutory Charges on Facility Management Operation at Mall Of Dubai, Abuja *Ogunsanya Kehinde Abraham and Shehu Janeth*

Abstract

In an attempt to generate income, government at various levels in Nigeria, has instituted various charges levied on property owners and users; others are service providers in nature. Apart from its negative influence; some of these charges are not known to the Facility Manager at the point of planning and budgeting. This is the case at the Mall of Dubai, a multi-tenanted edifies equipped with modern facilities. This research therefore seeks to identify the various statutory charges and service providers and the exploitation by government agents and staff and its subsequent effects on the smooth operation and maintenance of Mall of Dubai, Abuja.

Facility management encompasses multiple disciplines to ensure the functionality of the built environment by integrating people, places, process, and technology. People, processes, places, and technology represent an organization's physical workplace, from which facility managers determine the requirements for a safe, healthy, and productive workplace.

Facility management is vital in supporting employees, increasing productivity, and increasing job satisfaction. Facilities are typically a company's second largest asset after its employees. This means that facility management plays a vital role in supporting the employees. Effective facility management helps increase employee productivity and job satisfaction, leading to improved financial outcomes for the business and helps attract and retain employees.

Statutory charges are a non-negotiable component of a business premises or estate wherein facility management operation are required. The statutory charges and service providers come in different shapes and formats. The implementation of these charges have in one way or the other have both negative and positive effects on facility management operations. However, it depends on the way and manner such charges were handled by the Facility Manager. Efficient management of these charges is crucial to sustaining operations, maintaining good tenant relationship, and avoiding legal penalties. The effects are more to budgeting, planning, compliance, and operational flexibility of facility management at the Dall of Dubai

Key Words: Facility Management; Government Agencies; Mall of Dubai; Service Providers; Statutory Charges.

SUSTAINABLE FINANCING MODELS FOR REAL ESTATE INVESTMENT IN THE EMERGING AFRICAN MARKETS *Funso Ibikunle*

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Abstract

This study investigates the effectiveness of sustainable financing models in enhancing the performance and investment viability of Real Estate Investment Trusts (REITs) in Nigeria's emerging urban real estate markets. With rapid urbanization and persistent housing deficits confronting Nigerian cities, traditional financing mechanisms have proven inadequate in supporting scalable and inclusive property development. The study adopts a quantitative research design, drawing data from 102 real estate finance professionals across Lagos, Abuja, Port Harcourt, and Enugu. Four sustainable financing models green bonds, blended finance, Islamic real estate investment funds, and public-private partnerships (PPPs) were examined using multiple regression analysis. Findings reveal that green bonds and PPPs exert the most significant positive influence on REIT performance, enhancing project bankability, investor confidence, and long-term viability. Blended finance models also demonstrate effectiveness, particularly in reducing project risks and attracting private sector capital through concessional layering. While Islamic real estate funds showed a positive but statistically insignificant impact, their potential for ethical investment mobilization remains notable. The results underscore the transformative potential of sustainable financing instruments in expanding Nigeria's real estate capital base and improving REIT scalability. The study concludes that diversifying Nigeria's real estate finance ecosystem through sustainable models can significantly strengthen the resilience and inclusiveness of urban development across the country. Policy recommendations include strengthening regulatory frameworks, expanding green certification systems, and incentivizing blended and ethical investment structures.

Key words: Sustainable Finance, Green Bonds, REITs, PPPs, Blended Finance, Islamic Real Estate Funds, Nigeria, Urban Development

Capital City Relocations in Africa: Motivations and Impacts *Abukar Warsame¹ and Henry Muyingo²*

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² Royal Institute of Technology, KTH, Stockholm, Sweden (henry.muyingo@abe.kth.se)

Abstract

Historically, many African capital cities were established by colonial powers to concentrate administrative authority and economic control, resulting in the creation of primate cities—urban centers that dominate national life in terms of population, resources, and influence. These cities often suffer from extreme congestion, socio-economic disparities, and regional imbalances.

In response several African governments have pursued capital city relocation as a strategy to redistribute development, reduce pressure on overstretched urban systems, and symbolize a break from colonial legacies. Through detailed case studies of Abuja (Nigeria), Dodoma (Tanzania), and the New Administrative Capital (Egypt), this paper investigates the motivations behind the relocations in Africa and assesses the outcomes of such decisions across multiple dimensions, including governance, diplomacy, infrastructure, and economic development. The analysis highlights both the potential benefits such as improved geographic centrality, new infrastructure development, and national integration—and the persistent challenges, including high financial costs, slow administrative transition, and resistance from domestic and international actors.

The paper aims to provide a nuanced understanding of the political, economic, and spatial dimensions of capital relocation in post-colonial Africa and assesses whether these projects have lived up to their promises not least from the real estate investment perspective.

Key words: Capital City Relocation, Primate Cities, Real Estate Valuation, Infrastructure and Governance

Examining the social value of healthy placemaking in real estate asset portfolio management *Kathy Pain*¹; *Nalumino Akakandelwa*²; *Oliver Tannor*³; *Eleanor Eaton*⁴ ; *Alistair Hunt*⁵

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Abstract

The paper reports findings from a real estate study examining asset management decision-making outcomes for urban population health and wellbeing in a five-year programme funded by the United Kingdom Prevention Research Partnership (UKPRP). We find that despite an industry appetite for demonstrating how portfolio strategies promote sustainable urban environments that produce resilient risk-adjusted returns on investment, there is a paucity of health and well-being data to inform portfolio management models. Evidence of responsible Environmental, Social, Governance (ESG) performance has become seen as a commercial priority, but environmental sustainability has taken precedence in investor reporting due to the superior availability of carbon data. Focusing on two large investment management funds with extensive UK urban asset portfolios, we take on the challenge of testing how monetised health and wellbeing value generated by urban redevelopment can inform asset management, healthy urban placemaking aligned with investor financial returns aspirations. We conclude that in the context of the contemporary financialization of property and assetization of urban space, urban land and property repurposing and upgrading present an opportunity to create social value in operational models for wealth creation.

Key words: Real estate, Asset portfolio, Healthy placemaking, Social value

Building a Real Estate Index for Africa: Are listed real estate markets aligned or segmented? *Omokolade Akinsomi and Babatunde Odusami*

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² School of Business Administration, Widener University, One University Pl, Chester, PA, USA, boodusami@widener.edu

Abstract

This paper aims to create a listed real estate activity index for Africa. We collect real estate-related publicly listed stock indexes on all exchanges in Africa. Using the monthly price history of real estate stocks in 12 countries in Africa: Botswana, Egypt, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Malawi, Mauritius, Morocco, South Africa, Tunisia, Zambia, and Zimbabwe. We created an African Real Estate Index (market-weighted) and a regional African real estate index covering the East, North, South, and Western parts of Africa. Our findings reveal that 12 out of 54 countries have an active real estate

public market, and a significant degree of real estate activity does not occur via the securitized markets in Africa, impacting liquidity constraints. This paper is essential for institutional investors interested in investing in real estate markets in Africa and financial regulatory agencies interested in expanding and creating a thriving real estate ecosystem in their respective African countries.

Keywords: Real Estate Index, Securitisation, Institutional Investors, Financial Regulatory Agencies, Africa.

Common Risk Factors in African Real Estate **Stocks** Babatunde Odusami¹ and Omokolade Akinsomi²

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Abstract

It is well established that cross-sectional and time-varying returns of U.S stocks are driven by common risk factors such as size, valuation, momentum, profitability, and capital investment strategy. This paper investigates whether there are common latent risk factors that can explain the cross-sectional and time variations in the returns of real estate-related stocks that trade on exchanges across Africa. Specifically, it estimates fundamental and statistical risk factors extracted using the principal component analysis (PCA) of the daily returns of actively traded real estate-related stock listed on all African stock exchanges. Factor premia are then derived by second-pass regression of the returns on the estimated risk factors. Lastly, the paper distinguishes between global, regional, country-level, and industry-level risk factors. The preliminary result obtained shows that the daily exposures to ten latent statistical factors account for more than half of the time- and cross-sectional variations in the monthly returns of the real estate stocks in Africa. Furthermore, the risk premium that can be attributed to these factors is also significant. The average monthly return of the portfolio with the top decile level of exposure to the first risk factor is 1.9% greater than the portfolio in the bottom decile level. Similarly, the average monthly return of the portfolios in the top decile exposure to the second risk factor is 1.85% lower than the bottom decile exposure to the same factor. Exposures to these risk factors also vary significantly across the industry. On average, stocks of real estate development companies have significantly higher negative exposure to the first latent risk factor than the stocks of REITs and real estate services companies. REIT stocks have significantly higher exposure to the second latent risk factor than the stock of real estate development and real estate services companies.

Keywords: Statistical Risk Factors, Equity Returns, African, Real Estate

Affordable smart housing initiatives for a successful smart city development in Akure, Nigeria Priscilla Oyebola Bello¹ and Princebell Oyewande Bello²

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Abstract

Smart cities have emerged as innovative responses to urbanisation challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, traffic congestion, insecurity, and social inequality. However, affordable housing, a critical component of a city, is often neglected in the pursuit of smart city development. This study investigates how innovative construction techniques

can facilitate the integration of affordable housing into smart city development. Data was collected from architects practising in Akure and analysed with descriptive statistics such as weighted mean score and relative importance index (RII). The findings revealed that majority of the respondents are generally aware of smart building technologies, but only 31.25% have participated in a smart building or smart city project. Furthermore, mud bricks and laterite ranked highest (RII=0.67) as a locally sourced construction material based on its perceived importance in reducing the cost of smart housing in the study area. The study contributes to the academic discourse on affordable smart housing and provides practical insights for policy and urban development stakeholders driving for inclusive and sustainable smart cities in Nigeria.

Key words: Affordable housing; Smart city; Smart housing; Sustainable urban development; Smart building

Challenges in Corporate Real Estate Portfolio Maintenance: A Case Study of UrbanVista Properties Company in Gaborone *Kealeboga Jeanet Sibanda-Gouwe*

Abstract

This study investigates the challenges of corporate real estate portfolio maintenance at UrbanVista Properties Company in Gaborone, Botswana, through a qualitative research approach. Data were gathered using semi-structured interviews and open-ended questionnaires administered to maintenance staff, supervisors, property managers, and tenants. The study aimed to understand the lived experiences and perspectives of those directly involved in or affected by property maintenance operations. The findings reveal that plumbing and Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) issues are the most common maintenance challenges, exacerbated by a reliance on reactive maintenance strategies and limited use of preventive and predictive approaches. These challenges negatively impact property value, tenant satisfaction, and operational efficiency. The study recommends shifting towards proactive maintenance practices, adopting modern technologies, increasing skilled personnel, and improving organizational planning to enhance maintenance outcomes. Addressing these challenges is crucial for sustaining property value and ensuring long-term asset performance in the corporate real estate sector. Key words: Maintenance, Corporate Real Estate, Challenges, Gaborone, Botswana

What factors drive REITs returns in South Africa? *Omokolade Akinsomi¹; Emmanuel Joel Aikins Abakah²; Maurice Shapiro³ and Lawrence Rapp⁴*

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Abstract

Since the global economic recession of 2008, a central and persistent question in the real estate finance literature has been: *What fundamental factors drive real estate asset returns?* Earlier studies on developed real estate markets have documented the significant influence of both market-based factors and broader macroeconomic conditions on real estate asset returns (Cheng & Yeng, 2019; Akinsomi et al., 2024; Bouri et al., 2017, etc.). In South Africa (SA), the influence of REITs on capital market depth and investment strategies is increasingly critical for policymakers, regulators, and asset managers, especially in volatile and politically sensitive environments (Korsah & Mensah, 2023;

Moeketsi & Letaba, 2022; Oliver et al., 2022). Few studies provide empirical evidence on the determinants of South Africa's real estate asset market (Agyei et al., 2022; Ajayi & Akinsomi, 2022; Korsah & Mensah, 2023). Given the dynamic nature of the factors that affect REIT returns in emerging markets, the changing traits of real estate investment over time, and the forecast horizon, merit investigation. In this paper, we take a different perspective and contribute to the literature by investigating the effect of firm-level policies, macroeconomic, and global uncertainty factors on SA REITs' returns. Next, we examine the impact of corporate governance practices, business regulations & institutional quality on the relationship. We obtain data on 42 SA REIT firms with data spanning from 2000 to 2024. We use linear and nonlinear pool OLS and threshold panel regressions as estimation techniques.

Keywords: South Africa REIT returns, firm-level outcomes, macroeconomic factors, policy uncertainty, geopolitical events

Big Tech Stocks and REITs Market with Portfolio Implications *Omokolade Akinsomi*¹; *Emmanuel Joel Aikins Abakah*²

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Abstract

This paper examines the relationship between big tech stocks and the global REIT market in the era of the AI boom and provides insights for portfolio diversification. We analyze big tech stocks, including Apple, Microsoft, Amazon, Alphabet (Google), Meta Platforms (formerly Facebook), Tesla, and Nvidia, along with the MSCI World REITs Index, Dow Jones Equity All REITs (USA), and REIT Europe Price to represent the REIT market. Data covers the period from May 18, 2012, to March 23, 2025. We employ quantile coherency (QC) and quantile-on-quantile regression (QQR) as our estimation methods. Findings from the QC approach reveal that coherency increases within the higher quantiles ($\tau > 0.75$) for Alphabet (GOOG), Apple (AAPL), and Microsoft (MSFT), demonstrating how favorable market conditions promote correlated movements between the MAG7 tech stocks and global REITs. In the lower quantile ($\tau < 0.25$), we observe asymmetric coherence between REITs and Tesla (TSLA), Nvidia (NVDA), and Meta (META). From the QQR, results show an asymmetric relationship between REITs and the big tech stocks across different quantiles. EU REITs show less sensitivity to shocks from big tech stocks. For portfolio investors, our findings reveal that REITs can serve as a hedge to giant tech stocks depending on the market conditions.

Keywords: REITs, big tech stocks, quantile coherency, diversification.